

Different Digits Selfie Fractions: Two and Three Digits Numerators

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Abstract

The **addable fractions** are proper fractions, where addition can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. The same is true for other operations, such as, **addition, subtraction, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. For more details refer author's work [10]. This work brings **selfie fractions** with single and/or multiple representations in different digits with all operations. The numerator values are with two and three digits numbers. The denominator values considered are maximum up to 6-digits. The results are in increasing order of numerator values. Also, numerator is always less than denominator. The repeated digits **selfie fractions** are given in another work by author [12].

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1 Introduction

Kieth [2, 3] for the first gave an idea of **dottable fraction**. It is a proper fraction where multiplication signs can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. Keith's [2, 3] idea was only with multiplication. For the first time, we extended it to other operations also, such as, with **addition, subtraction, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. See below some examples studied by author [5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

1.1 Selfie Fraction

• Addable Fractions

$$\frac{96}{352} = \frac{9+6}{3+52}, \quad \frac{182}{6734} = \frac{18+2}{6+734}, \text{ etc.} \quad (1)$$

• Subtractable Fractions

$$\frac{204}{357} = \frac{20-4}{35-7}, \quad \frac{726}{1089} = \frac{72-6}{108-9}, \text{ etc.} \quad (2)$$

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• **Dottable Fraction**

$$\frac{13}{624} = \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}, \quad \frac{416}{728} = \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}, \text{ etc.} \quad (3)$$

• **Dottable with Potentiation Fractions**

$$\frac{95}{342} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}, \quad \frac{728}{1456} = \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56}, \text{ etc.} \quad (4)$$

• **Mixed Fractions: All Operations**

$$\frac{4980}{5312} = \frac{4 - 9 + 80}{5 \times (3 + 1)^2}, \quad \frac{3249}{5168} = \frac{(3 + 2^4) \times 9}{(5 - 1) \times 68}, \text{ etc.} \quad (5)$$

Observing the above examples, the numerator and denominator follows the same orders of digits in both sides of each fraction separated by operations. These type of fractions, we called **Selfie fractions**. There are two situations. One when all digits appearing in each fraction are distinct and second, when there are repetitions of digits. The idea of **equivalent e fractions** is explained below.

1.2 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Above we have given **selfie fractions** with single value in each case. There are many fractions, that can be written in multiple ways. See below

• **Equivalent: Addable**

$$\frac{1453}{2906} = \frac{1 + 453}{2 + 906} = \frac{145 + 3}{290 + 6} = \frac{1 + 45 + 3}{2 + 90 + 6}, \text{ etc.} \quad (6)$$

• **Equivalent: Subtractable**

$$\frac{932}{1864} = \frac{9 - 32}{18 - 64} = \frac{93 - 2}{186 - 4}, \text{ etc.} \quad (7)$$

• **Equivalent: Dottable and Addable**

$$\frac{1680}{59472} = \frac{1 \times 6 \times 80}{59 \times 4 \times 72} = \frac{1 + 6 + 8 + 0}{59 + 472}, \text{ etc.} \quad (8)$$

• **Equivalent: Dottable, Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{302}{8154} = \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} = \frac{3 + 02}{81 + 54} = \frac{3 - 02}{81 - 54}, \text{ etc.} \quad (9)$$

• **Symmetric Equivalent: Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{645}{1290} = \frac{6 - 45}{12 - 90} = \frac{6 + 45}{12 + 90}, \text{ etc.} \quad (10)$$

● **Equivalent: Dottable and Addable together**

$$\frac{284}{639} = \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} = \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)}, \text{ etc.} \quad (11)$$

● **Equivalent: Mixed - All Operations**

$$\frac{73842}{90516} = \frac{7 - 3 \times (8 - 4^2)}{9 \times 05 - 1 - 6} = \frac{7 \times (3 + 8) + 4^2}{90 + (5 - 1) \times 6} = \frac{738 + 4 + 2}{905 + 1 + 6}, \text{ etc.} \quad (12)$$

In 2016, the author worked on **selfie fractions** in different ways and with different digits, i.e., without repetition of digits in numerators and denominators. See below resumed work.

- (i) Selfie Fractions: Addable - [5];
- (ii) Selfie Fractions: Dottable and Pontentiable - [6];
- (iii) Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together - [7];
- (iv) Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Dottable, Addable and Subtractable - [8];
- (v) Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together - [9].

The combined and enlarged version of above five items can seen in author's two recent work [10, 11]. In this work our aim is to bring **selfie fractions** with mixed operations with single or multiple representations, in increasing order of numerator without repetition of digits. This paper brings numerator in two and three digits, while next works are in four and five digits in numerators. Moreover, the **selfie fractions** are with denominator up to 6-digits. The work includes all basic operations, such as **addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, potentiation**, etc. The work with repetition of digits up to 3-digits numerator is given in Taneja [11]. Due to high quantity of numbers, the denominator is only up to 5-digits. Also, in all the case, the numerator is always less than denominator.

Remark 1.1. *The following two situations are considered:*

- (i) *The first number of the r.h.s of the fraction are always positive, for example,*

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{4 + 1508}{7 + 2639}.$$

The following expression also give selfie fraction,

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{-4 + 1508}{-7 + 2639}.$$

This kind of expressions are not considered as the first members of numerator and denominator are negative.

- (ii) *Even thought, the final expression is positive, but the numerator and denominator are not considered negative, for example,*

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{2 + 1564}{9 + 7038} := \frac{2 - 1564}{9 - 7038}$$

- (iii) *In all the case, the numerator is always less than denominator.*

2 Different Digits Selfie Fractions: Two Digits Numerator

This section brings **selfie fractions** for the numerator 2-digits numbers. Due to high quantity of number there are lot of extra brackets like "(...)". These can be removed easily by simplifications.

● **Numerator 12**

$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{36} := \frac{1+2}{3+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3456} := \frac{1^2}{(3+45) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{84956} := \frac{1+2}{8^4 \times 9 - 5^6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{48} := \frac{1+2}{4+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3840} := \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{89376} := \frac{1^2}{8 \times (937 - 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{54} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4896} := \frac{1^2}{4 \times ((8+9) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{369084} := \frac{1 \times 2}{3^6 \times 90 - 8^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{384} := \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{7584} := \frac{1^2}{7 + (5^{8-4})}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{394560} := \frac{1^2}{(3+9^4) \times 5 + 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{396} := \frac{1^2}{39-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{7968} := \frac{1^2}{7 \times 96 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{706854} := \frac{1 \times 2}{7^{06} + 8 \times 5 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{540} := \frac{1+2}{5+40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{34560} := \frac{1^2}{(3+45) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{709536} := \frac{1^2}{70 + 9^5 + 3 + 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{594} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5+94}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{37548} := \frac{1 \times 2}{(3+7) \times 5^4 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{735840} := \frac{1 \times 2}{7 \times 3 \times 5840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{648} := \frac{1^2}{6+48}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{39468} := \frac{1 \times 2}{3 + 9^4 + 6 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{958704} := \frac{1+2}{(9^5 + 870) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{756} := \frac{1^2}{7+56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{48960} := \frac{1^2}{4 \times (8+9) \times 60}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{864} := \frac{1^2}{8+64}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{73584} := \frac{1 \times 2}{7 \times 3 \times 584}$	

• Numerator 13

$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26} := \frac{1+3}{2+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2756} := \frac{1^3}{2+7 \times 5 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{47658} := \frac{1^3}{47 \times 6 \times (5+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{208} := \frac{1^3}{2 \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{5928} := \frac{1^3}{(59-2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{48672} := \frac{1^3}{(4+8 \times 6) \times 72}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{286} := \frac{1^3}{28-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{6240} := \frac{1^3}{6 \times 2 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{54782} := \frac{1^3}{54 \times 78 + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{429} := \frac{1+3}{2+86}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{7956} := \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{56784} := \frac{1+3}{56 \times 78 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{429} := \frac{1^3}{4+29}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{7956} := \frac{1^3}{(7+95) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{59280} := \frac{1^3}{(59-2) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{624} := \frac{1^3}{6 \times 2 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24960} := \frac{1 \times 3}{(2+4) \times 960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{68952} := \frac{1^3}{6 \times (8+9) \times 52}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2496} := \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24960} := \frac{1+3}{2 \times 4 \times 960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{79560} := \frac{1^3}{(7+95) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2496} := \frac{1 \times 3}{(2+4) \times 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{46579} := \frac{1^3}{4^6 - 57 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{87529} := \frac{1^3}{(87-5)^2 + 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2496} := \frac{1+3}{2 \times 4 \times 96}$		

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{280956} &:= \frac{1^3}{(2 + 80 \times 9 \times 5) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{285467} &:= \frac{1^3}{28^{5+4-6} + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{425867} &:= \frac{1^3}{(4 \times 2)^5 - 8 + 6 - 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{426985} &:= \frac{1^3}{4 + 2^6 + 9 + 8^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{452608} &:= \frac{1^3}{4^5 \times (26 + 08)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{452608} &:= \frac{1 + 3}{4^5 \times 2 \times (60 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{465920} &:= \frac{1 + 3}{4^6 \times 5 \times (9 - 2 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{486720} &:= \frac{1^3}{(4 + 8 \times 6) \times 720} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{567840} &:= \frac{1 + 3}{56 \times 78 \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{689520} &:= \frac{1^3}{6 \times (8 + 9) \times 520} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13}{852046} &:= \frac{1^3}{8^5 \times (2 + 0 \times 4) + 6} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 14

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{28} &:= \frac{1 + 4}{2 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{63} &:= \frac{1 \times 4}{6 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{308} &:= \frac{1^4}{30 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{630} &:= \frac{1 \times 4}{6 \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2856} &:= \frac{1 + 4}{2 \times (85 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3276} &:= \frac{1^4}{3 \times (2 + 76)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{9072} &:= \frac{1^4}{9 \times (0 + 72)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{9576} &:= \frac{1 + 4}{9 \times 5 \times 76} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{28560} &:= \frac{1 + 4}{2 \times (85 \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{29736} &:= \frac{1^4}{(2 + (9 + 7^3)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{32760} &:= \frac{1^4}{(32 + 7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{37065} &:= \frac{1 \times 4}{3 \times (706 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{37296} &:= \frac{1^4}{(3 + (7^2 \times 9)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{37968} &:= \frac{1^4}{((37 \times 9) + 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{53928} &:= \frac{1^4}{((53 + 9)^2) + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{95760} &:= \frac{1 + 4}{9 \times (5 \times 760)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{205968} &:= \frac{1^4}{(205 \times 9 - 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{297360} &:= \frac{1^4}{(2 + 9 + 7^3) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{372960} &:= \frac{1^4}{(3 + 7^2 \times 9) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{379680} &:= \frac{1^4}{(37 \times 9 + 6) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 15

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{24} &:= \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{27} &:= \frac{1 \times 5}{2 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{240} &:= \frac{1^5}{2^4 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{297} &:= \frac{1 \times 5}{2 + 97} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{432} &:= \frac{1 \times 5}{(4 \times 3)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{480} &:= \frac{1^5}{4 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{3240} &:= \frac{1 + 5}{(3 \times 2)^4 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{9720} &:= \frac{1^5}{9 \times (72 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{23790} &:= \frac{1^5}{2 \times (3 + 790)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{27648} &:= \frac{1 \times 5}{2^7 \times 6 \times (4 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{27864} &:= \frac{1 \times 5}{27 \times 86 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{34680} &:= \frac{1^5}{34 \times 68 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{43620} &:= \frac{1^5}{4 \times (3^6 - 2 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{43860} &:= \frac{1^5}{43 \times (8 + 60)} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{62394} := \frac{1 \times 5}{62 + (3 + 9)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{276480} := \frac{1^5}{2^7 \times (64 + 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{846720} := \frac{1^5}{8 \times 4 \times (6 \times 7)^2 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{64890} := \frac{1^5}{6 + 48 \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{278640} := \frac{1 \times 5}{27 \times (86 \times 40)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{84672} := \frac{1 \times 5}{((8 - 4) \times 6 \times 7)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{603792} := \frac{1 \times 5}{60 + 3^7 \times 92}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{263790} := \frac{1^5}{(2 + 6) \times 3^7 + 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{680943} := \frac{1 \times 5}{(6 \times 8 + 09 + 4)^3}$	

● Numerator 16

$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{528} := \frac{1^6}{5 + 28}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{37248} := \frac{1^6}{(3 + 72 \times 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{385472} := \frac{1^6}{38 \times (5^4 + 7 + 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2048} := \frac{1^6}{2^{04} \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{37824} := \frac{1^6}{37 \times 8^2 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{537920} := \frac{1^6}{5 \times (3 + 79)^2 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{5328} := \frac{1^6}{5 + 328}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{53824} := \frac{1^6}{(5 + 3 \times 8)^2 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{538240} := \frac{1^6}{(5 + 3 \times 8)^2 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{8352} := \frac{1^6}{8^3 + 5 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{257984} := \frac{1^6}{2^5 \times 7 \times 9 \times 8 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{807592} := \frac{1 \times 6}{(80 + 7) \times 59^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{9072} := \frac{1 + 6}{(9 \times 07)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{327584} := \frac{1^6}{3 - 2 - 7 + 5 \times 8^4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{35472} := \frac{1^6}{3 + 5 + 47^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{372480} := \frac{1^6}{(3 + 72 \times 4) \times 80}$	

● Numerator 17

$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{85} := \frac{1 + 7}{8 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{4386} := \frac{1 + 7}{43 \times 8 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{29648} := \frac{1 \times 7}{(2 + 8 \times 3^5) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{238} := \frac{1^7}{2 \times 3 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{4692} := \frac{1 + 7}{4 \times 6 \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{34680} := \frac{1^7}{(2 + 9 \times 6 \times 4) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{306} := \frac{1^7}{3 \times 06}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{4862} := \frac{1^7}{(48 \times 6) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{34986} := \frac{1 + 7}{34 \times 6 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{850} := \frac{1 + 7}{8 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{8432} := \frac{1^7}{8 \times ((4^3) - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{34986} := \frac{1^7}{3 \times 49 \times (8 + 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{2805} := \frac{1^7}{(2 \times 80) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{25364} := \frac{1^7}{2 \times ((5^3 \times 6) - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{35649} := \frac{1^7}{(3^5 - 6 - 4) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{2958} := \frac{1^7}{2 \times (95 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{28305} := \frac{1^7}{(2 \times 830) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{38964} := \frac{1^7}{3 \times (8 \times 96 - 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{3468} := \frac{1 + 7}{34 \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{28356} := \frac{1^7}{(283 - 5) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{43860} := \frac{1 + 7}{43 \times 8 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{4352} := \frac{1^7}{4 \times (3 + 5)^2}$		

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{46920} &:= \frac{1+7}{4 \times 6 \times 920} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{58429} &:= \frac{1^7}{5+8 \times 429} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{65824} &:= \frac{1+7}{((6+5) \times 8)^2 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{68952} &:= \frac{1^7}{(6+8 \times 9) \times 52} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{95438} &:= \frac{1^7}{9 \times 5^4 - 3 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{96305} &:= \frac{1^7}{9 \times 630 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{243865} &:= \frac{1^7}{2 \times 4 + 3^8 + 6^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{283560} &:= \frac{1 \times 7}{(2+8 \times 3^5) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{283560} &:= \frac{1^7}{(283-5) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{296480} &:= \frac{1^7}{(2+9 \times 6 \times 4) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{346528} &:= \frac{1^7}{(3+46) \times 52 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{352648} &:= \frac{1^7}{3+5+2 \times 6^4 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{352648} &:= \frac{1+7}{(3+5+(2 \times 6)^4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{356490} &:= \frac{1^7}{(3^5-6-4) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{452608} &:= \frac{1^7}{4^5 \times 26 + 0 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{452608} &:= \frac{1+7}{4^5 \times 26 \times 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{524603} &:= \frac{1 \times 7}{5+2 \times 4+60^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{539648} &:= \frac{1^7}{(53+9) \times 64 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{658240} &:= \frac{1+7}{((6+5) \times 8)^2 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{689520} &:= \frac{1^7}{(6+8 \times 9) \times 520} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 18

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{36} &:= \frac{1+8}{3 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{45} &:= \frac{1 \times 8}{4 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{324} &:= \frac{1^8}{3 \times (2+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{342} &:= \frac{1^8}{3+4^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{360} &:= \frac{1+8}{3 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{432} &:= \frac{1^8}{4 \times 3 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{450} &:= \frac{1 \times 8}{4 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2304} &:= \frac{1^8}{2^{3+04}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2736} &:= \frac{1^8}{2 \times 73+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3546} &:= \frac{1^8}{3^5-46} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3645} &:= \frac{1 \times 8}{36 \times 45} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{4320} &:= \frac{1^8}{4 \times 3 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{4536} &:= \frac{1^8}{(45-3) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{7056} &:= \frac{1^8}{7 \times 056} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{7326} &:= \frac{1^8}{7^3+2^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{7695} &:= \frac{1 \times 8}{76 \times 9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{7926} &:= \frac{1+8}{(7 \times 9)^2 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20736} &:= \frac{1^8}{20^7 \times (3+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23490} &:= \frac{1^8}{(2 \times 3)^4 + 9 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{29736} &:= \frac{1^8}{2 \times (97+3^6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{36450} &:= \frac{1 \times 8}{36 \times 450} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37206} &:= \frac{1^8}{3^7-20 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37296} &:= \frac{1^8}{37 \times (2+9 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39254} &:= \frac{1+8}{3^9-2-54} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39426} &:= \frac{1+8}{3^9+4+26} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39452} &:= \frac{1+8}{3^9+45-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39462} &:= \frac{1+8}{3^9+4 \times 6 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39472} &:= \frac{1+8}{3^9+4+7^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{45360} &:= \frac{1^8}{(45-3) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{45927} &:= \frac{1 \times 8}{(45+9)^2 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{59472} &:= \frac{1^8}{59 \times 4 \times 7 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{63504} &:= \frac{1+8}{63 \times 504} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{76950} &:= \frac{1 \times 8}{76 \times 9 \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{79632} := \frac{1+8}{7 \times 9 \times 632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{354762} := \frac{1^8}{3^{5+4} + (7+6) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{594720} := \frac{1^8}{59 \times 4 \times 7 \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{92736} := \frac{1^8}{(9-2) \times (7+3^6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{459270} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(45+9)^2 \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{756324} := \frac{1 \times 8}{7^5 \times (6 \times 3 + 2) + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{263574} := \frac{1^8}{2 + (6+3-5+7)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{459270} := \frac{1^8}{45 \times 9^2 \times 7 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{796320} := \frac{1+8}{7 \times 9 \times 6320}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{354276} := \frac{1^8}{3^{5+4} - 2 + 7 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{472536} := \frac{1+8}{4 \times ((7+2)^5 + 3 \times 6)}$	

● Numerator 19

$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{247} := \frac{1^9}{2+4+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{3724} := \frac{1 \times 9}{((3 \times 7)^2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{37240} := \frac{1 \times 9}{(3 \times 7)^2 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{285} := \frac{1^9}{2+8+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{3857} := \frac{1^9}{(3 \times 8 + 5) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{38570} := \frac{1^9}{(3 \times 8 + 5) \times 70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{342} := \frac{1 \times 9}{3^4 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{4237} := \frac{1^9}{((4+2)^3) + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{57684} := \frac{1^9}{5 \times 76 \times 8 - 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{342} := \frac{1^9}{3 \times (4+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{6327} := \frac{1^9}{6+327}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{67450} := \frac{1^9}{(67+4) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{627} := \frac{1^9}{6+27}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{6574} := \frac{1^9}{6 \times 57 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{82574} := \frac{1^9}{82 \times (57-4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{836} := \frac{1^9}{8+36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{6745} := \frac{1^9}{(67+4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{234650} := \frac{1^9}{(23-4) \times 650}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2546} := \frac{1^9}{(2^5 \times 4) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{8436} := \frac{1^9}{8+436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{243675} := \frac{1^9}{(2^4+3) \times 675}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2736} := \frac{1^9}{(27-3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23465} := \frac{1^9}{(23-4) \times 65}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{253460} := \frac{1^9}{(2^5-3) \times 460}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{3420} := \frac{1 \times 9}{3^4 \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{25346} := \frac{1^9}{(2^5-3) \times 46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{357048} := \frac{1 \times 9}{3^5 \times (704-8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{3648} := \frac{1 \times 9}{36 \times 48}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{27360} := \frac{1^9}{(27-3) \times 60}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{3705} := \frac{1^9}{3 \times (70-5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{36480} := \frac{1 \times 9}{36 \times 480}$	

● Numerator 21

$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{63} := \frac{2-1}{6-3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{84} := \frac{2-1}{8-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{378} := \frac{2-1}{3+7+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{63} := \frac{2+1}{6+3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{84} := \frac{2+1}{8+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{385} := \frac{2+1}{(3+8) \times 5}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{546} := \frac{2-1}{5 \times 4 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{6048} := \frac{2-1}{6 \times 048}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{63798} := \frac{2-1}{6 + 379 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{693} := \frac{2-1}{6 + 9 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{6384} := \frac{2+1}{6 \times 38 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{63840} := \frac{2+1}{6 \times 38 \times 40}$
$\quad := \frac{2 \times 1}{69 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{7035} := \frac{2-1}{(70 - 3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{75684} := \frac{2-1}{75 \times 6 \times 8 + 4}$
$\quad := \frac{2+1}{6+93}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{7350} := \frac{2+1}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{90867} := \frac{2-1}{90 \times 8 \times 6 + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{735} := \frac{2+1}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{7560} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(7+5) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{93450} := \frac{2-1}{(93-4) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{756} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(7+5) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{9345} := \frac{2-1}{(93-4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{358974} := \frac{2-1}{3 \times (5+8 \times 9) \times 74}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{3675} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(3+67) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{53760} := \frac{2+1}{(5-3)^7 \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{367584} := \frac{2-1}{3^6 + 7^5 - 8 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{3850} := \frac{2+1}{(3+8) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{34587} := \frac{2+1}{3^4 \times (5+8 \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{398475} := \frac{2+1}{(3+9 \times 84) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{3906} := \frac{2+1}{(3+90) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{35679} := \frac{2 \times 1}{3+5 \times 679}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{470589} := \frac{2+1}{4 \times 7^{05} + 8 - 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{4368} := \frac{2-1}{4+3 \times 68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{36750} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(3+67) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{470659} := \frac{2+1}{4 \times 7^{0 \times 6 + 5} + 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{5376} := \frac{2+1}{(5-3)^7 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{63504} := \frac{2+1}{6 \times 3 \times 504}$	

● Numerator 23

$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{46} := \frac{2+3}{4+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{49680} := \frac{2^3}{4 \times 9 \times 6 \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{905418} := \frac{2 \times 3}{9^{05} \times 4 \times 1^8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{69} := \frac{2+3}{6+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{94185} := \frac{2^3}{((9^4) - 1 - 8) \times 5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{4968} := \frac{2^3}{4 \times (9 \times 6 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{105984} := \frac{2^3}{1^{05} \times 9 \times 8^4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{47081} := \frac{2^3}{4^7 - 08 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{795846} := \frac{2^3}{79 \times 584 \times 6}$	

● Numerator 24

$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{36} := \frac{2+4}{3+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{168} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(1+6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{675} := \frac{2^4}{6 \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{150} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{396} := \frac{2+4}{3+96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{735} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 \times 35}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1539} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 + (5 - 3)^9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17850} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 7 \times 850}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{358176} := \frac{2 \times 4}{3 \times 581 + 7^6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1680} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(1 + 6) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{18796} := \frac{2 + 4}{1 + 87 \times 9 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{586107} := \frac{2^4}{5^8 + 6 + 107}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1785} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 7 \times 85}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{167835} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 67 \times 835}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{586137} := \frac{2^4}{5^8 + ((6 + 13) \times 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{6750} := \frac{2^4}{6 \times 750}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{176538} := \frac{2^4}{1 \times 7^6 + 5 + 38}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{786513} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 + 8^6 + 5 \times (1 + 3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{7350} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 \times 350}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{176589} := \frac{2^4}{1 \times 7^6 + 5 + 8 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{786591} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 + 8^6 + 5 \times 9 + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{9375} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(9 + 3 - 7)^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{176895} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(1 - 7) \times (6 + 8) + 9^5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10935} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 09^3 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{186579} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 + 8 \times (6^5 + 7 - 9)}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{187503} := \frac{2^4}{1 + 8 - 7 + 50^3}$	

• Numerator 26

$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{39} := \frac{2 + 6}{3 + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{98735} := \frac{2 + 6}{9 \times (8 + 7)^3 + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{189735} := \frac{2 \times 6}{18 \times 973 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{143} := \frac{2 + 6}{1 + 43}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{180947} := \frac{2 \times 6}{(1 \times 8 + 09)^4 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{539487} := \frac{2 + 6}{53 \times 9 \times 4 \times 87}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{18954} := \frac{2 \times 6}{18 \times 9 \times 54}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{189540} := \frac{2 \times 6}{18 \times 9 \times 540}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{93184} := \frac{2 + 6}{(9 - 3 + 1) \times 8^4}$		

• Numerator 27

$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{150} := \frac{2 + 7}{1 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{10935} := \frac{2 + 7}{1 \times 09^3 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{483165} := \frac{2 + 7}{4 + (8 + 3 \times 16)^5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{168} := \frac{2 + 7}{(1 + 6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{18456} := \frac{2 + 7}{1 \times 8 + 4^5 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{653184} := \frac{2^7}{6 \times (5^3 + 1) \times 8^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1539} := \frac{2 + 7}{1 + (5 - 3)^9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{98415} := \frac{2 + 7}{9^{8-4 \times 1} \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{653184} := \frac{2 + 7}{6^5 \times (3 \times 1 \times 8 + 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1680} := \frac{2 + 7}{(1 + 6) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{184305} := \frac{2 + 7}{(-1 + 8^4 \times 3) \times 05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{680943} := \frac{2 + 7}{(6 \times 8 + 09 + 4)^3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1854} := \frac{2 + 7}{1 - 8 + 5^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{184635} := \frac{2 + 7}{(1 + 8^4 + 6) \times 3 \times 5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{5184} := \frac{2^7}{(5 + 1) \times 8^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{196548} := \frac{2 + 7}{1 + 9 - 6 \times 5 + 4^8}$	

● Numerator 28

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{154} := \frac{2+8}{1+54} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{45360} := \frac{2+8}{45 \times 360} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{179354} := \frac{2 \times 8}{1+7 \times (9-3+5)^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{4536} := \frac{2+8}{45 \times 36} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{95760} := \frac{2+8}{9 \times 5 \times 760} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{9576} := \frac{2+8}{9 \times 5 \times 76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{103495} := \frac{2 \times 8}{10+3^4+9^5} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{43750} := \frac{2^8}{4 \times (3+7)^5+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28}{109375} := \frac{2^8}{(1+09)^{3 \times (7-5)}} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 29

$$\begin{array}{ll} \blacktriangleright \frac{29}{10846} := \frac{2+9}{10+(8+4^6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29}{507384} := \frac{2 \times 9}{(5+07) \times 3^8 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{29}{475136} := \frac{2+9}{4^7 \times (5+1^3 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29}{856341} := \frac{2 \times 9}{(8+5^6) \times 34 \times 1} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 31

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{62} := \frac{3-1}{6-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{2945} := \frac{3-1}{(2+9 \times 4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{80259} := \frac{3 \times 1}{(8-02)^5-9} \\ & := \frac{3+1}{6+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{90675} := \frac{3-1}{90 \times (6+7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{248} := \frac{3-1}{24-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{9486} := \frac{3-1}{(94+8) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{94705} := \frac{3-1}{94 \times (70-5)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 1}{2 \times (4+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{25048} := \frac{3-1}{(2+50 \times 4) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3+1}{24+8} & := \frac{3 \times 1}{(9+4) \times 705} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{279} := \frac{3-1}{2+7+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{26784} := \frac{3-1}{(2 \times 6)^{7-8+4}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{94860} := \frac{3-1}{(94+8) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{3+1}{27+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{254076} := \frac{3+1}{2 \times (5+40^7)+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{496} := \frac{3+1}{4^9-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{29574} := \frac{3-1}{(2^9-5 \times 7) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{295740} := \frac{3-1}{(2^9-5 \times 7) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{682} := \frac{3 \times 1}{68-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{29605} := \frac{3-1}{2 \times (960-5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{406782} := \frac{3-1}{(40 \times 6-78)^2} \\ & := \frac{3+1}{6+82} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{408952} := \frac{3 \times 1}{408 \times (95+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{2046} := \frac{3 \times 1}{204-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{74586} := \frac{3-1}{(7^4+5) \times (8-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{784269} := \frac{3 \times 1}{(7+8426) \times 9} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 1}{7 \times (4^5+8)-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31}{796824} := \frac{3+1}{7 \times 9 \times 8 \times 24} \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31}{847695} := \frac{3 \times 1}{(8 + 4^7 + 6 + 9) \times 5}$$

• Numerator 32

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{64} := \frac{3-2}{6-4}$$

$$:= \frac{3+2}{6+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{96} := \frac{3-2}{9-6}$$

$$:= \frac{3+2}{9+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{576} := \frac{3-2}{5+7+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1504} := \frac{3-2}{1+50-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1568} := \frac{3-2}{1+56-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{14976} := \frac{3-2}{1 \times 4 \times 9 \times (7+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{17408} := \frac{3-2}{17 \times 4 \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 2}{(1+7) \times 408}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{17856} := \frac{3-2}{(1+7+85) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{85760} := \frac{3-2}{8 \times 5 \times (7+60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{104768} := \frac{3+2}{1 \times 04^7 - 6 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{147968} := \frac{3-2}{(1+4+7 \times 9) \times 68}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{156480} := \frac{3-2}{15 \times (6+4 \times 80)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{178560} := \frac{3-2}{(1+7+85) \times 60}$$

• Numerator 34

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{68} := \frac{3+4}{6+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{612} := \frac{3 \times 4}{6^{1+2}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{952} := \frac{3+4}{(9+5)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1258} := \frac{3+4}{1+258}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2176} := \frac{3 \times 4}{2^{1 \times 7} \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2516} := \frac{3+4}{2+516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2958} := \frac{3 \times 4}{2 \times 9 \times 58}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{15062} := \frac{3+4}{1+50 \times 62}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{19856} := \frac{3+4}{(1+9 \times 8) \times 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{21760} := \frac{3 \times 4}{2^{1 \times 7} \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{29580} := \frac{3 \times 4}{2 \times 9 \times 580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{186592} := \frac{3+4}{((1 \times 8 + 6) \times (5 + 9))^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{198560} := \frac{3+4}{(1+9 \times 8) \times 560}$$

• Numerator 35

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35}{189} := \frac{3 \times 5}{(1+8) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35}{1890} := \frac{3 \times 5}{(1+8) \times 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35}{17920} := \frac{3+5}{(1+7 \times 9)^2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35}{84672} := \frac{3 \times 5}{84 \times 6 \times 72}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35}{846720} := \frac{3 \times 5}{84 \times 6 \times 720}$$

• Numerator 36

$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{48} := \frac{3+6}{4+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{5184} := \frac{3+6}{(5+18)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{705894} := \frac{3 \times 6}{70^5 \times (8+9+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{198} := \frac{3 \times 6}{1+98}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{14728} := \frac{3+6}{14 \times (7+2^8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{948712} := \frac{3+6}{9+487^{1 \times 2}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1024} := \frac{3^6}{(10+2)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{15842} := \frac{3 \times 6}{(1 \times 5+84)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{958704} := \frac{3+6}{(9^5+870) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1028} := \frac{3+6}{1+02^8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{17504} := \frac{3+6}{1+7 \times 50^4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1254} := \frac{3 \times 6}{1 \times 2+5^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{197428} := \frac{3+6}{1+9 \times (74^2+8)}$	

● Numerator 37

$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{148} := \frac{3+7}{(1+4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{28416} := \frac{3+7}{2^8 \times (4+1) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{621859} := \frac{3^7}{(6 \times 2+1+8)^5 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{1480} := \frac{3+7}{(1+4) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{159840} := \frac{3+7}{15 \times 9 \times 8 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{804195} := \frac{3^7}{(804+1) \times 9^5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{15984} := \frac{3+7}{15 \times (9 \times 8 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{284160} := \frac{3+7}{2^8 \times (4+1) \times 60}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{291486} := \frac{3+7}{(2 \times 9^{1 \times 4} + 8) \times 6}$	

● Numerator 38

$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{1406} := \frac{3+8}{1+406}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{4750} := \frac{3 \times 8}{4 \times 750}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{475} := \frac{3 \times 8}{4 \times 75}$	

● Numerator 39

$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{286} := \frac{3+9}{2+86}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{5486} := \frac{3 \times 9}{(5^4+8) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{3+9}{1 \times 8 \times 720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{1248} := \frac{3+9}{12 \times 4 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{12480} := \frac{3+9}{12 \times 4 \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{21840} := \frac{3+9}{21 \times 8 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{1768} := \frac{3+9}{(1+7) \times 68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{14625} := \frac{3+9}{((1+4) \times 6)^2 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{54860} := \frac{3 \times 9}{(5^4+8) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{1872} := \frac{3 \times 9}{18 \times 72}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{17680} := \frac{3+9}{(1+7) \times 680}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{56784} := \frac{3+9}{56 \times 78 \times 4}$
$:= \frac{3+9}{1 \times (8 \times 72)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{18720} := \frac{3 \times 9}{18 \times 720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{81562} := \frac{3+9}{8 \times (1+56^2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{2184} := \frac{3+9}{21 \times 8 \times 4}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{128076} := \frac{3+9}{((1+2)^8+07) \times 6}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{146250} := \frac{3+9}{((1+4) \times 6)^2 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{451672} := \frac{3 \times 9}{4 \times (5^{1+6} + 7^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{567840} := \frac{3+9}{56 \times 78 \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{184275} := \frac{3+9}{18 \times 42 \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{452608} := \frac{3+9}{4^5 \times 2 \times (60+8)}$$

• Numerator 41

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{82} := \frac{4-1}{8-2}$$

$$:= \frac{4+1}{3 \times (6+9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{36859} := \frac{4 \times 1}{(3^6 - 8) \times 5 - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{4+1}{8+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{902} := \frac{4 \times 1}{90-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{58097} := \frac{4 \times 1}{5+809 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{205} := \frac{4-1}{20-5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{3075} := \frac{4-1}{3 \times 075}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{89257} := \frac{4-1}{(8+925) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{4+1}{20+5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{2706} := \frac{4 \times 1}{270-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{93275} := \frac{4-1}{(93-2) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{287} := \frac{4-1}{28-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{3280} := \frac{4+1}{(3+2) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{275069} := \frac{4+1}{2 \times 7^5 - 069}$$

$$:= \frac{4+1}{28+7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{3608} := \frac{4 \times 1}{360-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{753826} := \frac{4+1}{7 \times (5+3^8) \times 2+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{328} := \frac{4-1}{32-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{6273} := \frac{4+1}{6 \times 2^7 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4+1}{32+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{20869} := \frac{4-1}{2^{08} \times 6 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{369} := \frac{4-1}{36-9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{35629} := \frac{4-1}{(3^5 - 6) \times (2+9)}$$

• Numerator 42

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{63} := \frac{4-2}{6-3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{189} := \frac{4^2}{1 \times 8 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{385} := \frac{4+2}{(3+8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4+2}{6+3}$$

$$:= \frac{4-2}{18-9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{651} := \frac{4-2}{6 \times 5+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{105} := \frac{4-2}{1 \times 05}$$

$$:= \frac{4+2}{18+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{693} := \frac{4-2}{6+9 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4+2}{10+5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{315} := \frac{4-2}{3 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4+2}{6+93}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{168} := \frac{4-2}{16-8}$$

$$:= \frac{4+2}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{735} := \frac{4+2}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4+2}{16+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{378} := \frac{4-2}{3+7+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1365} := \frac{4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 65}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{4-2}{1^3 \times 65} \\
 := \frac{4+2}{1 \times 3 \times 65} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1386} := \frac{4-2}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1596} := \frac{4-2}{1 + 5 \times (9 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1680} := \frac{4-2}{1^6 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1785} := \frac{4^2}{17 \times 8 \times 5} \\
 := \frac{4-2}{1^7 \times 85} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1806} := \frac{4-2}{1 \times 80 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1890} := \frac{4^2}{1 \times 8 \times 90} \\
 := \frac{4-2}{1 + 89 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{1953} := \frac{4-2}{1 + 95 - 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{3150} := \frac{4-2}{3 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 := \frac{4+2}{3 \times 150} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{3850} := \frac{4+2}{(3+8) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{3906} := \frac{4+2}{(3+90) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{5376} := \frac{4+2}{(5-3)^7 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{5691} := \frac{4-2}{5 \times 6 \times 9 + 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{7035} := \frac{4-2}{(70-3) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{7350} := \frac{4+2}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{7938} := \frac{4 \times 2}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{10836} := \frac{4-2}{10 + (8^3 - 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13650} := \frac{4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 650} \\
 := \frac{4-2}{1^3 \times 650} \\
 := \frac{4+2}{1 \times 3 \times 650} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13860} := \frac{4-2}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13965} := \frac{4-2}{(139-6) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13986} := \frac{4-2}{(13+98) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{15379} := \frac{4+2}{1^5 + 3^7 + 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{17850} := \frac{4^2}{17 \times 8 \times 50} \\
 := \frac{4-2}{1^7 \times 850} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{18375} := \frac{4-2}{(1+8 \times 3) \times 7 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{18753} := \frac{4-2}{18 + 7 \times 5^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{30618} := \frac{4 \times 2}{3^{06} \times 1 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{36981} := \frac{4-2}{3 \times (6 \times 98 - 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{51639} := \frac{4^2}{5 - 16 + 3^9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{53760} := \frac{4+2}{(5-3)^7 \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{63798} := \frac{4-2}{6 + 379 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{71568} := \frac{4-2}{71 \times (56-8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{79380} := \frac{4 \times 2}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{90867} := \frac{4-2}{90 \times 8 \times 6 + 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{138096} := \frac{4-2}{1 \times 3^8 + 09 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{139650} := \frac{4-2}{(139-6) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{139860} := \frac{4-2}{(13+98) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{159768} := \frac{4-2}{(15 \times 9 \times 7 + 6) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{169057} := \frac{4+2}{1 + 690 \times 5 \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{175938} := \frac{4 \times 2}{(1+7)^5 + 93 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{183750} := \frac{4-2}{(1+8 \times 3) \times 7 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{196875} := \frac{4+2}{1 \times 9 \times (6-8+7)^5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{197568} := \frac{4+2}{1 \times 9 \times 7 \times 56 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42}{675318} := \frac{4^2}{6 \times ((7 \times 5)^3 + 1) + 8}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 43

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43}{86} := \frac{4-3}{8-6} \\
 := \frac{4+3}{8+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43}{129} := \frac{4-3}{12-9}
 \end{array}$$

$\frac{43}{215} := \frac{4+3}{(2-1) \times 5}$	$\frac{43}{18576} := \frac{4 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 576}$	$\frac{43}{169850} := \frac{4+3}{(1+69 \times 8) \times 50}$
$\frac{43}{258} := \frac{4+3}{2+5 \times 8}$	$\frac{43}{18705} := \frac{4-3}{1 \times 87 \times 05}$	$\frac{43}{169850} := \frac{4-3}{(1+6+9 \times 8) \times 50}$
$\frac{43}{516} := \frac{4-3}{5+1+6}$	$\frac{43}{19608} := \frac{4 \times 3}{1 \times 9 \times 608}$	$\frac{43}{170925} := \frac{4-3}{1+(7 \times 09)^2+5}$
$\frac{43}{1290} := \frac{4-3}{1+29+0}$	$\frac{43}{26015} := \frac{4-3}{(2 \times 60+1) \times 5}$	$\frac{43}{185760} := \frac{4 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 5760}$
$\frac{43}{1806} := \frac{4-3}{(-1+8) \times 06}$	$\frac{43}{26187} := \frac{4-3}{(2+6-1) \times 87}$	$\frac{43}{187265} := \frac{4-3}{(18+7^2) \times 65}$
$\frac{43}{2150} := \frac{4-3}{(2-1) \times 50}$	$\frac{43}{26789} := \frac{4^3}{2^6 \times 7 \times 89}$	$\frac{43}{210786} := \frac{4-3}{2+(10 \times 7)^{8-6}}$
$\frac{43}{2580} := \frac{4-3}{2+58+0}$	$\frac{43}{56029} := \frac{4 \times 3}{5^6+02+9}$	$\frac{43}{215086} := \frac{4-3}{2 \times (1+50^{8-6})}$
$\frac{43}{2709} := \frac{4-3}{2+70-9}$	$\frac{43}{81270} := \frac{4-3}{(8-1) \times 270}$	$\frac{43}{261870} := \frac{4-3}{(2+6-1) \times 870}$
$\frac{43}{7095} := \frac{4-3}{70+95}$	$\frac{43}{82560} := \frac{4-3}{8^2 \times 5 \times 6+0}$	$\frac{43}{267890} := \frac{4^3}{2 \times 6 \times 7 \times 890}$
$\frac{43}{8127} := \frac{4-3}{(8-1) \times 27}$	$\frac{43}{96750} := \frac{4-3}{(9-6) \times 750}$	$\frac{43}{267890} := \frac{4^3}{2^6 \times 7 \times 890}$
$\frac{43}{9675} := \frac{4-3}{(9-6) \times 75}$	$\frac{43}{106597} := \frac{4-3}{1+06 \times 59 \times 7}$	$\frac{43}{268750} := \frac{4-3}{2 \times (6-8+7)^5+0}$
$\frac{43}{16985} := \frac{4-3}{(1+6+9 \times 8) \times 5}$	$\frac{43}{127968} := \frac{4-3}{(1-2+7 \times 9) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\frac{43}{756198} := \frac{4^3}{(7+5^6) \times 1 \times 9 \times 8}$
$\frac{43}{16985} := \frac{4+3}{(1+69 \times 8) \times 5}$	$\frac{43}{157896} := \frac{4-3}{(1+5 \times 7) \times (8+9) \times 6}$	

• Numerator 45

$\frac{45}{180} := \frac{4 \times 5}{1 \times 80}$	$\frac{45}{3690} := \frac{4+5}{3^6+9+0}$
$\frac{45}{378} := \frac{4 \times 5}{3 \times 7 \times 8}$	$\frac{45}{3780} := \frac{4 \times 5}{3 \times 7 \times 80}$
$\frac{45}{1280} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 2^8+0}$	$\frac{45}{327680} := \frac{4+5}{(3+2-7+6)^8+0}$

• Numerator 46

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46}{253} &:= \frac{4+6}{2+53} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46}{58029} &:= \frac{4 \times 6}{58^{01} \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46}{129375} &:= \frac{4+6}{(1+2) \times 9375} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46}{352107} &:= \frac{4+6}{35 \times (2+1)^{07}} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 48

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{132} &:= \frac{4+8}{1+32} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{396} &:= \frac{4+8}{3+96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{675} &:= \frac{4 \times 8}{6 \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{972} &:= \frac{4 \times 8}{9 \times 72} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{6750} &:= \frac{4 \times 8}{6 \times 750} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{9720} &:= \frac{4 \times 8}{9 \times 720} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{10932} &:= \frac{4 \times 8}{10 \times 9^3 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{92736} &:= \frac{4+8}{92 \times 7 \times 36} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{137592} &:= \frac{4 \times 8}{13 \times (75+9)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{157392} &:= \frac{4+8}{1-5+(-7+3^9) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{192036} &:= \frac{4+8}{1 \times 9 + 20^3 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{201756} &:= \frac{4+8}{(2+01) \times (7^5+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{927360} &:= \frac{4+8}{92 \times 7 \times 360} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 49

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{49}{3675} &:= \frac{4 \times 9}{36 \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{49}{36750} &:= \frac{4 \times 9}{36 \times 750} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 51

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{204} &:= \frac{5-1}{2^{04}} \\ &:= \frac{5+1}{20+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{289} &:= \frac{5+1}{2 \times (8+9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{306} &:= \frac{5-1}{30-6} \\ &:= \frac{5+1}{30+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{408} &:= \frac{5-1}{4 \times 08} \\ &:= \frac{5+1}{40+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{748} &:= \frac{5+1}{(7+4) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{2346} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{23 \times (4+6)} \\ &:= \frac{5+1}{2 \times 3 \times 46} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{2703} &:= \frac{5-1}{2+(70 \times 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{3264} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{32 \times (6+4)} \\ &:= \frac{5+1}{3 \times 2 \times 64} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{3927} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{392-7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{4692} &:= \frac{5+1}{4 \times 69 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{4896} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{4 \times 8 \times (9+6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{7480} &:= \frac{5+1}{(7+4) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{23460} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{(2+3) \times 460} \\ &:= \frac{5+1}{2 \times 3 \times 460} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{24837} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{248+3^7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{30294} &:= \frac{5+1}{(30^2-9) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{32640} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{(3+2) \times 640} \\ &:= \frac{5+1}{3 \times 2 \times 640} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{34068} &:= \frac{5-1}{(340-6) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{34986} &:= \frac{5+1}{(3+4) \times 98 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{37264} &:= \frac{5+1}{3^7 \times 2 + 6 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{38046} &:= \frac{5+1}{380 + 4^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{39678} &:= \frac{5-1}{(396-7) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{46920} &:= \frac{5+1}{4 \times 69 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{243780} &:= \frac{5+1}{2^{4 \times 3} \times 7 + 8 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{283764} &:= \frac{5-1}{28^3 + 76 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{293760} &:= \frac{5-1}{2^9 \times (3+7 \times 6) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{349860} &:= \frac{5+1}{(3+4) \times 98 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{382976} &:= \frac{5+1}{(3+8) \times 2^{(9-7) \times 6}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{396780} &:= \frac{5-1}{(396-7) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{397426} &:= \frac{5+1}{3+97+(4+2)^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{473926} &:= \frac{5+1}{4^7 + 3^9 \times 2 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{793628} &:= \frac{5+1}{(7+9 \times 36^2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51}{942837} &:= \frac{5 \times 1}{(9^4 \times 2 + 83) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 52

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{78} &:= \frac{5 \times 2}{7+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{104} &:= \frac{5-2}{10-4} \\ &:= \frac{5+2}{10+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{416} &:= \frac{5-2}{4 \times 1 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{1768} &:= \frac{5+2}{17 \times (6+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{3016} &:= \frac{5-2}{(30-1) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{3796} &:= \frac{5-2}{3 \times (79-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{4160} &:= \frac{5-2}{4 \times 1 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{8736} &:= \frac{5-2}{8 \times 7 \times (3+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{37908} &:= \frac{5-2}{3^7 \times (9-08)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{37960} &:= \frac{5-2}{3^7 + 9 - 6 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{87360} &:= \frac{5-2}{(87-3) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{103896} &:= \frac{5-2}{(103+8) \times 9 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{487396} &:= \frac{5+2}{4^8 + 7 \times 3 + 9 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{761384} &:= \frac{5+2}{7 + (6+1) \times (3+8)^4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 53

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{106} &:= \frac{5+3}{10+6} \\ &:= \frac{5-3}{10-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{742} &:= \frac{5+3}{7 \times 4^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{1749} &:= \frac{5-3}{1+74-9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{1908} &:= \frac{5-3}{1 \times 9 \times 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{2014} &:= \frac{5-3}{(20-1) \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{2968} &:= \frac{5+3}{(2+9 \times 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{17649} &:= \frac{5-3}{17+649} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{29468} &:= \frac{5-3}{2 \times (94 \times 6 - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{29680} &:= \frac{5+3}{(2+9 \times 6) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{49608} &:= \frac{5-3}{4 \times 9 \times (60-8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{160749} &:= \frac{5-3}{1+6074-9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{217406} &:= \frac{5-3}{2 \times ((1+7)^4 + 06)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{276819} &:= \frac{5 \times 3}{(2^7 \times 68 + 1) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{280476} &:= \frac{5-3}{(2^8 - 04) \times 7 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{297648} &:= \frac{5-3}{2 \times 9 \times (7+6) \times 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{410697} &:= \frac{5-3}{41 \times 06 \times 9 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53}{461789} &:= \frac{5+3}{4^6 \times 17 + 8 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53}{869147} := \frac{5+3}{8 \times (6+9+1 \times 4^7)}$$

● Numerator 54

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{108} := \frac{5+4}{10+8}$$

$$:= \frac{5-4}{10-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{120} := \frac{5+4}{1 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{162} := \frac{5-4}{1^6+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{918} := \frac{5-4}{9+1 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{972} := \frac{5-4}{9+7+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{1296} := \frac{5-4}{1+29-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{1782} := \frac{5-4}{17+8 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3672} := \frac{5-4}{3+67-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3726} := \frac{5-4}{3+72-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{10368} := \frac{5-4}{(1+03) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{10692} := \frac{5-4}{106+92}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{12096} := \frac{5+4}{(1+20) \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{12690} := \frac{5-4}{1+26 \times 9+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{12798} := \frac{5-4}{(1+2) \times (7+9 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{20196} := \frac{5-4}{20 \times 19-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{36720} := \frac{5-4}{3^6-7^2+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{37296} := \frac{5+4}{3 \times 7 \times 296}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{37902} := \frac{5+4}{3+7 \times 902}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{70362} := \frac{5-4}{7+036^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{93762} := \frac{5+4}{(9+3-7)^6+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{163728} := \frac{5-4}{(1+6+372) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{182736} := \frac{5-4}{((1+8)^2 \times 7-3) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{187392} := \frac{5+4}{((18+7)^3-9) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{203796} := \frac{5-4}{20 \times 3 \times 7 \times 9-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{217836} := \frac{5-4}{2 \times (1+7 \times 8 \times 36)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{237168} := \frac{5-4}{2 \times (3^7+1^6+8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{237816} := \frac{5-4}{2 \times (3^7+8+1+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{271890} := \frac{5-4}{2+7 \times (-1+8 \times 90)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{283176} := \frac{5 \times 4}{2 \times 8 \times (3^{1+7}-6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{368172} := \frac{5-4}{3+6817-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{372960} := \frac{5+4}{3 \times 7 \times 2960}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{613089} := \frac{5 \times 4}{61^3+089}$$

● Numerator 57

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{1368} := \frac{5+7}{1 \times 36 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{2698} := \frac{5+7}{(2+69) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{3648} := \frac{5+7}{3 \times (6-4)^8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{6498} := \frac{5+7}{6^4+9 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{13680} := \frac{5+7}{1 \times 36 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{26980} := \frac{5+7}{(2+69) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{29184} := \frac{5+7}{2^9 \times 1 \times (8+4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{43928} := \frac{5+7}{(43-9)^2 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{83106} := \frac{5+7}{8 \times 3^{1+06}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{102638} := \frac{5+7}{10^2 \times 6^3+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{249318} := \frac{5+7}{2 \times 4 \times 9^{3+18}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{291840} := \frac{5^7}{(2+9-1)^8 \times 4+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{426930} := \frac{5 \times 7}{(4 \times 2)^6+9-3+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{439280} := \frac{5+7}{(43-9)^2 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{904628} := \frac{5+7}{90 \times 46^2+8}$$

● Numerator 58

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{58}{1972} &:= \frac{5+8}{1+9 \times 7^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{58}{36192} &:= \frac{5+8}{3 \times (61-9)^2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 59

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{59}{17346} &:= \frac{5+9}{17+3+4^6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{59}{238714} &:= \frac{5+9}{238^{7-1-4}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{59}{21476} &:= \frac{5 \times 9}{2+1 \times 4^7-6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 61

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{305} &:= \frac{6-1}{30-5} & & := \frac{6 \times 1}{5+49} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{72834} &:= \frac{6 \times 1}{7 \times 2 \times 8^3-4} \\ &:= \frac{6+1}{30+5} & & := \frac{6+1}{54+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{205387} &:= \frac{6+1}{((20-5)^3-8) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{427} &:= \frac{6-1}{42-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{3294} &:= \frac{6 \times 1}{3^2 \times 9 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{298534} &:= \frac{6-1}{29^{8-5}+3^4} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 1}{(4+2) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{4270} &:= \frac{6 \times 1}{(4+2) \times 70} & & \\ &:= \frac{6+1}{42+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{25437} &:= \frac{6 \times 1}{2+5^4 \times (-3+7)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{549} &:= \frac{6-1}{54-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61}{32940} &:= \frac{6 \times 1}{3^2 \times 9 \times 40} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 62

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{93} &:= \frac{6+2}{9+3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{13485} &:= \frac{6+2}{1 \times 348 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{134850} &:= \frac{6+2}{1 \times 348 \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{6-2}{9-3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{13950} &:= \frac{6+2}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{193750} &:= \frac{6 \times 2}{(1+9) \times 3750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{341} &:= \frac{6+2}{3+41} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{14539} &:= \frac{6+2}{14 \times (5^3+9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{349587} &:= \frac{6-2}{(34 \times 95-8) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{1395} &:= \frac{6+2}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{19375} &:= \frac{6 \times 2}{(1+9) \times 375} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{1953} &:= \frac{6-2}{1^9+5^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62}{94705} &:= \frac{6-2}{94 \times (70-5)} & & \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 63

$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{84} := \frac{6+3}{8+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{4725} := \frac{6-3}{(47-2) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{6-3}{(4+5) \times 9 \times 27}$
$:= \frac{6-3}{8-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{4781} := \frac{6^3}{4^7+8 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{47082} := \frac{6-3}{4 \times 70 \times 8+2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{105} := \frac{6+3}{10+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{4872} := \frac{6+3}{4 \times 87 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{47250} := \frac{6-3}{(47-2) \times 50}$
$:= \frac{6-3}{1 \times 05}$	$:= \frac{6-3}{4 \times (8 \times 7+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{47810} := \frac{6^3}{(4^7+8) \times 10}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{140} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{7840} := \frac{6 \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{48720} := \frac{6+3}{4 \times 87 \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{147} := \frac{6+3}{14+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{8925} := \frac{6-3}{(8+9) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{51408} := \frac{6-3}{51 \times (40+8)}$
$:= \frac{6-3}{14-7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{9240} := \frac{6-3}{(9+2) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{51492} := \frac{6-3}{51+49^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{189} := \frac{6+3}{18+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{10584} := \frac{6-3}{(1+05) \times 84}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{59472} := \frac{6 \times 3}{59 \times 4 \times 72}$
$:= \frac{6-3}{18-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{10752} := \frac{6-3}{(1+07)^{5-2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{89250} := \frac{6-3}{(8+9) \times 250}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{294} := \frac{6-3}{2 \times 9-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{17850} := \frac{6-3}{1^7 \times 850}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{91854} := \frac{6 \times 3}{9^{1+8-5} \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{784} := \frac{6 \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{19425} := \frac{6-3}{(1+9 \times 4) \times 25}$	$:= \frac{6-3}{9 \times (1+8) \times 54}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{924} := \frac{6-3}{(9+2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{20895} := \frac{6-3}{(208-9) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{94752} := \frac{6+3}{94 \times (7+5)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1428} := \frac{6+3}{14^2+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{21945} := \frac{6-3}{2+19+4^5}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 3}{9 \times 4 \times 752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1470} := \frac{6-3}{1^4 \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{24150} := \frac{6-3}{(24-1) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{108927} := \frac{6-3}{10+(8 \times 9)^2-7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1785} := \frac{6-3}{1^7 \times 85}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{27951} := \frac{6-3}{2 \times 7 \times 95+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{120974} := \frac{6+3}{(1+2)^{09}-7^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1792} := \frac{6+3}{(1 \times 7+9)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{29841} := \frac{6-3}{29 \times (8+41)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{125874} := \frac{6-3}{(1+2 \times 5 \times 8) \times 74}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1890} := \frac{6-3}{1+89+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{42819} := \frac{6-3}{4 \times 2^{8+1}-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{142597} := \frac{6+3}{1+42 \times 5 \times 97}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1974} := \frac{6-3}{1+97-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{42987} := \frac{6-3}{4 \times 2^9-8+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{187425} := \frac{6 \times 3}{18 \times 7 \times 425}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{2079} := \frac{6-3}{20+79}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{45927} := \frac{6+3}{(4+5)^{9+2-7}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{187425} := \frac{6+3}{(1+8) \times 7 \times 425}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{194250} := \frac{6-3}{(1+9 \times 4) \times 250}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{459270} := \frac{6-3}{(4+5) \times 9 \times 270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{594720} := \frac{6 \times 3}{59 \times 4 \times 720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{412895} := \frac{6+3}{(4-12) \times 8 + 9^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{470512} := \frac{6+3}{4 \times (7^{05} - 1 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{947520} := \frac{6 \times 3}{9 \times 4 \times 7520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{451927} := \frac{6+3}{((4^5 + 1) \times 9 - 2) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{470589} := \frac{6+3}{4 \times 7^{05} + 8 - 9}$$

• Numerator 64

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{128} := \frac{6+4}{12+8}$$

$$:= \frac{6-4}{12-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{5920} := \frac{6+4}{5+920}$$

$$:= \frac{6-4}{5+9 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{139872} := \frac{6 \times 4}{1+3^9+8^{7-2}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{352} := \frac{6+4}{3+52}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{7392} := \frac{6-4}{7 \times 3 \times (9+2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{195328} := \frac{6-4}{(1-9) \times (5-3 \times 2^8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{512} := \frac{6-4}{(5-1)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{8192} := \frac{6-4}{(8-1+9)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{381792} := \frac{6-4}{3 \times (8+1 \times (7 \times 9)^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{832} := \frac{6-4}{8 \times 3 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{18792} := \frac{6 \times 4}{1 \times 87 \times 9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{519872} := \frac{6+4}{5+(19 \times (8+7))^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{1792} := \frac{6-4}{(1+7) \times (9-2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{53792} := \frac{6-4}{(5-(3-7) \times 9)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{807592} := \frac{6 \times 4}{(80+7) \times 59^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{1952} := \frac{6-4}{1 \times 9 + 52}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{73952} := \frac{6-4}{7+(3+9 \times 5)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{5280} := \frac{6-4}{5+2 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{135872} := \frac{6+4}{(1+3^5) \times 87+2}$$

• Numerator 65

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{1248} := \frac{6 \times 5}{12 \times 48}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{7280} := \frac{6-5}{7 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{218790} := \frac{6-5}{2 \times 187 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{1820} := \frac{6-5}{1 \times 8 + 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{12480} := \frac{6-5}{1 \times 24 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{241930} := \frac{6-5}{2+4 \times 1 \times 930}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{2340} := \frac{6-5}{2+34+0}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 5}{12 \times 480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{2730} := \frac{6-5}{2 \times 7 \times 3 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{12870} := \frac{6-5}{128+70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{4810} := \frac{6+5}{4+810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{180947} := \frac{6 \times 5}{(1 \times 8 + 09)^4 - 7}$$

• Numerator 57

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{4958} := \frac{6+7}{4+958}$$

• Numerator 68

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{374} := \frac{6+8}{3+74}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{952} := \frac{6+8}{(9+5)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1275} := \frac{6 \times 8}{12 \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{12750} := \frac{6 \times 8}{12 \times 750}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{49572} := \frac{6^8}{((4+9+5)^7) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{139247} := \frac{6 \times 8}{(1 \times 3 - 9) \times (2 - 4^7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{495720} := \frac{6^8}{(4+9+5)^7 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{704123} := \frac{6 \times 8}{(704+1)^2 + 3}$$

• Numerator 69

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{69}{253} := \frac{6+9}{2+53}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{69}{13248} := \frac{6 \times 9}{(1+3+2)^4 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{69}{14375} := \frac{6+9}{(1 \times 4 \times 3 - 7)^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{69}{132480} := \frac{6 \times 9}{(1+3+2)^4 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{69}{352107} := \frac{6+9}{35 \times (2+1)^{07}}$$

• Numerator 71

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{284} := \frac{7+1}{28+4}$$

$$:= \frac{7-1}{2 \times (8+4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{426} := \frac{7+1}{4 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{7-1}{42-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{568} := \frac{7+1}{56+8}$$

$$:= \frac{7-1}{56-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{639} := \frac{7+1}{6 \times (3+9)}$$

$$:= \frac{7-1}{63-9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{923} := \frac{7-1}{9^2-3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{3905} := \frac{7 \times 1}{390-5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{4260} := \frac{7+1}{4 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{7-1}{(4+2) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{6248} := \frac{7-1}{(62+4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{23856} := \frac{7 \times 1}{624-8}$$

$$:= \frac{7+1}{2 \times 3 \times 8 \times 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{25986} := \frac{7+1}{(2+59) \times 8 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{26483} := \frac{7 \times 1}{2 \times (6^4+8) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{38624} := \frac{7+1}{((3+8) \times 6)^2 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{38695} := \frac{7+1}{(3+869) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{40896} := \frac{7+1}{(40+8) \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{62480} := \frac{7-1}{(62+4) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{83496} := \frac{7-1}{8 \times 3 \times 49 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{238560} := \frac{7+1}{2 \times 3 \times 8 \times 560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{259860} := \frac{7+1}{(2+59) \times 8 \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{295360} := \frac{7+1}{2^9 \times (5^3 - 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{386950} := \frac{7+1}{(3+869) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71}{409386} := \frac{7-1}{4 \times 093^{8-6}}$$

● Numerator 72

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{3456} := \frac{7 \times 2}{3 \times 4 \times 56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{39168} := \frac{7-2}{(39+1) \times 68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{163584} := \frac{7+2}{16^3 \times 5 - 8 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{5184} := \frac{7-2}{5 \times 18 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{51840} := \frac{7-2}{5 \times 18 \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{163840} := \frac{7+2}{(1+63) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{10368} := \frac{7-2}{10 \times (3+6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{59184} := \frac{7-2}{5+9+1 \times 8^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{348160} := \frac{7+2}{34 \times 8 \times 160} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{16384} := \frac{7+2}{(1+63) \times 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{94536} := \frac{7-2}{9^4 - 5 + 3 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{361584} := \frac{7+2}{3^6 \times (1 \times 58 + 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{31608} := \frac{7-2}{3^{1+6} + 08} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{94680} := \frac{7-2}{9^4 + 6 + 8 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{391680} := \frac{7-2}{(39+1) \times 680} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{34560} := \frac{7 \times 2}{3 \times 4 \times 560} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{134568} := \frac{7+2}{(1 \times 3 + 4)^5 + 6 + 8} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{34816} := \frac{7+2}{34 \times 8 \times 16} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72}{156480} := \frac{7+2}{15 \times (6^4 + 8) + 0} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 73

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{146} := \frac{7+3}{14+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{9125} := \frac{7-3}{(9+1)^2 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{91542} := \frac{7-3}{(9-1) \times 5^4 + 2} \\ & := \frac{7-3}{14-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{142058} := \frac{7-3}{(1 \times 4 + 2)^{05} + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{219} := \frac{7+3}{21+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{18250} := \frac{7-3}{(18+2) \times 50} & \\ & := \frac{7-3}{2+1+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{84096} := \frac{7-3}{(8+40) \times 96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{1825} := \frac{7-3}{(18+2) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73}{91250} := \frac{7-3}{(9+1)^2 \times 50} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 74

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{296} := \frac{7-4}{2 \times 9 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{23680} := \frac{7-4}{(2 \times 3 + 6) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{302956} := \frac{7-4}{3 \times (-02 + (9-5)^6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{1036} := \frac{7-4}{(10-3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{31968} := \frac{7-4}{3 \times 1 \times 9 \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{319680} := \frac{7-4}{3 \times 1 \times 9 \times 6 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{2368} := \frac{7-4}{(2 \times 3 + 6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{36852} := \frac{7-4}{3 \times 6 \times (85-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{391682} := \frac{7-4}{3 + (9 \times (1 \times 6 + 8))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{12506} := \frac{7-4}{1^2 + 506} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74}{103896} := \frac{7 \times 4}{(1 \times 03^8 - 9) \times 6} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 76

$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{152} := \frac{7-6}{1^5 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{5928} := \frac{7-6}{5+9^2-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{153824} := \frac{7+6}{(15+3^8+2) \times 4}$
$\quad := \frac{7+6}{1+5^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{12540} := \frac{7-6}{125+40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{243580} := \frac{7-6}{(2 \times 4-3)^5+80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{912} := \frac{7-6}{9+1+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{13452} := \frac{7-6}{(1+34) \times 5+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{249318} := \frac{7 \times 6}{(2-4+9) \times 3^{1+8}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{1520} := \frac{7-6}{1^5 \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{15048} := \frac{7-6}{150+48}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{291840} := \frac{7-6}{(2+9+1) \times 8 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{1824} := \frac{7-6}{1 \times 8+2^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{15428} := \frac{7-6}{1+5 \times 42-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{350892} := \frac{7-6}{3^5 \times (08+9+2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{2508} := \frac{7-6}{25+08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{18240} := \frac{7-6}{(1 \times 8-2) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{385092} := \frac{7-6}{3 \times (8+(50-9)^2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{2584} := \frac{7-6}{2 \times (5+8+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{25308} := \frac{7-6}{25+308}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{391248} := \frac{7-6}{39 \times (124+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{3192} := \frac{7-6}{31+9+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{25384} := \frac{7-6}{2 \times 5^3+84}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{3420} := \frac{7-6}{3+42+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{29184} := \frac{7-6}{(2+9+1) \times 8 \times 4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{3952} := \frac{7-6}{3 \times 9+5^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76}{43092} := \frac{7-6}{(4+3) \times 09^2}$	

● Numerator 78

$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{156} := \frac{7+8}{1 \times 5 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{14560} := \frac{7+8}{(1+4) \times 560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{192634} := \frac{7+8}{1+(9+2 \times 6)^3 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{520} := \frac{7+8}{5 \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{16250} := \frac{7+8}{(1+6-2)^5+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{539214} := \frac{7+8}{5 \times (3+(9+2+1)^4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{1456} := \frac{7+8}{(1+4) \times 56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{21346} := \frac{7+8}{(2+1) \times 3+4^6}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{78}{1560} := \frac{7+8}{1 \times 5 \times 60}$		

● Numerator 79

$\blacktriangleright \frac{79}{316} := \frac{7+9}{(3-1)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{79}{12640} := \frac{7+9}{1 \times 2^6 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{79}{102384} := \frac{7+9}{(1^{01}+3+8)^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{79}{1264} := \frac{7+9}{1 \times 2^6 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{79}{34128} := \frac{7+9}{3^{4-1} \times 2^8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{79}{138645} := \frac{7+9}{13 \times 8 \times 6 \times 45}$

● Numerator 91

$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{243} := \frac{8 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{2673} := \frac{8 \times 1}{267 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{36450} := \frac{8 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times 4 \times 50}$
$\quad := \frac{8 + 1}{24 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{3240} := \frac{8 + 1}{3^2 \times 40}$	$\quad := \frac{8 + 1}{(3 + 6) \times 450}$
$\quad := \frac{8 - 1}{24 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{3429} := \frac{8 + 1}{3 + 42 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{45639} := \frac{8 + 1}{4 + 563 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{324} := \frac{8 + 1}{32 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{3564} := \frac{8 \times 1}{356 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{45927} := \frac{8 + 1}{(4 + 5) \times 9^2 \times 7}$
$\quad := \frac{8 - 1}{32 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{3645} := \frac{8 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times 4 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{59472} := \frac{8 + 1}{(5 + 9) \times 472}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{405} := \frac{8 + 1}{40 + 5}$	$\quad := \frac{8 + 1}{(3 + 6) \times 45}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{72063} := \frac{8 + 1}{7 + 20^{6-3}}$
$\quad := \frac{8 - 1}{40 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{5346} := \frac{8 \times 1}{534 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{95760} := \frac{8 + 1}{(9 + 5) \times 760}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{567} := \frac{8 + 1}{56 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{5463} := \frac{8 + 1}{5^4 - 6 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{459270} := \frac{8 + 1}{(4 + 5) \times 9^2 \times 70}$
$\quad := \frac{8 - 1}{56 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{6237} := \frac{8 \times 1}{623 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{563904} := \frac{8 + 1}{(5^6 + 39) \times 04}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{729} := \frac{8 + 1}{72 + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{6534} := \frac{8 + 1}{6 \times (5^3 - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{564930} := \frac{8 + 1}{5^6 \times 4 + 9 \times 30}$
$\quad := \frac{8 - 1}{72 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{7290} := \frac{8 + 1}{(7 + 2) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{594720} := \frac{8 + 1}{(5 + 9) \times 4720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{792} := \frac{8 + 1}{7 + 9^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{9576} := \frac{8 + 1}{(9 + 5) \times 76}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{2430} := \frac{8 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81}{20736} := \frac{8 + 1}{2^{07} \times 3 \times 6}$	

● Numerator 82

$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{164} := \frac{8 + 2}{16 + 4}$	$\quad := \frac{8 - 2}{36 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{1763} := \frac{8 \times 2}{1 + (7^{6-3})}$
$\quad := \frac{8 - 2}{16 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{451} := \frac{8 + 2}{4 + 51}$	$\quad := \frac{8 - 2}{(1 + 7 \times 6) \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{369} := \frac{8 \times 2}{3 + 69}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{1435} := \frac{8 + 2}{(1 + 4) \times 35}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{3075} := \frac{8 - 2}{3 \times 075}$
$\quad := \frac{8 + 2}{3 \times (6 + 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{1476} := \frac{8 \times 2}{(1 + 47) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{82}{3690} := \frac{8 \times 2}{3^6 - 9 + 0}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{14063} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{14^{06-3}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{49036} &:= \frac{8-2}{4 \times (903-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{14350} &:= \frac{8+2}{(1+4) \times 350} & \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{70315} &:= \frac{8-2}{7^{03} \times 15} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{14760} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{(1+47) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{361907} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{(3^6-1) \times (90+7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{17630} &:= \frac{8-2}{(1+7 \times 6) \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{82}{974365} &:= \frac{8^2}{97 \times (4^3+6^5)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 83

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{249} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{4150} &:= \frac{8-3}{(4+1) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{125496} &:= \frac{8-3}{(1+2 \times 5^4+9) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8+3}{24+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{10624} &:= \frac{8^3}{(10-6)^{2 \times 4}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{254976} &:= \frac{8^3}{(2+5+4^9-7) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8-3}{2+4+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{20169} &:= \frac{8-3}{201 \times 6+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{269750} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{(2+6) \times 9750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{415} &:= \frac{8-3}{(4+1) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{20916} &:= \frac{8-3}{20 \times 9 \times (1+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{2490} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{2 \times (4 \times 90)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{26975} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{(2+6) \times 975} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{83}{2905} &:= \frac{8-3}{(2 \times 90)-5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 84

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{105} &:= \frac{8-4}{1 \times 05} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{693} &:= \frac{8-4}{6+9 \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1372} &:= \frac{8+4}{(1+3) \times 7^2} \\ &:= \frac{8+4}{10+5} & &:= \frac{8+4}{6+93} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1596} &:= \frac{8-4}{1+5 \times (9+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{126} &:= \frac{8-4}{12-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{735} &:= \frac{8+4}{7 \times 3 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1792} &:= \frac{8+4}{(1 \times 7+9)^2} \\ &:= \frac{8+4}{12+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1260} &:= \frac{8-4}{1^2 \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1932} &:= \frac{8-4}{1+93-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{231} &:= \frac{8+4}{2+31} & &:= \frac{8+4}{(1+2) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1953} &:= \frac{8-4}{1+95-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{315} &:= \frac{8-4}{3 \times 1 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1302} &:= \frac{8-4}{(1+30) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{2079} &:= \frac{8-4}{20+79} \\ &:= \frac{8+4}{3 \times 15} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{1365} &:= \frac{8-4}{1^3 \times 65} & \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{3150} &:= \frac{8-4}{3 \times 1 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{84}{651} &:= \frac{8-4}{6 \times 5+1} & &:= \frac{8+4}{1 \times (3 \times 65)} & &:= \frac{8+4}{3 \times 150} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{3906} := \frac{8+4}{(3+90) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{13965} := \frac{8-4}{(139-6) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{137529} := \frac{8+4}{1-37+(5-2)^9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{5376} := \frac{8+4}{(5-3)^7 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{15379} := \frac{8+4}{1^5+3^7+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{139650} := \frac{8-4}{(139-6) \times 50}$
$\quad := \frac{8^4}{(5 \times 3 - 7)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{16275} := \frac{8-4}{(162-7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{162750} := \frac{8-4}{(162-7) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{5691} := \frac{8-4}{5 \times 6 \times 9 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{21357} := \frac{8-4}{(2-1+3)^5-7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{163275} := \frac{8-4}{1+6^{3+2}-7+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{7035} := \frac{8-4}{(70-3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{27951} := \frac{8-4}{2 \times 7 \times 95 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{169057} := \frac{8+4}{1+690 \times 5 \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{7203} := \frac{8 \times 4}{(7 \times 2)^{03}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{35721} := \frac{8-4}{3^5 \times 7 \times (2-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{173502} := \frac{8-4}{17 \times 3^5 \times 02}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{7350} := \frac{8+4}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$	$\quad := \frac{8+4}{3^5 \times 7 \times (2+1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{192675} := \frac{8+4}{(19^2+6) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{10752} := \frac{8-4}{(1+07)^{5-2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{37926} := \frac{8-4}{3 \times 7 \times (92-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{291375} := \frac{8-4}{(2 \times 91+3) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{12096} := \frac{8+4}{12^{09-6}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{51639} := \frac{8 \times 4}{5-16+3^9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{326571} := \frac{8+4}{(3 \times 2)^6+5-7-1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{13629} := \frac{8-4}{1+36 \times 2 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{53760} := \frac{8+4}{(5-3)^7 \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{927360} := \frac{8+4}{9 \times 2 \times 7360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{13650} := \frac{8-4}{1^3 \times 650}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{92736} := \frac{8+4}{9 \times 2 \times (7+3^6)}$	
$\quad := \frac{8+4}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{109256} := \frac{8+4}{1-09 \times 2+5^6}$	

• Numerator 85

$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{340} := \frac{8-5}{3 \times 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{29376} := \frac{8 \times 5}{2^9 \times (3 \times 7 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{139264} := \frac{8 \times 5}{(1 \times 3 + 9 - 2 + 6)^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{731} := \frac{8 \times 5}{7^3 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{31620} := \frac{8-5}{31 \times 6^2 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{371620} := \frac{8+5}{(3^7-1) \times (6+20)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{4692} := \frac{8 \times 5}{4 \times 6 \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{36720} := \frac{8-5}{3 \times 6 \times 72 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{371960} := \frac{8-5}{(3^7+1^9) \times 6 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{4760} := \frac{8-5}{4 \times 7 \times 6 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{37162} := \frac{8 \times 5}{(3^7-1) \times (6+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{417639} := \frac{8 \times 5}{(4^{1 \times 7} - 6) \times (3+9)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{6120} := \frac{8-5}{6^{1+2} + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{46920} := \frac{8 \times 5}{4 \times 6 \times 920}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{21760} := \frac{8-5}{2^{1 \times 7} \times 6 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{123760} := \frac{8-5}{1 \times 2 \times 3^7 - 6 + 0}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{27914} := \frac{8 \times 5}{2 \times (7 + 9^{1 \times 4})}$		

● Numerator 86

$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{129} := \frac{8-6}{12-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{2709} := \frac{8-6}{2+70-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{194532} := \frac{8-6}{1-9+4532}$
$\quad := \frac{8+6}{12+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{3741} := \frac{8-6}{3 \times (7 \times 4 + 1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{249357} := \frac{8-6}{2 \times 4 \times (9^3 - 5) + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{215} := \frac{8-6}{(2-1) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{4257} := \frac{8-6}{42+57}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{251937} := \frac{8-6}{(2^5 - 1) \times 9 \times 3 \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{473} := \frac{8+6}{4+73}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{7095} := \frac{8-6}{70+95}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{293475} := \frac{8-6}{(2+93-4) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{1247} := \frac{8-6}{1^2 + 4 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{13975} := \frac{8-6}{1+3 \times 9 \times (7+5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{297345} := \frac{8-6}{(2+9+7^3 \times 4) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{1290} := \frac{8-6}{1+29+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{19350} := \frac{8+6}{1 \times 9 \times 350}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{319275} := \frac{8-6}{3 \times 1 \times 9 \times 275}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{1935} := \frac{8-6}{1+9+35}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{42957} := \frac{8-6}{42+957}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{704512} := \frac{8+6}{7 \times 04^{5+1 \times 2}}$
$\quad := \frac{8+6}{1 \times 9 \times 35}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{45193} := \frac{8-6}{4^5 \times 1 + 9 \times 3}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{2150} := \frac{8-6}{(2-1) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{170925} := \frac{8-6}{1+(7 \times 09)^2 + 5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{2451} := \frac{8-6}{2+4+51}$		

● Numerator 87

$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{145} := \frac{8+7}{(1+4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{4263} := \frac{8 \times 7}{(4 \times 2 + 6)^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{35409} := \frac{8-7}{3-5+409}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{435} := \frac{8-7}{(4-3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{4350} := \frac{8-7}{(4-3) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{35496} := \frac{8-7}{(3+5 \times (4+9)) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{1305} := \frac{8-7}{1 \times 3 \times 05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{5916} := \frac{8-7}{5+9 \times (1+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{43065} := \frac{8-7}{430+65}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{1392} := \frac{8-7}{1-3+9 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{10962} := \frac{8 \times 7}{(10 \times 9 - 6)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{54201} := \frac{8-7}{5^4 - 2 \times 01}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{1450} := \frac{8+7}{(1+4) \times 50}$	$\quad := \frac{8-7}{10 \times 9 + 6^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{60291} := \frac{8-7}{602+91}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{2349} := \frac{8-7}{2+34-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{12354} := \frac{8-7}{1 \times 2 + 35 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{91350} := \frac{8-7}{(9+1)^3 + 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{3045} := \frac{8-7}{(3+04) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{23490} := \frac{8-7}{(2-3+4) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{129456} := \frac{8-7}{12 \times (94+5 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{3915} := \frac{8-7}{3 \times (9+1+5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{32016} := \frac{8-7}{(3+20) \times 16}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87}{152946} := \frac{8-7}{(1+5) \times 294-6}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{87}{215934} &:= \frac{8-7}{(2^{1+5} + 9) \times 34} & \blacktriangleright \frac{87}{354960} &:= \frac{8-7}{(3+5 \times (4+9)) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{87}{236901} &:= \frac{8-7}{2+3 \times (6+901)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{87}{423516} &:= \frac{8-7}{4 \times (2+3^5 \times (-1+6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{87}{316245} &:= \frac{8-7}{(3^{1 \times 6} + 2-4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{87}{425169} &:= \frac{8-7}{4^2 \times 51 \times 6-9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 89

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{89}{3204} &:= \frac{8+9}{3 \times 204} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{89}{617304} &:= \frac{8+9}{6 \times 17^3 \times 04} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 91

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{273} &:= \frac{9-1}{27-3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{728} &:= \frac{9-1}{72-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{20475} &:= \frac{9-1}{(20+4) \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(2+7) \times 3} & &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{25480} &:= \frac{9-1}{(2^5-4) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{9+1}{27+3} & &:= \frac{9+1}{72+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{38675} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+8 \times 6) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{364} &:= \frac{9-1}{36-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{2548} &:= \frac{9-1}{(2^5-4) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{58240} &:= \frac{9+1}{(5 \times 8)^2 \times 4+0} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+6) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{2730} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(2+7) \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{284375} &:= \frac{9+1}{(2+8) \times (4 \times 3-7)^5} \\ &:= \frac{9+1}{36+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{3640} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+6) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{386750} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+8 \times 6) \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{546} &:= \frac{9-1}{54-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{5460} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{438256} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(4+38^2 \times 5) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{5824} &:= \frac{9+1}{5 \times 8 \times 2^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{438256} &:= \frac{9-1}{43 \times 8 \times 2 \times 56} \\ &:= \frac{9+1}{54+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{6370} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(6+3) \times 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{528346} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(5+2^8 \times 34) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{637} &:= \frac{9-1}{63-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{6734} &:= \frac{9+1}{6+734} & & \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(6+3) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{91}{7280} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 80} & & \\ &:= \frac{9+1}{63+7} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 92

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{92}{184} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(1+8) \times 4} && := \frac{9+2}{36+8} \\ &:= \frac{9+2}{18+4} && := \frac{9-2}{36-8} \\ &:= \frac{9-2}{18-4} && \blacktriangleright \frac{92}{1840} := \frac{9 \times 2}{(1+8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{92}{368} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 8} && \blacktriangleright \frac{92}{3680} := \frac{9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 93

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{124} &:= \frac{9+3}{1 \times 2^4} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{1674} := \frac{9+3}{1 \times 6^{7-4}} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{74586} := \frac{9-3}{(7^4+5) \times (8-6)} \\ &:= \frac{9-3}{1 \times 2 \times 4} && := \frac{9-3}{16 \times 7-4} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{102765} := \frac{9-3}{102 \times (7+6) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{186} &:= \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 6} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{1860} := \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 60} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{158472} := \frac{9+3}{1+5 \times (8^4-7)+2} \\ &:= \frac{9+3}{18+6} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{2170} := \frac{9-3}{2 \times 1 \times 70} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{162750} := \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+62) \times 750} \\ &:= \frac{9-3}{18-6} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{4185} := \frac{9^3}{(4-1)^8 \times 5} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{162750} := \frac{9-3}{(16-2) \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{217} &:= \frac{9+3}{21+7} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{15872} := \frac{9-3}{(1-5+8)^{7-2}} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{254076} := \frac{9+3}{2 \times (5+4^{07})+6} \\ &:= \frac{9-3}{2 \times (1 \times 7)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{16275} := \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+62) \times 75} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{254107} := \frac{9-3}{2 \times 5+4^{1 \times 07}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{248} &:= \frac{9+3}{24+8} && := \frac{9-3}{(16-2) \times 75} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{406782} := \frac{9-3}{(40 \times 6-78)^2} \\ &:= \frac{9-3}{24-8} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{25048} := \frac{9-3}{(2+50 \times 4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{682} &:= \frac{9+3}{6+82} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{26784} := \frac{9-3}{(2 \times 6)^{7-8+4}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{1240} &:= \frac{9-3}{1 \times 2 \times 40} && \blacktriangleright \frac{93}{41850} := \frac{9^3}{(4-1)^8 \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 94

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{94}{2538} &:= \frac{9+4}{(2+5)^3+8} && \blacktriangleright \frac{94}{21056} := \frac{9-4}{2 \times 10 \times 56} && \blacktriangleright \frac{94}{201536} := \frac{9-4}{20 \times 1 \times 536} \\ &:= \frac{9-4}{2+5^3+8} && \blacktriangleright \frac{94}{53862} := \frac{9+4}{53+86^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{94}{10528} &:= \frac{9-4}{10 \times (5+2) \times 8} && \blacktriangleright \frac{94}{102836} := \frac{9 \times 4}{((1+02)^8+3) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 95

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{342} := \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{1083} := \frac{9 \times 5}{1 + 08^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{3420} := \frac{9 - 5}{(3 \times 4)^2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{3648} := \frac{9 \times 5}{36 \times 48}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{3724} := \frac{9 \times 5}{(3 \times 7)^2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{6840} := \frac{9 - 5}{6 \times (8 + 40)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{16340} := \frac{9 - 5}{16 \times (3 + 40)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{27360} := \frac{9 - 5}{2^7 \times (3 + 6) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{36480} := \frac{9 - 5}{3 \times 64 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{9 \times 5}{36 \times 480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{37240} := \frac{9 \times 5}{(3 \times 7)^2 \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{138472} := \frac{9 \times 5}{(1 + 3)^8 + 4 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{95}{172368} := \frac{9 \times 5}{1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 3^6 \times 8}$$

● Numerator 96

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{128} := \frac{9 - 6}{12 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{9 + 6}{12 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{352} := \frac{9 + 6}{3 + 52}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{384} := \frac{9 - 6}{3 \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{512} := \frac{9 - 6}{(5 - 1)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{832} := \frac{9 - 6}{8 \times 3 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{1024} := \frac{9 - 6}{(10 - 2) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{9 + 6}{10 \times 2^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{1472} := \frac{9 - 6}{1 - (4 - 7^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{1504} := \frac{9 - 6}{1 + (50 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{2048} := \frac{9 - 6}{2 \times 04 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{2304} := \frac{9 \times 6}{(2 \times 3)^{04}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{5280} := \frac{9 - 6}{5 + 2 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{12384} := \frac{9 - 6}{1 + 2 + 384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{14752} := \frac{9 + 6}{1 + (4 \times (7 + 5))^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{17408} := \frac{9 - 6}{17 \times 4 \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{35840} := \frac{9 - 6}{35 \times 8 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{53472} := \frac{9 - 6}{5 + 34 \times 7^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{123584} := \frac{9 - 6}{1 - 235 + 8^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{130784} := \frac{9 - 6}{1 - 3 - 07 + 8^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{134528} := \frac{9 - 6}{1 \times 3^4 \times 52 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{135872} := \frac{9 + 6}{(1 + 3^5) \times 87 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{178432} := \frac{9 - 6}{17 \times 8 \times (43 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{314720} := \frac{9 + 6}{3 \times (1 + 4^7) + 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{314752} := \frac{9 + 6}{3 \times (1 + 4^7) + 5^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{415872} := \frac{9 - 6}{4 \times (1^5 + 8 \times 7)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{96}{435712} := \frac{9 - 6}{4 \times (3^5 \times 7 + 1) \times 2}$$

● Numerator 97

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{97}{1358} := \frac{9 - 7}{1 + 35 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{97}{4268} := \frac{9 - 7}{4^2 \times 6 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{97}{4365} := \frac{9 + 7}{4 \times 36 \times 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9-7}{(4 \times 3 + 6) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{6208} & := \frac{9-7}{6 \times 20 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{13580} & := \frac{9-7}{1 \times 35 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{18624} & := \frac{9-7}{1 \times 8 \times 6 \times 2 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{20564} & := \frac{9-7}{(20 \times 5 + 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{24153} & := \frac{9-7}{2 + 4 \times (-1 + 5^3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{24638} & := \frac{9-7}{2 + 46 \times (3 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{26384} & := \frac{9-7}{2^{6+3} + 8 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{43650} & := \frac{9+7}{4 \times 36 \times 50} \\ & := \frac{9-7}{(4 \times 3 + 6) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{52380} & := \frac{9-7}{(5 \times 2)^3 + 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{132405} & := \frac{9-7}{13 \times (2 + 40) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{186240} & := \frac{9-7}{1 \times 8 \times 6 \times 2 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{97}{426315} & := \frac{9+7}{4 \times (26^3 - 1 + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 98

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{1274} & := \frac{9-8}{1 \times 2 + 7 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{1372} & := \frac{9-8}{1^3 \times 7 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{1764} & := \frac{9 \times 8}{1^7 \times 6^4} \\ & := \frac{9-8}{1 + 7 + 6 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{2156} & := \frac{9-8}{2 \times (1 \times 5 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{3675} & := \frac{9 \times 8}{36 \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{3724} & := \frac{9-8}{3 \times 7 \times 2 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{4312} & := \frac{9-8}{43 + 1^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{7056} & := \frac{9-8}{(7 + 05) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{7546} & := \frac{9-8}{75 - 4 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{13426} & := \frac{9-8}{1 - 34 \times (2 - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{13720} & := \frac{9-8}{1^3 \times 7 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{17640} & := \frac{9-8}{176 + 4 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{21756} & := \frac{9-8}{(2 + 1 \times 7 \times 5) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{23716} & := \frac{9-8}{237 - 1 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{31654} & := \frac{9-8}{3 + 16 \times 5 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{31752} & := \frac{9-8}{(3 \times (1^7 + 5))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{36750} & := \frac{9 \times 8}{36 \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{37142} & := \frac{9-8}{371 + 4 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{40572} & := \frac{9-8}{405 + 7 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{45276} & := \frac{9-8}{(4 + 5 + 2) \times 7 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{50274} & := \frac{9-8}{502 + 7 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{57134} & := \frac{9-8}{571 + 3 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{65072} & := \frac{9-8}{650 + 7 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{67032} & := \frac{9-8}{(6 + 70) \times 3^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{75264} & := \frac{9-8}{(7 + 5^2) \times 6 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{76342} & := \frac{9-8}{763 + 4^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{125734} & := \frac{9-8}{1 + 2 + 5 \times (7 - 3)^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{145726} & := \frac{9-8}{1 + 4 + 57 \times 26} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{173264} & := \frac{9-8}{17 \times (32 - 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{217560} & := \frac{9-8}{(2 + 1 \times 7 \times 5) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{247156} & := \frac{9-8}{2 + 4 \times 7 \times 15 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{357210} & := \frac{9-8}{3 \times ((5 \times 7)^2 - 10)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{98}{452760} & := \frac{9-8}{(4 + 5 + 2) \times 7 \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

3 Different Digits Selfie Fractions: Three Digits Numerator

This section brings **selfie fractions** for the numerator 3-digits numbers. Due to high quantity of number there are lot of extra brackets like "(...)". These can be removed easily by simplifications.

• Numerator 102

$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{357} := \frac{10-2}{35-7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{7854} := \frac{1^{01}}{78-5+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{65739} := \frac{10+2}{6^5+(7 \times (3-9))}$
$\quad := \frac{10+2}{35+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{7956} := \frac{1^{01}}{79+5-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{73695} := \frac{1 \times 01}{((7^3)-(6 \times 9)) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{459} := \frac{10-2}{45-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{8534} := \frac{1+02}{85 \times 3-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{74358} := \frac{1^{01}}{(7-4)^{3-5+8}}$
$\quad := \frac{10+2}{45+9}$	$\quad := \frac{10+2}{8 \times 5^3+4}$	$\quad := \frac{1+02}{(7-4)^{3 \times 5-8}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{748} := \frac{10+2}{(7+4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{8976} := \frac{1^{01}}{89-7+6}$	$\quad := \frac{10-2}{(7-4) \times (3^5 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{3468} := \frac{1^{01}}{(3+4) \times 6-8}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times 01}{8 \times (9+7+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{75684} := \frac{1 \times 01}{7 \times ((5+6 \times 8) \times 4)}$
$\quad := \frac{1+02}{34+68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{9384} := \frac{1^{01}}{(9+3) \times 8-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{76398} := \frac{1^{01}}{7 \times (6+(3+98))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{3876} := \frac{1^{01}}{38 \times (7-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{34578} := \frac{1 \times 01}{3+45 \times (7+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{78693} := \frac{1 \times 01}{7+(((8-6)^9) \times 3)}$
$\quad := \frac{1+02}{38+76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{34986} := \frac{10+2}{(3+4) \times 98 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{345678} := \frac{1^{01}}{3-4+5 \times 678}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{3978} := \frac{1+02}{39+78}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{35496} := \frac{1^{01}}{3 \times (5 \times 4+96)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{385764} := \frac{10+2}{3 \times 8+5 \times 7 \times 6^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{4386} := \frac{1 \times 01}{43 \times (8-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{35649} := \frac{1 \times 01}{3 \times (56 \times 4+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{389674} := \frac{1+02}{3+(8+9) \times 674}$
$\quad := \frac{1+02}{43+86}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{39678} := \frac{1^{01}}{3+9 \times 6 \times 7+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{439875} := \frac{1 \times 01}{(43+9 \times 8) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{4896} := \frac{1 \times 01}{4 \times 8 \times (9-6)}$	$\quad := \frac{10-2}{(396-7) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{498576} := \frac{1^{01}}{4 \times (9+85) \times (7+6)}$
$\quad := \frac{1+02}{48+96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{46359} := \frac{1 \times 01}{(4 \times (6^3))+5 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{539648} := \frac{1+01}{(5 \times 396+4) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{6375} := \frac{1 \times 01}{(6 \times 3+7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{47685} := \frac{10-2}{(4+7) \times (68 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{539784} := \frac{10 \times 2}{5 \times 3 \times 9 \times 784}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{6834} := \frac{1^{01}}{68+3-4}$	$\quad := \frac{10+2}{(4+7) \times (6 \times 85)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{647598} := \frac{1 \times 01}{6 \times 47 \times 5 \times 9+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{7548} := \frac{1 \times 01}{7 \times 5 \times 4+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{59874} := \frac{1^{01}}{598-7-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{748935} := \frac{1 \times 01}{(7+4) \times 89 \times 3 \times 5}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{754698} := \frac{1^{01}}{7 \times (5^4 + 6 \times 9 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{948753} := \frac{1 \times 01}{9 \times (4 \times 8 + 7) \times 53}$$

• Numerator 103

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{824} := \frac{1 \times 03}{8 + 2^4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03}{8 + 24}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{927} := \frac{1 + 03}{9 + 27}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{2678} := \frac{1 + 03}{26 + 78}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + 3}{2 + 6 \times 7 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{2987} := \frac{1^{03}}{29 \times (8 - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03}{29 + 87}$$

$$:= \frac{10 - 3}{2 \times 98 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{5768} := \frac{1 \times 03}{(5 + 7) \times (6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times 3}{5 \times 7 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{6489} := \frac{1^{03}}{6 + 48 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{6798} := \frac{1^{03}}{67 - 9 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03}{(6 \times 7 - 9) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{8652} := \frac{1 + 03}{8 \times 6 \times (5 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{25647} := \frac{1^{03}}{(2 \times 5 - 6)^4 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + 3}{2 + 5 \times 647}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{26574} := \frac{1^{03}}{2 + (6 + 5 - 7)^4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03}{(265 - 7) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{29458} := \frac{1^{03}}{(2 \times 9 + 4) \times (5 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{47586} := \frac{1^{03}}{(4 \times 7 + 5) \times (8 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03}{(4 \times 75 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{48925} := \frac{1^{03}}{(4 + 89 + 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 03}{(48 + 9) \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03}{(4 + 8 \times 9) \times 25}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{49852} := \frac{1 + 03}{4 \times (9 + 8 + 5)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{54796} := \frac{1^{03}}{547 - 9 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{84975} := \frac{1 + 03}{(8 + 4 \times 9) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{98674} := \frac{1^{03}}{986 - 7 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{427965} := \frac{1 + 03}{(42 \times 79 + 6) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{479568} := \frac{1^{03}}{(4 + 79) \times 56 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{952647} := \frac{1^{03}}{9 + 5 \times 264 \times 7}$$

• Numerator 104

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{572} := \frac{10 - 4}{5 \times 7 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + 4}{5 + 72}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{728} := \frac{1 + 04}{7 + 28}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{832} := \frac{1^{04}}{8 \times (3 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 04}{8 + 32}$$

$$:= \frac{10 - 4}{8 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{936} := \frac{1 \times 04}{(9 - 3) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 04}{9 + 36}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{3692} := \frac{10 - 4}{3 \times (69 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{3796} := \frac{10 - 4}{3 \times (79 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{3952} := \frac{10 - 4}{3 + (9 \times (5^2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{5382} := \frac{1 \times 04}{(5^3) + 82}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{5837} := \frac{10 \times 4}{58 + (3^7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{8632} := \frac{1 \times 04}{8 + ((6 \times 3)^2)}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{8736} := \frac{1^{04}}{87 + 3 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{39728} := \frac{1 \times 04}{((3 \times 9 \times 7) + 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{259376} := \frac{1^{04}}{25 \times (93 + 7) - 6}$
$\quad := \frac{10 - 4}{8 \times (7 \times (3 + 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{52936} := \frac{1 + 04}{5 \times (2^9 + 3 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{325689} := \frac{10 \times 4}{(32 + 5^6) \times 8 + 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{9568} := \frac{1^{04}}{((9 + 5) \times 6) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{53976} := \frac{1^{04}}{(53 \times 9) + 7 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{356928} := \frac{1^{04}}{3 \times (5 + 69 \times 2) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{9672} := \frac{1^{04}}{9 + (6 \times (7 \times 2))}$	$\quad := \frac{10 - 4}{(((5 - 3)^9) + 7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{387296} := \frac{1 \times 04}{38 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{25376} := \frac{1^{04}}{2 \times (((5 - 3)^7) - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{65728} := \frac{1^{04}}{(65 + 7 \times 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{683592} := \frac{1 \times 04}{6 \times (8 + 3^5 \times 9 \times 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{25896} := \frac{10 - 4}{(258 - 9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{67392} := \frac{10 + 4}{(67^{-3}) \times (9 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{927368} := \frac{1^{04}}{9 + (2^7 + 3) \times 68}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{35672} := \frac{1 \times 04}{3 + (((5 \times 6) + 7)^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{73528} := \frac{1^{04}}{735 - 28}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{37856} := \frac{10 - 4}{3^7 + (8 - (5 + 6))}$	$\quad := \frac{1 + 04}{7 + 3528}$	

● Numerator 105

$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{294} := \frac{1 \times 05}{2 \times 9 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{6384} := \frac{10 + 5}{6 \times (38 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{84672} := \frac{1 \times 05}{8 + ((4^6) - 72)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{378} := \frac{1 \times 05}{3 + 7 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{23478} := \frac{1 \times 05}{2 \times ((3^4 \times 7) - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{86247} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(8^{6-2}) + 4 + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{462} := \frac{1 \times 05}{4 \times 6 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{24738} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(24 + 7) \times 38}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{92736} := \frac{10 + 5}{9 \times (2 \times (7 + 3^6))}$
$\quad := \frac{10 + 5}{4 + 62}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{26439} := \frac{1 \times 05}{2 + ((6^4) - 39)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{367248} := \frac{10 + 5}{(3 - 6 + (7 + 2)^4) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{693} := \frac{1 \times 05}{6 + 9 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{28476} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(2 + (8 \times (4 \times 7))) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{469728} := \frac{1 \times 05}{4 \times (697 + 2) \times 8}$
$\quad := \frac{10 + 5}{6 + 93}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{37926} := \frac{1 \times 05}{3 \times (7 \times (92 - 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{689472} := \frac{1 \times 05}{6 \times 8 \times 9 \times (4 + 72)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{924} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(9 + 2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{42987} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(4 \times (2^9)) - 8 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{789264} := \frac{1 \times 05}{7 \times (8 \times 9)^2 + 6^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2436} := \frac{1 \times 05}{2 \times ((4^3) - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{63294} := \frac{1 \times 05}{6 + (32 \times 94)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{829346} := \frac{10 + 5}{829 + (3 + 4)^6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{4368} := \frac{1 \times 05}{4 + 3 \times 68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{63798} := \frac{1 \times 05}{6 + (379 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{928746} := \frac{1 \times 05}{9^2 \times (87 + 4) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{4872} := \frac{1 \times 05}{4 \times ((8 \times 7) + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{78624} := \frac{1 \times 05}{78 \times (6 \times 2 \times 4)}$	
$\quad := \frac{10 + 5}{4 \times (87 \times 2)}$	$\quad := \frac{10 + 5}{78 \times 6 \times 24}$	

● Numerator 106

$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{583} := \frac{10 + 6}{5 + 83}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{5724} := \frac{10 - 6}{(5 + 7^2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{47382} := \frac{10 - 6}{(47 \times 38) + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{742} := \frac{1 \times 06}{7 \times (4 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{8374} := \frac{1^{06}}{8 - (3 - 74)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{57293} := \frac{1 \times 06}{(5 \times (72 \times 9)) + 3}$
$\quad := \frac{1 + 06}{7 + 42}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{9275} := \frac{1 \times 06}{(9 - 2) \times 75}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{72398} := \frac{1^{06}}{((72 + 3) \times 9) + 8}$
$\quad := \frac{10 + 6}{7 \times (4^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{27348} := \frac{10 - 6}{((2^7) - 3 + 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{83475} := \frac{10 - 6}{(8 + 34) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{954} := \frac{1^{06}}{9 \times (5 - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{27984} := \frac{1^{06}}{2 \times (((7 + 9) \times 8) + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{283974} := \frac{10 - 6}{2 + (8 + 3) \times 974}$
$\quad := \frac{1 + 06}{9 + 54}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{32754} := \frac{1^{06}}{(3^2) + (75 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{439582} := \frac{10 \times 6}{4 + (3 + 9)^5 - 8 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{2385} := \frac{10 - 6}{2 + (3 + 85)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{35298} := \frac{1^{06}}{35 + 298}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{573248} := \frac{1 \times 06}{(5 + 7 \times 3)^2 \times 48}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{3498} := \frac{1^{06}}{34 - 9 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{37842} := \frac{1^{06}}{3 \times 7 + (8 \times 42)}$	
$\quad := \frac{10 - 6}{3 \times (4 \times 9 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{37948} := \frac{1 \times 06}{3^7 + (9 - 48)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{4293} := \frac{10 - 6}{(4 + 2) \times (9 \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{38425} := \frac{1 \times 06}{(3 + 84) \times 25}$	

● Numerator 107

$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{428} := \frac{1 + 07}{4 + 28}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2568} := \frac{1^{07}}{(2 - 5 + 6) \times 8}$	$\quad := \frac{10 - 7}{(2 \times 39 + 6) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{642} := \frac{1 + 07}{6 + 42}$	$\quad := \frac{10 - 7}{2 + (5 \times (6 + 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{24396} := \frac{1^{07}}{2 \times (4 \times 3 \times 9 + 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{856} := \frac{1 + 07}{8 + 56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{3852} := \frac{1^{07}}{3 + (8 + 5^2)}$	$\quad := \frac{1 + 07}{(2^4 + 3) \times 96}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{963} := \frac{1^{07}}{(9 - 6) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{5243} := \frac{1^{07}}{(5 + 2) \times (4 + 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{25894} := \frac{1^{07}}{2 \times ((5 + 8) \times 9 + 4)}$
$\quad := \frac{10 - 7}{9 \times (6 - 3)}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times 07}{(5 - 2 + 4)^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{29853} := \frac{1^{07}}{(((2 + 9) \times 8) + 5) \times 3}$
$\quad := \frac{1 + 07}{9 + 63}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{8453} := \frac{10 - 7}{(84 - 5) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{36594} := \frac{1 + 07}{((3^6) - (5 \times 9)) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2354} := \frac{1^{07}}{2 \times (3 \times 5 - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{9523} := \frac{1^{07}}{95 - 2 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{42693} := \frac{1^{07}}{426 - (9 \times 3)}$
$\quad := \frac{10 - 7}{(2 \times 35) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{23968} := \frac{1^{07}}{(2 \times 3)^{9-6} + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{45368} := \frac{1 \times 07}{4 \times (5 + ((3^6) + 8))}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{53928} := \frac{1^{07}}{(5-3) \times (9 \times 28)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{269854} := \frac{1^{07}}{26 \times (98 - 5 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{582936} := \frac{1 \times 07}{5 \times 82 \times 93 + 6}$$

• Numerator 108

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{243} := \frac{1 \times 08}{(2+4) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{3672} := \frac{10-8}{3+(67-2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{43956} := \frac{10-8}{4+(3 \times (9 \times 5 \times 6))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{264} := \frac{1+08}{26-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{3726} := \frac{10-8}{3+(72-6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{45792} := \frac{1^{08}}{4 \times (((5+7) \times 9) - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{297} := \frac{1 \times 08}{29-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{3924} := \frac{1+08}{3+(9^2 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{52974} := \frac{10-8}{5+(2+974)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{324} := \frac{1 \times 08}{3 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{4536} := \frac{1^{08}}{45+3-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{53946} := \frac{10-8}{53+946}$$

$$:= \frac{1+08}{3+24}$$

$$:= \frac{10-8}{4 \times (5 \times 3 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{54972} := \frac{1^{08}}{5+(4 \times (9 \times (7 \times 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{396} := \frac{1+08}{39-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{4752} := \frac{1^{08}}{47-5+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{63492} := \frac{10+8}{((6^3) \times 49) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{432} := \frac{1^{08}}{4 \times (3-2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{5346} := \frac{10-8}{53+46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{67524} := \frac{1+08}{6+((75^2) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+08}{4+32}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{7236} := \frac{1^{08}}{(7^2) + 3 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{93762} := \frac{10+8}{((9+3-7)^6) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{594} := \frac{10+8}{5+94}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{7452} := \frac{10-8}{(7 \times 4 \times 5) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{234765} := \frac{1 \times 08}{(2+3476) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{756} := \frac{1+08}{7+56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{7542} := \frac{10+8}{7+((5^4) \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{245736} := \frac{1+08}{2-4+5 \times (7-3)^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{924} := \frac{1+08}{9^2-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{9234} := \frac{10-8}{9+(2 \times (3^4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{247536} := \frac{1 \times 08}{24 \times (7 \times 5 + 3^6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{972} := \frac{10-8}{9+7+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{24576} := \frac{1+08}{2 \times 4^5 \times (7-6)}$$

$$:= \frac{10-8}{(2+4) \times (7 \times 5 + 3^6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+08}{9+72}$$

$$:= \frac{10+8}{2^{(4+5-7) \times 6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{273456} := \frac{1^{08}}{(2+7 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2376} := \frac{1^{08}}{23-7+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{29754} := \frac{10-8}{2+(9 \times (7+54))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{274536} := \frac{1^{08}}{2^7 \times 4 \times 5 - 3 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{3456} := \frac{10-8}{(3+4-5)^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{35964} := \frac{1^{08}}{(3^5) + (9 \times (6+4))}$$

$$:= \frac{10-8}{2-7 \times (4-5^3) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1+08}{(3+45) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{37296} := \frac{10+8}{3 \times (7 \times 296)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{275364} := \frac{10+8}{2-7 \times (5-(3+6)^4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{3564} := \frac{1^{08}}{35-6+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{37692} := \frac{1^{08}}{(3 \times ((7+6) \times 9)) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{326574} := \frac{10+8}{3-2+6^5 \times 7-4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{327564} &:= \frac{1^{08}}{3^2 + 756 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{435672} &:= \frac{1^{08}}{4^3 \times (56 + 7) + 2} & & := \frac{1^{08}}{(6^4 + 7 \times 3^5) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{354726} &:= \frac{10 - 8}{3^{5-4+7} + 2 + 6} & & := \frac{1^{08}}{4 \times 3 \times (67 \times 5 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{653724} &:= \frac{1 + 08}{(6^5 + 3) \times 7 + 24} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{362475} &:= \frac{1 \times 08}{(362 - 4) \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{456732} &:= \frac{1^{08}}{4 + (5 + 6 \times (7 + 3))^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{743256} &:= \frac{1^{08}}{74 \times 3 \times (25 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{365472} &:= \frac{1^{08}}{3 + (65 + 4) \times 7^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{476523} &:= \frac{10 \times 8}{(4 + 7^6 + 5 + 2) \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{945672} &:= \frac{1 + 08}{((9^4 + 5) \times 6 + 7) \times 2} \\ & & & & & \\ & := \frac{10 - 8}{3 \times 6 \times (54 \times 7 - 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{592734} &:= \frac{10 + 8}{5 + 9 \times (2 \times 7)^3 \times 4} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{374592} &:= \frac{1 + 08}{3 - 7^4 \times (5 - 9 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{108}{647352} &:= \frac{1 \times 08}{6^4 \times (7 + 3 \times 5 \times 2)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 109

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{327} &:= \frac{1 \times 09}{3 \times (2 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{26378} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{2 + (6 + (3 \times 78))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{72485} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{((7 - 2)^4) + (8 \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{1 + 09}{3 + 27} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{27468} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{2 \times (7 \times (4 + 6 + 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{73248} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{7 \times (3 \times (24 + 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{436} &:= \frac{1 \times 09}{4 \times (3 + 6)} & & := \frac{10 + 9}{(2 \times (7^4)) - (6 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{73684} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{((7 + 3) \times 68) - 4} \\ & := \frac{1 + 09}{4 + 36} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{46325} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{(4 + ((6 + 3)^2)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{83276} &:= \frac{1 \times 09}{(83^2) - (7 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{654} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{6 \times (5 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{53628} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{(5^3 \times (6 - 2)) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{234568} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{(2 - 3 + 45 \times 6) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 09}{6 \times (5 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{53846} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{(5^3 \times (8 - 4)) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{436872} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{4 \times 3 \times (6 \times 8 \times 7 - 2)} \\ & := \frac{1 + 09}{6 + 54} & & := \frac{1 \times 09}{(53 \times 84) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{572468} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{57 \times 2 \times 46 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{763} &:= \frac{1 \times 09}{7 \times (6 + 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{62784} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{6 \times ((2^7) - 8 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{742835} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{7 + 4 + 28 \times 3^5} \\ & := \frac{1 + 09}{7 + 63} & & := \frac{1 \times 09}{6 \times (27 \times 8 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{872436} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{87 \times (2 \times 43 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{872} &:= \frac{1 \times 09}{8 \times (7 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{64528} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{(6 \times (4 \times (5^2))) - 8} & & \\ & := \frac{1 + 09}{8 + 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{68452} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{((6 + 8) \times 45) - 2} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{109}{2834} &:= \frac{1^{09}}{(2 \times (8 + 3)) + 4} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 120

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{120}{594} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{5 + 94} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{120}{37548} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{((3 + 7) \times 5^4) + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{120}{39468} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{3 + ((9^4) + 6 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{120}{73584} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{7 \times (3 \times 584)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 123

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{984} &:= \frac{12 \times 3}{9 \times 8 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{4059} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 3}{40 + 59} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{4756} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 3}{4 \times ((7 \times 5) - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{4879} &:= \frac{1 + 2^3}{(4 \times 87) + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{5740} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 3}{5 \times (7 \times (4 + 0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{9840} &:= \frac{12 \times 3}{9 \times 8 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{40795} &:= \frac{1 + 2 + 3}{(407 - 9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{45879} &:= \frac{1^{23}}{(4 \times ((5 + 8) \times 7)) + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{408975} &:= \frac{1 + 2^3}{(408 - 9) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{807495} &:= \frac{1 + 2^3}{8 + 07 \times 4 + 9^5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 124

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{3069} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{30 + 69} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 4}{306 - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{3596} &:= \frac{1 - 2 + 4}{3 + ((5 + 9) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{3906} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{3 \times (90 - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{6758} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{(6 \times 7 \times 5) + 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + 4)}{(67 \times 5) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{6975} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{(6 + 9)^{7-5}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{7936} &:= \frac{1 + 2 \times 4}{(7 + 9) \times 36} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{9765} &:= \frac{1 \times 24}{9 \times (7 \times 6 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{30597} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{((30 \times 5) - 9) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{63798} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{(6 - 3) \times (7 \times 98)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 4}{(6 + 3) \times (7 \times 98)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 24}{6 \times (3 \times (7 \times 98))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{79360} &:= \frac{1 + 2 \times 4}{(7 + 9) \times 360} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{90675} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{90 \times ((6 + 7) \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{97650} &:= \frac{1 \times 24}{9 \times (7 \times (6 \times 50))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{97836} &:= \frac{1 + 2 \times 4}{9 \times (783 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{98735} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{(98 - 7) \times 35} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{367598} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{(3 \times 6 \times 7 - 5) \times 98} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{637980} &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 4}{(6 + 3) \times 7 \times 980} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 24}{6 \times 3 \times 7 \times 980} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{124}{685937} &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 4}{(6 + (8 + 5) \times 9^3) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 125

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{125}{3690} := \frac{1 \times 25}{(3^6) + 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{125}{43780} := \frac{1 \times 25}{(4 \times (3^7)) + 8 + 0}$$

- Numerator 126

$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{308} := \frac{1+2+6}{30-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{35840} := \frac{1+2+6}{(3+5) \times 8 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{374850} := \frac{12-6}{3 \times (5+8 \times 9) \times 74}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{378} := \frac{12-6}{3+7+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{37890} := \frac{1^2+6}{3^7+(8-90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{374850} := \frac{1^{26}}{(3+74 \times 8) \times 5+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{385} := \frac{1+26}{3+78}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{39074} := \frac{1+2+6}{390+(7^4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{380457} := \frac{1 \times (2+6)}{3 \times (8045+7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{385} := \frac{12+6}{(3+8) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{39480} := \frac{12 \times 6}{3 \times (94 \times 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{387450} := \frac{1^{26}}{3 \times (8-7+4^5)+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{504} := \frac{1-2+6}{5 \times 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{43750} := \frac{1+2+6}{(4 \times 3-7)^5+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{394758} := \frac{1^{26}}{(3-9+4+7)^5+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{735} := \frac{12+6}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{45738} := \frac{1 \times (2+6)}{(4 \times 5+7^3) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{397458} := \frac{1^2+6}{3^9+7^4+5-8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{3584} := \frac{1+2+6}{(3+5) \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{73584} := \frac{1^{26}}{((7+3) \times 58)+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{398475} := \frac{12+6}{(3+9 \times 84) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{3850} := \frac{12+6}{(3+8) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{437598} := \frac{1^2+6}{7-(3 \times 5-8^4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{437598} := \frac{1^{26}}{43+7 \times 5 \times 98}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{3948} := \frac{12 \times 6}{3 \times (94 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{93450} := \frac{12-6}{(93-4) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{457380} := \frac{1 \times (2+6)}{(4 \times 5+7^3) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{7035} := \frac{12-6}{(70-3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{95438} := \frac{1+2+6}{((9-5)^4)+(3^8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{470589} := \frac{12+6}{4 \times 7^{05}+8-9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{7350} := \frac{12+6}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{308574} := \frac{1-2+6}{30 \times 8+5 \times 7^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{539784} := \frac{1^{26}}{(5+39+7) \times 84}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{9345} := \frac{12-6}{(93-4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{345780} := \frac{1^2+6}{34 \times (5+7 \times 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{735840} := \frac{1^{26}}{73 \times (5 \times 8+40)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{34587} := \frac{12+6}{3^4 \times (5+8 \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{345870} := \frac{1^{26}}{3 \times (45+870)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{879354} := \frac{1^{26}}{(8+7) \times 93 \times 5+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{35784} := \frac{1^{26}}{(3 \times ((5+7) \times 8)) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{357840} := \frac{1^{26}}{(3 \times 5+7 \times 8) \times 40}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{35784} := \frac{12 \times 6}{3-(5 \times (7-8^4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{358974} := \frac{1^{26}}{3+5 \times 89+7^4}$	

● Numerator 127

$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{508} := \frac{1+2+7}{5 \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{635} := \frac{1 \times (2+7)}{(6+3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{4953} := \frac{12-7}{(4+9) \times (5 \times 3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{635} := \frac{1 \times (2+7)}{(6+3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{3048} := \frac{1^{27}}{3 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{6350} := \frac{1 \times (2+7)}{(6+3) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{3048} := \frac{1^{27}}{3 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{3048} := \frac{1 \times 27}{(3^{04}) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{6985} := \frac{1^{27}}{6+(9+(8 \times 5))}$
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{3048} := \frac{1-2+7}{3 \times (0+48)}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{3048} := \frac{1+2 \times 7}{30 \times (4+8)}$	

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{127}{8509} := \frac{1^2 \times 7}{(69 + 8) \times 5} \\ \frac{127}{69850} := \frac{1^{27}}{8 + (50 + 9)} \\ \frac{127}{59436} := \frac{1^{27}}{(5 + (9 + 4^3)) \times 6} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{127}{53086} := \frac{12 - 7}{5 \times ((9 + 4) \times 36)} \\ \frac{127}{49530} := \frac{1^{27}}{(53 \times 08) - 6} \\ \frac{127}{356489} := \frac{12 - 7}{(4 + 9) \times (5 \times 30)} \\ \frac{127}{356489} := \frac{1^{27}}{(356 - 4) \times 8 - 9} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{127}{405638} := \frac{1^{27}}{4 + 05 \times 638} \\ \frac{127}{594360} := \frac{1^{27}}{(5 + 9 + 4^3) \times 60} \\ \frac{127}{609854} := \frac{1 \times 2^7}{(6 + 09 + 8 + 5)^4} \end{array}$$

• Numerator 128

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{128}{369} := \frac{1 \times 2^8}{(3^6) + 9} \\ \frac{128}{576} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{(5 + 7) \times 6} \\ \frac{128}{3456} := \frac{12 - 8}{5 + 7 + 6} \\ \frac{128}{3456} := \frac{1^{28}}{3^{4+5-6}} \\ \frac{128}{3456} := \frac{1^2 + 8}{3^{4-5+6}} \\ \frac{128}{4736} := \frac{1 + (2 \times 8)}{3 + 456} \\ \frac{128}{4736} := \frac{1^{28}}{4 \times 7 + 3 + 6} \\ \frac{128}{4736} := \frac{12 + 8}{4 + (7 + 3^6)} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{128}{5376} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{(5 + 3) \times 7 \times 6} \\ \frac{128}{5760} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{(5 + 7) \times 60} \\ \frac{128}{34560} := \frac{1^2 + 8}{3^4 \times (5 \times (6 + 0))} \\ \frac{128}{39456} := \frac{12 - 8}{3 \times ((9 \times 45) + 6)} \\ \frac{128}{45360} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{45 \times (3 + 60)} \\ \frac{128}{49536} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{4 \times ((9 \times 5) + 3^6)} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{128}{53760} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{(5 + 3) \times (7 \times 60)} \\ \frac{128}{75904} := \frac{1^{28}}{7 + (590 - 4)} \\ \frac{128}{97536} := \frac{1^{28}}{(9 - (7 - (5^3))) \times 6} \\ \frac{128}{349056} := \frac{1^{28}}{3 + (4 + 90 \times 5) \times 6} \\ \frac{128}{956304} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{9^5 + 6 \times 30 \times 4} \end{array}$$

• Numerator 129

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{129}{387} := \frac{1^{29}}{3 \times (8 - 7)} \\ \frac{129}{473} := \frac{1 + 29}{3 + 87} \\ \frac{129}{473} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(4 + 7) \times 3} \\ \frac{129}{473} := \frac{1 + 2 + 9}{47 - 3} \\ \frac{129}{473} := \frac{12 + 9}{4 + 73} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{129}{645} := \frac{1^{29}}{6 + 4 - 5} \\ \frac{129}{3870} := \frac{1^2 + 9}{(6 + 4) \times 5} \\ \frac{129}{3870} := \frac{12 - 9}{6 + 4 + 5} \\ \frac{129}{3870} := \frac{12 - 9}{3 + (87 + 0)} \\ \frac{129}{4386} := \frac{1^{29}}{4 - ((3 - 8) \times 6)} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{129}{645} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(43 + 8) \times 6} \\ \frac{129}{4730} := \frac{12 - 9}{(4 \times 3 \times 8) + 6} \\ \frac{129}{4730} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(4 + 7) \times 30} \\ \frac{129}{5074} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(50 \times 7) + 4} \\ \frac{129}{6450} := \frac{1^{29}}{(6 + 4) \times (5 + 0)} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{129}{6708} := \frac{1^2 + 9}{(6 + 4) \times 50} \\
 \frac{129}{8643} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{6 \times (70 + 8)} \\
 \frac{129}{43860} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(43 + 8) \times 60} \\
 \frac{129}{47085} := \frac{1^{29}}{8^{6-4} + 3} \\
 \frac{129}{48375} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(48 - 3) \times 75} \\
 \frac{129}{67854} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{8 \times (64 + 3)} \\
 \frac{129}{78045} := \frac{1^{29}}{(4 \times 70) + 85} \\
 \frac{129}{80367} := \frac{1^{29}}{(80 + 3 + 6) \times 7} \\
 \frac{129}{80754} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(48 - 3) \times 75} \\
 \frac{129}{80754} := \frac{1 + 2 + 9}{(4 + 8) \times 375}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{129}{53406} := \frac{12 - 9}{(4 + 8 + 3) \times 75} \\
 \frac{129}{58437} := \frac{1^{29}}{5 + (3 + 406)} \\
 \frac{129}{67854} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{6 \times (785 + 4)} \\
 \frac{129}{78045} := \frac{1^{29}}{(7 \times 80) + 45} \\
 \frac{129}{80367} := \frac{1^{29}}{(80 + 3 + 6) \times 7} \\
 \frac{129}{80754} := \frac{1^{29}}{8 + (0 - (7 - (5^4)))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{129}{84753} := \frac{1^{29}}{((8 \times (4 \times 7)) - 5) \times 3} \\
 \frac{129}{375046} := \frac{12 - 9}{(3^7 - 5) \times 04 - 6} \\
 \frac{129}{375648} := \frac{12 - 9}{3 \times 7 \times (56 - 4) \times 8} \\
 \frac{129}{483750} := \frac{1 + 2 + 9}{(4 + 8) \times 3750} \\
 \frac{129}{538704} := \frac{1 \times (2 + 9)}{5 + 3^8 \times 7 + 04} \\
 \frac{129}{756843} := \frac{1^{29}}{7 \times 5 + (6 + 8 + 4)^3}
 \end{array}$$

• Numerator 130

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{130}{624} := \frac{1 \times 30}{6 \times 24} \\
 \frac{130}{2496} := \frac{1 \times 30}{(2 + 4) \times 96} \\
 \frac{130}{2795} := \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{2 + 79 + 5} \\
 \frac{130}{24895} := \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{2 + 4 + 8 \times 95} \\
 \frac{130}{26975} := \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{2 + 69 \times (7 + 5)} \\
 \frac{130}{28795} := \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{2 + 879 + 5}
 \end{array}$$

• Numerator 132

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{132}{540} := \frac{13 - 2}{5 + 40} \\
 \frac{132}{648} := \frac{13 - 2}{6 + 48} \\
 \frac{132}{756} := \frac{13 - 2}{7 + 56} \\
 \frac{132}{864} := \frac{13 - 2}{8 + 64} \\
 \frac{132}{4576} := \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(45 + 7) \times 6} \\
 \frac{132}{4796} := \frac{1^3 + 2}{4 + (7 \times (9 + 6))} \\
 \frac{132}{4896} := \frac{13 - 2}{4 \times ((8 + 9) \times 6)} \\
 \frac{132}{5896} := \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(58 + 9) \times 6} \\
 \frac{132}{7546} := \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{7^{5+4-6}} \\
 \frac{132}{7584} := \frac{13 - 2}{7 + (5^{8-4})} \\
 \frac{132}{7854} := \frac{1 + 3 - 2}{7 \times (8 + 5 + 4)} \\
 \frac{132}{7968} := \frac{13 - 2}{7 \times 96 - 8} \\
 \frac{132}{8976} := \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{8 \times (9 + 7 \times 6)} \\
 \frac{132}{8976} := \frac{1 + 3^2}{8 \times (9 + 76)} \\
 \frac{132}{9768} := \frac{1 \times (3 + 2)}{(9 \times 7 \times 6) - 8} \\
 \frac{132}{45760} := \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(45 + 7) \times 60} \\
 \frac{132}{47058} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 2}{4 \times (705 + 8)} \\
 \frac{132}{47685} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 2}{(4 \times 7 + 6) \times 85} \\
 \frac{132}{48576} := \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{4 \times ((85 + 7) \times 6)} \\
 \frac{132}{48960} := \frac{13 - 2}{4 \times ((8 + 9) \times 60)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{57948} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 + 2)}{5 \times (7 + (9 \times 48))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{58960} &:= \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(58 + 9) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{67584} &:= \frac{1 \times 32}{(6 - (7 - 5)) \times 8^4} \\ &:= \frac{1^3 + 2}{6 \times ((7 + 5 - 8)^4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 2}{(6 + (7 - 5))^{8-4}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{68750} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{(6 - 8 + 7)^5 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{69784} &:= \frac{1 \times 3^2}{6 \times (9 + 784)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{75460} &:= \frac{1^3 + 2}{7 \times (5 + 4 \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{84956} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{(8^4 \times 9) - 5^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{87956} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{8 + 7 \times 95 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{89760} &:= \frac{1^{32}}{8 \times (9 + 76) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{476850} &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 2}{(4 \times 7 + 6) \times 850} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{485760} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{4 \times (85 + 7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{487905} &:= \frac{(1 + 3)^2}{4 + 87 + 9^{05}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{574860} &:= \frac{1^{32}}{5 \times (7 + 4 + 860)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{132}{958704} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{(9^5 + 870) \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 133

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{268} &:= \frac{(1 + 3)^4}{2^6 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{2 - 6 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 4}{2 + 6 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{13 - 4}{26 - 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 34}{2 + 68} \\ &:= \frac{13 + 4}{26 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2680} &:= \frac{(1 + 3)^4}{2^6 \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{1^{34}}{2 \times 6 + 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{5628} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{56 + 28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{5762} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{5 \times 7 + 6 + 2} \\ &:= \frac{1^3 + 4}{5 \times (7 + 6^2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 4}{(57 \times 6) + 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{5829} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{58 + 29} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{5896} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{5 + (89 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times 4)}{(58 \times 9) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{6298} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{6 + ((2 + 9) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{8576} &:= \frac{13 - 4}{8 \times ((5 + 7) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{9782} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{9 \times 7 + 8 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{27068} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{270 - 68} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 34}{2 + 7068} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{29078} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{(2^9 + 0) - 78} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{52796} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{((5^2) \times (7 + 9)) - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{56280} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{5 \times (6 - (2 - 80))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{5 \times (6 \times (28 + 0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{58692} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{5 + (869 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{65928} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{6 \times ((5 \times 9 \times 2) - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{72695} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{(72 \times (6 + 9)) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{85760} &:= \frac{13 - 4}{8 \times ((5 + 7) \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{90785} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 4}{(90 \times (7 + 8)) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{207968} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{(20 \times 7 + 9 \times 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{650972} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{6 + 50 \times 97 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{695728} &:= \frac{1^{34}}{(6 + 9 + 57)^2 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 135

$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{240} := \frac{1+3+5}{2^4+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{4968} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{4 \times (9 \times 6 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{268947} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(2^6 \times 89 - 4) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{270} := \frac{1+35}{2+70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{6480} := \frac{1-3+5}{64+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276408} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{2^7 \times 6 \times 40 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{297} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{2 \times 9 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{7290} := \frac{1^3 + 5}{6 \times (48 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{2^7 \times (6 + 4) \times 8 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{468} := \frac{1 \times 35}{(2+9) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{7290} := \frac{1-3+5}{72+90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{2^{7+6-4} \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{480} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{4+6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{8640} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(7+2) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 5}{2^{7 \times (6+4-8)} + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{480} := \frac{1+3+5}{4 \times 8 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{8640} := \frac{1^{35}}{8^{6-4} + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{1 \times 35}{2 \times 7 \times 64 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{486} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{4+8+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{8640} := \frac{1-3+5}{8 \times (6 \times (4+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{1^{35}}{2^7 + 6 \times 4 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{486} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{48+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{8640} := \frac{1 \times (3+5)}{8 \times (64+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{1+3 \times 5}{2^7 \times (6-4)^8 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{486} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+8) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{8964} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{(89-6) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{1+3+5}{2^7 \times (64+80)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{648} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{6 \times (4+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{9720} := \frac{1+3+5}{9 \times (72+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{276480} := \frac{13+5}{2^7 \times 6 \times 48 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{729} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{72+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{27648} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(2^{7+6-4}) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{278640} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(2+7) \times 86 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{792} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{7+9^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{27648} := \frac{1 \times 35}{2 \times (7 \times 64 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{286470} := \frac{1-3+5}{2+86 \times (4+70)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{864} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{8+6 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{27864} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(2+7) \times 86 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{287496} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{(2 \times (8+7-4))^{9-6}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2970} := \frac{1^{35}}{29-7+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{42768} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+(2^7)) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{289467} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{2 \times 894 \times 6 - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2970} := \frac{1 \times 35}{(2+9) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{48672} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{4 \times (8 \times ((6+7)^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{294768} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{2+(9-4^7) \times (6-8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{4608} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(4+60) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{48672} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{4 \times (8 \times ((6+7)^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{294786} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(2-9+4^7) \times (8-6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{4680} := \frac{1-3+5}{4 \times 6 + 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{64890} := \frac{1+3+5}{6+(48 \times 90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{420687} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(4+2)^{06} + 87}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{4860} := \frac{1-3+5}{48+60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{76482} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{7 \times ((6^4) - 82)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{427680} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+2^7) \times 6 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{4860} := \frac{1 \times (3+5)}{48 \times (6+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{84672} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8 \times (4 \times (6 \times (7^2)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{476280} := \frac{1+3 \times 5}{4 \times (7 \times 6)^2 \times 8 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{4860} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+8) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{89640} := \frac{1-3+5}{8 \times (9+(6 \times 40))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{476928} := \frac{1 \times 35}{4 \times 7 \times 6 \times 92 \times 8}$
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{89640} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{(89-6) \times 40}$	

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{135}{689472} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 5}{6 \times (8 + 9 \times 472)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{135}{846720} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 + 5)}{((8 + 4 \times 6) \times 7)^2 + 0} & & := \frac{1 + 35}{8 \times (4 \times 6 \times 7)^2 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{135}{762048} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(7 \times 6)^2 \times 048} & & := \frac{1 + 3 + 5}{8 \times 4 \times (6 \times 7)^2 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{135}{786240} &:= \frac{1^3 + 5}{7 \times 8 \times 624 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 136

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{204} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{2 + 04} & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{2958} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{29 + 58} & & := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 6}{(2 + 7) \times 540} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{408} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{4 + 08} & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{4590} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{45 + 90} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{29784} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 6}{2 + (9 \times 7 + (8^4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{459} &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 6}{(4 + 5) \times 9} & & := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 6}{(4 + 5) \times 90} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{59024} := \frac{1^{36}}{(5 \times 90) - (2^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{748} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 6}{7 + 48} & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{5984} &:= \frac{13 - 6}{(5 + 9 \times 8) \times 4} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{59840} := \frac{13 - 6}{(5 + 9 \times 8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{782} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{7 + 8 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{7480} &:= \frac{1^{36}}{7 + (48 + 0)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{75480} := \frac{1^{36}}{7 + (548 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{952} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{(9 + 5) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{7548} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 6}{7 + 548} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{92480} := \frac{1^{36}}{(9^2 + 4) \times (8 + 0)} \\ & & & := \frac{1 \times (3 + 6)}{9 \times (5 + 2)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{9248} := \frac{1 + 3 + 6}{(9^2 + 4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{2584} &:= \frac{1^{36}}{2 + (5 + 8 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{9520} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{(9 + 5) \times 20} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{507824} := \frac{1^3 \times 6}{50 \times 7 \times 8^2 + 4} \\ & & & := \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{(2 \times (5 \times 8)) - 4} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{2754} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{2 + (75 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{25908} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6}{2 + ((5 + 90) \times 8)} & & \\ & & & := \frac{1^3 \times 6}{27 \times (5 + 40)} & & \\ & & & := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 6}{(2 + 7) \times 54} & & \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 137

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{548} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 7}{5 \times 4 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{6028} &:= \frac{1^{37}}{6^{01} + 8} & & := \frac{1^3 + 7}{9 \times 8^{6-4}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{4658} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 7}{46 \times 5 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{8905} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 7}{8 \times 90 - 5} & & := \frac{1 \times 3 + 7}{9 \times 8 \times (6 + 4)} \\ & & & := \frac{1^3 + 7}{(4 + 6 \times 5) \times 8} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{28496} := \frac{1^{37}}{28 \times 4 + 96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{5480} &:= \frac{13 - 7}{5 \times 48 + 0} & & := \frac{1^3 \times 7}{9 \times (8 + 6) \times 4} & & := \frac{13 - 7}{2 \times 8 \times (4 + 9) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{46580} &:= \frac{1^{37}}{(4 \times 65) + 80} \\ &:= \frac{13 - 7}{4 \times (6 \times (5 + 80))} \\ &:= \frac{1^3 + 7}{(4 + 6 \times 5) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{98640} &:= \frac{1^{37}}{9 \times (8 \times (6 + 4 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{1^3 \times 7}{9 \times ((8 + 6) \times 40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{284960} &:= \frac{13 - 7}{2 \times 8 \times (4 + 9) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{137}{859264} &:= \frac{1^{37}}{(8 + 5 \times 9 \times 2) \times 64} \\ &:= \frac{13 + 7}{(8 \times (5 + 9))^2 \times (6 + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 138

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{207} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8}{2 + 07}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{276} := \frac{1^{38}}{2 \times (7 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 38}{2 + 76}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{506} := \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{50 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{529} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8}{5 + 2 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{759} := \frac{1^3 \times 8}{7 \times 5 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{7 + 59}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2760} := \frac{1^{38}}{2 \times 7 + 6 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{4692} := \frac{1^{38}}{4 + ((6 + 9) \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{5290} := \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{5 \times (2 + 90)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{5796} := \frac{1^{38}}{(5 - 7 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{(5 + 79) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{6072} := \frac{1^{38}}{(6 \times 07) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{7245} := \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{7 \times 2 \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{7406} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8}{7 \times (40 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{7452} := \frac{1^{38}}{7 + (45 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 + 8}{((7 - 4)^5) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{7659} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8}{(7 + 6 \times 5) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{7 + 659}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{20976} := \frac{1^{38}}{2 \times ((0 \times 9) + 76)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 + 8}{2 \times (09 \times 76)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{27945} := \frac{1^3 \times 8}{(2 + 79) \times 4 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{27 \times (9 \times 4 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{29647} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8}{((2 \times (9 - 6))^4) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{40572} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8}{(40 - 5 + 7)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{57960} := \frac{1^{38}}{(5 - 7 + 9) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 \times 8}{5 \times (7 \times (96 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{(5 + 79) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{65274} := \frac{1^{38}}{((65 + 2) \times 7) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{72450} := \frac{1 + 3 + 8}{7 \times (2 \times 450)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{74520} := \frac{1^{38}}{(7 + 4 \times 5) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 + 8}{((7 - 4)^5) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{75624} := \frac{1^{38}}{(75 + 62) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{76452} := \frac{1^{38}}{(7 + (6 \times 45)) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{76590} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8}{(7 + 6 \times 5) \times 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{279450} := \frac{1^3 \times 8}{(2 + 79) \times 4 \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{27 \times 9 \times 4 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{452709} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{4 \times (5 - 2)^7 \times 09}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{756240} := \frac{1^{38}}{(75 + 62) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{764520} := \frac{1^{38}}{(7 + 6 \times 45) \times 20}$$

• Numerator 139

$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{278} := \frac{(1+3) \times 9}{(2+7) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{4587} := \frac{13-9}{4 \times (5 \times 8 - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{460785} := \frac{1^{39}}{(46-07) \times 85}$
$\quad := \frac{1+39}{2+78}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{4726} := \frac{1^{39}}{4 + ((7-2) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{678042} := \frac{1^{39}}{6 \times (7+804+2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{2085} := \frac{1^{39}}{2 - (0 - (8+5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{46287} := \frac{1^{39}}{46 + 287}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{705286} := \frac{1^{39}}{(7+052) \times 86}$
$\quad := \frac{1-3+9}{20+85}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{57268} := \frac{1^{39}}{(5 \times (7 \times 2 \times 6)) - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{840672} := \frac{1^{39}}{84 \times (0 \times 6 + 72)}$
$\quad := \frac{13-9}{20 \times (8-5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{250478} := \frac{1^{39}}{2 + 50 \times (4 \times 7 + 8)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{2780} := \frac{(1+3) \times 9}{(2+7) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{407826} := \frac{1^{39}}{(407+82) \times 6}$	
$\quad := \frac{13-9}{2+(78+0)}$		

• Numerator 140

$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{392} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+9+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{7896} := \frac{1+4+0}{(7 \times 8 - 9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{372568} := \frac{1+4+0}{(3^7 + 2^5) \times 6 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{952} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+5^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{8295} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 0}{(8 \times 29) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{376852} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+(76+8 \times 5)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2695} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 0}{2 + ((6+9) \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{37625} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 0}{(37+6) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{639275} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 0}{6 \times 3 \times 9^2 + 7^5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2765} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 0}{2 + (7 \times (6+5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{38675} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 0}{((38 \times 6) - 7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{683592} := \frac{1+4+0}{68 \times 359 + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2968} := \frac{1+4+0}{2+(96+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{79632} := \frac{1+4+0}{79 \times (6 \times 3 \times 2)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{3276} := \frac{1+4+0}{3^2 \times (7+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{285376} := \frac{1+4+0}{28^{5-3} \times (7+6)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{6328} := \frac{1+4+0}{6^3 + 2 + 8}$		

• Numerator 142

$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{568} := \frac{14-2}{56-8}$	$\quad := \frac{(1+4) \times 2}{6+39}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3976} := \frac{1^{42}}{3 \times 9 + 7 - 6}$
$\quad := \frac{1 \times (4^2)}{56+8}$	$\quad := \frac{14-2}{63-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{5396} := \frac{1^{42}}{5+(39-6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{639} := \frac{1 \times (4-2)}{6 \times 3 - 9}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times (4^2)}{6 \times (3+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{5680} := \frac{1 \times (4+2)}{5 \times (6 \times (8+0))}$
$\quad := \frac{1 \times (4+2)}{(6-3) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3905} := \frac{(1+4) \times 2}{(3 \times 90) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{6390} := \frac{1^{42}}{6+(39+0)}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{1 \times (4 + 2)}{(6 - 3) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{6958} & := \frac{1 \times (4 + 2)}{6 \times (9 + 5 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{((6 \times 9) - 5) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{37985} & := \frac{1 \times (4 - 2)}{3 - (7 \times (9 - 85))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{38695} & := \frac{1 \times (4^2)}{(3 + 869) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{57936} & := \frac{1 + 4 - 2}{(5 + 7 \times 9) \times 3 \times 6} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (4 + 2)}{(5 + 7 \times 9) \times 36} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{58930} & := \frac{1^{42}}{(5 \times 89) - 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{69580} & := \frac{1^{42}}{(6 \times 95) - 80} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{((6 \times 9) - 5) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{73059} & := \frac{1 \times (4 + 2)}{(7^{3+0 \times 5}) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{76538} & := \frac{1^{42}}{7 - (6 - 538)} \\ & := \frac{1 + 4 - 2}{((7 + 6) \times (5^3)) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{95637} & := \frac{1 \times (4 - 2)}{9 + (((5 + 6)^3) + 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{307856} & := \frac{1^{42}}{3^{07} - 8 - 5 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{358976} & := \frac{1 + 4 - 2}{(3 + (5 + 8) \times 97) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{386950} & := \frac{1 \times (4^2)}{(3 + 869) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{579360} & := \frac{1^4 + 2}{(5 + 7 \times 9) \times 3 \times 60} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 4 + 2}{(5 + 7 \times 9) \times 360} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{637580} & := \frac{1^4 + 2}{6 \times (3^7 + 58) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{142}{765380} & := \frac{1^4 + 2}{7 \times 6 \times (5 + 380)} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 143

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{208} & := \frac{14 - 3}{2 \times 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{286} & := \frac{1 + 4 - 3}{2^{8-6}} \\ & := \frac{1 + 4 + 3}{2 + 8 + 6} \\ & := \frac{1 + 43}{2 + 86} \\ & := \frac{14 - 3}{28 - 6} \\ & := \frac{14 + 3}{28 + 6} \\ & := \frac{(1 + 4)^3}{(2^8) - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{605} & := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{60 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{726} & := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{72 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{968} & := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{96 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2756} & := \frac{14 - 3}{2 + (7 \times 5 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2860} & := \frac{1^4 \times 3}{(2 + 8) \times (6 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{5928} & := \frac{14 - 3}{(59 - 2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{6578} & := \frac{1^4 + 3}{(6 \times 5 - 7) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{6875} & := \frac{1 + 4^3}{(6 - 8 + 7)^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{7865} & := \frac{1^{43}}{7 \times 8 - 6 + 5} \\ & := \frac{1^4 \times 3}{(7 + 8) \times (6 + 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{7956} & := \frac{14 - 3}{(7 + 95) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{26598} & := \frac{1 + 4 - 3}{(26 \times (5 + 9)) + 8} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (4 + 3)}{2 \times (659 - 8)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 3}{(26 + 5) \times (9 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{59280} & := \frac{14 - 3}{(59 - 2) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{65780} & := \frac{1^4 + 3}{(6 \times 5 - 7) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{67925} & := \frac{1^4 + 3}{((6 \times 7 \times 9) + 2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{68952} & := \frac{14 - 3}{6 \times ((8 + 9) \times 52)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{70928} & := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{(70 \times 92) + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{79560} & := \frac{14 - 3}{(7 + 95) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{87529} & := \frac{14 - 3}{((87 - 5)^2) + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{260975} & := \frac{1^4 \times 3}{(2^6 + 09) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{265980} & := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 3}{(26 + 5) \times 9 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{275968} & := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{2^7 \times (5 + 9) \times (6 + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{280956} &:= \frac{14-3}{(2+80 \times 9 \times 5) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{672958} &:= \frac{1^{43}}{(6+7) \times (2+9 \times 5 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{867295} &:= \frac{1^{43}}{(86 \times 7 \times 2+9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{296758} &:= \frac{1+4^3}{2+(9 \times 6+7^5) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{679250} &:= \frac{1^4+3}{(6 \times 7 \times 9+2) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{143}{769208} &:= \frac{1+4 \times 3}{76 \times 920+8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 145

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{638} &:= \frac{1+4+5}{6+38} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{7830} &:= \frac{1-4+5}{78+30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{89726} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{(8+9) \times (7 \times 26)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{290} &:= \frac{1 \times (4+5)}{2 \times (9+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{9628} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{9 \times 6^2+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{287390} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{(2+8)^{7-3}-90} \\ &:= \frac{1+45}{2+90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{9860} &:= \frac{1 \times (4+5)}{9 \times (8+60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{396720} &:= \frac{14+5}{(3 \times (9+67))^2+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2378} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{(2 \times 37)+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{26390} &:= \frac{1 \times (4+5)}{((2 \times 6)^3)-90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{897260} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{(8+9) \times 7 \times 260} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2639} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{2^6+3 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{27608} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{2 \times (7 \times (60+8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2697} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5}{2-(6-97)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{39208} &:= \frac{1 \times 45}{39^2 \times 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{6380} &:= \frac{1^{45}}{6+38+0} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 146

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{7592} &:= \frac{1^{46}}{((7 \times 5)-9) \times 2} & &:= \frac{1 \times 46}{((53-7)^2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{380257} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 6}{(-3+8) \times 02+5^7} \\ &:= \frac{1-4+6}{75+9^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{75920} &:= \frac{1^{46}}{((7 \times 5)-9) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{537280} &:= \frac{1^{46}}{(53+7)^2+80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{8395} &:= \frac{14-6}{(83+9) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{83950} &:= \frac{14-6}{(83+9) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{9782} &:= \frac{1^{46}}{9+(7 \times 8+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{97382} &:= \frac{1^{46}}{(9 \times 73)+8+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{53728} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 6}{5+(3^7+(2 \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 147

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{385} &:= \frac{14+7}{(3+8) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{693} &:= \frac{14-7}{6+9 \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2058} &:= \frac{1-4+7}{(2+05) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{539} &:= \frac{1+4+7}{5+39} & &:= \frac{14+7}{6+93} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3528} := \frac{1^{47}}{3 + (5 + (2 \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + 7)}{(35 - 2) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 7}{(2 + 5) \times 9 \times 308}$
$:= \frac{14 - 7}{3 \times ((5 + 2) \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{50862} := \frac{1^{47}}{((50 + 8) \times 6) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{295680} := \frac{1 \times (4 \times 7)}{2^9 \times (5 \times 6 + 80)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + 7)}{3 + (5 + (2^8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{52983} := \frac{14 - 7}{(5 \times (2^9 - 8)) + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{308259} := \frac{1^{47}}{(30 \times 8 - 2 - 5) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3850} := \frac{14 + 7}{(3 + 8) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{59682} := \frac{1^{47}}{((5 \times 9 + 6) \times 8) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{358092} := \frac{1^{47}}{3 \times (5 + 809 - 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3906} := \frac{14 + 7}{(3 + 90) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{89250} := \frac{14 - 7}{(8 + 9) \times 250}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{508326} := \frac{1^{47}}{(50 + 83) \times 26}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{8526} := \frac{1^4 + 7}{8 \times (52 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{95823} := \frac{14 - 7}{9 \times (((5 + 8)^2) \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{586329} := \frac{14 \times 7}{5^8 + (6 + 3) \times 29}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{8925} := \frac{14 - 7}{(8 + 9) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{208593} := \frac{1 \times (4 + 7)}{-2 \times 08 + 5^{9-3}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{692853} := \frac{14 + 7}{((6 + 9)^2 + 8^5) \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{20895} := \frac{14 - 7}{(208 - 9) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{239568} := \frac{14 - 7}{23 \times (9 \times 56 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{958230} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{9 \times (5 + 8)^2 \times 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{35280} := \frac{1^{47}}{3 \times (5 \times (2 \times 8 + 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{253869} := \frac{1^{47}}{2 - 5 \times (3 - 8) \times 69}$	
$:= \frac{14 - 7}{3 \times ((5 + 2) \times 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{259308} := \frac{1^{47}}{2 + 59 \times 30 - 8}$	

• Numerator 148

$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{296} := \frac{1 + 48}{2 + 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{23976} := \frac{1^{48}}{2 \times (39 + 7 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{14 - 8}{(3 + 759) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{14 - 8}{2 \times 9 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{32560} := \frac{1^{48}}{(32 \times 5) + 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{37629} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{((3 \times 76) - 2) \times 9}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + 8)}{2 \times 9 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{35076} := \frac{1^{48}}{(3^{5+0 \times 7}) - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{37925} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{(3 + 79) \times 25}$
$:= \frac{1 + 4 \times 8}{(2 + 9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{37296} := \frac{1^{48}}{3 \times ((7 - 2 + 9) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{62937} := \frac{1 \times 48}{(6 - 2) \times ((9^3) \times 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{592} := \frac{1 + 48}{(5 + 9)^2}$	$:= \frac{14 - 8}{((37^{-2}) + 9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{67932} := \frac{1^{48}}{(6 \times 7 + 9) \times 3^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{962} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{9 \times 6 - 2}$	$:= \frac{1^4 + 8}{3 \times (7 \times (2 \times 9 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{69375} := \frac{(1 + 4) \times 8}{6 \times ((9 + 3 - 7)^5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2960} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 8}{(2 + 9) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{1^{48}}{3 \times (((7 \times 2)^9) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + 8)}{(6 + 9) \times 375}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{3256} := \frac{1^{48}}{3 + (25 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{37592} := \frac{1^{48}}{(3 \times (75 + 9)) + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{79365} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{(7 \times 9 + 3) \times 65}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{9657} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{9 \times (65 - 7)}$		

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{90576} := \frac{1^{48}}{(90+5+7) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{372960} := \frac{1^{48}}{3 \times (7-2+9) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{379250} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{(3+79) \times 250} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{97236} := \frac{1^{48}}{9+(72 \times (3+6))} & := \frac{1^4+8}{3 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{693750} := \frac{1 \times (4+8)}{6 \times 9375+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{290376} := \frac{1^{48}}{(290+37) \times 6} & := \frac{1^{48}}{3 \times (7 \times 2)^9 \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{793650} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{(7 \times 9+3) \times 650} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{302956} := \frac{14-8}{3 \times (-02+(9-5)^6)} & := \frac{14-8}{(3^{7-2}+9) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{972360} := \frac{1^{48}}{9+(7+2) \times 3^6+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{306952} := \frac{1^4+8}{306 \times (9+52)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{375920} := \frac{14-8}{(3+759) \times 20} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{307692} := \frac{1^{48}}{3^{07}-6 \times 9 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{376290} := \frac{1^4 \times 8}{(3 \times 76-2) \times 90} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 149

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{3278} := \frac{1^{49}}{3+(27-8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{6258} := \frac{1-4+9}{6 \times (2+5 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{37250} := \frac{1^{49}}{(3+7) \times (25+0)} \\ & := \frac{14-9}{32+78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{6705} := \frac{1^4+9}{6 \times (70+5)} & := \frac{1^4+9}{(3+7) \times 250} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{3576} := \frac{1^4 \times 9}{3 \times ((5+7) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{35760} := \frac{1^4 \times 9}{3 \times ((5+7) \times 60)} & := \frac{1+(4 \times 9)}{37 \times 250} \\ & := \frac{1+4+9}{(3+5) \times 7 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{280567} := \frac{1^{49}}{(280-5-6) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{3725} := \frac{1^{49}}{((3+7) \times 2)+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{36207} := \frac{1^{49}}{3^{6 \times 2-07}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{367285} := \frac{1^{49}}{(3+(6+7) \times 2) \times 85} \\ & := \frac{1^4+9}{(3+7) \times 25} & \\ & := \frac{1+(4 \times 9)}{37 \times 25} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 150

$$\begin{array}{ll} \blacktriangleright \frac{150}{297} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2+97} & \blacktriangleright \frac{150}{27864} := \frac{1 \times 50}{27 \times 86 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{150}{432} := \frac{1 \times 50}{(4 \times 3)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{150}{62394} := \frac{1 \times 50}{62+(3+9)^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{150}{27648} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2^7 \times (6 \times (4+8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{150}{84672} := \frac{1 \times 50}{((8-4) \times (6 \times 7))^2} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 152

$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{304} := \frac{15-2}{30-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3876} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{(3 \times (8+7)) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{38760} := \frac{1^{52}}{(3 \times 87) - (6+0)}$
$:= \frac{15+2}{30+4}$	$:= \frac{1+5-2}{(3 \times 8-7) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1+5-2}{(3 \times 8-7) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{608} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{6 \times 08}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2}{(3 \times 87) - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{39748} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{3 - ((9-74) \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{15-2}{60-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{6384} := \frac{1^{52}}{6 \times (3+8-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{40736} := \frac{1^{52}}{4 \times (0+(73-6))}$
$:= \frac{15+2}{60+8}$	$:= \frac{1+5-2}{6 \times (3 \times 8+4)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2}{40 \times (73-6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{684} := \frac{1+5-2}{6+8+4}$	$:= \frac{(1+5)^2}{6 \times (3 \times 84)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{47690} := \frac{1 \times 52}{(4^7) - (69+0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{836} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{8-3+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{6498} := \frac{1+5+2}{6 \times (49+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{63840} := \frac{(1+5)^2}{6 \times (3 \times 840)}$
$:= \frac{1+5+2}{8+36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{6840} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{6+(84+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{73986} := \frac{1+5+2}{((73 \times 9) - 8) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(8+3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{7980} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{7+(98+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{89376} := \frac{1^{52}}{(8+(9 \times (3+7))) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3078} := \frac{1+5-2}{3-(0-78)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{8360} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(8+3) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{349068} := \frac{1+5+2}{3 \times (4+90 \times 68)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3496} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{3+(49-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{8436} := \frac{1+5+2}{8+436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{387904} := \frac{1 \times (5-2)}{3 \times (8+7 \times 90) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (5-2)}{((3+4) \times 9) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{36480} := \frac{1^{52}}{3 \times ((6+4) \times (8+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{438976} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{4 \times 38^{9-7} \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3648} := \frac{1^{52}}{36-(4+8)}$	$:= \frac{1^5 \times 2}{3 \times ((6-4) \times 80)}$	$:= \frac{(1+5)^2}{4 \times 38 \times 9 \times 76}$
$:= \frac{1^5 \times 2}{3 \times ((6-4) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (5-2)}{(3^{6-4}) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 5-2}{4 \times 38 \times (9 \times 7-6)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (5-2)}{(3^{6-4}) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2}{3 \times ((6+4) \times 80)}$	$:= \frac{1^{52}}{4 \times (38+9 \times 76)}$
$:= \frac{1+5-2}{3 \times (6 \times 4+8)}$	$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(3+6) \times (4 \times 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{463790} := \frac{1+5-2}{4^6 \times 3+7-90}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (5+2)}{3 \times (64-8)}$	$:= \frac{(1+5)^2}{3 \times (6 \times 480)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{786904} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{(7+8) \times 690+4}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2}{3 \times ((6+4) \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{36784} := \frac{1^{52}}{3 \times 6+(7 \times 8 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{893760} := \frac{1^{52}}{(8+9 \times (3+7)) \times 60}$
$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(3+6) \times 4 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (5-2)}{(3^6) - (7-8+4)}$	
$:= \frac{(1+5)^2}{3 \times (6 \times 48)}$		

• Numerator 153

$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{476} := \frac{1+53}{4 \times 7 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{8976} := \frac{1+5-3}{8 \times (9+7+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{247860} := \frac{1 \times (5-3)}{(2-4+7 \times 8) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{204} := \frac{15-3}{2^{04}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{24786} := \frac{1 \times (5-3)}{(2-(4-(7 \times 8))) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{264078} := \frac{1+5-3}{2+(640+7) \times 8}$
$\quad := \frac{15+3}{20+4}$	$\quad := \frac{1+5-3}{2+(478+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{268974} := \frac{1^5+3}{2+(6+89) \times 74}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{289} := \frac{15+3}{2 \times (8+9)}$	$\quad := \frac{1+5+3}{2 \times ((4+7-8)^6)}$	$\quad := \frac{1^{53}}{2+(6 \times 8 \times 9+7) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{408} := \frac{15-3}{4 \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{27846} := \frac{1^{53}}{2^7+(8+46)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{279684} := \frac{1+5-3}{2 \times 7^{9-6} \times 8-4}$
$\quad := \frac{15+3}{40+8}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times (5-3)}{2 \times (7 \times ((8 \times 4)-6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{287946} := \frac{1^{53}}{28 \times (7 \times 9+4)+6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{629} := \frac{1+5^3}{6+(2^9)}$	$\quad := \frac{15 \times 3}{2 \times (7-(8-(4^6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{289476} := \frac{1+5-3}{2-8+947 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{748} := \frac{15+3}{(7+4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{27948} := \frac{1+5+3}{(2^7+9) \times (4+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{296480} := \frac{1+5+3}{(2+9 \times 6 \times 4) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{4692} := \frac{1+5-3}{((4+6) \times 9)+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{28764} := \frac{1^{53}}{2 \times (((8+7) \times 6)+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{462978} := \frac{1 \times (5-3)}{4+6 \times 2 \times 9 \times 7 \times 8}$
$\quad := \frac{15+3}{4 \times (69 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{29648} := \frac{1+5+3}{(2+(9 \times 6 \times 4)) \times 8}$	$\quad := \frac{1^{53}}{4+6 \times (2^9-7)-8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{4760} := \frac{1+53}{4 \times (7 \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{42687} := \frac{1^{53}}{4+(268+7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{468792} := \frac{1^{53}}{4 \times 6 \times 8 \times (7+9)-2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{4862} := \frac{1+5+3}{(48 \times 6)-2}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times 5-3}{(4+2) \times (6+87)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{470628} := \frac{1^{53}}{470 \times 6+2^8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{4896} := \frac{1+5-3}{4 \times (8 \times (9-6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{46920} := \frac{1+5-3}{(4+6) \times (92+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{480726} := \frac{1^5+3}{4 \times ((8 \times 07)^2+6)}$
$\quad := \frac{1^5+3}{4 \times 8+96}$	$\quad := \frac{15+3}{4 \times (69 \times 20)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{689724} := \frac{1^{53}}{(6+8+9) \times 7^2 \times 4}$
$\quad := \frac{1 \times (5 \times 3)}{4 \times (8 \times (9+6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{48960} := \frac{1+53}{4 \times (8 \times (9 \times 60))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{742968} := \frac{1 \times (5+3)}{(7^4 \times 2+9 \times 6) \times 8}$
$\quad := \frac{1+53}{4 \times (8 \times 9 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{64872} := \frac{1^{53}}{(6^4)-872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{847926} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{8+4^7+9 \times 26}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{7480} := \frac{15+3}{(7+4) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{89267} := \frac{1+5+3}{((8 \times 9)^2)+67}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{8704} := \frac{1+5+3}{8^{7-04}}$		

• Numerator 154

$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{308} := \frac{15-4}{30-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{9072} := \frac{15-4}{9 \times (0+72)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{297360} := \frac{15-4}{(2+9+7^3) \times 60}$
$\quad := \frac{15+4}{30+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{9702} := \frac{1^{54}}{9 \times (7+0 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{298760} := \frac{1 \times (5+4)}{(298-7) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{693} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{6+9+3}$	$\quad := \frac{1+5-4}{9 \times (7 \times 01)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{307692} := \frac{1 \times (5+4)}{(30+7) \times 6 \times 9^2}$
$\quad := \frac{1+5+4}{(6+9) \times 3}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 4}{9 \times (70 \times 2)}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times 54}{(30+7) \times (6 \times 9)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{2387} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{2 \times (38-7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{29736} := \frac{15-4}{(2+(9+7^3)) \times 6}$	$\quad := \frac{1+5-4}{(30+7) \times 6 \times 9 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{3276} := \frac{15-4}{3 \times (2+76)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{29876} := \frac{1^{54}}{2 \times (98-7+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{327096} := \frac{1+5-4}{3 \times 2 \times 709-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{3927} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{3+(92+7)}$	$\quad := \frac{1 \times (5+4)}{(298-7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{370986} := \frac{1+5-4}{(3+70) \times (9 \times 8-6)}$
$\quad := \frac{1+5+4}{3 \times (92-7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{32760} := \frac{15-4}{(32+7) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{372960} := \frac{15-4}{(3+7^2 \times 9) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{6930} := \frac{1^{54}}{6+(9+30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{36729} := \frac{1+5-4}{36+(7^2 \times 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{379680} := \frac{15-4}{(37 \times 9+6) \times 80}$
$\quad := \frac{1+5+4}{(6+9) \times 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{37268} := \frac{1^{54}}{(3 \times (72+6)) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{387926} := \frac{1+5-4}{3+(8+7 \times 9)^2-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{7238} := \frac{1^{54}}{7+(2+38)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{37296} := \frac{15-4}{(3+(7^2 \times 9)) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{678293} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{6 \times 7+(8+2 \times 9)^3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{7392} := \frac{1^{54}}{7+(39+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{37968} := \frac{15-4}{((37 \times 9)+6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{692307} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{6 \times 9^2 \times (30+7)}$
$\quad := \frac{1+5-4}{7-(3-92)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{39270} := \frac{1^{54}}{3 \times (92-7+0)}$	$\quad := \frac{(1+5) \times 4}{(6 \times 9)^2 \times (30+7)}$
$\quad := \frac{1+5 \times 4}{7 \times ((3+9)^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{76923} := \frac{1+5-4}{76+923}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{809732} := \frac{1^{54}}{8 \times 09 \times 73+2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{7623} := \frac{1+5-4}{76+23}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{96382} := \frac{1+5 \times 4}{9+((6+(3^8)) \times 2)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{8932} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{8 \times (9 \times 3+2)}$		

• Numerator 156

$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{208} := \frac{1+5+6}{2 \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{234} := \frac{1-5+6}{2-3+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{702} := \frac{1-5+6}{7+02}$
$\quad := \frac{15+6}{20+8}$	$\quad := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{2+3+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{832} := \frac{15-6}{8 \times 3 \times 2}$
$\quad := \frac{15-6}{20-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{429} := \frac{1+5+6}{4+29}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2834} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{28+3^4}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3289} := \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{(3 \times 2^8) - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{39728} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{((3 \times 9 \times 7) + 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{473928} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{4 \times 7 \times (3 + 9^2 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{4329} := \frac{1+5+6}{4+329}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{43290} := \frac{1-5+6}{43+2^9+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{489723} := \frac{1+5+6}{4 \times (8+97^2) + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{8320} := \frac{15-6}{8 \times 3 \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{72930} := \frac{1-5+6}{7-2+930}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{704392} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{70 \times 43 \times 9 + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{9048} := \frac{1^{56}}{90 - (4 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{78234} := \frac{1-5+6}{7 + (((8+2)^3) - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{937248} := \frac{1^{56}}{(9 \times 3 + 724) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{30784} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{(30+7) \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{79248} := \frac{1-5+6}{(7 \times (9 \times 2^4)) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{978432} := \frac{1^{56}}{(9+7) \times 8 \times (4+3)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{37284} := \frac{1^{56}}{(3^{7-2}) - 8 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{94380} := \frac{1 \times (5+6)}{94 + (3^8 + 0)}$	$:= \frac{1^5 + 6}{(9+7+8+4)^3 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{37492} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 6}{(3 \times (7^4)) + 9 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{293748} := \frac{1-5+6}{2 \times 9 + 3748}$	$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{9 \times 784 \times 32}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{37908} := \frac{15-6}{3^7 \times (9-08)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{397280} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{(3 \times 9 \times 7 + 2) \times 80}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{437892} := \frac{1^5 + 6}{(4 + 3^7 - 8) \times 9 + 2}$	

• Numerator 157

$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{628} := \frac{1^{57}}{6 \times 2 - 8}$	$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{42 \times 3 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{24806} := \frac{1-5+7}{((2+4) \times 80) - 6}$
$:= \frac{1^5 \times 7}{6^2 - 8}$	$:= \frac{1+5+7}{(42-3) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{24963} := \frac{1^{57}}{(2 \times ((4+9) \times 6)) + 3}$
$:= \frac{15-7}{(6-2) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1-5+7}{(4+2+3) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{29830} := \frac{1^{57}}{2 \times (98-3+0)}$
$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{6 \times 28}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{4396} := \frac{1^{57}}{43 - (9+6)}$	$:= \frac{1-5+7}{(2+9+8) \times 30}$
$:= \frac{1-5+7}{6-2+8}$	$:= \frac{1-5+7}{4 \times (3 \times 9 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{42390} := \frac{1^{57}}{(4+2-3) \times 90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{942} := \frac{1 \times (5+7)}{9 \times 4 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{6280} := \frac{15-7}{(6-2) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{15-7}{4 \times (2 \times (3 \times 90))}$
$:= \frac{1-5+7}{9 \times (4-2)}$	$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{6 \times 280}$	$:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{42 \times (3 \times 90)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{2983} := \frac{1-5+7}{(2+9+8) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{9420} := \frac{1 \times (5+7)}{9 \times (4 \times 20)}$	$:= \frac{1+5+7}{(42-3) \times 90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{4239} := \frac{1^{57}}{(4+2-3) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{23864} := \frac{1^{57}}{2 \times (38 \times (6-4))}$	$:= \frac{1-5+7}{(4+2+3) \times 90}$
$:= \frac{15-7}{4 \times (2 \times 3 \times 9)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (5+7)}{2 \times (38 \times 6 \times 4)}$	

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{157}{96084} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 7}{9 \times ((60 \times 8) - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{157}{238640} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + 7)}{2 \times 38 \times 6 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{157}{326089} &:= \frac{1 - 5 + 7}{3 \times 260 \times 8 - 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{157}{362984} &:= \frac{1^{57}}{(36 - 2) \times (9 + 8) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{157}{634280} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 + 7}{(6^3 + 4)^2 + 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{863029} := \frac{1^{57}}{(8 + 6)^3 \times 02 + 9}$$

• Numerator 158

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{158}{237} &:= \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{2 - 3 + 7} \\ &:= \frac{1^5 \times 8}{2 + 3 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{158}{632} &:= \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{6 \times 3 - 2} \\ &:= \frac{1^5 + 8}{6 \times 3 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times 8}{6 \times 32} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2370} := \frac{1^{58}}{2^3 + 7 + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{158}{3476} &:= \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{3 \times 4 + 76} \\ &:= \frac{1^5 + 8}{3 \times ((4 + 7) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{158}{3792} &:= \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{3 \times ((7 + 9) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1^{58}}{(3 \times 7 - 9) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{158}{6320} &:= \frac{1^5 + 8}{6 \times 3 \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times 8}{6 \times 320} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{32706} := \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{3 \times (270 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{34760} := \frac{1^5 + 8}{3 \times ((4 + 7) \times 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{36024} := \frac{1^{58}}{3 \times (60 + 2^4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{36972} := \frac{1^{58}}{3 \times (69 + 7 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{37920} := \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{3 \times ((7 + 9) \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{58}}{(3 \times 7 - 9) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{79632} := \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{(7 + 9) \times (63 \times 2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 + 5 + 8}{(7 \times (9 + 6 - 3))^2} \\ &:= \frac{1^5 \times 8}{7 \times (96 \times 3 \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{270496} := \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{2 \times (70 \times 49 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{293406} := \frac{1 - 5 + 8}{2 \times (93 \times 40 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{294670} := \frac{15 - 8}{2 \times 9^4 - 67 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{324769} := \frac{1^5 \times 8}{3 \times 2 + 4^7 + 6 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{369720} := \frac{1^{58}}{36 \times (9 \times 7 + 2) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{796320} := \frac{1^5 \times 8}{7 \times 96 \times 3 \times 20}$$

• Numerator 159

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{742} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 9}{7 \times (4 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{15 + 9}{7 \times (4^2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{2067} := \frac{1 \times (5 + 9)}{(20 + 6) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{2703} := \frac{1^{59}}{(2 \times (7 + 0)) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{3286} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{(3 + 28) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{7632} := \frac{1^{59}}{7 \times 6 + 3 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{27348} := \frac{15 - 9}{((2^7) - 3 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{30846} := \frac{1^{59}}{30 \times 8 - 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{32860} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{(3 + 28) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{34768} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{(34 + 7) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{37206} := \frac{1^{59}}{3 \times (72 + 06)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{37842} := \frac{1^{59}}{((3 + (7 \times 8)) \times 4) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{40863} := \frac{1^{59}}{(40 \times 8) - 63}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{47382} &:= \frac{1^{59}}{(4 \times 73) + 8 - 2} \\ &:= \frac{15 - 9}{(47 \times 38) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{60738} &:= \frac{1^{59}}{(60 \times 7) - 38} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{64872} &:= \frac{1^{59}}{6 \times (4 - (8 - 72))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times 9}{(6^4) \times (8 + 7 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - 5 + 9}{6 \times (4 \times (87 - 2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{70384} &:= \frac{15 - 9}{(70 \times 38) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{73246} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times 9)}{((7 + 3 + 2)^4) - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{86072} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 9}{8 \times (607 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{203467} &:= \frac{15 - 9}{20^3 - 46 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{237864} &:= \frac{1^{59}}{(2 + 378 - 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{273480} &:= \frac{15 - 9}{(2^7 - 3 + 4) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{280476} &:= \frac{15 - 9}{(2^8 - 04) \times 7 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{347680} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 9}{(34 + 7) \times 6 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{374286} &:= \frac{1^{59}}{3 + 7^4 - 2 - 8 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{473820} &:= \frac{1^{59}}{(47 \times 3 + 8) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{634728} &:= \frac{1^{59}}{6^3 + 472 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 162

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{405} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{4 \times 05} \\ &:= \frac{16 - 2}{40 - 5} \\ &:= \frac{16 + 2}{40 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{7938} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 2}{7 \times (9 - 3 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 6 - 2}{7 \times (9 \times 3 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 6)^2}{7^{9+3-8}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{34587} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 2}{(3 + 4) \times (5 + 8 \times 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{35478} &:= \frac{1^{62}}{3 + ((5 \times 4 + 7) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{37098} &:= \frac{1^{62}}{(3 \times (70 + 9)) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{37584} &:= \frac{1^{62}}{(((3 + 7) \times 5) + 8) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 6^2}{37 \times (58 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{37854} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{3^7 - (8 - (5^4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{37890} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 2}{3^7 + (8 - 90)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{53784} &:= \frac{1^{62}}{((5 + 37) \times 8) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{54837} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 2}{5 + (4 \times (8 \times (3 \times 7)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{58473} &:= \frac{16 + 2}{(5 + 84) \times 73} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{73584} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 2}{7 - (3 \times 5 - 8^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{85374} &:= \frac{1 + 6 - 2}{85 \times (3 + 7 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{345780} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 2}{34 \times (5 + 7 \times 80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{375840} &:= \frac{1^{62}}{(3 + 7) \times 58 \times 4 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{375840} &:= \frac{1 + 6^2}{37 \times 58 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{375894} &:= \frac{1^6 + 2}{(3 + 7) \times 5 \times 8 + 9^4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{394875} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 2}{39 \times (4 \times 8 - 7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{394875} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{3 \times (9^4 - 8 \times 7 - 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{394875} &:= \frac{16 - 2}{3 \times (9 + 4) \times 875} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{397458} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 2}{3^9 + 7^4 + 5 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{539487} &:= \frac{16 + 2}{53 \times (9 + 4) \times 87} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{539784} &:= \frac{1^6 + 2}{(5 + 3 + 9) \times 7 \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{548937} &:= \frac{1 \times 6^2}{54 \times (8 \times 9 + 3^7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{584730} &:= \frac{16 + 2}{(5 + 84) \times 730} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{162}{875934} &:= \frac{1^{62}}{8 \times 75 \times 9 + 3 + 4} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 163

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{489} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{4+8-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{27058} &:= \frac{16-3}{78 \times 2 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{87205} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{(87+20) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{16-3}{48-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{54279} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{2 \times (70+5+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{409782} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{40 \times 9 \times 7 - 8 + 2} \\ &:= \frac{1+(6 \times 3)}{48+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{542790} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{((5 \times (4+2))+7) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{542790} &:= \frac{1^6+3}{(5 \times 4 + 2^7) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{978} &:= \frac{1+6-3}{9+7+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{542790} &:= \frac{1+6-3}{(5 \times 4 + (2^7)) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{542790} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{(5 \times (4+2)+7) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{4075} &:= \frac{1 \times (6-3)}{40+(7 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{78240} &:= \frac{16-3}{78 \times (2 \times 40)} & & \\ &:= \frac{1+63}{40^{7-5}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{85249} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{8+(524-9)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{163}{7824} &:= \frac{1^{63}}{7 \times 8 - 2 \times 4} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 164

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{205} &:= \frac{16-4}{20-5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2378} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{2 \times (37-8)} & & := \frac{1^{64}}{7+(38+0)} \\ &:= \frac{16+4}{20+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2583} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{2+(58+3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{23780} &:= \frac{1+6-4}{(2+3) \times (7+80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{287} &:= \frac{1 \times 64}{2 \times 8 \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2870} &:= \frac{1 \times 64}{2 \times (8 \times 70)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{23985} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(2+3) \times (9 \times (8+5))} \\ &:= \frac{16-4}{28-7} & & := \frac{1 \times 6-4}{28+7+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{25789} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(2+5 \times 7) \times (8+9)} \\ &:= \frac{16+4}{28+7} & & := \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(2+8) \times (7+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{37925} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{((3+7) \times 92) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{328} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(3-2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{3075} &:= \frac{16-4}{3 \times (0+75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{38950} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-4}{3+(8 \times (9+50))} \\ &:= \frac{16-4}{32-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{3280} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-4}{32+8+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{39852} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-4}{3 \times (9 \times (8+5 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{16+4}{32+8} & & := \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(3-2) \times 80} & & := \frac{1^{64}}{3 \times (9 \times ((8-5)^2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{3 \times 2 \times 8} & & := \frac{16+4}{(3+2) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{53792} &:= \frac{1^{64}}{(5 \times (3+7 \times 9)) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{738} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{7+3+8} & & := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{3 \times (2 \times 80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{59327} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(5 \times (9 \times 32)) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6+4)}{7+38} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{7298} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-4}{72+9+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{72980} &:= \frac{1^{64}}{(7-2) \times (9+80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{820} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-4}{8+2+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{7380} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-4}{7+3+80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{89257} &:= \frac{16-4}{(8+925) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{902} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-4}{9+02} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{92537} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(9 \times (2 \times (5^3))) + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{93275} &:= \frac{16 - 4}{(93 - 2) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{97580} &:= \frac{1^{64}}{(9 \times 75) - 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{379250} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{(3 + 7) \times 925 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{398520} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 - 4}{3^{(9-8) \times 5} \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{164}{538207} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 4}{5 + 3^8 \times 2 + 0 \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times 4}{(5 + 3^8 \times 2) \times 07} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{578920} := \frac{1^{64}}{5 \times 78 \times 9 + 20}$$

• Numerator 165

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{240} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + 5)}{2^4 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{480} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + 5)}{4 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{924} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(9 - 2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{2904} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{2 + (90 - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{2970} &:= \frac{1^{65}}{2 + (9 + 7 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 6 - 5}{29 + 7 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{3240} &:= \frac{1 + 65}{(3 \times 2)^4 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{3498} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{34 + 9 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{3894} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{3 \times 8 + 94} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{9240} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(9 - 2) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{9720} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + 5)}{9 \times (72 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{9834} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(98 \times 3) + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{23790} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + 5)}{2 \times (3 + 790)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{70983} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(709 + 8) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{97284} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(9 + 728) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{287430} &:= \frac{1^{65}}{2 \times (874 - 3) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{165}{972840} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(9 + 728) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 167

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{835} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 7}{8 - 3 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{4509} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 7}{45 + 09} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{9352} &:= \frac{16 - 7}{(9 + (3^5)) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{2839} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{2 + ((8 \times 3) - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 7}{28 - 3 + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{25384} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{((2 \times (5 \times 3)) + 8) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1^6 \times 7}{2 \times (((5^3) + 8) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{29058} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{2 \times (90 + 5 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 7}{290 + 58} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{39245} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{(3 + ((9 + 2) \times 4)) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{84502} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{8 - (4 - 502)} \\ &:= \frac{1^6 + 7}{8 \times (4 + 502)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{93520} &:= \frac{16 - 7}{(9 + (3^5)) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{253840} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 7}{2 \times (5^3 + 8) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{1^{67}}{2 \times 5 \times 38 \times 4 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{258349} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{(2 \times 58 + 3) \times (4 + 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{348529} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{3 - 4 \times (8 - 529)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{392450} &:= \frac{1^{67}}{(3 + (9 + 2) \times 4) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 168

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{240} := \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{2 \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{294} := \frac{16-8}{2 \times 9-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{297} := \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{2+97} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{324} := \frac{1 \times 6+8}{3+24} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{392} := \frac{1^6+8}{3 \times (9-2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{432} := \frac{1 \times 6+8}{4+32} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{(4 \times 3)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{504} := \frac{1-6+8}{5+04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{540} := \frac{1 \times 6+8}{5+40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{735} := \frac{16+8}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{7 \times 35} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{924} := \frac{16-8}{(9+2) \times 4} \\
 \qquad := \frac{1 \times 6+8}{9^2-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{972} := \frac{1 \times 6+8}{9+72} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2079} := \frac{16-8}{20+79} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3024} := \frac{1-6+8}{30+24} \\
 \qquad := \frac{1^{68}}{3 \times (0+2+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3402} := \frac{16-8}{(3^4+0) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3472} := \frac{1-6+8}{(3+(4 \times 7)) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{4032} := \frac{1-6+8}{40+32} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{4725} := \frac{16-8}{(47-2) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{7035} := \frac{16-8}{(70-3) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{7350} := \frac{16+8}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{7 \times 350} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{7392} := \frac{168}{7+(39-2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{9072} := \frac{1-6+8}{90+72} \\
 \qquad := \frac{1+6+8}{90 \times (7+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{9240} := \frac{16-8}{(9+2) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{9375} := \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{(9+3-7)^5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{9345} := \frac{16-8}{(93-4) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{30492} := \frac{16+8}{(30+(4 \times 9))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{34209} := \frac{16-8}{(3^4 \times 20)+9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{34720} := \frac{1-6+8}{(3+(4 \times 7)) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{35427} := \frac{16-8}{(3^5-4+2) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3924} := \frac{1 \times 6+8}{3+(9^2 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{45927} := \frac{16-8}{(4+5) \times 9 \times 27} \\
 \qquad := \frac{16+8}{(4+5)^{9+2-7}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{47250} := \frac{16-8}{(47-2) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{49257} := \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{(4^9-2)+5 \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{59472} := \frac{1-6+8}{59 \times (4+7 \times 2)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{59 \times (4 \times 72)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{74592} := \frac{1+6+8}{74 \times (5 \times 9 \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{93072} := \frac{1^{68}}{((9 \times 30)+7) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{93450} := \frac{16-8}{(93-4) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{94752} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{9 \times (4 \times 752)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{16+8}{94 \times ((7+5)^2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{235704} := \frac{1^{68}}{23 \times (57+04)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{345072} := \frac{1^{68}}{(3+4^{5+0 \times 7}) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{352947} := \frac{16 \times 8}{((3-5) \times (2-9))^4 \times 7} \\
 \qquad := \frac{16-8}{((3+5) \times 2-9)^4 \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{354270} := \frac{16-8}{(3^5-4+2) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{357042} := \frac{16-8}{3^5 \times 70-4 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{374592} := \frac{1 \times 6+8}{3-7^4 \times (5-9 \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{394527} := \frac{16-8}{3^9-4^5+2^7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{395472} := \frac{1^{68}}{3-9+5 \times 472} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{168}{435792} := \frac{1^{68}}{4-35 \times (7-9^2)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{459270} := \frac{16 - 8}{(4 + 5) \times 9 \times 270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{594720} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{59 \times 4 \times 720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{709524} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{70 + 9^5 + 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{745920} := \frac{1 + 6 + 8}{74 \times 5 \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{947520} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{9 \times 4 \times 7520}$$

• Numerator 169

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{507} := \frac{1 - 6 + 9}{5 + 07}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{845} := \frac{1 - 6 + 9}{(8 - 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{2704} := \frac{1^6 \times 9}{(2 \times 70) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{2873} := \frac{1^6 + 9}{2 + (8 \times 7 \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{3042} := \frac{1^{69}}{3 \times (0 + (4 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 6 + 9}{30 + 42}$$

$$:= \frac{1^6 \times 9}{(3^{04}) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1^6 + 9}{30 \times (4 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{16 - 9}{3 \times (0 + 42)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 69}{30 \times 42}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{4732} := \frac{1^{69}}{4 \times (7^{3-2})}$$

$$:= \frac{1^6 \times 9}{4 \times (7 \times 3^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{16 - 9}{(4 + 7 + 3)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times 9}{4 \times ((7 \times 3)^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{8450} := \frac{1 - 6 + 9}{(8 - 4) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{28054} := \frac{1^{69}}{(2 \times (80 + 5)) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{28730} := \frac{1^{69}}{2 + (8 \times (7 \times (3 + 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{30758} := \frac{1 \times (6 + 9)}{30 \times (7 \times (5 + 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{47320} := \frac{1^{69}}{(4 + 7 + 3) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{53742} := \frac{1^{69}}{53 \times ((7 - 4) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{16 - 9}{53 \times (7 \times (4 + 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{283075} := \frac{1^{69}}{(28 + 307) \times 5}$$

• Numerator 170

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{935} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{9 + 35}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{3825} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{(38 - 2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{9435} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{9 + 435}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{28356} := \frac{1 \times 70}{(2 + (8 \times 3^5)) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{29835} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{2 \times (9 \times (83 - 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{46325} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{(4 + ((6^3) \times 2)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{63495} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{6 \times (3 + 495)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{98345} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{(9 \times (8^3)) + 4 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{469285} := \frac{1 + 7 + 0}{4 + 6 \times 92 \times 8 \times 5}$$

• Numerator 172

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{645} := \frac{1 \times 72}{6 \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{946} := \frac{1^7 \times 2}{9 - 4 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 7 - 2}{9 + 4 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 7 + 2}{9 + 46}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times 2}{94 - 6}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{3698} := \frac{1+7+2}{(3 \times 69) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{34658} := \frac{1^7 \times 2}{3 + ((4+6) \times (5 \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7-2)}{((6^3) \times 9) - 84}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{3956} := \frac{1^{72}}{3 + (9 + 5 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{35604} := \frac{1^{72}}{3 \times (5 + (60 + 4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{93568} := \frac{1^{72}}{(9 + (3 + 56)) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{1^7 + 2}{39 + 5 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{35948} := \frac{1^{72}}{(3 \times 59) + 4 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1^7 + 2}{(9 + 3 \times 5) \times 68}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{6450} := \frac{1 \times 72}{6 \times 450}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{36980} := \frac{1^{72}}{(3 \times 69) + 8 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7+2)}{9 \times ((3+5) \times 68)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{9460} := \frac{1^{72}}{9 + (46 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{40936} := \frac{1 \times (7+2)}{((40 \times 9) - 3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{95460} := \frac{1^{72}}{9 + (546 + 0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{9546} := \frac{1+7-2}{9 + (54 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{49536} := \frac{1^{72}}{4 \times (9 \times (5 - 3 + 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{389064} := \frac{1^{72}}{(3^8 - 906) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{1+7+2}{9 + 546}$	$:= \frac{1^7 \times 2}{4 \times ((9 + (5 \times 3)) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{495360} := \frac{1^7 \times 2}{4 \times (9 + 5 \times 3) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{3096} := \frac{1^{72}}{3 - (0 - (9 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{1+7-2}{4 \times (9 \times ((5+3) \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{693504} := \frac{1 \times (7+2)}{6 \times (9+3) \times 504}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7-2)}{30 \times (9-6)}$	$:= \frac{(1+7) \times 2}{(4^{9-5}) \times 3 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{935680} := \frac{1^7 + 2}{(9 + 3 \times 5) \times 680}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7+2)}{3 \times (0 + (9 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{50396} := \frac{1^{72}}{5 - (0 - (3 \times 96))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7+2)}{9 \times (3+5) \times 680}$
$:= \frac{(1+7) \times 2}{3 \times (0 + 96)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{59684} := \frac{1^{72}}{5 + (9 \times (6 + 8 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{1^{72}}{(9 + 3 + 56) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{34056} := \frac{1^7 \times 2}{340 + 56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{63984} := \frac{1^7 \times 2}{6 \times ((39 - 8) \times 4)}$	
$:= \frac{1^7 + 2}{(3 \times (40 \times 5)) - 6}$		

• Numerator 173

$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{692} := \frac{17-3}{(6 \times 9) + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{29064} := \frac{1^{73}}{(2-9) \times (0 - (6 \times 4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{85462} := \frac{1^{73}}{(8 \times 54) + 62}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{865} := \frac{17-3}{(8+6) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7-3)}{2 \times ((90-6) \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{826594} := \frac{1^7 + 3}{8 \times (265 \times 9 + 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{8650} := \frac{17-3}{(8+6) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{80964} := \frac{1+7 \times 3}{8 \times (0 - (9 - (6^4)))}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{25604} := \frac{1 \times (7-3)}{2 \times ((5 \times 60) - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{173}{82694} := \frac{1^{73}}{(8^2 \times 6) + 94}$	

• Numerator 174

$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{580} := \frac{1+7+4}{5 \times 8+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{28536} := \frac{1+7-4}{2 \times (8 \times (5+36))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{268395} := \frac{1+7-4}{(2+683) \times 9+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{638} := \frac{1 \times 7-4}{6-3+8}$	$:= \frac{1^{74}}{2 \times (85+3-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{285360} := \frac{1^{74}}{2^8 \times 5+360}$
$:= \frac{1+7+4}{6+38}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{29058} := \frac{1^{74}}{(2 \times 90)-(5+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{289536} := \frac{1^{74}}{2 \times (8+95+3^6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2958} := \frac{1 \times 7-4}{2-(9-58)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{29568} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{(2+9) \times 56 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1+7+4}{2^8 \times (9 \times (5+3)+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3596} := \frac{1 \times 7-4}{3+(5+(9 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{29580} := \frac{1^{74}}{(2 \times 9 \times 5)+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{295680} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{(2+9) \times 56 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{8236} := \frac{17+4}{((8+2)^3)-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{29638} := \frac{1 \times 7-4}{2^9-(6+3-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{305892} := \frac{1^{74}}{30 \times 58+9 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{8352} := \frac{(1+7) \times 4}{(8^3) \times (5-2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{30856} := \frac{1+7+4}{(30+8) \times 56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{586293} := \frac{1^7 \times 4}{(5 \times 8+6) \times 293}$
$:= \frac{1^7+4}{8 \times (3 \times 5 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{39528} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{3 \times 9+((5-2)^8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{590382} := \frac{1^7 \times 4}{5 \times 90+3^8 \times 2}$
$:= \frac{1^{74}}{8 \times (3+5-2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{50286} := \frac{1^{74}}{((5^{01})-8)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{658329} := \frac{1^7 \times 4}{(6+5 \times 8) \times 329}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{9802} := \frac{1 \times 7-4}{9+(80 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{83520} := \frac{1^7+4}{8 \times (3 \times (5 \times 20))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{836592} := \frac{1^{74}}{8 \times (3+6+592)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{25839} := \frac{1+7-4}{2+(583+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{92568} := \frac{1^{74}}{(9 \times (2 \times 5 \times 6))-8}$	

• Numerator 175

$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{630} := \frac{1^7 \times 5}{6 \times 3+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{349860} := \frac{1^7 \times 5}{3 \times 49 \times (8+60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{394260} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{3^9 \times 4+2 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{3024} := \frac{1 \times 75}{(3 \times 01)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{364280} := \frac{1^7 \times 5}{(3+6^4+2) \times 8+0}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{3690} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{(3^6)+9+0}$		

• Numerator 176

$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{352} := \frac{1+7+6}{3+5^2}$	$:= \frac{17-6}{5+28}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{4928} := \frac{(1+7)^6}{(4^9) \times 28}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{528} := \frac{1^7 \times 6}{5 \times 2+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2048} := \frac{17-6}{(2^{04}) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7+6)}{(4+9) \times 28}$
$:= \frac{1^7+6}{5+(2 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2904} := \frac{1+7-6}{29+04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{5280} := \frac{1+7-6}{52+8+0}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{5328} &:= \frac{17-6}{5+328} &:= \frac{1+7+6}{(235 \times 8) - 4} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 6}{(59-8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{5984} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 6}{(59-8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{29304} &:= \frac{1+7-6}{29+304} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{83952} &:= \frac{1^7}{((8-3) \times 95) + 2} \\ &:= \frac{1+7+6}{(59 \times 8) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{39248} &:= \frac{1^7}{(3 \times (9^2 - 4)) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{529408} &:= \frac{1 \times (7+6)}{52 \times 94 \times 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{8352} &:= \frac{17-6}{(8^3) + 5 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{49280} &:= \frac{(1+7)^6}{(4^9) \times 280} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{958320} &:= \frac{1^7}{9 \times 5 \times (8+3)^2 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{9328} &:= \frac{1^7}{(9 \times (3+2)) + 8} & &:= \frac{1 \times (7+6)}{(4+9) \times 280} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{23584} &:= \frac{1^7}{2 + (3 \times (5 \times 8 + 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{53824} &:= \frac{17-6}{((5+3 \times 8)^2) \times 4} & & \\ &:= \frac{1+7-6}{(2^{3+5}) + 8 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{59840} &:= \frac{1^7}{5 \times ((9+8) \times (4+0))} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 178

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{356} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{3-5+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{5340} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{5 \times (3 \times 4 + 0)} & &:= \frac{1^7 \times 8}{3 \times (60 \times (4+5))} \\ &:= \frac{1^7}{3+5-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{5429} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{54-2+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{50463} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(5+04) \times 63} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{534} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{5-3+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{6942} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{6+(9 \times 4 \times 2)} & &:= \frac{1+7+8}{504 \times (6+3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{623} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{6-2+3} & &:= \frac{1^7}{6-(9-42)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{92560} &:= \frac{1^7}{(92 \times 5) + 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2403} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{24+03} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{9345} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(9+3 \times 4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{93450} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(9+3 \times 4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{1+7+8}{(2+4+0)^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{23496} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(2^3 + (4 \times 9)) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{234960} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(2^3 + 4 \times 9) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{3026} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{30-2+6} & &:= \frac{1^7}{2+(34+96)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{294056} &:= \frac{1+7+8}{(2^9 - 40) \times 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{3204} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{3^2 \times 04} & &:= \frac{1+7+8}{234 \times 9 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{342650} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(3^4 + 2 - 6) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{1^7}{3 \times (2+04)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{34265} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{((3^4) + 2 - 6) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{465203} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{4 \times 6 + 5203} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{3649} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{36-4+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{36045} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(3+6+0) \times 45} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{178}{4539} &:= \frac{1-7+8}{(4 \times (5 \times 3)) - 9} & &:= \frac{1+7+8}{360 \times (4+5)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 179

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{179}{358} &:= \frac{1-7+9}{3-5+8} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 9}{2 \times (8+64)} &:= \frac{1+7 \times 9}{2 \times (8 \times 640)} \\ &:= \frac{17-9}{3+5+8} &:= \frac{1^7+9}{2 \times (8 \times (6+4))} &:= \frac{1 \times 7+9}{2^8 \times (6+4+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{179}{2506} &:= \frac{1-7+9}{(2+(5+0)) \times 6} &:= \frac{1+7 \times 9}{2 \times (8 \times 64)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{82340} &:= \frac{1 \times 7+9}{8 \times (23 \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{17-9}{2 \times (50+6)} &:= \frac{1 \times 7+9}{2^{(8-6) \times 4}} &\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{328465} &:= \frac{1^{79}}{(32+8) \times 46-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{179}{2685} &:= \frac{1^{79}}{2 \times 6+8-5} &:= \frac{17-9}{2 \times (8^{6-4})} &\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{368024} &:= \frac{1^{79}}{3 \times 680+2^4} \\ &:= \frac{1-7+9}{2+(6 \times 8-5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{8234} &:= \frac{1 \times 7+9}{8 \times 23 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{179}{2864} &:= \frac{1^{79}}{2 \times ((8-6) \times 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{28640} &:= \frac{1^{79}}{2 \times (8 \times (6+4+0))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 180

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2475} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+0}{2 \times ((4+7) \times 5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{7695} &:= \frac{1 \times 80}{76 \times 9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{180}{3645} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+0}{3 \times (6 \times (4+5))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{29745} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+0}{2 \times ((9 \times 74)-5)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 80}{36 \times 45} &\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{45927} &:= \frac{1 \times 80}{((45+9)^2) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{180}{6975} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+0}{(69-7) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{756324} &:= \frac{1 \times 80}{7^5 \times (6 \times 3+2)+4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 182

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{182}{364} &:= \frac{1^8+2}{3 \times (6-4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{546} &:= \frac{1^{82}}{5+4-6} &:= \frac{1 \times (8-2)}{(6-3) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times 2}{3 \times 6 \times 4} &&:= \frac{1^8 \times 2}{(5-4) \times 6} &:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times 2)}{63-7} \\ &:= \frac{1+8-2}{3 \times 6-4} &&:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times 2)}{54-6} &:= \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(6+3) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{1+8+2}{3 \times 6+4} &&:= \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(5+4) \times 6} &:= \frac{18+2}{63+7} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times 2)}{36-4} &&:= \frac{18+2}{54+6} &\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{936} &:= \frac{1+8-2}{(9-3) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(3+6) \times 4} &&:= \frac{1+8 \times 2}{5+46} &\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{3094} &:= \frac{1^{82}}{30-(9+4)} \\ &:= \frac{18+2}{36+4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{637} &:= \frac{18 \times 2}{6 \times (3 \times 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{3549} := \frac{1 \times (8 + 2)}{3 \times (5 \times (4 + 9))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{6370} := \frac{1^8 \times 2}{63 + 7 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 + 2}{3 \times (5^4 + 90)}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 2}{(35 + 4) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{18 \times 2}{6 \times (3 \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 2}{(35 + 4) \times 90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{3640} := \frac{1^8 \times 2}{36 + 4 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - 2)}{(6 - 3) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{45360} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{45 \times 360}$
$:= \frac{18 \times 2}{3 \times (6 \times 40)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 2}{(6 + 3) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{53690} := \frac{1 + 8 + 2}{5 + (36 \times 90)}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 2}{(3 + 6) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{6734} := \frac{1^8 \times 2}{67 + 3 + 4}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 2}{(53 + 6) \times 90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{4095} := \frac{1 \times (8 - 2)}{40 + 95}$	$:= \frac{18 + 2}{6 + 734}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{65793} := \frac{1^8 \times 2}{6 - (5 + (7 - (9^3)))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{4536} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{45 \times 36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{9360} := \frac{1 + 8 - 2}{(9 - 3) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{67340} := \frac{1^8 \times 2}{6 + (734 + 0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{5096} := \frac{1^8 + 2}{(5 + 09) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{9576} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{9 \times 5 \times 76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{95760} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{9 \times (5 \times 760)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{5369} := \frac{(1 + 8) \times 2}{(53 + 6) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{30576} := \frac{18^2}{(30 + 5 - 7) \times 6}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{5460} := \frac{1^8 \times 2}{54 + 6 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1^8 \times 2}{(3 + 05) \times 7 \times 6}$	
$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 2}{(5 + 4) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{35490} := \frac{18^2}{3 \times (5 \times (4 + 9 + 0))}$	

• Numerator 183

$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{427} := \frac{1 + 8 - 3}{(4 - 2) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 3}{(5 + 4) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{1^8 \times 3}{40 + 26}$
$:= \frac{18 - 3}{42 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{976} := \frac{1 + 8 + 3}{(9 - 7)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{4270} := \frac{1 + 8 - 3}{(4 - 2) \times 70}$
$:= \frac{18 + 3}{42 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{2074} := \frac{1 + 8 + 3}{(20 \times 7) - 4}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times 3)}{4 \times (2 \times 70)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times 3)}{4 \times 2 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{2745} := \frac{18^3}{2 - (7 - (4 \times 5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{4697} := \frac{18 - 3}{(46 + 9) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{549} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{(5 - 4) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 - 3}{(2 \times 7 + 4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{5246} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{(5 \times 2^4) + 6}$
$:= \frac{1 + 8 - 3}{5 + 4 + 9}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 + 3}{(2 + 7) \times 4 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{5429} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{(5 \times (4^2)) + 9}$
$:= \frac{18 - 3}{54 - 9}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 3}{(2 + 7) \times 45}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{5490} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{(5 - 4) \times 90}$
$:= \frac{18 + 3}{54 + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{4026} := \frac{18^3}{(4^{01}) + 6}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 - 3}{5 \times (4 \times (9 + 0))}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(1+8) \times 3}{(5+4) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{6405} & := \frac{1+8-3}{6 \times (40-5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{7259} & := \frac{1+8-3}{7 \times (25+9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{20496} & := \frac{1^{83}}{(2^{04}) + 96} \\ & := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{(20 + (4 \times 9)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{27450} & := \frac{1^{83}}{(2+7 \times 4) \times (5+0)} \\ & := \frac{1+8-3}{(2 \times 7+4) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{1+8+3}{(2+7) \times (4 \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{(1+8) \times 3}{(2+7) \times 450} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{46970} & := \frac{18-3}{(46+9) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{52704} & := \frac{1 \times 8-3}{5 \times ((2+70) \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{69540} & := \frac{1+8-3}{6 \times (95 \times (4+0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{96075} & := \frac{1^{83}}{(9+6+0) \times 7 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{247965} & := \frac{1^{83}}{2^4 \times (79+6) - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{256749} & := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{25 \times 6 \times 7 \times 4+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{275049} & := \frac{1 \times 8-3}{2+7504+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{275964} & := \frac{1^{83}}{2 \times 759-6-4} \\ & := \frac{1+8+3}{2+7^5-9+6^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{296704} & := \frac{1+8+3}{2^9 \times (6 \times 7-04)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{450729} & := \frac{1^{83}}{4+50 \times 7^2+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{490257} & := \frac{1^8+3}{(4+90) \times 2 \times 57} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 184

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{230} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{2+3+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{276} & := \frac{18-4}{27-6} \\ & := \frac{18+4}{27+6} \\ & := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{506} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{5+06} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{690} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{6+9+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{736} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{7+3+6} \\ & := \frac{1^{84}}{7+3-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{920} & := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2530} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{2+(53+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2576} & := \frac{1^{84}}{2-((5-7) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2760} & := \frac{1^{84}}{2+(7+6+0)} \\ & := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{3726} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{3+(72+6)} \\ & := \frac{18 \times 4}{(3^{7-2}) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{3+726} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{5290} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{(5^2)+90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{5796} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{(5+7+9) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{6072} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{60+72} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{7590} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{75+90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{9752} & := \frac{1^{84}}{(9 \times 7)-(5 \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{20976} & := \frac{1 \times 8+4}{2 \times (0+9 \times 76)} \\ & := \frac{1^{84}}{2 \times (0+(9 \times 7)-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{23506} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{2+(3+506)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{32706} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{3+(2+706)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{37260} & := \frac{18 \times 4}{(3^{7-2}) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{57960} & := \frac{1 \times 8-4}{(5+7+9) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{92736} & := \frac{1^{84}}{(9+(2+73)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{359720} & := \frac{1^{84}}{3 \times 5+97 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{796352} & := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{(7+9) \times (6^3 \times 5+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{184}{927360} & := \frac{1^{84}}{(9+2+73) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 185

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{296} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{2^{9-6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{24790} &:= \frac{1^{85}}{2 \times (4 + (7 \times (9 + 0)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{93240} &:= \frac{1^{85}}{(9 + 3) \times (2 + 40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{370} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{3 + 7 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{26973} &:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 5}{((2 \times 6 - 9)^2) \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{97236} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{((9 \times (7^2)) - 3) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{407} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4 + 07} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{27306} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{2 + (7 + (3^{06}))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{206793} &:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 5}{(2 + 067) \times 9^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{629} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{6 + 2 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{43290} &:= \frac{1^{85}}{((4 \times 3)^2) + 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{269730} &:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 5}{(2 \times 6 - 9)^7 \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{4329} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{(4 + 3^2) \times 9} & &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{(4 + 3^2) \times 90} & &:= \frac{1 + 8 - 5}{2 \times (6 + 97 \times 30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{6290} &:= \frac{1 \times (8 - 5)}{6 \times 2 + 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{47360} &:= \frac{1^{85}}{4 \times (7 - (3 - 60))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{376290} &:= \frac{1^{85}}{(3 \times 76 - 2) \times 9 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{9324} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5}{9 \times (32 - 4)} & &:= \frac{1^8 + 5}{(47^{-3}) \times (6 + 0)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{185}{9620} &:= \frac{1^{85}}{9 \times 6 - 2 + 0} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 186

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{279} &:= \frac{18 - 6}{2 + 7 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{3472} &:= \frac{1 + 8 - 6}{3 + (4 + 7^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{27435} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 - 6}{(2 - (7 - 4^3)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 6}{2 + 79} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{3720} &:= \frac{1^{86}}{(3 + 7) \times (2 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{27590} &:= \frac{1 + 8 - 6}{2 - (7 - (5 \times 90))} \\ &:= \frac{18 + 6}{27 + 9} & &:= \frac{18 \times 6}{3 \times 720} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{29357} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{2 + (9 \times (3 \times 5 \times 7))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{372} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{3 + 7 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{4092} &:= \frac{1^{86}}{4 - (0 - (9 \times 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{29450} &:= \frac{18 - 6}{(2 + 9 \times 4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times 6}{3 \times 72} & &:= \frac{1 \times 8 - 6}{4 \times (0 + 9 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{29543} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{2 + (954 - 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{527} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{5 \times 2 + 7} & &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{40 + 92} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{29574} &:= \frac{1^{86}}{(2^9 \times 5) - (7^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{930} &:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 6}{9 \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{5394} &:= \frac{1^{86}}{5 - ((3 - 9) \times 4)} & &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{2 \times (9 \times (57 - 4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{2573} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{2 \times 5 + 73} & &:= \frac{1 \times 8 - 6}{53 + 9 - 4} & &:= \frac{18 - 6}{(2^9 - (5 \times 7)) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{2790} &:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 6}{(2 + 7) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{7905} &:= \frac{1 \times (8 + 6)}{7 \times (90 - 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{30597} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{((30 \times 5) - 9) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{2945} &:= \frac{18 - 6}{(2 + 9 \times 4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{9207} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 - 6}{92 + 07} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{94302} &:= \frac{1 + 8 - 6}{((9 + 4) \times (3 + 0))^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{94705} &:= \frac{18-6}{94 \times (70-5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{357492} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{3 \times (57-4+9)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{457932} &:= \frac{18+6}{4+5 \times 7+9^{3+2}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{203794} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 6}{2 \times 03+7+9^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{357492} &:= \frac{1 \times 8-6}{(35+(7-4) \times 9)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{549072} &:= \frac{1^{86}}{(5+4 \times 9) \times 072} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{205437} &:= \frac{1 \times 8-6}{2+05 \times 4+3^7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{370295} &:= \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{3 \times (70 \times 2^9-5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{723540} &:= \frac{1 \times (8+6)}{7 \times (2 \times 3)^5+4+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{274350} &:= \frac{1 \times 8-6}{(2-7+4^3) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{379254} &:= \frac{1^{86}}{37 \times (9+2) \times 5+4} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{186}{295740} &:= \frac{18-6}{(2^9-5 \times 7) \times 40} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 187

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{306} &:= \frac{18-7}{3 \times 06} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{35649} &:= \frac{18-7}{(3^5-6-4) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{253946} &:= \frac{1+8-7}{(2+5) \times (394-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{935} &:= \frac{(1+8) \times 7}{9 \times 35} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{35904} &:= \frac{1^{87}}{(3+(5 \times (9+0))) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{354926} &:= \frac{1^{87}}{3 \times (5^4+9)+2-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{4352} &:= \frac{18-7}{4 \times ((3+5)^2)} & &:= \frac{1 \times (8+7)}{(3+5) \times (90 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{356490} &:= \frac{18-7}{(3^5-6-4) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{4692} &:= \frac{1+87}{4 \times 6 \times 92} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{40392} &:= \frac{1^{87}}{4 \times (0+(3 \times 9 \times 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{365024} &:= \frac{1^{87}}{3 \times (650+2)-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{5049} &:= \frac{1+8-7}{5-(0-49)} & &:= \frac{1+8-7}{40+392} & &:= \frac{1+8-7}{3 \times 650 \times 2+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{5236} &:= \frac{1^{87}}{(5^2)-3+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{46920} &:= \frac{1+87}{4 \times (6 \times 920)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{450296} &:= \frac{1^{87}}{4+50^2-96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{5423} &:= \frac{1^{87}}{5+(4 \times 2 \times 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{63954} &:= \frac{1+8-7}{(6^3-9 \times 5) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{639540} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 7}{63 \times 95 \times 4+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{9350} &:= \frac{(1+8) \times 7}{9 \times 350} & &:= \frac{1^8 \times 7}{6 \times (395+4)} & &:= \frac{1^{87}}{(6+3) \times 95 \times 4+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{25364} &:= \frac{18-7}{2 \times ((5^3 \times 6)-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{96305} &:= \frac{18-7}{9 \times 630-5} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{30294} &:= \frac{1+8-7}{(3^{01}) \times (9 \times 4)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 187

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{189}{462} &:= \frac{1+8+9}{46-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{189}{350} &:= \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{3 \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{189}{735} &:= \frac{18+9}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{18-9}{4 \times 6-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{189}{546} &:= \frac{18-9}{5 \times 4+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{189}{756} &:= \frac{1-8+9}{7-5+6} \\ &:= \frac{18+9}{4+62} & \blacktriangleright \frac{189}{567} &:= \frac{1-8+9}{5-6+7} & &:= \frac{1+8+9}{(7+5) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{2436} := \frac{18-9}{2 \times ((4^3) - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{7035} := \frac{18-9}{(70-3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{256473} := \frac{1^{89}}{2^5 - 6 + (4+7)^3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{2457} := \frac{1-8+9}{2 \times (4 \times 5 - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{7203} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 9}{(7 \times (2+0))^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{267435} := \frac{1^{89}}{(26 \times (7+4) - 3) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{2604} := \frac{1+8+9}{(2+60) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{7350} := \frac{18+9}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 9}{(2 \times (6+7^4) - 3) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{18-9}{(2 \times 60) + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{7560} := \frac{1+8+9}{(7+5) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{275436} := \frac{18+9}{((2 \times 7 - 5)^4 - 3) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3024} := \frac{1-8+9}{30-2+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{24570} := \frac{1^{89}}{(2-4) \times (5-70)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{326074} := \frac{18+9}{(3 \times 2)^6 - 074}$
$:= \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{(3 \times 01)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{35427} := \frac{18-9}{(3^5 - 4 + 2) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{342657} := \frac{1^{89}}{34^2 + 657}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3402} := \frac{1^{89}}{3 \times (4+02)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{36750} := \frac{1+8+9}{(3+67) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{354270} := \frac{18-9}{(3^5 - 4 + 2) \times 70}$
$:= \frac{1-8+9}{34+02}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{40635} := \frac{1^{89}}{4 - (0 - ((6^3) - 5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{357042} := \frac{18-9}{3^5 \times 70 - 4 \times 2}$
$:= \frac{18-9}{(3^4 + 0) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{45360} := \frac{1-8+9}{4 \times ((5-3) \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{367542} := \frac{18+9}{(3+6 \times 7 \times 5^4) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3675} := \frac{1+8+9}{(3+67) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{46305} := \frac{1^{89}}{(46+3+0) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{435267} := \frac{1^{89}}{43 \times 52 + 67}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{4536} := \frac{1-8+9}{4 \times ((5-3) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{47250} := \frac{18-9}{(47-2) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{436275} := \frac{18-9}{4^3 \times 62 + 7^5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{4725} := \frac{1^{89}}{4 - (7 \times (2-5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{50274} := \frac{1-8+9}{(5 - (0 - (2^7))) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{470652} := \frac{18+9}{4 \times (7^{0 \times 6 + 5} + 2)}$
$:= \frac{1-8+9}{47-2+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{53760} := \frac{18+9}{((5-3)^7) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{627543} := \frac{18 \times 9}{6 + (2 \times 7)^5 + 4^3}$
$:= \frac{18-9}{(47-2) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{63504} := \frac{18+9}{6 \times (3 \times 504)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{647325} := \frac{1^{89}}{(64+73) \times 25}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{5376} := \frac{18+9}{((5-3)^7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{247065} := \frac{1+89}{2+4+7^{06}-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{653240} := \frac{18+9}{(6^5 \times 3 + 2) \times 4 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{6237} := \frac{1^{89}}{6 \times 2 + (3 \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{253764} := \frac{1+8+9}{((2 \times 5)^3 + 7) \times 6 \times 4}$	
$:= \frac{1-8+9}{62-3+7}$		

● Numerator 190

$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{247} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+4+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{342} := \frac{1+9+0}{3 \times (4+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{627} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+27}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{285} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+8+5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 90}{3^4 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{836} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+36}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2546} := \frac{1+9+0}{(2^5 \times 4) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2736} := \frac{1+9+0}{(27-3) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{3648} := \frac{1 \times 90}{36 \times 48}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{3724} := \frac{1 \times 90}{((3 \times 7)^2) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{3857} := \frac{1+9+0}{(3 \times 8+5) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{4237} := \frac{1+9+0}{((4+2)^3) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{6327} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+327}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{6574} := \frac{1+9+0}{6 \times 57+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{6745} := \frac{1+9+0}{(67+4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{8436} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{23465} := \frac{1+9+0}{(23-4) \times 65}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{25346} := \frac{1+9+0}{(2^5-3) \times 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{57684} := \frac{1+9+0}{(5 \times 76 \times 8) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{82574} := \frac{1+9+0}{82 \times (57-4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{243675} := \frac{1+9+0}{(2^4+3) \times 675}$$

• Numerator 192

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{384} := \frac{19-2}{38-4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 2}{3 \times (8+4)}$$

$$:= \frac{19+2}{38+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{576} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{5+7-6}$$

$$:= \frac{19-2}{57-6}$$

$$:= \frac{19+2}{57+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{640} := \frac{1^9+2}{6+4+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{704} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+04}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 2}{70-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{768} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{(7-6) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{19-2}{76-8}$$

$$:= \frac{19+2}{76+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{864} := \frac{(1+9) \times 2}{86+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3456} := \frac{192}{3+(4+5+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9+2}{3+(45+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+9) \times 2}{3 \times (4 \times 5 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3504} := \frac{1+9-2}{(3 \times 50) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3648} := \frac{192}{3+((6-4) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9 \times 2}{(3 \times (6+4)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9+2}{3+(6+48)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+9-2}{(36 \times 4) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3840} := \frac{192}{3 \times 8 - 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{4608} := \frac{192}{4 \times (6+0 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9+2}{4+(60+8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+9-2}{4 \times (6 \times 08)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{5376} := \frac{192}{5 \times 3 + 7 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9 \times 2}{(5 \times (3+7)) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9+2}{5+(3+76)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+9+2}{(5+3) \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{5760} := \frac{1 \times (9-2)}{5 \times (7 \times (6+0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{7584} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{75+8-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{7680} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{(7-6) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{8640} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{86+4+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{34560} := \frac{192}{3 \times (4 + (56 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9 \times 2}{3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+9) \times 2}{3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 60))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{45360} := \frac{1+9+2}{45 \times (3+60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{47360} := \frac{1^9+2}{4+(7+(3^6+0))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{48576} &:= \frac{1^{92}}{(48 \times 5) + 7 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{75648} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 2}{756 + 4 \times 8} & & := \frac{1^{92}}{4 + 3^7 + (5 + 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{50368} &:= \frac{1^9 + 2}{50 + ((3^6) + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{75840} &:= \frac{1^{92}}{75 + (8 \times 40)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{453760} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 2}{4 \times 5 \times (3^7 - 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{53760} &:= \frac{1^{92}}{5 \times (3 - (7 - 60))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{350784} &:= \frac{1^{92}}{3 + (50 + 7) \times 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{576384} &:= \frac{1^9 + 2}{57 \times (6 + 38 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1^9 + 2}{(5 - 3) \times (7 \times 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{374856} &:= \frac{1 + 9 - 2}{(3 \times 7 + 4)^{8-5} - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{786304} &:= \frac{1 + 9 + 2}{78 \times 630 + 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 9 + 2}{(5 + 3) \times (7 \times 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{437568} &:= \frac{1 \times (9 - 2)}{43 \times 7 \times (5 + 6 \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 193

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{4825} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{4 + ((8 \times 2) + 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{47285} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{((4 \times 7 + 2) \times 8) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{254760} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 3}{2 \times (5 + 4 \times 7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{1^9 + 3}{(4 + 8 \times 2) \times 5} & &:= \frac{19 - 3}{4 \times (7 \times (28 \times 5))} & &:= \frac{1^{93}}{(25 + 4 - 7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 3}{(4 \times 8 - 2) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{48250} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{(48 + 2) \times (5 + 0)} & &:= \frac{1 + 9 - 3}{(2 + 5 \times 4) \times 7 \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 3}{(4 + 8) \times 25} & &:= \frac{1^9 + 3}{(4 + 8 \times 2) \times 50} & &:= \frac{19 - 3}{2^5 \times (4 + 7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{20458} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{2 \times (0 + (45 + 8))} & &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 3}{(4 \times 8 - 2) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{270586} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 3}{(2 \times 705 - 8) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{25476} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{2 + (54 + 76)} & &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 3}{(4 + 8) \times 250} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{284675} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 3}{(28 \times 4 + 6) \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{1^9 \times 3}{2 \times ((5 + (4 \times 7)) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{56742} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{5 + ((6 + 7 + 4)^2)} & &:= \frac{1^{93}}{(2^8 + 46 - 7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 9 - 3}{(2 + 5 \times 4) \times 7 \times 6} & &:= \frac{1 + 9 - 3}{(56 - 7) \times 42} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{567420} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 7 \times 42 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{19 - 3}{2^5 \times ((4 + 7) \times 6)} & &:= \frac{(1 + 9) \times 3}{5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 42))} & &:= \frac{(1 + 9) \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 7 \times 420} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{27406} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{(2 \times (74 + 0)) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{65427} &:= \frac{19 + 3}{6 \times (((5^4) \times 2) - 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{654270} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{6 \times (5 + 4 \times 2 \times 70)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{28564} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{2 \times (((8 + 5) \times 6) - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{76042} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{(7 \times (60 - 4)) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{845726} &:= \frac{1^{93}}{8 + (4 \times 5 + 7)^2 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{1^9 + 3}{28 + 564} & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{246075} &:= \frac{1^9 + 3}{(2 \times 4 + 60) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 194

$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{582} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 4}{5 + 8 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{6208} := \frac{1^{94}}{(6 - 2 + 0) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{52380} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{((5 \times 2)^3) + 80}$
$:= \frac{1 + 9 + 4}{5 \times 8 + 2}$	$:= \frac{1^9 \times 4}{(6 \times 20) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{52768} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 4}{52 \times (76 - 8)}$
$:= \frac{19 + 4}{5 + 8^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{8730} := \frac{1^{94}}{8 + (7 + 30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{57230} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 4}{5 + (7^2 \times 30)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{873} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{8 + 7 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{26578} := \frac{1^{94}}{2^6 - (5 - 78)}$	$:= \frac{1 + 9 - 4}{(57 + 2) \times 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{2037} := \frac{(1 + 9) \times 4}{20 \times (3 \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{27063} := \frac{1 + 9 - 4}{(2 \times (70 \times 6)) - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{73526} := \frac{1^{94}}{(7 \times (3 + 52)) - 6}$
$:= \frac{1^9 \times 4}{2 \times (0 + (3 \times 7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{32786} := \frac{1 + 9 - 4}{3 \times (2 + (7 \times 8 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{237068} := \frac{1^{94}}{2 \times (3 + (70 + 6) \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{5238} := \frac{1^{94}}{5 + (2 \times (3 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{1^{94}}{(3 \times 2 + 7)^{8-6}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{380725} := \frac{1 + 9 - 4}{3 \times (80 \times 7^2 + 5)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 4}{((5 + 2)^3) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{36278} := \frac{1^{94}}{(3 \times 62) - 7 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{603728} := \frac{1^9 + 4}{60^3 \times 72 + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{5723} := \frac{1 + 9 - 4}{(57 + 2) \times 3}$	$:= \frac{1^9 \times 4}{(3 \times (6^2 \times 7)) - 8}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{5820} := \frac{1^{94}}{5 \times (8 - 2 + 0)}$		

● Numerator 195

$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{208} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{2 \times 08}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (9 - 5)}{2^3 + 40}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{6 \times 240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{260} := \frac{1^9 + 5}{2 + 6 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2470} := \frac{1^9 + 5}{2 + (4 + 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{6 \times (2 \times 40)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{286} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{28 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2860} := \frac{1^9 + 5}{2 + (86 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{8320} := \frac{1^9 + 5}{8 \times (32 + 0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{624} := \frac{1 + 9 - 5}{(6 - 2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{3276} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{3 \times (2 \times 7 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{19 + 5}{(8^3) \times (2 + 0)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{6 \times 24}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{4368} := \frac{1 + 9 - 5}{4 \times (36 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{8346} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{(8 \times (3^4)) - 6}$
$:= \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{6 \times 2 \times 4}$	$:= \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{(4 + 3) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{8736} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{8 \times (7 \times 36)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{780} := \frac{1 \times (9 + 5)}{7 \times 8 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{6240} := \frac{1^{95}}{6^2 - 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{28743} := \frac{1 + 9 - 5}{2 - (8 - 743)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2340} := \frac{1^{95}}{2^3 + 4 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 + 9 - 5}{(6 - 2) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{30264} := \frac{1 + 9 - 5}{(30 \times 26) - 4}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{32760} &:= \frac{1+9+5}{3 \times (2 \times (7 \times 60))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{486720} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 5}{48 \times (6+7) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{43628} &:= \frac{1+9+5}{(((4^3) - 6)^2) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{78624} &:= \frac{1+9-5}{7 \times (8 \times (6 \times (2+4)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{486720} &:= \frac{1^9}{4 \times 8 \times (6+72) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{43680} &:= \frac{1^9}{(4 \times 36) + 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{83460} &:= \frac{1^9}{8 + ((3+4) \times 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{486720} &:= \frac{1+9+5}{(4+8 \times 6) \times 720} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9-5)}{(4^3) \times (6+8+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{87360} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{8 \times (7 \times 360)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{786240} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(78+6) \times 240} \\ &:= \frac{1+9+5}{(4+3) \times 6 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{283764} &:= \frac{1+9-5}{((2^8+3) \times 7+6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{48672} &:= \frac{1+9-5}{48 \times ((6+7) \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{195}{364728} &:= \frac{(1+9) \times 5}{(3+6^4) \times 72 - 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 196

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{245} &:= \frac{1 \times 96}{24 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3528} &:= \frac{1^96}{3 + (5+2+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{30478} &:= \frac{1+9+6}{(304+7) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{280} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{2+8+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{35280} &:= \frac{1 \times (9-6)}{3 \times (5 \times 2+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{35280} &:= \frac{1^96}{3 \times (52+8+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{308} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{3+08} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3724} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{3 \times ((5-2) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{37240} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{(3 \times 7-2) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{735} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{7+3+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3724} &:= \frac{1^96}{(3 \times (7-2)) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{37485} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{3 \times ((7-4) \times 85)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{784} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{7 \times (8-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3724} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{(3 \times 7-2) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{54782} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{(5 \times (4 \times 7 \times 8)) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{19-6}{7 \times 8-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{4032} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{(4 \times 03)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{73248} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{((7^3) - (2^4)) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9+6)}{(7+8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{5824} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{(5+8) \times 2^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{73584} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{73 \times (5 \times 8-4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2058} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{2+05 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{7203} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{7^2 \times 03} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{74382} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{74 + (38^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2380} &:= \frac{1^9+6}{2+3+80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{7840} &:= \frac{1 \times (9+6)}{(7+8) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{374850} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{3 \times (7-4) \times 850} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2450} &:= \frac{1 \times 96}{24 \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{20384} &:= \frac{1^96}{(2 - (0 - (3 \times 8))) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2548} &:= \frac{1^96}{25 - (4+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{25480} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{(2^{5+4}) + 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9-6)}{2 + (5+4 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{196}{27048} &:= \frac{1+9-6}{(2 \times (70 \times 4)) - 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 197

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{197}{2364} &:= \frac{1^{97}}{2 \times (3 \times (6 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 7}{2 + (3 \times 6 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 9 - 7}{(2 \times 3)^{6-4}} \\ &:= \frac{19 - 7}{2 \times (3 \times 6 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9 + 7)}{2^3 \times 6 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{197}{3546} &:= \frac{1^{97}}{3 + (5 + 4 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 9 - 7}{3 + (5 + 46)} \\ &:= \frac{1^9 + 7}{3 \times (54 - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{6304} := \frac{1^{97}}{6 + (30 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{20685} := \frac{19 - 7}{20 \times (68 - 5)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{197}{23640} &:= \frac{1^{97}}{(2 + 3) \times (6 \times (4 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 7}{236 + 4 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{19 - 7}{2 \times (3 \times (6 \times 40))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9 + 7)}{2^3 \times (6 \times 40)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{197}{35460} &:= \frac{1^{97}}{3 \times (54 + 6 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 7}{3 \times (5 \times (4 \times 6 + 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{197}{36248} &:= \frac{1 + 9 - 7}{(3 + (62 + 4)) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{1^9 \times 7}{(((3 \times 6)^2) \times 4) - 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{40385} := \frac{1^{97}}{(40 \times 3) + 85}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{40582} := \frac{1^{97}}{(40 \times 5) + 8 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{48265} := \frac{1^{97}}{(4 \times (8^2)) - (6 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{50432} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 7}{504 \times 32}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{197}{50826} &:= \frac{1^{97}}{50 + (8 \times 26)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 7}{508 + 2 + 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{64025} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 7}{640 + (2 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{304562} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 7}{3 \times (04^5 + 6) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{362480} := \frac{1 + 9 - 7}{(3 + 62 + 4) \times 80}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{197}{863254} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 7}{(8 + 6) \times (3^{2+5} + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1^{97}}{8 + (6 + 3)^2 \times 54} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 198

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{264} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{2 + 6 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{324} := \frac{19 - 8}{3 \times (2 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{342} := \frac{19 - 8}{3 + 4^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{352} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{(3 + 5) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{360} := \frac{1 + 98}{3 \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{374} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{3 \times 7 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{432} := \frac{19 - 8}{4 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{605} := \frac{1 + 9 + 8}{60 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{726} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{7 + 26}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2304} := \frac{1 + 9 + 8}{72 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2304} := \frac{19 - 8}{2^{3+04}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2376} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{23 + 7 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2376} := \frac{1^{98}}{2 - (3 - (7 + 6))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2376} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(23 - 7) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2475} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(2 - 4 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2574} := \frac{1^{98}}{2 \times 5 + 7 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2673} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(2 - 6 + 7)^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2736} := \frac{19 - 8}{2 \times 73 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3267} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{32 - 6 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3267} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{3 \times (2 + (6 \times 7))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3465} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(3 \times (4 + 6)) + 5}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{198}{3520} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(34 - 6) \times 5} \\ \frac{198}{3546} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{(3 + 5) \times 20} \\ \frac{198}{3564} := \frac{19 - 8}{3^5 - 46} \\ \frac{198}{3564} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(3 \times 5 - 6) \times 4} \\ \frac{198}{4257} := \frac{1^98}{3 + (5 + 6 + 4)} \\ \frac{198}{4320} := \frac{19 + 8}{3^5 \times (6 - 4)} \\ \frac{198}{4320} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{4 + (2^5 + 7)} \\ \frac{198}{4320} := \frac{19 - 8}{4 \times 3 \times 20} \\ \frac{198}{4356} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{43 - 5 + 6} \\ \frac{198}{4536} := \frac{19 - 8}{(45 - 3) \times 6} \\ \frac{198}{4653} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(4 \times (6 + 5)) + 3} \\ \frac{198}{5247} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(5^2) + (4 \times 7)} \\ \frac{198}{5346} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{5 + (3 + 46)} \\ \frac{198}{5643} := \frac{19 \times 8}{5 + (3 + 4^6)} \\ \frac{198}{5643} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{56 + 4 - 3} \\ \frac{198}{5742} := \frac{1^98}{5 \times 7 - 4 - 2} \\ \frac{198}{6237} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(6 \times 2 - 3) \times 7} \\ \frac{198}{6435} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{6 \times (2 \times (3 \times 7))} \\ \frac{198}{6435} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{6 + ((4^3) - 5)} \\ \frac{198}{6534} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{6 + (5 \times (3 \times 4))} \\ \frac{198}{6732} := \frac{19 + 8}{(6 + 5) \times (3^4)} \\ \frac{198}{7056} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{67 + 3 - 2} \\ \frac{198}{7056} := \frac{19 - 8}{7 \times (056)} \\ \frac{198}{7326} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{7 + (3 + 2^6)} \\ \frac{198}{7425} := \frac{1^98}{7 + ((3 + 2) \times 6)} \\ \frac{198}{7425} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(7 + (4 \times 2)) \times 5} \\ \frac{198}{7546} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{7^5 + 4 - 6} \\ \frac{198}{7623} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{7 \times (6 + 2 + 3)} \\ \frac{198}{7634} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{(7^{6-3}) + 4} \\ \frac{198}{20736} := \frac{19 - 8}{(20^7) \times (3 + 6)} \\ \frac{198}{23760} := \frac{1^98}{2 \times ((3 + 7) \times (6 + 0))} \\ \frac{198}{24057} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(23 - 7) \times 60} \\ \frac{198}{24057} := \frac{1 + 9 + 8}{(2 - 4 + 05)^7} \\ \frac{198}{24750} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(2 - 4 + 7) \times 50} \\ \frac{198}{25047} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{250 - 4 + 7} \\ \frac{198}{26730} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{267 + 3 + 0} \\ \frac{198}{32076} := \frac{1^98}{3 \times ((2 + 07) \times 6)} \\ \frac{198}{34650} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(34 - 6) \times 50} \\ \frac{198}{35640} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{3 \times (5 \times (6 \times (4 + 0)))} \\ \frac{198}{37026} := \frac{1^98}{3 \times (56 + 4 + 0)} \\ \frac{198}{37026} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{370 - 2 + 6} \\ \frac{198}{37206} := \frac{19 - 8}{3^7 - (20 \times 6)} \\ \frac{198}{45276} := \frac{19 + 8}{(4^5 - 2 + 7) \times 6} \\ \frac{198}{45360} := \frac{19 - 8}{(45 - 3) \times 60} \\ \frac{198}{52734} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{((5 + 2) \times (7^3)) - 4} \\ \frac{198}{53064} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(530 + 6) \times 4} \\ \frac{198}{53460} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{534 + 6 + 0} \\ \frac{198}{57024} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{5 \times (3^4 \times (6 + 0))} \\ \frac{198}{57024} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{((5 + 7 + 0)^2) \times 4} \\ \frac{198}{62073} := \frac{1^98}{(5 + 7 + 0) \times 24} \\ \frac{198}{62073} := \frac{1 \times (9 \times 8)}{(5 + (7 + 0 \times 2))^4} \\ \frac{198}{62370} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{6 + (207 \times 3)} \\ \frac{198}{62370} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{623 + 7 + 0} \\ \frac{198}{63504} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{6 \times (2 \times (3 \times 70))} \\ \frac{198}{63504} := \frac{1 + 98}{63 \times 504} \\ \frac{198}{64350} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{(6 + 4 + 3) \times 50} \\ \frac{198}{65043} := \frac{1 + 98}{650 + 4 + 3} \\ \frac{198}{65340} := \frac{1 + 9 - 8}{6 \times (5 \times 3 + 40)} \\ \frac{198}{65340} := \frac{1^98}{6 \times (5 \times 3 + 40)} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{73062} &:= \frac{1+9-8}{7+((3^{06})+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{74250} &:= \frac{1+9-8}{(7+(4 \times 2)) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{75042} &:= \frac{1+9-8}{750+(4 \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{263574} &:= \frac{19-8}{2+(6+3-5+7)^4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{342056} &:= \frac{1^9+8}{3-4 \times 20+5^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{342650} &:= \frac{1^9+8}{(3+4-2)^6-50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{354276} &:= \frac{19-8}{3^{5+4}-2+7-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{354762} &:= \frac{19-8}{3^{5+4}+(7+6) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{364705} &:= \frac{1+9+8}{((3+6)^4+70) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{452760} &:= \frac{19+8}{(4^5-2+7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{198}{472536} &:= \frac{1+98}{4 \times ((7+2)^5+3 \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 201

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{469} &:= \frac{2+01}{4-6+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{536} &:= \frac{2+01}{5-3+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{938} &:= \frac{2+01}{9-3+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{5896} &:= \frac{2+01}{5+(89-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{6834} &:= \frac{2-01}{(6 \times (8-3))+4} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{(6+8+3) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{2+01}{6+(8 \times (3 \times 4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{7638} &:= \frac{2-01}{76-38} \\ &:= \frac{2+01}{76+38} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{7839} &:= \frac{2-01}{78-39} \\ &:= \frac{2+01}{78+39} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{8643} &:= \frac{2-01}{86-43} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{86 \times (4-3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2+01}{86+43} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{9648} &:= \frac{2-01}{96-48} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{(9-6) \times 4 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{2+01}{9 \times ((6-4) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{36984} &:= \frac{2+01}{3 \times (((6 \times 9)-8) \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{57486} &:= \frac{2-01}{5-(7-(48 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{574-8+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{68943} &:= \frac{2-01}{(68 \times (9-4))+3} \\ &:= \frac{20+1}{((6-8+9)^4) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{69345} &:= \frac{2-01}{(6+(9 \times (3+4))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{6+(9 \times ((3^4)-5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{76983} &:= \frac{2-01}{(7 \times 6 \times 9)+(8-3)} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{7+(69 \times (8+3))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{87435} &:= \frac{2-01}{87 \times ((4-3) \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{93465} &:= \frac{2-01}{93 \times (4+6-5)} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{(9 \times 3+4) \times 6 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2+01}{93 \times (4+6+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{97485} &:= \frac{2-01}{(9+((7+4) \times 8)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2^{01}}{(9-7) \times 485} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{439587} &:= \frac{2+01}{(4-3) \times 9^{5-8+7}} \\ &:= \frac{2-01}{(4+3+9-5-8)^7} \\ &:= \frac{20+1}{(4+3-9+5)^8 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{475968} &:= \frac{2^{01}}{(4+7 \times (5+9) \times 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{201}{538479} &:= \frac{20+1}{(5^3+8) \times 47 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 203

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{5481} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{5 + (48 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 03}{54 + 81}$$

$$:= \frac{20 \times 3}{5 \times 4 \times 81}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{5684} := \frac{2 + 03}{56 + 84}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{03}}{56 \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{17864} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{178 - 6 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{48517} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{485 - 1 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{51968} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{((5 - 1)^{9-6}) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{148596} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{1 \times 4 \times (8 \times 5 \times 9 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{03}}{(1 + (4 + 8) \times 5) \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{158746} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{(1 + 5 \times 8 - 7) \times 46}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 03}{(15 + 87) \times 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{561498} := \frac{20 \times 3}{((5 + 6 + 1)^4 + 9) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{574896} := \frac{2^{03}}{(57 \times 4 + 8) \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{741965} := \frac{20 + 3}{(7^{4+19} + 6) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{891576} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{8 \times (91 \times (5 + 7) + 6)}$$

• Numerator 204

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{918} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{9 \times 1^8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 04}{9 + 18}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{04}}{9 \times 1 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{357} := \frac{2^{04}}{35 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + 4}{35 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{561} := \frac{20 + 4}{5 + 61}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{816} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{8 \times 1^6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 04}{8 + 16}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1683} := \frac{2 \times 04}{1 \times (6 \times (8 + 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1836} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{1 + 8 + 3 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 04}{18 + 36}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 04}{1 \times (8 \times (3 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{04}}{1 \times (8 \times 3 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1938} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{1 \times (9 \times 3 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 04}{19 + 38}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{3876} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{38 \times (7 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 04}{38 + 76}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{3978} := \frac{2 + 04}{39 + 78}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{5916} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{59 - 1^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{7956} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{79 + 5 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 04}{(7 + 9 \times 5) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{8976} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{89 - 7 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{39168} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{(3 - (9 \times (1 - 6))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 04}{3 \times ((9 - 1) \times 6 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 04}{(3 + 9) \times (16 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{39678} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{3 + ((9 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{04}}{(396 - 7) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{65739} := \frac{20 + 4}{6^5 + (7 \times (3 - 9))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{76398} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{7 \times (6 + (3 + 98))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{81396} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{813 - (9 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{139876} := \frac{2 + 04}{1 - 3 + 98 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{156978} := \frac{2 + 04}{1 + (-5 + 6 \times 97) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{195738} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{1957 - 38}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 04}{19 + 5738}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 04}{(195 + 7) \times 38}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{371586} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{3^{7-1} \times 5 - 8 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{615978} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{61 + 5978}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{716958} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 4}{71 + 6958}$$

● Numerator 205

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{369} &:= \frac{2 \times 05}{3 + 6 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{4879} &:= \frac{20 - 5}{(4 \times 87) + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{84173} &:= \frac{2 \times 05}{(8^4 \times 1) + 7 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{20 - 5}{36 - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{9184} &:= \frac{20 - 5}{(9 - 1) \times 84} & \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{193684} &:= \frac{20 + 5}{(1 + (9 + 3^6) \times 8) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{20 + 5}{3 \times (6 + 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{13489} &:= \frac{2 \times 05}{1 + (((3^4) - 8) \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{316479} &:= \frac{2 \times 05}{31 \times 6 \times (4 + 79)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1476} &:= \frac{2 \times 05}{(1 + 4 + 7) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{63714} &:= \frac{2 \times 05}{6 \times (37 \times 14)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1763} &:= \frac{20 - 5}{(1 + 7 \times 6) \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 206

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1854} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{1 + (8 + 5 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{15347} &:= \frac{20 - 6}{(153 - 4) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{95481} &:= \frac{2 \times 06}{9 \times (5^4 - (8 - 1))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 06}{1 \times (8 \times (5 + 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{34917} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{3 + (4 \times (91 - 7))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{385941} &:= \frac{20 - 6}{(3^8 + 5 - 9) \times 4 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1957} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{1 - (9 \times (5 - 7))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{43157} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{431 - (5 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{457938} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{(4 \times 5 - 7) \times 9 \times 38} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 06}{19 + 57} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{51397} &:= \frac{2 + 06}{(51 \times 39) + 7} & &:= \frac{2 + 06}{(45 + 7) \times 9 \times 38} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{3914} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{39 - 1^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{54178} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{541 - (7 + 8)} & &:= \frac{2 \times 06}{4 \times ((5 + 7) \times 9 + 3^8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 06}{(39 - 1) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{59843} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{5 + (9 \times ((8 - 4)^3))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{715438} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{7 \times (1 + 54) + 3^8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{7931} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 6}{7 \times (9 + 3 - 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{84975} &:= \frac{2 + 06}{(8 + (4 \times 9)) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 207

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{1495} &:= \frac{2 + 07}{1 \times ((4 + 9) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{3519} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 7}{35 - 1^9} & &:= \frac{2 \times 07}{(4 \times 9 + 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{1863} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 7}{1 + (8 + 6 + 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{3864} &:= \frac{2 + 07}{3 \times ((8 + 6) \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{6831} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 7}{6 \times (8 + 3 \times 1)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 07}{18 + 63} & \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{4968} &:= \frac{2^{07}}{4 \times 96 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{8694} &:= \frac{2 + 0 \times 7}{8 \times 6 + 9 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{9315} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 7}{9 \times ((3-1) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2+07}{9 \times (3 \times 15)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{13685} &:= \frac{2+07}{(13-6) \times 85} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{13869} &:= \frac{2+07}{(1+((3+8) \times 6)) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{16583} &:= \frac{2+07}{1+(6 \times (5 \times (8 \times 3)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{19458} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 7}{1 \times ((9 \times 4 \times 5) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{20-7}{1 \times (94 \times (5+8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{31648} &:= \frac{20+7}{((3+1)^6) + 4 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{38456} &:= \frac{2+07}{38 \times (4 \times (5+6))} \\ &:= \frac{20+7}{(3+8) \times 456} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{39468} &:= \frac{2+07}{3 \times ((94 \times 6) + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{69345} &:= \frac{20-7}{(6 \times ((9^3) - 4)) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{95634} &:= \frac{2^{07}}{9^5 + (6+3^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{146395} &:= \frac{2+07}{1 \times (4+63) \times 95} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{195684} &:= \frac{2+07}{19 \times 56 \times 8 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{365148} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 7}{3 \times 6 \times (51 \times 4 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 07}{(3+6 \times 514) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{207}{453169} &:= \frac{2+07}{4 \times 5 + 3^{16 \times 9}} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 208

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{416} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{4 \times 1^6} \\ &:= \frac{2+08}{4+16} \\ &:= \frac{20-8}{4 \times 1 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{936} &:= \frac{2+08}{9+36} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{(9+3) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1456} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{1 \times (4 \times 5 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2+08}{14+56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1495} &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{(14+9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1976} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{19 \times (7-6)} \\ &:= \frac{2+08}{19+76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{3159} &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{3^{1-5+9}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{3796} &:= \frac{20-8}{3 \times (79-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{4576} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{45-7+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{7956} &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{(7+95) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{14365} &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{(14+3) \times 65} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{17563} &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{1+(75 \times 6 \times 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{43576} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{(((4^3) - 5) \times 7) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{46579} &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{(4^6) - (57 \times 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{53469} &:= \frac{2 \times 08}{5+(3+(4^6+9))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{53976} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{(53 \times 9) + 7 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{20-8}{(((5-3)^9) + 7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{79456} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{794-(5 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{94536} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{(9 \times 4 \times 5) + 3^6} \\ &:= \frac{2+08}{9+4536} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{137956} &:= \frac{20-8}{1 \times 3 + 7956} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{419536} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{4 \times (19 \times 53) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{534976} &:= \frac{2+0 \times 8}{(5+3^4 \times 9) \times 7 + 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 209

$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{361} := \frac{2+09}{3 \times 6 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1843} := \frac{2+09}{1+8 \times 4 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{57684} := \frac{2+09}{(5 \times 76 \times 8) - 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{418} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{4 \times 1^8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{3857} := \frac{2+09}{(3 \times 8 + 5) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{63745} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{((6 \times (3 \times 7)) - 4) \times 5}$
$\quad := \frac{2+09}{4+18}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{5168} := \frac{2+09}{(5-1) \times 68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{415378} := \frac{2+09}{(4+1+5) \times (3^7) - 8}$
$\quad := \frac{2 \times 09}{4 \times (1+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{5643} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{5+6+43}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{416537} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{(4-1) \times (6+5)^3 - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{836} := \frac{2+09}{8+36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{6574} := \frac{2+09}{6 \times 57 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{481536} := \frac{2 \times 09}{4 \times 8 \times (1+5)^3 \times 6}$
$\quad := \frac{2 \times 09}{8 \times (3+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{6745} := \frac{2+09}{(67+4) \times 5}$	$\quad := \frac{2^{09}}{4^8 \times 1^5 \times 3 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1368} := \frac{2+09}{1+3+68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{7315} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{7 \times ((3-1) \times 5)}$	$\quad := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{48 \times (1+5 \times 3) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1463} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{1+4+6+3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{7581} := \frac{2+09}{7 \times (58-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{645183} := \frac{2 \times 09}{6 \times (4 \times 5 + 1^8)^3}$
$\quad := \frac{2+09}{14+63}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{8436} := \frac{2+09}{8+436}$	$\quad := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{6 \times (4^5 + 1) + 8 \times 3}$
$\quad := \frac{2 \times 09}{14 \times (6+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{14763} := \frac{2+09}{14+763}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1786} := \frac{2+09}{1+7+86}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{36784} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{(3 \times 6 - 7) \times 8 \times 4}$	

• Numerator 210

$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{693} := \frac{2 \times 10}{69 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{4375} := \frac{2+10}{(43+7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{64785} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{6 + 47 \times (8 + 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{735} := \frac{2+10}{7+35}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{4935} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{49 + 3 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{364875} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{(36 + 4) \times 87 - 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{756} := \frac{2 \times 10}{(7+5) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{9765} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{9 \times 7 + 6 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{398475} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{(3 + 9 \times (8 + 4) \times 7) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{945} := \frac{2+10}{9+45}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{35679} := \frac{2 \times 10}{3+5 \times 679}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{738465} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{7 + 3^8 + 465}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{3465} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{34 - 6 + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{37485} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{3 \times 7 \times (4 + 8 + 5)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{3675} := \frac{2 \times 10}{(3+67) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{49875} := \frac{2 \times 1 + 0}{(4+98-7) \times 5}$	

• Numerator 213

$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{497} := \frac{21-3}{49-7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{8946} := \frac{2+1^3}{(8+9+4) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{59640} := \frac{2-1^3}{5 \times (96-40)}$
$\quad := \frac{21+3}{49+7}$	$\quad := \frac{2 \times (1+3)}{8 \times (9 \times 4+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{67095} := \frac{2+1+3}{6 \times (7 \times (0+9 \times 5))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{568} := \frac{21-3}{56-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{40896} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{4 \times (0 \times 8+96)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{67450} := \frac{2+1+3}{(6 \times 7-4) \times 50}$
$\quad := \frac{21+3}{56+8}$	$\quad := \frac{2+1 \times 3}{40 \times (8 \times (9-6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{86904} := \frac{2-1^3}{8 \times 6+(90 \times 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{5680} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 8+0}$	$\quad := \frac{2+1+3}{(4+08) \times 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{89460} := \frac{2+1^3}{(8+9+4) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{5964} := \frac{2-1^3}{(5+9) \times (6-4)}$	$\quad := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{4 \times (0+(8 \times 9 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{497568} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{4 \times (9+7) \times (5+68)}$
$\quad := \frac{2+1 \times 3}{(5+9) \times (6+4)}$	$\quad := \frac{2^{1+3}}{4 \times (0+(8 \times 96))}$	$\quad := \frac{2+1^3}{4 \times (9+7 \times 5 \times 6) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{6745} := \frac{2+1+3}{(6 \times 7-4) \times 5}$	$\quad := \frac{21+3}{(40+8) \times 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{748695} := \frac{2+1+3}{74 \times (8 \times 6+9) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{6958} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{6 \times (9+5 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{50694} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{(50+69) \times 4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{8094} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{(8 \times 09)+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{213}{57084} := \frac{2-1^3}{(5+(70-8)) \times 4}$	

• Numerator 214

$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{856} := \frac{2+14}{8+56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{9630} := \frac{2-1^4}{9+(6+30)}$	$\quad := \frac{2 \times 1^4}{7 \times (6+((3+9) \times 8))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{963} := \frac{2 \times 1^4}{(9-6) \times 3}$	$\quad := \frac{2 \times 1^4}{(9-6) \times 30}$	$\quad := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{7 \times (6 \times (3 \times (9+8)))}$
$\quad := \frac{(2-1) \times 4}{9+6+3}$	$\quad := \frac{2-1+4}{9+(6^3+0)}$	$\quad := \frac{2+1^4}{7 \times ((6+3) \times (9+8))}$
$\quad := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{9 \times (6-3)}$	$\quad := \frac{2 \times (1+4)}{(9+6) \times 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{83567} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 4}{((8-3)^5)+6-7}$
$\quad := \frac{2 \times (1+4)}{(9+6) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{37985} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{3 \times ((79-8) \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{379850} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{3 \times (79-8) \times 50}$
$\quad := \frac{2+14}{9+63}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{63879} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{((6^3) \times 8)+7 \times 9}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{8560} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{8 \times (5 \times (6+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{76398} := \frac{2-1^4}{7 \times ((6-3) \times (9+8))}$	

• Numerator 215

$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{387} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 5}{3 + 8 + 7}$	$:= \frac{(2-1) \times 5}{3 + (87 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{9460} := \frac{2 \times 1^5}{94 - (6 + 0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{430} := \frac{2^{1 \times 5}}{4^3 + 0}$	$:= \frac{2 - 1 + 5}{38 + 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{9804} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 5}{9 \times (80 - 4)}$
$:= \frac{2 - 1 + 5}{4 \times 3 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{4386} := \frac{(2-1) \times 5}{(4 \times 3 \times 8) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{43860} := \frac{2 - 1^5}{4 \times (3 + (8 \times (6 + 0)))}$
$:= \frac{2 + 15}{4 + 30}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 5}{4 \times (3 + 8 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times 5}{(43 + 8) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{473} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 5}{(4 + 7) \times 3}$	$:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times 5}{(43 + 8) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{67940} := \frac{2 - 1 + 5}{6 \times (79 \times (4 + 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{860} := \frac{2 \times (1 + 5)}{8 \times (6 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{4730} := \frac{2 \times 1^5}{47 - 3 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{368940} := \frac{2 - 1^5}{3 \times (68 \times 9 - 40)}$
$:= \frac{2 + 15}{8 + 60}$	$:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times 5}{(4 + 7) \times 30}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{3096} := \frac{(2 - 1) \times 5}{(3 + 09) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{6708} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 5}{6 \times (70 + 8)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{3870} := \frac{2 - 1^5}{3 + (8 + 7 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{9073} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 5}{(90 \times 7) + 3}$	

• Numerator 216

$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{540} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 6}{5 \times (4 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{38475} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{3 \times (8 \times 475)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{357048} := \frac{2 - 1^6}{3^5 \times 7 - 048}$
$:= \frac{2 + 16}{5 + 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{47385} := \frac{2 \times 16}{4 \times ((7^3 + 8) \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{384750} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{3 \times 8 \times 4750}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{837} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 6}{8 \times 3 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{54378} := \frac{2 \times 16}{((5 \times 4)^3) + (7 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{394875} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(3 + 9) \times 4875}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{984} := \frac{2 + 1 + 6}{9 + 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{73584} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{7 - (3 \times 5 - 8^4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{397458} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{3^9 + 7^4 + 5 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3504} := \frac{2 + 1 + 6}{(3 \times 50) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{73845} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 6}{((7^3) \times 8) - (4 + 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{459378} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 6}{4 + 5 \times 9 \times 378}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{5940} := \frac{2 \times 1^6}{59 - 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{84375} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{8 \times ((4 \times 3 - 7)^5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{473850} := \frac{2 \times 16}{4 \times (7^3 + 8) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{7584} := \frac{2 + 16}{7 + (5^{8-4})}$	$:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 6}{(((8 - 4) \times 3) - 7)^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{537894} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 6}{5 + 3 \times (78 + 9^4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{9408} := \frac{2 + 1 + 6}{(9 + 40) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{345780} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{34 \times (5 + 7 \times 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{548937} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 6}{(5 + 4) \times (8 \times 9 + 3^7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{35748} := \frac{2 \times 1^6}{(3^5) + ((7 + 4) \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{350784} := \frac{2 - 1^6}{(350 + 7 \times 8) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{593784} := \frac{2 + 1^6}{593 \times 7 + 8^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{37890} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{3^7 + (8 - 90)}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{735840} := \frac{2 + 1 + 6}{73 \times 5 \times 84 + 0}$

● Numerator 217

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{465} := \frac{(2-1) \times 7}{4+6+5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{496} := \frac{21+7}{4^{9-6}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{3069} := \frac{(2-1) \times 7}{30+69} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(2+1) \times 7}{306-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{3689} := \frac{2-1^7}{3 \times 6+8-9} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+1^7}{(3 \times (6+8))+9} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+1 \times 7}{(3+6+8) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{3906} := \frac{2-1^7}{3+(9+06)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times 1^7}{(3-9) \times (-06)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+1 \times 7}{3 \times (9 \times 06)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times (1 \times 7)}{3 \times (90-6)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times (1+7)}{3 \times (90+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{8463} := \frac{2 \times 1^7}{((8 \times 4)-6) \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{9486} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times 7)}{(94+8) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{34968} := \frac{(2-1) \times 7}{3 \times ((4 \times 96)-8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{36890} := \frac{2+1 \times 7}{(3+6+8) \times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{38564} := \frac{21 \times 7}{((3^8)-(5 \times 6)) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{84630} := \frac{2 \times 1^7}{((8 \times 4)-6) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{94860} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times 7)}{(94+8) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{96348} := \frac{2-1^7}{96+348} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{349680} := \frac{(2-1) \times 7}{(3 \times 49-6) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{380649} := \frac{(2-1) \times 7}{3 \times 8^{0 \times 6+4}-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{385640} := \frac{21 \times 7}{(3^8-5 \times 6) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{217}{965340} := \frac{(2+1) \times 7}{(9+6^5) \times 3 \times 4+0}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 218

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{436} := \frac{2+1^8}{(4-3) \times 6} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times 18}{4 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2-1+8}{4 \times 3+6} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+1+8}{4+3 \times 6} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{4 \times (3+6)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+18}{4+36} \\
 \qquad := \frac{21+8}{(4^3)-6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{654} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{6 \times (5-4)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{6 \times (5+4)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+18}{6+54} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{763} := \frac{2 \times 18}{7 \times 6 \times 3} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{7 \times (6+3)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+18}{7+63} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{3597} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{35-9+7} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(2-1) \times 8}{35+97} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{4360} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{4+(36+0)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2+1^8}{(4-3) \times 60} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2 \times 18}{4 \times (3 \times 60)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{4796} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{47-9+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{4905} := \frac{(2-1) \times 8}{4 \times (9 \times 05)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{6540} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{6+(54+0)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{2-1+8}{6 \times (5+40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{218}{7630} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{7+(63+0)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{218}{9374} := \frac{2 \times 18}{7 \times (6 \times 30)} \\
 & \frac{218}{9374} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{9 + (3 + 74)} \\
 & \frac{218}{9374} := \frac{(2 - 1) \times 8}{(93 - 7) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{218}{30956} := \frac{2 + 1^8}{(30 \times (9 + 5)) + 6} \\
 & \frac{218}{37496} := \frac{2 + 1^8}{(3 + (74 + 9)) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{218}{54936} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{5 + (493 + 6)} \\
 & \frac{218}{60495} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{60 + 495} \\
 & \frac{218}{76954} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{7 + (695 + 4)} \\
 & \frac{218}{93740} := \frac{2 - 1^8}{(7 \times (6 + 9 \times 5)) - 4} \\
 & \frac{218}{93740} := \frac{(2 - 1) \times 8}{(93 - 7) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{218}{374960} := \frac{2 + 1^8}{(3 + 74 + 9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{218}{463795} := \frac{2 \times 18}{46 \times (37 \times 9 \times 5)} \\
 & \frac{218}{549360} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{((5 + 4) \times 9 + 3) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{218}{765943} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{7 + 65 \times 9 \times 4 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{218}{60495} := \frac{2 + 1^8}{5^4 \times (9 + 3) + 60} \\
 & \frac{218}{765943} := \frac{2 \times 1^8}{7 + 65 \times 9 \times 4 \times 3}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 219

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{219}{365} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 9}{(3 + 6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{219}{438} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{4 \times 3 - 8} \\
 & \frac{219}{438} := \frac{2 - 1 + 9}{4 \times 3 + 8} \\
 & \frac{219}{438} := \frac{2 + 19}{4 + 38} \\
 & \frac{219}{657} := \frac{2 + 19}{6 + 57} \\
 & \frac{219}{730} := \frac{2 + 1^9}{7 + 3 + 0} \\
 & \frac{219}{803} := \frac{2 + 1^9}{8 + 03} \\
 & \frac{219}{803} := \frac{2 + 19}{80 - 3} \\
 & \frac{219}{876} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{8 \times (7 - 6)} \\
 & \frac{219}{876} := \frac{2 + 19}{8 + 76} \\
 & \frac{219}{3504} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{(3 + (5 + 0)) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{219}{3650} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 9}{(3 + 6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{219}{4380} := \frac{2 - 1^9}{4 \times 3 + 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{219}{5037} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{50 + 3 - 7} \\
 & \frac{219}{5840} := \frac{(2 - 1) \times 9}{5 \times (8 + 40)} \\
 & \frac{219}{5840} := \frac{2 + 1^9}{5 \times 8 + 40} \\
 & \frac{219}{34675} := \frac{2 + 1^9}{3 + (467 + 5)} \\
 & \frac{219}{35478} := \frac{2 + 1^9}{3 + (5 + 478)} \\
 & \frac{219}{35478} := \frac{21 + 9}{3^5 \times ((4 \times 7) - 8)} \\
 & \frac{219}{47085} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{470 - (8 \times 5)} \\
 & \frac{219}{58473} := \frac{2 - 1^9}{(5 + ((8 + 4) \times 7)) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{219}{58473} := \frac{2 + (1 \times 9)}{(5 \times (84 \times 7)) - 3} \\
 & \frac{219}{63875} := \frac{(2 - 1) \times 9}{(6 - 3) \times 875} \\
 & \frac{219}{63875} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 9}{(6 + 3) \times 875} \\
 & \frac{219}{68547} := \frac{21 \times 9}{63 \times 875} \\
 & \frac{219}{68547} := \frac{2 + 1 + 9}{6 \times (8 + (5^4 - 7))} \\
 & \frac{219}{73584} := \frac{2^{1 \times 9}}{(7 + 35) \times 8^4} \\
 & \frac{219}{73584} := \frac{2 - 1^9}{7^3 + (5 - (8 + 4))} \\
 & \frac{219}{73584} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{7 \times ((3 + 5) \times (8 + 4))} \\
 & \frac{219}{73584} := \frac{2 - 1 + 9}{7 \times (3 \times (5 \times 8 \times 4))} \\
 & \frac{219}{73584} := \frac{(2 + 1) \times 9}{7 \times ((3 - 5 + 8)^4)} \\
 & \frac{219}{84753} := \frac{2 - 1^9}{(8 \times (4 \times (7 + 5))) + 3} \\
 & \frac{219}{354780} := \frac{(2 - 1) \times 9}{3^5 \times 4 \times (7 + 8) + 0} \\
 & \frac{219}{354780} := \frac{2 - 1^9}{3 \times 5 \times (4 \times 7 + 80)} \\
 & \frac{219}{354780} := \frac{2 + 1^9}{3^5 \times (4 \times 7 - 8) + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{219}{357408} &:= \frac{(2-1) \times 9}{3 \times (5+7) \times 408} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 1^9}{(3 \times 5 - 7) \times 408} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{386754} := \frac{2 \times 19}{((3-8) \times 6 + 7^5) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{453768} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{(4 \times (5-3)^7 + 6) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{638750} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(6+3) \times 8750}$$

$$:= \frac{21 \times 9}{63 \times 8750}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{745038} := \frac{2+1+9}{7 \times (4+5)^{03} \times 8}$$

• Numerator 230

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{874} := \frac{2+3+0}{8+7+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1564} := \frac{2+3+0}{1 \times ((5 \times 6) + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{4186} := \frac{2+3+0}{4+(1+86)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{4968} := \frac{2+3+0}{4+(96+8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{5796} := \frac{2+3+0}{(5+7+9) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{6578} := \frac{2+3+0}{65+78}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{17986} := \frac{2+3+0}{1 - ((7-9 \times 8) \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{94875} := \frac{2 \times (3+0)}{9 \times ((48+7) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^3+0}{(9 \times 4+8) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{96715} := \frac{2^3+0}{9+(671 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{158746} := \frac{2+3+0}{1+5 \times (8+7) \times 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{158976} := \frac{2+3+0}{(1+5) \times (89+7) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{197846} := \frac{2+3+0}{197+8+4^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{894516} := \frac{2+3+0}{(8 \times 9 \times 45+1) \times 6}$$

• Numerator 231

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{594} := \frac{2^3-1}{5+9+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{756} := \frac{23-1}{(7+5) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{847} := \frac{23+1}{8 \times (4+7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{5698} := \frac{23+1}{(5+69) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{5940} := \frac{2^3-1}{5 \times (9 \times 4+0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{7546} := \frac{2^3+1}{(75 \times 4) - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{7560} := \frac{23-1}{(7+5) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{7854} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{(7 \times 8 - 5) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{8547} := \frac{2^{3-1}}{8+(5 \times (4 \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^3+1}{(85 \times 4) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{9548} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{((9-5)^4) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2^3+1}{(95 \times 4) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{46508} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{(4 \times (6 \times 50)) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{47586} := \frac{2+3 \times 1}{(4 \times ((7-5)^8)) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{3 \times 1}}{4 \times ((7 \times 58) + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{47685} := \frac{2^3-1}{(4+7+6) \times 85}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{48675} := \frac{2^3-1}{((48 \times 6) + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{54978} := \frac{2^{3 \times 1}}{((5 \times 49) - 7) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{56749} := \frac{2^3+1}{(5 \times (6 \times 74)) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{56980} := \frac{23+1}{(5+69) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{74085} := \frac{2^3-1}{(7 \times (40 \times 8)) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{78540} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{(7 \times 8 - 5) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{2^3-1}{7 \times 85 \times 4+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{85470} := \frac{2^{3 \times 1}}{8 \times (5 \times (4+70))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{231}{470589} &:= \frac{2+31}{4 \times 7^{05} + 8 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{2+31}{4 \times 7^{0 \times 6 + 5} + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{231}{476850} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{(4 + 7 + 6) \times 850} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{231}{486750} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{(48 \times 6 + 7) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 234

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{819} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 4}{8 - 1^9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{975} &:= \frac{2 \times (3^4)}{9 \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1508} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1 \times (50+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1560} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1^5 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1768} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1 \times (76-8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1976} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1^9 \times 76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{5967} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 4}{5 \times (9 + (6 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{(5 \times 9 + 6) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{7605} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 4}{(7+6+0) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{7 \times (60+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{7956} &:= \frac{2+3-4}{(7 \times (9-5)) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 4}{79 - (5+6)} \\ &:= \frac{2^3 + 4}{(7 \times 9 + 5) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{9750} &:= \frac{2 \times (3^4)}{9 \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{15678} &:= \frac{2+3-4}{1 \times (5 + (6 + (7 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 4}{1 \times (56 + 78)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{17680} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1^7 \times 680} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{19578} &:= \frac{2-3+4}{195 + (7 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{19760} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1^9 \times 760} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{57681} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 4}{5 \times (7 + (6 \times 81))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{59670} &:= \frac{2+3-4}{5 \times (9 + (6 \times (7+0)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{(5 \times 9 + 6) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{75816} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 4}{(7+5) \times ((8+1) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2-3+4}{(7-5) \times (81 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{79560} &:= \frac{2^3 + 4}{(7 \times 9 + 5) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{85176} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 4}{8 \times ((5 \times 17) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2-3+4}{(85-1) \times (7+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{108576} &:= \frac{2+3-4}{10 \times (8 \times 5 + 7) - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{156780} &:= \frac{2^3 + 4}{15 \times 67 \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{2^3 - 4}{1 \times 5 \times 67 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{170586} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 4}{(1 \times 70 - 58)^6} \\ &:= \frac{2+3-4}{1^7 \times (-05+8)^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{175968} &:= \frac{2+3-4}{(1+75) \times 9 + 68} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{176085} &:= \frac{2^3 - 4}{(1-7+608) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{185679} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 4}{(18+5) \times (6+7 \times 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{234}{185796} &:= \frac{2+3-4}{1-8+5+796} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 235

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{470} &:= \frac{2+35}{4+70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{846} &:= \frac{(2+3) \times 5}{84+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{987} &:= \frac{(2+3) \times 5}{98+7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1974} &:= \frac{2+3+5}{1+9+74} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 9 \times 7 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{7896} &:= \frac{(2+3) \times 5}{7 \times 8 \times (9+6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{8460} &:= \frac{2-3+5}{84+60} \\ &:= \frac{2^3+5}{8+460} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{9870} &:= \frac{2-3+5}{98+70} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{17860} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 5}{1 + (7 + (8 + 60))} & := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 9 \times 7 \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{78960} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 5)}{7 \times 8 \times 96 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{19740} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 5}{1 + (9 + (74 + 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{71064} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5}{7 \times (1 \times (0 + (6^4)))} \\ &:= \frac{2^3 - 5}{1 \times (9 \times (7 \times (4 + 0)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{76140} &:= \frac{23 + 5}{7 \times 6^{1 \times 4} + 0} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 236

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{590} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 6)}{5 \times (9 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{10974} &:= \frac{2^3 - 6}{1 \times 097 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{80417} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 6}{(8^{04 \times 1}) - 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 36}{5 + 90} & &:= \frac{2 + 3 \times 6}{10 \times (97 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{85904} &:= \frac{2^3 - 6}{8 \times (5 + (90 - 4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{708} &:= \frac{2 - 3 + 6}{7 + 08} & \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{14750} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 6}{1^4 \times 750} & \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{94518} &:= \frac{2^3 - 6}{(94 - 5) \times (1 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1475} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 6}{1^4 \times 75} & &:= \frac{2^3 \times 6}{1 \times (4 \times 750)} & & \\ &:= \frac{2^3 \times 6}{1 \times (4 \times 75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{19470} &:= \frac{2^3 - 6}{1 + (94 + 70)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1947} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 6}{1 \times 9 \times (4 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{236}{71508} &:= \frac{2 - 3 + 6}{7 + 1508} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 237

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{1580} &:= \frac{2 - 3 + 7}{1 \times (5 \times 8 + 0)} & := \frac{2^3 + 7}{1 \times (8 \times (9 + 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{108546} &:= \frac{2^3 - 7}{(108 + 5) \times 4 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 7}{1^5 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{9480} &:= \frac{2^3 - 7}{(9 - 4) \times (8 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{156894} &:= \frac{2^3 - 7}{1 + (5 + 68) \times 9 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{1659} &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 7}{1 \times (6 \times (5 + 9))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{18960} &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 7}{1^8 \times 960} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{180594} &:= \frac{2^3 - 7}{1 + (80 + 5) \times 9 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{1896} &:= \frac{2^3 - 7}{1 - (8 - (9 + 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{59408} &:= \frac{2^3 + 7}{5 \times (94 \times 08)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{901548} &:= \frac{2^3 + 7}{90 \times (1 + 5^4 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 7}{1 + 89 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{60514} &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 7}{(60 \times 51) + 4} & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times (8 + 96)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{84609} &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 7}{84 \times (60 - 9)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 238

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{476} := \frac{2 + 38}{4 + 76} \quad := \frac{2 + 3 \times 8}{4 \times (7 + 6)} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{510} := \frac{2 - 3 + 8}{5 + 10}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{714} := \frac{2-3+8}{7+14} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{15096} := \frac{2-3+8}{1 \times ((50 \times 9) - 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{97461} := \frac{2^3+8}{9 \times (((7-4)^6) - 1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1496} := \frac{2-3+8}{1+(49-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{16490} := \frac{2-3+8}{1-(6-490)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{104567} := \frac{2 \times 3+8}{1 \times 04^5 \times 6+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{4590} := \frac{2-3+8}{45+90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{17459} := \frac{2 \times 3+8}{1-(7-(4^5+9))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{176409} := \frac{2 \times 3+8}{(1+7) \times 6^4+09} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{5916} := \frac{2 \times 3+8}{(59-1) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{50796} := \frac{2 \times 3+8}{(507-9) \times 6} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{10795} := \frac{2 \times 3+8}{(10 \times 7 \times 9)+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{59160} := \frac{2 \times 3+8}{(59-1) \times 60} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{14076} := \frac{2-3+8}{1+(407+6)} & & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 239

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{239}{478} := \frac{2+39}{4+78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{239}{41586} := \frac{2-3+9}{4 \times (1 \times (58 \times 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{239}{605148} := \frac{2 \times 3+9}{60 \times (5^{1 \times 4}+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{239}{8604} := \frac{2^3+9}{8+604} & \blacktriangleright \frac{239}{74568} := \frac{2-3+9}{(7+45) \times 6 \times 8} & \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{239}{415860} := \frac{2-3+9}{4 \times 1 \times 58 \times 60} & \\ & := \frac{2 \times (3+9)}{860+4} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 240

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{735} := \frac{2 \times 40}{7 \times 35} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{6915} := \frac{2^4+0}{6+(91 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{196875} := \frac{2^4+0}{1 \times (9+6) \times 875} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1365} := \frac{2^4+0}{1+(3 \times 6 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{9375} := \frac{2 \times 40}{(9+3-7)^5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{358176} := \frac{2 \times 40}{3 \times 581+7^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1395} := \frac{2^4+0}{1-(3-95)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{16875} := \frac{2^4+0}{(1+6+8) \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{786513} := \frac{2 \times 40}{7+8^6+5 \times (1+3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1539} := \frac{2 \times 40}{1+((5-3)^9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{167835} := \frac{2 \times 40}{1 \times 67 \times 835} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{786591} := \frac{2 \times 40}{7+8^6+5 \times 9+1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1785} := \frac{2 \times 40}{1 \times (7 \times 85)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{176895} := \frac{2 \times 40}{(1-7) \times (6+8)+9^5} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1875} := \frac{2^4+0}{(18+7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{240}{186579} := \frac{2 \times 40}{1+8 \times (6^5+7-9)} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 241

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{241}{3856} := \frac{2+4-1}{3 \times 8+56} \quad := \frac{2+4 \times 1}{(3+8+5) \times 6} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{7953} := \frac{24 \times 1}{795-3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{37596} &:= \frac{2+4 \times 1}{3 \times ((7+5 \times 9) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{80976} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 1}{8 \times (0 + (9 \times 7 \times 6))} & & := \frac{2^4 \times 1}{(3+7 \times 59) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 1}{((3 \times 75) + 9) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{85073} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 1}{8 \times ((50 \times 7) + 3)} & & := \frac{2+4 \times 1}{3 \times (7+5 \times 9) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{2^4 \times 1}{(3+7 \times 59) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{87965} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 1}{8 \times ((79-6) \times 5)} & & := \frac{2+4+1}{3^7 \times 5-9-6+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{38560} &:= \frac{2+4 \times 1}{(3+8+5) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{90375} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 1}{9 \times (0+375)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{397650} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 1}{(3 \times 97+6) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{39765} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 1}{((3 \times 97) + 6) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{97605} &:= \frac{2^4 + 1}{9 \times (760+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{65793} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+1)}{65 \times (7 \times (9-3))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{350896} &:= \frac{24+1}{350 \times (8+96)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{80735} &:= \frac{2+4-1}{(80 \times 7 \times 3) - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{241}{375960} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 1}{(3 \times 75+9) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 243

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{567} &:= \frac{24-3}{56-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{15687} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{(15+68) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{86751} &:= \frac{2-4+3}{(8+6-7) \times 51} \\ &:= \frac{24+3}{56+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{15768} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{1 \times (576+8)} & & := \frac{2 \times (4-3)}{(8-6) \times (7 \times 51)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{810} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{8 \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{15876} &:= \frac{2+4-3}{15 \times 8+76} & & := \frac{2+4-3}{(8+6+7) \times 51} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{891} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{89-1} & & := \frac{2+4+3}{(1+5+8) \times 7 \times 6} & & := \frac{2 \times (4+3)}{(8+6) \times (7 \times 51)} \\ &:= \frac{24+3}{8+91} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{16875} &:= \frac{2+43}{1 \times ((6-8+7)^5)} & & := \frac{2^4 \times 3}{8 \times (6 \times (7 \times 51))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{5670} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times (6 \times (7+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{17658} &:= \frac{2+4-3}{1 \times ((7 \times 6 \times 5) + 8)} & & := \frac{2 \times 43}{86 \times (7 \times 51)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{6075} &:= \frac{2-4+3}{60-(7 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{75168} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{(7+51) \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{95760} &:= \frac{24+3}{(9+5) \times 760} \\ &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{6 \times (0+75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{75816} &:= \frac{2-4+3}{(7+(5 \times (8+1))) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{106785} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{10 \times (6+785)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{7695} &:= \frac{2+4-3}{(7-6) \times 95} & & := \frac{2+4-3}{(75+81) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{156870} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{(15+68) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{8019} &:= \frac{2+4-3}{80+19} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{76950} &:= \frac{2+4-3}{(7-6) \times 950} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{156978} &:= \frac{2-4+3}{1-5 \times (6-9 \times (7+8))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{801-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{81756} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{8 \times (1+756)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{157680} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{(1+(5+7) \times 6) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{9576} &:= \frac{24+3}{(9+5) \times 76} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{158679} := \frac{2-4+3}{(1+5+86) \times 7+9}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+70 \times 5) \times 8 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{196875} := \frac{24+3}{(19+6) \times 875}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (4-3)}{15 \times 86+7+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{175608} := \frac{2+4-3}{(1+7 \times 5) \times 60+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{751680} := \frac{2+4+3}{(7+51) \times 6 \times 80}$
$:= \frac{2+4+3}{1+5867+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{175689} := \frac{2+4-3}{(1^7+5 \times 6 \times 8) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{867510} := \frac{2^4 \times 3}{8 \times 6 \times 7 \times 510}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{158760} := \frac{2+4+3}{(1+5+8) \times 7 \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{186705} := \frac{2+4-3}{1+(8 \times 6)^{7-05}}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (4+3)}{(8+6) \times 7 \times 510}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{169785} := \frac{24+3}{(1+6 \times 9) \times 7^{8-5}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{196587} := \frac{2-4+3}{(1+96+5) \times 8-7}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 43}{86 \times 7 \times 510}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{170586} := \frac{2-4+3}{(1+70 \times 5) \times (8-6)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (4-3)}{1+(-9+6 \times 5 \times 8) \times 7}$	

● Numerator 245

$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{980} := \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{9 \times 8+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{38710} := \frac{2+4-5}{(3 \times 8 \times 7)-10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{368970} := \frac{2+4-5}{3 \times (6 \times 8 \times 9+70)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1890} := \frac{2^4+5}{18 \times 9+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{63910} := \frac{2^4+5}{6 \times (3+910)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{893760} := \frac{(2+4)^5}{(8 \times 9)^3 \times 76+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1960} := \frac{24 \times 5}{1 \times 960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{67130} := \frac{2-4+5}{6 \times (7+130)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{903168} := \frac{2^4 \times 5}{9 \times (03+1)^6 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{6370} := \frac{2+4+5}{6^3+70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{137690} := \frac{2+4-5}{1+3 \times 7+6 \times 90}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{6790} := \frac{2^4+5}{6 \times (7+90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{176890} := \frac{2+4-5}{1+7-6+8 \times 90}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{8960} := \frac{2^4+5}{8 \times (96+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{178360} := \frac{2+4-5}{1 \times 7-8+3^6+0}$	

● Numerator 246

$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{738} := \frac{2-4+6}{7-3+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{10578} := \frac{2^4-6}{10 \times (5 \times 7+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{38950} := \frac{24 \times 6}{3 \times (8 \times 950)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3075} := \frac{24-6}{3 \times (0+75)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{31857} := \frac{2 \times 4-6}{(((3+1) \times 8)+5) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{58179} := \frac{2 \times 4-6}{(58 \times (1+7))+9}$
$:= \frac{2-4+6}{(3+07) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{24+6}{3 \times (185 \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{70315} := \frac{24-6}{(7^3) \times 15}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3198} := \frac{2 \times 4-6}{((3-1) \times 9)+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{31980} := \frac{2-4+6}{((3-1)^9)+8+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{73185} := \frac{2 \times 4+6}{(7^{3-1}) \times 85}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3895} := \frac{24 \times 6}{3 \times (8 \times 95)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{35178} := \frac{2+4+6}{(((3^5)+1) \times 7)+8}$	$:= \frac{2-4+6}{7 \times ((3-1) \times 85)}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{246}{81795} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 - 6}{(8 - 1^7) \times 95} &:= \frac{2 - 4 + 6}{(8 - 1 + 7) \times 95} &\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{318570} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 - 6}{((3 + 1) \times 8 + 5) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 6}{(8 - 1) \times (7 \times 95)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{105739} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 6}{1 - 0 + 573 \times 9} &:= \frac{24 + 6}{3 \times 185 \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{24 - 6}{(8 + 1) \times (7 \times 95)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{175398} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 - 6}{1 + 75 \times (3 \times 9 - 8)} \\ & &\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{195078} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 6}{1 + 9507 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 247

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{361} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{3 \times 6 + 1} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{5168} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{(5 - 1) \times 68} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{51680} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{(5 - 1) \times 680} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{589} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{5 \times 8 - 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{5681} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 - 7}{5 \times 6 - (8 - 1)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{56810} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 - 7}{(5 \times 6 \times 8) - 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{836} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{8 + 36} & &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 7}{5 \times (68 + 1)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{95608} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{(9 \times 560) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{1368} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{1 + 3 + 68} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{10963} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{10 + (9 \times 63)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{159068} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 - 7}{(1 + 5 \times 9) \times (06 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{1539} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{(1 + 5 + 3) \times 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{13680} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{1 \times ((3 + 6) \times 80)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{369018} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 - 7}{3 \times 6 \times (90 + 1 - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{1596} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{1 \times ((5 + 9) \times 6)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{15390} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{(1 + 5 + 3) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{1938} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{1 + (93 + 8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{15960} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 7}{1 \times ((5 + 9) \times 60)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 248

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{310} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{3 \times 10} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{1953} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{1 + (9 + 53)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{9765} &:= \frac{(2 + 4) \times 8}{9 \times (7 \times 6 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{1395} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{1 + (39 + 5)} & &:= \frac{24 - 8}{1^9 + 5^3} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{10695} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{1 \times (0 + (69 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{24 + 8}{(1 + 3) \times 9 \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{3069} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{30 + 69} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{13950} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{1^3 \times (9 \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{1 \times (3 \times 9 \times 5)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{306 - 9} & &:= \frac{24 + 8}{(1 + 3) \times (9 \times 50)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{1705} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{170 - 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{3596} &:= \frac{2 - 4 + 8}{3 + ((5 + 9) \times 6)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{1 \times (3 \times (9 \times 50))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{1736} &:= \frac{2 + 48}{1 + (7^3 + 6)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{3906} &:= \frac{24 - 8}{3 \times (90 - 6)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{15376} &:= \frac{2 - 4 + 8}{1 - (5 - 376)} \\ & &\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{6975} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{(6 + 9)^{7-5}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{19375} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 8}{(1+9) \times 375} & \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{193657} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{1+9 \times (3^6 - 5 \times 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{361057} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+8)}{(3+610) \times 57} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{30597} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{((30 \times 5) - 9) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{193750} &:= \frac{2^4 \times 8}{1^9 \times (3+7)^5 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{671305} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 8}{6 \times 71 \times 305} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{90675} &:= \frac{24 - 8}{90 \times ((6+7) \times 5)} & &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 8}{(1+9) \times 3750} & \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{915306} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{9^{1 \times 5} + 3 + 0 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{97650} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 8}{9 \times 7 \times 6 \times 50} & &:= \frac{2 \times 4^8}{(19+3 \times 7)^5 + 0} & &:= \frac{2 \times 48}{(9^{1 \times 5} + 3) \times 06} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{106795} &:= \frac{2^4 - 8}{(10+679) \times 5} & &:= \frac{2 \times 48}{(1+9)^3 \times 75 + 0} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{130975} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+8)}{13 \times 0975} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 249

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{581} &:= \frac{2+4+9}{5 \times (8-1)} & &:= \frac{2+4+9}{(1+8+6) \times 75} & &:= \frac{2+4+9}{15 \times (73+6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{830} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{8 \times 30} & &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 9}{(1+8) \times (6 \times 75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{168075} &:= \frac{2^4 + 9}{1 \times 68 + 07^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{10375} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 9}{10 \times (3 \times 75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{30876} &:= \frac{2+4+9}{30 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{186750} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 9}{(1+8) \times 6 \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{15687} &:= \frac{2-4+9}{1 \times ((56 \times 8) - 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{107568} &:= \frac{2+4+9}{10 \times (75+6) \times 8} & &:= \frac{2-4+9}{(1+8 \times (6+7)) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{2^4 + 9}{1568 + 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{156870} &:= \frac{2-4+9}{(15+6 \times 8) \times 70} & &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{1 \times 8 \times 6750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{18675} &:= \frac{2-4+9}{(1+(8 \times (6+7))) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{157368} &:= \frac{2-4+9}{(1+5) \times (7+3^6) + 8} & &:= \frac{2+4+9}{(1+8+6) \times 750} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{1 \times (8 \times 675)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (4+9)}{(1-5+7^3 \times 6) \times 8} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 251

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{251}{4769} &:= \frac{2^{5-1}}{4 \times (7+69)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (5+1)}{(3 \times (6+8))^{9-7}} & &:= \frac{2+5 \times 1}{96 \times (3 \times 8+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{251}{9036} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 - 1}{9 \times (0+36)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{251}{86093} &:= \frac{2 \times (5-1)}{(8+(6+0 \times 9))^3} & &:= \frac{2 \times 5 - 1}{96 \times (3 \times (8+4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{251}{36897} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 1}{3 \times ((68+9) \times 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{251}{96384} &:= \frac{2+5-1}{(9+63) \times 8 \times 4} & &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 1}{96 \times ((3+8) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{5+1}}{(9-6+3) \times 8^4}$$

$$:= \frac{25-1}{96 \times (3 \times 8 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{308479} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{3 \times 08^4 - 7 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{368970} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 1}{3 \times (68 + 9) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 1)}{(36 - 8) \times 9 \times 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{963840} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 1}{96 \times (3 + 8) \times 40}$$

• Numerator 253

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{7084} := \frac{2 + 5 + 3}{70 \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 5) \times 3}{7 \times (0 + 84)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times 3)}{70 \times (8 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{8096} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 3)}{8^{09-6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{9614} := \frac{2 + 5 + 3}{(96 - 1) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{17986} := \frac{25 - 3}{17 \times (98 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{61479} := \frac{2^{5-3}}{(61 + 47) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{67804} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 3}{67 \times (80 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{96140} := \frac{2 + 5 + 3}{(96 - 1) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{98164} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 3)}{(98 - 1) \times 64}$$

• Numerator 254

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{381} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 4}{3 \times (8 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 4)}{3 \times (8 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 54}{3 + 81}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1397} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 4)}{13 - 9 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 5 - 4}{1 + (39 - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^5 - 4}{(13 + 9) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{8763} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 4)}{87 - (6 \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{13970} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 4)}{1 + (39 + 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^5 - 4}{(13 + 9) \times 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{18796} := \frac{2 - 5 + 4}{1^8 + (79 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 5 - 4}{(18 \times 7) + 96}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 5 + 4}{18 + 796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{30861} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 4)}{3^{0 \times 8 + 6 - 1}}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 5 - 4}{3^{0 \times 8 + 6 \times 1}}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 4)}{3^{0 \times 8 + 6 + 1}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{61087} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 4)}{(61 \times 08) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{183769} := \frac{2 \times 5 - 4}{((1 + 8)^3 - 7) \times 6 + 9}$$

• Numerator 256

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{384} := \frac{2 + 56}{3 + 84}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{704} := \frac{2 \times 5 - 6}{7 + 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{784} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{7 \times 84}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1408} := \frac{2 \times 5 - 6}{14 + 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1984} := \frac{2 \times 5 - 6}{19 + 8 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{7104} := \frac{2 \times 5 - 6}{7 + 104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3840} := \frac{2 + 5 - 6}{3 + (8 + 4 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{7840} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{7 \times 840}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{17408} &:= \frac{2+5-6}{17 \times (4+0 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2-5+6}{17 \times (4+08)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 5-6}{(1-(7-40)) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(2+5) \times 6}{1 \times (7 \times 408)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{73984} &:= \frac{2+5-6}{7+(3 \times (98-4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{93184} &:= \frac{2-5+6}{(9+3+1) \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{98304} &:= \frac{2-5+6}{9 \times (8+(30 \times 4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{137408} &:= \frac{2+5 \times 6}{(1 \times 3^7-40) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{137984} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+6}{(1+3 \times 7) \times 98 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{187904} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-6}{1 \times 8 \times (7+90 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 257

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{257}{3084} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-7}{3 \times (08+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{257}{4369} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-7}{((4+3) \times 6)+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{257}{106398} := \frac{2-5+7}{(1 \times 06^3-9) \times 8}$$

● Numerator 258

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{473} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+8}{(4+7) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{2^5-8}{47-3} \\ &:= \frac{2+5 \times 8}{4+73} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{946} &:= \frac{2+5+8}{9+46} \\ &:= \frac{2^5-8}{94-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1376} &:= \frac{2+5+8}{1+(3+76)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3096} &:= \frac{2^5-8}{3 \times (0+96)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{4730} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+8}{(4+7) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{9073} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+8}{(90 \times 7)+3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{13674} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-8}{(13 \times 6)+7 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{31476} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-8}{(31^4)+7-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{37410} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-8}{3+7 \times 41+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{37496} &:= \frac{2+5+8}{3^7-4-9+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{41796} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+8}{4 \times ((1-7+9)^6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{147963} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-8}{1+4+(7 \times 9 \times 6) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{307149} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+8}{30 \times 714+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{317469} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+8}{(317+4) \times 69} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{371649} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+8}{(3 \times 7-1) \times 6^4+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{469173} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-8}{4^6-9 \times 17 \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 259

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{1036} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-9}{1+(0-3+6)} \\ &:= \frac{2-5+9}{(1+03) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times 9)}{10 \times 36} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{3108} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-9}{3+(1+08)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{6734} &:= \frac{2-5+9}{(6+7) \times (3 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{13468} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-9}{1-(3-(46+8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{14763} &:= \frac{2 \times 5-9}{1+(47+6+3)} \\ &:= \frac{2+5+9}{1 \times (4 \times (76 \times 3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{47138} &:= \frac{2-5+9}{4 \times (7 \times (1+38))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{2+5+9}{4 \times (7 \times (13 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{138047} & := \frac{2 \times 5 - 9}{1^3 + (80 - 4) \times 7} & := \frac{2+59}{3^7 \times 1 \times 40 - 6} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (5 \times 9)}{4^7 + (1 + 3 - 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{147630} & := \frac{2 \times 5 - 9}{(1 - 4 + 7) \times 6 \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{471380} & := \frac{2+5+9}{4 \times 7 \times 13 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{63714} & := \frac{2 \times 5 - 9}{6 \times (37 + 1 \times 4)} & & := \frac{2+5+9}{1 \times 4 \times 76 \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{637140} & := \frac{2^5 + 9}{6 \times (3 + 7^{1+4}) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{67340} & := \frac{2 - 5 + 9}{(6 + 7) \times (3 \times 40)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{371406} & := \frac{2 \times 5 - 9}{(37 - 1) \times 40 - 6} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 260

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{715} & := \frac{2+6+0}{7+15} & \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{43875} & := \frac{2+6+0}{(4+(38 \times 7)) \times 5} & := \frac{2^6+0}{3 \times 9 \times 48 \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{1495} & := \frac{2+6+0}{1^4+9 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{189735} & := \frac{2 \times 60}{18 \times 973 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{18954} & := \frac{2 \times 60}{18 \times (9 \times 54)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{394875} & := \frac{2 \times 6 + 0}{3^{9+4-8} \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 261

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{348} & := \frac{26+1}{3 \times (4+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{38570} & := \frac{2+6+1}{38 \times (5 \times 7 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{359078} & := \frac{2+6+1}{3 \times 590 \times 7 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{783} & := \frac{26-1}{78-3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{49735} & := \frac{26+1}{49 \times (7 \times 3 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{375840} & := \frac{2+6 \times 1}{3 \times (7+5) \times 8 \times 40} \\ & := \frac{26+1}{78+3} & & := \frac{2+61}{49 \times (7 \times 35)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{378450} & := \frac{2+6+1}{(37-8) \times 450} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{957} & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 1}{9+5 \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{53940} & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 1}{(53+9) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{453908} & := \frac{2+6+1}{4 \times (5+3908)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{3857} & := \frac{2+6+1}{(3 \times 8 - 5) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{74095} & := \frac{2+6+1}{7 \times (40 \times 9 + 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{489375} & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 1}{4 \times (8 \times 9 + 3) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{5394} & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 1}{5 + (3^9-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{74385} & := \frac{2+6 \times 1}{(7 \times 4^3 + 8) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{497350} & := \frac{2+61}{49 \times 7 \times 350} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{7859} & := \frac{2+6+1}{(7 \times 8 \times 5) - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{87435} & := \frac{2 \times 6 + 1}{(874 - 3) \times 5} & & := \frac{26+1}{49 \times 7 \times 3 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{37584} & := \frac{2+6 \times 1}{3 \times ((7+5) \times 8 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{348957} & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 1}{3 \times (4+8 \times 95) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{539487} & := \frac{2+6+1}{53 \times 9 \times (4 \times 8 + 7)} \\ & := \frac{2+6+1}{(3 \times (7-5))^{8-4}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{350784} & := \frac{2^{6+1}}{(35+07) \times 8^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{584379} & := \frac{2+6+1}{((5+8) \times 4 + 3^7) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{37845} & := \frac{2+6+1}{(37-8) \times 45} & & := \frac{26-1}{3 \times 50 \times 7 \times 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{735498} & := \frac{2 \times (6+1)}{7 \times (3+5^4 \times 9+8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{261}{743850} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 1}{(7 \times 4^3 + 8) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{261}{859473} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 1}{8 \times (5 \times 94 \times 7 + 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{261}{958740} := \frac{2 + 6 + 1}{95 \times 87 \times 4 + 0}$$

● Numerator 263

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{789} := \frac{2^{6-3}}{7 + 8 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 63}{1 \times (5 \times 78)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{54178} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 3}{((5^4 \times 1) - 7) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{26 - 3}{78 - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{26 \times 3}{(1 + 5) \times 78}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{174895} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 3}{(17 + 4) \times 8 \times 95}$$

$$:= \frac{26 + 3}{78 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{15780} := \frac{2 + 63}{1 \times (5 \times 780)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 - 3)}{(1 - 7 + 48) \times 95}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{1578} := \frac{2 + 6 - 3}{15 + 7 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{26 \times 3}{(1 + 5) \times 780}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{6-3}}{(1 + 7 + 48) \times 95}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 6 + 3}{1 + (57 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{17095} := \frac{2 + 6 + 3}{1 + (709 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 6 + 3}{(1 + 5) \times (7 + 8)}$$

● Numerator 264

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{1980} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{1 + (9 + 80)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{35970} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(3^5 \times 9) - 7 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{159038} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{1 \times 5 + 903 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{3795} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(37 + 9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{37059} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{3^7 + 059}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{189750} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 4}{(18 + 97) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{10395} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 4}{(10 - 3) \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{37158} := \frac{2^{6-4}}{(37 \times 15) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{193875} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(1 + 9 \times 3 \times 87) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{13750} := \frac{2^6 - 4}{(1 - 3 + 7)^5 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{37950} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(37 + 9) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 6 - 4}{(1 + 9^3) \times 8 + 7 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{15708} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{1 + (5 + 708)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{70983} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 4}{(709 + 8) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{371580} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{3 + 7^{1 \times 5} + 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{17358} := \frac{2^{6-4}}{(17 \times 3 \times 5) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{98175} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 4}{(9 + 8) \times 175}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{378510} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 4)}{3 + 7 \times 8^{5-1} + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{18975} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 4}{(18 + 97) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{103785} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 4}{1 \times 037 \times 85}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{153978} := \frac{2^{6-4}}{1 \times 5 + 3 \times 97 \times 8}$$

● Numerator 265

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{1378} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 78} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{3180} := \frac{2-6+5}{3+(1+8+0)} \\ \quad := \frac{2 \times (6-5)}{3 \times (1 \times 8+0)} \\ \quad := \frac{2 \times 6-5}{3+(1+80)} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{13780} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 780} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{17490} := \frac{2-6+5}{1+(74-(9+0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{34980} := \frac{2-6+5}{3+(49+80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{41870} := \frac{2 \times (6-5)}{4 \times (1+(8+70))} \end{array} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{94870} := \frac{2-6+5}{(9 \times 4 \times 8)+70}$$

● Numerator 267

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{534} := \frac{2-6+7}{5-3+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{801} := \frac{2-6+7}{8+01} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{1958} := \frac{2-6+7}{1 \times (9+5+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{4183} := \frac{26+7}{4+(1+(8^3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{4539} := \frac{2+6-7}{(4 \times (5-3))+9} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} := \frac{2-6+7}{(4 \times (5 \times 3))-9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{5340} := \frac{2-6+7}{5 \times (3 \times 4+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{9345} := \frac{2-6+7}{(9+3 \times 4) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{15308} := \frac{2-6+7}{((1+5) \times 30)-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{40851} := \frac{2-6+7}{408+51} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{54913} := \frac{2-6+7}{5^4-(9-1^3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{84105} := \frac{2+6-7}{(8 \times (4 \times 10))-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{93450} := \frac{2-6+7}{(9+3 \times 4) \times 50} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 268

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{1407} := \frac{2-6+8}{14+07} \\ \quad := \frac{2 \times (6+8)}{140+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{3015} := \frac{2-6+8}{3 \times 015} \\ \quad := \frac{2+6+8}{30 \times (1+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{3417} := \frac{2-6+8}{3+41+7} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} := \frac{2+6+8}{3 \times (4 \times 17)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{7035} := \frac{2-6+8}{7 \times 03 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{7504} := \frac{2+6 \times 8}{7 \times (50 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{9045} := \frac{2-6+8}{90+45} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{14539} := \frac{2+6+8}{14 \times (53+9)} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{30954} := \frac{2+6+8}{3 \times (0-(9-(5^4)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{34170} := \frac{2+6+8}{3 \times (4 \times 170)} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 269

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{538} := \frac{2-6+9}{5-3+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{807} := \frac{2-6+9}{8+07} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1345} := \frac{2-6+9}{(1^3+4) \times 5} \\ := \frac{2+6+9}{(13+4) \times 5} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} := \frac{26+9}{(1+34) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{4035} := \frac{2-6+9}{40+35} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{4573} &:= \frac{2 \times 6 - 9}{(4 \times (5 + 7)) + 3} & := \frac{26 + 9}{(1 + 34) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{174850} &:= \frac{2 \times 6 - 9}{(1 \times 7 + 4 \times 8) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{7801} &:= \frac{2 \times 6 - 9}{7 + (80 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{17485} &:= \frac{2 \times 6 - 9}{1 \times ((7 + 4 \times 8) \times 5)} & := \frac{2 - 6 + 9}{(17 + 48) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{13450} &:= \frac{2 - 6 + 9}{(1^3 + 4) \times 50} & := \frac{2 - 6 + 9}{(17 + 48) \times 5} & := \frac{2 + 6 + 9}{(17 - 4) \times 850} \\ & := \frac{2 + 6 + 9}{(13 + 4) \times 50} & := \frac{2 + 6 + 9}{(17 - 4) \times 85} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{81507} &:= \frac{2 - 6 + 9}{8 + 1507} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 271

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{271}{4065} &:= \frac{2 + 7 - 1}{4 \times (0 + 6 \times 5)} & := \frac{27 \times 1}{894 - 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{271}{8943} &:= \frac{2 + 7 - 1}{8 \times (9 \times 4 - 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{271}{30894} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 1)}{(30 + 8) \times (9 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 273

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{416} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{4 \times 16} & := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 4 \times 56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{18564} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 3)}{(18 \times 5 \times 6) + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{468} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{4 + 68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{4095} &:= \frac{2 + 7 + 3}{4 \times (0 + 9 \times 5)} & := \frac{27 + 3}{1 \times (85 \times 6 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{546} &:= \frac{27 - 3}{54 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{4160} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{4 \times 160} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{85904} &:= \frac{2 + 7 - 3}{8 \times (59 \times 04)} \\ & := \frac{(2 + 7) \times 3}{(5 + 4) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{5460} &:= \frac{2 + 7 - 3}{5 \times (4 \times 6 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{149058} &:= \frac{2 + 7 \times 3}{14 \times (905 - 8)} \\ & := \frac{27 + 3}{54 + 6} & & := \frac{2^{7-3}}{5 \times (4 + 60)} & := \frac{27 + 3}{14 \times 90 \times (5 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{819} &:= \frac{2 + 7 - 3}{8 + 1 + 9} & & := \frac{(2 + 7) \times 3}{(5 + 4) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{165984} &:= \frac{2^7 \times 3}{(1 + 65 - 9) \times 8^4} \\ & := \frac{27 - 3}{8 \times (1 \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{8190} &:= \frac{27 - 3}{8 \times (1 \times 90)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{185094} &:= \frac{2 + 7 - 3}{1 \times 8 \times 509 - 4} \\ & := \frac{(2 + 7) \times 3}{(8 + 1) \times 9} & & := \frac{(2 + 7) \times 3}{(8 + 1) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{185640} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 3)}{1 \times 85 \times 64 + 0} \\ & := \frac{27 + 3}{81 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{10465} &:= \frac{2 + 7 - 3}{1 \times (0 + (46 \times 5))} & := \frac{27 + 3}{1 \times 85 \times 6 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{910} &:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times 3}{9 \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{14560} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times (4 \times 560)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{186459} &:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times 3}{(1 + (8 - 6) \times 4^5) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1456} &:= \frac{2 + 7 + 3}{(1 - 4 + 5)^6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{195468} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{(1 \times 9 + 5^4 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{598416} := \frac{27 + 3}{(5 + 9 + 8^4) \times 16}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{459186} := \frac{2 \times (7 - 3)}{4 \times (59 - 1)^{8-6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{645918} := \frac{2 + 7 + 3}{6 \times (4 + 591 \times 8)}$$

● Numerator 274

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{8905} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 4)}{(8 \times 90) - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{19865} := \frac{2 \times (7 - 4)}{(1^9 + 86) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{695138} := \frac{2 + 7 \times 4}{6 + 9513 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{18906} := \frac{2 + 7 + 4}{1 + (890 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{198650} := \frac{2 \times (7 - 4)}{(1^9 + 86) \times 50}$$

● Numerator 275

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{275}{360481} := \frac{2 \times 75}{3 \times (6 + 04^8 \times 1)}$$

● Numerator 276

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{483} := \frac{2 \times 7 + 6}{4 \times 8 + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 7 - 6}{1 \times ((8^3) + 5 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 7 + 6}{(105 - 9) \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{1380} := \frac{2 - 7 + 6}{13 - (8 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{59340} := \frac{2 - 7 + 6}{5 \times (9 + (34 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 6)}{(10 + 5 + 9) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{1840} := \frac{(2 + 7) \times 6}{(1 + 8) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 7 - 6}{5 \times (9 + (3 \times 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 7 - 6}{(105 - 9) \times (8 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{4830} := \frac{2 \times (7 - 6)}{4 \times 8 + 3 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{93150} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6}{9 \times 3150}$$

$$:= \frac{27 - 6}{(105 - 9) \times 84}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{9108} := \frac{2 + 7 - 6}{91 + 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{93840} := \frac{2 - 7 + 6}{(93 - 8) \times (4 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{148350} := \frac{2 \times (7 - 6)}{1 + 4^{8-3} + 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{9315} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6}{9 \times 315}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{105984} := \frac{2 \times 7 - 6}{(105 - 9) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{318504} := \frac{2 - 7 + 6}{(31 - 8) \times 50 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{13984} := \frac{2 + 7 + 6}{1 + (3 + (9 \times 84))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times 6}{(-1 \times 05 + 9 + 8)^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{18354} := \frac{2 \times (7 - 6)}{1 - (8 - (35 \times 4))}$$

● Numerator 278

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{695} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 8)}{(6 + 9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{1390} := \frac{(2 + 7) \times 8}{(1 + 3) \times 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{1946} := \frac{2 + 7 - 8}{1 \times (9 + 4 - 6)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{2-7+8}{19-4+6} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 8}{1 \times (9 \times 4 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{3614} & := \frac{2+7-8}{3+(6+1 \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{2-7+8}{36-1+4} \\
 & := \frac{27-8}{3+(61 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{6394} & := \frac{2+7-8}{((6-3) \times 9) - 4} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 8}{6 \times (3 \times 9 - 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{6950} & := \frac{2-7+8}{(6+9) \times (5+0)} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(6+9) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{10564} & := \frac{2-7+8}{(10 \times (5+6)) + 4} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 8}{(1+056) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{14039} & := \frac{(2+7) \times 8}{(1+403) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{2+78}{1+4039} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{19460} & := \frac{2+7-8}{(19 \times 4) - (6+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{39615} & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 8}{(3+(9 \times 6)) \times 15} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{45036} & := \frac{2+7-8}{(4+(5+0)) \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{2-7+8}{(4+50) \times (3+6)} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 8}{(4+50) \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{27-8}{((4^5+0) \times 3) + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{63940} & := \frac{2+7-8}{(6 \times 39) - 4 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{103694} & := \frac{2^7 + 8}{103 + (6+9)^4} \\
 & := \frac{2+7-8}{1 \times 0369 + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{278}{396150} & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 8}{(3+9 \times 6) \times 150} \\
 & := \frac{2+7-8}{3 \times (96-1) \times 5+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 279

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{341} & := \frac{27+9}{3+41} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{1860} & := \frac{2+79}{(1+8) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{4185} & := \frac{2-7+9}{(4+1 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{6138} & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 9}{6+(13 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{13485} & := \frac{27+9}{1 \times (348 \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{14508} & := \frac{2-7+9}{1 \times ((4 \times 50) + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{41850} & := \frac{2-7+9}{(4+1 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{63054} & := \frac{2-7+9}{(6 \times (30 \times 5)) + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{134850} & := \frac{27+9}{1 \times 348 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{143685} & := \frac{2-7+9}{1+4+3 \times 685} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{145638} & := \frac{2-7+9}{(1 \times 45 + 6^3) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{346518} & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 9}{3 \times 46 \times 5 \times (1+8)} \\
 & := \frac{2-7+9}{3 \times 4 \times (6+51 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{361584} & := \frac{2 \times 7 - 9}{36 \times 15 \times (8+4)} \\
 & := \frac{2+7+9}{3 \times 6^{15+8-4}} \\
 & := \frac{2+79}{(3 \times 6 \times 15^8)^4} \\
 & := \frac{27 \times 9}{3 \times (6-1+5+8)^4} \\
 & := \frac{27+9}{36^{15-8-4}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{279}{813564} & := \frac{2 \times (7+9)}{8 \times (1+3+5) \times 6^4} \\
 & := \frac{2+7+9}{(8+1) \times 3^5 \times 6 \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 280

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{315} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{3 + 15} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{364} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{3 + 6 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{476} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{4 + 7 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{735} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{7 + 35} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{945} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 45} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1365} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{13 + 65} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1456} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{1 + (45 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{4375} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{(43 + 7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{4536} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{(4 + 5) \times 3 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{16975} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{1 - (6 - 975)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{280}{179354} &:= \frac{2 \times 80}{1 + 7 \times (9 - 3 + 5)^4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 281

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{281}{37654} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 1)}{376 \times 5 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{281}{307695} &:= \frac{2 + 8 \times 1}{(3^{07} - 6 + 9) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 283

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{283}{5094} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 3)}{5 \times (0 + 9 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{283}{17546} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 3)}{1^7 + (5^4 - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 284

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{639} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 4)}{6 + 3 + 9} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 4}{(6 - 3) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (8 + 4)}{63 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^8) - 4}{63 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{1065} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 4)}{1 \times (0 + 6 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{10 + 65} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{3195} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 4)}{(3 - 1) \times 9 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 4}{3 \times (1 \times 9 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2^{8-4}}{(3 + 1) \times 9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{3905} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{(3 \times 90) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{6390} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 4}{(6 - 3) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{(2^8) - 4}{63 \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{17395} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 4}{1 + (739 - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^8) - 4}{1 \times ((7^3) \times 9 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{30175} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 + 4)}{30 \times (17 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{31950} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 4)}{(3 - 1) \times (9 \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 4}{3 \times (1 \times (9 \times 50))} \\ &:= \frac{2^{8-4}}{(3 + 1) \times (9 \times 50)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{57936} &:= \frac{2 + 8 - 4}{(5 + 7 \times 9) \times 3 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 4}{(5 + 7 \times 9) \times 36} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{67095} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 4)}{6 \times (7 \times (0 + 9 \times 5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{73059} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 4}{(7^{3+0 \times 5}) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{173950} &:= \frac{(2^8) - 4}{1 \times 7^3 \times 9 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{284}{613795} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 + 4)}{6 \times 13 \times 7 \times 95} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 285

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{361} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{3 \times 6 + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{13794} &:= \frac{2 + 8 - 5}{1 + ((3 \times 79) + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{143697} &:= \frac{2 + 8 - 5}{1 + (4 + 36) \times 9 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1064} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{(10 \times 6) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{14763} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{14 + 763} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{173964} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{1 \times 7 \times (3 + 9 + 6^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1463} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{14 + 63} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{17936} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{1 + (7 + 936)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{179436} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{1 + 7 + 9436} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1976} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{1 + (97 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{47196} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{(47 - 1) \times 9 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{379601} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{37 \times 9 \times 60 - 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{4731} &:= \frac{2 + 8 - 5}{(4 \times 7 \times 3) - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{74613} &:= \frac{2 + 8 - 5}{7 \times (4 + (61 \times 3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{285}{10963} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 5}{10 + (9 \times 63)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 286

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{715} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 6}{(7 + 1) \times 5} & & := \frac{2 + 8 + 6}{15 + 73} & \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{14950} &:= \frac{28 - 6}{(14 + 9) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1495} &:= \frac{28 - 6}{(14 + 9) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{3159} &:= \frac{28 - 6}{3^{1-5+9}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{19734} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 6}{(1 + 9) \times (73 - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1573} &:= \frac{2^{8-6}}{1^5 + 7 \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{4719} &:= \frac{2^{8-6}}{4 + (71 - 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{54197} &:= \frac{2^{8-6}}{5^4 + (19 \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (8 + 6)}{157 - 3} & & := \frac{2 \times (8 + 6)}{471 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 - 6}{1 + (57 - 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{286}{7150} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 6}{(7 + 1) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 287

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{369} &:= \frac{28 - 7}{36 - 9} & & := \frac{2 + 8 - 7}{1^4 \times 3 \times 5} & & := \frac{28 + 7}{(1 + 4) \times 35} \\ &:= \frac{28 + 7}{3 \times (6 + 9)} & & := \frac{2 - 8 + 7}{1 - (4 - 3 - 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1640} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 \times 7}{1 \times 640} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{451} &:= \frac{28 + 7}{4 + 51} & & := \frac{2 + 8 + 7}{(14 + 3) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{6314} &:= \frac{2 + 8 - 7}{63 - 1 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1435} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 7)}{(1 + 4 - 3) \times 5} & & & & := \frac{2 - 8 + 7}{6 \times 3 \times 1 + 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{14063} &:= \frac{2-8+7}{1 \times (40+6+3)} & := \frac{2+8-7}{1 \times ((6^3) - (5 \times 9))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{109634} &:= \frac{2-8+7}{10+(96-3) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{14350} &:= \frac{2 \times (8-7)}{(1+4-3) \times 50} & := \frac{2-8+7}{1-(6-(3+59))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{154693} &:= \frac{2-8+7}{1+5^4+6-93} \\ & := \frac{2+8-7}{1^4 \times 3 \times 50} & := \frac{2 \times (8+7)}{((1+6) \times 3^5)+9} & & := \frac{2 \times (8-7)}{1+5 \times 4 \times 6 \times 9-3} \\ & := \frac{2-8+7}{1-(4-(3+50))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{35014} &:= \frac{2 \times (8-7)}{(3^5+0)+1^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{163590} &:= \frac{2+8-7}{1 \times 6 \times 3 \times (5+90)} \\ & := \frac{2+8+7}{(14+3) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{49036} &:= \frac{28-7}{4 \times (903-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{169043} &:= \frac{2-8+7}{1-(6-90) \times (4+3)} \\ & := \frac{28+7}{(1+4) \times 350} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{63140} &:= \frac{2-8+7}{(6^{3 \times 1})+4+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{340956} &:= \frac{2-8+7}{3 \times 4 \times 09 \times (5+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{16359} &:= \frac{2 \times (8-7)}{((1+6) \times 3 \times 5)+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{287}{96145} &:= \frac{2-8+7}{((9 \times (6+1))+4) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 289

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{306} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{30+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{7514} &:= \frac{2+8-9}{7+(5+14)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{137564} &:= \frac{2-8+9}{137-5+6^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{357} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{35+7} & &:= \frac{2-8+9}{75-1+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{163574} &:= \frac{2 \times 8-9}{16 \times 3^5+74} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{561} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+61} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{16473} &:= \frac{2+8-9}{1+(6+(47+3))} & &:= \frac{2-8+9}{1+(6-3)^5 \times 7-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1530} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(1+5) \times 30} & &:= \frac{2-8+9}{1 \times ((6 \times (4 \times 7))+3)} & &:= \frac{2+8-9}{1-6-3+574} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1734} &:= \frac{2+8-9}{1 \times (7+3-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{17340} &:= \frac{2+8-9}{17+(3+40)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{164730} &:= \frac{2-8+9}{(1 \times 64-7) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{2-8+9}{1+(7 \times 3-4)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{17 \times (3 \times 40)} & &:= \frac{2+8-9}{(1-6 \times (4-7)) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{2 \times 8-9}{1+(7+34)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{53176} &:= \frac{2+8-9}{5+(3+176)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{310675} &:= \frac{2+8-9}{3+1067+5} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{17 \times (3 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{289}{73406} &:= \frac{2-8+9}{(7+(3 \times 40)) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 290

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{856341} := \frac{2 \times 90}{(8 + 5^6) \times 34 \times 1}$$

● Numerator 291

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{873} := \frac{29 - 1}{87 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + 1}{87 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{4365} := \frac{2 + 9 + 1}{4 \times ((3 + 6) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{4753} := \frac{2 + 9 + 1}{4 \times (7^{5-3})}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{8536} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 1}{(85 + 3) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{43650} := \frac{2 + 9 + 1}{4 \times ((3 + 6) \times 50)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{45687} := \frac{2 \times (9 + 1)}{4 + (56 \times 8 \times 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{48306} := \frac{2 + 9 + 1}{4 \times (83 \times 06)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{54708} := \frac{2 + 9 - 1}{5 \times (47 \times 08)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{76048} := \frac{2 + 9 + 1}{7 \times ((60 - 4) \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{85360} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 1}{(85 + 3) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{376845} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 1}{37 \times (6 + 8) \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{856704} := \frac{2^9 \times 1}{8^5 \times (6 \times 7 + 04)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 9 \times 1}{(8 \times 5 + 6) \times 704}$$

● Numerator 293

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{586} := \frac{29 - 3}{58 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + 3}{58 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{1465} := \frac{2 + 9 - 3}{(14 - 6) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 9 + 3}{1 + (4 + 65)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 3)}{1 \times (4 \times 6 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{1758} := \frac{2 + 9 - 3}{1 + (7 + 5 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 9 + 3}{1 + (75 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{5860} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 3)}{5 \times (8 \times (6 + 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{10548} := \frac{2 + 9 - 3}{(1 + 05) \times 48}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - 3)}{1 \times (0 + (54 \times 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{14650} := \frac{2 + 9 - 3}{(14 - 6) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 3)}{1 \times (4 \times (6 \times 50))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{16408} := \frac{2 + 9 - 3}{(16 + 40) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{17580} := \frac{2 + 9 - 3}{(1^7 + 5) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{46587} := \frac{2 \times (9 + 3)}{4^6 - 5 \times 8 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{147086} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 3)}{1 \times 4 + 70 \times 86}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{748615} := \frac{(2 + 9) \times 3}{(7^4 + 8) \times (6 + 1) \times 5}$$

● Numerator 294

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{315} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{3 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{378} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{3 + 7 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{651} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{6 \times 5 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{756} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{7 + 5 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1365} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{1^3 \times 65}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1386} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{1 + (38 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{1 \times ((3 + 8) \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1638} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{1^6 + 38}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1680} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{1^6 \times 80}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1785} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{17 \times 85}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{15078} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{1 + ((50 \times 7) + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{71568} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{71 \times (56 - 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1806} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{1 \times (80 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{15876} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{(1^5 + 8) \times 7 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{107856} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{(10 - 7) \times 856}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3150} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{3 \times 1 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{158760} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 4)}{(1 + 5) \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{158760} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 4)}{(1 + 5) \times (8 + 7) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3570} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{3 \times 5 + 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{17850} := \frac{29 - 4}{15 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{173586} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{(1^5 + 8) \times 7 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3675} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 4)}{(3 \times 6 + 7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{18375} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{17 \times 850}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{183750} := \frac{29 - 4}{15 \times (8 + 7) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3780} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{3 + (7 + 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{18375} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 4)}{1 + (8 \times (3 + 75))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{173586} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{(17 \times 3^5) + 8 - 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{7350} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 4)}{7 + (3^5 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{183750} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{(1 + 8 \times 3) \times 7 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{183750} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{(1 + 8 \times 3) \times 7 \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{7035} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{(70 - 3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{18753} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{18 + (7 \times (5^3))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{376810} := \frac{2 \times (9^4)}{(3^7 + 6^8) \times 10}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{10836} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{10 + ((8^3) - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{30618} := \frac{2 + 9 - 4}{3^{06 \times 18}}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{13650} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{1^3 \times 650}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{36750} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 4)}{(3 \times 6 + 7) \times 50}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{13860} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 4}{1 \times ((3 + 8) \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{37681} := \frac{2 \times (9^4)}{3^7 + (6^8 \times 1)}$	

• Numerator 295

$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{3481} := \frac{(2 + 9) \times 5}{(3^4 \times 8) + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{31860} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 5)}{3 + (1 + 860)}$
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• Numerator 296

$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{370} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{3 + 7 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{814} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{8 + 14}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{4107} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{4 + 107}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{407} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{4 + 07}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{1480} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{(1 + 4) \times (8 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{13875} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{(13 - 8) \times 75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{481} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{4 + 8 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{1850} := \frac{2 + 9 + 6}{1 + (4 + 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{14578} := \frac{2 + (9 \times 6)}{1 \times (3 \times 875)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{518} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{5 + 1 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{1850} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{1^8 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{14578} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{1 \times (4 + (5 \times 78))}$
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{3145} := \frac{2^{9-6}}{(3 + 14) \times 5}$	

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{296}{31450} &:= \frac{2^{9-6}}{(3+14) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{296}{138750} &:= \frac{2^{9-6}}{(13-8) \times 750} & \blacktriangleright \frac{296}{318570} &:= \frac{2^{9-6}}{3 \times (1+8 \times 5) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{296}{31857} &:= \frac{2^{9-6}}{3+(1+857)} & &:= \frac{2+9 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 8750} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{296}{37851} &:= \frac{2^{9-6}}{((3-7+8)^5)-1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{296}{185037} &:= \frac{2^{9-6}}{1+8 \times 5^{-03+7}} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 297

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{486} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{4 + 8 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3168} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{(3 + 1) \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{14850} &:= \frac{2^{9-7}}{(1 + 4) \times (8 \times (5 + 0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{540} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{5 \times (4 + 0)} & &:= \frac{29 + 7}{3 \times (16 \times 8)} & &:= \frac{29 - 7}{(14 + 8) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{864} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{8 + 6 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3465} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{(3 + 4) \times 6 \times 5} & &:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 7)}{1 \times (4 \times 8 \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{29 - 7}{8^{6-4}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3564} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{3 \times ((5 + 6) \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{15840} &:= \frac{29 + 7}{(1 + 5) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1350} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{1^3 \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3645} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(3 + 6 \times 4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{16038} &:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 7)}{1 \times ((6^{03}) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 9) \times 7}{1 \times 350} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3861} &:= \frac{2^{9-7}}{3 + (8 \times 6 + 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{16830} &:= \frac{29 + 7}{1 \times (68 \times 30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1386} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{1 - (3 - 86)} & &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(3 \times 8 \times 6) - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{18456} &:= \frac{2 + 97}{1 \times (8 + (4^5 \times 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1458} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{1 + (45 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{4158} &:= \frac{2^{9-7}}{4 \times (1 + 5 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{31548} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{((3^{1 \times 5}) - 4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1485} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{1 + (4 + 85)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{5184} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(5 + 1) \times 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{31680} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{(3 + 1) \times 6 \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{29 - 7}{(14 + 8) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{5346} &:= \frac{2^{9-7}}{(5 + 3 + 4) \times 6} & &:= \frac{29 + 7}{3 \times (16 \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 9 + 7}{(1 + 4)^{8-5}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{6048} &:= \frac{29 - 7}{(60 - 4) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{34650} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{(3 + 4) \times (6 \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 7)}{1 \times (4 \times 8 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{6318} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{6 \times (31 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{35046} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{(350 + 4) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1584} &:= \frac{29 + 7}{(1 + 5) \times 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{6804} &:= \frac{29 - 7}{6 \times (80 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{35640} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{3 \times ((5 + 6) \times 40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1680} &:= \frac{2 + 97}{(1 + 6) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{8316} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 7}{(83 + 1) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{36450} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(3 + 6 \times 4) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1683} &:= \frac{29 + 7}{1 \times (68 \times 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{13608} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{1 \times ((3 + 60) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{51840} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(5 + 1) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1854} &:= \frac{2 + 97}{1 - (8 - (5^4))} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{53460} := \frac{2^{9-7}}{(5+3+4) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{163548} := \frac{29+7}{(1+6) \times 354 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{354186} := \frac{29-7}{(3 \times 5^4 - 1) \times (8+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{83106} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{((8^3) + 1 + 0) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{183546} := \frac{2^{9-7}}{(1+83 \times 5 - 4) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{368145} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(3+681 \times 4) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{83160} := \frac{2+9+7}{(83+1) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{183654} := \frac{29-7}{18^3 + 6^5 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{483165} := \frac{2+97}{4+(8+3 \times 1^6)^5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{135486} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(1 \times 3 + 5^4) \times 8 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{184305} := \frac{2+97}{(-1+8^4 \times 3) \times 05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{653184} := \frac{2+97}{6^5 \times (3 \times 1 \times 8 + 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{153468} := \frac{2 \times 9 - 7}{(1+5 \times 3^4) \times (6+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{184635} := \frac{2+97}{(1+8^4+6) \times 3 \times 5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{153846} := \frac{2+9 \times 7}{(15^3 - 8) \times (4+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{186354} := \frac{29-7}{(18+6)^3 - 5 \times 4}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{315480} := \frac{2+9+7}{(3^{1 \times 5} - 4) \times 80}$	

● Numerator 298

$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{1043} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{1 \times 04 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{35164} := \frac{2-9+8}{3-(5 \times (1-(6 \times 4)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{5 \times (3 \times (6 \times (4+0)))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{3576} := \frac{2-9+8}{3 \times (5-7+6)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{(3 \times (5 \times 16)) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{60345} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{(6+03) \times 45}$
$:= \frac{2+9-8}{35+7-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{35760} := \frac{2-9+8}{3+(57+60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{61537} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{(6+(1 \times 53)) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times 8)}{3 \times 576}$	$:= \frac{2+9-8}{(3+57) \times (6+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{74351} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{(7 \times 4^3) + 51}$
$:= \frac{2+9+8}{(3+5 \times 7) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times 8)}{3 \times 5760}$	$:= \frac{(2+9) \times 8}{(7 \times 4)^3 + 5 - 1}$
$:= \frac{29-8}{(35+7) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{2+9+8}{(3+5 \times 7) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{153470} := \frac{2-9+8}{15 \times 3 + 470}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{5364} := \frac{2-9+8}{5+(3+6+4)}$	$:= \frac{29-8}{(35+7) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{170456} := \frac{2+9-8}{(1+70 \times 4+5) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{2 \times 9-8}{5 \times ((3+6) \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{43657} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{(43 \times 6) + 5 \times 7}$	$:= \frac{29-8}{1+7^04 \times 5+6}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{(5 \times 3-6) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{51703} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{5-(1-(7^03))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{350746} := \frac{2+9-8}{3507+4 \times 6}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times 8)}{(5-3) \times (6^4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{53640} := \frac{2-9+8}{5 \times ((3+6) \times (4+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{436570} := \frac{2 \times 9-8}{4 \times 3^6 \times 5+70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{7301} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{7^{3-01}}$	$:= \frac{2+9-8}{536+4+0}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{15347} := \frac{2 \times (9-8)}{15+((3^4)+7)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 9-8}{5 \times ((3+6) \times 40)}$	

● Numerator 301

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{7826} &:= \frac{3-01}{78-26} \\ &:= \frac{3^{01}}{(7+8-2) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3+01}{78+26} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{8729} &:= \frac{3-01}{87-29} \\ &:= \frac{3+01}{87+29} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{26789} &:= \frac{3-01}{267-89} \\ &:= \frac{3^{01}}{(2-6+7) \times 89} \\ &:= \frac{3+01}{267+89} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{48762} &:= \frac{3-01}{4 \times ((8+7-6)^2)} \\ &:= \frac{3+01}{4 \times ((87-6) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{52976} &:= \frac{3^{01}}{529-7+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{56287} &:= \frac{3^{01}}{562-8+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{97524} &:= \frac{3-01}{(9^{7-5}) \times 2 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{3+01}{(9+(7-(5 \times 2)))^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{97825} &:= \frac{3-01}{(9+(7 \times 8)) \times 2 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3^{01}}{(97 \times (8+2)) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{264579} &:= \frac{3^{01}}{((2^6-4) \times 5-7) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{285649} &:= \frac{3-01}{2 \times (8+5) \times (64+9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{296485} &:= \frac{3-01}{(2+96 \times 4+8) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{301}{926478} &:= \frac{3^{01}}{9^2 \times 6 \times (4+7+8)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 302

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{8154} &:= \frac{3-02}{8-(1-(5 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{3+0 \times 2}{(8-1 \times 5)^4} \\ &:= \frac{3+02}{81+54} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 01}{8+154} \\ &:= \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{8456} &:= \frac{3-02}{84-56} \\ &:= \frac{3+02}{84+56} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 01}{(8+4 \times 5) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{14798} &:= \frac{3-02}{1+((4-7+9) \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 2}{147 \times (9-8)} \\ &:= \frac{3+02}{1+((4 \times 7 \times 9)-8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{41978} &:= \frac{3-02}{4+(1 \times (9 \times (7+8)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{57984} &:= \frac{3-02}{(57-9) \times (8-4)} \\ &:= \frac{3+0 \times 2}{(57-9) \times (8+4)} \\ &:= \frac{3+02}{5 \times ((7+9) \times (8+4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{74896} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 2}{((74+8) \times 9) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{85617} &:= \frac{3 \times 01}{((8-5)^{6-1}) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{157946} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 2}{1579-4-6} \\ &:= \frac{3-02}{1 \times 57 \times 9+4+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{184975} &:= \frac{3 \times 01}{(1+8 \times (4+9)) \times 7 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{417968} &:= \frac{3-02}{4 \times (1+7^{9-6}+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{461758} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 2}{4+61 \times 75+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{302}{841976} &:= \frac{3 \times 01}{8 \times 41 \times (9+7 \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 304

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{912} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 4}{9 \times 1^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{12768} &:= \frac{30+4}{(1+2) \times (7 \times 68)} & & := \frac{3^{04}}{(5+(2^8)) \times 9 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3+04}{9+12} & & := \frac{3+0 \times 4}{1 \times (2^7+6-8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{58976} &:= \frac{30 \times 4}{5 \times (8 \times (97 \times 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1672} &:= \frac{3 \times 04}{1+(67-2)} & & := \frac{3+04}{(1+2) \times (7 \times (6+8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{157928} &:= \frac{3 \times 04}{1^5+79^2-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{5168} &:= \frac{3+04}{51+68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{27968} &:= \frac{3+04}{2 \times (7 \times (9 \times 6-8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{176928} &:= \frac{3 \times 04}{1 \times 76 \times 92-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{7296} &:= \frac{3+04}{7 \times (2 \times 9+6)} & & := \frac{3 \times 04}{2 \times ((7 \times 9+6) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{561792} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 4}{56 \times (1 \times 7+92)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{8512} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 4}{85-1^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{304}{52896} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 4}{5 \times 2+(8^{9-6})} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 305

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{427} &:= \frac{30+5}{42+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{4697} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{(4 \times 6+9) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{71248} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{(71+2) \times 48} \\ &:= \frac{30-5}{42-7} & & := \frac{30-5}{(46+9) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{217648} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{(217+6) \times 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{671} &:= \frac{30+5}{6+71} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{19642} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{1 \times (964+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{218746} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{21 \times 8^{7-4}+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{2196} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{2 \times (1 \times 9 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{19764} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{1 \times (976-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{948672} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{9 \times (4+8) \times 6 \times 72} \\ &:= \frac{30-5}{(21+9) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{61427} &:= \frac{30+5}{((6 \times 14)^2)-7} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{305}{2684} &:= \frac{3 \times 05}{(2 \times 68)-4} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 306

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{459} &:= \frac{30+6}{45+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{782} &:= \frac{3+06}{7+8 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1275} &:= \frac{30+6}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{30-6}{45-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{918} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 6}{9 \times 1^8} & & := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{714} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 6}{7 \times 1^4} & & := \frac{3+06}{9+18} & \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1428} &:= \frac{3+0 \times 6}{1 \times (4+2+8)} \\ &:= \frac{3+06}{7+14} & & := \frac{30-6}{9 \times 1 \times 8} & & := \frac{3+06}{14+28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{748} &:= \frac{30+6}{(7+4) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{306}{952} &:= \frac{3+06}{(9+5) \times 2} & & := \frac{30-6}{1 \times (4 \times 28)} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1598} := \frac{3 \times 06}{1 - (5 - 98)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{12495} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1 + 2) \times (49 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{30 - 6}{(49 + 5) \times 72}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1972} := \frac{3 + 06}{1 \times (9 + 7^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{12954} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{1 + (2 \times (9 + 54))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{58429} := \frac{3 \times 06}{5 + (8 \times 429)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{2584} := \frac{3 + 06}{(2 \times (5 \times 8)) - 4}$	$:= \frac{3 + 06}{1^2 + (95 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{59874} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{598 - (7 + 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{2754} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{27 \times (5 - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{14875} := \frac{3 \times 06}{1^4 \times 875}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{89471} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(8 \times (94 \times 7)) - 1}$
$:= \frac{3 + 06}{2 + (75 + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{14892} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{(1^4 + (8 \times 9)) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{92718} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{927 - 18}$
$:= \frac{3^{06}}{(2 \times 7 - 5)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{17289} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1 + (7 \times 2 \times 8)) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{3 + 06}{9 + 2718}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{2958} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{2 - (9 \times (5 - 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{17459} := \frac{3 \times 06}{1 - (7 - (4^5 + 9))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{95472} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{9 \times ((5 + 47) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{3 + 06}{29 + 58}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{17952} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{179 - 5 + 2}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 06}{(9 \times 5^4) - (7 + 2)}$
$:= \frac{3 \times 06}{2 \times (95 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{19584} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{(1^9 + 5) \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{129574} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(12 \times 9 - 5) \times 74}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{4182} := \frac{3 + 06}{41 + 82}$	$:= \frac{3 + 06}{1 - (9 - 584)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{178942} := \frac{3 + 06}{1 + 7 \times 8 \times 94 - 2}$
$:= \frac{3 \times 06}{41 \times (8 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 06}{(1 + 95) \times (8 + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{278154} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{27 \times (81 + 5 \times 4)}$
$:= \frac{30 - 6}{4 \times (1 \times 82)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{27948} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(2^7 + 9) \times (4 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{3 + 06}{27 + 8154}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{5712} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{57 - 1^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{29784} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{(2 + (9 \times 7 + 8)) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{892415} := \frac{30 + 6}{8 + (9 \times 2)^4 + 1 + 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{5814} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{58 - 1^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{41752} := \frac{3 + 06}{4 - (1 - ((7 \times 5)^2))}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{7259} := \frac{3 \times 06}{7 \times (2 + 59)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{49572} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{495 - (7 + 2)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{7854} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 6}{78 - 5 + 4}$		

● Numerator 307

$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{614} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 7}{6 \times 1^4}$	$:= \frac{3 + 07}{9 + 21}$	$:= \frac{3^{07}}{((1 + 8)^4) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{3 + 07}{6 + 14}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{1842} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 7}{(1 + 8) \times (4 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{2149} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 7}{((2 + 1) \times 4) + 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{921} := \frac{3 + 0 \times 7}{9 \times (2 - 1)}$	$:= \frac{3 + 07}{18 + 42}$	$:= \frac{3 + 07}{21 + 49}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{3 \times 07}{(2+1) \times 49} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{2456} & := \frac{3+0 \times 7}{(2 \times (4+5)) + 6} \\ & := \frac{3+07}{24+56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{4298} & := \frac{3+0 \times 7}{42 \times (9-8)} \\ & := \frac{3+07}{42+98} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{4912} & := \frac{3+0 \times 7}{4 \times (9+1+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{5219} & := \frac{3+0 \times 7}{52-1^9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{9824} & := \frac{3+0 \times 7}{98+2-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{12894} & := \frac{3+07}{((12 \times 8) + 9) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{15964} & := \frac{3+0 \times 7}{1 \times ((5 \times 9 - 6) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{30+7}{(1+(5 \times 96)) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{307}{19648} & := \frac{3+0 \times 7}{(1+9-6) \times 48} \\ & := \frac{3+07}{1-(9-648)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 308

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{476} & := \frac{3+08}{4+7+6} \\ & := \frac{30-8}{4 \times 7+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{924} & := \frac{3+08}{9+24} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 08}{9 \times 2 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{952} & := \frac{3+08}{9+5^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1456} & := \frac{3+08}{1+(45+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1624} & := \frac{3+08}{1 \times (62-4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1652} & := \frac{3+08}{1+(6+52)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1792} & := \frac{3+08}{(17-9)^2} \\ & := \frac{30-8}{(1+7 \times 9) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{2156} & := \frac{3+0 \times 8}{((2+1) \times 5) + 6} \\ & := \frac{3+08}{21+56} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{3 \times 08}{(2+1) \times 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{4256} & := \frac{3+08}{4 \times (2^5+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{15624} & := \frac{3+08}{1 \times (562-4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{16492} & := \frac{3+08}{1+(6 \times (49 \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{21756} & := \frac{3+08}{21 \times (7+5 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{21945} & := \frac{3 \times 08}{2 \times (19 \times 45)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{29456} & := \frac{30-8}{(2^9 \times 4) + 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{52976} & := \frac{3+0 \times 8}{5+(2^9-7+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{59472} & := \frac{3+08}{59 \times (4 \times (7+2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{64512} & := \frac{3+08}{(6 \times (4+5-1))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{67452} & := \frac{30-8}{6+((7^4+5) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{67914} & := \frac{3 \times 08}{6 \times (7 \times (9 \times 14))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{71456} & := \frac{3+0 \times 8}{(71+45) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{91476} & := \frac{3+0 \times 8}{9+(147 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{127596} & := \frac{3+08}{1+2+759 \times 6} \\ & := \frac{30-8}{(1+2 \times 759) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{149765} & := \frac{3 \times 08}{(1+4 \times 97) \times 6 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{156492} & := \frac{3+08}{(1 \times 5+64) \times 9^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{416752} & := \frac{3+08}{(41+6+75)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{429576} & := \frac{3+08}{(4+2^9 \times 5-7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{308}{927465} & := \frac{3 \times 08}{(9+(2+7)^4) \times (6+5)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 309

$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{412} := \frac{3+09}{4+12}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 09}{27 \times (8+1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{61285} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{(6+1^2) \times 85}$
$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{4 \times 1^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{5768} := \frac{3 \times 09}{(57+6) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{30-9}{((6+1)^2) \times 85}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{618} := \frac{3+09}{6+18}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{7416} := \frac{3+09}{(7+41) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 09}{(61+2) \times 85}$
$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{6 \times 1^8}$	$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{(7+4+1) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{62418} := \frac{3+09}{6+2418}$
$:= \frac{3 \times 09}{6 \times (1+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{8652} := \frac{3+09}{8 \times (6 \times (5+2))}$	$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{624-18}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{721} := \frac{3+09}{7+21}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{12875} := \frac{30-9}{(1+(2 \times 87)) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{81576} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{8 \times ((15 \times 7) - 6)}$
$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{7 \times (2-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{15862} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{158-6+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{164285} := \frac{3+09}{(1-6) \times (4-2^8 \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{30-9}{7^2 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{16274} := \frac{3+09}{1+(627+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{187254} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{1872-54}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{824} := \frac{3+09}{8+24}$	$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{1 \times ((6 \times 27) - 4)}$	$:= \frac{3+09}{18+7254}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1648} := \frac{3+09}{16+48}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{24617} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{2+((4 \times 61) - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{217845} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{(2+1)^7 - 8 \times (4+5)}$
$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{1 \times ((6-4) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{30+9}{2+(5 \times 647)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{245861} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{2-45 \times (8-61)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1854} := \frac{3+09}{1 \times (8 \times (5+4))}$	$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{((2 \times 5 - 6)^4) - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{274186} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{2 \times (7+4)^{1+8-6}}$
$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{1+(8+5+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{26471} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{(2 \times ((6-4)^7)) + 1}$	$:= \frac{3+09}{(2 \times (7+4))^{1+8-6}}$
$:= \frac{3 \times 09}{18 \times (5+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{26574} := \frac{3+09}{(265-7) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{287164} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{2 \times 87 \times 16+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{2678} := \frac{30+9}{2+(6 \times 7 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{2+((6+5-7)^4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{421785} := \frac{3+09}{42 \times 1 \times 78 \times 5}$
$:= \frac{3+09}{26+78}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{47586} := \frac{3+09}{((4 \times 75) + 8) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{728416} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{(7+2+8) \times 416}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{2781} := \frac{3+09}{27+81}$	$:= \frac{3+0 \times 9}{(4 \times 7+5) \times (8+6)}$	
$:= \frac{30-9}{27 \times (8-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{54178} := \frac{3+0 \times 9}{541-(7+8)}$	

● Numerator 310

$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{465} := \frac{3-1+0}{4-6+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{9765} := \frac{3-1+0}{9 \times (7 \times (6-5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{87265} := \frac{3-1+0}{(8 \times (7+2^6)) - 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{682} := \frac{3 \times 10}{68-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{28675} := \frac{3+1+0}{(2+8) \times (6 \times 7-5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{276985} := \frac{3-1+0}{2-7 \times (6-9) \times 85}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{2945} := \frac{3-1+0}{2 \times 9-4+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{69285} := \frac{3+1+0}{6 \times (9+(28 \times 5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{784269} := \frac{3 \times 10}{(7+8426) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{6975} := \frac{3+1+0}{6+(9+75)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{72695} := \frac{3-1+0}{7 \times (((2+6) \times 9) - 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{847695} := \frac{3 \times 10}{(8+4^7+6+9) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{7285} := \frac{3+1+0}{7+(2+85)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{74586} := \frac{3 \times 10}{(7 \times (4^5+8)) - 6}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{79825} := \frac{3-1+0}{(7+(98-2)) \times 5}$	

● Numerator 312

$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{468} := \frac{3+1^2}{4-6+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{9568} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{((9+5) \times 6) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{74958} := \frac{3+1^2}{7-(4-958)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{546} := \frac{3+1^2}{5-4+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{40768} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{4 \times (0+(7 \times (6+8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{79456} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{794-(5 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{780} := \frac{3+1+2}{7+8+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{40976} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{(4 \times (0+97)) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{79560} := \frac{3-1 \times 2}{(7 \times 9 \times 5) - 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{4056} := \frac{3-1^2}{(4 \times 05) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{45760} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{4 \times 5 + (7 \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{80496} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{(80+49) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{4576} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{45-7+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{48750} := \frac{(3+1) \times 2}{(4 \times 8-7) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{95784} := \frac{3+1^2}{((9 \times 5 \times 7) - 8) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{4680} := \frac{3+1+2}{4+(6+80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{56784} := \frac{3+12}{5 \times (6 \times (7+84))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{476580} := \frac{(3+1)^2}{47 \times 65 \times 8+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{4875} := \frac{(3+1) \times 2}{(4 \times 8-7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{56940} := \frac{3-1^2}{5 \times (69+4+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{498576} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{(4+98) \times (5+7 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{7956} := \frac{(3+1)^2}{(7 \times 9+5) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{57408} := \frac{3-1 \times 2}{(5-(7 \times 4)) \times (-08)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{567840} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{5 \times (6+7) \times 84+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{9048} := \frac{3-1^2}{90-(4 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{74568} := \frac{3 \times 1^2}{(5-74) \times (-08)}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{74568} := \frac{3-1 \times 2}{7+((4 \times 56) + 8)}$	

● Numerator 314

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{628} &:= \frac{3 - 1^4}{6 \times 2 - 8} \\ &:= \frac{31 + 4}{62 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 4}{6 - 2 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (1 + 4)}{6 + 2 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - 1)^4}{(6 - 2) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 14}{6 + 28} \\ &:= \frac{31 - 4}{62 - 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{785} &:= \frac{3 + 1^4}{7 + 8 - 5} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (1 + 4)}{7 + 8 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{6280} &:= \frac{(3 - 1)^4}{(6 - 2) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1^4}{6 \times (2 + 8 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{6908} &:= \frac{3 + 1^4}{6 + (90 - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{7065} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 4}{70 + 65} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{7850} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^4}{(7 + 8) \times (5 + 0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{8792} &:= \frac{3 + 1^4}{8 \times (7 + 9 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 4}{87 + 9^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{68295} &:= \frac{3 - 1^4}{((6 \times (8 \times 2)) - 9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{97026} &:= \frac{3 - 1^4}{(9 \times (70 - 2)) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{314}{725968} &:= \frac{3 + 1 \times 4}{7 \times (25 + 9) \times 68} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 315

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{420} &:= \frac{3 + 15}{4 + 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{462} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{4 + 62} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{4 \times 6 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{840} &:= \frac{3 + 15}{8 + 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{924} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(9 + 2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{2079} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{20 + 79} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{2604} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(2 \times 60) + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{4620} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^5}{46 - 2 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{4680} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 5}{4 \times 6 + 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{4860} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 5}{48 + 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{4872} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{4 \times (87 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{4 \times ((8 \times 7) + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{6048} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 5}{6 \times (0 + 4 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{6 \times (0 + 48)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{6480} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 5}{64 + 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{7290} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 5}{72 + 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{7840} &:= \frac{3 + 1 + 5}{7 \times (8 \times (4 + 0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{8064} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 5}{8 \times (0 + 64)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{8640} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 5}{8 \times (6 \times (4 + 0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{8960} &:= \frac{3 + 15}{8^9 - 6 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{9240} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^5}{92 - 4 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(9 + 2) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{27468} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 5}{2 \times ((74 \times 6) - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{28476} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(2 + (8 \times (4 \times 7))) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{42987} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(4 \times (2^9)) - 8 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{47082} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(4 \times (70 \times 8)) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{47628} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 5}{4 \times (7 \times (62 - 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{48720} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{4 \times (87 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{78246} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 5}{(7 \times 8 - 2) \times 46} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{78624} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 5}{78 \times (6^2 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{78 \times 6 \times 24} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{78 \times (6 \times 2 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{84672} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 5}{8 \times (4 \times (6 \times (7 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{8 + ((4^6) - 72)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{86247} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(8^6 - 2) + 4 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{86940} &:= \frac{3 - 1^5}{((8 - 6)^9) + 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{468720} &:= \frac{3 - 1^5}{4^6 - 8 \times 7 \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{789264} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{7 \times (8 \times 9)^2 + 6^4} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 1 \times 5}{8 \times (69 \times (4 + 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{469728} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{4 \times (697 + 2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{846720} &:= \frac{(3 + 1)^5}{8^4 \times 672 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{89640} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 5}{8 \times (9 + (6 \times 40))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{486927} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 5}{4 + 8 \times 6 \times 92 \times 7} & &:= \frac{3 \times 1^5}{(8 + 4) \times 672 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{90867} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(90 \times 8 \times 6) + 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{649278} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 5}{64 \times 92 \times 7 + 8} & &:= \frac{3 + 1 \times 5}{8 \times 4 \times 672 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{284760} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(2 + 8 \times 4 \times 7) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{689472} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{6 \times 8 \times 9 \times (4 + 72)} & &:= \frac{3 + 1^5}{8 \times (4 + 67 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{286470} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 5}{2 + 86 \times (4 + 70)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{786240} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{78 \times 6 \times 2 \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{928746} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{9^2 \times (87 + 4) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{297486} &:= \frac{31 \times 5}{(29^{7-4} + 8) \times 6} & &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{78 \times 6 \times 240} & & \\ & & &:= \frac{3 \times 1^5}{78 \times 6 \times 2^4 + 0} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 316

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{948} &:= \frac{3 + 16}{9 + 48} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{45978} &:= \frac{3 \times 16}{(4 + 5) \times (97 \times 8)} & &:= \frac{3 \times 1^6}{957 - 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{4029} &:= \frac{3 + 1^6}{40 + 2 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{59724} &:= \frac{3 + 1 + 6}{5 \times (9 \times (7 \times (2 + 4)))} & &:= \frac{3 + 16}{9 + 5748} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{4582} &:= \frac{3 - 1^6}{45 - (8 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{74892} &:= \frac{3 - 1^6}{(7 \times (4 \times (8 + 9))) - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{459780} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 6}{45 \times 97 \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 6}{4 \times (5 + 82)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{75840} &:= \frac{3 + 1 + 6}{75 \times (8 \times (4 + 0))} & &:= \frac{3 \times 16}{(4 + 5) \times 97 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{7584} &:= \frac{3 - 1^6}{(7 + 5) \times (8 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{82950} &:= \frac{3 - 1^6}{8 + (2^9 + (5 + 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{597240} &:= \frac{3 + 1^6}{5 \times 9 \times 7 \times 24 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 1^6}{7 + (5 + 84)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{95748} &:= \frac{3 - 1^6}{9 + (5 + (74 \times 8))} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{316}{8295} &:= \frac{3 + 1^6}{8 + (2 + 95)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 317

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{26945} &:= \frac{3 - 1^7}{((2 \times (6 + 9)) + 4) \times 5} & &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 7}{((26 \times 9) + 4) \times 5} & &:= \frac{31 + 7}{589 \times 6 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 1^7}{(2 + 6 + 9) \times 4 \times 5} & &:= \frac{3 \times 1^7}{(2^6 - (9 + 4)) \times 5} & &:= \frac{3 \times 1^7}{(58 \times 9) + 6^2} \\ &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 7}{(2 + 6 + 9) \times 45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{58962} &:= \frac{3 - 1^7}{(5 - 8 + 9) \times 62} & \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{64985} &:= \frac{3 - 1^7}{(6 + (4 + 9 \times 8)) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{84956} &:= \frac{3 - 1^7}{8 \times 4 + (9 \times 56)} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 7}{(2 + 6 + 9) \times 450} & \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{589620} &:= \frac{31 + 7}{589 \times 6 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{92564} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^7}{(9 \times 25) - 6) \times 4} & := \frac{3 \times 1^7}{(2^6 - 9 - 4) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{849560} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^7}{84 \times 95 + 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{269450} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 7}{(26 \times 9 + 4) \times 50} & := \frac{3 + 1^7}{(2 + 6 + 9) \times 4 \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{3 - 1^7}{(2 \times (6 + 9) + 4) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{317}{408296} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 7)}{(40 \times 8 + 2) \times 96} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 318

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{742} &:= \frac{3 + 18}{7 + 42} & := \frac{(3 + 1) \times 8}{572 + 4} & := \frac{(3 - 1)^8}{(4 \times (57 - 9))^2} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{7 \times 4 \times 2} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 8}{5 \times ((7 + 2) \times 4)} & := \frac{(3 - 1) \times 8}{(4 + (5 \times 7 + 9))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{795} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times 5} & := \frac{3 + 1 + 8}{(5 + 7^2) \times 4} & := \frac{3 \times (1 + 8)}{4 \times ((5 + 7) \times 9^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{954} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^8}{9 \times (5 - 4)} & := \frac{(3 - 1) \times 8}{(5 + 7) \times 24} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{52470} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^8}{(5^2) + 470} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 18}{9 + 54} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{6042} &:= \frac{3 + 1^8}{60 + 4^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{57240} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 8}{((5 + 7)^2) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 8)}{9 \times (5 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{7420} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{7 \times (4 \times 20)} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 8}{5 \times ((7 + 2) \times 40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{2067} &:= \frac{3 + 1^8}{2 \times (0 + 6 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{7526} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^8}{75 + 2 - 6} & := \frac{3 + 1 + 8}{(5 + 7^2) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{2597} &:= \frac{3 \times 18}{(2 + 5) \times 9 \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{7950} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times 50} & := \frac{(3 - 1) \times 8}{(5 + 7) \times 240} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{2 \times ((5 + 9) \times 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{25970} &:= \frac{3 \times 18}{(2 + 5) \times (9 \times 70)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{70596} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{(70 - 5 + 9) \times 6} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{2756} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^8}{27 + 5 - 6} & := \frac{3 + 1 + 8}{2 \times 5 + 970} & := \frac{3 \times 1^8}{70 + 596} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{5247} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{(5 \times 2 \times 4) - 7} & := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{2 \times ((5 + 9) \times 70)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{207495} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{20 \times (74 - 9) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{5406} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 8}{5 \times (40 - 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{29574} &:= \frac{3 + 1^8}{2^9 - (5 \times 7 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{259647} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 8}{2 \times (5 \times (9 + 6^4) + 7)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1^8}{5 + (40 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{45792} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{(4 + 5 + 7) \times 9 \times 2} & := \frac{3 - 1^8}{(2^5 - 9) \times (64 + 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{5724} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{5 + (7 + 24)} & := \frac{3 + 1^8}{4 + (5 + (7 \times 9^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{270459} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{27 \times (04 + 59)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 1^8}{(5 + 7) \times (2 + 4)} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 8}{45 \times ((7 + 9) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{279045} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{27 \times (9 + 04) \times 5} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 8}{45 \times (7 + 9) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{962745} &:= \frac{3 + 1^8}{(9 + 6 \times 2 + 7^4) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{457602} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{4 \times (5 + 7) \times 60 - 2} & := \frac{3 + 1 \times 8}{4 \times 5 \times 792 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{457920} &:= \frac{3 - 1^8}{(4 + 5 + 7) \times 9 \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{318}{529470} &:= \frac{3 + 1^8}{5 \times 2 \times 9 \times (4 + 70)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 319

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{580} &:= \frac{3 + 19}{5 \times 8 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{4872} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{(4 + 8) \times (7 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{48256} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{4 \times ((82 \times 5) + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{725} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{(7 - 2) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{5742} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^9}{5 + (7 + 42)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{48720} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{(4 + 8) \times (7 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{7250} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{(7 - 2) \times 50} & &:= \frac{3 + 1^9}{(5 + 7) \times (4 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{57420} &:= \frac{3 - 1^9}{5 \times (74 - 2 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{2784} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{(2^7) - 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{27405} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{27 \times (40 - 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{75284} &:= \frac{3 + 1 + 9}{((7 + 5) \times 2^8) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{4582} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{(4 \times (5 \times 8)) - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{27608} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{2 \times (7 \times (60 + 8))} & &:= \frac{3 \times 1^9}{(7 + 52) \times (8 + 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{4756} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 9}{4 \times (7 \times 5 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{47850} &:= \frac{3 - 1^9}{4 \times ((7 + 8) \times (5 + 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{265408} &:= \frac{3 - 1^9}{(2 + 6 + 5 \times 40) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{4785} &:= \frac{3 + (1 \times 9)}{(4 \times 7 + 8) \times 5} & &:= \frac{3 + (1 \times 9)}{(4 \times 7 + 8) \times 50} & &:= \frac{3 \times 1^9}{2 \times 6 \times (5 \times 40 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 1 + 9}{(47 - 8) \times 5} & &:= \frac{3 + 1 + 9}{(47 - 8) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 320

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1856} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{18 + 5 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{17856} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{((1 + 7 \times 8) \times 5) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{197568} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{1 \times 9 \times 7^{5+6-8}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1984} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{19 + 8 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{19648} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{19 + 6 \times 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{7168} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{(7 + 1 + 6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{147968} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{(1 - (4 - 7) \times 96) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{9856} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 0}{98 + 56} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 321

$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{749} := \frac{3+21}{7+49}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{47508} := \frac{3-2 \times 1}{4 \times 7 \times 5 + 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{87954} := \frac{3-2+1}{8 \times (7 \times 9 + 5) + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{856} := \frac{3+21}{8+56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{75649} := \frac{3 \times (2-1)}{756-49}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{97584} := \frac{3-2 \times 1}{(9+75-8) \times 4}$
$\quad := \frac{32+1}{8 \times (5+6)}$	$\quad := \frac{3+21}{7+5649}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{98547} := \frac{3-2 \times 1}{9 \times 8 + 5 \times 47}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{4708} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 1}{(4+7) \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{78645} := \frac{3+2-1}{(7^{8-6}) \times 4 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{467590} := \frac{3 \times (2-1)}{(4+6 \times 7) \times (5+90)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{8560} := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{8 \times 5 \times 6 + 0}$	$\quad := \frac{3^2-1}{7 \times ((8+6) \times 4 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{697854} := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{6+978 \times 5 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{45796} := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{4 \times (5 \times 7 \times 9 + 6)}$	$\quad := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{(7^{8-6}) \times 45}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{46759} := \frac{3 \times (2-1)}{4 \times 6 + 7 \times 59}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{79608} := \frac{3-2+1}{7+9+60 \times 8}$	

● Numerator 324

$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{567} := \frac{32-4}{56-7}$	$\quad := \frac{3 \times 2 - 4}{1 \times (5 + (87 + 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{75816} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{(75+81) \times 6}$
$\quad := \frac{32+4}{56+7}$	$\quad := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{15 \times 8 + 76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{76950} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{(7-6) \times 950}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{756} := \frac{3+24}{7+56}$	$\quad := \frac{3+2+4}{1 \times ((5 \times 87) + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{81756} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{8 \times (1+756)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{891} := \frac{32+4}{8+91}$	$\quad := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{1 + (5 + 876)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{86751} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{(8+6+7) \times 51}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{6075} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{6 \times (0+75)}$	$\quad := \frac{3 \times 24}{(1+587) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{87156} := \frac{3+2-4}{(((8 \times 7) - 1) \times 5) - 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{7056} := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{7 \times (056)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{17658} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{1 \times ((7 \times 6 \times 5) + 8)}$	$\quad := \frac{3 \times 2 - 4}{(8 \times 71) - (5 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{7560} := \frac{3+2+4}{7 \times (5 \times (6+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{18576} := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{(18 \times 57) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{95760} := \frac{32+4}{(9+5) \times 760}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{7695} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{(7-6) \times 95}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{57186} := \frac{3 \times 2 - 4}{(5 \times 71) - 8 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{106785} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{10 \times (6+785)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{7968} := \frac{3+24}{7 \times 96 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{71568} := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{7 \times (1 \times 568)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{107568} := \frac{3 \times 2 - 4}{(107+5) \times 6 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{8019} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{80+19}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{75168} := \frac{3+2-4}{((7 \times 5 \times 1) - 6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{107856} := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 07 \times 856}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{9576} := \frac{32+4}{(9+5) \times 76}$	$\quad := \frac{3 \times 2 - 4}{((75+1) \times 6) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{156978} := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{1 + (5+6)^{9-7} \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{15876} := \frac{3+2-4}{15 - (8-7 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{75618} := \frac{3 \times 24}{(7^5) + (6 - (1+8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{158760} := \frac{3 \times 24}{(1+587) \times 60}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{167508} := \frac{3+2-4}{16-7+508}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{186705} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{1+(8 \times 6)^{7-05}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{597861} := \frac{(3+2) \times 4}{(597+8) \times 61}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{169785} := \frac{32+4}{(1+6 \times 9) \times 7^{8-5}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{187056} := \frac{3+2+4}{(1+870-5) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{715680} := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{7 \times 1 \times 5680}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{175608} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{(1+7 \times 5) \times 60+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{187596} := \frac{3+2-4}{(1+8^{7-5}) \times 9-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{791568} := \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{(7+915 \times 6) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{175689} := \frac{(3-2) \times 4}{(1^7+5 \times 6 \times 8) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{196875} := \frac{32+4}{(19+6) \times 875}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{795168} := \frac{3+2+4}{(7+9 \times 51 \times 6) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{179658} := \frac{3 \times 2+4}{1+7 \times 9 \times (6+5) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{197568} := \frac{3 \times 24}{(1+97) \times 56 \times 8}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{185976} := \frac{3+24}{(1+8 \times 5) \times 9 \times 7 \times 6}$		

● Numerator 325

$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{819} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(8-1) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{4680} := \frac{(3-2) \times 5}{4+(68+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{17680} := \frac{3+2+5}{(1+7) \times 68+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{4160} := \frac{(3-2) \times 5}{4+(1 \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{8190} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(8-1) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{147680} := \frac{3+2^5}{1 \times 4^7-6 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{4186} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(41 \times 8)-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{9841} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(9 \times 84)+1}$	

● Numerator 326

$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{978} := \frac{3+26}{9+78}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{4890} := \frac{3 \times (2^6)}{4 \times (8 \times 90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{194785} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 6}{1 \times 9 \times 478 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{489} := \frac{32-6}{48-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{10758} := \frac{(3-2)^6}{1 \times (0-(7-(5 \times 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{198045} := \frac{3^2 \times 6}{1 \times 9^{8-04} \times 5}$
$\quad := \frac{32+6}{48+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{15974} := \frac{(3-2)^6}{1+(59-(7+4))}$	$\quad := \frac{(3-2) \times 6}{(1^9+80) \times 45}$
$\quad := \frac{3 \times (2^6)}{4 \times 8 \times 9}$	$\quad := \frac{3+2 \times 6}{1+(5+(9^{7-4}))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{418095} := \frac{3 \times (2+6)}{4 \times (1+80) \times 95}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{4075} := \frac{(3-2) \times 6}{40+(7 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{159740} := \frac{(3-2)^6}{1+5 \times 97+4+0}$	
$\quad := \frac{3 \times (2+6)}{4 \times (0+75)}$		

● Numerator 327

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{327}{654} &:= \frac{3^2 - 7}{(6 - 5) \times 4} &:= \frac{(3^2) + 7}{(9 - 1) \times 56} &:= \frac{(3 - 2)^7}{108 + 56 \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{6 + 5 \times 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{41856} &:= \frac{(3 - 2)^7}{(4 \times 18) + 56} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + 2 \times 7}{6 \times 5 + 4} &&:= \frac{3^2 - 7}{4 \times (1 \times (8 + 56))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (2 + 7)}{6 \times (5 + 4)} &&:= \frac{3 + 2 + 7}{(4^{1+8-5}) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + 27}{6 + 54} &\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{48069} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{(4 \times (80 \times 6)) - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{327}{981} &:= \frac{3 \times (2 + 7)}{9 \times (8 + 1)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{91560} &:= \frac{3^2 - 7}{(9 + 1) \times (56 + 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + 27}{9 + 81} &&:= \frac{(3^2) + 7}{(9 - 1) \times 560} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{327}{4905} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 7}{4 \times (9 \times 05)} &&:= \frac{(3 - 2)^7}{((4 - 1) \times 6 - 5) \times 98} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{327}{6540} &:= \frac{3^2 - 7}{(6 - 5) \times 40} &\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{105948} &:= \frac{3^2 - 7}{(1 + 05) \times 9 \times (4 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{65 \times (4 + 0)} &&:= \frac{(3 + 2) \times 7}{105 \times 9 \times (4 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{327}{9156} &:= \frac{3^2 - 7}{((9 + 1) \times 5) + 6} &&:= \frac{3 - 2 + 7}{(1 + 05) \times 9 \times 48} \\
 &&&\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{108564} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{(1085 - 6) \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 328

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{328}{451} &:= \frac{32 + 8}{4 + 51} &\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{5740} &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times 8}{5 \times (7 \times (4 + 0))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{328}{615} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 15} &\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{5904} &:= \frac{3^2 - 8}{5 + (9 + 04)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{328}{1640} &:= \frac{3^2 - 8}{1^6 + 4 + 0} &\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{6150} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 150} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 8}{1 + (64 + 0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{14760} &:= \frac{(3^2) + 8}{1 + (4 + 760)} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{1 \times (6 \times 40)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{14965} &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times 8}{1 + (4 \times (96 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times 8}{1^6 \times 40} &\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{19475} &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times 8}{1^9 \times 475} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{328}{4059} &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times 8}{40 + 59} &&:= \frac{3^2 \times 8}{1 \times (9 \times 475)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{328}{4756} &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times 8}{4 \times ((7 \times 5) - 6)} &&
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 329

$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{517} := \frac{3+2+9}{5+17}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{6815} := \frac{3+2 \times 9}{(6+81) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{46718} := \frac{(3-2) \times 9}{(4+67) \times 18}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{658} := \frac{32-9}{6+5 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{10857} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{1 \times (0+(8 \times 5-7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{65471} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{(6 \times (5+(4 \times 7))) + 1}$
$:= \frac{3+29}{6+58}$	$:= \frac{3-2+9}{10 \times (8 \times 5-7)}$	$:= \frac{32-9}{(654 \times 7) - 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{846} := \frac{3+2 \times 9}{8+46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{14805} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{1+4+8 \times 05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{68150} := \frac{3+2 \times 9}{(6+81) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{1457} := \frac{3+2+9}{1+(4+57)}$	$:= \frac{(3-2) \times 9}{1+(4+(80 \times 5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{87514} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{8 \times 7 \times 5 - 14}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{1645} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{1 \times (6+4-5)}$	$:= \frac{(3^2)+9}{1+(4+805)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{165487} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{(1+65-4) \times 8+7}$
$:= \frac{(3-2) \times 9}{1^6 \times 45}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (2+9)}{1480+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{461587} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{(4 \times 6-1) \times (5+8 \times 7)}$
$:= \frac{3-2+9}{1 \times ((6+4) \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{16450} := \frac{(3-2)^9}{(1^6) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{467180} := \frac{(3-2) \times 9}{(4+67) \times 180}$
$:= \frac{3+2+9}{1+(64+5)}$	$:= \frac{(3-2) \times 9}{1^6 \times 450}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{540876} := \frac{3+2+9}{(540+8) \times 7 \times 6}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times 9)}{1 \times (6 \times 45)}$	$:= \frac{3-2+9}{1 \times ((6+4) \times 50)}$	
$:= \frac{(3+2)^9}{(1+6 \times 4)^5}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times 9)}{1 \times (6 \times 450)}$	

● Numerator 340

$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{612} := \frac{3 \times 40}{6^{1+2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2958} := \frac{3 \times 40}{2 \times 9 \times 58}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{250976} := \frac{3+4 \times 1}{2+50 \times (97+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1275} := \frac{3 \times 4+0}{1 \times ((2+7) \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{18275} := \frac{3 \times 4+0}{(1^8+(2^7)) \times 5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2176} := \frac{3 \times 40}{(2^{1 \times 7}) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{98175} := \frac{3 \times 4+0}{(98+1) \times 7 \times 5}$	

● Numerator 341

$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{527} := \frac{3 \times 4-1}{5 \times 2+7}$	$:= \frac{3+4-1}{6+8-2}$	$:= \frac{3+41}{6+82}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{682} := \frac{34-1}{68-2}$	$:= \frac{3+4+1}{6+8+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{6572} := \frac{3 \times 4-1}{(6 \times 5 \times 7)+2}$
$:= \frac{34+1}{6+8^2}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 4-1}{6+8 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{6758} := \frac{3 \times 4-1}{(6 \times 7 \times 5)+8}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{6975} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 1}{(6 + 9)^{7-5}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{80259} &:= \frac{34 - 1}{((8 - 02)^5) - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{265980} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 1}{2 \times 65 \times 9 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{7502} &:= \frac{34 \times 1}{750 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{87296} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 1}{(8 - 7) \times (2^9 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{275869} &:= \frac{3 + 4 + 1}{2 \times (6 \times 5 + 9) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{9207} &:= \frac{3 + 4 + 1}{9 + 207} & &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 1)}{8 \times ((7 - 2) \times 96)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{275869} &:= \frac{3 + 4 - 1}{2 \times (7 \times 58 \times 6 - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - 1)}{9 \times (20 + 7)} & &:= \frac{3^{4-1}}{8 \times ((7 + 2) \times 96)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{285076} &:= \frac{3 + 4 - 1}{(2 \times 8 + 50) \times 76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{26598} &:= \frac{3 + 4 - 1}{2 - (6 - (59 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{341}{259687} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 1}{25 + 96 \times 87} & & \\ &:= \frac{3 + 4 + 1}{2 \times ((6 \times 5 + 9) \times 8)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 342

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{570} &:= \frac{3 + 42}{5 + 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{7581} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{7 \times (58 - 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{95608} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{(9 \times 560) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{589} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{5 \times 8 - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{9576} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - 2)}{(9 - 5) \times 7 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{95760} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - 2)}{(9 - 5) \times (7 \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{798} &:= \frac{3 + 42}{7 + 98} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{15789} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{(15 \times 7 \times 8) - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{106875} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 2}{(1 \times 06 - 8 + 7)^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{950} &:= \frac{3^4 \times 2}{9 \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{15876} &:= \frac{3 + 4^2}{1 + (5 + 876)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{107856} &:= \frac{3 + 4^2}{1 \times 07 \times 856} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1596} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{1 \times ((5 + 9) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{15960} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{1 \times ((5 + 9) \times 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{108756} &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 2}{(10 + 8 + 7 \times 5) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1957} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{1 + (95 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{16758} &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 2}{1 - ((6 - (7 + 5)) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{150879} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - 2)}{1 + (50 - 8) \times 7 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1976} &:= \frac{3^{4-2}}{1 + (9 + 7 \times 6)} & &:= \frac{(3 + 4)^2}{(1 + 6)^{7+5-8}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{169708} &:= \frac{3^{4-2}}{(1 + 6) \times (9 \times 70 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{1 + (97 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{18576} &:= \frac{3 + 4^2}{(18 \times 57) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{178695} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 2}{1 \times (7 + 8 \times 6) \times 95} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{5168} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{(5 - 1) \times 68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{51680} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{(5 - 1) \times 680} & &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{(1 + 7 \times (8 + 6)) \times 95} \\ &:= \frac{3^4 \times 2}{51 \times 6 \times 8} & &:= \frac{3^4 \times 2}{51 \times 6 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{715680} &:= \frac{3 + 4^2}{7 \times 1 \times 5680} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1786} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{1 + 7 + 86} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{51870} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - 2)}{(5 + 1 \times 8) \times 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{785916} &:= \frac{(3 + 4) \times 2}{7 \times (85 \times 9 + 1) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{5187} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - 2)}{5 - (1 - 87)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{71568} &:= \frac{3 + 4^2}{7 \times (1 \times 568)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{791568} &:= \frac{3 + 4^2}{(7 + 915 \times 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{7056} &:= \frac{3 + 4^2}{7 \times (056)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{915876} := \frac{(3+4) \times 2}{91 \times (58 \times 7 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{961875} := \frac{34+2}{9 \times (6 \times 1875)}$$

• Numerator 345

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{621} := \frac{(3+4) \times 5}{62+1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 5}{6 \times (21+0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{162978} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{(1 - (6 - 2^9) \times 7) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{690} := \frac{3 \times (4+5)}{6 \times (9+0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3+4+5}{6^{2+1}+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{198720} := \frac{3-4+5}{(1 - (9 - 8 \times 7))^2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3+45}{6+90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{9720} := \frac{3+4 \times 5}{9 \times (72+0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{6210} := \frac{3+4-5}{6^{2 \times 1} + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{26910} := \frac{3+4+5}{26+910}$$

$$:= \frac{3-4+5}{6 \times (2+10)}$$

• Numerator 346

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{519} := \frac{34-6}{51-9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 6}{1^2 \times (9 \times 75)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 6}{(1+29) \times 75 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (4+6)}{5 \times (1 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{34-6}{(1+29) \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+4) \times 6}{(12+9) \times 750}$$

$$:= \frac{34+6}{51+9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+4) \times 6}{(12+9) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{3+4-6}{(12+9 \times 7) \times 5+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{5190} := \frac{3+4-6}{5+(1+9+0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{21798} := \frac{3-4+6}{217+98}$$

$$:= \frac{34-6}{(1+29) \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{3+4+6}{5+190}$$

$$:= \frac{3+4+6}{21+798}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{270918} := \frac{3 \times 4 - 6}{(270 - 9) \times 18}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (4+6)}{5 \times (1 \times 90)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{87192} := \frac{3+4-6}{(8+7-1) \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{7958} := \frac{3+4-6}{(7 \times 9) - (5 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 6}{8 \times (7 \times (1 \times 9^2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{12975} := \frac{3 \times 4 - 6}{(12 - 9) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{129750} := \frac{3 \times 4 + 6}{1^2 \times 9 \times 750}$$

• Numerator 347

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{15268} := \frac{3 \times 4 - 7}{152 + 68}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{15962} := \frac{3 \times 4 - 7}{1 \times (5 + ((9 + 6)^2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{58296} := \frac{3 \times 4 - 7}{5 + (829 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3-4+7}{1-(5-268)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{19085} := \frac{3 \times 4 - 7}{190 + 85}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{68012} := \frac{3+4+7}{(6+8+0)^{1+2}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{347}{106529} &:= \frac{34-7}{1+06^5+2^9} &:= \frac{3-4+7}{(1 \times 6 + 8^2 \times 9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{347}{168295} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 7}{(1 + 6 \times 8 \times 2) \times 95} &\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{952168} &:= \frac{3 + 4 + 7}{(9 + 5)^{2+1} \times (6 + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 348

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{348}{957} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 8}{9 - 5 + 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{7105} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 8)}{7 \times 105} &:= \frac{(3 + 4) \times 8}{2 \times 1750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{348}{1276} &:= \frac{3 + 4 + 8}{1 + ((2 + 7) \times 6)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{9657} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 8}{9 \times 6 + 57} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{60291} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 8}{602 + 91} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{348}{1972} &:= \frac{3 + 48}{(1 + 9 + 7)^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{10962} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 8}{(10 \times 9) + 6^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{65192} &:= \frac{34 + 8}{6^5 \times 1 + 92} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{348}{2175} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 8)}{(2 + 1) \times 75} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{17052} &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 8}{1 \times 7^{05-2}} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{76125} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 8}{7 \times ((6 - 1) \times 25)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 4) \times 8}{2 \times 175} &&:= \frac{(3 + 4)^8}{1 \times 7^{05 \times 2}} && \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{348}{5916} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 8}{5 + (9 \times (1 + 6))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{21750} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 8)}{(2 + 1) \times 750} && \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 349

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{349}{8725} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 9}{8 + (72 - 5)} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 6) \times ((7 + 5)^2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{150768} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 + 9)}{(1 + 50 \times 7) \times 6 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 9}{8 \times ((7 - 2) \times 5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{26175} &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 9}{(2 + 6 \times 1) \times 75} &\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{167520} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 9}{1 \times 6 \times (7 + 5) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 4 + 9}{(8 + 72) \times 5} &&:= \frac{34 - 9}{(26 - 1) \times 75} &&:= \frac{3 - 4 + 9}{16 \times (7 + 5) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{349}{16752} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 9}{1 \times ((6 \times (7 - 5))^2)} &:= \frac{(3 + 4) \times 9}{(2 + 61) \times 75} &\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{261750} &:= \frac{(3 + 4) \times 9}{(2 + 61) \times 750} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 49}{((1 + 6) \times (7 + 5))^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{61075} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 - 9}{(6 + 1 + 0) \times 75} &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 9}{(2 + 6 \times 1) \times 750} \\ &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 9}{16 \times ((7 + 5) \times 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{87250} &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 9}{8 \times ((7 - 2) \times 50)} &:= \frac{34 - 9}{(26 - 1) \times 750} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 9}{1 \times ((6 \times (7 + 5))^2)} &&:= \frac{3 + 4 + 9}{(8 + 72) \times 50} && \\ &:= \frac{3 + 4 + 9}{16 + 752} && && \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 350

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{350}{84672} := \frac{3 \times 50}{84 \times (6 \times 72)}$$

● Numerator 351

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{429} := \frac{35 + 1}{4 \times (2 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{4 - 2 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 1)}{4 + 2 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{468} := \frac{3 \times (5 - 1)}{4 \times 6 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 51}{4 + 68}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{624} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{(6 - 2) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 1)}{6^2 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{5-1}}{6 \times 24}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 51}{6 \times 2^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{702} := \frac{35 - 1}{70 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{35 + 1}{70 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 - 1}{7 \times 01}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{728} := \frac{3 + 51}{7 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{2496} := \frac{3 \times (5 + 1)}{2 \times (4^9 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{5-1}}{(2 + 4) \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{6084} := \frac{3 \times (5 - 1)}{(60 - 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{6240} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{(6 - 2) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 1)}{(6 + 2) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{5-1}}{6 \times 240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{7280} := \frac{3 + 51}{7 \times (2 \times 80)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{24960} := \frac{3^{5-1}}{(2 + 4) \times 960}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{47268} := \frac{3 \times (5 - 1)}{((4 \times (7^2)) + 6) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 51}{4 + 7268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{48672} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{48 \times ((6 + 7) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 1)}{4 \times (8 \times (6 + 72))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{4 \times (8 \times (67 - 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{78624} := \frac{35 + 1}{7 \times (8 \times 6 \times 24)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 - 1}{7 \times ((8 + 6) \times 2^4)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 \times 1}{7 \times (8 + (62 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{7 \times (8 \times (6 \times (2 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 - 1)}{7 \times (8 \times (6 \times 2 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 5 - 1}{(786 - 2) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{80496} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{80 \times (49 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{247806} := \frac{3 + 5 \times 1}{2 + 4 + 7 \times 806}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{248976} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{2 \times (4 + 8 \times 9) \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{279864} := \frac{3 \times (5 - 1)}{2 \times (798 \times 6 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{287469} := \frac{3 \times (5 - 1)}{2 \times (87 + 4) \times 6 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{467298} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{4 + 67 \times 298}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{469872} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{4 \times 6 \times (9 \times 8 \times 7 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{478296} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{4 \times 7 \times (8^2 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{486720} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{48 \times (6 + 7) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{746928} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 1}{7 \times (4 + 6 + 9) \times 2^8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{786240} := \frac{3 + 5 \times 1}{7 \times 8 \times (6 + 2) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{(78 + 6) \times 240}$$

$$:= \frac{35 + 1}{7 \times 8 \times 6 \times 240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{864279} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{8 + (64^2 + 7) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{928746} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 1}{9 \times 28 \times 7 \times 4 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{986427} := \frac{3 + 5 + 1}{9 + 86 \times 42 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{987402} := \frac{3 \times (5 + 1)}{9 + (8 + 7)^4 + 02}$$

● Numerator 352

$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{704} := \frac{35-2}{70-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1980} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{1+(9+80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{18496} := \frac{35-2}{(1+(8 \times 4 \times 9)) \times 6}$
$\quad := \frac{35+2}{70+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{4096} := \frac{35-2}{4 \times (0+96)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{89760} := \frac{3+5^2}{(8+9) \times (7 \times 60)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{968} := \frac{3+5^2}{9+68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{8976} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{8 \times (9+7 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{104768} := \frac{3+52}{1 \times 04^7 - 6 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1408} := \frac{3+5-2}{(1-4) \times (-08)}$	$\quad := \frac{3+5^2}{(8+9) \times 7 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{104896} := \frac{3+5-2}{(10+4 \times 8 \times 9) \times 6}$
$\quad := \frac{3+5+2}{(1+4+0) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{9768} := \frac{3+5^2}{9+768}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{140679} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{1 \times 406 \times 7 \times 9}$
$\quad := \frac{3+5^2}{14 \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{14608} := \frac{3+5-2}{1+((4 \times 60)+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{184960} := \frac{35-2}{(1+8 \times 4 \times 9) \times 60}$
$\quad := \frac{35-2}{140-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{16984} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{16+(9 \times 84)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{184976} := \frac{3+5-2}{1+8 \times (4 \times 97+6)}$
$\quad := \frac{35+2}{140+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{17864} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{(17 \times 8 \times 6) - 4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1496} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{14+(9 \times 6)}$		

● Numerator 352

$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{708} := \frac{35-4}{70-8}$	$\quad := \frac{3+5-4}{60+1 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{86907} := \frac{3-5+4}{8-(69 \times (-07))}$
$\quad := \frac{35+4}{70+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{8260} := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{8+(2+60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{98176} := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{9+(817+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{1062} := \frac{3-5+4}{10-6+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{12980} := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{1+(29+80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{170628} := \frac{3+5+4}{(1 \times 70+6)^2+8}$
$\quad := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{1-(0-6-2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{18290} := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{1+(8^2+90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{170982} := \frac{3-5+4}{(170-9) \times (8-2)}$
$\quad := \frac{3+5-4}{1 \times (0+(6 \times 2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{18762} := \frac{3-5+4}{1 \times ((8 \times (7+6))+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{186027} := \frac{3-5+4}{18 \times (60-2)+7}$
$\quad := \frac{3+5+4}{1 \times (0+6^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{20178} := \frac{3-5+4}{2 \times (0+(1+(7 \times 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{279601} := \frac{3+5+4}{2 \times (79 \times 60-1)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{1298} := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{1+(2 \times 9-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{20768} := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{(2^0^7)+6 \times 8}$	
$\quad := \frac{3 \times (5+4)}{1^2+98}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{27081} := \frac{3-5+4}{2+(70+81)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{6018} := \frac{3 \times (5-4)}{60-(1+8)}$		

● Numerator 356

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{712} &:= \frac{3+5-6}{7-1-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{10947} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{10 \times (9+4) - 7} & & := \frac{3+5+6}{8 \times (9 \times (7^{1 \times 2}))} \\ &:= \frac{3-5+6}{7+1^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{21894} &:= \frac{3+5-6}{21+(8+94)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{197402} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{1 \times 9+(7+40)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{801} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{8+01} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{71289} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{(7+1 \times 2) \times 89} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{271984} &:= \frac{3+5-6}{2 \times (7+1+9 \times 84)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{2047} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{(2^{04})+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{72891} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{728+91} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{298417} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{(2^9+8-41) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{7209} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{(7+2+0) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{89712} &:= \frac{3+5-6}{8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 1^2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{7298} &:= \frac{3+5-6}{7+(2 \times (9+8))} & &:= \frac{3-5+6}{8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 1 \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{356}{7921} &:= \frac{3-5+6}{7+(9^2+1)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 357

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{408} &:= \frac{35-7}{4 \times 08} & &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{41 \times (8 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{41820} &:= \frac{35-7}{4 \times (1 \times 820)} \\ &:= \frac{35+7}{40+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{4692} &:= \frac{35+7}{4 \times (69 \times 2)} & &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{41 \times (8 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{612} &:= \frac{35+7}{6 \times 12} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{6018} &:= \frac{35-7}{(60-1) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{46920} &:= \frac{35+7}{4 \times (69 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{816} &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{8 \times 16} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{6120} &:= \frac{35+7}{6 \times 120} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{140896} &:= \frac{3 \times (5+7)}{(140+8) \times 96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{918} &:= \frac{35-7}{9 \times 1 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{8160} &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{8 \times 160} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{142086} &:= \frac{3+5-7}{14 \times (20+8)+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{1428} &:= \frac{3+5-7}{14-(2+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{9180} &:= \frac{35-7}{9 \times 1 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{184926} &:= \frac{3+5-7}{1 \times 8+(4+9^2) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3-5+7}{1 \times (4+(2 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{14280} &:= \frac{3+5-7}{1 \times (4 \times (2+8+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{196248} &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{1 \times 962 \times 4 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 5-7}{1 \times (4+28)} & &:= \frac{3-5+7}{((1+4)^2) \times (8+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{264180} &:= \frac{35-7}{2 \times (6^4-1) \times 8+0} \\ &:= \frac{35-7}{1 \times (4 \times 28)} & &:= \frac{35-7}{1 \times (4 \times 280)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{294168} &:= \frac{3-5+7}{(2^9+4-1^6) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{14 \times 2 \times 8} & &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{14 \times (2 \times 80)} & &:= \frac{3+5-7}{(2+94+1+6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2618} &:= \frac{3+5+7}{2+6 \times 18} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{26418} &:= \frac{3+5-7}{2+(6 \times (4+1 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{468129} &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{(4 \times 68-1)^2-9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{4182} &:= \frac{35-7}{4 \times (1 \times 82)} & &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times 7}{2+((6^{4+1})-8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{469812} &:= \frac{3-5+7}{4+6+9+81^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - 7}{4^6 \times 9 - 8 \times 1 \times 2}$$

● Numerator 358

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{716} := \frac{3 - 5 + 8}{7 - 1 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 5 - 8}{7 + 1 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{1074} := \frac{3 \times 5 - 8}{10 + 7 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - 8}{(10 - 7)^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{1790} := \frac{3 + 5 + 8}{1 + (79 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{4296} := \frac{(3 + 5) \times 8}{4 \times (2 \times 96)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 + 8}{(4 - 2) \times 96}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - 8}{(4 + 2) \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{42960} := \frac{(3 + 5) \times 8}{4 \times (2 \times 960)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 5 + 8}{(4 - 2) \times 960}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - 8}{(4 + 2) \times (9 \times 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{102746} := \frac{3 - 5 + 8}{(10 + 2)^{7-4} - 6}$$

● Numerator 359

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{718} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 9}{(7 - 1) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - 5 + 9}{7 - 1 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{48106} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 9}{4 \times (810 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{7180} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 9}{(7 - 1) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{80416} := \frac{3 \times 5 - 9}{(80 + 4) \times 16}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{127086} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 9}{1 \times 2 \times 708 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{140728} := \frac{3 \times 5 - 9}{(140 + 7) \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - 5 + 9}{14 \times 07 \times 28}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - 9}{14 \times 0728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{148267} := \frac{3 - 5 + 9}{(1 + 482) \times 6 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{267814} := \frac{35 + 9}{(2 + 6) \times (7 + 8^{1 \times 4})}$$

● Numerator 360

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1254} := \frac{3 \times 60}{1 \times (2 + (5^4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{15842} := \frac{3 \times 60}{1 \times ((5 + 84)^2)}$$

● Numerator 361

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{589} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{5 \times 8 - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 6 - 1}{7 + ((9 + 4)^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 6 \times 1}{9 \times (025)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{7942} := \frac{36 \times 1}{794 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{9025} := \frac{36 \times 1}{90 \times 2 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{9728} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{(9 - 7) \times 2^8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{361}{27094} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{2 \times (709 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{361}{82574} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{82 \times (57 - 4)} & &:= \frac{3 + 61}{4^2 \times 59 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{361}{42598} &:= \frac{3 + 61}{(4^2) \times (59 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{361}{280497} &:= \frac{36 + 1}{(2 + 8^{04} + 9) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 6 - 1}{(4 - 2) \times (59 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{361}{425980} &:= \frac{3 + 6 - 1}{(4 - 2) \times 59 \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 362

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{362}{905} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{9 \times 05} & &:= \frac{3 \times 6 - 2}{8 \times (1 \times 45)} & &:= \frac{3 \times 6 - 2}{8 \times (1 \times 450)} \\ &:= \frac{36 - 2}{90 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{362}{19548} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - 2)}{1 \times (9 \times ((5 + 4) \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{362}{195480} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - 2)}{1 \times 9 \times (5 + 4) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{36 + 2}{90 + 5} & &:= \frac{36 \times 2}{1 \times (9 \times (54 \times 8))} & &:= \frac{3 + 6 - 2}{1 \times 9 \times 5 \times (4 + 80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{362}{8145} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{(8 + 1) \times 45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{362}{81450} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{(8 + 1) \times 450} & &:= \frac{36 \times 2}{1 \times 9 \times 54 \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{3^6 \times 2}{((8 + 1)^4) \times 5} & &:= \frac{3^6 \times 2}{((8 + 1)^4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{36 \times 2}{81 \times 4 \times 5} & &:= \frac{36 \times 2}{81 \times (4 \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 364

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{728} &:= \frac{36 - 4}{72 - 8} & &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - 4)}{1 \times (0 + 9 \times 2)} & &:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times 4}{18 \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{(7 + 2) \times 8} & &:= \frac{3 + 6 \times 4}{1 \times (0 + 9^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1872} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 - 4}{1 \times (8 \times (7 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{36 + 4}{72 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1508} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 - 4}{1 \times (50 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{5180} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 4}{5 + 180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{819} &:= \frac{36 - 4}{8 \times (1 \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1729} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{(17 + 2) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{7189} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{(71 + 8) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{(8 + 1) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1792} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 4}{(17 - 9)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{7280} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{(7 + 2) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{36 + 4}{81 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1820} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 4}{1 + (8^2 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{8092} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 4}{(8 + 09)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{952} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 4}{9 + 5^2} & &:= \frac{36 - 4}{1 \times (8 \times 20)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{8190} &:= \frac{36 - 4}{8 \times (1 \times 90)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{910} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{9 \times 10} & &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{(1 + 8) \times 20} & &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4}{(8 + 1) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1092} &:= \frac{3 - 6 + 4}{1^{09} + 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{15708} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{1^5+(70 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{71890} &:= \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(71+8) \times 90} & & := \frac{3 \times 6 - 4}{9 \times (1 \times (7^2 \times 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{17290} &:= \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(17+2) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{72891} &:= \frac{36-4}{72 \times (89 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{189072} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 - 4}{1 \times 8 \times (907+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{18720} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 - 4}{1^8 \times 720} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{81250} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 - 4}{(8-1-2)^5+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{271908} &:= \frac{3-6+4}{27+1 \times 90 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{52780} &:= \frac{3+6-4}{5+((2+7) \times 80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{89712} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{89 \times ((7-1)^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{891072} &:= \frac{3+6 \times 4}{(8+910) \times 72} \\ & & & & & := \frac{3 \times (6-4)}{5 \times (2 \times (7+80))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{364}{91728} &:= \frac{3-6+4}{9 \times (1^7 \times 28)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 365

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{365}{2190} &:= \frac{3-6+5}{2+(1+9+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{365}{9271} &:= \frac{(3+6) \times 5}{9 \times ((2^7)-1)} & & := \frac{3+6-5}{2^9 \times 7 - 8 \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (6-5)}{2 \times (1 \times (9+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{365}{28470} &:= \frac{3-6+5}{2+(84+70)} & & \\ &:= \frac{(3+6) \times 5}{(2+1) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{365}{297840} &:= \frac{3-6+5}{2 \times (97 \times 8 + 40)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 367

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{367}{12845} &:= \frac{3+6-7}{1 \times ((2+8+4) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{367}{24589} &:= \frac{3+6-7}{(2-4) \times (5-(8 \times 9))} & & := \frac{3+6+7}{1 \times 28 \times 4 \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{3-6+7}{(1-2+8) \times 4 \times 5} & &:= \frac{3-6+7}{2 \times (45+89)} & & := \frac{3+6-7}{(1 \times 2+8+4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{3+6+7}{1 \times (28 \times 4 \times 5)} & &:= \frac{3+6+7}{2^4 \times (58+9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{367}{140928} &:= \frac{3-6+7}{(1-4+09) \times 2^8} \\ &:= \frac{36-7}{1-(2+(8-(4^5)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{367}{52481} &:= \frac{3-6+7}{52 \times (4+8-1)} & & := \frac{3+6-7}{(1 \times 4+092) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{367}{20185} &:= \frac{3+6-7}{20+(18 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{367}{128450} &:= \frac{3-6+7}{(1-2+8) \times 4 \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 368

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{920} &:= \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{9 \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1472} &:= \frac{3-6+8}{1 \times (4 \times (7-2))} & & := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{1 \times (4 \times 72)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{7452} := \frac{36-8}{7 \times ((4+5)^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{41952} := \frac{3-6+8}{(4-1) \times (95 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{279450} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 8}{27 \times 9 \times 450} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{14720} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{1 \times (4 \times 720)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{51704} := \frac{3 \times 6-8}{5 \times (1+(70 \times 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{419520} := \frac{3-6+8}{(4-1) \times 95 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{27945} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 8}{27 \times (9 \times 45)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{175904} := \frac{3+6-8}{1+7+5 \times (90+4)} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 369

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{451} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+51} & := \frac{3 \times 6-9}{(5 \times 24)+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{47150} := \frac{3+6+9}{(47-1) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{820} := \frac{3+69}{8 \times 20} & := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{5 \times (2^4 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{48175} := \frac{36-9}{(48-1) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{1025} := \frac{3 \times 6-9}{1 \times 025} & := \frac{36-9}{(52-4) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{52480} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{5 \times (2^4 \times 80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{1845} := \frac{3^6 \times 9}{((1+8)^4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{5740} := \frac{3 \times 6-9}{5 \times (7 \times (4+0))} & := \frac{36-9}{(52-4) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 9}{18 \times 45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{174250} := \frac{3 \times 6-9}{17 \times 4250} \\ & := \frac{3+69}{1 \times (8 \times 45)} & := \frac{3+69}{(1+7) \times 4250} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 6-9}{1^8 \times 45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{182450} := \frac{3+6+9}{(182-4) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{(3+6) \times 9}{(1+8) \times 45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{187452} := \frac{3+69}{18 \times (7+45^2)} \\ & := \frac{3+6+9}{1+(84+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{271584} := \frac{3-6+9}{27^{-1} \times 5+8^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{2870} := \frac{3 \times 6-9}{(2+8) \times (7+0)} & := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 9}{18 \times 450} & \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{281547} := \frac{3-6+9}{(28+1+5^4) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{4182} := \frac{3-6+9}{4+(1 \times (8^2))} & := \frac{3+69}{1 \times (8 \times 450)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{4715} := \frac{3+6+9}{(47-1) \times 5} & := \frac{3 \times 6-9}{1^8 \times 450} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{369}{5248} := \frac{3 \times 6^9}{((5-2) \times 4)^8} & := \frac{(3+6) \times 9}{(1+8) \times 450} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 370

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{481} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{4+8+1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{518} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{5+1+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{592} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{5+9+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{629} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{6+2+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{814} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{8+14} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1258} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{1+25+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1295} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{1+29+5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1628} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{1 \times (6^2 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{2849} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{2 + (84 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{5291} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{52+91} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{5698} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{56+98} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{8214} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{8+214} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{14689} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{1 - ((4 - 6 \times 8) \times 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{14985} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{((1 + 49) \times 8) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{16428} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{16 + 428} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{18426} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{(1 + (84 - 2)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{28194} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{2 + (8 \times (1 + 94))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{28416} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{2^8 \times (4 - 16)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{189625} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{(1 + 8^{9-6} \times 2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{195286} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{1 - 9 + 5286} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{582491} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{((5 + 8)^2 + 4) \times 91} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{649128} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{6 \times (4 \times 9^{1+2} + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{370}{864912} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{8 \times (6 + 4 \times 9^{1+2})} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 371

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{371}{689} &:= \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{6 \times 8 - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{371}{2968} &:= \frac{37 - 1}{296 - 8} \\ &:= \frac{37 + 1}{296 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 7 + 1}{2 \times (96 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (7 + 1)}{(2 \times 9 + 6) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{371}{6095} &:= \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{(60 + 9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{371}{8904} &:= \frac{3^7 \times 1}{8 \times (9^{04})} \\ &:= \frac{37 + 1}{8 + 904} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{371}{29680} &:= \frac{3 \times (7 + 1)}{(2 \times 9 + 6) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{371}{94658} &:= \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{94 \times (65 - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{371}{290864} &:= \frac{3 + 7 - 1}{(2 + 90 - 8)^{6-4}} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 372

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{465} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{4+6+5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{496} &:= \frac{3+72}{4+96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{1860} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{1^8 \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 72}{18 \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{1984} &:= \frac{3^{7+2}}{(1+9+8)^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{4185} &:= \frac{3+7-2}{4+(1+85)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{6541} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{6+(5 \times 41)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{10695} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{1 \times (0 + (69 \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(3+7) \times 2}{(106+9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{19685} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{(1+(9 \times (6+8))) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{196850} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{(1+9 \times (6+8)) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{954180} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{95 \times 4 \times (1+80)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 374

$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{528} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{(5 - 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2856} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 4)}{(2 + (8 \times 5)) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{28560} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 4)}{(2 + (8 \times 5)) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{918} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 4)}{9 \times (1 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{5168} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 4)}{(51 + 6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{29568} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{2 \times ((9 + 5) \times 6 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{952} := \frac{3 + 74}{(9 + 5)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{5280} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{(5 - 2) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{51680} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 4)}{(51 + 6) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1258} := \frac{3 + 74}{1 + 258}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{5610} := \frac{37 + 4}{5 + 610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{91520} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{(9 - 1) \times 520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1980} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{1 + (9 + 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{8296} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 4)}{(82 \times 9) - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{186592} := \frac{3 + 74}{((1 \times 8 + 6) \times (5 + 9))^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2516} := \frac{3 + 74}{2 + 516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{9152} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{(9 - 1) \times 52}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{198560} := \frac{3 + 74}{(1 + 9 \times 8) \times 560}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2596} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{2 \times (5 + (9 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{10285} := \frac{3 + 7 - 4}{(10 \times 2 \times 8) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{295680} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{2 \times (9 + 5) \times 6 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2618} := \frac{3 + 7 - 4}{2 + ((6 - 1) \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{10692} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{1 \times (0 + (6 \times 9^2))}$	
$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{3 \times (7 - 4)}{2^6 - 1^8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{15062} := \frac{3 + 74}{1 + (50 \times 62)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2816} := \frac{3 \times 7 - 4}{2^{8-1^6}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{19856} := \frac{3 + 74}{(1 + 9 \times 8) \times 56}$	

● Numerator 375

$\blacktriangleright \frac{375}{12960} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 5}{12^{9-6} + 0}$

● Numerator 376

$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{940} := \frac{3 - 7 + 6}{9 - 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1598} := \frac{3 + 7 - 6}{1^5 \times (9 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{3 + 7 - 6}{4 \times ((5 + 1) \times 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1504} := \frac{3 + 7 - 6}{(1 - 5) \times (-04)}$	$:= \frac{3 + 7 + 6}{1 - (5 - 9 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{37 + 6}{4 + 512}$
$:= \frac{3 \times 7 - 6}{15 \times 04}$	$:= \frac{(3 + 7) \times 6}{15 \times (9 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{3 + 7 \times 6}{45 \times 12}$
$:= \frac{3 \times 7 \times 6}{1 \times 504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{4512} := \frac{3 - 7 + 6}{4 \times (5 + 1^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{9024} := \frac{3 \times (7 - 6)}{9 \times (0 + 2 \times 4)}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3+7-6}{90+2+4} \\ &:= \frac{(3+7) \times 6}{90 \times 2^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{10528} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{1 \times (0 + ((5+2) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 7 - 6}{(10+5) \times 28} \\ &:= \frac{(3+7) \times 6}{105 \times 2 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{12408} &:= \frac{3+7-6}{124+08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{14852} &:= \frac{3+7-6}{1 \times ((4 \times 8 \times 5) - 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{15980} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{1 - (5 - (9 + 80))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{19458} &:= \frac{3+7-6}{194+5+8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{25098} &:= \frac{3+7-6}{250+9+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{45120} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{4 \times (5 \times (12+0))} \\ &:= \frac{3+7-6}{4 \times ((5+1) \times 20)} \\ &:= \frac{3+7 \times 6}{45 \times 120} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{59408} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{5 - (9 - (40 \times 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{81592} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{(8 \times ((1+5) \times 9)) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{189504} &:= \frac{3 \times 7 + 6}{(18+9) \times 504} \\ &:= \frac{3-7+6}{(1-8+9) \times 504} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{194580} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{19+4^5-8+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{219584} &:= \frac{3 \times 7 + 6}{(2+1) \times 9 \times 584} \\ &:= \frac{(3+7) \times 6}{219 \times 5 \times 8 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{3-7+6}{2 \times 1^9 \times 584} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (7-6)}{(2+1^9) \times 584} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{241580} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{241 \times 5 + 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{419052} &:= \frac{3-7+6}{4 - (1 - 90) \times 5^2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 378

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{450} &:= \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{462} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{4 \times 6 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{546} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{5 \times 4 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{651} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{6 \times 5 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{924} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(9+2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{945} &:= \frac{3-7+8}{9-4+5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1260} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{1^2 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1596} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{1 + (5 \times (9+6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2415} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(24-1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2604} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(2 \times 60) + 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{5691} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(5 \times 6 \times 9) + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{9240} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(9+2) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{9261} &:= \frac{3+7-8}{(9-2) \times (6+1)} \\ &:= \frac{3-7+8}{92+6 \times 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{10962} &:= \frac{3+7-8}{((1+09) \times 6) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{3-7+8}{((10+9) \times 6) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{12096} &:= \frac{3+7-8}{1 \times 20 \times 9 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{15246} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(1 + (5 \times 24)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{15624} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(1+5 \times 6) \times 24} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{16254} &:= \frac{3+7-8}{((16+2) \times 5) - 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3-7+8}{(1 + (6 \times (2+5))) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 7 - 8}{1 + (62 \times (5+4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{19425} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(1+9 \times 4) \times 25} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{21546} &:= \frac{3+7-8}{(2 \times (1 \times 54)) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{3-7+8}{2 \times ((15+4) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{21945} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{2 + (19 + (4^5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{24150} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(24-1) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{26145} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{(2 \times ((6-1)^4)) - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{51492} &:= \frac{3+7+8}{51 + (49^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{52164} &:= \frac{3+7-8}{(5 + (2^{1 \times 6})) \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{54621} := \frac{3+7+8}{(5+46)^2 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{156492} := \frac{(3+7) \times 8}{15 \times 6 \times 4 \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{261954} := \frac{3+7-8}{2 \times (6+1) \times (95+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{61425} := \frac{3-7+8}{(61+4) \times 2 \times 5}$	$:= \frac{3-7+8}{1564+92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{269514} := \frac{3-7+8}{2+6 \times 95 \times (1+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{64512} := \frac{3+78}{(6 \times 4)^{5-1 \times 2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{162540} := \frac{3-7+8}{(1+6 \times (2+5)) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{294056} := \frac{3+78}{2^9 + 4 \times 05^6}$
$:= \frac{3+7+8}{6 \times ((4^5-1) \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{165942} := \frac{3+7-8}{1-65+942}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{296541} := \frac{3+7-8}{(2^9+6+5) \times (4-1)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{92610} := \frac{3-7+8}{(92+6) \times 10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{194250} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+9 \times 4) \times 250}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{456192} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{4^5 \times (6+192)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{105462} := \frac{3-7+8}{1054+62}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{195426} := \frac{3-7+8}{(1-95) \times (4-26)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{496125} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times 9 \times 6125}$
$:= \frac{3+7-8}{(1 \times 05+4) \times 62}$	$:= \frac{3+7-8}{19 \times 54+2+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{546210} := \frac{3+7+8}{(5+46)^2 \times 10}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{152460} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+5 \times 24) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{215460} := \frac{3-7+8}{2 \times (15+4) \times 60}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{156240} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+5 \times 6) \times 240}$	$:= \frac{3+7-8}{21 \times 54+6+0}$	

• Numerator 379

$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{20845} := \frac{3+7-9}{2-(0-(8+45))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{48512} := \frac{3+7-9}{4 \times (8 \times (5-1^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{485120} := \frac{3 \times (7+9)}{(4+8) \times 5120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{25014} := \frac{3+7-9}{2+(50+14)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (7+9)}{(4+8) \times 512}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{28046} := \frac{3+7-9}{2+((8+04) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{52681} := \frac{3+7-9}{5+(2 \times (68-1))}$	
$:= \frac{3-7+9}{2-(8 \times (0-46))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{150842} := \frac{3+7-9}{1 \times 50 \times 8-4+2}$	

• Numerator 380

$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{475} := \frac{3 \times 80}{4 \times 75}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{207645} := \frac{3+8+1}{20 \times (7+64 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{759460} := \frac{3+8+1}{(7+5 \times 9) \times 460}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{16245} := \frac{3 \times 8+0}{1^6 \times (2+(4^5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{247650} := \frac{3 \times 8-1}{(2^4+7) \times 650}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{29165} := \frac{3 \times 8+0}{2 \times (916+5)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 1}{24 \times (7+6) \times 50}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{61275} := \frac{3 \times 8+0}{6 \times ((1+(2^7)) \times 5)}$		

- Numerator 381

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{762} := \frac{38 - 1}{76 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + 1}{76 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{2794} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 1)}{(2 \times 79) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{4572} := \frac{38 \times 1}{4 \times (57 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 8 \times 1}{4 \times (5 \times 7 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{20574} := \frac{3 + 8 \times 1}{20 + 574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{24765} := \frac{3 \times 8 - 1}{(2^4 + 7) \times 65}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 1}{24 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{45720} := \frac{38 \times 1}{4 \times (57 \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 8 + 1}{4 \times (5 \times (72 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + 1)}{45 \times (72 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{47625} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 1}{(4 - (7 - 6 - 2))^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{65024} := \frac{3^8 \times 1}{6^{5+02} \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{75946} := \frac{3 + 8 + 1}{(7 + 5 \times 9) \times 46}$$

• Numerator 382

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{764} := \frac{3 + 8 \times 2}{7 \times 6 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 + 2}{(7 + 6) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{38 - 2}{76 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + 2}{76 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{7640} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 2}{(7 + 6) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{79456} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 2)}{(7 + (9 + (4^5))) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{45076} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 2)}{(4 + 50 \times 7) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{170945} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 2)}{(170 + 9) \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{194056} := \frac{3 \times 82}{(1 - 9) \times (4 - 05^6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{794560} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 2)}{(7 + 9 + 4^5) \times 60}$$

• Numerator 384

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{512} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{(5 - 1)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + 4)}{1 \times (9 \times 20)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{9216} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{9 \times (2 \times 16)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{576} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{5 + 7 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{38 - 4}{57 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{1952} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{1 \times 9 + 52}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 - 4}{(9^2 - 1) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + 4}{57 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{2176} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 4)}{2 \times (17 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{8-4}}{9 \times 216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{1056} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 4)}{105 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{2976} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{2 + (97 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{12096} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 4)}{(1 + 20) \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{1792} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{(1 + 7) \times (9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 8 + 4}{((1 + 7) \times 9) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{5920} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{5 + (9 \times 20)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{21760} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 4)}{2 \times (17 \times 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{1920} := \frac{3 \times 8 - 4}{(1 + 9)^2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{6912} := \frac{3 + 8 - 4}{6 \times (9 + 12)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + 4)}{6 \times (9 \times 12)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{69120} := \frac{3 \times 8 - 4}{(6 \times (9 + 1))^2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + 4)}{6 \times (9 \times 120)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{384}{92160} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{9 \times (2 \times 160)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 8 - 4}{(9^2 - 1) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3^{8-4}}{9 \times 2160} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{384}{201756} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{(2 + 01) \times (7^5 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 385

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{385}{462} &:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times 5}{4 + 62} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 5}{4 \times 6^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{385}{6790} &:= \frac{38 - 5}{6 \times (7 + 90)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{385}{9240} &:= \frac{3 + 8 - 5}{9 \times (2^4 + 0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{385}{17920} &:= \frac{3 + 85}{(1 + 7 \times 9)^2 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{385}{120974} &:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times 5}{(1 + 2)^{09} - 7^4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{385}{1260} := \frac{(3 + 8) \times 5}{(1 + 2) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 - 5)}{9 \times (24 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{385}{1792} := \frac{(3 + 8) \times 5}{1 \times (7 + 9)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{385}{12096} := \frac{(3 + 8) \times 5}{12^{09-6}}$$

• Numerator 386

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{386}{579} &:= \frac{38 - 6}{57 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{38 + 6}{57 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 - 6)}{7 \times (2 \times (9 \times (5 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 8 - 6}{(72 - 9) \times 54} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{386}{452971} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 6)}{(4^5 - 2 \times 9) \times 7 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{386}{49215} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 6)}{(49 + 2) \times 15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{386}{251479} := \frac{3 \times 8 - 6}{((2 + 5 - 1)^4 + 7) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{386}{72954} := \frac{3 - 8 + 6}{7 + (2 + (9 \times 5 \times 4))}$$

• Numerator 387

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{516} &:= \frac{3 + 8 + 7}{(5 - 1) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{5 - 1^6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{2451} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{(2 \times (4 + 5)) + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{10492} := \frac{3 + 8 + 7}{(10 \times 49) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{645} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{6 + 4 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{4902} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{4 \times 9 + 02}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{10965} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{10 + ((9 + 6) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{1290} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{1^2 + 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{5160} := \frac{3 + 8 + 7}{(5 - 1) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{16254} := \frac{3 - 8 + 7}{1 \times (6 \times (2 \times 5 + 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{2064} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{(2 \times 06) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{6192} := \frac{3 - 8 + 7}{(6 + 1 + 9) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 8 - 7}{1 \times (6 \times (2^5 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 87}{20 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{6 \times (1 + 9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 8 + 7}{(16 - 2) \times 54}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{2150} := \frac{3 + 8 + 7}{2 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{6450} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{(6 + 4) \times (5 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 - 7)}{1 \times (6 \times (25 - 4))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{24510} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(24-5) \times 10} & := \frac{3+8-7}{10 \times (6+4^2) \times 5} & := \frac{3+8-7}{1 \times 6 \times (2+5) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{40592} &:= \frac{3 \times (8+7)}{40 \times (59 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{126549} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(1+2 \times 6 \times (5+4)) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{215946} &:= \frac{3-8+7}{(2+(1+5 \times 9) \times 4) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{41925} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(4+(1 \times 9)) \times 25} & := \frac{3+8+7}{1^2 \times 654 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{215946} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{((2+1)^5 + 9 \times 4) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{61920} &:= \frac{3-8+7}{(6+1+9) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{129645} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(1+2 \times (96+4)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{249615} &:= \frac{3-8+7}{(2+4^{9-6+1}) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{69015} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(6 \times (90 \times 1)) - 5} & := \frac{3+8-7}{(1+(2+9) \times 6) \times 4 \times 5} & := \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{2 \times (4+961) + 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{105264} &:= \frac{3-8+7}{(10 \times 52) + 6 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{154026} &:= \frac{3-8+7}{(1-5 \times 40) \times (2-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{419250} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(4+1 \times 9) \times 250} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(105 \times 2 - 6) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{154026} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(1+5 \times 40 - 2) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{451629} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(451 - 62) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{3+8-7}{(10+5+2) \times 64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{162540} &:= \frac{3-8+7}{(1+(6-2) \times 5) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{387}{106425} &:= \frac{3-8+7}{(10+(6+4)^2) \times 5} & := \frac{3 \times (8-7)}{(1+62) \times 5 \times 4 + 0} \\
 & & := \frac{3+8+7}{(16-2) \times 540}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 389

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{20617} &:= \frac{3-8+9}{206-1+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{25674} &:= \frac{3+8-9}{2+(56+74)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{256740} &:= \frac{3+8-9}{(2^5-6+7) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{24507} &:= \frac{3+8-9}{2 \times ((4+(5+0)) \times 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{65741} &:= \frac{3+8-9}{(6 \times 57) - 4 \times 1} \\
 &:= \frac{3-8+9}{245+07}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 390

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{390}{715} &:= \frac{3+9+0}{7+15} & \blacktriangleright \frac{390}{5486} &:= \frac{3 \times 90}{(5^4+8) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{390}{451672} &:= \frac{3 \times 90}{4 \times (5^{1+6} + 7^2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{390}{1872} &:= \frac{3 \times 90}{18 \times 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{390}{7215} &:= \frac{3+9+0}{7+215} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{390}{2145} &:= \frac{3+9+0}{21+45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{390}{21645} &:= \frac{3+9+0}{21+645}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 391

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{391}{782} &:= \frac{39-1}{78-2} \\ &:= \frac{39+1}{78+2} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times 1}{7 \times 8 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{391}{8602} &:= \frac{39 \times 1}{860 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{391}{25806} &:= \frac{39 \times 1}{2580 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{391}{76245} &:= \frac{39 \times 1}{((7+6)^2) \times 45} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{391}{468027} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-1)}{(4^6 + 8 + 0 \times 2) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{391}{762450} := \frac{39 \times 1}{(7+6)^2 \times 450}$$

● Numerator 392

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{476} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{4+7+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{560} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-2)}{5 \times (6+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{784} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{7 \times (8-4)} \\ &:= \frac{39-2}{78-4} \\ &:= \frac{39+2}{78+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{1078} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{10 + (7 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{1456} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{1 + (45+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{1540} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{1 + (54+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{1568} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{(1^5+6) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-2)}{(1+5) \times (6+8)} \\ &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(1+5+6) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{39-2}{156-8} \\ &:= \frac{39+2}{156+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{5180} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{5+180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{6048} &:= \frac{3+9^2}{6^{-04+8}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{6517} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(6+51) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{7056} &:= \frac{3 \times 9 - 2}{(70+5) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{7168} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{(7+1-6)^8} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9-2)}{(7+1) \times 6 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{10584} &:= \frac{3 \times 9^2}{((10^5) + 8)^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{15680} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{(1^5+6) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(1+5+6) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{15708} &:= \frac{3+9+2}{1^5 + (70 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{15876} &:= \frac{3+9-2}{1 \times (5 \times (87-6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{65170} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(6+51) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{71680} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-2)}{(7+1) \times 6 \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 394

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{394}{1576} &:= \frac{3+9+4}{1+(57+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{394}{2167} &:= \frac{3+9-4}{2+(1 \times (6 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{3+9+4}{21+67} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{394}{2758} &:= \frac{3+9+4}{(2+(7+5)) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{394}{12608} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-4)}{1^2 \times (60 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3+9+4}{1 \times ((2^6+0) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{394}{21867} &:= \frac{3+9+4}{21+867} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{394}{27580} &:= \frac{3+9-4}{2 \times 7 \times 5 \times 8 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3+9+4}{(2+7+5) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{394}{217685} &:= \frac{3+9+4}{(2+17 \times 6) \times 85} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 395

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{395}{1264} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{395}{126874} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 5}{1 \times 2^6 + 8 \times 7^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{395}{12640} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 640} & &:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times 5}{(12+6) \times (8+7^4)} \\ &:= \frac{3^{9-5}}{1 \times 2 \times 6^4 + 0} & &:= \frac{39 \times 5}{1 \times 26 \times (8+7^4)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 396

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{540} &:= \frac{39-6}{5+40} & &:= \frac{3 \times 9 - 6}{1^5 \times 84} & &:= \frac{3+9+6}{(5-2) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{528} &:= \frac{3+9+6}{(5-2) \times 8} & &:= \frac{3 \times (9+6)}{15 \times (8+4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{5412} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-6)}{(5^{4-1}) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{39-6}{52-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{1782} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{17+8+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{7524} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-6)}{(7 \times (5^2)) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9+6)}{52+8} & &:= \frac{3+9+6}{1+(78+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{7584} &:= \frac{39-6}{7+(5^{8-4})} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{1028} &:= \frac{3+96}{1-(0-(2^8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{2178} &:= \frac{3+9+6}{21+78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{7854} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{7 \times (8+5+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{1254} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{1+(2 \times (5+4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{2475} &:= \frac{3 \times 96}{24 \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{10824} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{(10 \times (8 \times 2)) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{3+9+6}{1+(2+54)} & &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{(2+4) \times 75} & &:= \frac{39 \times 6}{((10 \times 8)^2) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times 6}{1+(2^{5+4})} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{2784} &:= \frac{39-6}{(2+(7 \times 8)) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{14058} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{((1+40) \times 5) + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{1408} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-6)}{1 \times (4 \times 08)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{4128} &:= \frac{39-6}{(41+2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{14728} &:= \frac{3+96}{14 \times (7+(2^8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{1452} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{1-(4-(5^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{4158} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{4+(1+58)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{14872} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-6)}{1 \times ((48 \times 7) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{3+9+6}{14+52} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{4752} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{47+5^2} & &:= \frac{3+9+6}{(1+(4 \times 8-7))^2} \\ &:= \frac{3+(9 \times 6)}{1+(4 \times 52)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{5148} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{(5 \times 14) + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{15708} &:= \frac{3+9+6}{1+(5+708)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{1584} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{(1+5) \times (8-4)} & &:= \frac{3 \times (9-6)}{5+(14 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{15840} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{1 \times (5 \times (8+40))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9-6)}{1 \times (5 \times 8-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{5184} &:= \frac{3+96}{(5+18)^4} & &:= \frac{3 \times (9-6)}{(1^5+8) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{3+9+6}{(1+5) \times (8+4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{5280} &:= \frac{3+9-6}{5 \times (2 \times 8+0)} & &:= \frac{3+9+6}{15 \times (8+40)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{3 \times 9 - 6}{1^5 \times 840} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{17504} := \frac{3 + 96}{1 + (7 \times (5^{04}))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{18502} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 6}{1 \times ((8 + 50)^2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{18524} := \frac{3 \times (9 - 6)}{1 + ((8 \times 52) + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{24750} := \frac{3 \times 96}{24 \times 750} \\
 := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 6}{(2 + 4) \times 750} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{27840} := \frac{39 - 6}{(2 + (7 \times 8)) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{28740} := \frac{39 - 6}{2 - (8 - (7^4 + 0))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{41280} := \frac{39 - 6}{(41 + 2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{45012} := \frac{3 \times (9 - 6)}{4^5 - 01^2} \\
 := \frac{3 + 9 + 6}{(4^5 - 01) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{57024} := \frac{(3 + 9)^6}{(5 + 7)^{02 \times 4}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{145728} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 6}{(1 + 45) \times 72 \times 8} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (9 - 6)}{(1 + 45) \times (7 + 2) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{3 + 9 - 6}{(145 - 7) \times 2 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{147852} := \frac{39 - 6}{(14 \times 7 + 8 + 5)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{175824} := \frac{3 + 9 - 6}{(1 + 7) \times (5 + 82 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{185724} := \frac{3 \times (9 - 6)}{(1 \times 8 + 57)^2 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{187524} := \frac{39 - 6}{1 + 8 - 7 + 5^{2+4}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{215784} := \frac{39 - 6}{(2 + 1)^5 \times (78 - 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{481572} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 6}{(4 + 815) \times 7^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{571824} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 6}{57 \times 1824} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{396}{817452} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 6}{(8 \times (1 + 7) \times 4 + 5)^2}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 397

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{15086} := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{((1 - 5) \times (-08)) + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{25408} := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{2 + (54 + 08)} \\
 := \frac{3 + 9 - 7}{2 \times (5 \times (4 \times 08))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (9 - 7)}{2 \times ((5 \times 40) - 8)} \\
 := \frac{3^{9-7}}{(2^5 + 40) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{41685} := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{4 + (16 + 85)} \\
 := \frac{39 - 7}{4 \times (168 \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{46052} := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{4 + (60 + 52)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{50816} := \frac{3 + 9 - 7}{5 \times (0 + (8 \times 16))} \\
 := \frac{39 - 7}{(5 + ((0 \times 8) - 1))^6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{52801} := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{5 + (2^{8-01})} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{124658} := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{1 \times 2 + 4 \times 6 \times (5 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{184605} := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{(1 + 8 \times 4 + 60) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{3^{9-7}}{(1 + 8) \times (460 + 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{406528} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 7}{4^{06} \times (5 + 2 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{(3 + 9)^7}{(4 \times 06)^{5+2} \times 8} \\
 := \frac{3 - 9 + 7}{4^{-06+5-2+8}} \\
 := \frac{3 + 9 - 7}{4 \times (0 \times 6 + 5 \times 2^8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{416850} := \frac{39 - 7}{4 \times (168 \times 50)}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 398

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{5174} := \frac{3 - 9 + 8}{5 + (17 + 4)} := \frac{3 \times (9 - 8)}{(5 \times (1 \times 7)) + 4} := \frac{3 + 9 - 8}{(5 + 1 + 7) \times 4}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{7164} := \frac{3-9+8}{(7-1)^{6-4}}$	$:= \frac{3+9+8}{14+726}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{70645} := \frac{3-9+8}{(7-(0-64)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{3+9-8}{7+(1+64)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{25074} := \frac{3-9+8}{2+(50+74)}$	$:= \frac{3+9+8}{(706+4) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{7562} := \frac{3-9+8}{7-(5-(6^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{25671} := \frac{3-9+8}{(2 \times (5 \times (6+7))) - 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{71640} := \frac{3+9-8}{716+4+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{10547} := \frac{3-9+8}{1-(0-(5+47))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{27064} := \frac{3-9+8}{2+(70+64)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{75421} := \frac{3-9+8}{(7 \times 54)+2-1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{10746} := \frac{3-9+8}{1-(0-(7+46))}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (9-8)}{(2 \times 70)+64}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{104276} := \frac{3 \times (9-8)}{(104+27) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (9-8)}{1-(0-(74+6))}$	$:= \frac{3+9-8}{270+6-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{147260} := \frac{3-9+8}{14+726+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{14527} := \frac{3-9+8}{1+(4 \times ((5^2)-7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{47561} := \frac{3-9+8}{(4 \times 75)-61}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{154026} := \frac{3+9-8}{1540+2+6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{14726} := \frac{3-9+8}{1+(47+26)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{51740} := \frac{3+9-8}{(5+1+7) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{405761} := \frac{3-9+8}{40 \times (57-6)-1}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (9-8)}{1 \times (47+2^6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{65471} := \frac{3-9+8}{(6 \times (5 \times (4+7))) - 1}$	

• Numerator 401

$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{23659} := \frac{4-01}{236-59}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{36892} := \frac{4-01}{368-92}$	$:= \frac{4-01}{(2-7+8) \times 695}$
$:= \frac{4+01}{(2-3+6) \times 59}$	$:= \frac{4+01}{(3-6+8) \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{385762} := \frac{4^{01}}{38+5 \times 762}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{35689} := \frac{4-01}{356-89}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{63759} := \frac{4-01}{(6 \times (3+75))+9}$	$:= \frac{4-01}{3 \times (8+5) \times (76-2)}$
$:= \frac{4^{01}}{(3-5+6) \times 89}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{68972} := \frac{4-01}{6 \times (8 \times 9+7 \times 2)}$	
$:= \frac{4+01}{356+89}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{269873} := \frac{4^{01}}{2-6 \times 9+8 \times 7^3}$	
$:= \frac{40+1}{(35+6) \times 89}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{401}{278695} := \frac{4^{01}}{278 \times (6+9-5)}$	

• Numerator 402

$\blacktriangleright \frac{402}{536} := \frac{4+02}{5-3+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{402}{3618} := \frac{40 \times 2}{(3^6)-(1+8)}$	$:= \frac{4+0 \times 2}{36 \times 1^8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{402}{938} := \frac{4+02}{9-3+8}$	$:= \frac{4-02}{3 \times (6 \times 1^8)}$	$:= \frac{4+02}{36+18}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{4 \times 01}{3 \times (6 + 18)} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{3 \times (6 \times 1 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{3819} & := \frac{4 - 02}{3 + (8 - 1 + 9)} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{38 \times 1^9} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{38 + 19} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{5896} & := \frac{4 + 02}{5 + (89 - 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{7638} & := \frac{40 \times 2}{(7 \times (6^3)) + 8} \\
 & := \frac{4 - 02}{76 - 38} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{76 + 38} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{7839} & := \frac{4 - 02}{78 - 39} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{78 + 39} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{13869} & := \frac{4 - 02}{1 \times (3 \times (8 + 6 + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{138 + 69} \\
 & := \frac{40 + 2}{(13 + 8) \times 69} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{1^3 \times (8 \times 69)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{15678} & := \frac{4 - 02}{1 + (5 - (6 - 78))} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{(1 - 5 + 6) \times 78} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{156 + 78} \\
 & := \frac{40 + 2}{(15 + 6) \times 78} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{(1 + ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{15879} & := \frac{40 \times 2}{1 \times (5 \times (8 \times 79))} \\
 & := \frac{4 - 02}{158 - 79} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{158 + 79} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 01}{(1 - 5 + 8) \times 79} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{1^5 \times (8 \times 79)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{18693} & := \frac{4 - 02}{1 + (86 + 9 - 3)} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{(1 - (8 - 69)) \times 3} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{(1 + 8 - 6) \times 93} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{1 + (8 + (6 + (9^3)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{31758} & := \frac{4 - 02}{((3 - 1) \times 75) + 8} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 01}{(3 + (1 + 75)) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{37185} & := \frac{4 - 02}{37 \times (1^8 \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{40 + 2}{3 \times (7 \times 185)} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{37 \times (1 \times 8 \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{63918} & := \frac{4 - 02}{6 + (39 \times 1 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{68139} & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{6 \times ((8 \times 13) + 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{71958} & := \frac{4 - 02}{(7 \times ((1 + 9) \times 5)) + 8} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{719 + 5 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{76983} & := \frac{4 - 02}{(7 \times 6 \times 9) + (8 - 3)} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{7 + (69 \times (8 + 3))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{135876} & := \frac{4 + 02}{(1 + 3^5) \times 8 + 76} \\
 & := \frac{4 - 02}{(1 + 3) \times (5 + 8) \times (7 + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{40 - 2}{13 \times (5 + 8) \times 76} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{137685} & := \frac{4^{01}}{(1^3 + 7) \times 685} \\
 & := \frac{4 - 02}{1 + 3 \times 76 \times (8 - 5)} \\
 & := \frac{40 + 2}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 685} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{156378} & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{1 + (5 + 6^3) \times 7 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{157986} & := \frac{4 - 02}{1 \times 5 + 7 + 9 \times 86} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{167835} & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{1 + (6 \times 7 \times 8 - 3) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{(1^6 + 7) \times 835} \\
 & := \frac{4 - 02}{1 - 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{173865} & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{(1 + 7^3 + 8 - 6) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 02}{17 \times 3 \times 865} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 01}{1 \times (7 - 3) \times 865} \\
 & := \frac{4 - 02}{17^3 \times 865} \\
 & := \frac{40 + 2}{1 \times 7 \times 3 \times 865} \\
 & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{(1 + 8 - 7) \times 935} \\
 & := \frac{4^{01}}{(1^8 + 7) \times 935} \\
 & := \frac{4 - 02}{1 - 8 + 7 + 935} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{196578} & := \frac{4^{01}}{1 - 9 + 6^5 + 7 \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{197583} &:= \frac{4 + 02}{(1 \times 975 + 8) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 02}{(1 + 9 + 7) \times 58 - 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{402}{385719} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{3857 - 19} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 02}{38 + 5719} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{402}{871536} := \frac{4 + 0 \times 2}{8 \times (71 \times 5 + 3^6)}$$

• Numerator 403

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{403}{6851} &:= \frac{4 - 03}{6 \times (8 - 5) - 1} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 03}{68 + 51} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{403}{9672} &:= \frac{4 - 03}{9 + 6 + 7 + 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 03}{96 + 72} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{403}{12896} &:= \frac{4 - 03}{1 \times 2^{8-9+6}} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 03}{128 + 96} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 03}{128 \times (9 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{40 \times 3}{1 \times (2^8 \times (9 + 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{26195} := \frac{4 - 03}{2^6 + 1^{95}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 3}{(2^6 + 1) \times (9 - 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{26598} := \frac{4 - 03}{2 - ((6 - (5 + 9)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 3}{2 \times (6 \times (5 + 9 + 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{51987} := \frac{4 - 03}{51 - (9 - 87)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 3}{5 + ((1 + 9 \times 8) \times 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{57629} := \frac{4 - 03}{5 \times 7 + (6 \times (2 \times 9))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{82615} := \frac{4 - 03}{(8 \times (26 - 1)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 3}{82 \times (6 - 1 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 03}{82 \times (6 \times 1 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{198276} := \frac{4 + 03}{1^9 \times 82 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 03}{(1 + 9 + 8 \times (2 + 7)) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{267189} := \frac{4 + 0 \times 3}{26 \times (7 - 1) \times (8 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 03}{2 \times 6 \times 7 \times 1 \times 8 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{916825} := \frac{4 \times 03}{91 \times 6 \times (8 + 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 3}{91 \times (68 + 2^5)}$$

• Numerator 405

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{405}{729} &:= \frac{40 - 5}{72 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{40 + 5}{72 + 9} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 05}{7 + 29} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{792} := \frac{40 + 5}{7 + 9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{891} := \frac{40 + 5}{8 + 91}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{1368} := \frac{40 + 5}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{2187} := \frac{40 - 5}{2 + 187}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 05}{21 + 87}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{2673} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(2 + (6 \times 7)) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{12798} := \frac{4 \times 05}{1^2 \times (79 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{19278} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(19 - 2) \times 7 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{19683} := \frac{4 \times 05}{1 + (968 + 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{73629} := \frac{4 \times 05}{7 + 3629}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{91368} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(91 + 3) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{91728} := \frac{40 + 5}{91 \times (7 \times 2 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{138267} := \frac{4 \times 05}{1 \times 3^8 + 267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{178362} := \frac{4 \times 05}{17 \times (8^3 + 6) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{183627} := \frac{40 - 5}{((18 + 3) \times 6)^2 - 7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{405}{237168} &:= \frac{4 \times 05}{(2 \times 3^{7-1} + 6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{405}{367281} &:= \frac{40 + 5}{(3^6 \times 7 - 2) \times 8 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{405}{267381} &:= \frac{4 \times 05}{2 \times (6 \times 7 + 3^8 - 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{405}{371628} &:= \frac{4 \times 05}{37 \times 1 \times 62 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 406

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{812} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{8 \times 1^2} & & := \frac{4 + 06}{(1 \times 27 + 8) \times 9} & & := \frac{4^{06}}{(1 + 7)^5 \times 3 \times 9 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 06}{8 + 12} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{19285} &:= \frac{40 - 6}{(1 + 9 \times 2) \times 85} & & := \frac{40 + 6}{(1^7 + 5)^3 \times 92} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{1827} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{1 + 8 + 2 + 7} & & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{(1 + (9 + 28)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{213759} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{(2 + 1) \times (3 + 75) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 06}{18 + 27} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{23751} &:= \frac{40 - 6}{(2 + 37) \times 51} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{279531} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{2 + 7 + (9 + 5)^3 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{3857} &:= \frac{4 + 06}{3 + (85 + 7)} & & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{(2 + 37) \times (5 + 1)} & & := \frac{40 - 6}{(2 \times 79 - 5)^{3-1}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{5278} &:= \frac{4 + 06}{52 + 78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{35728} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{(35 + 7 + 2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{319725} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{(3 - 1) \times 9 \times 7 \times 25} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{8932} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{89 - 3 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{52983} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{5 + (2^9 + (8 - 3))} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{12789} &:= \frac{40 - 6}{(127 - 8) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{139258} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 92 \times 5 - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{406}{175392} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{(1 \times 7 + 5) \times (3 + 9)^2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 6}{(1 - 2 + 7 + 8) \times 9} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 407

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{518} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{5 + 1 + 8} & & := \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{1 \times (6 + 2 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{3256} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{32 + 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{592} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{5 + 9 + 2} & & := \frac{4 + 07}{1 \times (6^2 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{3589} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{3 + (5 + 89)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{629} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{6 + 2 + 9} & & := \frac{4 \times 07}{(16 - 2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{5291} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{52 + 91} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{1258} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{1 + 25 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{2368} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{(2 \times 36) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{5698} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{56 \times (9 - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{1295} &:= \frac{40 - 7}{(12 + 9) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{3182} &:= \frac{40 - 7}{((3 - 1)^8) + 2} & & := \frac{4 + 07}{56 + 98} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 07}{1 + 29 + 5} & & := \frac{4 + 07}{3 + (1 + 82)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{6512} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{65 - 1^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{1628} &:= \frac{4^{07}}{1 \times ((6 - 2)^8)} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{13986} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{1 \times (3 \times (9 \times (8 + 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{16539} &:= \frac{40 - 7}{1 + (((6 + 5)^3) + 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{36852} &:= \frac{40 - 7}{36 \times (85 - 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{253968} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{(25 + 3 \times 9) \times 6 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{16983} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{1 - ((6 \times 9) - (8^3))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{56832} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{(56 - 8) \times 32} & &:= \frac{4 + 07}{(2^5 \times 3 \times 9 - 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{19536} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{195 + 3 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{59681} &:= \frac{40 - 7}{(5 \times 968) - 1} & &:= \frac{4 \times 07}{2^5 \times 39 \times (6 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 07}{1 - (9 - 536)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{63825} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{((6^3) \times 8) + (2 - 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{286935} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{(2 \times 86 \times 9 + 3) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{25863} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{(2 \times (58 \times 6)) + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{95238} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{9 \times ((5 + 2^3) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{396825} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{39 \times (68 + 2^5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{31968} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{(3 - 1) \times (9 \times 6 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{189625} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{(1 + 8^{9-6} \times 2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{32856} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{32 + 856} & \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{195286} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{1 - 9 + 5286} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{407}{35816} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 7}{358 - 1 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 408

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{561} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{5 + 61} & &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{1 + (6 + 3^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{6732} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{67 - 3 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{612} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{6 \times 1^2} & &:= \frac{40 + 8}{1 \times (6 \times 32)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{7956} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{79 + 5 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{40 + 8}{6 \times 12} & &:= \frac{4 + 08}{16 + 32} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{17952} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{179 - 5 + 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 08}{6 + 12} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1972} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{1 \times (9 + 7^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{29376} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{2 \times 9 \times (3 + 7 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{952} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{(9 + 5) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{2176} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{2^{17 \times 6}} & &:= \frac{40 \times 8}{2^9 \times (3 + 7 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1275} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{3162} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{31 \times (6 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{37162} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{((3^7 - 1) \times 6) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1326} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{13 \times (2 + 6)} & &:= \frac{40 + 8}{31 \times 6 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{65739} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{6^5 + (7 \times (3 - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{1 - (3 \times (2 - 6))} & &:= \frac{4 + 08}{31 + 62} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{67932} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{6 \times (79 + 32)} \\ &:= \frac{40 + 8}{13 \times 2 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{3672} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{36 + 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{251379} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{2^5 + 1 + 3^7 \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 08}{1 + (32 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{5712} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{57 - 1^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{597312} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{(5 \times 97 + 3) \times 12} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1632} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{(1 + 63) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{5916} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{59 - 1^6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{408}{793152} &:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times 3^{1 \times 5} \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 08}{(7 + 9) \times 3^{1+5} \times 2}$$

● Numerator 409

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{2863} := \frac{4 \times 09}{28 \times (6 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 09}{2 + (86 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 0 \times 9}{2 + (8 + (6 \times 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{3681} := \frac{4 \times 09}{36 \times (8 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 09}{36 + 81}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{5317} := \frac{4 + 0 \times 9}{53 - 17}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{7362} := \frac{4 + 0 \times 9}{7 + (3 + 62)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{37628} := \frac{4 + 0 \times 9}{(3 + (7 + 6^2)) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{68712} := \frac{4 + 0 \times 9}{6 \times (8 \times (7 \times 1 \times 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{156238} := \frac{4 + 0 \times 9}{(1 \times 5 + 62 \times 3) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{379865} := \frac{4 \times 1 + 0}{3 + 7 \times (9 + 8 \times 65)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{3526} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{3 + (5 \times (2 + 6))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{3895} := \frac{4 \times 1 + 0}{3 \times 8 + 9 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 10}{38 + 95}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{5986} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{59 + 8 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{7298} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{72 + 9 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{8692} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{8 + (6 + 92)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{9635} := \frac{4 \times 1 + 0}{96 + 3 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{23698} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{(23 - 6) \times (9 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{23985} := \frac{4 \times 1 + 0}{2 \times (39 \times (8 - 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{36859} := \frac{4 \times 10}{(((3^6) - 8) \times 5) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{36982} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{369 + 82}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{37925} := \frac{4 + 10}{(3 + ((7 + 9)^2)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{39852} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{3 \times (9 \times (8 + 5 \times 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{62935} := \frac{4 \times 1 + 0}{629 - (3 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{69782} := \frac{4 + 1 + 0}{69 + 782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{93275} := \frac{4 + 10}{(93 - 2) \times 7 \times 5}$$

● Numerator 412

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{3708} := \frac{4 - 1 \times 2}{3 + (7 + 08)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 1^2}{3 \times (7 + 08)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 1)^2}{3 + (70 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{5768} := \frac{4 - 1 - 2}{5 + (7 - 6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 2)}{(5 + 7) \times (6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1)^2}{(57 \times 6) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{6798} := \frac{4 \times 1^2}{67 - 9 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1) \times 2}{67 + 98}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 12}{(6 \times 7 - 9) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{37698} := \frac{4 + 1 \times 2}{3 + (7 \times (6 + 9 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 12}{3 \times ((7 + (6 \times 9)) \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{53869} := \frac{4 \times 1^2}{538 - (6 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{57680} := \frac{4 - 1^2}{5 \times (76 + 8 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 2)}{5 \times (7 \times (6 \times (8 + 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{59637} := \frac{4 \times 1^2}{5 + ((9 \times 63) + 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{60358} := \frac{4 - 1 \times 2}{((60 - 3) \times 5) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{67980} := \frac{4 - 1 - 2}{6 + (79 + 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 1 \times 2}{6 \times ((7 \times 9) - (8 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 12}{(6 \times 7 - 9) \times 80}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{70658} &:= \frac{4-1 \times 2}{7^{06+5-8}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{98056} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^2}{(9+8+0) \times 56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{586379} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^2}{5+8 \times (6+3) \times 79} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{75396} &:= \frac{41+2}{(7 \times (5^3 \times 9)) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{376980} &:= \frac{4+12}{3 \times (7+6 \times 9) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{837596} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 2}{(8+3 \times 75 \times 9) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{87035} &:= \frac{4+12}{((8+7+0)^3) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{578963} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^2}{5+78 \times (9+63)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{412}{90537} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{(90 \times 5) + (3^7)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 413

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{826} &:= \frac{4^{1+3}}{8 \times (2^6)} & &:= \frac{41+3}{20 \times (6+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{57820} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^3}{5 \times (7 \times (8 \times (2+0)))} \\ &:= \frac{4+1-3}{8+2-6} & &:= \frac{4^{1 \times 3}}{(2^{06}) \times 5} & &:= \frac{4+1 \times 3}{5 \times (7 \times (8+20))} \\ &:= \frac{4+1^3}{(8 \times 2) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{5782} &:= \frac{4-1 \times 3}{5 - (7 - (8 \times 2))} & &:= \frac{4 \times (1+3)}{5 \times (7 \times (8^2+0))} \\ &:= \frac{4-1+3}{8-2+6} & &:= \frac{4+1-3}{5+(7+8 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{60298} &:= \frac{4+1-3}{60+(29 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{4+1+3}{8+2+6} & &:= \frac{4+1 \times 3}{(57-8) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{285796} &:= \frac{4-1 \times 3}{2 \times (8-5+7^{9-6})} \\ &:= \frac{4+13}{8+26} & &:= \frac{(4+1) \times 3}{5 \times (7 \times (8-2))} & &:= \frac{4-1^3}{2^8 \times 5 + 796} \\ &:= \frac{41-3}{82-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{8260} &:= \frac{4-1 \times 3}{8+(2 \times 6+0)} & &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 3}{2 \times 8 \times (57 \times 9+6)} \\ &:= \frac{41+3}{82+6} & &:= \frac{4-1^3}{(8+2) \times (6+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{295708} &:= \frac{(4-1) \times 3}{2 \times 9 \times (5 \times 70+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{2065} &:= \frac{4-1 \times 3}{(2 \times (0 \times 6)) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{9086} &:= \frac{4-1^3}{(9 \times 08) - 6} & &:= \frac{4-1 \times 3}{2 \times (9-5) + 708} \\ &:= \frac{4+1-3}{2 \times ((0 \times 6) + 5)} & &:= \frac{4 \times 1^3}{90-8+6} & &:= \frac{4^{1+3}}{2^9 \times (5 \times 70+8)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 1^3}{20 \times (6-5)} & &:= \frac{4+1+3}{90+86} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{697085} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 3}{(69+70) \times 85} \\ &:= \frac{4+1+3}{(2+06) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{20768} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 3}{(2-(0-7 \times 6)) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{708295} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^3}{70 \times (8+2 \times 9 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 3}{2 \times (0+6 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{26078} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 3}{((2+60) \times 7) + 8} \\ &:= \frac{4+13}{20+65} & \blacktriangleright \frac{413}{57289} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 3}{(5 \times (7 \times 28)) - 9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 415

$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{830} := \frac{4+15}{8+30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{23987} := \frac{4+1^5}{2+((3 \times 98)-7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{73206} := \frac{(4-1) \times 5}{((7 \times 3)^2 + 0) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{2739} := \frac{4+1^5}{(2 \times 7 \times 3) - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{26809} := \frac{(4-1) \times 5}{(2 \times (6 \times 80)) + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{79680} := \frac{4 \times 1^5}{(7+9) \times (6 \times (8+0))}$
$:= \frac{4+1+5}{2+(73-9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{27390} := \frac{(4-1) \times 5}{(2 \times 7 - 3) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{297306} := \frac{(4-1) \times 5}{2^9 \times 7 \times 3 - 06}$
$:= \frac{(4-1) \times 5}{(2 \times 7 - 3) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{4 \times 1^5}{273 - (9+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{297638} := \frac{(4-1) \times 5}{(2+976) \times (3+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{6308} := \frac{(4-1) \times 5}{6 \times (30+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{27639} := \frac{4+1+5}{27+639}$	$:= \frac{4+1^5}{2 \times (9+(7+6^3) \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{6723} := \frac{4+1^5}{6+(72+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{30627} := \frac{4+1+5}{(3^06)+2+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{679023} := \frac{4+1+5}{6 \times (7+902) \times 3}$
$:= \frac{4+1+5}{6 \times ((7+2) \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{30876} := \frac{(4+1) \times 5}{30 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{890673} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 5}{(8+90) \times 6 \times 73}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{6972} := \frac{4+1^5}{6 \times (9+7-2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{38927} := \frac{4+1+5}{3+(8+927)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{8632} := \frac{(4+1) \times 5}{8 \times (63+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{67230} := \frac{4-1+5}{6 \times (72 \times (3+0))}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{9628} := \frac{4+1^5}{(9 \times 6 \times 2) + 8}$	$:= \frac{4+1+5}{6 \times ((7+2) \times 30)}$	

• Numerator 416

$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{520} := \frac{4+16}{5+20}$	$:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{37908} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{3^7 \times (9-08)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{572} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{5 \times 7 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{2730} := \frac{4 \times 16}{2 \times (7 \times 30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{39052} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{3 + (90 \times (5^2))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{728} := \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{3952} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{3 + (9 \times (5^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{53872} := \frac{4+1 \times 6}{5 \times ((3 \times 87) - 2)}$
$:= \frac{4+16}{7+28}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{5720} := \frac{4 \times 1^6}{57-2+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{73528} := \frac{4 \times 1^6}{735-28}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{832} := \frac{4^{1+6}}{8^{3+2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{7280} := \frac{4 \times 1^6}{7 \times (2+8+0)}$	$:= \frac{4+16}{7+3528}$
$:= \frac{4 \times 1^6}{8 \times (3-2)}$	$:= \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times (2 \times 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{85293} := \frac{4 \times 16}{(8+5 \times 2) \times 9^3}$
$:= \frac{4+1^6}{(8-3) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{8320} := \frac{4+1^6}{(8-3) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{258739} := \frac{4 \times 16}{2 \times (58 \times 7^3 + 9)}$
$:= \frac{4+1+6}{(8+3) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{4+1+6}{(8+3) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{278395} := \frac{4 \times 16}{(27+8)^3 - 9 \times 5}$
$:= \frac{4+16}{8+32}$	$:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{507832} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{(50+7) \times (8^3+2)}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{507923} := \frac{4 \times 16}{5^{07} + 9 + 2^3}$$

● Numerator 417

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{695} &:= \frac{4+1+7}{6+9+5} &:= \frac{4-1^7}{2-(8-(35 \times 6))} &:= \frac{4+1+7}{2 \times (93-5) \times 6 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{2085} &:= \frac{41-7}{2 \times (0+85)} &:= \frac{4+1^7}{3 \times 5 \times 028} &:= \frac{4+17}{(2+9) \times 3 \times 56 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{4-1+7}{(2+08) \times 5} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^7}{(3+5 \times 8) \times (6+2)} &:= \frac{41+7}{2^9 \times (3-5+68)} \\ &:= \frac{4+1+7}{20 \times (8-5)} &:= \frac{4-1+7}{3-(5-862)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{358620} &:= \frac{4-1^7}{3 \times 5 \times 86 \times 2+0} \\ &:= \frac{4-1^7}{2-(0-(8+5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{58936} &:= \frac{4-1^7}{(5 \times (89-3)) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{362095} &:= \frac{4-1^7}{(3+6+2^{09}) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4+17}{20+85} & \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{93825} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 7}{9 \times (3+8) \times 25} & \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{568093} &:= \frac{4+1+7}{5^6+80 \times 9+3} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times 7)}{(20+8) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{293568} &:= \frac{4-1^7}{(2 \times 9 \times 3 \times 5-6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{938250} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 7}{9 \times (3+8) \times 250} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{3058} &:= \frac{4+1+7}{30+58} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^7}{(29+3) \times (5+6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{417}{28356} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^7}{283-(5+6)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 418

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{532} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{5+3^2} &:= \frac{(4+1) \times 8}{(3+7) \times 6^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{37620} &:= \frac{(4+1) \times 8}{((3+7) \times 6)^2 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{627} &:= \frac{4+18}{6+27} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{37+62} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^8}{(3+7) \times (6^2+0)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (1+8)}{6 \times (2+7)} &:= \frac{4+1^8}{3 \times (7+6+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{37905} &:= \frac{4+18}{3 \times (7 \times (90+5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{2356} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{2 \times 3+56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{6327} &:= \frac{4+18}{6+327} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{37962} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{37+962} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{2736} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{(2+7+3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{27056} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{2 \times ((70 \times 5) + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{67032} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{(6 \times (7+0 \times 3))^2} \\ &:= \frac{4+18}{(27-3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{27360} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{(2+7+3) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{67925} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 8}{6 \times ((7 \times 9+2) \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{3705} &:= \frac{4+18}{3 \times (70-5)} &:= \frac{4+18}{(27-3) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{237956} &:= \frac{4-1+8}{2 \times ((3-7+9)^5+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{3762} &:= \frac{4-1^8}{3^{7-6+2}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{35967} &:= \frac{4+18}{3+(5 \times (9 \times (6 \times 7)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{257906} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 8}{25 \times 790-6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{305976} &:= \frac{(4+1) \times 8}{305 \times (9+7) \times 6} &:= \frac{4+1^8}{35 \times (6 \times 9 + 7) \times 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{963072} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+8)}{(96 \times (3+0 \times 7))^2} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 1^8}{(3+05 \times 97) \times 6} &\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{359062} &:= \frac{4+18}{35 \times 90 \times 6-2} &:= \frac{4 \times 18}{9 \times 6 \times 3072} \\ &:= \frac{4+1^8}{30 \times (5+9 \times (7+6))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{372609} &:= \frac{4+18}{(3^7-2-6) \times 09} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^8}{96^{3 \times 0 \times 7+2}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{418}{356972} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^8}{35+69 \times 7^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{376029} &:= \frac{4+18}{(3^7+6 \times 02) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{4+1 \times 8}{3 \times 56 \times (9 \times 7-2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{679250} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 8}{6 \times (7 \times 9+2) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 419

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{419}{5028} &:= \frac{41-9}{(50-2) \times 8} &:= \frac{4-1^9}{3 \times ((6 \times (8+7)) - 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{419}{278635} &:= \frac{4-1^9}{(2+7+8 \times 6) \times 35} \\ &:= \frac{4+1^9}{50+2+8} &:= \frac{4+1^9}{368+72} &:= \frac{4+1^9}{(2+7+86) \times 35} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{419}{6285} &:= \frac{41-9}{6 \times (2 \times 8 \times 5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{419}{62850} &:= \frac{41-9}{6 \times (2 \times 8 \times 50)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{419}{368720} &:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times 9)}{(36+8) \times 720} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 1^9}{(6-2+8) \times 5} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^9}{(6-2+8) \times 50} &\blacktriangleright \frac{419}{762580} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^9}{7 \times (6+2+5) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{4+1^9}{62+8+5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{419}{76258} &:= \frac{4-1^9}{(7+6) \times (2+5 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{419}{36872} &:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times 9)}{(36+8) \times 72} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^9}{7 \times ((6+2+5) \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 420

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{420}{735} &:= \frac{4+20}{7+35} &\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{7938} &:= \frac{4 \times 20}{7 \times (9 \times 3 \times 8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{175938} &:= \frac{4 \times 20}{(1+7)^5 + 93 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{420}{1365} &:= \frac{4 \times 20}{(1+3) \times 65} &\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{16975} &:= \frac{4+20}{1-(6-975)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{196875} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+0)}{(1+9) \times (68+7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4+20}{13+65} &\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{18795} &:= \frac{4^2+0}{((1+8) \times 79) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{420}{1785} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+0)}{1-(7-(8 \times 5))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{137865} &:= \frac{4+20}{13+7865} \\ &:= \frac{4+20}{17+85} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 421

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{3789} &:= \frac{4-2-1}{3+(7+8-9)} \\ &:= \frac{4-2 \times 1}{3 \times (7+8-9)} \\ &:= \frac{4-2+1}{3+(7+8+9)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (2-1)}{(3-7+8) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{4+2 \times 1}{(3 \times (7+8))+9} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 1}{3 \times (7+8+9)} \\ &:= \frac{42+1}{378+9} \\ &:= \frac{42-1}{378-9} \\ &:= \frac{4+21}{(3 \times 78)-9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{9683} &:= \frac{4-2+1}{(9+6+8) \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 1}{(9 \times 6-8) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{37890} &:= \frac{4-2-1}{3+(78+9+0)} \\ &:= \frac{4-2 \times 1}{(3+7-8) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (2-1)}{(3-7+8) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 1}{(3+7) \times (8 \times (9+0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{78306} &:= \frac{4-2-1}{(7+(8 \times (3+0))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (2-1)}{7+(8+(3^{06}))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 2+1}{(7 \times 8 \times 30)-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{86305} &:= \frac{4+2+1}{(8 \times (6 \times 30))-5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{89673} &:= \frac{4-2-1}{(8 \times 9+6-7) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4-2 \times 1}{89-(6-(7^3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{96830} &:= \frac{4-2+1}{(9+6+8) \times 30} \\ &:= \frac{4+2 \times 1}{(9 \times 6-8) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{421}{386057} &:= \frac{4-2-1}{3 \times (8+60 \times 5)-7} \\ &:= \frac{4-2+1}{3 \times (860+57)} \\ &:= \frac{4+2-1}{((3+8) \times 60-5) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 423

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{517} &:= \frac{4+2+3}{5-1+7} \\ &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+17} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{705} &:= \frac{42-3}{70-5} \\ &:= \frac{42+3}{70+5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{987} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{(9-8) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{42-3}{98-7} \\ &:= \frac{42+3}{98+7} \\ &:= \frac{(4+2)^3}{9 \times 8 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{1598} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{1-(5-9 \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4+23}{(1+5) \times (9+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{5076} &:= \frac{(4-2) \times 3}{(5+07) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{5781} &:= \frac{(4-2) \times 3}{5+78-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{6815} &:= \frac{4+23}{(6+81) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{7896} &:= \frac{4+2+3}{7 \times (8 \times (9-6))} \\ &:= \frac{42-3}{7 \times (8+96)} \\ &:= \frac{42+3}{7 \times (8 \times (9+6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{8601} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 3}{8 \times (60+1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{9165} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{((9+1) \times 6)+5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 3}{(9-1) \times 65} \\ &:= \frac{4+23}{9 \times (1 \times 65)} \\ &:= \frac{42 \times 3}{91 \times 6 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{9870} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{(9-8) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{(4+2)^3}{9 \times (8 \times 70)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{15087} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{1+(50+8 \times 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{50619} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{(50 \times (6+1))+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{56917} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{(5 \times 69+1) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{68150} &:= \frac{4+23}{(6+81) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{81075} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{(8+107) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{107865} &:= \frac{4+2^3}{(10+7 \times 86) \times 5} & & := \frac{4+2+3}{(1+7 \times 5) \times (96+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{86715} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{(8 \times 6-7) \times 15} & \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{156087} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 3}{(1+5) \times (608+7)} & & := \frac{4+2-3}{(1 \times 7+5) \times (96+8)} \\ &:= \frac{(4-2)^3}{8 \times ((6 \times 7-1) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{167508} &:= \frac{4^2+3}{16+7508} & \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{178506} &:= \frac{4+2^3}{(1-7+850) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{91650} &:= \frac{4+2-3}{(9+1) \times 65+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{175968} &:= \frac{4^2+3}{(1+75) \times (96+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{569170} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{(5 \times 69+1) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 3}{(9-1) \times 650} & &:= \frac{(4-2) \times 3}{(1 \times 7+5 \times 9) \times 6 \times 8} & & \\ &:= \frac{4+23}{9 \times 1 \times 650} & &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+7+5) \times 96 \times 8} & & \\ &:= \frac{42 \times 3}{91 \times 6 \times 50} & &:= \frac{4+2 \times 3}{(1+7) \times 5 \times (96+8)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 425

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{425}{680} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{6 \times 8+0} & &:= \frac{4 \times 25}{19 \times (3 \times 80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{425}{67830} &:= \frac{(4-2) \times 5}{6 \times (7 \times (8+30))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{425}{1938} &:= \frac{4 \times 25}{19 \times 3 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{425}{39780} &:= \frac{(4-2) \times 5}{(3+9) \times (78+0)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{425}{3978} &:= \frac{4 \times 25}{(3+9) \times 78} & &:= \frac{4 \times 25}{(3+9) \times 780} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{425}{19380} &:= \frac{(4-2) \times 5}{19 \times (3 \times 8+0)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 426

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{781} &:= \frac{4+26}{7 \times 8-1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{18957} &:= \frac{4 \times 2-6}{1+(8 \times (9-5+7))} & &:= \frac{4-2+6}{(7^3) \times (-05+9)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 6}{7+81} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{30175} &:= \frac{42-6}{30 \times (17 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{137598} &:= \frac{4 \times 2-6}{(1 \times 3+7 \times 5) \times (9+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{3195} &:= \frac{4 \times 2-6}{3 \times (1+9-5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{31950} &:= \frac{4 \times 2-6}{3 \times (1^9 \times 50)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{137598} &:= \frac{4^2-6}{(1+37) \times 5 \times (9+8)} \\ &:= \frac{4-2+6}{(3+(1 \times 9)) \times 5} & &:= \frac{4-2+6}{(3+(1 \times 9)) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{150378} &:= \frac{4 \times 2-6}{1+(50-3) \times (7+8)} \\ &:= \frac{4+2+6}{(3-1) \times 9 \times 5} & &:= \frac{4+2+6}{(3-1) \times (9 \times 50)} & &:= \frac{4^2-6}{1+503 \times 7+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{3905} &:= \frac{4+26}{(3 \times 90)+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{73059} &:= \frac{4 \times 2-6}{7^{3-0 \times 59}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{189357} &:= \frac{4 \times 2+6}{(1+893-5) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{13987} &:= \frac{4+26}{1-(3-987)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 \times 2 - 6}{(18 \times 9 - 35) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{931875} & := \frac{4 + 2 \times 6}{(9 + 31) \times 875} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{426}{378501} & := \frac{4 \times (2 + 6)}{3^7 \times (8 + 5) + 01} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 427

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{610} & := \frac{(4 + 2) \times 7}{6 \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{6039} & := \frac{(4 + 2) \times 7}{603 - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{316590} & := \frac{(4 + 2) \times 7}{(3 + 1) \times (6^5 + 9) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{1098} & := \frac{(4 + 2) \times 7}{10 + 98} & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{31598} & := \frac{4 \times 2 - 7}{3 - 1^5 + 9 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{360815} & := \frac{4 \times (2 + 7)}{(3 + 6081) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{1586} & := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 7}{1 \times (58 - 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{139568} & := \frac{(4 + 2) \times 7}{(1 + 3 \times 95) \times 6 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{1830} & := \frac{4 \times 2 \times 7}{1 \times 8 \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{169580} & := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 7}{1 \times 695 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{5368} & := \frac{(4 + 2) \times 7}{536 - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{315980} & := \frac{4 \times 2 - 7}{(3 + 1) \times 5 + 9 \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 428

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{963} & := \frac{4^2 - 8}{9 + 6 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{9630} & := \frac{4 - 2 + 8}{9 + (6^3 + 0)} & & := \frac{4^2 + 8}{(51 - 3) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{4 + (2 \times 8)}{(9 + 6) \times 3} & & := \frac{4 + (2 \times 8)}{(9 + 6) \times 30} & & := \frac{4 + 28}{((5 - 1)^3) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{4 + 28}{9 + 63} & & := \frac{(4^2) \times 8}{96 \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{103576} & := \frac{4 - 2 + 8}{10 \times (3^5 - 7 + 6)} \\ & := \frac{(4^2) \times 8}{96 \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{10593} & := \frac{4^2 - 8}{105 + 93} & \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{179653} & := \frac{4^2 - 8}{1 + 7 \times 96 \times 5 - 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{1605} & := \frac{4^2 - 8}{1 \times (6 \times 05)} & & := \frac{4^2 + 8}{1 + 0593} & \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{193670} & := \frac{4 \times 28}{(1 + 9^3 - 6) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{5136} & := \frac{4 - 2 + 8}{5 \times ((1 + 3) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{19367} & := \frac{4 \times (2 + 8)}{1 + (9 \times (3 \times 67))} \\ & := \frac{4^2 + 8}{(51 - 3) \times 6} & & := \frac{4 \times 28}{(1 + ((9^3) - 6)) \times 7} \\ & := \frac{4 + 28}{((5 - 1)^3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{428}{51360} & := \frac{4 - 2 + 8}{5 \times ((1 + 3) \times 60)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 429

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{429}{715} & := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 9}{(7 - 1) \times 5} & & := \frac{4 \times (2 + 9)}{105 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{429}{1573} & := \frac{4 + 2 + 9}{1 + (57 - 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{429}{1053} & := \frac{4 + 2 \times 9}{1 + 053} & \blacktriangleright \frac{429}{1365} & := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{(13 - 6) \times 5} & & := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 9}{(15 + 7) \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{1638} := \frac{4 \times (2 + 9)}{(1 + 6) \times 3 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{18603} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{1 \times ((8 \times 60) - 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{158730} := \frac{4 + 29}{(1 + 58 \times 7) \times 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{3861} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{38 + 61}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{35061} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{(3 \times (50 \times 6)) - 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{173680} := \frac{4 + 29}{(173 - 6) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{6318} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{6 \times (3 \times (1 + 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{63180} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{(6 + 3) \times 180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{178035} := \frac{4 \times 2 + 9}{17 \times (80 + 3) \times 5}$
$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{4 + 2 \times 9}{6 \times (3 \times 18)}$	$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{4 + 2 \times 9}{6 \times (3 \times 180)}$	$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{4^2 - 9}{1 \times 7 \times (80 + 3) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{7150} := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 9}{(7 - 1) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{67158} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{6 \times (7 \times (1 + 5 \times 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{187356} := \frac{4 \times (2 + 9)}{1 \times 8 + 7^3 \times 56}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{7865} := \frac{4 + 2 + 9}{(7 + 8 \times 6) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{75816} := \frac{4 + 29}{(7 + 5) \times (81 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{316758} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{31 \times (6 + (7 - 5)^8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{13650} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{(13 - 6) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{78650} := \frac{4 + 2 + 9}{(7 + 8 \times 6) \times 50}$	$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{4 \times (2 + 9)}{((3 + 1)^6 - 7 \times 5) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{15730} := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 9}{(15 + 7) \times 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{85137} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{(8 + 51) \times 37}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{385671} := \frac{42 + 9}{(3^8 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{15873} := \frac{4 + 29}{(1 + (58 \times 7)) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{85371} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{8 - (5 - (3^7 - 1))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{758160} := \frac{4 + 29}{(7 + 5) \times 81 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{16380} := \frac{4 \times (2 + 9)}{(1 + 6) \times (3 \times 80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{106587} := \frac{4 + 29}{(10 - 6)^5 \times 8 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{853710} := \frac{4 \times (2 + 9)}{8 \times (5 \times 3^7 + 10)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{17368} := \frac{4 + 29}{(173 - 6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{107835} := \frac{4 - 2 + 9}{(1 + 078) \times 35}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{17563} := \frac{4 + 29}{1 + (75 \times 6 \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{156780} := \frac{4 + 2 \times 9}{15 \times 67 \times 8 + 0}$	

● Numerator 430

$\blacktriangleright \frac{430}{12685} := \frac{4 + 30}{(126 \times 8) - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{430}{26875} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 0}{2 \times ((68 + 7) \times 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{430}{18576} := \frac{4 \times 30}{(1 + 8) \times 576}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{430}{69875} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 0}{6 \times ((9 + 8 \times 7) \times 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{430}{26789} := \frac{4 \times 30}{2 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{430}{726915} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 0}{7^2 \times 69 \times (1 + 5)}$

● Numerator 431

$\blacktriangleright \frac{431}{862} := \frac{4 - 3 + 1}{8 - 6 + 2}$	$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{4 \times (3 - 1)}{8 + 6 + 2}$	$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{43 - 1}{86 - 2}$
$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{4 + 3 - 1}{8 + 6 - 2}$	$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{43 + 1}{86 + 2}$	$\quad \quad \quad := \frac{4^{3-1}}{8 \times (6 - 2)}$

$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4+31}{8+62}$	$\frac{431}{8620} := \frac{4^3-1}{2 \times 5 + 86}$	$\frac{431}{68529} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 1}{(5+6) \times (8 \times 9 \times 2)}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4-3 \times 1}{2 \times (5-8+6)}$	$\frac{431}{8620} := \frac{4-3 \times 1}{8+(6 \times 2+0)}$	$\frac{431}{68529} := \frac{4-3 \times 1}{6+(8+(5 \times 29))}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4-3+1}{2+(5 \times (8-6))}$	$\frac{431}{8620} := \frac{4-3+1}{(8-6) \times 20}$	$\frac{431}{68529} := \frac{4+3-1}{((6 \times 8)+5) \times (2 \times 9)}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4+3-1}{2+(5 \times 8-6)}$	$\frac{431}{25860} := \frac{4-3+1}{2+(58+60)}$	$\frac{431}{87062} := \frac{4+31}{8+7062}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4 \times (3-1)}{2+(5 \times 8+6)}$	$\frac{431}{25860} := \frac{4+3-1}{(2+58) \times (6+0)}$	$\frac{431}{95682} := \frac{4+3-1}{95 \times (6+8)+2}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{43+1}{258+6}$	$\frac{431}{25860} := \frac{4 \times (3-1)}{2 \times (5 \times (8 \times (6+0)))}$	$\frac{431}{568920} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 1}{(5+6) \times 8 \times 9 \times 20}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{43-1}{(2+5 \times 8) \times 6}$	$\frac{431}{25860} := \frac{43-1}{(2+5 \times 8) \times 60}$	$\frac{431}{685290} := \frac{4 \times 31}{6 \times (8^5+2+90)}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4 \times 3-1}{2+(58+6)}$	$\frac{431}{25860} := \frac{4^{3+1}}{2^5 \times (8 \times 60)}$	$\frac{431}{825796} := \frac{4 \times (3+1)}{8^2 \times (5+79 \times 6)}$
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 1}{2+(5 \times (8+6))}$	$\frac{431}{56892} := \frac{4+3-1}{56+(8 \times 92)}$	
$\frac{431}{2586} := \frac{4^{3+1}}{2^5 \times 8 \times 6}$		

• Numerator 432

$\frac{432}{576} := \frac{4-3+2}{5-7+6}$	$\frac{432}{15876} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{1+(5+876)}$	$\frac{432}{57168} := \frac{4-3+2}{5+(7 \times ((1+6) \times 8))}$
$\frac{432}{756} := \frac{4+32}{7+56}$	$\frac{432}{17850} := \frac{(4 \times 3)^2}{1 \times (7 \times 850)}$	$\frac{432}{58176} := \frac{4-3+2}{(5 \times 81)-7+6}$
$\frac{432}{1056} := \frac{43+2}{10 \times (5+6)}$	$\frac{432}{17856} := \frac{4+3+2}{(1+(7 \times 8+5)) \times 6}$	$\frac{432}{71568} := \frac{4-3+2}{7 \times (1+5 \times (6+8))}$
$\frac{432}{1680} := \frac{(4 \times 3)^2}{(1+6) \times 80}$	$\frac{432}{18576} := \frac{(4-3)^2}{1 \times (85-7 \times 6)}$	$\frac{432}{75168} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{7 \times (1 \times 568)}$
$\frac{432}{1785} := \frac{(4 \times 3)^2}{1 \times 7 \times 85}$	$\frac{432}{18576} := \frac{(4-3) \times 2}{1+(85 \times (7-6))}$	$\frac{432}{75168} := \frac{4 \times (3-2)}{(7+5 \times 16) \times 8}$
$\frac{432}{5076} := \frac{4 \times (3-2)}{5+07 \times 6}$	$\frac{432}{18576} := \frac{4 \times (3-2)}{185-(7+6)}$	$\frac{432}{107856} := \frac{4-3+2}{107 \times (8+5-6)}$
$\frac{432}{7056} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{7 \times 056}$	$\frac{432}{18576} := \frac{(4+3) \times 2}{1+((85 \times 7)+6)}$	$\frac{432}{107856} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{1 \times 07 \times 856}$
$\frac{432}{7968} := \frac{4+32}{7 \times 96-8}$	$\frac{432}{18576} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{(18 \times 57)+6}$	$\frac{432}{150768} := \frac{(4-3) \times 2}{(1-50 \times 7) \times (6-8)}$
$\frac{432}{15768} := \frac{(4-3) \times 2}{1 \times (5+(76-8))}$		

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(4-3)^2}{1+50 \times 7+6-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{179856} & := \frac{4-3+2}{1+(7+9) \times (8+5) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{197856} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 2}{(1+9) \times 7 \times (8+5)+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{158760} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 2}{1 \times 5 \times (87+60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{180576} & := \frac{(4-3)^2}{(1+80) \times 5+7+6} & & := \frac{(4-3)^2}{1+9+7 \times (8+56)} \\
 & := \frac{(4-3)^2}{(1+5 \times 8) \times 9-7+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{185976} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 2}{1+859+7-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{715680} & := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{7 \times 1 \times 5680} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (3-2)}{(15+8) \times (9-7)^6} & & := \frac{4+32}{(1+8 \times 5) \times 9 \times 7 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{786591} & := \frac{(4 \times 3)^2}{7+8^6+5 \times 9+1} \\
 & := \frac{4+3+2}{(1+5) \times 8 \times (9 \times 7+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{186579} & := \frac{(4 \times 3)^2}{1+8 \times (6^5+7-9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{791568} & := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{(7+915 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{176895} & := \frac{(4 \times 3)^2}{(1-7) \times (6+8)+9^5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{187596} & := \frac{4 \times (3-2)}{1+8+(7+5)^{9-6}} & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{178560} & := \frac{4+3+2}{(1+7 \times 8+5) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{432}{189756} & := \frac{4 \times (3-2)}{18 \times 97+5+6} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 435

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{870} & := \frac{4+35}{8+70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{18270} & := \frac{(4-3)^5}{1 \times ((8-2) \times (7+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{60291} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 5}{602+91} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{8961} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 5}{8+(96-1)} & & := \frac{(4-3) \times 5}{(1^8+2) \times 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{127890} & := \frac{4 \times 3-5}{(1+2) \times 7 \times (8+90)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{1827} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 5}{(1^8+2) \times 7} & & := \frac{4-3+5}{18 \times (2 \times (7+0))} & & := \frac{(4-3) \times 5}{(1+2 \times 7) \times (8+90)} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{18 \times 2 \times 7} & & := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{18 \times (2 \times 70)} & & := \frac{4+3-5}{(1-2+7) \times (8+90)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{2610} & := \frac{(4-3)^5}{2-(6-10)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{26970} & := \frac{(4-3)^5}{2^6-(9-7+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{187920} & := \frac{4+3+5}{(1-8-79)^2+0} \\
 & := \frac{4+3-5}{2 \times (6 \times 1+0)} & & := \frac{4+3-5}{2 \times (69-7+0)} & & := \frac{43+5}{((1+8+7) \times 9)^2+0} \\
 & := \frac{4-3+5}{26+10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{28710} & := \frac{(4-3)^5}{2+(8 \times (7+1+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{279618} & := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{(2+79 \times 61) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{10962} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 5}{(10 \times 9)+6^2} & & := \frac{4+3-5}{2 \times ((8 \times 7)+10)} & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{435}{12789} & := \frac{(4-3) \times 5}{1 \times ((2 \times 78)-9)} & & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 436

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{436}{872} := \frac{4+3-6}{(8-7) \times 2} \qquad := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{8 \times (7+2)} \qquad := \frac{4+36}{8+72}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{981} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 + 6)}{9 \times (8 + 1)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 36}{9 + 81} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{2180} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 \times 6}{2 \times 180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{8175} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 + 6)}{(8 + 1) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{8720} &:= \frac{4 + 3 - 6}{(8 - 7) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{19075} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times (90 \times 7 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{25179} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 + 6)}{(2^5 + 1) \times 7 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{81750} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 + 6)}{(8 + 1) \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{109872} &:= \frac{(4 - 3) \times 6}{(10 + 98) \times 7 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 3 - 6}{(1 + 09 + 8) \times 7 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 36}{10 \times 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{170258} &:= \frac{(4 - 3) \times 6}{(1 + 70) \times (25 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{251790} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 + 6)}{(2^5 + 1) \times 7 \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{290158} &:= \frac{4 + 3 \times 6}{(2 + 9 + 0)^{1-5+8}} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 437

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{529} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{5 + 2 \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - 3) \times 7}{(10 \times 9 \times 2) - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{621} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{6 + 21} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 3 + 7}{10 \times ((9 - 2) \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{2185} &:= \frac{(4 - 3)^7}{2 + 1 \times 8 - 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{(10 + 9) \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{43 - 7}{10 \times (9 \times 2 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 3 - 7}{2 + (18 + 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{2691} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{26 + 91} \\ &:= \frac{43 - 7}{2 \times (18 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{5681} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 - 7}{5 \times (6 + 8 - 1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{10925} &:= \frac{(4 - 3)^7}{((1 + 09) \times 2) + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{16928} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1^6 \times (92 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{21850} &:= \frac{(4 - 3)^7}{(2 - 1^8) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 3 + 7}{(2 - 1) \times 8 \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{43 - 7}{2 \times (18 \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{50692} &:= \frac{(4 - 3)^7}{50 + (6 \times (9 + 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{82156} &:= \frac{(4 - 3)^7}{8 + (2 \times (15 \times 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{102695} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 - 7}{(1 + 026 \times 9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{169280} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1^6 \times 92 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{289156} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{28 \times (91 \times 5 - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{437}{290168} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{2 + 901 \times (6 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - 3) \times 7}{290 \times 16 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 438

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{657} &:= \frac{4 + 38}{6 + 57} \\ &:= \frac{(4^3) - 8}{10 \times (9 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - 3) \times 8}{1 \times (7 + 5^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{1095} &:= \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(1 + 09) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 3 + 8}{(1^7 + 5)^2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 38}{10 + 95} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{4+3+8}{1+(7+52)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{17520} & := \frac{(4-3)^8}{1 \times ((7-5) \times 20)} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 8}{(1 \times 69 - 7) \times 25} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(1+7) \times 5 \times 2} & & := \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(1+7) \times (5 \times 20)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{176952} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 8}{(1+7) \times (6+95) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (3+8)}{1+(7 \times (5^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{27156} & := \frac{(4-3)^8}{2 \times (7 - ((1-5) \times 6))} & := \frac{(4-3)^8}{1+7 \times 6 \times 9 + 5^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{2190} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 8}{2 \times (1+9+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{59276} & := \frac{4-3+8}{(((5+9)^2) + 7) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{276159} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 8}{2+7 \times 6 \times (1+59)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{6570} & := \frac{4-3+8}{65+70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{150672} & := \frac{(4-3)^8}{1 \times 50 + 6 \times 7^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{7592} & := \frac{4-3+8}{75+9^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{169725} & := \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(16 \times 97 - 2) \times 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 439

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{1756} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 9}{1 \times ((7-5) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{51802} & := \frac{(4-3)^9}{(51+8+0) \times 2} & := \frac{(4-3)^9}{(7 + ((6+8) \times 2)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(4-3) \times 9}{(1^7+5) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{52680} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 9}{5 \times (2^6+8+0)} & := \frac{4-3+9}{7 \times (((6 \times 8) + 2) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{4+3+9}{1+(7+56)} & & := \frac{(4-3)^9}{(5 \times (2+6)) + 80} & := \frac{4 \times (3+9)}{7 \times (6 \times (8 \times 25))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{5268} & := \frac{(4-3)^9}{5 \times 2 - 6 + 8} & & := \frac{4-3+9}{(5^2) \times (6 \times (8+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{287106} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 9}{(2^8+71) \times 06} \\
 & := \frac{4-3+9}{52+68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{60582} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 9}{6 \times (0+(5+8^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{768250} & := \frac{4 \times (3+9)}{7 \times 6 \times 8 \times 250} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{17560} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 9}{1 \times ((7-5) \times 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{439}{76825} & := \frac{4 \times 3 - 9}{7 \times (6+(8^2+5))} \\
 & := \frac{(4-3) \times 9}{(1^7+5) \times 60}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 451

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{902} & := \frac{4+5 \times 1}{9 \times 01} & & := \frac{45+1}{270+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{6273} & := \frac{4+51}{(6 \times 2^7) - 3} \\
 & := \frac{45-1}{90-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{3280} & := \frac{4+51}{(3+2) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{36982} & := \frac{4+5-1}{(3^6) + (9-82)} \\
 & := \frac{45+1}{90+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{3608} & := \frac{4+5 \times 1}{(3+6+0) \times 8} & & := \frac{4+5 \times 1}{(3 \times 6 - 9) \times 82} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{2706} & := \frac{4+5 \times 1}{(2+7+0) \times 6} & & := \frac{45-1}{360-8} & & := \frac{4+5+1}{(3^6) + (9+82)} \\
 & := \frac{45-1}{270-6} & & := \frac{45+1}{360+8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{45 \times 1}{3 \times ((6 + 9) \times 82)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{78023} & := \frac{4 + 5 \times 1}{(780 \times 2) - 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{283679} & := \frac{4 \times 5 + 1}{(2^8 + 3) \times (6 \times 7 + 9)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{296307} & := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 1}{2 \times 9 + 6 \times 3^{07}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{369820} & := \frac{4 + 5 \times 1}{(3^6 + 9) \times (8 + 2) + 0} \\ & := \frac{45 \times 1}{3 \times (6 + 9) \times 820} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{451}{739068} & := \frac{4^5 + 1}{7 \times (3 + 9) + 06^8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 452

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{678} & := \frac{4 + 5 \times 2}{6 + 7 + 8} \\ & := \frac{4 + 52}{6 + 78} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{791} & := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 2}{7 \times (9 + 1)} \\ & := \frac{4 + 52}{7 + 91} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{8136} & := \frac{4 - 5 + 2}{8 + (1 + 3 + 6)} \\ & := \frac{4 + 5 - 2}{(8 + 13) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{4 + 5 \times 2}{(8 - 1) \times 36} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 2}{(8 + 1) \times 36} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (5 + 2)}{(81 + 3) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 5)^2}{81 \times 3 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{10396} & := \frac{4 \times (5 - 2)}{(10 \times 3 \times 9) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{18306} & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 2}{1^8 \times 3^{06}} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 2}{(1 + 8) \times (30 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{37968} & := \frac{4 - 5 + 2}{3 - (7 - 96 + 8)} \\ & := \frac{4 + 5 + 2}{(3 + 7 \times 9) \times (6 + 8)} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (5 - 2)}{((3 + 7)^{9-6}) + 8} \\ & := \frac{4 \times 5 + 2}{3 \times (7 \times (96 - 8))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times 52}{(3^7 - 9 + 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{68139} & := \frac{4 \times (5 - 2)}{(68 - 1) \times 3 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{78196} & := \frac{4 - 5 + 2}{78 - (1 - 96)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{81360} & := \frac{4 + 5 - 2}{(8 + 13) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{4 + 5 \times 2}{(8 - 1) \times 360} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 2}{(8 + 1) \times 360} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 \times (5 + 2)}{(81 + 3) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 5)^2}{81 \times (3 \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{109836} & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 2}{(1^{09} + 8)^3 \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 5)^2}{(10 + 9 + 8) \times 3^6} \\ & := \frac{4 - 5 + 2}{(10 + 9 + 8) \times (3 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{137860} & := \frac{4 + 5 - 2}{1 \times 3^7 + 8 - 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{310976} & := \frac{4 - 5 + 2}{3 + 1 + 09 \times 76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{452}{379680} & := \frac{4 \times 5 + 2}{(3 \times 79 - 6) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{4 \times 52}{(3^7 - 9 + 6) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 453

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{906} & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 3}{9 \times 06} \\ & := \frac{45 - 3}{90 - 6} \\ & := \frac{45 + 3}{90 + 6} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{1208} & := \frac{4 + 5 - 3}{1 \times (2 \times 08)} \\ & := \frac{45 - 3}{120 - 8} \\ & := \frac{45 + 3}{120 + 8} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 3)}{1 \times (20 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{2718} & := \frac{4 - 5 + 3}{2 \times (7 - 1^8)} \\ & := \frac{4 + 5 - 3}{27 + 1 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{4+5+3}{(2+7 \times 1) \times 8} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{(1+08) \times 72} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{(2+7) \times 180} \\
 & := \frac{4^{5-3}}{2 \times ((7-1) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{12986} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{1^2 \times (9 \times 86)} & := \frac{45-3}{2 \times (7 \times 180)} \\
 & := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{(2+7) \times 18} & & := \frac{4+53}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 86} & \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{129860} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{1^2 \times 9 \times 860} \\
 & := \frac{45-3}{2 \times (7 \times 18)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{19026} & := \frac{4+5^3}{(1+902) \times 6} & := \frac{4+53}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 860} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{10268} & := \frac{4+5-3}{1 \times (0+(2 \times 68))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{27180} & := \frac{4-5+3}{(2^7 \times 1) - (8+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{297168} & := \frac{4 \times (5+3)}{2^9 \times (7 \times (1+6) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 3)}{10 \times (2 \times 68)} & & := \frac{4+5+3}{2+(718+0)} & & := \frac{4+5-3}{(2+9+71) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{453}{10872} & := \frac{4+5-3}{(10-8) \times 72} & := \frac{4^{5-3}}{2 \times ((7-1) \times 80)} & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 456

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{798} & := \frac{4+56}{7+98} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 6}{9 \times 120} & := \frac{4+5+6}{1+((8^3)+92)} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{912} & := \frac{4+5-6}{9-1-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{10792} & := \frac{4+5-6}{10+((7 \times 9)-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{38912} & := \frac{4+5-6}{(3 \times 8 - (9-1))^2} \\
 & := \frac{4-5+6}{9+1^2} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{10982} & := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 6}{10 \times ((9+8)^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{97280} & := \frac{4+5-6}{(9 \times 72) - (8+0)} \\
 & := \frac{(4+5) \times 6}{9 \times 12} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{17328} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 6}{(1-(7^3)) \times (2-8)} & & \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{3192} & := \frac{4+5-6}{3 \times (1 \times (9-2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{18392} & := \frac{4+5-6}{1-(8 \times (3-(9 \times 2)))} & & \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{456}{9120} & := \frac{4-5+6}{(9+1)^2+0} & & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 457

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{6398} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 7}{(6+3) \times 98} & := \frac{4-5+7}{(21+9 \times 3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{61238} & := \frac{4 \times 5 - 7}{6 + ((12^3) + 8)} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{10968} & := \frac{4+5-7}{(10^9) \times 6 \times 8} & := \frac{4+5+7}{2^{1+9-3} \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{63980} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 7}{(6+3) \times 980} \\
 & := \frac{45-7}{(10+9) \times 6 \times 8} & & := \frac{4 \times 5 + 7}{(219-3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{102368} & := \frac{4+5-7}{((10 \times (2+3)) + 6) \times 8} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{21936} & := \frac{4+5-7}{(2^{19+3}) \times 6} & := \frac{4+5 \times 7}{2 \times (1 \times 936)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{106938} & := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 7}{(1-06) \times (9-38)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{457}{219360} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 + 7}{(219 - 3) \times 60} &:= \frac{4 + 5 + 7}{2^{1+9-3} \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 5 + 7}{(21 + 9 \times 3) \times 60} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 7}{2^{19+3} \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 5 \times 7}{2 \times 1 \times 9360} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{457}{392106} := \frac{4 + 5 - 7}{(3 \times 92 + 10) \times 6}$$

● Numerator 458

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{458}{916} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 8}{9 - 1 - 6} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + 8)}{((19^2) + 3) \times 6} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + 8)}{(19^2 + 3) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 5 + 8}{9 - 1 + 6} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 8}{2 \times ((6 + 7) \times (9 \times 3))} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 8}{(1^9 + 2 \times 3) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 8}{9 \times 16} &:= \frac{458}{32976} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 8}{2 \times (6 + 7) \times 9 \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{458}{1603} &:= \frac{4 + 58}{1 + (6^{03})} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 8}{3^2 \times ((9 + 7) \times 6)} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 8}{(2 + 6 + 7) \times (9 + 30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{458}{3206} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 8}{3 - (2 - 06)} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 + 8}{(329 + 7) \times 6} &:= \frac{458}{329760} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 + 8}{(329 + 7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{458}{9160} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 8}{9 \times 160} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + 8)}{32 \times (9 \times (7 + 6))} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 8}{3^2 \times (9 + 7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{458}{19236} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 8}{((1 + 9 + 2) \times 3) + 6} &:= \frac{458}{61372} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 8}{(6 \times (1 + (3 \times 7))) + 2} &:= \frac{4 + 5 - 8}{3 \times 2 \times (9 - 7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 5 + 8}{(((1 + 9)^2) \times 3) - 6} &:= \frac{458}{137629} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 8}{(1 \times 3 + 7^{6-2}) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 8}{1 - 9 + 2^{3+6}} &:= \frac{458}{192360} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 8}{(1 \times 9^2 + 3) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 459

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{612} &:= \frac{45 + 9}{6 \times 12} &:= \frac{45 + 9}{1 \times (6 \times 32)} &:= \frac{45 - 9}{1 \times (8 \times 3 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{1326} &:= \frac{45 - 9}{13 \times (2 + 6)} &:= \frac{4 + 59}{(1 + 6) \times 32} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 9}{18 \times 3 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{45 + 9}{13 \times 2 \times 6} &:= \frac{459}{1683} &:= \frac{4 + 5 + 9}{1 \times (6 \times (8 + 3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{1360} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 9}{(1 + 3) \times 60} &:= \frac{459}{1836} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 9}{1 \times (8 + 36)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{1632} &:= \frac{45 - 9}{(1 + 63) \times 2} &:= \frac{459}{3162} &:= \frac{4 + 5 + 9}{31 \times (6 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{45 - 9}{(1 + 63) \times 2} &:= \frac{459}{3162} &:= \frac{45 - 9}{31 \times (6 + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{45 + 9}{31 \times 6 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{3672} & := \frac{4 + 59}{36 \times (7 \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 9}{(3 + 6) \times 72} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{6018} & := \frac{45 - 9}{(60 - 1) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{6120} & := \frac{45 + 9}{6 \times 120} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{12376} & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 9}{1 + (2 + (3^7 - 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{13260} & := \frac{45 - 9}{(1 + 3) \times 260} \\ & := \frac{45 + 9}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{16320} & := \frac{45 - 9}{(1 + 63) \times 20} \\ & := \frac{45 + 9}{1 \times (6 \times 320)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 + 59}{(1 + 6) \times 320} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{16728} & := \frac{4 + 5 + 9}{16 \times ((7^2) - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{17238} & := \frac{45 - 9}{(172 - 3) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{18360} & := \frac{4 + 5 + 9}{(1 + 8 + 3) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{45 - 9}{1 \times (8 \times (3 \times 60))} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 9}{18 \times (3 \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{31620} & := \frac{4 + 5 + 9}{(3 - 1) \times 620} \\ & := \frac{45 - 9}{(3 + 1) \times 620} \\ & := \frac{45 + 9}{31 \times (6 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{36720} & := \frac{4 + 59}{36 \times (7 \times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 9}{(3 + 6) \times 720} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{37128} & := \frac{45 + 9}{((3^7 + 1) \times 2) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{37162} & := \frac{45 + 9}{((3^{7-1}) \times 6) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{128367} & := \frac{4 + 5 + 9}{1 - (2 + 8 - 3^6) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{130628} & := \frac{45 + 9}{(130 - 6)^2 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{167382} & := \frac{4 + 5 + 9}{1 - (6 - 7) \times (3^8 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{172380} & := \frac{45 - 9}{(172 - 3) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{459}{371620} & := \frac{45 + 9}{(3^7 - 1^6) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 460

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{782} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{7 + 8 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{2875} & := \frac{4 \times 6 + 0}{2 \times ((8 + 7) \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{1932} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{1 + (9 + 32)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{5382} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{53 + 8^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{13892} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{13 + ((8 + 9)^2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{15732} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{1 \times (57 \times 3 \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{23598} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{23 + (5 \times 98)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{37812} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{3 + (7 + 812)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{129375} & := \frac{4 \times 6 + 0}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 375} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{139725} & := \frac{4^6 + 0}{(1 \times 3 + 9)^{7-2} \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 + 60}{(1 + 3) \times 972 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{317285} & := \frac{4 \times 6 + 0}{(3 + 1)^7 + 2 \times 85} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{460}{719532} & := \frac{4 + 6 + 0}{7 + 1 + 9 + 5^{3 \times 2}} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 461

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{461}{2305} & := \frac{4 + 6 \times 1}{2 \times (30 - 5)} \\ & := \frac{4 + 6 + 1}{(2 \times 30) - 5} \\ & := \frac{46 - 1}{230 - 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{46 + 1}{230 + 5} \\ & := \frac{4 \times 6 - 1}{23 \times 05} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{461}{37802} & := \frac{4 + 6 \times 1}{(3 + 7) \times (80 + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{461}{87590} := \frac{4 \times (6 + 1)}{8 \times (7 \times (5 + 90))}$$

● Numerator 462

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{735} := \frac{4+62}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{1785} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{17 \times 85} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{1890} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{1 + 89 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{1953} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{1 + 95 - 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{3150} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{3 \times 1 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{3850} := \frac{4+62}{3 \times 150} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{3850} := \frac{4 \times 6^2}{3 \times 8 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{7035} := \frac{4+62}{(3+8) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{7035} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{(70-3) \times 5} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{7315} := \frac{4+6+2}{(7+31) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{7350} := \frac{4+62}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{10395} := \frac{4+6-2}{(1+03) \times 9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{10857} := \frac{4 \times 6 + 2}{(10+3) \times 9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{10857} := \frac{(4+6) \times 2}{10 \times (8 \times 5 + 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{15379} := \frac{4+62}{1^5 + (3^7 + 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{15708} := \frac{4+6-2}{(1-(5 \times 7)) \times (-08)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{15708} := \frac{(4+6) \times 2}{(15+70) \times 8} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{17850} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{17 \times 850} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{18375} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{(1+8 \times 3) \times 7 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{18753} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{18 + (7 \times (5^3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{73150} := \frac{4+6+2}{(7+31) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{91875} := \frac{46-2}{(9+1) \times 875} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{462}{183750} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 2}{(1+8 \times 3) \times (7 \times 50)} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 463

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{1852} := \frac{4-6+3}{1^8 + 5 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{1852} := \frac{4+6-3}{(1+8+5) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{1852} := \frac{4+6+3}{1^8 \times 52} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{1852} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 3}{1 + (85 - 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{1852} := \frac{4 + (6 \times 3)}{1 + (85 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{1852} := \frac{46-3}{(1+85) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{1852} := \frac{46+3}{(1+8+5)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{15279} := \frac{4-6+3}{15 + (2+7+9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{15279} := \frac{4+6-3}{152+79} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{18520} := \frac{4 \times (6-3)}{(15 \times 27) - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{18520} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 3}{(1+5 \times 2) \times 7 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{18520} := \frac{4+6-3}{(1+8+5) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{81025} := \frac{4+6+3}{1^8 \times 520} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{81025} := \frac{46-3}{(1+85) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{81025} := \frac{4-6+3}{(8-1+0) \times 25} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{85192} := \frac{4-6+3}{8 \times (5 + (1 \times 9 \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{85192} := \frac{4+6-3}{(8+5+1) \times 92} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{90285} := \frac{46-3}{(85+1) \times 92} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{90285} := \frac{4 \times (6-3)}{90 \times (2 \times (8+5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{152790} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 3}{(1+5 \times 2) \times 7 \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{152790} := \frac{4 \times (6+3)}{15 \times (2+790)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{152790} := \frac{4 \times (6-3)}{1 \times 5 \times (2+790)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{463}{257891} := \frac{4-6+3}{2-5+7 \times 8 \times (9+1)} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 465

$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{837} := \frac{(4+6) \times 5}{83+7}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{930} := \frac{4-6+5}{9-3+0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{1023} := \frac{4+6-5}{10-2+3}$ $:= \frac{4+6+5}{10+23}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{2170} := \frac{4-6+5}{2 \times (1 \times (7+0))}$ $:= \frac{4+6+5}{(2-1) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{2790} := \frac{4-6+5}{2+(7+9+0)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{8370} := \frac{4+6-5}{83+7+0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{9207} := \frac{4+6-5}{92+07}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{13702} := \frac{4+6+5}{1+((3 \times (7+0))^2)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{23870} := \frac{4-6+5}{2 \times ((3+8) \times (7+0))}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{78120} := \frac{4 \times (6-5)}{7 \times (8 \times (12+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{189720} := \frac{4-6+5}{(1 \times 8+9) \times 72+0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{281790} := \frac{4-6+5}{28+1790}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{309287} := \frac{4+6+5}{(30+9) \times 2^8-7}$
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● Numerator 467

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{467}{193805} := \frac{4+6-7}{(1 \times 9+3 \times 80) \times 5}$$

● Numerator 468

$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{702} := \frac{4-6+8}{7+02}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{729} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{72+9}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{792} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{7+9^2}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{1053} := \frac{4 \times (6+8)}{1-(0-(5^3))}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{1350} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{1352} := \frac{4+6+8}{1^3 \times 52}$ $:= \frac{46+8}{1 \times (3 \times 52)}$ $:= \frac{4+68}{(1+3) \times 52}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{1593} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{1 \times (59 \times 3)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{2730} := \frac{4+68}{2 \times (7 \times 30)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{3120} := \frac{4-6+8}{(3-1) \times 20}$	$:= \frac{46+8}{3 \times 120}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{3510} := \frac{4+6-8}{3 \times (5 \times 1+0)}$ $:= \frac{4-6+8}{3 \times (5+10)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{7290} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{(7+2) \times 90}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{13520} := \frac{4+6+8}{1^3 \times 520}$ $:= \frac{46+8}{1 \times (3 \times 520)}$ $:= \frac{4+68}{(1+3) \times 520}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{13572} := \frac{4+6-8}{1+(3+(5+7^2))}$ $:= \frac{4-6+8}{1+((3 \times 57)+2)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{15930} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{1 \times (59 \times 30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{17352} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{(1+7) \times (3^5-2)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{19032} := \frac{4+6+8}{1+((9^0)^3)+2)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{31590} := \frac{4+6-8}{3 \times 1 \times 5 \times 9+0}$ $:= \frac{4-6+8}{3 \times 15 \times 9+0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{32175} := \frac{4 \times 6-8}{(3+217) \times 5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{72930} := \frac{4-6+8}{7-(2-930)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{73125} := \frac{4 \times 6+8}{((7+3)^{1+2}) \times 5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{107523} := \frac{4 \times 6-8}{1+(07 \times 5)^2 \times 3}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{127530} := \frac{4+6-8}{1+2 \times 7+530}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{130572} := \frac{4 \times 6-8}{(1+30) \times (5+7)^2}$ $:= \frac{4-6+8}{(1+30) \times (5+7^2)}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{135720} := \frac{4+6-8}{(1+35-7) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{175032} := \frac{4+6-8}{17 \times (50-3 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{371592} := \frac{4+6-8}{3-7+1592}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{137592} := \frac{4-6+8}{(1+3-7+5 \times 9)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{192375} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{1 \times 9 \times 2375}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{375921} := \frac{4 \times (6+8)}{(3^7-5 \times 9) \times 21}$
$\quad := \frac{4+6-8}{1 \times 3-7+592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{213759} := \frac{4+68}{2 \times ((1+3)^7+59)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{397512} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{(3^9+7^5-1) \times 2}$
$\quad := \frac{4+68}{1 \times 3 \times (75+9)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{219375} := \frac{4 \times 6-8}{2 \times (1+9) \times 375}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{507923} := \frac{4+68}{50^7+9+2^3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{153270} := \frac{4-6+8}{15 \times (3+2^7)+0}$	$\quad := \frac{4 \times (6+8)}{(21+9^3) \times 7 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{731250} := \frac{4 \times 6+8}{(7+3)^{1+2} \times 50}$
$\quad := \frac{4+6-8}{1 \times 5 \times (3+2^7)+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{321750} := \frac{4 \times 6-8}{(3+217) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{739125} := \frac{4+6 \times 8}{73 \times 9 \times 125}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{170352} := \frac{4+6-8}{1 \times 703+5^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{352170} := \frac{4+6-8}{35+21 \times 70}$	

• Numerator 469

$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{1072} := \frac{4-6+9}{(1+07) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{21708} := \frac{4-6+9}{2 \times (170-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{82075} := \frac{4+6-9}{(8+(20+7)) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{3015} := \frac{4-6+9}{3 \times (015)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{27135} := \frac{4-6+9}{27 \times (1 \times 3 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{128037} := \frac{4 \times 6-9}{1-2+8^{-03+7}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{3082} := \frac{4-6+9}{30+8 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{31825} := \frac{4-6+9}{(31+8^2) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{135072} := \frac{4+6-9}{(1+3 \times 50-7) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{3752} := \frac{4+6-9}{(3 \times (7-5))+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{37051} := \frac{4+6-9}{3+(70+5+1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{271350} := \frac{4-6+9}{27 \times 1 \times 3 \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{7035} := \frac{4+6-9}{7-(0-3-5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{37520} := \frac{4+6-9}{3+(75+2+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{318250} := \frac{4-6+9}{(31+8^2) \times 50}$
$\quad := \frac{4-6+9}{7 \times (0+3 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{53801} := \frac{4-6+9}{5-(3-801)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{325017} := \frac{4+6-9}{3 \times (2^5+01) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{17085} := \frac{4-6+9}{170+85}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{57218} := \frac{4+6-9}{(57 \times 2 \times 1)+8}$	

• Numerator 471

$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{628} := \frac{4+7+1}{6+2+8}$	$\quad := \frac{4 \times (7-1)}{(6-2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{3925} := \frac{4+7+1}{3+(92+5)}$
$\quad := \frac{47+1}{(6+2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{2983} := \frac{4+7+1}{2-(9-83)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{6280} := \frac{47+1}{(6+2) \times 80}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 1)}{(6 - 2) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{471}{68295} &:= \frac{47 + 1}{6 \times (8 \times (29 \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{471}{608532} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 1}{(60 + 8) \times 532} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{471}{682950} &:= \frac{47 + 1}{6 \times 8 \times 29 \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 472

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{472}{590} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 + 2)}{5 \times (9 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 72}{5 + 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{472}{10856} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 2)}{10 \times (8 \times 5 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{472}{53690} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 + 2)}{5 \times ((3^6) + 90)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{472}{95816} &:= \frac{4 + 7 \times 2}{9 \times (58 \times (1 + 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{472}{189036} := \frac{4 \times (7 - 2)}{1 \times 890 \times (3 + 6)}$$

● Numerator 473

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{516} &:= \frac{(4 + 7) \times 3}{(5 + 1) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{1290} &:= \frac{(4 + 7) \times 3}{1^2 \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{1892} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 3}{1 \times (8 \times (9 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 7 \times 3}{1 \times (8 + 92)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (7 + 3)}{(18 \times 9) - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{2150} &:= \frac{(4 + 7) \times 3}{(2 + 1) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{5160} &:= \frac{(4 + 7) \times 3}{(5 + 1) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{16985} &:= \frac{4 + 73}{(1 + (69 \times 8)) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{21586} &:= \frac{(4 + 7) \times 3}{(((2 + 1)^5) + 8) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{169850} &:= \frac{4 + 73}{(1 + 69 \times 8) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{473}{215860} &:= \frac{(4 + 7) \times 3}{((2 + 1)^5 + 8) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 476

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{952} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 6}{9 - 5 + 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{(9 - 5) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{9 + 5^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{1820} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{1 + (8^2 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{2380} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 6}{23 - (8 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{2 + 3 + 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 + 76}{(2 + 3) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{2958} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 6}{2 \times 9 \times 58} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{3108} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{3 + 108} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{3192} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{3 \times (19 \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{5180} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{5 + 180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{8092} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{(8 + 09)^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{8925} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{(8 + 9 - 2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{9520} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{(9 - 5) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{29580} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 6}{2 \times (9 \times 580)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{31892} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 6}{3 + (18 \times (9 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{(3 \times (1 + 89)) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{31920} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{3 \times (19 \times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{53928} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 + 6}{((53 + 9)^2) + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{139825} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{(1 + 39 \times (8 - 2)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{182903} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{1^8 + 2^9 \times 03} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{89250} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{(8 + 9 - 2) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{150892} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 6}{1 + 50 \times (8 + 9 + 2)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{102935} &:= \frac{4 \times (7 - 6)}{10 \times 29 \times 3 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{476}{158032} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 6}{(1 + 5) \times (80 + 3) \times 2} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 478

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{478}{956} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 8}{9 - 5 + 6} & & := \frac{4 \times (7 + 8)}{(1 + 2) \times (90 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{478}{69310} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 8}{6 + ((9^3) - 10)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{478}{2390} &:= \frac{4 + 7 - 8}{2 \times 3 + 9 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{478}{15296} &:= \frac{4 + 7 - 8}{1 \times ((5 + 2 + 9) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{478}{152960} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 + 8}{(1 + 5) \times 2 \times 960} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 8}{2 + (3 + 90)} & & := \frac{4 \times 7 + 8}{(1 + 5) \times (2 \times 96)} & & := \frac{4 + 7 - 8}{1 \times 5 \times 2 \times 96 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{478}{12906} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 8}{129 + 06} & & := \frac{47 - 8}{(15 - 2) \times 96} & & := \frac{47 - 8}{(15 - 2) \times 960} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 8}{1 + 2^{9+0 \times 6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{478}{30592} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 + 8}{(3 - (0 - (5 \times 9)))^2} & & \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times 7) - 8}{1^2 \times (90 \times 6)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 479

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{479}{10538} &:= \frac{4 + 7 - 9}{1 - (0 - (5 + 38))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{479}{153280} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 9}{(15 + 3^2) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{479}{350628} &:= \frac{4 + 7 - 9}{(3 + 5 \times 06^2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{479}{15328} &:= \frac{4 + 7 - 9}{1 + (53 + 2 + 8)} & & := \frac{4 \times (7 + 9)}{(1 + 5 \times 3)^2 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{479}{523068} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 9}{52 \times 30 \times (6 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 9}{(15 + 3^2) \times 8} & & := \frac{4 + 7 - 9}{(1^5 + 3) \times (2 \times 80)} & & \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (7 + 9)}{1 \times ((5 + 3) \times 2^8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{479}{208365} &:= \frac{4 - 7 + 9}{20 + (8^3 + 6) \times 5} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 480

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{675} &:= \frac{4 \times 80}{6 \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1395} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{1 - (3 - 95)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{137592} &:= \frac{4 \times 80}{13 \times (75 + 9)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{972} &:= \frac{4 \times 80}{9 \times 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{6915} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{6 + (91 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{192675} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{(19^2 + 6) \times 7 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1365} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{1 + (3 \times 6 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{19275} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{((1 + 9) \times 2^7) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{480}{219375} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{(2 + 193) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{291375} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{(2^{9-1} + 3) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{291765} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{2^{9-1} \times 76 - 5}$$

• Numerator 481

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{592} := \frac{4 + 8 + 1}{5 + 9 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{629} := \frac{4 + 8 + 1}{6 + 2 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{962} := \frac{4 \times (8 + 1)}{9 \times (6 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{48 - 1}{96 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{48 + 1}{96 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - 1)}{9 \times 6 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{2035} := \frac{4 + 8 + 1}{20 + 35}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{3256} := \frac{4 + 8 + 1}{32 + 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{27306} := \frac{4 + 8 + 1}{2 + (7 + (3^{06}))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{36075} := \frac{4 \times (8 + 1)}{36 \times (0 + 75)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{79365} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 1}{(7 \times 9 + 3) \times 6 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{97236} := \frac{4 + 8 + 1}{((9 \times (7^2)) - 3) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{235690} := \frac{48 \times 1}{(2 + 3^5) \times (6 + 90)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{793650} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 1}{(7 \times 9 + 3) \times 6 \times 50}$$

• Numerator 482

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{3615} := \frac{4 + 8 - 2}{3 \times ((6 - 1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 8 + 2}{3 \times ((6 + 1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - 2)}{36 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{17593} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 2}{(17^5) + (9^3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{36150} := \frac{4 + 8 - 2}{3 \times ((6 - 1) \times 50)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 8 + 2}{3 \times ((6 + 1) \times 50)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - 2)}{36 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{37596} := \frac{48 \times 2}{(3 + 75) \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{39765} := \frac{4 \times (8 - 2)}{(3 + 9 \times 7) \times 6 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{65793} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 2}{65 \times (7 \times (9 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + 2)}{65 \times (7 \times (9 + 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{90375} := \frac{4 \times (8 - 2)}{90 \times ((3 + 7) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{97605} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 2}{9 \times (760 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{375960} := \frac{4 + 8 + 2}{3^7 \times 5 - 9 - 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{48 \times 2}{(3 + 75) \times 960}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{397650} := \frac{4 \times (8 - 2)}{(3 + 9 \times 7) \times 6 \times 50}$$

• Numerator 483

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{483}{621} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 3}{6^2 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{483}{759} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 3}{7 \times 5 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{483}{2576} := \frac{(4 + 8) \times 3}{(25 + 7) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{483}{5796} := \frac{4 + 8 - 3}{5 + (7 + 96)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 8 + 3}{(5 + 7) \times (9 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{48 \times 3}{(5 + 7)^{9-6}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 8 - 3}{5 + (7^{9-6})}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times 3)}{(5 + 7) \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{483}{6210} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 3}{6^2 \times 10}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{483}{12075} &:= \frac{4+8-3}{(1+2+0) \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{483}{25760} &:= \frac{(4+8) \times 3}{(25+7) \times 60} & &:= \frac{4+8 \times 3}{2 \times (1+97) \times 65} \\ &:= \frac{4+8 \times 3}{1 \times (20 \times 7 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{483}{57960} &:= \frac{4+8 \times 3}{5 \times (7 \times (96+0))} & &:= \frac{4+8-3}{(2-1) \times 9 \times 7 \times 65} \\ &:= \frac{(4+8) \times 3}{12 \times (0+75)} & &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times 3)}{(5+7) \times 960} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{483}{16905} &:= \frac{4+8-3}{(1+6) \times (9 \times 05)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{483}{219765} &:= \frac{4 \times (8-3)}{2 \times (1+9) \times 7 \times 65} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 485

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{970} &:= \frac{4-8+5}{9-7+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{27160} &:= \frac{4-8+5}{2-7+1+60} & &:= \frac{4 \times 8 \times 5}{2^7 \times (9+3) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{2716} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 \times 5}{2^7 \times (1+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{27936} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 \times 5}{2^7 \times (9+3) \times 6} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{6790} &:= \frac{4 \times 8-5}{6 \times 7 \times 9+0} & &:= \frac{(4+8) \times 5}{2^7 \times (9+3 \times 6)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{26190} &:= \frac{4-8+5}{2+61-9+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{279360} &:= \frac{4-8+5}{2+7+9 \times (3+60)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 486

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{729} &:= \frac{48-6}{72-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{3159} &:= \frac{4-8+6}{3+(1^5+9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{13905} &:= \frac{4+8+6}{(13+90) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{48+6}{72+9} & &:= \frac{4+8-6}{3-((1-5) \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{15309} &:= \frac{4-8+6}{1+(53+09)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{792} &:= \frac{48+6}{7+9^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{7290} &:= \frac{48+6}{(7+2) \times 90} & &:= \frac{4+8-6}{((1+5) \times 30)+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{972} &:= \frac{4-8+6}{9-7+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{9720} &:= \frac{4-8+6}{(9-7) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{15930} &:= \frac{48+6}{1 \times (59 \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{4^{8-6}}{(9+7) \times 2} & &:= \frac{4^{8-6}}{(9+7) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{17253} &:= \frac{4-8+6}{1+(7 \times (2+5+3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{1350} &:= \frac{4+8+6}{1^3 \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{10395} &:= \frac{4+8+6}{(10 \times 39)-5} & &:= \frac{4+8-6}{(1+(7 \times 2 \times 5)) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{48+6}{1 \times 3 \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{10935} &:= \frac{4-8+6}{1-(0-(9+35))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{17352} &:= \frac{48+6}{(1+7) \times (3^5-2)} \\ &:= \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{(1+3) \times 50} & &:= \frac{4+8-6}{1 \times (0+(9 \times 3 \times 5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{19035} &:= \frac{4+8-6}{1-(9+(0-(3^5)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{1539} &:= \frac{4+8-6}{1+((5-3) \times 9)} & &:= \frac{48-6}{10+935} & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{23571} &:= \frac{4-8+6}{(2^3 \times (5+7))+1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{1593} &:= \frac{48+6}{1 \times (59 \times 3)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{27135} := \frac{4+8-6}{((2^{7-1})+3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{170235} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{((1+70)^2+3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{275319} := \frac{4-8+6}{(2+7) \times 5^3-1+9}$
$\quad := \frac{4+8+6}{((2+7+1)^3)+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{172530} := \frac{4+8-6}{(1+7 \times 2 \times 5) \times 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{352917} := \frac{4+8-6}{3^5 \times 2 \times 9-17}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{31752} := \frac{48-6}{((3-1) \times 7)^{5-2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{173259} := \frac{4-8+6}{(1+7 \times 3) \times 2^5+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{357210} := \frac{4-8+6}{(3+(5+7)^2) \times 10}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{35721} := \frac{4-8+6}{3+((5+7)^2 \times 1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{173502} := \frac{4-8+6}{(1 \times 7+350) \times 2}$	$\quad := \frac{4 \times (8-6)}{(35-7) \times 210}$
$\quad := \frac{4 \times (8-6)}{(35-7) \times 21}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{175203} := \frac{4-8+6}{1 \times 7 \times (5 \times 20+3)}$	$\quad := \frac{4^{8-6}}{(3+5) \times 7 \times 210}$
$\quad := \frac{4^{8-6}}{(3+5) \times (7 \times 21)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{179253} := \frac{4+8-6}{1+79 \times (25+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{357291} := \frac{4+8-6}{35 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9+1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{52731} := \frac{4+8-6}{(5-2) \times (7 \times 31)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{192375} := \frac{4+8+6}{(1 \times 92+3) \times 75}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{372519} := \frac{4-8+6}{3 \times 7 \times (2^{5+1}+9)}$
$\quad := \frac{4 \times 8+6}{(5+(2^7)) \times 31}$	$\quad := \frac{4+8-6}{1^9 \times 2375}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{397512} := \frac{48+6}{(3^9+7^{5-1}) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{53217} := \frac{4-8+6}{5-(3-217)}$	$\quad := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 9 \times 2375}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{527310} := \frac{4 \times 8+6}{(5+2^7) \times 310}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{90153} := \frac{4 \times 8-6}{(90+1) \times 53}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{192537} := \frac{4+8-6}{1+9 \times 2 \times (5^3+7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{592731} := \frac{4+8+6}{(5+9+2 \times 7)^3+1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{103275} := \frac{4-8+6}{10 \times 3 \times 2 \times 7+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{193752} := \frac{4+8-6}{(1 \times 9+37) \times 52}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{715392} := \frac{4 \times 8^6}{(7+1)^{5+3} \times 92}$
$\quad := \frac{4+8-6}{10^3+275}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{197235} := \frac{4+8-6}{((1+9) \times 7^2-3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{739125} := \frac{48+6}{73 \times 9 \times 125}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{125307} := \frac{4+8-6}{12+5 \times 307}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{231579} := \frac{4-8+6}{2^3+15 \times 7 \times 9}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{139725} := \frac{4 \times (8-6)}{1+(3 \times (9+7))^2-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{271350} := \frac{4+8-6}{(2^{7-1}+3) \times 50}$	

● Numerator 487

$\blacktriangleright \frac{487}{9253} := \frac{4-8+7}{(9+(2 \times 5)) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{487}{165093} := \frac{4 \times (8-7)}{1 \times 6+50 \times 9 \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{487}{92530} := \frac{4-8+7}{(9+(2 \times 5)) \times 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{487}{192365} := \frac{4-8+7}{(1 \times 9^2 \times 3-6) \times 5}$
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{487}{236195} := \frac{4-8+7}{2 \times (3^6+1^9)-5}$

● Numerator 489

$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{652} := \frac{4+8+9}{6 \times 5 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{20375} := \frac{4+8-9}{20+(3 \times 7 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{4-8+9}{5 \times ((7+2) \times 13)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{1630} := \frac{4+8-9}{1+6+3+0}$	$:= \frac{(4+8) \times 9}{20 \times (3 \times 75)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{125673} := \frac{4+8+9}{(1+256) \times 7 \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{3260} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times 9}{32 \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{52160} := \frac{4+8-9}{5 \times (1^6+0)}$	$:= \frac{4+8-9}{125 \times 6 + 7 \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{5216} := \frac{4+8-9}{5+(21+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{53627} := \frac{4+8-9}{5+(36 \times (2+7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{536270} := \frac{4+8+9}{(5+(3 \times 6)^2) \times 70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{6031} := \frac{4+8-9}{6-(0-31)}$	$:= \frac{4+8+9}{(5+((3 \times 6)^2)) \times 7}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{6357} := \frac{4-8+9}{63-5+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{57213} := \frac{4+8-9}{5+((7^2+1)+3)}$	
$:= \frac{4+8+9}{6^3+57}$		

● Numerator 490

$\blacktriangleright \frac{490}{3675} := \frac{4 \times 90}{36 \times 75}$

● Numerator 491

$\blacktriangleright \frac{491}{23568} := \frac{4 \times 9 + 1}{(2+35) \times 6 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{49-1}{3 \times (6 \times (8 \times 25))}$	$:= \frac{4+9 \times 1}{(2^3+5) \times 6 \times 80}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (9+1)}{2^3 \times (5 \times 6 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{49 \times 1}{((3^6)+8-2) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{491}{368250} := \frac{4+9+1}{3 \times (6+8^2) \times 50}$
$:= \frac{4+9-1}{2^3+568}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{491}{62357} := \frac{4+9 \times 1}{6+(235 \times 7)}$	$:= \frac{4+9-1}{3 \times 6 \times (8+2) \times 50}$
$:= \frac{4+9 \times 1}{(2^3+5) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{491}{208675} := \frac{4+9-1}{(20+8 \times 6) \times 75}$	$:= \frac{49 \times 1}{(3^6+8-2) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{491}{36825} := \frac{4+9-1}{3 \times (6 \times ((8+2) \times 5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{491}{235680} := \frac{4 \times 9 + 1}{(2+35) \times 6 \times 80}$	$:= \frac{49-1}{3 \times 6 \times 8 \times 250}$
$:= \frac{4+9+1}{3 \times ((6+8^2) \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (9+1)}{2^3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 80}$	

● Numerator 492

$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{615} := \frac{4 \times (9-2)}{(6+1) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{861} := \frac{4 \times (9-2)}{8 \times 6 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{3567} := \frac{4 \times (9-2)}{(35-6) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{6 \times 15}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{1763} := \frac{4+92}{1+(7^6-3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{6150} := \frac{4 \times (9-2)}{(6+1) \times 50}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{6 \times 150} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{492}{35670} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - 2)}{(35 - 6) \times 70} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{492}{73185} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - 2)}{(7^3 - 1) \times 85} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{492}{158670} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - 2)}{15 \times 86 \times 7 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 493

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{493}{86275} := \frac{4 + 9 - 3}{(8 \times 6 + 2) \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{493}{120785} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - 3)}{(1 + 20) \times 7 \times 8 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{49^3}{1^{20} \times 7^8 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 494

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{1280} := \frac{4 + 95}{1 \times (2^8 + 0)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{495}{23760} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - 5)}{2^3 + 760} &:= \frac{4 + 9 - 5}{((3 - 1)^6) \times (8 + 0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{1386} := \frac{(4 + 9) \times 5}{13 \times (8 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{26730} := \frac{4 + 9 - 5}{2 \times (6 + (7 \times 30))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{2673} := \frac{(4 + 9) \times 5}{2 + (6 + 7^3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{28160} := \frac{49 + 5}{(2^{8+1}) \times (6 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{31680} := \frac{4^{9 \times 5}}{(3 + 1)^{6 \times 8} + 0}$$

• Numerator 496

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{15872} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{1 + (5 \times 8 - (7 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 9 \times 6}{3^5 \times ((7 + 1)^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{158720} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{(15 + 8 - 7) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{18352} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{1 + (8 + (3 + 5^2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{53072} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{(5 \times (3 \times 07)) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{183520} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{18 + 352 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 9 - 6}{18 + (3^5 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{58032} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{5 + (80 + 32)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{357120} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{3 + 5 + 712 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{30752} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{3 - (0 - (7 + 52))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{85312} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{(85 \times (3 - 1)) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 9 - 6}{(35 + 7) \times 120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{35712} := \frac{4 - 9 + 6}{3 \times (5 + (7 + 12))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{87120} := \frac{49 - 5}{(87 + 1)^2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 9 - 6}{(35 + 7) \times 12}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{327680} := \frac{4 + 95}{(3 + 2 - 7 + 6)^8 + 0}$$

• Numerator 497

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{497}{568} := \frac{49 - 7}{56 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{49 + 7}{56 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{497}{23856} := \frac{4 - 9 + 7}{2 + (3 + (85 + 6))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 + 9 - 7}{(2^3 + (8 \times 5)) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (9 - 7)}{2 \times (3 \times (8 + 56))} \\ & := \frac{49 + 7}{2 \times (3 \times (8 \times 56))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (9 + 7)}{2^{3 \times (8-5)} \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{497}{36281} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 7}{3 + (62 + 81)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{497}{238560} & := \frac{4 \times (9 + 7)}{2^{3 \times (8-5)} \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{497}{238560} & := \frac{4 \times (9 - 7)}{2^{3+8-5} \times 60} \\ & := \frac{4 + 9 - 7}{(2^3 + 8 \times 5) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{49 + 7}{2 \times 3 \times 8 \times 560} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{497}{310625} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 7}{(3 - 1) \times 0625} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{497}{362810} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 7}{3^6 \times 2 - 8 + 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{497}{581632} & := \frac{(4 + 9) \times 7}{(5 + 8) \times 16^3 \times 2} \\ & := \frac{49 + 7}{(5 \times 8 \times 1 + 6^3)^2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 498

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{3652} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{3 - (6 - (5^2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{5312} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{5 + (3^{1+2})} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{6723} & := \frac{4 \times 98}{((6 \times 7)^2) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{23157} & := \frac{4 + 9 \times 8}{2 \times (31 \times 57)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{36105} & := \frac{4 \times (9 - 8)}{(-3 + 61) \times 05} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{37516} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{(3 \times 75) + 1^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{53120} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{(5 \times 3 + 1) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{61752} & := \frac{4 + 9 - 8}{617 + 5 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{65072} & := \frac{4 + 9 + 8}{(6 + 50) \times (7^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{67230} & := \frac{4 + 9 - 8}{672 + 3 + 0} \\ & := \frac{4 \times 98}{((6 \times 7)^2) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{73206} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{(7 \times 3)^{2+0 \times 6}} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times 9) - 8}{(7^3) \times (2 \times 06)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{106572} & := \frac{4 + 9 - 8}{1065 + 7 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{107236} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{(10 + 7) \times (2 + 36)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{123670} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{(123 \times 6) + 7 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{130725} & := \frac{(4 \times 9) - 8}{1 \times 30 \times 7^2 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{156372} & := \frac{4 \times (9 - 8)}{(1 + 5) \times (6^3 - 7) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{205176} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{(205 + 17) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{4 + 9 + 8}{(205 + 1) \times 7 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{231570} & := \frac{4 + 9 \times 8}{2 \times 31 \times 570} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{498}{310752} & := \frac{4 - 9 + 8}{(3 + 10) \times (7 + 5)^2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 501

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{2839} & := \frac{5 + 01}{28 - 3 + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{3674} & := \frac{5 + 01}{(3 \times 6 - 7) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{7682} & := \frac{5 + 01}{76 + 8 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{93687} & := \frac{5^{01}}{936 - 8 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{238476} & := \frac{5 + 01}{2 \times (38 - 4) \times 7 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{286739} & := \frac{5 + 01}{2 + 8 \times (6 \times 73 - 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{364728} & := \frac{5 + 01}{3 \times (6 - 4) \times 728} \\ & := \frac{5^{01}}{(3 + 6 - 4) \times 728} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{392784} & := \frac{5 + 01}{3 \times (9 - 2) \times (7 \times 8 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{5 - 01}{(3 + 9 + 2) \times 7 \times 8 \times 4} \\ & := \frac{50 - 1}{(3 + 9 - 2 \times (7 - 8))^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{501}{436872} & := \frac{5 + 01}{(4 - 3) \times 6 \times 872} \\ & := \frac{50 - 1}{(43 + 6) \times 872} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{501}{486972} := \frac{5 + 01}{(4 + 8 + 69) \times 72}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{501}{847692} := \frac{50 \times 1}{8 \times 47 \times (6 + 9)^2}$$

● Numerator 502

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{36897} := \frac{5 \times 01}{(3 + (6 \times (8 + 9))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 02}{91 \times (3 \times 6 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{184736} := \frac{5 + 0 \times 2}{184 \times (7 - 3 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{37148} := \frac{5 - 02}{37 \times (14 - 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{93874} := \frac{5 + 0 \times 2}{938 - 7 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 02}{1847 + 3^6}$$

$$:= \frac{50 - 2}{(3 + 71) \times 48}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{94376} := \frac{5 \times 01}{(9 - 4) \times 376}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 01}{(1 + 8 - 4) \times (7 + 3^6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{46937} := \frac{5 \times 01}{4 - (6 - 937)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{96384} := \frac{5 - 02}{(9 + 6 + 3) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5^{01}}{1 + 8^4 + 7 \times 3^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{79316} := \frac{5 + 0 \times 2}{79 \times (3 + 1 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 01}{96 \times (3 \times 8 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{196784} := \frac{5 - 02}{(1^9 + 6 + 7) \times 84}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{91364} := \frac{5 - 02}{91 \times (3 \times (6 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{50 - 2}{96 \times (3 \times 8 \times 4)}$$

● Numerator 503

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{503}{28671} := \frac{5 - 03}{2 + (8 \times (6 + 7 + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{50 \times 3}{(2^9 \times 17) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 03}{71 \times (4 + 26)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{503}{29174} := \frac{5 - 03}{(2 \times ((9 - 1) \times 7)) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{503}{71426} := \frac{5 + 0 \times 3}{71 \times (4^2 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{503}{479862} := \frac{5 + 03}{(4 + 79 \times 8) \times 6 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 0 \times 3}{2 + (9 \times ((1 + 7) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 03}{71 \times (4 + 2 \times 6)}$$

● Numerator 504

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{728} := \frac{5 + 04}{7 - 2 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{3192} := \frac{5 + 04}{3 \times (1 + 9 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{17892} := \frac{5 \times 04}{((1 + 7) \times 89) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{1372} := \frac{50 + 4}{1 \times (3 \times (7^2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{7896} := \frac{5 + 04}{((7 + 8) \times 9) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{29736} := \frac{5 - 04}{((2 + 9) \times 7) - (3 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{1792} := \frac{5 + 04}{1 \times ((7 + 9) \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{12376} := \frac{5 + 04}{1 - (2 - (37 \times 6))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{37296} := \frac{5 - 04}{3 + ((7 \times (2 + 9)) - 6)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{50 + 4}{37 \times (2 \times 9 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{39816} & := \frac{5 - 04}{39 - (8 \times (1 - 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{69832} & := \frac{5 + 04}{((6 + 9) \times 83) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{79128} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 4}{791 + 2 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{79632} & := \frac{5 - 04}{(7 + (9 + 63)) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 4}{796 - 3 \times 2} \\ & := \frac{5 + 04}{79 \times ((6 + 3) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{86912} & := \frac{5 + 04}{8 \times ((6 + 91) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{89712} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 4}{89 \times (7 + 1 + 2)} \\ & := \frac{50 + 4}{8 + ((97 + 1)^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{91728} & := \frac{5 \times 04}{91 \times ((7 - 2) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{92736} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 4}{92 \times (7 - 3 + 6)} \\ & := \frac{5 + 04}{927 + 3^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{504}{96831} & := \frac{50 \times 4}{9 + ((6 + 8)^{3+1})} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 506

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{782} & := \frac{5 + 06}{7 + 8 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{874} & := \frac{5 + 06}{8 + 7 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{1932} & := \frac{5 + 06}{1 + (9 + 32)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{2438} & := \frac{5 + 06}{2 + (43 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{12834} & := \frac{5 + 06}{1 \times (283 - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{13248} & := \frac{5 + 06}{1 \times (3 \times (2 \times 48))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{13294} & := \frac{5 + 06}{1 + (3 \times (2 + 94))} \\ & := \frac{50 - 6}{(1 + (32 \times 9)) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{13892} & := \frac{5 + 06}{13 + ((8 + 9)^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{13984} & := \frac{5 + 06}{(1 + (3 + 9 \times 8)) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{14398} & := \frac{5 + 06}{1^4 + (39 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{23184} & := \frac{5 + 06}{2 \times (3 \times (1 \times 84))} \\ & := \frac{50 - 6}{(23 + 1) \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{28934} & := \frac{50 - 6}{(2 + (8 \times 9)) \times 34} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{29348} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 6}{2 + ((9 - 3) \times 48)} \\ & := \frac{50 \times 6}{(2^9 \times 34) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{37812} & := \frac{5 + 06}{3 + (7 + 812)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{81972} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 6}{819 - (7 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{127834} & := \frac{5 + 06}{1 \times 2783 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{312984} & := \frac{5 + 06}{3 \times (1 + 2) \times 9 \times 84} \\ & := \frac{50 - 6}{3 \times 12 \times 9 \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{718934} & := \frac{5 + 06}{(7 + 1 + 8 + 9)^3 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{506}{784392} & := \frac{5 + 06}{7 \times 84 \times (3 \times 9 + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 507

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{8619} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 7}{86 - 1^9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{13689} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 7}{1 \times ((3 \times 6 \times 8) - 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{46982} & := \frac{5 + 07}{(4 + (69 \times 8)) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{82134} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 7}{(8 + 2 \times 1) \times (3^4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{5 + 07}{8 \times ((2 + 1) \times (3^4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{243698} & := \frac{5 + 07}{2 \times 4 \times (3^6 - 9) + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{168324} & := \frac{5 + 07}{1 \times 6 \times 83 \times 2 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{392418} & := \frac{5 + 07}{3 \times 9 \times (2 + 41) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{241839} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 7}{(241 + 8 \times 3) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 508

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{508}{1397} & := \frac{5 \times 08}{13 + 97} & \blacktriangleright \frac{508}{39624} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 8}{396 - 2 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{508}{214376} & := \frac{5 + 08}{2 \times (14^3 - 7 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{508}{14732} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 8}{(1 + (4 \times 7)) \times (3 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{508}{93472} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 8}{934 - (7 \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{508}{31496} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 8}{((3 + 1)^4) + (9 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{508}{179324} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 8}{1 + 7 \times 9 \times (32 - 4)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 509

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{509}{7126} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 9}{7 - (1 - (2^6))} & := \frac{5 + 09}{2 \times (7 \times (48 + 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{509}{216834} & := \frac{5 + 09}{21 \times (68 + 3) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{509}{18324} & := \frac{5 + 09}{(1 + 83) \times (2 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{509}{34612} & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 9}{34 \times ((6 - 1) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{5 + 0 \times 9}{18 \times (3 \times 2 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{509}{41738} & := \frac{5 \times 09}{(4 + 1) \times 738} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{509}{27486} & := \frac{5 \times 09}{27 \times (4 + 86)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{509}{123687} & := \frac{5 \times 09}{1^2 \times 3^6 \times (8 + 7)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 510

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{782} & := \frac{5 + 10}{7 + 8 \times 2} & := \frac{5 \times 10}{32 \times (6 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{3927} & := \frac{5 \times 10}{392 - 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{2346} & := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{2 - (3 - (4 \times 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{3468} & := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{((3 + 4) \times 6) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{3978} & := \frac{5 + 10}{39 + 78} \\ & := \frac{5 + 10}{23 + 46} & & := \frac{5 + 10}{34 + 68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{4386} & := \frac{5 + 10}{43 + 86} \\ & := \frac{5 \times 10}{23 \times (4 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{3672} & := \frac{5 + 10}{36 + 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{4692} & := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{4 + (6 \times (9 - 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{3264} & := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{(3 \times 2 \times 6) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{3876} & := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{38 \times (7 - 6)} & & := \frac{5 + 10}{46 + 92} \\ & := \frac{5 + 10}{3 \times ((2 + 6) \times 4)} & & := \frac{5 + 10}{38 + 76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{510}{4896} & := \frac{5 + 10}{48 + 96} \\ & & & & & := \frac{5 \times 10}{4 \times (8 \times (9 + 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{6732} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{67 - 3 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{34782} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{347 - 8 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{83742} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{837 - (4^2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{6834} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{68 + 3 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{39678} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{3 + ((9 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{279684} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{2 + 7^{9-6} \times 8 - 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{8976} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{89 - 7 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{43792} := \frac{5 + 10}{(4 + 3 + 7) \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{287436} := \frac{5 + 10}{2^8 \times (7 + 4) \times 3 + 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{9384} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{((9 + 3) \times 8) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{43962} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{439 - 6 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{328746} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{3 + (2 + 8) \times 7 \times 46}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{23698} := \frac{5 + 10}{2 - (3 - 698)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{47362} := \frac{5 + 10}{((4 + 7)^3) + 62}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{389674} := \frac{5 + 10}{3 + (8 + 9) \times 674}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{24837} := \frac{5 \times 10}{248 + (3^7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{62934} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{629 - (3 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{743682} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{7^4 \times 3 + 6 + 82}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{27438} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{274 + 3 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{67932} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{6 \times (79 + 32)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{942837} := \frac{5 \times 10}{(9^4 \times 2 + 83) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{29376} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{2 \times (9 \times (3 + 7 + 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{76398} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{7 \times (6 + (3 + 98))}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{29784} := \frac{5 \times 1 + 0}{(2 + (9 \times 7 + 8)) \times 4}$		

● Numerator 512

$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{640} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{6 + 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{4608} := \frac{5 \times (1 + 2)}{40 \times (9 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{47936} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{4 + (7 + (9 + 3^6))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{704} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{7 + 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{4608} := \frac{5 + 12}{40 + 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{73984} := \frac{5 - 1 - 2}{7 + (3 \times (98 - 4))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{768} := \frac{5 + 1^2}{7 - 6 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{4608} := \frac{5 - 1 - 2}{4 + (6 + 08)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{98304} := \frac{5 + 1^2}{9 \times (8 + (30 \times 4))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{960} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{9 + 6 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{4608} := \frac{5 + 1^2}{46 + 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{369408} := \frac{(5 + 1) \times 2}{3 \times (6 + 9 \times 40 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{3648} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{3 + (6 + 48)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{3648} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{4 + (60 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{389760} := \frac{(5 - 1)^2}{(38 - 9) \times 7 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{3648} := \frac{(5 - 1)^2}{3 \times (6 + 4 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{4736} := \frac{5 - 1^2}{4 \times 7 + 3 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{403968} := \frac{5^{1 \times 2}}{40 + 3^9 - 6 + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{3840} := \frac{5 - 1 - 2}{3 + (8 + 4 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{7680} := \frac{5 \times 1^2}{7 + (68 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{487936} := \frac{5 + 1^2}{(4 \times 8 \times 7 + 9^3) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{3968} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{3 - (9 - 68)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{30976} := \frac{5 - 1 - 2}{30 + (97 - 6)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{4096} := \frac{5 - 1 \times 2}{4 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{38976} := \frac{(5 - 1)^2}{(38 - 9) \times 7 \times 6}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{4096} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{4^{09-6}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{47360} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2}{4 + (7 + (3^6 + 0))}$	

● Numerator 513

$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{627} := \frac{5+1+3}{6-2+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{82764} := \frac{5+1-3}{(8+2 \times 7)^{6-4}}$	$:= \frac{5+1+3}{2 \times (7^4+9-6+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{684} := \frac{5+13}{6 \times (8-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{248976} := \frac{(5-1) \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 8 \times (97-6)}$	$:= \frac{5+1-3}{((27-4) \times 9-6) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{51-3}{68-4}$	$:= \frac{5+1^3}{(24+8) \times (97-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{278046} := \frac{5+1+3}{(2+7+804) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{51+3}{6 \times (8+4)}$	$:= \frac{5+1+3}{2 \times (4+8-9)^7-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{287964} := \frac{5+1^3}{(2+8 \times 7 \times (9+6)) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{2679} := \frac{5+1+3}{((2+6) \times 7)-9}$	$:= \frac{5+1-3}{(24-8) \times (97-6)}$	$:= \frac{5+1-3}{2 \times 8 \times 7 \times (9+6)+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{2907} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 3}{2+(90-7)}$	$:= \frac{5+13}{2 \times 48 \times (97-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{289674} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 3}{(2+8 \times 96) \times (7+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{2964} := \frac{5+1+3}{2+(9 \times 6-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{264708} := \frac{5+1-3}{(26-4) \times 70+8}$	$:= \frac{5+1^3}{28 \times (9 \times (6+7)+4)}$
$:= \frac{5+13}{(2 \times 9 \times 6)-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{270864} := \frac{5-1 \times 3}{2 \times 70 \times 8-64}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{402876} := \frac{5+1-3}{(40-2) \times (8 \times 7+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{6498} := \frac{(5-1) \times 3}{(6+4+9) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{5-1-3}{(2 \times 7+08) \times 6 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{462897} := \frac{5+1+3}{4^6 \times 2-8-9 \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{8094} := \frac{5+13}{(80-9) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{5+1^3}{(2+70) \times (8 \times 6-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{689472} := \frac{5+13}{6 \times 8 \times 9 \times 4 \times 7 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{9728} := \frac{(5+1)^3}{(9+7) \times 2^8}$	$:= \frac{51+3}{(2 \times 7+08) \times 6^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{894672} := \frac{5+13}{8 \times 9 \times (4+6 \times 72)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{27968} := \frac{51+3}{2^7 \times (9+6+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{274968} := \frac{(5+1)^3}{(2+7^4+9) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{972648} := \frac{5 \times 1^3}{(9+7^2 \times 6 \times 4) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{48906} := \frac{5+1^3}{4 \times 8+(90 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{5-1 \times 3}{2 \times (7+4 \times (9+6)) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{5+1^3}{(9 \times 7 \times 2+6^4) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{64980} := \frac{(5-1) \times 3}{(6+4+9) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{5-1-3}{(2+7+4+9 \times 6) \times 8}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{513}{72846} := \frac{5+1-3}{(7+(2 \times 8 \times 4)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{5+1^3}{(2+74-9) \times 6 \times 8}$	

● Numerator 514

$\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{32896} := \frac{(5-1)^4}{32 \times (8^9-6)}$	$:= \frac{5-1+4}{(3-2) \times (8^9-6)}$	$:= \frac{5-1+4}{(6-(2^7)) \times (-08)}$
$:= \frac{5-1 \times 4}{(3-(2+8-9))^6}$	$:= \frac{5 \times 14}{(3+2) \times 896}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{76329} := \frac{5+1-4}{(7-(6-32)) \times 9}$
$:= \frac{5-1^4}{3+((2^8)-9+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{62708} := \frac{5+1-4}{(6^2 \times (7+0))-8}$	$:= \frac{5+1^4}{(7 \times (63 \times 2))+9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{514}{230786} &:= \frac{5 - 1^4}{2 + (307 - 8) \times 6} &:= \frac{5 - 1^4}{2^9 + 7 \times 86 \times 3} &:= \frac{5 + 1^4}{32 \times 8 \times (9 + 6) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{514}{287069} &:= \frac{5 + 1 - 4}{2 \times (8 \times 70 - 6) + 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{307629} &:= \frac{5 + 1^4}{((3 + 07) \times 6)^2 - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{514}{297863} &:= \frac{(5 - 1) \times 4}{2 + 9 + (7 + 8 + 6)^3} &\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{328960} &:= \frac{5 - 1^4}{(3 + 2) \times 8^{9-6} + 0} \\ & & &:= \frac{5 \times 14}{(3 + 2) \times 8960} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 516

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{516}{2709} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 6}{2 + (70 - 9)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{9804} &:= \frac{(5 + 1) \times 6}{9 \times (80 - 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{207948} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{20 \times 79 + 4 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - 1) \times 6}{2 \times (7 \times 09)} & &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{(9 \times 8 + 0) + 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{234780} &:= \frac{(5 - 1) \times 6}{2 \times (3 + 4) \times 780} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{516}{3827} &:= \frac{(5 + 1) \times 6}{3 \times (82 + 7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{23478} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{2 + (3 \times (4 \times (7 + 8)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{247938} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{2 + 4 \times (7 \times 9 - 3) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{516}{3870} &:= \frac{5 + 1^6}{3 \times (8 + 7 + 0)} & &:= \frac{(5 - 1) \times 6}{2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 78)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{249830} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 6}{(2 - 4 + 9) \times 830} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 6}{3 + (87 + 0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{23908} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 6}{2 \times ((3 \times 90) + 8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{270384} &:= \frac{5 + 16}{(2^7 + 03) \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{516}{4730} &:= \frac{(5 + 1) \times 6}{(4 + 7) \times 30} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{24897} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{(2 \times (4 + 89)) + 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{294378} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{2^9 \times 4 + 3 \times 78} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{516}{4902} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{(4 \times (9 + 0)) + 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{24983} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 6}{(2 - 4 + 9) \times 83} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{390827} &:= \frac{(5 + 1) \times 6}{3 \times (9082 + 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{516}{7482} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{74 - (8 \times 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{39087} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{390 - 87} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{516}{9073} &:= \frac{(5 + 1) \times 6}{(90 \times 7) + 3} &\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{78432} &:= \frac{5 - 1^6}{(7 + 8 + 4) \times 32} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 517

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{517}{846} &:= \frac{51 - 7}{(8 + 4) \times 6} &:= \frac{(5 - 1) \times 7}{(20 - 6) \times 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{4982} &:= \frac{5 - 1 + 7}{((4 + 9) \times 8) + 2} \\ &:= \frac{5 - 1 + 7}{8 + 4 + 6} & &:= \frac{5 \times 1^7}{(2 \times 06) + 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{6204} &:= \frac{5 - 1^7}{6 \times (2 \times 04)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{517}{2068} &:= \frac{5 - 1^7}{2 - (0 - (6 + 8))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{3948} &:= \frac{5 - 1 + 7}{3 \times (9 \times 4 - 8)} & &:= \frac{5 \times (1 + 7)}{6 \times (20 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 17}{20 + 68} &\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{4230} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{(4 + 2) \times 30} & &:= \frac{5 + 1 \times 7}{6 \times (20 + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{6298} := \frac{5-1+7}{62+9 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{23406} := \frac{5-1+7}{(2+(3^4+0)) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{60489} := \frac{5-1+7}{(6^{-04+8})-9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{8460} := \frac{51-7}{(8+4) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{34968} := \frac{5-1+7}{3 \times (4 \times (9 \times 6 + 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{98324} := \frac{5-1+7}{(9+((8^3)+2)) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{9306} := \frac{5-1^7}{(9+3+0) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{40326} := \frac{5-1^7}{4 \times 03 \times 26}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{293468} := \frac{5-1+7}{2 \times (9 \times 346 + 8)}$
$:= \frac{5+1 \times 7}{9 \times (30-6)}$	$:= \frac{5 \times (1+7)}{40 \times 3 \times 26}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{386904} := \frac{5+17}{3 \times 8 \times (690-4)}$
$:= \frac{5+1+7}{(9+30) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{48269} := \frac{5-1+7}{((4 \times 8^2)-6+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{496320} := \frac{5+1^7}{4 \times (9+63) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{9823} := \frac{5-1^7}{9+(8^2+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{49632} := \frac{(5-1)^7}{(4^9) \times (6 \times (3-2))}$	
$:= \frac{5 \times 1^7}{(9 \times 8) + 23}$	$:= \frac{5-1^7}{4 \times (96 \times (3-2))}$	
	$:= \frac{5+1^7}{4 \times ((9+63) \times 2)}$	

• Numerator 518

$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{629} := \frac{5+1+8}{6+2+9}$	$:= \frac{5+1 \times 8}{((3 \times (7^2))+9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{94276} := \frac{5+1^8}{(9+4) \times (2 \times 7 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{4329} := \frac{5+1+8}{(4+3^2) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{5 \times (1+8)}{3 \times (72 \times (9+6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{97236} := \frac{5+1+8}{((9 \times (7^2))-3) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{6734} := \frac{5-1+8}{(6+7) \times (3 \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{5+1^8}{(3+7-2) \times 9 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{293706} := \frac{5-1^8}{2 \times 9 \times 3 \times 7 \times 06}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{9324} := \frac{5-1^8}{(9+3^2) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{5 \times 1^8}{3 \times ((7 \times (2 \times 9)) - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{293706} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 8}{2 \times 9 \times 3 \times 70 \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(5-1) \times 8}{((9+3)^2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{43290} := \frac{5+1+8}{(4+3^2) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{307692} := \frac{5-1^8}{(30 \times 7 + 6) \times (9+2)}$
$:= \frac{5-1+8}{9 \times (3 \times 2 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{67340} := \frac{5-1+8}{(6+7) \times (3 \times 40)}$	$:= \frac{5+1 \times 8}{30+7692}$
$:= \frac{5+1+8}{9 \times (32-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{92463} := \frac{5+1^8}{(9+2 \times 4) \times 63}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{309246} := \frac{5-1^8}{(30+92 \times 4) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{5 \times 1^8}{9 \times (3 \times 2 + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{93240} := \frac{5-1^8}{(9+3^2) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{370629} := \frac{5-1^8}{3 \times (70+6^2) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{27306} := \frac{5+1+8}{2+(7+(3^{06}))}$	$:= \frac{(5-1) \times 8}{((9+3)^2) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{372960} := \frac{5-1^8}{(3+(7-2) \times 9) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{37296} := \frac{5-1^8}{(3+((7-2) \times 9)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{5-1+8}{9 \times (3 \times (2 \times 40))}$	$:= \frac{5+1 \times 8}{(3 \times 7^2 + 9) \times 60}$
		$:= \frac{5+1^8}{(3+7-2) \times 9 \times 60}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{630924} := \frac{5 \times 1^8}{6 + (30 + 9)^2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{942760} := \frac{5 + 1^8}{(9 + 4) \times 2 \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{924630} := \frac{5 + 1^8}{(9 + 2 \times 4) \times 630}$$

● Numerator 519

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{2076} := \frac{5 + 19}{20 + 76}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 1^9}{(2 \times 07) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{8304} := \frac{5 + 1^9}{8 \times (3 \times 04)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - 1 + 9}{8 \times (30 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{38406} := \frac{5 + 1^9}{38 + 406}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{238740} := \frac{5 \times 19}{(2 + 3) \times 8740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{2768} := \frac{5 + 1^9}{2^{7+6-8}}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 1 + 9}{(2^7) - 6 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{51 + 9}{8 \times (30 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{23874} := \frac{5 + 1^9}{((2 + 38) \times 7) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 1^9}{(2 \times 38 - 7) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{3287} := \frac{5 + 1^9}{3 + (28 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{51 - 9}{3 + ((2^8) + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - 1 + 9}{2 \times 3 + (8 \times 74)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - 1^9}{(2 \times (3 + 87)) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{307248} := \frac{5 - 1^9}{(30 + 7) \times 2 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 1^9}{(30 + 7) \times 2 \times 48}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 1 + 9}{30 \times (72 \times 4 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{3460} := \frac{5 + 1^9}{34 + 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 19}{(2 + 3) \times 874}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{3806} := \frac{5 + 1^9}{38 + 06}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 1^9}{2 \times 3 + (8 \times 7 \times 4)}$$

● Numerator 520

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{936} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 0}{9 + 3 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 20}{9 + 36}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{1976} := \frac{5 + 20}{19 + 76}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{78936} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 0}{7 \times 8 \times 9 \times 3 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{1768} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 0}{1 \times (7 \times 6 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 20}{1 + (76 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{4836} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 0}{4 + (83 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{7384} := \frac{5 + 20}{7^3 + 8 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{61984} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 0}{(6 \times 198) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{481936} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 0}{4 + 8 \times 193 \times 6}$$

● Numerator 521

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{3647} := \frac{5 - 2 \times 1}{3 - (6 \times (4 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 - 1)}{(3 + 6 - 4) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 2 - 1}{3 \times ((6 - 4) \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 2 + 1}{3 + (6 + 47)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 1}{(3^{6-4}) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{52 - 1}{364 - 7}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{4689}$	$:= \frac{52+1}{364+7}$	$:= \frac{5 \times (2-1)}{9+(3+78)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{46890}$	$:= \frac{5-2-1}{(4+6-8) \times 90}$
	$:= \frac{5-2-1}{(4+6-8) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{5+2-1}{93+7+8}$		$:= \frac{5+2-1}{(4-6+8) \times 90}$
	$:= \frac{5-2 \times 1}{4+(6+8+9)}$	$:= \frac{5 \times 2-1}{9 \times (3+7+8)}$		$:= \frac{5+2+1}{(4+6) \times (8 \times (9+0))}$
	$:= \frac{5 \times (2-1)}{46+8-9}$	$:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 1}{(9+3) \times (7+8)}$		$:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 1}{4+(6+890)}$
	$:= \frac{5+2-1}{(4-6+8) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{52 \times 1}{(9+3) \times 78}$		$:= \frac{52 \times 1}{(4+6 \times 8) \times 90}$
	$:= \frac{5+2 \times 1}{4+(68-9)}$	$:= \frac{5+21}{(9-3) \times 78}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{64083}$	$:= \frac{5+2-1}{6 \times (40+83)}$
	$:= \frac{5 \times 2-1}{4+(68+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{34907}$		$:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 1}{6+(408 \times 3)}$
	$:= \frac{5 \times 2+1}{4+(6+89)}$	$:= \frac{5-2 \times 1}{3 \times (4-(9 \times (-07)))}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{93780}$
	$:= \frac{5 \times (2+1)}{46+89}$	$:= \frac{5 \times (2-1)}{3+(4 \times (90-7))}$		$:= \frac{5-2+1}{9 \times ((3+7) \times (8+0))}$
	$:= \frac{52-1}{468-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{36470}$		$:= \frac{52 \times 1}{(9+3) \times 780}$
	$:= \frac{52 \times 1}{(4+6 \times 8) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{5-2 \times 1}{3 \times ((6+4) \times (7+0))}$		$:= \frac{5+21}{(9-3) \times 780}$
	$:= \frac{52+1}{468+9}$	$:= \frac{5 \times (2-1)}{(3+6-4) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{430867}$	$:= \frac{5-2-1}{4+30 \times (8 \times 6+7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{9378}$	$:= \frac{5-2-1}{9 \times (3-7+8)}$	$:= \frac{5+2-1}{3 \times ((6-4) \times 70)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{468379}$	$:= \frac{5 \times (2-1)}{4-(6-8^3+7) \times 9}$
	$:= \frac{5-2 \times 1}{9+(3 \times (7+8))}$	$:= \frac{5 \times 2-1}{(3^{6-4}) \times 70}$		
		$\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{40638}$		
		$:= \frac{52+1}{(4^{06})+38}$		

● Numerator 523

$\blacktriangleright \frac{523}{1046}$	$:= \frac{5+2-3}{10+4-6}$	$:= \frac{52+3}{104+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{523}{140687}$	$:= \frac{5+2 \times 3}{1+(40-6) \times 87}$
	$:= \frac{5-2+3}{10-4+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{523}{19874}$		$:= \frac{(5-2) \times 3}{(1-8+40) \times 96}$
	$:= \frac{5+2+3}{10+4+6}$	$:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 3}{19 \times ((8+7) \times 4)}$		$:= \frac{5-2+3}{(18+4) \times 096}$
	$:= \frac{5+23}{10+46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{523}{97801}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{523}{198740}$
	$:= \frac{52-3}{104-6}$	$:= \frac{(5-2)^3}{9 \times ((7 \times 80)+1)}$		$:= \frac{5-2+3}{(1^9+8 \times 7) \times 40}$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 3}{19 \times (8 + 7) \times 40}$$

● Numerator 524

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{786} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 4}{7 + 8 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 4}{7 + 8 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{52 - 4}{78 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{52 + 4}{78 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{917} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4}{(9 + 1) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{52 - 4}{91 - 7} \\ &:= \frac{52 + 4}{91 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{7860} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 4}{(7 + 8) \times (6 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{9170} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4}{(9 + 1) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{38907} &:= \frac{5 \times 24}{3 + 8907} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{61308} &:= \frac{5 + 2 - 4}{(6 + 1)^3 + 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{79386} &:= \frac{(5 + 2) \times 4}{7 \times ((93 + 8) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{90783} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4}{90 \times (7 \times (8 + 3))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{173968} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 4}{(1 + 73 + 9) \times 6 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{179863} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 4}{1 \times 7 \times 98 \times 6 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{190736} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 4}{(1 + 90) \times (7 - 3) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{524}{793860} &:= \frac{(5 + 2) \times 4}{7 \times (93 + 8) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 526

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{789} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 6}{7 + 8 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 6}{7 + 8 + 9} \\ &:= \frac{52 - 6}{78 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{52 + 6}{78 + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{3419} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 6}{3 + 4 + 19} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 6}{(3 \times 4 + 1) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{7890} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 6}{(7 + 8) \times (9 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{9731} &:= \frac{5 \times (2 + 6)}{9 + 731} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{10783} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 6}{1 - (0 - (78 + 3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{34190} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 6}{(3 \times 4 + 1) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{97310} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 6}{9 + (731 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{130974} &:= \frac{5 + 2 - 6}{1 \times 3 \times (09 + 74)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{307184} &:= \frac{5 + 2 - 6}{3 + 07 \times (-1 + 84)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{391870} &:= \frac{5 + 2 - 6}{(3 + 91) \times 8 - 7 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{526}{407913} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 6}{(40 - 7) \times (91 + 3)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 527

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{1860} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^8 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{3069} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{30 + 69} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{3689} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 7}{3 \times (6 - 8 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5 + 2 + 7}{3 + (6 + 89)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{9486} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 7}{9 \times (4 + 8 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 7}{94 + 86} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 7}{(9 + 48) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 7}{9 \times (48 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (2 + 7)}{9 \times (4 + 86)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{34968} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{3 \times ((4 \times 96) - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{94860} &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 7}{(9 + 48) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{349680} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{(3 \times 49 - 6) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{527}{380649} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{3 \times (8^{0 \times 6 + 4} - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{527}{693408} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{6 \times (93 \times 40 + 8)}$$

• Numerator 528

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{704} &:= \frac{5 + (2 \times 8)}{7 \times 04} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{1364} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 8}{1 - (3 - 64)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{1430} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 8}{1 + (4^3 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{1496} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 8}{1 - (4 - (9 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 8}{14 + (9 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{1760} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 8}{1^7 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{1936} &:= \frac{5 + 2 + 8}{19 + 36} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 8}{1 + (93 - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{6930} &:= \frac{(5 + 2) \times 8}{6 + (9^3 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{7634} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 8}{(7^{6-3}) + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{13904} &:= \frac{5 + 2 + 8}{1 + (390 + 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{14976} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 8}{(((1 + 4) \times 9) + 7) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 28}{(149 + 7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{74096} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 8}{(7 \times (40 \times 9)) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{97416} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 8}{9 \times ((7 \times (4 + 1)) + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{134976} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 8}{(1^3 + 4 \times 9) \times 76} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{134 \times 9 \times 7 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{52 - 8}{(1 + 3 \times 49) \times 76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{149760} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 8}{((1 + 4) \times 9 + 7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 28}{(149 + 7) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{160974} &:= \frac{(5^2) \times 8}{1 + 60974} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{528}{317460} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times 8}{(3 + 1 + 7^4) \times 6 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 529

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{1748} &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 9}{17 \times 4 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{1863} &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 9}{18 + 63} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{3174} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 9}{3 + (1 \times 7 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 2 + 9}{3 \times ((1 + 7) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 29}{3 \times (17 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{4761} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 9}{47 + 61} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{3864} &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 9}{3 \times (8 + 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{6348} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 9}{(6 + 3 \times 4) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 9}{6^3 + 4 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + 2) \times 9}{63 \times (4 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{7406} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 9}{7 \times 4 \times 06} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 9}{7 \times (40 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{8073} &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 9}{8 + 07^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{31740} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 9}{3 + 17 + 40} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 2 + 9}{3 \times ((1 + 7) \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 29}{3 \times (17 \times 40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{38617} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 9}{38 + ((6 - 1) \times 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{38640} &:= \frac{5 + 2 \times 9}{3 \times ((8 + 6) \times 40)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{47081} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 9}{((4 + 7 + 0) \times 8) + 1} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 9}{(6 + 3 \times 4) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{47610} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 9}{4 + 76 + 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{103684} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 9}{1 + 03 + 6 \times 8 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{63480} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 - 9}{6 + 34 + 80} &:= \frac{5 - 2 + 9}{(10 + 3 \times 6) \times 84} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 530

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{530}{742} &:= \frac{5 + 30}{7 + 42} & \blacktriangleright \frac{530}{276819} &:= \frac{5 \times 30}{(2^7 \times 68 + 1) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{530}{18974} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 0)}{1 + (8 \times (9 \times 7 + 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{530}{279416} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 0)}{2 \times (7 \times 94 + 1) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{530}{79182} &:= \frac{5 + 30}{7 \times (9 \times (1 + 82))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 531

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{649} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 1}{6 - 4 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{28674} &:= \frac{5 - 3 - 1}{2 \times 8 + (6 \times 7 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{62894} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 1}{6 + (((2^8) + 9) \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{2478} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{(2 \times (4 + 7)) - 8} &:= \frac{5 - 3 \times 1}{2 \times (8 + (6 \times 7 + 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{64782} &:= \frac{5 - 3 - 1}{6 + (4 + (7 \times (8 \times 2)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{4602} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{(4 \times 6 + 0) + 2} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{2 - (8 - (6 \times 7 \times 4))} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{6 \times (4 - (7 - (8^2)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{4897} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 1}{4 + (8 \times 9 + 7)} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 - 1}{((2^8) - 67) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 - 1)}{(6^4) - (78 - 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{8496} &:= \frac{5 + 3 \times 1}{8 \times 4 + 96} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 1)}{2 \times ((8 \times 67) + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{68204} &:= \frac{5 + 31}{68^{2+0 \times 4}} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 3 - 1}{8 + (4 \times 9 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{46728} &:= \frac{5 - 3 - 1}{4 \times ((6 \times (7 - 2)) - 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{84960} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{8 \times (4 \times (9 + 6 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 3 \times 1}{8 \times ((4 \times 9) - 6)} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{(4 \times 6 + 7 + 2) \times 8} &:= \frac{5^{3-1}}{8^4 - (96 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{20768} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 1}{(2 - (0 - 7 \times 6)) \times 8} &:= \frac{5 + 3 \times 1}{(4 + (6 \times (7 \times 2))) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{86907} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{8 - (69 \times (-07))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{26078} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 1}{((2 + 60) \times 7) + 8} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 + 1}{4 \times ((6 \times 7 + 2) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{90624} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 1}{(90 + 6) \times 2^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{28497} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{(2 + (8 + 4 + 9)) \times 7} &:= \frac{53 \times 1}{4672 - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{204789} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 1}{(2 + 04 + 7) \times 89} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 1}{((2 + 8) \times 49) - 7} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 1)}{4 \times ((6 \times 72) + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{269748} &:= \frac{5 - 3 \times 1}{2^{6+9-7} \times 4 - 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{5-3-1}{2+6 \times (9+74)+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{427986} & := \frac{5-3 \times 1}{4+2 \times (798+6)} & := \frac{5 \times (3+1)}{4 \times (6+7^2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{5-3+1}{2 \times (6+9 \times 7 \times (4+8))} & & := \frac{5-3-1}{4-2+798+6} & := \frac{5+3 \times 1}{(4+6 \times 7 \times 2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{5+3 \times 1}{2^{6 \times (9-7)} - 4 \times 8} & & := \frac{5-3+1}{(4+27) \times (9 \times 8+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{680742} & := \frac{5 \times 3 \times 1}{6+8 \times (07^4+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{284970} & := \frac{5-3+1}{(2+8+4+9) \times 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{467280} & := \frac{5 \times 3+1}{4 \times (6 \times 7+2) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{726408} & := \frac{5+3 \times 1}{(72+6^4) \times 08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{286740} & := \frac{5 \times 3-1}{(2^8-67) \times 40} & & := \frac{5-3 \times 1}{4 \times (6 \times 72+8)+0} & & \\
 & := \frac{5-3 \times 1}{2 \times (8 \times 67+4)+0} & & := \frac{5-3+1}{(4 \times 6+7+2) \times 80} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 532

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{684} & := \frac{5+3^2}{6+8+4} & & := \frac{53+2}{106+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{147098} & := \frac{5-3+2}{14 \times (7+09 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{798} & := \frac{5-3+2}{7-9+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{1976} & := \frac{5+3^2}{1+(9+7 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{147896} & := \frac{5-3+2}{14 \times (7+8 \times 9)+6} \\
 & := \frac{(5+3) \times 2}{7+9+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{9614} & := \frac{5+3^2}{9+(61 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{148960} & := \frac{(5+3) \times 2}{(1+4) \times 896+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{1064} & := \frac{5-3+2}{10-6+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{14896} & := \frac{5 \times 32}{(1+4) \times 896} & & := \frac{5 \times 32}{(1+4) \times 8960} \\
 & := \frac{5^{3-2}}{1 \times (0+6+4)} & & := \frac{53-2}{14 \times ((8+9) \times 6)} & & := \frac{5+3-2}{14 \times 8 \times (9+6)+0} \\
 & := \frac{5+3-2}{10+6-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{16074} & := \frac{5+3^2}{((1+60) \times 7)-4} & & := \frac{53-2}{14 \times (8+9) \times 60} \\
 & := \frac{5+3+2}{10 \times (6-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{17689} & := \frac{5-3+2}{1 \times (7+((6+8) \times 9))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{169708} & := \frac{5+3^2}{(1+6) \times (9 \times 70+8)} \\
 & := \frac{5+3^2}{(1+06) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{19684} & := \frac{5^{3-2}}{1+((9 \times 6-8) \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{741608} & := \frac{5+3^2}{7 \times 41 \times (60+8)} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times 3+2}{10+6 \times 4} & & := \frac{5 \times 3-2}{1+((9+6) \times 8 \times 4)} & & \\
 & := \frac{5+32}{10+64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{532}{108794} & := \frac{5-3+2}{10+8 \times (7+94)} & & \\
 & := \frac{53-2}{106-4} & & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 534

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{712} := \frac{5-3+4}{7+1^2} \qquad := \frac{5+3+4}{(7+1) \times 2} \qquad \blacktriangleright \frac{534}{801} := \frac{5-3+4}{8+01}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{1068} := \frac{5+3-4}{(1^0) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{7120} := \frac{5+3+4}{(7+1) \times 20}$	$:= \frac{(5-3) \times 4}{(7-1) \times (2 \times 89)}$
$:= \frac{5-3+4}{10-6+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{7209} := \frac{5-3+4}{(7+2+0) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{72891} := \frac{5+3-4}{(7 \times 2-8) \times 91}$
$:= \frac{5+3+4}{10+6+8}$	$:= \frac{(5-3)^4}{7+209}$	$:= \frac{5-3+4}{728+91}$
$:= \frac{(5-3)^4}{(10-6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{7921} := \frac{5-3+4}{7+(9^2+1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{81702} := \frac{5+3-4}{(8+1) \times (70-2)}$
$:= \frac{53-4}{106-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{9612} := \frac{5+3-4}{9 \times (6+1 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{89712} := \frac{5-3+4}{8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 1 \times 2))}$
$:= \frac{53+4}{106+8}$	$:= \frac{5-3+4}{9 \times (6 \times 1 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{96120} := \frac{5-3+4}{9 \times (6 \times (1 \times 20))}$
$:= \frac{5+34}{10+68}$	$:= \frac{(5-3)^4}{96 \times (1+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{160289} := \frac{5-3+4}{(1+6) \times 02^8+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{1602} := \frac{5+3-4}{1 \times (6 \times 01)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{10769} := \frac{5-3+4}{(10 \times (7+6)) - 9}$	$:= \frac{5+3+4}{1+60^2-8+9}$
$:= \frac{5-3+4}{16+02}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{16287} := \frac{(5-3) \times 4}{1-(6-((2^8)-7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{271806} := \frac{5+3+4}{2+71 \times (80+6)}$
$:= \frac{5+3+4}{1 \times (6^{01})}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{71289} := \frac{5+3-4}{(7-1^2) \times 89}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{1869} := \frac{5-3+4}{18-6+9}$	$:= \frac{5-3+4}{(7+1 \times 2) \times 89}$	

• Numerator 536

$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{804} := \frac{5-3+6}{8+04}$	$:= \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{18 \times 09}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{17420} := \frac{5-3+6}{(17-4) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{1072} := \frac{5-3+6}{(1+07) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{2814} := \frac{5-3+6}{2+(8 \times (1+4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{18492} := \frac{5+3-6}{18+(49+2)}$
$:= \frac{(5-3) \times 6}{10+7 \times 2}$	$:= \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{(2^8 \times 1) - 4}$	$:= \frac{5-3+6}{184+92}$
$:= \frac{5+36}{10+72}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{2948} := \frac{(5-3) \times 6}{2 \times 9+48}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{21708} := \frac{5+3-6}{2+(1+(70+8))}$
$:= \frac{5 \times (3+6)}{10 \times (7+2)}$	$:= \frac{5+3+6}{29+48}$	$:= \frac{5-3+6}{2 \times (170-8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{1407} := \frac{5-3+6}{14+07}$	$:= \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{(29+4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{29078} := \frac{5-3+6}{2^9-078}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{1742} := \frac{5-3+6}{1 \times (7 \times 4-2)}$	$:= \frac{(5-3)^6}{(2+9) \times 4 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{29480} := \frac{5+3-6}{2+(9 \times (4+8+0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{1809} := \frac{5-3+6}{18+09}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{8241} := \frac{5-3+6}{82+41}$	

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{(29+4) \times 80} & := \frac{(5-3)^6}{(2^9 \times 7) - (4 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{536}{197248} := \frac{(5-3) \times 6}{(1-97) \times (2-48)} \\ & := \frac{(5-3)^6}{(2+9) \times (4 \times 80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{536}{81204} := \frac{5-3+6}{8+1204} & := \frac{5+3+6}{(1 \times 9 \times 72-4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{536}{29748} & := \frac{5+3-6}{2+(97+4+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{536}{170984} := \frac{5 \times 3-6}{1+70 \times (9+8 \times 4)} & := \frac{5+3-6}{(1 \times 9+7 \times 2) \times 4 \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(5-3) \times 6}{2+((9+74) \times 8)} & := \frac{5-3+6}{(1 \times 70 \times 9+8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{536}{428197} := \frac{5-3+6}{42 \times 8 \times 19+7} \\ & := \frac{5+3+6}{29+748} & \blacktriangleright \frac{536}{179024} := \frac{5+3-6}{(1-(7-90) \times 2) \times 4} & \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{536}{182709} := \frac{5-3+6}{18+2709} & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 537

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{2148} & := \frac{5+3-7}{(2+1) \times 4-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{6981} := \frac{5 \times 3-7}{6+(98 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{81624} := \frac{5+3-7}{8 \times (1-(6-24))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times 3-7}{2^{1-4+8}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{16289} := \frac{5-3+7}{(16^2)+8+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{91648} := \frac{5-3+7}{(9-1) \times (6 \times 4 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{5-3+7}{(2 \times 14)+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{21480} := \frac{5+3-7}{(2-1+4) \times (8+0)} & := \frac{5+3+7}{(9+1) \times (6-4)^8} \\ & := \frac{(5-3)^7}{2^{1+8}} & := \frac{5 \times 3-7}{(2-1) \times (4 \times 80)} & := \frac{(5-3) \times 7}{1 \times 4+9^2 \times 8 \times 6} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (3+7)}{(21+4) \times 8} & := \frac{5 \times (3+7)}{(21+4) \times 80} & := \frac{5-3+7}{(1+49)^2+8-6} \\ & := \frac{(5+3) \times 7}{2 \times (14 \times 8)} & := \frac{(5+3) \times 7}{2 \times (14 \times 80)} & := \frac{5+3-7}{(1 \times 4 \times 9-2) \times 8+6} \\ & := \frac{(5-3) \times 7}{(2+(1+4)) \times 8} & := \frac{(5-3) \times 7}{(2+(1+4)) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{189024} := \frac{5 \times 3-7}{1 \times 8 \times (90-2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{2864} & := \frac{5+3+7}{2 \times 8+64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{28461} := \frac{5+3-7}{(2 \times ((8 \times 4)-6))+1} & := \frac{5-3+7}{18 \times (90 \times 2-4)} \\ & := \frac{53+7}{(2^8)+64} & := \frac{5-3+7}{2 \times 8+461} & := \frac{5+3-7}{1 \times 8 \times (9+02) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{4296} & := \frac{5+3-7}{(4-2)^{9-6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{46182} := \frac{5+3-7}{((4+6+1) \times 8)-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{249168} := \frac{5+3+7}{(2^4 \times 9+1) \times 6 \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(5-3)^7}{4^{2+9-6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{69810} := \frac{5+3-7}{((6+9) \times 8)+10} & := \frac{5+3-7}{2 \times 4 \times (9+1+6 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{5+3+7}{4 \times (2 \times (9+6))} & := \frac{5 \times 3-7}{(6+98) \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{537}{842016} := \frac{5+3+7}{8 \times 420 \times (1+6)} \\ & := \frac{(5-3) \times 7}{4+(2 \times 9 \times 6)} & & \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 37}{(8^4 + 20) \times 16}$$

● Numerator 538

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{538}{1076} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 - 8}{1 - (0 - (7 + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 38}{10 + 76} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{538}{2690} := \frac{5 \times 3 - 8}{26 + 9 + 0}$$

● Numerator 539

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{539}{1078} &:= \frac{5 + 3 \times 9}{(1 + 07) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 39}{10 + 78} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{4018} := \frac{5 + 39}{(40 + 1) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{6174} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{6 \times (17 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{8624} := \frac{5 \times 3 - 9}{8 \times (6 + 2 + 4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{8 \times (6 + 2^4)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - 3) \times 9}{8 \times (6 \times (2 + 4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 3 + 9}{8 \times (6 \times 2 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 3) \times 9}{8 \times 6 \times 24}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{14602} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{((1 + 4) \times 60) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{16807} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{(1 + (6 \times (8 + 0))) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{17248} := \frac{(5 + 3)^9}{(1 + (7 + 2 \times 4))^8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 3 - 9}{(1 + (7 + 2^4)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3 + 9}{1 \times ((72 - 4) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 3 + 9}{(1 + 7) \times (2 \times 48)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3 \times 9}{(1 + 7) \times (2^4 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 39}{(172 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + 9}{(1 + 7) \times 248}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 3) \times 9}{1 \times (72 \times 4 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{27048} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{(2 \times (70 \times 4)) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{84672} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{8 \times (4 \times (6 \times (7 + 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{86240} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{(8 + 6^2) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 3 + 9}{8 \times (6 \times (2 \times 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 3) \times 9}{8 \times (6 \times 240)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{140728} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{1 \times 40 \times 72 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{172480} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 9}{(1 + 7) \times 2 \times 480}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 3 - 9}{(1 + 7 + 2^4) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 3) \times 9}{1 \times 72 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3 \times 9}{(1 + 7) \times 2^4 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3 + 9}{(1 \times 72 - 4) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 39}{(172 + 4) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + 9}{(1 + 7) \times 2480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{182476} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{(1 + 8 \times (2 + 4)) \times 76}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{201684} := \frac{5 - 3 + 9}{20 + (16 - 8)^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{240786} := \frac{5 + 39}{(2 + 40) \times 78 \times 6}$$

● Numerator 540

$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{837} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{8 \times 3 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{6912} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(6 + 9 + 1)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{89376} := \frac{5 + 40}{8 \times (937 - 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{972} := \frac{5 + 40}{9 + 72}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{7128} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{7 + (1 + (2^8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{89712} := \frac{5 + 40}{89 \times (7 \times 12)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{1296} := \frac{5 + 40}{1 \times (2 \times 9 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{7968} := \frac{5 + 40}{7 \times 96 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{98172} := \frac{5 + 40}{9 + 8172}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{1728} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(1 - 2 + 9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{12768} := \frac{5 + 40}{(127 + 6) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{168792} := \frac{5 + 40}{16 \times 879 + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{1728} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{1 \times (72 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{13689} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{13 \times (6 \times 8 - 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{169872} := \frac{5 + 40}{1 - 6 + ((9 + 8) \times 7)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{1782} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{((1 + 7) \times 8) + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{18792} := \frac{5 + 40}{1 \times (87 \times 9 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{183792} := \frac{5 + 40}{(1^8 + 3^7) \times (9 - 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{2196} := \frac{5 + 40}{(21 \times 9) - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{18927} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{1 + ((8 + 92) \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{196728} := \frac{5 + 40}{(1 + 9 - 6)^7 + 2 + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{2673} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{26 + 73}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{19683} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{((1^{96}) + 8)^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{283176} := \frac{5 \times 40}{2 \times 8 \times (3^{1+7} - 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{2916} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{2 \times (9 \times 1 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{26973} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{26 + 973}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{813726} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{81 \times 372 + 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{3726} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(3 \times 7 + 2) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{27189} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(((2^7) - 1) \times 8) - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{862137} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(862 + 1) \times 37}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{3861} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(3 \times 8 \times 6) - 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{27891} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(2^7 \times 8) + 9 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{918372} := \frac{5 + 40}{91 \times (8 + 3 \times 7)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{6237} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(6^2 - 3) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{32967} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{3 + (29 \times (6 \times 7))}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{6318} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{6 \times (31 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{73926} := \frac{5 \times (4 + 0)}{(7 \times 392) - 6}$	

● Numerator 541

$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{9738} := \frac{5 - 4 \times 1}{9 \times (7 + 3 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{63297} := \frac{5 - 4 \times 1}{(6 \times 3^2) + 9 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{209367} := \frac{5 - 4 + 1}{2 \times 09 \times (36 + 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{9738} := \frac{5 + 4 \times 1}{9 \times (7 + 3 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{63297} := \frac{5 - (4 - 1)}{6 \times (3 + (29 + 7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{209367} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 1}{20 \times 9 \times (36 + 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{9738} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 1}{9 + (7^3 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{63297} := \frac{5 + 4 + 1}{6 \times (3 \times (2 + 9 \times 7))}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{28673} := \frac{5 - (4 - 1)}{2 \times (8 + (6 \times 7 + 3))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{97380} := \frac{5 - 4 \times 1}{97 + 3 + 80}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{97380} := \frac{5 - (4 - 1)}{9 + (7^3 + 8 + 0)}$	

● Numerator 542

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{813} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(8+1) \times 3} &:= \frac{54+2}{189+7} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 2}{31+(9+78)} \\
 &:= \frac{54-2}{81-3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{8130} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(8+1) \times 30} &:= \frac{5 \times (4-2)}{((3-1)^9)+78} \\
 &:= \frac{54+2}{81+3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{18970} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 2}{1+(8-(9-70))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{70189} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 2}{70+189} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{1897} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 2}{1+(8-9+7)} &:= \frac{5-4+2}{1 \times (8+(97+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{197830} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 2}{1+9 \times (78+3)+0} \\
 &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(18-9) \times 7} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(1+89) \times (7+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{319780} &:= \frac{(5-4)^2}{3 \times (1+9)+7 \times 80} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times (4+2)}{1 \times (8+97)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{19783} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 2}{1-(9-(78+3))} \\
 &:= \frac{54-2}{189-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{542}{31978} &:= \frac{(5-4)^2}{(3 \times (1+9+7))+8}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 543

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{1086} &:= \frac{(5-4)^3}{1 \times (0+8-6)} &:= \frac{54-3}{126-7} &:= \frac{54 \times 3}{2 \times (8 \times 9 \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{(10^8) \times 6} &:= \frac{54+3}{126+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{7602} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{7 \times (6+0 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{5-4+3}{10-8+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{1629} &:= \frac{(5-4)^3}{1 \times (6 \times 2-9)} &:= \frac{5-4+3}{7 \times (6+02)} \\
 &:= \frac{5+4-3}{10+8-6} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{(16^2) \times 9} &:= \frac{5+4-3}{7 \times (6 \times 01)} \\
 &:= \frac{5+4+3}{10+8+6} &:= \frac{5-4+3}{16+2+9} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 \times 3}{7 \times (60 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+08) \times 6} &:= \frac{5+4-3}{1+(6+2+9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{10679} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{1-(0-(67-9))} \\
 &:= \frac{5+43}{10+86} &:= \frac{5+4+3}{1+(6+29)} &:= \frac{5+4-3}{1-(0-((6+7) \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{54-3}{108-6} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+6+2) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{12670} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{1+(2+(67+0))} \\
 &:= \frac{54+3}{108+6} &:= \frac{54-3}{162-9} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+2+6) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{1267} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{(12^6) \times 7} &:= \frac{54+3}{162+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{16290} &:= \frac{(5-4)^3}{16+(29+0)} \\
 &:= \frac{5+4-3}{1^2+6+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{2896} &:= \frac{5+4-3}{2^{8-9+6}} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{(16^2) \times 90} \\
 &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+2+6) \times 7} &:= \frac{5+4+3}{2+(8+(9 \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{5+4-3}{1^6 \times (2 \times 90)} \\
 & := \frac{5+4+3}{1 \times ((6-2) \times 90)} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+6+2) \times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{28960} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{(2^8) - (96+0)} \\
 & := \frac{54 \times 3}{2 \times (8 \times (9 \times 60))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{61902} & := \frac{(5-4)^3}{6 \times (1 - (9 \times (-02)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{78192} & := \frac{(5-4)^3}{(7 \times (8+1)) + 9^2} \\
 & := \frac{5-4+3}{(7+(8+(1 \times 9)))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{79821} & := \frac{(5-4)^3}{7 \times ((9-8) \times 21)} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{7 \times (9 \times (8-2+1))} \\
 & := \frac{5+4 \times 3}{7 \times ((9+8) \times 21)} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{7 \times (9 \times (8^2-1))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{160728} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{160+728} \\
 & := \frac{5-4)^3}{((1+6^{0 \times 7+2}) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{180276} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 3}{(180-2 \times 7) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4)^3}{180+2 \times 76} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{186792} & := \frac{(5-4)^3}{1+8 \times 6 \times 7+9-2} \\
 & := \frac{5-4+3}{(1+8+679) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{269871} & := \frac{(5-4)^3}{(2+6-9+8) \times 71} \\
 & := \frac{5-4+3}{2 \times (6+987+1)} \\
 & := \frac{5+4+3}{(2 \times 6+9 \times 8) \times 71} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{278016} & := \frac{(5-4)^3}{2^{7+8-01 \times 6}} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times 4^3}{2^7 \times 80 \times 16} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times (4+3)}{2 \times 7 \times 80 \times 16} \\
 & := \frac{5+4+3}{2^7 \times 8 \times 01 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{5+4-3}{2^7 \times (8+016)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{691782} & := \frac{5+43}{6 \times 91 \times 7 \times 8 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{543}{798210} & := \frac{5+4 \times 3}{7 \times (9+8) \times 210}
 \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 546

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{702} & := \frac{5-4+6}{7+02} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{819} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{8+1^9} \\
 & := \frac{54-6}{8 \times (1 \times 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(8+1) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{54+6}{81+9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{910} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{9+1+0} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{9 \times 10} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{728} & := \frac{54-6}{72-8} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(7+2) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{54+6}{72+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1092} & := \frac{(5-4)^6}{(10^9) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{1-(0-(9+2))} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times 4-6}{10+9 \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{5+46}{10+92} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times (4+6)}{(1+09)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1302} & := \frac{5 \times 4+6}{(1+30) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1729} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{1+(7+2+9)} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(17+2) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1820} & := \frac{5+4-6}{1 \times (8+2+0)} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{18+2+0} \\
 & := \frac{54-6}{1 \times (8 \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(1+8) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1890} & := \frac{5 \times 4+6}{1+89+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1932} & := \frac{5 \times 4+6}{1+(93-2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{2079} & := \frac{5 \times 4+6}{20+79} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{2301} & := \frac{5 \times 4-6}{(2 \times 30)-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{2730} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{27+3+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{5+4+6}{2+(73+0)} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(2+7) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{3120} & := \frac{5-4+6}{(3-1) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times 4 - 6}{(3+1) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{7189} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{7+1 \times 8 \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(71+8) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{7280} & := \frac{5+4-6}{(7-2) \times (8+0)} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{72+8+0} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(7+2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{8190} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{81+9+0} \\
 & := \frac{54-6}{8 \times (1 \times 90)} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(8+1) \times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{8372} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{83+7+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{10283} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{102+8+3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{10738} & := \frac{5+4-6}{((10+7) \times 3) + 8} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{107+3+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{10829} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{108+2+9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{13728} & := \frac{5-4+6}{(1+3+7) \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times 4 - 6}{(1+(3 \times 7)) \times 2 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{17238} & := \frac{5-4+6}{17 \times (2+3+8)} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times 4 - 6}{17 \times (2+3 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{17290} & := \frac{5+4-6}{1 \times (7-(2-90))} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(17+2) \times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{20839} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{(2^{08}) - (3 \times 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{28301} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{2+(8+301)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{37128} & := \frac{(5-4)^6}{3+(71+2-8)} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{(3-71) \times (2-8)} \\
 & := \frac{5-4+6}{((3 \times 7+1)^2) - 8} \\
 & := \frac{5+4+6}{(3-7) \times (1-(2^8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{71890} & := \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(71+8) \times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{72891} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{(7+2) \times (89 \times 1)} \\
 & := \frac{54-6}{72 \times (89 \times 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{72930} & := \frac{5-4+6}{7-(2-930)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{73801} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{7+(3+801)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{73892} & := \frac{5+4-6}{7 \times ((38-9) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{7 \times (3 \times 8+92)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{91728} & := \frac{(5-4)^6}{(9-(1-7) \times 2) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{5+4-6}{9 \times (1+7)^2 - 8} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times 4 - 6}{(91-7) \times 28} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{108927} & := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{10+(8 \times 9)^2 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{137280} & := \frac{5 \times 4 - 6}{(1+3 \times 7) \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{5-4+6}{(1+3+7) \times 2 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{137802} & := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+3+78)^{02}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{137928} & := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(13 \times 7 \times 9 + 2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{173082} & := \frac{(5-4)^6}{1 \times 7 + 308 + 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{179283} & := \frac{5 \times 4 - 6}{1 \times 7 - 9 \times (2-8^3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{183092} & := \frac{5+4-6}{(1 \times 8^3 - 09) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{192738} & := \frac{(5-4)^6}{1+(9+2) \times (7-3) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{271908} & := \frac{(5-4)^6}{2+(71-9) \times 08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{290381} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{290 \times (3+8) + 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{372918} & := \frac{(5-4) \times 6}{3+7+(2^9-1) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{(5-4)^6}{(3+72) \times 9 \times 1+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{381290} & := \frac{5+4-6}{3^{8-1} - 2 - 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{546}{918372} & := \frac{5 \times (4+6)}{(9+1) \times (8+3 \times 7)^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 547

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{547}{3829} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 7}{38+2+9} \\ &:= \frac{5-4+7}{38+2 \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 4-7}{3+(8 \times (2+9))} \\ &:= \frac{5+4+7}{((3+8)^2)-9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{547}{26803} &:= \frac{5 \times 4-7}{((2+6) \times 80)-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{547}{36102} &:= \frac{(5-4)^7}{3+(61+02)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{547}{83691} &:= \frac{(5-4)^7}{(8+3+6) \times 9 \times 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{547}{102836} &:= \frac{(5-4)^7}{10+2 \times (83+6)} \\ &:= \frac{5+4 \times 7}{(10+2 \times 8^3) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{547}{396028} &:= \frac{5+4-7}{(3+9) \times 60 \times 2+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{547}{398216} &:= \frac{5+4-7}{(3 \times 9+8^2) \times 16} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 548

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{1096} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 8}{1-(0-(9+6))} \\ &:= \frac{5+48}{10+96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{1370} &:= \frac{5 \times 4+8}{1^3 \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 8}{13+7+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{9316} &:= \frac{5+4-8}{9+(3-1+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{23016} &:= \frac{5+4-8}{2 \times (3 \times (0+1+6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{30962} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 8}{(30 \times (9+6))+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{130972} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 8}{1+(30+9) \times 7^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{196732} &:= \frac{5+4-8}{19^{6-7+3}-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{379216} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 8}{3+7+921 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{5-4+8}{3+79^2-16} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{601293} &:= \frac{5 \times 4+8}{60 \times 1 \times 2^9+3} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 549

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{610} &:= \frac{5+49}{6 \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{671} &:= \frac{5+49}{67-1} \\ &:= \frac{54+9}{6+71} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{732} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{7+3+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{1708} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{1 \times (7 \times 08)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 4 \times 9}{1 \times (70 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{1830} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{1^8 \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{2013} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{20+13} \\ &:= \frac{5+49}{201-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{3172} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{3+(1 \times (7^2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{12078} &:= \frac{(5-4)^9}{1 \times ((2 \times 07)+8)} \\ &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{120+78} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{16287} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{1 \times (6 \times (2+87))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{23607} &:= \frac{(5-4)^9}{(2 \times (3 \times (6+0))) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 4-9}{(2^3 \times 60)-7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{27816} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{(2-(7-81)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{62830} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{6+(2 \times (8^3+0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{68137} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{6 \times 8-(1-(3^7))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{76128} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{(7+6) \times (12 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{127368} &:= \frac{(5-4)^9}{(1 \times 2+7 \times 3+6) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{127368} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{(12 \times 7 + 3) \times 6 \times 8} & := \frac{54 \times 9}{2 \times 3^7 \times 1 \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{367281} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 - 9}{(3^6 + 7) \times (2 + 8) - 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{172386} &:= \frac{(5-4)^9}{(17+23) \times 8 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{261873} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 9}{261 \times (8 \times 7 - 3)} & & := \frac{(5-4)^9}{3 + 6 \times (7 \times 2 \times 8 - 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{237168} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 - 9}{(2 + 37 \times 16) \times 8} & & := \frac{(5-4)^9}{2^{6-1} \times (8+7) - 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{378261} &:= \frac{(5-4)^9}{(3+7 \times 8 \times 2) \times 6 - 1} \\
 & := \frac{(5+4) \times 9}{2 \times 3^7 \times 1^6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{278160} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 9}{(2-7+81) \times 60} & & \\
 & := \frac{(5-4)^9}{(2+3+7 \times (1+6)) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{549}{281637} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 - 9}{(28-1) \times (6^3 - 7)} & & \\
 & := \frac{5+4+9}{(23 \times 7 + 1) \times 6 \times 8} & & := \frac{(5-4)^9}{2+8 \times 1 \times 63 + 7} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 560

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{560}{784} &:= \frac{5+60}{7+84} & \blacktriangleright \frac{560}{972384} &:= \frac{5 \times 6 + 0}{9 \times (723 \times 8 + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{560}{79184} &:= \frac{5+60}{7+9184} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 561

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{748} &:= \frac{5+61}{(7+4) \times 8} & := \frac{5 \times 6 - 1}{(3 \times 9 + 2) \times 7} & := \frac{5 \times 6 - 1}{(3 \times 9 + 2) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{2397} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{(2 \times 3 \times 9) - 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{7480} &:= \frac{5+61}{(7+4) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{40392} &:= \frac{5 \times 6 \times 1}{40 \times (3 \times 9 \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{3927} &:= \frac{5+6-1}{(3+9-2) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{24837} &:= \frac{56-1}{248+(3^7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{47328} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{4 \times ((7 \times 32) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{5+6 \times 1}{3+(9^2-7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{27489} &:= \frac{56 \times 1}{(2 \times 7)^{4+8-9}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{208743} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{(2 \times 08)^{7-4} - 3} \\
 & := \frac{5+6+1}{3+(9 \times (2+7))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{30294} &:= \frac{5+61}{(30^2-9) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{243780} &:= \frac{5+61}{2^{4 \times 3} \times 7 + 8 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times (6-1)}{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{39270} &:= \frac{5+6-1}{(3+9-2) \times 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{561}{274890} &:= \frac{5+6-1}{2 \times 7^4 + 8 + 90} \\
 & := \frac{56-1}{392-7} & & := \frac{5 \times (6-1)}{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 70} & & \\
 & := \frac{56+1}{392+7} & & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 562

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{843} &:= \frac{56-2}{84-3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{17984} &:= \frac{5-6+2}{(1+7 \times (9-8)) \times 4} & & := \frac{5+6+2}{1+7 \times 9+8^4+0} \\ &:= \frac{56+2}{84+3} & & := \frac{5+6-2}{1+7 \times (9+8 \times 4)} & & := \frac{5+6-2}{(1+79-8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{3091} &:= \frac{(5+6) \times 2}{30+91} & & := \frac{5+6 \times 2}{(1+7+9) \times 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{193047} &:= \frac{5 \times (6-2)}{19^3+04+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{8430} &:= \frac{5-6+2}{8+4+3+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{179840} &:= \frac{5-6+2}{(1+7 \times (9-8)) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{301794} &:= \frac{5 \times (6+2)}{30 \times 179 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{10397} &:= \frac{(5+6) \times 2}{10+397} & & := \frac{5+6 \times 2}{(1+7+9) \times 8 \times 40} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{562}{14893} &:= \frac{5 \times 6-2}{1+4+8+9^3} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 564

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{564}{987} &:= \frac{56-4}{98-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{564}{72380} &:= \frac{5-6+4}{7-2+380} \\ &:= \frac{56+4}{98+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{564}{170892} &:= \frac{5-6+4}{17+0892} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{564}{3807} &:= \frac{5 \times 6 \times 4}{3+807} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 567

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{891} &:= \frac{56+7}{8+91} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{23814} &:= \frac{5+6-7}{2 \times (3 \times ((8-1) \times 4))} & & := \frac{5+67}{103 \times 8 \times 2^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{2394} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{2^3 \times 9+4} & & := \frac{5-6+7}{238+14} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{104328} &:= \frac{5-6+7}{(10+4 \times 32) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{3024} &:= \frac{5-6+7}{30-2+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{24381} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{2 \times (43 \times (8+1))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{104832} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{1 \times 04 \times 832} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{3240} &:= \frac{56+7}{3^2 \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{30429} &:= \frac{5-6+7}{304+2 \times 9} & & := \frac{56+7}{(10+4) \times 832} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{3402} &:= \frac{5+6-7}{3 \times 4 \times 01} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{31248} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{31 \times (24+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{123984} &:= \frac{5-6+7}{(1 \times 2+39) \times 8 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{5-6+7}{34+02} & & := \frac{5+67}{31 \times (2^4 \times 8)} & & := \frac{5+6+7}{(1^2+3) \times 984} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{3429} &:= \frac{56+7}{3+(42 \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{41328} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{4 \times (1 \times 328)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{129438} &:= \frac{(5+6) \times 7}{1 \times 2+(9+4)^3 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{4032} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{4 \times (0+32)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{43092} &:= \frac{5+6-7}{((4+30) \times 9)-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{129843} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{1 \times 29+8^4-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{23184} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{23 \times (1 \times 8 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{103824} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{(1+03) \times 824} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{139482} &:= \frac{5-6+7}{(13+9-4) \times 82} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{148329} &:= \frac{56+7}{1+4 \times 8 \times (3+2^9)} & := \frac{5+6-7}{2 \times 3 \times (8-1) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{314928} &:= \frac{56+7}{3^{1+4} \times 9 \times 2 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{183204} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{18^3 - 2^{04}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{241983} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{2-(4-19) \times 8^3} & & := \frac{56-7}{3 \times 14 \times 9^2 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{184239} &:= \frac{56+7}{1 \times 8^4 \times (2+3) - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{284391} &:= \frac{56 \times 7}{(2 \times 8)^4 \times 3 + 9 - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{321489} &:= \frac{56-7}{3 \times 21^{4+8-9}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{184320} &:= \frac{56+7}{1 \times 8^4 \times (3+2) + 0} & & := \frac{56-7}{2+8^4 \times (-3+9) + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{381024} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{((3+8) \times 10)^2 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{213948} &:= \frac{5-6+7}{(2-1+3 \times 94) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{291438} &:= \frac{5+6-7}{(2^{9-1} + 4 - 3) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{413280} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{4 \times 1 \times 3280} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{214893} &:= \frac{5+6-7}{2 \times (14+8 \times 93)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{312480} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{(3+1) \times 2480} & \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{419328} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{4 \times (1+9+3) \times 2^8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{231840} &:= \frac{5+6+7}{23 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} & & := \frac{5+67}{31 \times 2^4 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{567}{238140} &:= \frac{5-6+7}{(2^3 \times 8 - 1) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 568

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{568}{923} &:= \frac{56-8}{9^2-3} & & := \frac{5 \times 6 - 8}{1 \times (70-4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{568}{1704} &:= \frac{5-6+8}{17+04} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 569

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{569}{13087} := \frac{5+6-9}{1-(3 \times (0-(8+7)))} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{569}{83074} := \frac{5+6-9}{(8 \times (30+7)) - 4}$$

● Numerator 570

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{570}{684} &:= \frac{5+70}{6+84} & \blacktriangleright \frac{570}{134862} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 + 0}{(1+(3+4+8) \times 6)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{570}{8436} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 + 0}{8 \times 4^3 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{570}{213864} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 + 0}{2 \times (1+3^8 + 6) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{570}{9234} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 + 0}{9^2 \times (3+4)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 571

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{571}{3426} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 - 1}{3 \times (4 + 2^6)} &:= \frac{57 - 1}{342 - 6} &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 1}{(3 + (4 \times 2)) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 7 + 1}{(34 + 2) \times 6} &:= \frac{57 + 1}{342 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 1}{3 \times (4^2 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{571}{34260} := \frac{5 \times 7 + 1}{(34 + 2) \times 60}$$

● Numerator 572

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{1430} &:= \frac{5 + 7 + 2}{1 + (4 + 30)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{9438} &:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times 2}{9 \times (4 \times (3 + 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{103896} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 - 2}{(103 + 8) \times 9 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{3016} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 - 2}{(30 - 1) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{36894} &:= \frac{5 + 7 + 2}{3 + (6 + 894)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{394680} &:= \frac{(5 + 7)^2}{3 \times 9 \times 46 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{3146} &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 2}{31 + 4 \times 6} & &:= \frac{5 \times (7 \times 2)}{3 + (6 \times (8 \times 94))} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 7 + 2}{31 + 46} & \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{39468} &:= \frac{(5 + 7)^2}{3 \times (9 \times (46 \times 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{572}{4160} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 - 2}{4 \times (1 \times 60)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 573

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{9168} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{9 - (1^6 - 8)} &:= \frac{5 + 7 + 3}{(1 + 9) \times (8 \times 6 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{291084} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{2^9 \times 10^8 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{19482} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{1 + (9 + (4 \times (8 - 2)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{41829} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{(4 \times (1 \times (8 \times 2))) + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{296814} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 - 3}{(2^9 + 6) \times 8 \times 1 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 3}{1 \times (9 \times (4 \times 8 + 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{91680} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{(9 - 1 - 6) \times 80} & &:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times 3}{(2^9 + 6) \times (8 + 1) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (7 - 3)}{(1 + 9) \times (4 + 8^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{104286} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{10 + 4 + 28 \times 6} & &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{2^9 - 6 + 8 + 1 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 7 + 3}{19 \times (4 + 8^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{104286} &:= \frac{57 - 3}{10^4 - 2 \times 86} & &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 3}{(2^9 + 6) \times (8 + 1^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{19864} &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 3}{(1 - (9 - 86)) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{194820} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 3}{(1 + 9) \times (4 \times 8 + 2) + 0} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{198640} &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 3}{(1 - 9 + 86) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 574

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{574}{861} &:= \frac{5 - 7 + 4}{8 - 6 + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{574}{1968} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 \times 4}{(1 + 9) \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{574}{8036} &:= \frac{5 + 7 \times 4}{(80 - 3) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{574}{19680} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 \times 4}{(1+9) \times 6 \times 80} &:= \frac{5+7-4}{19 \times 6 \times 3 \times 08} &\blacktriangleright \frac{574}{216398} &:= \frac{5-7+4}{2+16 \times (39+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{574}{19803} &:= \frac{5-7+4}{1-(9-(80-3))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{574}{203196} &:= \frac{5+7+4}{(20 \times 3-1) \times 96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{574}{196308} &:= \frac{5+7+4}{19 \times (6+30) \times 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{574}{208936} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-4)}{20 \times (89 \times 3+6)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 576

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{832} &:= \frac{5+7+6}{8 \times 3+2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{13824} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{1 \times (3 \times (8+24))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{93184} &:= \frac{5+7+6}{((9^3)-1^8) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{1024} &:= \frac{5+7+6}{(10-2) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{1 \times (3 \times ((8+2) \times 4))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{93248} &:= \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{(9 \times ((3 \times 2)^4)) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{1248} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1^2+4+8} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1 \times (3 \times (8 \times (2+4)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{104832} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{104 \times (8-3+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{1280} &:= \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{1 \times (2 \times 80)} &:= \frac{5 \times 7+6}{1 \times (3 \times (82 \times 4))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{123984} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{1+(23 \times 9+8) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{1920} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1^9 \times 20} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{13920} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1+((3+9)^2+0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{128304} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(1+2+8) \times 3^{04}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{2048} &:= \frac{5+7+6}{2 \times (0+4 \times 8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{14832} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{1+((48+3) \times 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{134208} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{1+34^2+08} \\ &:= \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{2^{0 \times 4+8}} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{18432} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{1 \times ((8-4) \times 32)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{134928} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{13-4+928} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{2304} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{(2+3+0) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times (3+2)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{138240} &:= \frac{5 \times 7+6}{1 \times 3 \times 82 \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{5+7-6}{2 \times (3 \times 04)} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times 3 \times 2))} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(1+3+8) \times 2 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{4032} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{40-3-2} &:= \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{18 \times (4 \times 32)} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{1 \times 3 \times (8+2) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{4320} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{43+2+0} &:= \frac{5+76}{18 \times ((4 \times 3)^2)} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1 \times 38^2-4+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{8192} &:= \frac{5+7+6}{(8-1+9)^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{32840} &:= \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{(3^2)+(8^4+0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{148032} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{1 \times 4+8^{03} \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{12384} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{1-(2-(3+84))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{34128} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(3^{4+1})+2-8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{184320} &:= \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{18 \times (4 \times 320)} \\ &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1+2^{3+8-4}} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{90432} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(90 \times (4+3))-2} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(1 \times 8-4) \times 320} \\ &:= \frac{5+7+6}{1+2+384} &\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{93120} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{9+31^2+0} &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{(1+8-4) \times 320} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{13248} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(1-3) \times (2-48)} & & &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1 \times 8 \times 4 \times 3 \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{189024} &:= \frac{5+7-6}{1-(8-90) \times 24} & \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{314928} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{3^{1 \times 4 + 9 + 2 - 8}} & & := \frac{5-7+6}{4 \times 1 \times (93-2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{192384} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{1+(9+2)^3 + 8 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{319824} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{3 \times (1+9 \times 82) + 4} & & := \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{(4+1) \times (93-2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{239184} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{2+3+9 \times 184} & \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{321984} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(3 \times 21 \times 9 - 8) \times 4} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{293184} &:= \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{(2^9 - 3) \times 18 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{348192} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(34-8) \times (1+92)} & & \\ &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(2^9 - 3 \times 1^8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{384192} &:= \frac{5-7+6}{(3 \times 8 + 4 + 1) \times 92} & & \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (7-6)}{(2^9 - 3) \times (1+8-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{576}{419328} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 + 6}{41 \times (93-2) \times 8} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 578

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{2601} &:= \frac{5-7+8}{26+01} & \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{23409} &:= \frac{5+7-8}{2 \times 3^4 + 0 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{219640} &:= \frac{5-7+8}{(2+1+9 \times 6) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{4913} &:= \frac{5+7-8}{4+((9+1) \times 3)} & &:= \frac{5-7+8}{(23+4+0) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{312409} &:= \frac{5+7-8}{3-1+240 \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{5-7+8}{49-1+3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{32946} &:= \frac{5-7+8}{(3 \times (29 \times 4)) - 6} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{13294} &:= \frac{5+7-8}{1+((3 \times 29) + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{132940} &:= \frac{5+7-8}{(1 \times 32 - 9) \times 40} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{578}{21964} &:= \frac{5-7+8}{(2+(1+(9 \times 6))) \times 4} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 579

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{2316} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{2+(3+1+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{8106} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{(8-1+0) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{46320} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{4+(6^3+20)} \\ &:= \frac{5-7+9}{23-1+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{24318} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{2 \times ((4^3) - 1^8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{130468} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{13 \times (04+6 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{3281} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{3+(2 \times (8-1))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{32810} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{((3^2) + 8) \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{362840} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{3 \times 628 - 4 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{4632} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{4 \times (6 \times (3-2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{579}{36284} &:= \frac{5+7-9}{(3+(6^2+8)) \times 4} & & \\ &:= \frac{5-7+9}{4 \times 6 + 32} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 580

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{1276} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{1392} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{1 + (3 + 92)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{1624} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{(1 + 6) \times 2^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{1972} := \frac{5 + 80}{(1 + 9 + 7)^2} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{2146} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{2 + 146} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{3219} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{3 + 219} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{4176} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{(41 + 7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{12934} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{1 + ((2 + 9) \times (3^4))} \end{array} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{580}{176349} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{(17 + 6)^3 + 4 - 9}$$

● Numerator 581

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{2739} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{2 + (73 - 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{4067} := \frac{58 - 1}{406 - 7} \\ \quad := \frac{58 + 1}{406 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{6723} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{6 \times ((7 + 2) \times 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{6972} := \frac{5 + 8 - 1}{(6 \times (9 - 7))^2} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{27639} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{27 + 639} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{30627} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{(3^{06}) + 2 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{67230} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{6 \times ((7 + 2) \times 30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{349762} := \frac{5 + 8 - 1}{3 - 4 + (9 + 76)^2} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{364702} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{3 \times 6^4 + 70^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{581}{679023} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{6 \times (7 + 902) \times 3} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 582

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{1067} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{10 + 67} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{1746} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 2}{17 + 46} \\ \quad := \frac{(5 + 8) \times 2}{(17 - 4) \times 6} \\ \quad := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{(17 + 4) \times 6} \\ \quad := \frac{58 - 2}{1 \times (7 \times (4 \times 6))} \\ \quad := \frac{58 + 2}{174 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{1940} := \frac{5 + 8 + 2}{1 + (9 + 40)} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{7469} := \frac{5 \times (8 - 2)}{7 \times (46 + 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{10476} := \frac{5 + 8 - 2}{((10 \times 4) - 7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{17460} := \frac{5 + 8 + 2}{(1 + 74) \times (6 + 0)} \\ \quad := \frac{(5 + 8) \times 2}{(17 - 4) \times 60} \\ \quad := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{(17 + 4) \times 60} \\ \quad := \frac{58 - 2}{1 \times (7 \times (4 \times 60))} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{63147} := \frac{58 - 2}{(6^3 + 1) \times (4 \times 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{79346} := \frac{5 \times (8 - 2)}{((7 - 9) \times 3) + 4^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{136479} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 2)}{1 - 3 + (6^4 + 7) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{582}{403617} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{40 \times (3^6 - 1) + 7} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 583

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{583}{742} &:= \frac{5+83}{7 \times (4^2)} & & := \frac{5 \times (8+3)}{174-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{583}{167904} &:= \frac{5+8-3}{(1^6+7) \times 90 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{583}{1749} &:= \frac{5+8-3}{1-(7-(4 \times 9))} & & := \frac{58+3}{174+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{583}{429671} &:= \frac{(5+8) \times 3}{429 \times 67 \times 1} \\ &:= \frac{(5+8) \times 3}{(17-4) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{583}{17490} &:= \frac{5 \times (8-3)}{1+(749+0)} & & \\ & & & := \frac{(5+8) \times 3}{(17-4) \times 90} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 584

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{36792} &:= \frac{5-8+4}{3+(67-9+2)} & & := \frac{5+8+4}{(3 \times 9+7 \times 1)^2} & & := \frac{5 \times (8-4)}{(3+67) \times 9 \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (8-4)}{(3+67) \times 9 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{61320} &:= \frac{5-8+4}{((6-1)^3)-20} & & := \frac{5+8-4}{(3+67) \times 9^2+0} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 8-4}{3 \times (6 \times (7 \times 9 \times 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{63072} &:= \frac{5-8+4}{6+(30+72)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{379016} &:= \frac{5-8+4}{3+7 \times 90+16} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 8+4}{36 \times (7 \times (9+2))} & & := \frac{5 \times 84}{630 \times 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{397120} &:= \frac{5-8+4}{(3 \times 9+7 \times 1) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{37960} &:= \frac{5-8+4}{3-(7-(9+60))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{367920} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-4}{3 \times 6 \times 7 \times 9 \times 20} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{584}{39712} &:= \frac{5-8+4}{3+((9 \times 7 \times 1)+2)} & & := \frac{5-8+4}{3^6-7-92+0} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 586

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{586}{2930} &:= \frac{5-8+6}{2 \times 9-3+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{586}{30472} &:= \frac{5+8-6}{(30-4) \times (7 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{5+8+6}{2+(93+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{586}{210374} &:= \frac{(5+8) \times 6}{2+10^3 \times 7 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 589

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{627} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-9}{6+27} & \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{2413} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-9}{2+((4+1)^3)} & & := \frac{58-9}{(4+1+2)^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{1064} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-9}{(10 \times 6)-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{2736} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-9}{(27-3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{4237} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-9}{((4+2)^3)+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{1463} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-9}{14+63} & \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{4123} &:= \frac{5+8-9}{4+(1+23)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{4712} &:= \frac{5+8-9}{4 \times (7+1^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{589}{1672} &:= \frac{5 \times 8-9}{16+72} & & := \frac{5-8+9}{41-2+3} & & := \frac{5-8+9}{4 \times ((7-1) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{589}{6327} := \frac{5 \times 8 - 9}{6 + 327}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{589}{14763} := \frac{5 \times 8 - 9}{14 + 763}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{589}{27360} := \frac{5 \times 8 - 9}{(27 - 3) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{589}{47120} := \frac{5 - 8 + 9}{4 \times ((7 - 1) \times 20)}$$

● Numerator 590

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{590}{21476} := \frac{5 \times 90}{2 + (1 \times ((47) - 6))}$$

● Numerator 591

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{2364} := \frac{5 + 91}{2 \times (3 \times 64)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 - 1}{(2^3 \times 6) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 \times 1}{(2^3 + 6) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{59 - 1}{236 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 + 1}{2 \times (3 \times (6 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{59 + 1}{236 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{4728} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 1)}{4 \times (72 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 - 1}{(4 + 7 + 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 9 \times 1}{(47 - 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{59 - 1}{472 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{59 + 1}{472 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{23640} := \frac{5 + 91}{2 \times (3 \times 640)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 \times 1}{(2^3 + 6) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{37824} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 1)}{(3 + 7) \times (8^2 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 + 1}{3 \times ((78 + 2) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{47280} := \frac{5 + 9 - 1}{(4 + 7 + 2) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 9 \times 1}{(47 - 2) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{230687} := \frac{5 + 9 + 1}{(2 + 3^{06}) \times 8 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{238764} := \frac{5 + 9 - 1}{2 \times 3 \times 876 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{378240} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 1)}{(3 + 7) \times 8^2 \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 + 1}{3 \times (78 + 2) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{591}{468072} := \frac{5 \times 9 - 1}{(4 + 6 \times 80) \times 72}$$

● Numerator 592

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{814} := \frac{5 + 9 + 2}{8 + 14}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 92}{47 + 3^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{47360} := \frac{5 + 9 - 2}{4 \times ((7 - 3) \times 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{1036} := \frac{5 + 9 + 2}{10 + 3 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{13468} := \frac{5 + 9 - 2}{1^3 + (4 \times 68)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{63714} := \frac{5 + 9 + 2}{6 \times (3 + (71 \times 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{1480} := \frac{5 + 9 + 2}{(1 + 4) \times (8 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{13764} := \frac{5 + 9 + 2}{1 \times (376 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{318607} := \frac{5 + 9 + 2}{3 + 1 + 8607}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{4107} := \frac{5 + 9 + 2}{4 + 107}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{30784} := \frac{5 + 9 \times 2}{(307 - 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{4736} := \frac{5 + 9 - 2}{4 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6)}$$

- Numerator 594

$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{627} := \frac{5+9+4}{6 \times 2+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{2871} := \frac{5+9+4}{2 \times 8+71}$	$:= \frac{59+4}{2 \times (3 \times (7 \times 60))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{1386} := \frac{5+9+4}{1 \times (3 \times (8+6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{3168} := \frac{5+9+4}{(3-1) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{26730} := \frac{5+9-4}{(2+6+7) \times 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{1683} := \frac{5+9+4}{1 \times ((6 \times 8)+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{3267} := \frac{5+9+4}{3 \times (26+7)}$	$:= \frac{(5+9) \times 4}{2 \times (6 \times (7 \times 30))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{1782} := \frac{5+9-4}{1 \times ((7+8) \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{3861} := \frac{5+9-4}{((3+8) \times 6)-1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{31680} := \frac{5+9+4}{(3-1) \times 6 \times 80}$
$:= \frac{5+9+4}{1 \times (7 \times 8-2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{6237} := \frac{5+9-4}{(6 \times 2+3) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{62073} := \frac{5+9+4}{(620+7) \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{2178} := \frac{5+9+4}{2 + ((1+7) \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{7128} := \frac{(5+9) \times 4}{7 \times (12 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{62370} := \frac{5+9-4}{(6 \times 2+3) \times 70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{2376} := \frac{5+9+4}{(2+3+7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{7623} := \frac{5+9+4}{7 \times (6^2-3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{71280} := \frac{(5+9) \times 4}{7 \times (12 \times 80)}$
$:= \frac{(5+9) \times 4}{2 + (37 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{8613} := \frac{5+9+4}{(86+1) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{86130} := \frac{5+9+4}{(86+1) \times 30}$
$:= \frac{59+4}{2 \times (3 \times 7 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{13728} := \frac{5+9+4}{1 \times ((3+7^2) \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{137280} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1 \times 3+7^2) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{2673} := \frac{5+9-4}{(2+6+7) \times 3}$	$:= \frac{59+4}{13 \times (7 \times 2 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{59+4}{13 \times 7 \times 2 \times 80}$
$:= \frac{5+9+4}{2 + (6+73)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{17820} := \frac{5+9-4}{1 \times ((7+8) \times 20)}$	
$:= \frac{(5+9) \times 4}{2 \times (6 \times 7 \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{23706} := \frac{59-4}{2+3^7+06}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{23760} := \frac{5+9+4}{(2+3+7) \times 60}$	

● Numerator 596

$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{2384} := \frac{5+9-6}{2^3 \times (8-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{3874} := \frac{5-9+6}{3 \times 8 - (7+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{10728} := \frac{5-9+6}{1 - (0 - (7+28))}$
$:= \frac{5 \times (9-6)}{(23-8) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{5+9-6}{3 \times 8 + 7 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{13708} := \frac{5-9+6}{1 + (3 \times (7+08))}$
$:= \frac{5+9+6}{(2 \times 38) + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{4172} := \frac{5-9+6}{4 + (1+7+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{17284} := \frac{5-9+6}{1 - (7 - (2 \times 8 \times 4))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{3278} := \frac{5+9+6}{32+78}$	$:= \frac{5+9-6}{4 \times (1 \times (7 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{5+9-6}{(1 + ((7^2) + 8)) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{3427} := \frac{5+9+6}{3 + ((4^2) \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{4321} := \frac{5+9+6}{((4 \times 3)^2) + 1}$	$:= \frac{5+9+6}{1 \times ((72 \times 8) + 4)}$

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{23840} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{2+(38+40)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (9-6)}{(23-8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{24138} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{2+(41+38)} \\ &:= \frac{5+9+6}{2 \times (413-8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{28310} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{2+(83+10)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{32184} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{3^{2+18} \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{5+9-6}{3 \times (2 \times 18 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{32780} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{3+(27+80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{34270} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{3+(42+70)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{38740} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{3+(87+40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{41720} &:= \frac{5+9-6}{4 \times (1 \times (7 \times 20))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{43210} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{((4 \times 3)^2) + 1 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{47382} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{4+(73+82)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{83142} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{83+(14^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{108472} &:= \frac{5+9-6}{(108-4) \times 7 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{123074} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{1+2 \times (30 \times 7-4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{172840} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{1 \times 72 \times 8+4+0} \\ &:= \frac{5+9-6}{(1+7^2+8) \times 40} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{174032} &:= \frac{5+9-6}{(-1+74) \times 032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{237804} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{2+(3+7) \times 80-4} \\ &:= \frac{5+9-6}{2 \times 3 \times 7 \times (80-4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{241380} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{2 \times (413-8)+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{596}{321840} &:= \frac{5-9+6}{3^{2+18} \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{5+9-6}{3 \times 2 \times 18 \times 40} \end{aligned}$
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● Numerator 597

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{3184} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{3+(1+8+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{10348} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{1-(0-(3+48))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{14328} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{1 \times ((4+3+2) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{5+9-7}{(1+(4 \times (3+2))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (9-7)}{(1+4) \times (3 \times 2 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{5+9+7}{(1+((4^3)-2)) \times 8} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{23084} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{2+(30+84)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{23681} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{2+(36+81)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{30248} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{(3-(0-(2^4))) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{31840} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{(3+1^8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{63481} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{((6+34) \times 8)-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{102684} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{1 \times 02^6 \times 8+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{142086} &:= \frac{5+9+7}{(1+4 \times 208) \times 6} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{143280} &:= \frac{5-9+7}{(1 \times 4+3+2) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (9-7)}{(1+4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{5+9+7}{(1+4^3-2) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{5+9-7}{(1+4 \times (3+2)) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{597}{162384} &:= \frac{5+9+7}{1 \times 6 \times 238 \times 4} \end{aligned}$
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● Numerator 598

$\blacktriangleright \frac{598}{10764} := \frac{5-9+8}{1-(0-(7+64))}$	$:= \frac{5 \times (9-8)}{10 \times (7+6-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{598}{17043} := \frac{5-9+8}{1+(70+43)}$
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$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{5+9-8}{170+4-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{598}{17342} & := \frac{5-9+8}{1+(73+42)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (9-8)}{1^7 + ((3 \times 4)^2)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{598}{26013} & := \frac{5+9-8}{260+1^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{598}{376142} & := \frac{5+9-8}{37 \times 6 \times (1+4^2)} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 601

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{25843} & := \frac{6-01}{(2-5+8) \times 43} \\ & := \frac{6^{01}}{258 \times (4-3)} \\ & := \frac{6+01}{258+43} \\ & := \frac{60 \times 1}{(2+58) \times 43} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{34257} & := \frac{6-01}{(3+4-2) \times 57} \\ & := \frac{6^{01}}{3 \times ((4-2) \times 57)} \\ & := \frac{6+01}{342+57} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{53489} & := \frac{6-01}{534-89} \\ & := \frac{6^{01}}{(5-3+4) \times 89} \\ & := \frac{6+01}{534+89} \\ & := \frac{60 \times 1}{5 \times (3 \times (4 \times 89))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{58297} & := \frac{6-01}{5 \times (((8+2) \times 9) + 7)} \\ & := \frac{6+01}{582+97} \\ & := \frac{60 \times 1}{(58+2) \times 97} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{85342} & := \frac{6+01}{(8 \times (5^3)) - 4 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{85943} & := \frac{6^{01}}{859-4+3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{349782} & := \frac{6+01}{(3+4) \times 97 \times (8-2)} \\ & := \frac{6-01}{(3+49) \times 7 \times 8-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{601}{437528} & := \frac{6-01}{(4^3 \times 7 + 5 + 2) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 602

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{5418} & := \frac{6-02}{54-18} \\ & := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{5+(41+8)} \\ & := \frac{6+02}{(5+4 \times 1) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{5719} & := \frac{6-02}{57-19} \\ & := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{57 \times 1^9} \\ & := \frac{6+02}{57+19} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{17458} & := \frac{6-02}{174-58} \\ & := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{1 \times ((7-4) \times 58)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{6+02}{(1+7-4) \times 58} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 01}{(17 \times 4 \times 5) + 8} \\ & := \frac{60-2}{(1+7 \times 4) \times 58} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{35819} & := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{358-1^9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{58394} & := \frac{6-02}{(5+(83+9)) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{60-2}{58 \times (3+94)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{94815} & := \frac{6+02}{9 \times (4 \times ((8-1) \times 5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{95417} & := \frac{6-02}{9+5^4 \times 17} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{175483} & := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{1754-8+3} \\ & := \frac{60 \times 2}{1+7 \times (5^4 \times 8-3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{318759} & := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{(318+7 \times 5) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{354879} & := \frac{6 \times 01}{(3+(5+4) \times 87) \times 9} \\ & := \frac{6-02}{(3+(5+4 \times 8) \times 7) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{602}{413875} & := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{(4+1) \times (3+8) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 603

$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{1742} := \frac{6 + 03}{1 \times (7 \times 4 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{18425} := \frac{6 \times 03}{(18 + 4) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{82745} := \frac{6 \times 03}{8^2 + (7^4 + 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{2479} := \frac{6 \times 03}{2 \times (4 \times 7 + 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{18492} := \frac{6 - 03}{1 + (84 + 9 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{85492} := \frac{6 + 03}{8 + ((5^4 + 9) \times 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{2814} := \frac{6 - 03}{2 \times (8 - 1^4)}$	$:= \frac{6 + 03}{184 + 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{97284} := \frac{6 - 03}{(9 + (7 \times 2 \times 8)) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{28 \times 1^4}$	$:= \frac{6^{03}}{18 \times (4 \times 92)}$	$:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{972 - 8 + 4}$
$:= \frac{6 + 03}{2 + (8 \times (1 + 4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{21574} := \frac{6 + 03}{2 \times (157 + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{97485} := \frac{6 - 03}{(9 + ((7 + 4) \times 8)) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{2948} := \frac{6 \times 03}{2 + (94 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{24589} := \frac{6 + 03}{((2 + 45) \times 8) - 9}$	$:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{(9 - 7) \times 485}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{4958} := \frac{6 \times 03}{4 \times (9 \times 5 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{24857} := \frac{6 + 03}{(((2 + 4) \times 8) + 5) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{128975} := \frac{6 + 03}{(1 - (2 - 8) \times 9) \times 7 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{5427} := \frac{6 - 03}{54 - 27}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 03}{2 \times ((48 + 5) \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{145792} := \frac{6 + 03}{(1 + 4^5 + 7 \times 9) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{5 + (42 + 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{29145} := \frac{6 - 03}{(2 - (9 \times (1 - 4))) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{159728} := \frac{6 \times 03}{(1 + 597 - 2) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{6 + 03}{54 + 27}$	$:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{29 \times (1 + 4 + 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{185724} := \frac{6 + 03}{(1 + 8) \times (5 + 72) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{60 + 3}{((5 + 4)^2) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 03}{2 \times ((91 - 4) \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 03}{18 \times (5 + 72) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{5829} := \frac{6 - 03}{58 - 29}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{29547} := \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{(2 - 9) \times (5 - 47)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{291584} := \frac{6 + 03}{2^{9-15} + 8^4}$
$:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{5 \times 8 + 2 \times 9}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 03}{2 \times ((9 + 54) \times 7)}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 03}{2^9 \times (1 \times 5 + 8 + 4)}$
$:= \frac{6 + 03}{58 + 29}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{29748} := \frac{6^{03}}{2 \times (9 \times (74 \times 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{428197} := \frac{6 + 03}{42 \times 8 \times 19 + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{8241} := \frac{6 - 03}{82 - 41}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{29815} := \frac{6 + 03}{(((2 + 9) \times 8) + 1) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{548127} := \frac{6 + 03}{54 + 8127}$
$:= \frac{6 + 03}{82 + 41}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{41875} := \frac{60 + 3}{(4 + 1) \times 875}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{754219} := \frac{6 + 03}{7 + 5^4 \times 2 \times 1 \times 9}$
$:= \frac{6 \times 03}{82 \times (4 - 1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{71958} := \frac{6 - 03}{(7 \times ((1 + 9) \times 5)) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{847952} := \frac{6 + 03}{8 \times (4 \times 79 \times 5 + 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{15879} := \frac{6 - 03}{158 - 79}$	$:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 3}{719 + 5 - 8}$	
$:= \frac{6 + 03}{158 + 79}$		

● Numerator 604

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{1359} &:= \frac{60+4}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{13892} &:= \frac{6-04}{1+(3 \times (8+9-2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{132578} &:= \frac{6+04}{(13-2 \times 5)^7+8} \\ &:= \frac{60-4}{135-9} & &:= \frac{6+04}{138+92} & &:= \frac{6-04}{1+3 \times 2 \times (-5+78)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 04}{(1^3+5) \times 9} & &:= \frac{6 \times 04}{(1-3+8) \times 92} & \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{173952} &:= \frac{6+0 \times 4}{(1 \times 7 \times 3-9)^{5-2}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{2718} &:= \frac{6-04}{2+(7 \times 18)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{19328} &:= \frac{60+4}{((19-3)^2) \times 8} & &:= \frac{6^04}{(1+7)^3 \times 9^{5-2}} \\ &:= \frac{6+0 \times 4}{2+(7+18)} & &:= \frac{60 \times 4}{(1+9) \times (3 \times 2^8)} & &:= \frac{6-04}{(1 \times 7+3+9+5)^2} \\ &:= \frac{6+04}{27+18} & &:= \frac{6-04}{1-(9 \times (3-(2+8)))} & &:= \frac{60+4}{(1+7) \times (3+9 \times 5)^2} \\ &:= \frac{60-4}{2 \times (7 \times 18)} & &:= \frac{6+0 \times 4}{(1-(9-32)) \times 8} & &:= \frac{60-4}{1 \times 7 \times (3+9 \times 5)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{5738} &:= \frac{6-04}{57-38} & &:= \frac{6+04}{1-(9-328)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{193582} &:= \frac{6+04}{1+9 \times (358-2)} \\ &:= \frac{6+04}{57+38} & &:= \frac{60-4}{(1+9-3) \times 2^8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{315892} &:= \frac{6+0 \times 4}{3 \times (1+58 \times 9) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{7852} &:= \frac{6-04}{78-52} & &:= \frac{6 \times 04}{(1+(93+2)) \times 8} & &:= \frac{6-04}{3-1+58 \times 9 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{6+04}{78+52} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{12835} &:= \frac{6 \times 04}{1+(2+((8^3)-5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{28539} &:= \frac{6 \times 04}{(2+(8 \times 5)) \times 3 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{604}{32918} &:= \frac{6+0 \times 4}{3+(2 \times (9 \times 18))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 605

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{847} &:= \frac{60+5}{84+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{2794} &:= \frac{60-5}{2+(7 \times (9 \times 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{182347} &:= \frac{60-5}{1+8^2 \times 3+4^7} \\ &:= \frac{60-5}{84-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{17248} &:= \frac{60-5}{1 \times (7^2 \times 4 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{384912} &:= \frac{60-5}{3 \times ((8+4) \times 9 \times 1)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{2178} &:= \frac{60+5}{(2+1) \times 78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{28193} &:= \frac{60-5}{(2^8 \times (1+9)) + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{2387} &:= \frac{60-5}{(23+8) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{28941} &:= \frac{60-5}{(28 \times 94) - 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{605}{2398} &:= \frac{60-5}{2+(3 \times (9 \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 607

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{607}{38241} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 7}{382 - 4 \times 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{607}{143859} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 7}{(1 + 4 \times 38 + 5) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{607}{81945} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 7}{(8 + 1 + 9) \times 45} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 608

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{608}{912} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 8}{9 \times 1^2} & & := \frac{6 + 08}{5 + (4 + 7)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{608}{143792} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 8}{1437 - 9 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 08}{9 + 12} & \blacktriangleright \frac{608}{9234} &:= \frac{6 \times 08}{9^{2-3+4}} & &:= \frac{6 + 08}{1 \times 43 \times 7 \times (9 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{608}{3952} &:= \frac{6 + 08}{39 + 52} & \blacktriangleright \frac{608}{14592} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 8}{(1 + 4 \times 5 - 9)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{608}{5472} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 8}{5 + 47 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{608}{75392} &:= \frac{6 + 08}{7 \times (5 + 3 \times 9^2)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 609

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{812} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{8 \times 1^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{4872} &:= \frac{6 + 09}{4 \times ((8 + 7) \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{23751} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{(2 + 37) \times (5 + 1)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 09}{8 + 12} & &:= \frac{6 \times 09}{48 \times (7 + 2)} & &:= \frac{60 - 9}{(2 + 37) \times 51} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{1827} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{1 + (8 + 2 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{5278} &:= \frac{6 + 09}{52 + 78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{24157} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{2 + (((4 - 1)^5) - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 09}{18 + 27} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{5481} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{5 + (48 + 1)} & &:= \frac{6 + 09}{(2^4 + 1) \times 5 \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 09}{18 \times (2 + 7)} & &:= \frac{6 + 09}{54 + 81} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{35728} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{(35 + 7 + 2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{3248} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{(3 \times 2 \times 4) + 8} & &:= \frac{6 \times 09}{5 + 481} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{48517} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{485 - 1 \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 09}{(3 \times 24) + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{15428} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{(1 + ((5 + 4) \times 2)) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{52374} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{(52 \times (3 + 7)) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 09}{3 \times (2 \times 48)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{15834} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{1 \times ((5 + 8) \times (3 \times 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{184527} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{1845 - 27} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{3451} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{((3 + 4) \times 5) - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{18473} &:= \frac{60 \times 9}{1 - (8 - (4^7 + 3))} & &:= \frac{6 + 09}{18 + 4527} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 09}{34 + 51} & \blacktriangleright \frac{609}{23548} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 9}{(2 + (3 \times (5 + 4))) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 610

$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{732} := \frac{6-1+0}{7-3+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{5734} := \frac{6-1+0}{5 \times 7 + 3 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{72834} := \frac{6 \times 10}{(7 \times (2 \times (8^3))) - 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{854} := \frac{6-1+0}{8-5+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{23485} := \frac{6 \times 1 + 0}{234 - 8 + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{358924} := \frac{6-1+0}{3-5+8 \times 92 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{2745} := \frac{6 \times 1 + 0}{(2 \times (7 + 4)) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{25437} := \frac{6 \times 10}{2 - ((5^4) \times (3 - 7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{372954} := \frac{6-1+0}{3 \times (7 \times 29 \times 5 + 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{3294} := \frac{6-1+0}{32-9+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{27938} := \frac{6-1+0}{2^7 + (93 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{379542} := \frac{6-1+0}{3 + (79 - 5) \times 42}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{3294} := \frac{6 \times 10}{3^2 \times (9 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{28975} := \frac{6 \times 1 + 0}{(2 - (8 - (9 \times 7))) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{397842} := \frac{6-1+0}{3 \times (9 \times 7 + (8 \times 4)^2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{3782} := \frac{6-1+0}{37-8+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{34892} := \frac{6-1+0}{(34-8) \times (9+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{398452} := \frac{6-1+0}{39 \times 84 - 5 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{4392} := \frac{6-1+0}{43-9+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{42395} := \frac{6 \times 1 + 0}{((4 \times 2)^3) - 95}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{45872} := \frac{6-1+0}{4 \times (5 + (87 + 2))}$	

• Numerator 612

$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{748} := \frac{6+1+2}{7-4+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{7854} := \frac{6 \times 1^2}{78-5+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{37094} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{3^7 - 09 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{748} := \frac{6 \times 12}{(7+4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{8534} := \frac{6+12}{(85 \times 3) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{37485} := \frac{6-1 \times 2}{(37+4+8) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{3570} := \frac{6+12}{3 \times (5 \times 7 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{8534} := \frac{6 \times 12}{(8 \times (5^3)) + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{39780} := \frac{6-1-2}{3 \times (9 + (7 \times 8 + 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{3978} := \frac{6-1 \times 2}{3 \times 9 + 7 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{8704} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{8^{7-04}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{39780} := \frac{6+1+2}{39 \times (7+8+0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{3978} := \frac{6+12}{39+78}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{9078} := \frac{6 \times 1^2}{90+7-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{47583} := \frac{6-1 \times 2}{(4 \times 75) + 8 + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{4590} := \frac{6+12}{45+90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{9384} := \frac{6 \times 1^2}{((9+3) \times 8) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{57834} := \frac{6-1 \times 2}{(5 \times 78) - (3 \times 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{5049} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{50+49}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{34578} := \frac{6-1 \times 2}{(34 \times 5) + (7 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{59840} := \frac{6+1+2}{(5+9+8) \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{5984} := \frac{6+1+2}{(5+9+8) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{5984} := \frac{6+1 \times 2}{3 + (457 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{59874} := \frac{6 \times 1^2}{598 - (7 + 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{7038} := \frac{6-1 \times 2}{70 - (3 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{7038} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{3 + (45 \times (7 + 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{70584} := \frac{6-1-2}{(70 \times 5) - 8 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{7480} := \frac{6 \times 12}{(7+4) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{35904} := \frac{6-1-2}{(35+9+0) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{73984} := \frac{6+1+2}{(7+3 \times 9) \times 8 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{7548} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{(7 \times 5 \times 4) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{7548} := \frac{6 \times 1^2}{(3 - (5 - 90)) \times 4}$	

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{612}{74358} &:= \frac{6 \times 1^2}{(7-4)^{3-5+8}} &:= \frac{6+1^2}{(3+4) \times (5+7 \times 80)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{748935} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{(7+4) \times 89 \times 3 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{6+1 \times 2}{(7 \times (4 \times 35)) - 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{357408} &:= \frac{6+1^2}{(3 \times 5 - 7)^4 - 08} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{753984} &:= \frac{6+1 \times 2}{7 \times (5+39) \times 8 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{6+12}{(7-4)^{3 \times 5-8}} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{374850} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 2}{(37+4+8) \times 50} &:= \frac{6+1^2}{(7+5 \times 3) \times 98 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{612}{75480} &:= \frac{6-1-2}{(7 \times 54) - (8+0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{384795} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 2}{(3 \times 8 + 479) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{798354} &:= \frac{(6+1) \times 2}{7 \times ((9+8^3) \times 5+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{612}{93058} &:= \frac{6+12}{(9 \times 305) - 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{439875} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 2}{(4^3 \times 9 - 8 + 7) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{937584} &:= \frac{6+1+2}{9 \times (375+8) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{612}{95438} &:= \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{(9 \times 5^4) - (3+8)} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{(43+9 \times 8) \times 75} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{948753} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{9 \times (4 \times 8 + 7) \times 53} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{612}{308754} &:= \frac{6 \times 1^2}{3+08 \times 7 \times 54} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{549780} &:= \frac{6+1+2}{5+(4+97) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{612}{345780} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{3 \times 4 \times (5+7 \times 80)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{739840} &:= \frac{6+1+2}{(7+3 \times 9) \times 8 \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 613

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{613}{50879} &:= \frac{6-1^3}{((50+8) \times 7) + 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{613}{280754} &:= \frac{6-1-3}{2 \times (80+7 \times 54)} &:= \frac{61+3}{4 \times (8 \times (05+9))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{613}{70495} &:= \frac{6 \times 1^3}{704 - (9+5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{613}{457298} &:= \frac{6+1-3}{(4+5 \times 72+9) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(6+1) \times 3}{(7^04) + 9 + 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{613}{480592} &:= \frac{(6+1) \times 3}{(4+80) \times (5+9)^2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 614

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{614}{7982} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 4}{7+(9+8+2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{614}{78592} &:= \frac{6-1-4}{7+(8 \times 5+9^2)} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 4}{2 \times (83-9) \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{6-1+4}{(7 \times (9+8)) - 2} &:= \frac{6+1^4}{7 \times (8 \times (5+9+2))} &:= \frac{6 \times 1^4}{(2+8+3 \times 9) \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{6+1 \times 4}{((7+9) \times 8) + 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{614}{79820} &:= \frac{6-1-4}{((7+9) \times 8) + 2 + 0} &\blacktriangleright \frac{614}{397258} &:= \frac{6-1^4}{3+9 \times 72 \times 5-8} \\ &:= \frac{6+(1+4)}{79+8^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{614}{90872} &:= \frac{6-1-4}{90+((8 \times 7)+2)} &:= \frac{6-1+4}{3+97 \times (2+58)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{614}{58023} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 4}{5-(8 \times (0-23))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{614}{207839} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 4}{2+(078-3) \times 9} &:= \frac{6+1-4}{3 \times 9 \times 72+5-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{614}{75829} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 4}{(((7-5) \times 8)^2) - 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{614}{283975} &:= \frac{6-1 \times 4}{(2 \times 8 \times (3+9) - 7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 1^4}{(75 \times (8+2)) - 9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 615

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{738} &:= \frac{6-1+5}{7-3+8} & := \frac{6+1^5}{4 \times 9+20} & := \frac{6+1^5}{(9 \times 8)+40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{820} &:= \frac{6+1+5}{8 \times (2+0)} & := \frac{6+1+5}{4+(92+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{29807} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{2 \times ((9 \times 80)+7)} \\ &:= \frac{6+15}{8+20} & := \frac{6 \times 15}{4 \times (9 \times 20)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{278349} := \frac{6-1^5}{2+7 \times (83 \times 4-9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{2870} &:= \frac{6+15}{28+70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{7380} := \frac{6-1 \times 5}{7-(3-(8+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{287943} := \frac{(6+1) \times 5}{2^8 \times (7+9) \times 4+3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{3280} &:= \frac{6+15}{32+80} & := \frac{6+1^5}{7-(3-80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{387942} := \frac{6-1+5}{38 \times (79+4) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 15}{3 \times (2 \times 80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{9348} := \frac{(6-1) \times 5}{(93 \times 4)+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{4920} &:= \frac{6+1-5}{(4 \times 9)-20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{615}{9840} := \frac{6+1-5}{(9 \times 8)-40} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 617

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{617}{3085} &:= \frac{6+1+7}{30+(8 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(6+1) \times 7}{30 \times 8+5} \\ &:= \frac{6+17}{30+85} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{617}{32084} &:= \frac{6 \times (1+7)}{3 \times (208 \times 4)} &:= \frac{6 \times 1^7}{3 \times (20+84)} \\ &:= \frac{6-1^7}{(32 \times 08)+4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 618

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{618}{927} &:= \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{9 \times (2+7)} \\ &:= \frac{6+18}{9+27} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{37492} := \frac{6 \times 1^8}{3-(7-(4 \times 92))} := \frac{6 \times 1^8}{4 \times 3 \times (50 \times 7+2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{42539} := \frac{6 \times 1^8}{425-(3+9)} := \frac{6+1^8}{4^3 \times (5+072)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{618}{4532} &:= \frac{6 \times 1^8}{4 \times (5+3 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{6+1+8}{4+(53 \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{45732} := \frac{6+1 \times 8}{4^5+(7+3+2)} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{618}{495327} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{(4+(9+5)^3) \times 2 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{70452} := \frac{6-1^8}{((70 \times 4)+5) \times 2} := \frac{6+1 \times 8}{49 \times (5+32 \times 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{20394} := \frac{6 \times 1^8}{203-9+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{73542} := \frac{6+18}{(73-5) \times 42} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{618}{749325} := \frac{6+1 \times 8}{7 \times (4+93) \times 25}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{618}{32754} &:= \frac{6 \times 1^8}{327-(5+4)} \\ &:= \frac{6+1^8}{((3+2) \times 75)-4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{379452} := \frac{6+1+8}{3-7+9 \times (4^5)-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{618}{435072} := \frac{6-1^8}{4^3 \times (50+7-2)}$$

● Numerator 619

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{619}{7428} &:= \frac{6+1^9}{74+2+8} \\ &:= \frac{6-1+9}{7 \times (4^2+8)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 1^9}{(7+4-2) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{619}{40235} := \frac{6-1^9}{(40 \times 2^3)+5} := \frac{6 \times 1^9}{(7+4-2) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{619}{73042} := \frac{6+1^9}{7 \times ((30 \times 4)-2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{619}{8047} := \frac{6+1^9}{80+4+7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{619}{74280} := \frac{6+1^9}{(7-4) \times 280}$$

● Numerator 620

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{1395} &:= \frac{6-2+0}{13-9+5} \\ &:= \frac{6+2+0}{1+(3+9+5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+0}{13+9+5} \\ &:= \frac{6^2+0}{1 \times (3^9-5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{620}{3875} := \frac{6+2+0}{(3 \times (8+7))+5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{6^2 + 0}{3 \times ((8 + 7) \times 5)} & := \frac{6 \times 2 + 0}{((1 - 3 + 4)^8) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{81375} & := \frac{6 - 2 + 0}{(8 - 1^3) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{4185} & := \frac{6 - 2 + 0}{4 + (18 + 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{13795} & := \frac{6 - 2 + 0}{1^3 - (7 - 95)} & & := \frac{6 \times 2 + 0}{(8 + 13) \times 75} \\ & := \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{41 + 8 + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{19375} & := \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{((19 \times 3) - 7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{194835} & := \frac{6 \times 2 + 0}{1 \times 9 \times (4 + 83 \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 2 + 0}{41 + (8 \times 5)} & & := \frac{6 \times 2 + 0}{1^9 \times 375} & \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{371845} & := \frac{6 - 2 + 0}{3 + 7^{1 \times 8 - 4} - 5} \\ & := \frac{6^2 + 0}{(4 - 1^8)^5} & & := \frac{6 \times 20}{(1 + 9) \times 375} & \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{431985} & := \frac{6^2 + 0}{4^{3+1} \times 98 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{13485} & := \frac{6 - 2 + 0}{1 - (3 - (4 + 85))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{620}{34875} & := \frac{6 - 2 + 0}{(3 + 4 + 8)^{7-5}} & & \\ & := \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{134 + (8 \times 5)} & & := \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{(34 + 8 \times 7) \times 5} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 621

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{759} & := \frac{6 + 2 + 1}{7 - 5 + 9} & & := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 1}{((73 \times 4) - 8) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{397854} & := \frac{6 \times (2 - 1)}{3 \times ((9 - 7)^8 \times 5) + 4} \\ & := \frac{6^2 \times 1}{7 \times 5 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{75348} & := \frac{6 - 2 - 1}{7 \times ((5 \times (3 \times 4)) - 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{398475} & := \frac{6 - 2 - 1}{(3 \times (9 + 8) + 4) \times 7 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{3450} & := \frac{62 + 1}{(3 + 4) \times 50} & & := \frac{6 \times (2 + 1)}{7 \times ((5 + 34) \times 8)} & & := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 1}{(3 \times 9 \times 8 + 4) \times 7 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{3795} & := \frac{6 + 2 + 1}{3 + (7 + 9 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{78039} & := \frac{6 \times (2 - 1)}{7 + ((80 + 3) \times 9)} & & := \frac{6^2 \times 1}{(39 \times 8 - 4) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{8073} & := \frac{6 + 21}{8 - (0 - (7^3))} & & := \frac{6 + 21}{(7 + 80) \times 39} & & := \frac{6 + 2 + 1}{3 \times (9 + 8 \times 47) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{30498} & := \frac{6 + 2 + 1}{(30 - 4) \times (9 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{87354} & := \frac{6 \times (2 - 1)}{(8 \times (7 \times 3 \times 5)) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{437598} & := \frac{6 - 2 - 1}{4 + 3^7 - 5 - 9 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{38709} & := \frac{6 + 2 + 1}{3 - ((8 - 70) \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{345897} & := \frac{6 \times (2 - 1)}{3 + (45 + 8) \times 9 \times 7} & & := \frac{62 + 1}{(4^3 \times 7 + 5) \times 98} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{58374} & := \frac{6 - 2 \times 1}{(5 \times (83 - 7)) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{375084} & := \frac{6 - 2 - 1}{3 \times (75 \times 08 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{589743} & := \frac{6 \times (2 + 1)}{(5 + 8 \times 9) \times 74 \times 3} \\ & := \frac{6 - 2 + 1}{5 \times (83 + 7 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{379845} & := \frac{6 - 2 - 1}{(3 - (7 - 98) \times 4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{753480} & := \frac{6 \times (2 + 1)}{7 \times (5 + 34) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{6 + 2 + 1}{5 + (837 + 4)} & & := \frac{6 + 21}{3 + (7 + 9) \times (8 + 4^5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{849735} & := \frac{6 \times 21}{(8^4 + 9) \times (7 + 35)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 2 + 1}{(58 \times (3 \times 7)) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{395784} & := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 1}{(3 + 95) \times 78 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{870435} & := \frac{6 + 21}{87 \times 0435} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{73485} & := \frac{6 - 2 - 1}{7^3 + (4 \times (8 - 5))} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{621}{873540} & := \frac{6^2 \times 1}{8 + 7 + (3 \times 5)^4 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 623

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{801} := \frac{6-2+3}{8+01} & \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{40851} := \frac{6-2+3}{408+51} & \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{94518} := \frac{6+2^3}{9 \times (4 \times (51+8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{1958} := \frac{6-2+3}{1 \times (9+5+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{51709} := \frac{6-2-3}{5-(1-(70+9))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{859740} := \frac{6+2^3}{8 \times (5+9+7^4)+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{5874} := \frac{6+2^3}{58+74} & \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{58740} := \frac{6+2^3}{(5 \times 8-7) \times 40} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{10947} := \frac{6-2+3}{(10 \times (9+4))-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{84105} := \frac{(6+2) \times 3}{8 \times (410-5)} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 624

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{780} := \frac{6+2+4}{7+8+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{15873} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(1+(58 \times 7)) \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{107835} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{(1+078) \times 35} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{819} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(8-1) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{19578} := \frac{6-2+4}{195+(7 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{130975} := \frac{6 \times 24}{(1+30) \times 975} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{1053} := \frac{6^2-4}{1+053} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{31590} := \frac{6-2+4}{3 \times (15 \times (9+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{158379} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(15+8)^3+7+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{1950} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{1^9 \times 50} & := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{(3+1+5) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{158730} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(1+58 \times 7) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 24}{1 \times (9 \times 50)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{159783} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{1^5 + ((9-7) \times 8)^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{3159} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{(3+1+5) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{37518} := \frac{6-2+4}{37 \times (5+1 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{173589} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{1+7^3 \times (5+8)-9} \\ & := \frac{6^2-4}{3+159} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{189735} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{1^8 \times 973 \times 5} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{3^{1-5+9}} & := \frac{6 \times 24}{(1+8) \times (973 \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 24}{3^{15-9}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{851370} := \frac{6 \times 2+4}{(8+51) \times 370} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{3510} := \frac{6-2+4}{3 \times (5+10)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{73905} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{(7 \times (3 \times 90)) + 5} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{8190} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(8-1) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{85137} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{(8+51) \times 37} & \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{624}{85371} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{8-(5-(3^7-1))} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 627

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{1045} := \frac{6+2+7}{(1+04)\times 5} \\
 := \frac{6+27}{10+45} \\
 := \frac{6\times(2+7)}{10\times(4+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{1485} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{1+(4+(8\times 5))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{1539} := \frac{6-2+7}{(1+5-3)\times 9} \\
 := \frac{6+27}{(1+5+3)\times 9} \\
 := \frac{62-7}{1\times(5\times 3\times 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{1843} := \frac{6+27}{1+8\times 4\times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{1938} := \frac{6-2+7}{1+(9+3\times 8)} \\
 := \frac{6+27}{1+(93+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{3498} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{34+9\times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{3591} := \frac{6-2+7}{3+59+1} \\
 := \frac{62-7}{35\times 9\times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{3819} := \frac{6-2+7}{3-(8\times(1-9))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{3894} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{3\times 8+94} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{4389} := \frac{6+2-7}{4-(3\times(8-9))} \\
 := \frac{6\times 2-7}{(4\times(3+8))-9} \\
 := \frac{6+2+7}{(4\times 3\times 8)+9} \\
 := \frac{6\times(2+7)}{(4+38)\times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{5940} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{5\times(9\times 4+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{9834} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{(98\times 3)+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{10395} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{(10-3)\times 9\times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{14850} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{(1^4+8)\times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{15048} := \frac{6+2-7}{((1-5)\times(-04))+8} \\
 := \frac{6\times 2-7}{15\times((0\times 4)+8)} \\
 := \frac{6+2\times 7}{15\times(0+4\times 8)} \\
 := \frac{(6-2)^7}{(1+(5+0))\times(4^8)} \\
 := \frac{6\times(2+7)}{(1+5)^{-04+8}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{15390} := \frac{6-2+7}{(1+5-3)\times 90} \\
 := \frac{6+27}{(1+5+3)\times 90} \\
 := \frac{62-7}{1\times(5\times(3\times 90))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{15840} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{15\times 8\times 4+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{15903} := \frac{62-7}{15\times(90+3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{35910} := \frac{62-7}{35\times(9\times 10)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{39501} := \frac{6+2-7}{3+9+50+1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{41895} := \frac{6+27}{(41+8)\times 9\times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{43890} := \frac{6+2-7}{(4\times(3-8))+90} \\
 := \frac{6\times(2+7)}{(4+38)\times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{59413} := \frac{6+27}{(5^9-4)-1+3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{84315} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{((8\times 4^3)-1)\times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{95304} := \frac{(6-2)\times 7}{(9+5)\times 304} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{134805} := \frac{6^2-7}{13\times 480-5} \\
 := \frac{6+2-7}{(1+34+8)\times 05} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{185493} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{1-8+(5^4\times 9+3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{189354} := \frac{6+2-7}{18\times(9+3+5)-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{189430} := \frac{6+27}{(1^8+9)^4-30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{194503} := \frac{6+27}{(1+9)\times 4^5-03} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{385149} := \frac{6-2+7}{3^8+(5-1)\times 49} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{398145} := \frac{6\times 2+7}{(3+9+(8-1)^4)\times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{627}{418950} := \frac{6+27}{(41+8)\times 9\times 50}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 628

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{1570} &:= \frac{6^2 - 8}{1^5 \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 28}{15 + 70} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 28}{(1 + 5) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{3140} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{(3 - 1) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 2) \times 8}{(3 + 1) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{9734} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{9 \times 7 + 3 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{43175} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{(4 + (3 \times 17)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{6 - 2 + 8}{(4 \times 3 - 1) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{54793} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{5 - (4 \times (7 - 93))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{71435} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{7 \times ((1 + 4 \times 3) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 2 + 8}{7 \times ((1 + 4^3) \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{109743} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{109 \times 7 - 4^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{149307} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{14 + 930 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{170345} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{((1 + 70) \times 3 + 4) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{431750} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 8}{(4 + 3 \times 17) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6 - 2 + 8}{(4 \times 3 - 1) \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{714350} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 + 8}{7 \times (1 + 4^3) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{6^2 + 8}{7 \times (143 \times 50)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{628}{753914} &:= \frac{6^2 + 8}{7 \times 539 \times 14} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 28}{7^5 \times (3 + 9 \times 14)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 629

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{814} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{8 + 14} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{1480} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(1 + 4) \times (8 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{1850} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{1^8 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{3145} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 9}{3 \times (1^4 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(3 + 14) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{6^2 - 9}{3 \times (1 \times 45)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 29}{(31 + 4) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 2) \times 9}{(3 + 1) \times 45} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{4107} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{4 + 107} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{13875} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(13 - 8) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{14578} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{1 \times (4 + (5 \times 78))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{14875} &:= \frac{6 + (2^9)}{14 \times 875} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{31450} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 9}{3 \times (1^4 \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(3 + 14) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{6^2 - 9}{3 \times (1 \times 450)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 29}{(31 + 4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 2) \times 9}{(3 + 1) \times 450} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{31857} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{3 + (1 + 857)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{37851} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{((3 - 7 + 8)^5) - 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{74851} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 9}{7 \times ((4 \times (8 + 5)) - 1)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 2) \times 9}{7 \times ((4 + 8) \times 51)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{7548} &:= \frac{6 + 29}{7 \times (5 \times (4 + 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{103785} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 - 9}{((10 + 3) \times 7 + 8) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{138750} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(13 - 8) \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{148750} &:= \frac{6 + (2^9)}{14 \times 8750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{185037} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{1 + 8 \times 5^{-03+7}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{629}{318570} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{3 \times (1 + 8 \times 5) \times 70} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 630

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{784} &:= \frac{6 \times 30}{7 \times 8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{12985} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 0}{1 + ((2 + 9 \times 8) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{187425} &:= \frac{6 \times 30}{18 \times 7 \times 425} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{945} &:= \frac{6 + 30}{9 + 45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{14875} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 0}{(1 + ((4 + 8) \times 7)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{294175} &:= \frac{6^3 + 0}{2 \times (9 + (4 - 1) \times 7^5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{1785} &:= \frac{6 + 30}{17 + 85} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{59472} &:= \frac{6 \times 30}{59 \times (4 \times 72)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{294875} &:= \frac{6 + 30}{2 + 9 + 4 \times 8 + 7^5} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 0}{1 \times (7 \times 8 - 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{91854} &:= \frac{6 \times 30}{(9^{1+8-5}) \times 4} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{1925} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 0}{1 \times ((9 + 2) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{94752} &:= \frac{6 \times 30}{9 \times (4 \times 752)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{630}{8295} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 0}{(8 \times 29) + 5} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 631

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{631}{5048} &:= \frac{63 + 1}{504 + 8} & &:= \frac{6 - 3 + 1}{(4^2) \times (9 + 08)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{631}{258079} &:= \frac{6 + 3 \times 1}{(2 + 5 \times 80 + 7) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 3 \times 1}{(5 + 04) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{631}{54897} &:= \frac{6 - 3 \times 1}{5 + (4 \times (8^9 - 7))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{631}{280795} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 1}{(2 + 80 + 7) \times 95} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (3 + 1)}{(50 \times 4) - 8} & &:= \frac{6 + 3 - 1}{5^4 + (8 + 9 \times 7)} & &:= \frac{6 + 3 \times 1}{(2 + 80 + 7) \times 9 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{63 - 1}{504 - 8} & &:= \frac{6^{3-1}}{5^{4-8+9} + 7} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{631}{42908} &:= \frac{6 - 3 - 1}{4 \times (2 \times (9 + 08))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{631}{75089} &:= \frac{6 - 3 \times 1}{7 \times (50 - 8 + 9)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 632

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{948} &:= \frac{6 + 32}{9 + 48} & &:= \frac{6 + 3 \times 2}{(7 + 5) \times (8 + 4)} & &:= \frac{6 \times (3 + 2)}{75 \times (8 + 40)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 32}{9 \times 4 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{9480} &:= \frac{6 \times 32}{9 \times (4 \times 80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{95748} &:= \frac{6 \times (3 - 2)}{957 - 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{1580} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 2}{1 \times (5 \times 8 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{17459} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 2}{1 + (7 \times (4 + 59))} & &:= \frac{6 + 32}{9 + 5748} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 32}{15 + 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{17854} &:= \frac{6 + 3 \times 2}{1 \times ((7^8 - 5) - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{179804} &:= \frac{(6 + 3) \times 2}{1 + (7 + 9) \times 80 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 32}{(1 + 5) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{59408} &:= \frac{6 - 3 + 2}{5 \times (94 + 0 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{190548} &:= \frac{6 \times (3 - 2)}{1 + 90 \times 5 \times 4 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{7584} &:= \frac{6 - 3 - 2}{((7 - 5) \times 8) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{632}{75840} &:= \frac{(6 - 3)^2}{((7 \times 5) - 8) \times 40} & & \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 3)^2}{((7 \times 5) - 8) \times 4} & &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{75 \times (8 \times (4 + 0))} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 633

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{634}{951} := \frac{(6+3) \times 4}{9 \times (5+1)}$$

$$:= \frac{6+34}{9+51}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{634}{1902} := \frac{6-3+4}{19+02}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{634}{5072} := \frac{6+3 \times 4}{(5+07)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{634}{9510} := \frac{6-3+4}{95+10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{634}{150892} := \frac{(6-3) \times 4}{(1+50) \times 8 \times (9-2)}$$

● Numerator 635

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{635}{1270} := \frac{6+3-5}{1^2+7+0}$$

$$:= \frac{6+3+5}{1+(27+0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6+35}{12+70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{635}{2794} := \frac{(6-3) \times 5}{2+((7+9) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{635}{9271} := \frac{(6+3) \times 5}{9 \times (2+71)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{635}{27940} := \frac{(6-3) \times 5}{2+(7 \times (94+0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{635}{87249} := \frac{(6-3) \times 5}{(((8+7)^2)+4) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{635}{109728} := \frac{(6+3) \times 5}{1 \times 0972 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{635}{198247} := \frac{6 \times 35}{19+(8 \times 2)^4+7}$$

● Numerator 637

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{819} := \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{8+19}$$

$$:= \frac{63-7}{8 \times (1 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{(8+1) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{63+7}{81+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{910} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{9 \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{1820} := \frac{63-7}{1 \times (8 \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{(1+8) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 \times 7)}{18 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{2184} := \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{2 \times ((1+8) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{2548} := \frac{6+3-7}{(2-5+4) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{6+3+7}{2+(54+8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{(2+5) \times (4+8)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 3+7}{(2 \times 54)-8}$$

$$:= \frac{6+(3 \times 7)}{(25 \times 4)+8}$$

$$:= \frac{63-7}{(2^5-4) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 3-7}{2^5+4+8}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 \times 7)}{(2^{5+4})-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{4095} := \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{40+95}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{5824} := \frac{63+7}{5 \times (8 \times 2^4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{8190} := \frac{63-7}{8 \times (1 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{(8+1) \times 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{21840} := \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{2 \times ((1+8) \times 40)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{25480} := \frac{6+3-7}{(2-5+4) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{2 \times (5 \times (4+80))}$$

$$:= \frac{63-7}{(2^5-4) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{58240} := \frac{63+7}{((5 \times 8)^2) \times (4+0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{59241} := \frac{6-3+7}{5+(924+1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{125489} := \frac{6+3-7}{1+2^5 \times (4+8)+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{129584} := \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{12 \times (9 \times 5 \times 8-4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{149058} := \frac{6 \times 3+7}{(1+4) \times 90 \times (5+8)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{1 + 4905 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{637}{194285} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 7}{(1+9) \times 42 \times 8 - 5} &:= \frac{6+3-7}{(1+9+4 \times 28) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{6+3-7}{1 \times 4 \times 9 \times (05+8)} & &:= \frac{(6-3) \times 7}{(1+(9-4) \times 2^8) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{63+7}{14 \times 90 \times (5+8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 638

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{957} &:= \frac{6+38}{9+57} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{5742} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{57+42} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{57942} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{57+942} \\
 &:= \frac{(6+3) \times 8}{9 \times (5+7)} & &:= \frac{6+3+8}{5+(74 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{71920} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{(71-9) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{9570} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{95+70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{7105} &:= \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{7 \times 105} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{179452} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{17 \times (9 \times 4 \times 5 + 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{1450} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{(1+4) \times (5+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{7192} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{(71-9) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{190472} &:= \frac{6+38}{(1 \times 9^4 + 7) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{1972} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{(1+9+7) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{19024} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{(1+(9^0)) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{290145} &:= \frac{6+38}{2 \times ((9+01)^4 + 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{2175} &:= \frac{6+38}{2 \times (1 \times 75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{19720} &:= \frac{6-3+8}{(1+9+7) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{291450} &:= \frac{6+38}{2 \times ((9+1)^4 + 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(2+1) \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{21750} &:= \frac{6+38}{2 \times (1 \times 750)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{5104} &:= \frac{6+3-8}{5-(1-04)} & &:= \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(2+1) \times 750}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 639

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{781} &:= \frac{6+39}{7 \times 8 - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{1420} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{1^4 \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{12780} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{12 \times (7+8+0)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+81} & &:= \frac{6+39}{(1+4) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{14058} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{140+58} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{852} &:= \frac{6+3+9}{8 \times (5-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{1704} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{(-1+7) \times 04} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{21087} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{210+87} \\
 &:= \frac{6+39}{8+52} & &:= \frac{6-3+9}{(1+7+0) \times 4} & &:= \frac{6+3 \times 9}{2+1087} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{1278} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{1+(2+7+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{2485} &:= \frac{6+3+9}{(2+4+8) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{24708} &:= \frac{6-3+9}{2+(470-8)} \\
 &:= \frac{6+3+9}{1+(27+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{2840} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{(2+8) \times (4+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{24850} &:= \frac{6+3+9}{(2+4+8) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{6+39}{12+78} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{25418} &:= \frac{(6-3) \times 9}{(2 \times 541) - 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{27548} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{2 + ((7 \times 54) + 8)} & := \frac{6 + 3 \times 9}{1 + 5 + (8^4 - 7) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{485072} &:= \frac{(6 + 3) \times 9}{(4 + 850) \times 72} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{70148} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{(70 \times 14) + 8} & := \frac{6 + 3 + 9}{1 \times (58 + 4) \times 72} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{158472} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 - 9}{15 + 8 + 47^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{639}{170542} &:= \frac{6 + 3 + 9}{1 + 7^{0 \times 5 + 4} \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 640

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{832} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{8 + 3 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{18792} &:= \frac{6 \times 40}{1 \times (87 \times 9^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{139872} &:= \frac{6 \times 40}{1 + 3^9 + 8^{7-2}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{1728} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{17 + 2 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{31872} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{(((3 - 1)^8) - 7) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{319872} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{(3 + 1 + 98) \times 7^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{1792} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{17 + 9 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{38592} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{3 + (8 + 592)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{8512} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{8 + (5^{1+2})} & \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{38912} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{38 \times ((9 - 1) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{640}{9152} &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 0}{91 + 52} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 641

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{641}{3205} &:= \frac{6 - 4 - 1}{3 + (2 - (0 \times 5))} & := \frac{(6 \times 4) - 1}{(3 + 20) \times 5} & := \frac{6 + 4 + 1}{5 \times 8 + 972} \\ &:= \frac{6 - 4 \times 1}{3 + (2 + 05)} & := \frac{64 - 1}{320 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{641}{98073} &:= \frac{6 + 4 - 1}{9 \times (80 + 73)} \\ &:= \frac{64 + 1}{320 + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{641}{58972} &:= \frac{6 - 4 - 1}{5 - (8 - (97 - 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{641}{293578} &:= \frac{6 - 4 - 1}{2^9 - 3 + 5 - 7 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 4 - 1}{3 \times (20 - 5)} & := \frac{6 - 4 \times 1}{((5 \times (8 + 9)) + 7) \times 2} & := \frac{6 - 4 + 1}{(2 + 9)^3 + 5 \times 7 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 4 + 1}{(3 \times 20) - 5} & := \frac{6 + 4 \times 1}{5 \times (8 \times (9 + 7 \times 2))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 642

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{642}{10593} &:= \frac{6 - 4 + 2}{10 + (59 - 3)} & := \frac{6^{4-2}}{1 + 0593} & \blacktriangleright \frac{642}{198057} &:= \frac{6 - 4 + 2}{1 + 9 \times (80 + 57)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 4 - 2}{105 + 9 \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{642}{15087} &:= \frac{6 - 4 + 2}{150 - (8 \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (4 - 2)}{105 + 93} & \blacktriangleright \frac{642}{57138} &:= \frac{6 - 4 + 2}{5 + ((7^{1 \times 3}) + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 643

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{643}{29578} &:= \frac{6-4+3}{((29+5) \times 7) - 8} && := \frac{(6+4) \times 3}{(2+08) \times 975} \\ &:= \frac{(6-4)^3}{(2+(9+5 \times 7)) \times 8} && := \frac{6 \times (4-3)}{2 \times (0 \times 8 + 975)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{643}{208975} &:= \frac{(6 \times 4) - 3}{(2+089) \times 75} && \blacktriangleright \frac{643}{295780} := \frac{(6-4)^3}{(2+9+5 \times 7) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 645

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{1032} &:= \frac{6+4-5}{(1+03) \times 2} && := \frac{6+4+5}{(8-1) \times 27} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{71982} := \frac{6+4-5}{(7 \times ((1+9) \times 8)) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{(6-4) \times 5}{(1+03)^2} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{8729} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 5}{8 \times (7 \times 29)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{81270} := \frac{6+4-5}{(8+1^2) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{1290} &:= \frac{6+4-5}{1^2+9+0} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{13029} := \frac{6+4-5}{130-29} && := \frac{6-4+5}{812+70} \\ &:= \frac{6+4+5}{1+(29+0)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{13287} := \frac{6+4-5}{((1+3)^2)+87} && := \frac{(6-4) \times 5}{(8+1) \times (2 \times 70)} \\ &:= \frac{6+45}{12+90} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{17028} := \frac{6+4-5}{1 \times ((70 \times 2) - 8)} && := \frac{6+4+5}{(8-1) \times 270} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (4+5)}{12 \times (9+0)} && := \frac{(6-4) \times 5}{1+(7-(0-(2^8)))} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{87290} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 5}{8 \times (7 \times 290)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{1720} &:= \frac{6 \times 45}{1 \times 720} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{17802} := \frac{6+4-5}{(17 \times (8+0)) + 2} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{107328} := \frac{(6-4) \times 5}{(10 \times 7 \times 3 - 2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{2193} &:= \frac{6+4-5}{(2 \times (1+9)) - 3} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{23908} := \frac{6+4+5}{2 \times ((3 \times 90) + 8)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{127839} := \frac{6+4-5}{1+(27+83) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{2709} &:= \frac{6+4+5}{2+(70-9)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{31089} := \frac{6+4+5}{3+(10 \times 8 \times 9)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{178923} := \frac{6+4-5}{1 \times 7 \times 8 + (9+2)^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{3870} &:= \frac{6+4+5}{3+(87+0)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{37281} := \frac{(6-4) \times 5}{3+((72 \times 8) - 1)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{198273} := \frac{6+4-5}{19 \times 82 - 7 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{8127} &:= \frac{6+4-5}{(8+1^2) \times 7} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{39087} := \frac{6+4-5}{390-87} && \\ &:= \frac{(6-4) \times 5}{(8+1) \times 2 \times 7} && \blacktriangleright \frac{645}{71208} := \frac{6+4-5}{(71-2+0) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 647

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{647}{5823} &:= \frac{6+4-7}{(5 \times (8-2)) - 3} && := \frac{(6-4) \times 7}{(5 \times 8 + 2) \times 3} && := \frac{(6-4)^7}{((1+03)^5) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{6-4+7}{58+23} && \blacktriangleright \frac{647}{10352} := \frac{6-4+7}{(10-3+5)^2} && := \frac{6 \times 4 + 7}{10 + (3^5 \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{647}{58230} &:= \frac{6+4-7}{5 \times 8 + 230} \\ &:= \frac{(6-4) \times 7}{(5 \times 8 + 2) \times 30} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{647}{93815} &:= \frac{6+4-7}{(9-(3-81)) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{647}{315089} &:= \frac{6+4-7}{31 \times 50 - 89} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 648

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{648}{729} &:= \frac{(6-4) \times 8}{7+2+9} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{7+29} \\ &:= \frac{64-8}{72-9} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{72+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{792} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{7+9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{972} := \frac{6+48}{9+72}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{1092} := \frac{6+48}{10+9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{1350} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{1593} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times (59 \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{7290} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{(7+2) \times 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{9153} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(91 \times 5) - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{9315} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(93 - 1) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{10935} := \frac{64-8}{10+935}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+4) \times 8}{10 \times (9 \times 3 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{15732} := \frac{6+4+8}{1-(5-((7 \times 3)^2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{15930} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times (59 \times 30)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{17253} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{((17^2) - 5) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{17352} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{(1+7) \times (3^5 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{19035} := \frac{(6-4) \times 8}{(1+(90+3)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{27135} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(271 - 3) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{31752} := \frac{6+4-8}{((3+17) \times 5) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{64-8}{((3-1) \times 7)^{5-2}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{35721} := \frac{(6-4) \times 8}{(35+7) \times 21}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(35+7)^2 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{52731} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 8}{5^{2+7-3} - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{73152} := \frac{6+4+8}{7+((3 \times 15)^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{93150} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(93 - 1) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{132795} := \frac{6 \times 48}{1-3-27+9^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{137052} := \frac{6+4-8}{1+370+52}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{159327} := \frac{(6+4) \times 8}{1-5-9+3^{2+7}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{159732} := \frac{(6-4) \times 8}{(1+5) \times 9 \times 73+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{172530} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(17^2 - 5) \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{175932} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(1-7) \times (5-9^3) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-4) \times 8}{(1-7) \times (5-9 \times 3^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{192375} := \frac{(6+4) \times 8}{(1+9) \times 2375}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 9 \times 2375}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{195372} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(1 \times 9 + 5^3) \times 72}$$

$$:= \frac{6+4-8}{1 \times 9 \times (53+7 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{271350} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(271 - 3) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{317520} := \frac{6-4+8}{((3-1) \times 7 \times 5)^2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{357210} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(35+7)^2 \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-4) \times 8}{(35+7) \times 210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{397512} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{(3^9 + 7^{5-1}) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{739125} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{73 \times (9+1)^2 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+4) \times 8}{(7+3) \times 9125}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{73 \times 9 \times 125}$$

● Numerator 649

$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{1357} := \frac{6-4+9}{1+(3 \times 5+7)}$	$:= \frac{(6-4)^9}{1 \times (((7+5) \times 2)^3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{132750} := \frac{6 \times 4+9}{1 \times 3^2 \times 750}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{2183} := \frac{6+49}{2+183}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 4 \times 9}{(1+(7+5 \times 2))^3}$	$:= \frac{6-4+9}{(1^3+2) \times 750}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{3127} := \frac{6 \times 4+9}{31+(2^7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{25370} := \frac{6-4+9}{2 \times (5+(3 \times 70))}$	$:= \frac{6+49}{(1+32 \times 7) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{5782} := \frac{6-4+9}{(57-8) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{53218} := \frac{6+4-9}{53+(21+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{175230} := \frac{6+4-9}{(1+7-5)^2 \times 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{8732} := \frac{6+49}{8+732}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{57820} := \frac{6-4+9}{5 \times (7 \times (8+20))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{308275} := \frac{(6-4) \times 9}{30 \times (8^2-7) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{10325} := \frac{6-4+9}{(10-3) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{83072} := \frac{6+4-9}{8 \times (30-(7 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{6+4-9}{30+(82+7) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{6 \times 4+9}{(103+2) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{85137} := \frac{6-4+9}{(8 \times 5-1) \times 37}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{387512} := \frac{6 \times 4+9}{(3^8+7) \times (5-1 \times 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{13275} := \frac{6-4+9}{(13+2)^{7-5}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{102837} := \frac{6-4+9}{(1+02) \times 83 \times 7}$	$:= \frac{6+49}{(3^8+7) \times 5 \times 1^2}$
$:= \frac{6 \times 4+9}{1 \times (3^2 \times 75)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{105728} := \frac{6-4+9}{10^5 \times 7 \times 2^8}$	
$:= \frac{6+49}{(1+(32 \times 7)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{6+49}{1 \times 05 \times 7 \times 2^8}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{17523} := \frac{6+4-9}{((1^75)+2)^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{127853} := \frac{6+4-9}{(1 \times 2+7) \times 8+5^3}$	

• Numerator 650

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{650}{1248} := \frac{6 \times 50}{12 \times 48}$$

• Numerator 651

$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{924} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{(9+2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{9240} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{(9+2) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{6 \times (5+1)}{((24 \times 7)+3) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{2079} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{20+79}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{20398} := \frac{6+5+1}{(20+3 \times 9) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{(2+(4 \times 7)) \times 38}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{2387} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{23+87}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{20 \times (39+8)}$	$:= \frac{6 \times 5+1}{(24+7) \times 38}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{3402} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{(3^4+0) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{23478} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{2 \times ((3^4 \times 7)-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{34209} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{(3^4 \times 20)+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{3472} := \frac{6^{5+1}}{(3 \times 4)^{7-2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{24738} := \frac{6-5 \times 1}{2+(4+((7-3) \times 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{42987} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{(4 \times (2^9))-8+7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{651}{4872} := \frac{6 \times 5+1}{4 \times ((8 \times 7)+2)}$		

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{651}{47082} &:= \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(4 \times (70 \times 8)) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{651}{247380} &:= \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(24 + 7) \times 380} & := \frac{6 \times (5 + 1)}{(24 \times 7 + 3) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{651}{80724} &:= \frac{6 - 5 \times 1}{(80 - 7^2) \times 4} & & := \frac{6 - 5 \times 1}{(2 \times 4 - 7) \times 380} & := \frac{6 + 5 - 1}{(2 + 473) \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{6 - (5 - 1)}{8 \times (0 + (7 + 24))} & & := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{(2 + 4 \times 7) \times 380} & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 652

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{978} &:= \frac{6 + 5 \times 2}{9 + 7 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{1793} &:= \frac{6 + 5 \times 2}{17 + 9 \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{149308} &:= \frac{6 + 5 + 2}{1 + 4 \times 93 \times 08} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 52}{9 + 78} & & := \frac{6 \times 5 - 2}{1 + (79 - 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{190384} &:= \frac{(6 - 5)^2}{(1 - 9 \times (0 \times 3 - 8)) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{1304} &:= \frac{(6 - 5)^2}{1 - (3 - 04)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{9780} &:= \frac{6 + 5 - 2}{9 \times (7 + 8 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{307418} &:= \frac{6 + 5 \times 2}{(30 - 7) \times 41 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 5) \times 2}{1 + (3 + 0 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{31948} &:= \frac{6 - 5 + 2}{3 \times (1^9 + 48)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{319480} &:= \frac{6 - 5 + 2}{3 \times (1 + 9 + 480)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 5 + 2}{1 \times (30 - 4)} & & := \frac{6 + 5 \times 2}{(3 + (1 + 94)) \times 8} & & := \frac{6 + 5 \times 2}{(3 + 1 + 94) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 5 \times 2}{1 \times (30 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{37490} &:= \frac{(6 - 5) \times 2}{3 \times 7 + (4 + 90)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{387940} &:= \frac{(6 - 5)^2}{3 + 8 \times 79 - 40} \\ &:= \frac{65 - 2}{130 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{40913} &:= \frac{6 + 5 \times 2}{4 - (0 - ((9 + 1)^3))} & & \\ &:= \frac{65 + 2}{130 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{652}{71394} &:= \frac{6 \times 5 \times 2}{7 - (1 - (3 + 9^4))} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 653

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{653}{9142} &:= \frac{(6 - 5)^3}{9 - (1 - 4 - 2)} & & := \frac{(6 - 5) \times 3}{1 - (2 \times (4 \times (-07)))} & & := \frac{6^{5-3}}{((4 - 1) \times (7 + 9))^2} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 5) \times 3}{((9 + 1) \times 4) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{653}{41792} &:= \frac{(6 - 5)^3}{4 - (1 - ((7 \times 9) - 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{653}{91420} &:= \frac{(6 - 5) \times 3}{(9 + 1) \times (42 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 5 + 3}{(9 + (1 + 4))^2} & & := \frac{6 - 5 + 3}{4 \times ((17 - 9)^2)} & & := \frac{6 \times 5 - 3}{9 \times (1 \times 420)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 5 - 3}{9 \times (1 \times 42)} & & := \frac{6 + 5 - 3}{4 \times ((1 + 7 \times 9) \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{653}{219408} &:= \frac{6 \times 5 - 3}{21 \times 9 \times (40 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{653}{12407} &:= \frac{(6 - 5)^3}{((1 + 2) \times (4 + 0)) + 7} & & := \frac{6 \times (5 - 3)}{(4 - 1) \times ((7 + 9)^2)} & & := \frac{(6 - 5) \times 3}{(2 + 19) \times (40 + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(6-5)^3}{(2 \times 19 + 4) \times 08} \\ &:= \frac{65 \times 3}{2 \times (1-9) + 4^{08}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{653}{417920} &:= \frac{(6-5)^3}{4 \times (1+79) \times 2 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{6+5-3}{4 \times (1+7 \times 9) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 654

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{654}{872} &:= \frac{6+54}{8+72} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{8 \times (7+2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{654}{981} &:= \frac{6+54}{9+81} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{9 \times (8+1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{654}{1308} &:= \frac{(6-5) \times 4}{(1^{30}) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{1+(3+08)} \\ &:= \frac{65+4}{130+8} \\ &:= \frac{65-4}{130-8} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 5 \times 4}{1 \times (30 \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{2180} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{2+18+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{2398} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{2+3+9+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{3270} := \frac{6-5+4}{32-7+0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{3+(27+0)} \\ &:= \frac{6+5-4}{(3+2) \times (7+0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{6+5+4}{3+(2+70)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{654}{8720} &:= \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{8+(72+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{654}{9810} &:= \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{9+(81+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{654}{13298} &:= \frac{6+5+4}{((1+32) \times 9) + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{654}{23871} &:= \frac{(6-5) \times 4}{2+(3 \times (8 \times (7-1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{28013} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{2^8 + 01^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{29103} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{(2-91) \times (-03)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{32918} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{3+(291+8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{73902} := \frac{(6-5)^4}{(7 \times 3) + (90+2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{83712} := \frac{(6-5)^4}{8 \times ((3 \times (7-1)) - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{89271} := \frac{(6-5) \times 4}{(89+2) \times (7-1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{108237} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{(1 \times 08 + 2)^3 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{6+54}{10 \times ((8+2)^3 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{109872} := \frac{(6-5)^4}{10+(9 \times 8+7) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{6-5+4}{10 \times (98-7 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{1 \times 09 \times 8 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{6+54}{10 \times 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{182793} := \frac{(6-5) \times 4}{1+8 \times 2^7 + 93}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{278931} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{2^7 \times (8+9+3) - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{371908} := \frac{6 \times (5-4)}{(37+1) \times 90 - 8}$$

● Numerator 657

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{657}{803} := \frac{6+57}{80-3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{657}{2409} := \frac{6+57}{240-9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{657}{3942} := \frac{(6-5)^7}{3+(9-4-2)}$$

$$:= \frac{6+5-7}{(3+9) \times (4-2)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (5+7)}{3 \times (9 \times (4^2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{657}{12483} := \frac{(6-5)^7}{1+(2 \times (4+(8-3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6+5-7}{1-(2 \times 4-83)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-5) \times 7}{((1+2^4) \times 8) - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{657}{24309} := \frac{(6-5)^7}{2-(4-(30+9))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{6 \times 5 - 7}{(2 \times 430) - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{34821} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{3 + (48 + 2 \times 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{124830} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{1 + 24 \times 8 - 3 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{134028} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{1 \times 3 \times (40 + 28)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{139284} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{1 + 3 \times 9^2 - 8 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{214839} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{2 + 1 + (4 + 8) \times 3 \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{219438} & := \frac{6 + 5 - 7}{(2 + 19) \times 4^3 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{238491} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{2 - 3 + (8 - 4) \times 91} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{239148} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{2^3 + 91 \times 4 - 8} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (5 + 7)}{2 \times 3 \times 91 \times 48} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 + 7}{2 - 3 + 9^{1 \times 4} - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{240389} & := \frac{6 + 5 + 7}{2 \times (40 - 3) \times 89} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{329814} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{3 + 2^9 - 8 - 1 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{348210} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{(3 + 48 + 2) \times 10} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{398142} & := \frac{(6-5) \times 7}{(3 + 98 \times 1) \times 42} \\
 & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{3 \times (98 - 1 + 4) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{657}{423108} & := \frac{(6-5)^7}{4 + 2^3 \times 10 \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 658

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{658}{1974} & := \frac{(6-5)^8}{1 - 9 + 7 + 4} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 - 8}{1 + (9 - 7) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{6 - 5 + 8}{1 \times 9 \times (7 - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 + 8}{19 \times (7 - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times 5 - 8}{1 - 9 + 74} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{658}{3290} & := \frac{6 + 5 - 8}{3 \times 2 + 9 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{6 - 5 + 8}{(3 + 2) \times 9 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 + 8}{3 + 2 + 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{658}{19740} & := \frac{(6-5)^8}{19 + 7 + 4 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{658}{123704} & := \frac{6 + 5 - 8}{1 \times 2^3 \times 70 + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{658}{130942} & := \frac{(6-5)^8}{1 \times 30 + (9 + 4)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{658}{147392} & := \frac{(6-5) \times 8}{1 \times 4^{7-3} \times (9 - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(6-5)^8}{1 + (4 + 7 \times 3) \times 9 - 2} \\
 & := \frac{6 - 5 + 8}{14 \times (7 \times 3 - 9)^2} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 \times 8}{14 \times (7 + (3 \times 9)^2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 + 8}{1 + 473 \times 9 - 2} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 - 8}{1 \times 4 \times 7 \times (3 + 9) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{65 + 8}{1 + 4^7 - 3 \times (9 + 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 659

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{659}{78421} & := \frac{(6-5)^9}{7 \times ((8 \times (4 - 2)) + 1)} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 - 9}{7 \times (8 \times 4 + 2 \times 1)} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 + 9}{(7^8 - 4) - 21} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{659}{130482} & := \frac{6 \times 5 - 9}{130 \times 4 \times 8 - 2} \\
 & := \frac{(6-5)^9}{130 + 4 + 8^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{659}{274803} & := \frac{6 + 5 - 9}{27 + (4 + 803)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{659}{308412} & := \frac{6 + 5 + 9}{30 \times 8 \times (41 - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 - 9}{3 \times 08 \times (41 - 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 671

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{671}{3294} &:= \frac{67-1}{3^2 \times (9 \times 4)} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+1)}{2^5 \times (49+8)} &:= \frac{6+7+1}{(2+3 \times 4 \times 8) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{671}{23485} &:= \frac{6+7-1}{2 \times ((34+8) \times 5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{671}{32940} &:= \frac{67-1}{3^2 \times (9 \times 40)} &:= \frac{6+7-1}{2 \times (34+8) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{6+7 \times 1}{(2 + ((3^4) + 8)) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{671}{34892} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 1}{(3 + (4 \times 8 - 9))^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{671}{458293} &:= \frac{6+7-1}{4^5 \times 8 - 2 + 9 - 3} \\ &:= \frac{6+7+1}{2 + (3 + 485)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{671}{59048} &:= \frac{67 \times 1}{5904 - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{671}{25498} &:= \frac{6+7+1}{(2+5) \times (4+9 \times 8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{671}{234850} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 1}{2 + (3^4 + 8) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 672

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{672}{3948} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 - 2}{(3^{9-4}) - 8} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 2}{((3^{1 \times 5}) - 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 2}{(3^{1 \times 5} - 8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{672}{31584} &:= \frac{6-7+2}{3 + (1 \times (5 \times 8 + 4))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{672}{91854} &:= \frac{6 \times 72}{9^{1^{85+4}}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{672}{315840} &:= \frac{6-7+2}{3 \times 158 - 4 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 673

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{673}{2019} &:= \frac{6+7-3}{20+1+9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{673}{24901} &:= \frac{6-7+3}{2 \times ((4 \times (9+0)) + 1)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{673}{91528} &:= \frac{6-7+3}{(9 + (1 \times (5^2))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (7+3)}{20 \times (1 \times 9)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{673}{49802} &:= \frac{6-7+3}{4 - (9 \times (8 \times (-02)))} &:= \frac{6+7-3}{(9 \times 152) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{67-3}{201-9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{673}{84125} &:= \frac{67-3}{((8 \times (4+1))^2) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{67+3}{201+9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 674

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{674}{5392} &:= \frac{6 \times (7-4)}{(5+3) \times 9 \times 2} &:= \frac{67-4}{(2 + (3^5)) \times (9+0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{674}{158390} &:= \frac{6-7+4}{15 \times (8+39) + 0} \\ &:= \frac{6+7+4}{(5^3) + 9 + 2} &:= \frac{6+7+4}{2 + (3+590)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{674}{218039} &:= \frac{6 \times (7-4)}{(2 \times (1+8))^{03} - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{674}{15839} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 + 4}{1 + (5 \times (8 \times 3 \times 9))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{674}{53920} &:= \frac{6+7-4}{5 \times ((3+9)^2 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{674}{23590} &:= \frac{6 \times (7-4)}{2 \times (35 \times (9+0))} &:= \frac{6 \times (7-4)}{(5+3) \times (9 \times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 675

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{675}{10932} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{(10 \times 9^3) - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{675}{184230} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{(1 \times 8^4 - 2) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{675}{18423} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{1 \times ((8^4 - 2) \times 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{675}{283419} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{(2 + 8^3 \times 41) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 678

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{2034} &:= \frac{6 - 7 + 8}{20 - 3 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{12543} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 - 8}{1^2 + (5^4 + 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{215943} &:= \frac{6 + 7 \times 8}{(2 + 1^5)^9 + 4^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{3051} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 - 8}{3 \times (0 + 51)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{91530} &:= \frac{6 - 7 + 8}{915 + 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{9153} &:= \frac{6 + 78}{9 \times (1 + 5^3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{120345} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 - 8}{(1203 + 4) \times 5} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{678}{132549} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 - 8}{13 \times 2^{5+4} - 9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 679

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{1358} &:= \frac{6 + 7 - 9}{(1^{35}) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{13580} &:= \frac{6 + 7 - 9}{(1^{35}) \times 80} & &:= \frac{6 - 7 + 9}{5 \times (4 \times (32 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{6 - 7 + 9}{1 \times (3 + 5 + 8)} & &:= \frac{6 - 7 + 9}{(1 + 3) \times (5 \times 8 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{132405} &:= \frac{6 - 7 + 9}{13 \times 24 \times 05} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 7 + 9}{1 + (3 + 5 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{31428} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 9}{3^{1+4+2} \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{314280} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 9}{3^{1+4+2} \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{5432} &:= \frac{6 + 7 - 9}{(5 - 4) \times 32} & \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{38024} &:= \frac{6 + 7 - 9}{(3 \times 80) - (2^4)} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{679}{54320} &:= \frac{6 + 7 - 9}{5 \times (4 + (3 \times 20))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 680

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{680}{1275} &:= \frac{6 \times 80}{12 \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{680}{139247} &:= \frac{6 \times 80}{(1 \times 3 - 9) \times (2 - 4^7)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 681

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{681}{2043} &:= \frac{68 - 1}{204 - 3} & &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 1}{2 - (0 - 43)} & &:= \frac{68 + 1}{340 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{68 + 1}{204 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{681}{3405} &:= \frac{68 - 1}{340 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{681}{7945} &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 1}{7 \times ((9 - 4) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{681}{42903} &:= \frac{6 \times 81}{42 \times (9^{03})} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 1}{(5 + ((2 \times 4)^3)) \times 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{681}{493725} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 \times 1}{4 \times (9 + 3) \times 725} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 1}{(4 + 290) \times 3} &\blacktriangleright \frac{681}{79450} &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 1}{7 \times ((9 - 4) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 1}{42 + 903} &\blacktriangleright \frac{681}{90573} &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 1}{(90 + 5) \times 7 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{681}{52437} &:= \frac{68 \times 1}{5243 - 7} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 682

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{682}{1395} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 2}{1 + (39 + 5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{1953} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 2}{1 + (9 + 53)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{19437} &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 2}{19 + 437} \\ &:= \frac{68 - 2}{1 \times (3 \times 9 \times 5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{3410} &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 2}{(3^4) - 1 + 0} &:= \frac{6 + 8^2}{(1 + 94) \times (3 \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 82}{(1 + 3) \times 9 \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{3751} &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 2}{37 + 51} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{30597} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 2}{((30 \times 5) - 9) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{682}{1457} &:= \frac{68 - 2}{1 + (4 \times 5 \times 7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{13950} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 2}{1^3 \times (9 \times 50)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{94705} &:= \frac{68 - 2}{(9 + 4) \times 705} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{682}{1705} &:= \frac{6 + 8 - 2}{(-1 + 7) \times 05} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{130975} &:= \frac{68 - 2}{1 \times (3 \times (9 \times 50))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{130975} &:= \frac{68 - 2}{13 \times 0975} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 2}{(1 + 7 + 0) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{14539} &:= \frac{6 + 82}{(1 + 3) \times (9 \times 50)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{149730} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 2}{(14 + 9) \times 7 \times 30} \\ &:= \frac{68 - 2}{170 - 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{14973} &:= \frac{6 + 82}{14 \times ((5^3) + 9)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{194370} &:= \frac{6 + 8^2}{(1 + 94) \times 3 \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 8^2}{170 + 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{682}{14973} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 2}{(14 + 9) \times 7 \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 683

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{683}{2049} &:= \frac{6 + 8 - 3}{20 + 4 + 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{683}{10245} &:= \frac{6 - 8 + 3}{(1 + (0 - 2 + 4)) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{683}{297105} &:= \frac{6 - 8 + 3}{((2 + 9) \times 7 + 10) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 8 + 3}{2 - (0 - 49)} &&:= \frac{6 + 8 - 3}{(10 \times 2^4) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{68 - 3}{204 - 9} &&:= \frac{6 + 8 + 3}{10 + 245} \\ &:= \frac{68 + 3}{204 + 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{683}{59421} &:= \frac{6 - 8 + 3}{5 + 9^{4-2} + 1} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 684

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{1539} &:= \frac{68-4}{(1+(5 \times 3)) \times 9} & := \frac{68-4}{(1+(5 \times 3)) \times 90} & := \frac{6+8-4}{(1+5 \times 93) \times (7-2)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{15+39} & := \frac{6+8-4}{((1+5)^3)+9+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{192375} := \frac{(6 \times 8)+4}{(192+3) \times 75} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times 8)+4}{1+((5^3)-9)} & := \frac{6+8+4}{15 \times (3 \times (9+0))} & := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{1 \times 9 \times 2 \times 375} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{153+9} & := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{1+(539+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{193572} := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{19^3+5-72} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times 84}{(1+5^3) \times 9} & := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(15+3) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{213750} := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{2 \times 1 \times 3750} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{2907} &:= \frac{6 \times 8-4}{(2 \times 90)+7} & := \frac{6 \times 84}{(1+5^3) \times 90} & := \frac{6+8-4}{(2-1-3+7)^5+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{3192} &:= \frac{6+8+4}{3+(1 \times 9^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{15732} := \frac{6+8-4}{1+(5+(7 \times 32))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{251370} := \frac{6-8+4}{(2 \times 51+3) \times 7+0} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{31+9^2} & := \frac{6+84}{(1+5) \times (7^3+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{312075} := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{(3+(1+2)^{07}) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{3591} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{35+91} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{15903} := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{(1+5) \times (90+3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{312759} := \frac{6 \times 8-4}{31 \times (2^7 \times 5+9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{5130} &:= \frac{6-8+4}{5 \times (1 \times (3+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{21375} := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{2 \times (1 \times 375)} & := \frac{(6+8) \times 4}{31 \times 2 \times 7 \times 59} \\
 &:= \frac{6+8+4}{5+130} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{35910} := \frac{6-8+4}{3 \times (5 \times 9-10)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{329175} := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{(329+1) \times 7 \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{(5+1) \times 30} & := \frac{6+8+4}{35+910} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{329517} := \frac{6 \times 8-4}{(32+9) \times 517} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{7125} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{7+((1+2)^5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{153729} := \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{(1+5 \times 37) \times 29} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{397512} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{3^9+7^{5-1^2}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{12597} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-4)}{1+((2+5) \times 9 \times 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{159372} := \frac{6-8+4}{1^5+93 \times (7-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{591372} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{5 \times 9^{1+3}+7^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{684}{15390} &:= \frac{6-8+4}{1+(5+(39+0))} & := \frac{6+8+4}{(1+5 \times 93) \times (7+2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 685

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{685}{1370} &:= \frac{6-8+5}{13-7+0} & := \frac{6+8+5}{2+(74+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{685}{49320} := \frac{6-8+5}{4 \times (9 \times (3 \times (2+0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{6+8+5}{1+(37+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{685}{4932} := \frac{(6^8) \times 5}{(4 \times 9)^{3+2}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{685}{2740} &:= \frac{6+8-5}{(2+7) \times (4+0)}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 687

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{2519} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{2^5 - (1+9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{30915} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{30 \times (9 \times 1^5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{295410} &:= \frac{6-8+7}{2^9 \times 5 - 410} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{4351} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{4 + (35-1)} & &:= \frac{6+8-7}{309+1+5} & &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{(2+(9-5)^4) \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{24503} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{2 + (4 \times (50+3))} & &:= \frac{6+8+7}{30+915} & \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{310295} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{(3 \times 10 + 2^9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{25419} &:= \frac{6+8-7}{(2 \times (5^4-1)) + 9} & &:= \frac{68-7}{3 \times (0+915)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{29541} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{2 + ((9-5)^4 \times 1)} & &:= \frac{6 \times (8+7)}{30 \times (9 \times 15)} & & \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{687}{43510} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-7)}{(43-5) \times 10} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 689

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{742} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 9}{7 \times (4+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{53742} &:= \frac{6+8-9}{5 \times (3 \times (7 \times 4 - 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{247351} &:= \frac{6+8-9}{(2^4 + 7^3) \times 5 \times 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{1325} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 9}{1 \times (3 \times 25)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{72345} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 \times 9}{7 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{723450} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 \times 9}{7 \times (2 \times 3)^4 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{3710} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 9}{3 \times (7 \times 10)} & &:= \frac{6 + (8 \times 9)}{7 \times (234 \times 5)} & &:= \frac{6+8 \times 9}{7 \times 234 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{13250} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 9}{1 \times (3 \times 250)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{72451} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 9}{7 - (2 - (4^{5+1}))} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{689}{217035} & & &:= \frac{6-8+9}{21 \times 7 \times 03 \times 5} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 690

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{782} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{7+8+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{13248} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{1 \times (3 \times (2 \times 48))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{23184} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{2 \times (3 \times (1 \times 84))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{874} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{8+7+4} & &:= \frac{6 \times 90}{((1+3+2)^4) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{25438} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{2+(543+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{2438} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{2+(43+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{14375} &:= \frac{6 \times (9+0)}{(1+4) \times (3 \times 75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{35742} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{35+742} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{3542} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{35+42} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{14582} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{1-(4-(5 \times (8^2)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{37812} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{3+(7+812)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{5382} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{53+8^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{15732} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{1 \times (57 \times 3 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{127834} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{1 \times 2783-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{12834} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{1 \times (283-4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{21735} &:= \frac{6 \times (9+0)}{(2-1) \times (7 \times 3^5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{185472} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{(1+8+5) \times 4 \times 72} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{217534} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{21 \times 75 \times 3+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{690}{431572} &:= \frac{6+9+0}{4+3 \times (1+5^{7-2})} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 691

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{691}{2073} &:= \frac{69-1}{207-3} &:= \frac{69+1}{483+7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{691}{53207} &:= \frac{69 \times 1}{5320-7} \\ &:= \frac{69+1}{207+3} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 1}{(4+8+3) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{6+9-1}{2 \times (0+7 \times 3)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{691}{48370} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 1}{(4+8+3) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{691}{4837} &:= \frac{69-1}{483-7} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 692

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{692}{1384} &:= \frac{6+9+2}{1 \times (38-4)} &:= \frac{69-2}{138-4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{692}{357418} &:= \frac{6+92}{(3+5+7)^4 \times 1-8} \\ &:= \frac{6+9 \times 2}{(1+3+8) \times 4} &:= \frac{69+2}{138+4} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (9-2)}{(13+8) \times 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{692}{13840} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 2}{(1+3+8) \times 40} \\ & & &:= \frac{6 \times (9-2)}{(13+8) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 693

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{847} &:= \frac{(6+9) \times 3}{8+47} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{1785} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{17 \times 85} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{5082} &:= \frac{6+9+3}{50+82} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (9+3)}{8 \times (4+7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{2415} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(24-1) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{7854} &:= \frac{6+9+3}{(7 \times 8-5) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{1078} &:= \frac{6 \times (9-3)}{1 \times (0+(7 \times 8))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{2541} &:= \frac{6+9+3}{25+41} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{8547} &:= \frac{6+9-3}{8+(5 \times (4 \times 7))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{1428} &:= \frac{69-3}{(1+4^2) \times 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{4158} &:= \frac{6+9-3}{(4+1 \times 5) \times 8} & &:= \frac{(6+9) \times 3}{8+547} \\ &:= \frac{6+93}{14^2+8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{4725} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(47-2) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{10584} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+05) \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{1470} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^4 \times 70} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{4872} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{4 \times ((8 \times 7)+2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{10752} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+07)^{5-2}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{1540} &:= \frac{6+9+3}{1^5 \times 40} & &:= \frac{6+93}{4 \times (87 \times 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{14280} &:= \frac{69-3}{(1+4^2) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{15708} &:= \frac{6+9-3}{(1-(5 \times 7)) \times (-08)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{47250} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(47-2) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{172480} &:= \frac{6 \times (9-3)}{1 \times 7 \times 2^4 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{17248} &:= \frac{6+9+3}{1 \times (7 \times (2 \times 4 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{48720} &:= \frac{6+93}{4 \times (87 \times 20)} & &:= \frac{6+9+3}{1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 4 \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (9-3)}{1 \times (7 \times (2^4 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{51408} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{51 \times (40+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{178024} &:= \frac{6 \times (9+3)}{(17 \times 8)^{-02+4}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{17850} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^7 \times 850} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{78540} &:= \frac{6+9+3}{(7 \times 8-5) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{187425} &:= \frac{6+93}{(1+8) \times (7 \times 425)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{24150} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(24-1) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{85470} &:= \frac{6 \times (9-3)}{8 \times (5^4-70)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{470512} &:= \frac{6+93}{4 \times 7^{05}-1-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{41580} &:= \frac{6+9-3}{(4+1 \times 5) \times 80} & &:= \frac{(6 \times 9)-3}{85 \times (4+70)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{724185} &:= \frac{6+9+3}{(7+2) \times 418 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{47082} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(4 \times (70 \times 8)) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{125874} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+2 \times 5 \times 8) \times 74} & & \\ &:= \frac{69-3}{4+(70 \times (8^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{693}{142758} &:= \frac{6+9-3}{(1+4 \times (2+75)) \times 8} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 694

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{694}{1735} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 4}{1 \times (7 \times 3 \times 5)} & &:= \frac{6+9 \times 4}{1 \times (7 \times 3 \times 50)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{694}{375801} &:= \frac{6+9 \times 4}{3 \times (7580+1)} \\ &:= \frac{6+94}{1 \times (7+(3^5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{694}{38170} &:= \frac{6-9+4}{38+(17+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{694}{385170} &:= \frac{6-9+4}{38+517+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{694}{17350} &:= \frac{6-9+4}{(1+7-3) \times (5+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{694}{213058} &:= \frac{6-9+4}{21 \times 3 \times 05-8} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{694}{317852} &:= \frac{6-9+4}{(3 \times 1 \times 78-5) \times 2} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 695

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{695}{2780} &:= \frac{6+9+5}{2+(78+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{695}{23074} &:= \frac{6+9-5}{2+(30 \times (7+4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{695}{81732} &:= \frac{6+9-5}{8 \times (1+(73 \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{695}{4170} &:= \frac{6-9+5}{4+(1+7+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{695}{41283} &:= \frac{6+9-5}{(41 \times 2)+(8^3)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 697

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{697}{3485} := \frac{6-9+7}{3+(4+8+5)} \quad := \frac{6+9-7}{3+(4 \times 8+5)} \quad := \frac{6^{9-7}}{3 \times ((4+8) \times 5)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{6 \times (9 + 7)}{3 \times (4 \times 8 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{697}{4182} & := \frac{6 - 9 + 7}{4 \times (1 \times (8 - 2))} \\ & := \frac{6 + 9 - 7}{(4 - 1) \times (8 \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (9 - 7)}{4 \times ((1 + 8) \times 2)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{6 \times (9 + 7)}{((4 - 1) \times 8)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{697}{34850} & := \frac{6 - 9 + 7}{(3 \times 4 - 8) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{6^{9-7}}{3 \times ((4 + 8) \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (9 + 7)}{3 \times (4 \times 8 \times 50)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{697}{41820} & := \frac{6 - 9 + 7}{(4 + 1 \times 8) \times 20} \\ & := \frac{6 + 9 - 7}{(4 - 1) \times (8 \times 20)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (9 - 7)}{4 \times ((1 + 8) \times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 698

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{698}{1745} & := \frac{6 \times (9 - 8)}{1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{698}{4537} & := \frac{6 \times (9 - 8)}{(4 \times (5 + 3)) + 7} \\ & := \frac{6 + 9 \times 8}{(4 \times (5^3)) + 7} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{698}{17450} & := \frac{6 - 9 + 8}{1 + (74 + 50)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (9 - 8)}{1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 50)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{698}{30712} & := \frac{6 + 9 - 8}{307 + 1^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{698}{45370} & := \frac{6 \times (9 - 8)}{4 \times 5 + 370} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{698}{305724} & := \frac{6 - 9 + 8}{30 \times (5 + 72 - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{698}{312704} & := \frac{6 - 9 + 8}{(3 + 1) \times 2 \times 70 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 701

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{701}{36452} & := \frac{70 \times 1}{364 \times 5 \times 2} \\ & := \frac{7 + 01}{364 + 52} \\ & := \frac{7^{01}}{3 + (((6 \times 4) - 5)^2)} \\ & := \frac{7 - 01}{3 \times ((6 - 4) \times 52)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{7 - 01}{483 - 69} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{701}{62389} & := \frac{7 + 01}{623 + 89} \\ & := \frac{7^{01}}{(6 - 2 + 3) \times 89} \\ & := \frac{7 - 01}{623 - 89} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{701}{86924} & := \frac{7 + 01}{(8 + (6 \times 9)) \times 2^4} \\ & := \frac{7^{01}}{(8 \times (6 \times 9 \times 2)) + 4} \\ & := \frac{7 - 01}{8 \times (69 + 24)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{701}{94635} & := \frac{7^{01}}{9 \times ((4 \times 6 - 3) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{701}{39256} & := \frac{7 + 01}{392 + 56} \\ & := \frac{7 - 01}{392 - 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{701}{48369} & := \frac{7 + 01}{483 + 69} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{701}{65894} & := \frac{70 \times 1}{6 + (5 + (8 + 9^4))} \\ & := \frac{7 + 01}{658 + 94} \\ & := \frac{7 - 01}{6 \times (58 + 9 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 702

$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{936} := \frac{7+02}{9-3+6}$	$:= \frac{7+0 \times 2}{63 \times 1^8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{135486} := \frac{7+0 \times 2}{1+3 \times 5 \times (4+86)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{1638} := \frac{70+2}{(1+6) \times 3 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{7+02}{63+18}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{143598} := \frac{7+02}{1-(4-3^5+9) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{7+02}{16-3+8}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 01}{6 \times (3+18)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{183456} := \frac{7+02}{(1 \times 8+34) \times 56}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{3159} := \frac{70-2}{315-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{8346} := \frac{7+02}{83+4 \times 6}$	$:= \frac{70+2}{(1+83) \times 4 \times 56}$
$:= \frac{70+2}{315+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{13689} := \frac{70-2}{13 \times (6 \times (8+9))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{354198} := \frac{70+2}{(3^5-4) \times 19 \times 8}$
$:= \frac{7 \times 01}{3+(1+59)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{18954} := \frac{7-02}{189-54}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{516438} := \frac{7+02}{(5+1) \times (6+4) + 3^8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{3861} := \frac{7 \times 01}{(3+8) \times (6+1)}$	$:= \frac{7+0 \times 2}{1+(8+(9 \times 5 \times 4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{531648} := \frac{7+02}{(53 \times 16+4) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{4368} := \frac{7+02}{(4-3+6) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{7+02}{189+54}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{6318} := \frac{7-02}{6+(31+8)}$	$:= \frac{70 \times 2}{189 \times 5 \times 4}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{64935} := \frac{7 \times 01}{(6^4)-(9-3-5)}$	

• Numerator 703

$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{4218} := \frac{7-03}{4+(2+18)}$	$:= \frac{7+0 \times 3}{(5 \times 6 \times 2)-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{19684} := \frac{7-03}{196-84}$
$:= \frac{7+0 \times 3}{42 \times 1^8}$	$:= \frac{7+03}{5 \times ((6-2) \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{7+0 \times 3}{((19+6) \times 8)-4}$
$:= \frac{7+03}{42+18}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{9842} := \frac{7-03}{98-42}$	$:= \frac{7+03}{196+84}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{4921} := \frac{7-03}{4 \times (9-2 \times 1)}$	$:= \frac{7+03}{98+42}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 03}{(1^9+6) \times 84}$
$:= \frac{7+0 \times 3}{49 \times (2-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{82954} := \frac{7-03}{8 \times (((2+9) \times 5)+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{128649} := \frac{7+0 \times 3}{1 \times 2-8+6^4-9}$
$:= \frac{7+03}{49+21}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{12654} := \frac{7-03}{1+(2+(65+4))}$	$:= \frac{7-03}{12+8 \times (6+4) \times 9}$
$:= \frac{7 \times 03}{49 \times (2+1)}$	$:= \frac{7+0 \times 3}{1 \times ((2 \times 65)-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{198246} := \frac{7+0 \times 3}{(1^9+82 \times 4) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{7^{03}}{49^2 \times 1}$	$:= \frac{7+03}{(1+2+6) \times 5 \times 4}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 03}{(1+982+4) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{5624} := \frac{7-03}{56-24}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 03}{(1^2+6) \times 54}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{703}{824619} := \frac{7+0 \times 3}{8+2 \times (4^6+1)+9}$

● Numerator 704

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{832} &:= \frac{7+04}{8+3+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{6592} &:= \frac{7+04}{6+(5+92)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{56832} &:= \frac{7+04}{56+832} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{1536} &:= \frac{7+04}{1+(5+3 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{6912} &:= \frac{70-4}{6 \times (9 \times 12)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{59136} &:= \frac{7-04}{(5+9 \times 1) \times 3 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{1856} &:= \frac{7+04}{18+5+6} & &:= \frac{7+04}{6 \times (9 \times 1 \times 2)} & &:= \frac{7+0 \times 4}{591+3-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{2368} &:= \frac{7+04}{23+6+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{8512} &:= \frac{7+04}{8+(5^{1+2})} & &:= \frac{7+04}{5+(913+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{2816} &:= \frac{7-04}{(2 \times (8+1)) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{9152} &:= \frac{7-04}{9+(15 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{61952} &:= \frac{7-04}{6 \times (1-(9-52))} \\ &:= \frac{7+0 \times 4}{2 \times (8+1 \times 6)} & &:= \frac{7+04}{91+52} & &:= \frac{7+0 \times 4}{619-5+2} \\ &:= \frac{7+04}{2+((8-1) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{9856} &:= \frac{7-04}{98-56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{129536} &:= \frac{7+04}{1295+3^6} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 04}{2 \times (8 \times (1+6))} & &:= \frac{7+04}{98+56} & &:= \frac{7-04}{((1+2 \times 9) \times 5-3) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{5632} &:= \frac{7-04}{56-32} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{13568} &:= \frac{7+04}{(1+3) \times (5+6 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{281536} &:= \frac{70-4}{(2+81) \times 53 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7+0 \times 4}{56 \times (3-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{16832} &:= \frac{7+04}{1+(6+(8 \times 32))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{356928} &:= \frac{7 \times 04}{(3+56 \times 9) \times 28} \\ &:= \frac{7+04}{(5 \times 6 \times 3) - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{29568} &:= \frac{7-04}{2 \times (9 \times (5-6+8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{368192} &:= \frac{7-04}{3+(6+81) \times 9 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{3968} &:= \frac{7+04}{3-(9-68)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{38592} &:= \frac{7+04}{3+(8+592)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{6528} &:= \frac{7+04}{6 \times ((5^2) - 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{704}{38912} &:= \frac{7+04}{38 \times ((9-1) \times 2)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 705

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{705}{846} &:= \frac{70-5}{84-6} & &:= \frac{70+5}{126+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{705}{294831} &:= \frac{7 \times 05}{(2+9)^4 - 8 + 3 + 1} \\ &:= \frac{70+5}{84+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{705}{34968} &:= \frac{7 \times 05}{((3 \times 4)^{9-6}) + 8} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{705}{1269} &:= \frac{70-5}{(1+2 \times 6) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{705}{39621} &:= \frac{70 \times 5}{3^9 - (6 \times 2 + 1)} & & \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 05}{(12 \times 6) - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{705}{169482} &:= \frac{70-5}{1^6 + (9-4)^{8-2}} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 706

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{706}{38124} &:= \frac{7-06}{3 \times (((8-1) \times 2) + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{706}{295814} &:= \frac{7-06}{(2+9 \times 5) \times (8+1) - 4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 708

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{2596} &:= \frac{7+08}{2+(59-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{34692} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 8}{(3+46) \times (9-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{532416} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 8}{(5+324) \times 16} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{4956} &:= \frac{7+08}{4+(95+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{45312} &:= \frac{7+08}{4-(5-(31^2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{13452} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 8}{1 \times ((3 \times 45) - 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{129564} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 8}{1-2-9-5+6^4} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{708}{341256} &:= \frac{7+08}{(3^{4+1}-2) \times 5 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 709

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{709}{2836} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 9}{2+(8+3 \times 6)} & &:= \frac{7+09}{6 \times (3 \times 8 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{709}{32614} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 9}{326-1 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{7+09}{28+36} & &:= \frac{7 \times 09}{63 \times (8+1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{709}{861435} &:= \frac{7+09}{8 \times (6+1 \times 4) \times 3^5} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 09}{28 \times (3+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{709}{24815} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 9}{(2+48-1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{709}{6381} &:= \frac{7+0 \times 9}{(6+3) \times (8-1)} & &:= \frac{7+09}{2^4 \times (8-1) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 710

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{2485} &:= \frac{7-1+0}{24-8+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{48635} &:= \frac{7+1+0}{4+(8 \times (63+5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{463985} &:= \frac{7-1+0}{4^6-(3 \times 9+8) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{6248} &:= \frac{7 \times 10}{624-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{62835} &:= \frac{7-1+0}{(62 \times 8) + 35} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{26483} &:= \frac{7 \times 10}{(2 \times (6^4+8)) + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{348965} &:= \frac{7-1+0}{3 \times (4+89 \times (6+5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{710}{38695} &:= \frac{7-1+0}{3 \times (8+(6+95))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 712

$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{3560} := \frac{7+12}{35+60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{9345} := \frac{7+1^2}{(9+3 \times 4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{93450} := \frac{7+1^2}{(9+3 \times 4) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{3649} := \frac{7+1^2}{36-4+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{36045} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{360 \times (4+5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{360984} := \frac{7+1 \times 2}{3+60 \times (9 \times 8+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{4539} := \frac{7+1^2}{(4 \times (5 \times 3)) - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{396584} := \frac{7+1^2}{(3+6+0) \times 45}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{396584} := \frac{7+1^2}{(3+9) \times 6 \times 5 + 8^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{4806} := \frac{7+1^2}{48+06}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{50463} := \frac{(7+1) \times 2}{3 \times (6 \times (0+45))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{563904} := \frac{7+1+2}{5 \times (6+390) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{5340} := \frac{7+1^2}{5 \times (3 \times 4+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{50463} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{504 \times (6+3)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{6408} := \frac{7-1^2}{6+(40+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{50463} := \frac{7+1^2}{(5+04) \times 63}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{6408} := \frac{7+1^2}{6 \times (4+08)}$		

● Numerator 713

$\blacktriangleright \frac{713}{260958} := \frac{7-1-3}{2 \times (60 \times 9+5) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{713}{460598} := \frac{7+1^3}{(4+60 \times 5) \times (9+8)}$
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● Numerator 714

$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{952} := \frac{7-1^4}{(9-5) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{5032} := \frac{7+14}{(2^8-5) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{5032} := \frac{7+14}{(50 \times 3) - 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{952} := \frac{7+(1+4)}{9+5+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{5032} := \frac{7+14}{28+56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{5236} := \frac{7-1 \times 4}{5+(23-6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{952} := \frac{7+14}{(9+5) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{5032} := \frac{(7+1) \times 4}{2 \times (8+56)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{5236} := \frac{7+(1+4)}{52+36}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2380} := \frac{7+(1+4)}{2+(38+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{6528} := \frac{71+4}{(2+8) \times 5 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{6528} := \frac{7 \times (1+4)}{(6 \times 52) + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2856} := \frac{7-1 \times 4}{(2 \times (8-5)) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2958} := \frac{7 \times 1^4}{2-(9 \times (5-8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2958} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(6-5) \times 2^8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2856} := \frac{7-1^4}{2-(8-(5 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2958} := \frac{7+14}{29+58}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{8092} := \frac{7-1 \times 4}{(8+09) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2856} := \frac{7+1^4}{(2 \times (8+5)) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{3502} := \frac{7+14}{3+(50 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{8925} := \frac{7-1^4}{(8+9-2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2856} := \frac{7-1+4}{2+(8+5 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{3689} := \frac{7+(1+4)}{3+(68-9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{8925} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(8 \times 9-2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{2856} := \frac{7+1 \times 4}{((2+8) \times 5) - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{3825} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{3 \times ((8+2) \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{714}{9520} := \frac{7-1^4}{(9-5) \times 20}$

	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{(9 + 5) \times 20}$		$:= \frac{7 - 1 + 4}{5 - (2 - (8 + 3^6))}$		$:= \frac{7 - 1^4}{(8 + 9 - 2) \times 50}$
▶ $\frac{714}{23698}$	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{2 - (3 - 698)}$		$:= \frac{7 + (1 + 4)}{52 + 836}$		$:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(8 \times 9 - 2) \times 50}$
▶ $\frac{714}{25398}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{(2 \times (5^3)) - 9 + 8}$		$:= \frac{7 + 14}{(5 - 2) \times ((8^3) + 6)}$	▶ $\frac{714}{93058}$	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{(9 \times 305) - 8}$
▶ $\frac{714}{25908}$	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{2 + ((5 + 90) \times 8)}$	▶ $\frac{714}{60928}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 \times 4}{(6 \times 0 \times 9) + (2^8)}$	▶ $\frac{714}{98532}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 \times 4}{9 \times ((8 + (5 \times 3)) \times 2)}$
▶ $\frac{714}{28356}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{2 \times (83 + 56)}$		$:= \frac{7 - 1^4}{(60 \times 9) - 28}$	▶ $\frac{714}{206958}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{2069 - 5 \times 8}$
▶ $\frac{714}{28560}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 - 4}{2 + ((8 + 5) \times (6 + 0))}$	▶ $\frac{714}{65280}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(6 \times 5 + 2) \times 80}$	▶ $\frac{714}{306952}$	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{3 + 0 \times 6 + 95^2}$
	$:= \frac{7 + (1 + 4)}{2 \times (8 \times (5 \times (6 + 0)))}$	▶ $\frac{714}{65382}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{65 + ((3 \times 8)^2)}$	▶ $\frac{714}{350268}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{3502 - 68}$
	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{28 \times (5 \times (6 + 0))}$	▶ $\frac{714}{68952}$	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{(6 \times 8 - 9) \times 52}$	▶ $\frac{714}{369852}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 \times 4}{3 \times (6 + 98) \times 5 - 2}$
	$:= \frac{71 + 4}{(2 + 8) \times (5 \times 60)}$		$:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{((6 \times 8) + 9 - 5)^2}$	▶ $\frac{714}{528360}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{5 \times 2 \times (8^3 + 6) + 0}$
▶ $\frac{714}{29308}$	$:= \frac{7 + 14}{(29 \times 30) - 8}$	▶ $\frac{714}{69258}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{692 - (5 + 8)}$	▶ $\frac{714}{536928}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^4}{(5 + 36 \times 9) \times 2 \times 8}$
▶ $\frac{714}{29580}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{29 \times (5 \times 8 + 0)}$		$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times 4}{6 + (9 \times 258)}$		$:= \frac{7 + 1^4}{(5 + 3^6 + 9 \times 2) \times 8}$
▶ $\frac{714}{38250}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{3 \times ((8 + 2) \times 50)}$	▶ $\frac{714}{80325}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times 4}{80 \times (3^2 \times 5)}$	▶ $\frac{714}{930852}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (1 + 4)}{9 \times 30 \times (8 + 5)^2}$
▶ $\frac{714}{52836}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 \times 4}{(5 + (2^{8-3})) \times 6}$	▶ $\frac{714}{89250}$	$:= \frac{7 + 1 - 4}{(8 + 92) \times (5 + 0)}$		

● Numerator 715

▶ $\frac{715}{2340}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 + 5}{2 + (34 + 0)}$		$:= \frac{7 \times (1 + 5)}{28 \times (6 + 0)}$		$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times 5}{(4 - 2) \times 90}$
▶ $\frac{715}{2640}$	$:= \frac{7 + 1 + 5}{2 + (6 + 40)}$	▶ $\frac{715}{3960}$	$:= \frac{7 + 1 + 5}{3 + (9 + 60)}$	▶ $\frac{715}{4680}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 + 5}{4 + (68 + 0)}$
▶ $\frac{715}{2860}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 - 5}{2^{8-6} + 0}$	▶ $\frac{715}{4290}$	$:= \frac{7 + 1 - 5}{(4 - 2) \times (9 + 0)}$	▶ $\frac{715}{6240}$	$:= \frac{7 - 1 + 5}{6 \times (2^4 + 0)}$
	$:= \frac{7 \times 1^5}{2 \times (8 + 6 + 0)}$		$:= \frac{7 + 1 \times 5}{4 \times (2 \times (9 + 0))}$	▶ $\frac{715}{8320}$	$:= \frac{7 + 15}{8 \times (32 + 0)}$
	$:= \frac{7 + 15}{2 + (86 + 0)}$		$:= \frac{7 + 15}{42 + 90}$	▶ $\frac{715}{9438}$	$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times 5}{9 \times (4 \times (3 + 8))}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{9680} := \frac{7+1+5}{96+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{48620} := \frac{7-1-5}{4+(8 \times (6+2+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{348920} := \frac{7-1 \times 5}{(3+4) \times 8+920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{24960} := \frac{7+15}{2 \times (4 \times (96+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{82940} := \frac{7-1 \times 5}{4 \times (8+(6+20))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{368940} := \frac{7-1-5}{(3+(6+8) \times 9) \times 4+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{26390} := \frac{71-5}{24 \times (96+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{82940} := \frac{7+1^5}{8 \times (29 \times (4+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{394680} := \frac{7+1 \times 5}{3^6 \times 8+9 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{28490} := \frac{7+15}{2+((6+3) \times 90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{94380} := \frac{7-1-5}{9+(43+80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{394680} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{(3 \times 94-6) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{28490} := \frac{7+1+5}{28+490}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{94380} := \frac{7-1 \times 5}{(9 \times 4-3) \times (8+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{394680} := \frac{7-1 \times 5}{(3 \times 9-4) \times 6 \times 8+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{28930} := \frac{7+1+5}{(2^8)+(9 \times 30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{94380} := \frac{7+1-5}{9 \times (4 \times (3+8+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{394680} := \frac{7+1^5}{(3+9) \times 46 \times 8+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{32890} := \frac{7+1-5}{(3 \times 2 \times 8)+90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{324896} := \frac{(7-1) \times 5}{32 \times (48 \times 9-6)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{715}{39468} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{((3 \times 94)-6) \times 8}$		

• Numerator 716

$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{3580} := \frac{7+16}{35+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{3580} := \frac{7-1^6}{(5 \times ((2+9) \times 8))+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{3580} := \frac{7+16}{(8-5) \times 920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8234} := \frac{7+1-6}{(8 \times 2)+3+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8234} := \frac{7-1+6}{(52 \times (9+8))+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{352809} := \frac{(7-1) \times 6}{3^5 \times (2+80-9)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8592} := \frac{7+1-6}{8+(5+9+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8592} := \frac{7+1+6}{52+984}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{385924} := \frac{7-1 \times 6}{3-8 \times (5-9 \times 2 \times 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8592} := \frac{7 \times 1^6}{8-(5-(9^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{59428} := \frac{7-1 \times 6}{(5 \times (9+(4+2)))+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{385924} := \frac{7-1+6}{3^8-5-92+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8592} := \frac{7+1^6}{8 \times (5+9-2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{59428} := \frac{7+1-6}{5+(((9+4)^2)-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{385924} := \frac{7+1^6}{(3 \times 8 \times 5 \times 9-2) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8592} := \frac{7-1+6}{(8-5+9)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{59428} := \frac{7-1^6}{(5 \times 94)+28}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{385924} := \frac{7+1-6}{3 \times (8 \times 5 \times 9-2)+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8592} := \frac{7+16}{(8-5) \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{59428} := \frac{7 \times 1^6}{5+(9 \times (4 \times 2 \times 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{389504} := \frac{7+1-6}{(3 \times 89+5+0) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{35084} := \frac{7-1 \times 6}{3+(50-8+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{85920} := \frac{7+1-6}{(8-5+9) \times 20}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{35084} := \frac{7 \times (1+6)}{((3 \times (5+0))-8)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{85920} := \frac{7-1^6}{8 \times (5 \times (9 \times (2+0)))}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{52984} := \frac{7+1-6}{((5 \times 2+9) \times 8)-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{52984} := \frac{7+1^6}{8 \times 5+920}$	

• Numerator 718

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{3590} &:= \frac{7 \times (1 + 8)}{35 \times (9 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{36259} &:= \frac{7 - 1^8}{362 - 59} & & := \frac{7 + 1 \times 8}{(3^5 + 4) \times (6 + 9) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 18}{35 + 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{296534} &:= \frac{7 - 1 + 8}{2 \times (965 \times 3 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{362590} &:= \frac{7 \times 1^8}{3625 - 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{5026} &:= \frac{7 - 1^8}{(5 + 02) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{306945} &:= \frac{7 - 1^8}{(3 + 06 \times 9) \times 45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{369052} &:= \frac{7 \times 1^8}{(3^6 - 9) \times 05 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{23694} &:= \frac{7 + 18}{2 + ((3^6) + 94)} & &:= \frac{7 + 1^8}{30 \times (69 + 45)} & & \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 1^8}{236 - 9 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{718}{354692} &:= \frac{7 - 1^8}{(3 + 54) \times (6 \times 9 - 2)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 719

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{719}{56082} &:= \frac{7 + 1^9}{560 + 8^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{719}{406235} &:= \frac{7 + 1^9}{40 \times (6^2 \times 3 + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 720

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{864} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{8 - 6 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{49536} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{4 \times (95 - (3 + 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{315648} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(3 \times 15 \times 6 + 4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{1584} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{15 - 8 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{51984} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(5 \times (1 + 9 \times 8)) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{354816} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(3 \times 54 - 8) \times 16} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{3456} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(3 - 4 + 5) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{59184} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(5 \times (91 - 8)) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{413568} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(4 - 1 + 356) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 20}{3 \times 4 \times 56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{143856} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{143 + 856} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{5184} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{5 - (1 - 8 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{154368} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{15 \times 4 \times 3 \times 6 - 8} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{13968} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{1 - ((3 - (9 + 6)) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{163584} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{16 + 35 \times 8 \times 4} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{39168} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(39 + 1 - 6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{720}{183456} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 0}{(1^8 + 3)^4 \times 5 - 6} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 721

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{721}{3605} &:= \frac{72 - 1}{360 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{721}{4635} &:= \frac{7 \times (2 + 1)}{(4 \times 6 + 3) \times 5} & & := \frac{7 + 21}{4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{(3 + 6 + 0) \times 5} & &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{4 + (6 + 35)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{721}{6489} &:= \frac{7 - 2 \times 1}{6 + (48 - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{72 + 1}{360 + 5} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{72 - 1}{648 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{(6 \times (4 + 8)) + 9} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 + 1}{(6 - 4 + 8) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 1}{6 \times (4 + 8 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{72 + 1}{648 + 9} \\ &:= \frac{72 \times 1}{6 \times ((4 + 8) \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{6 + (48 + 9)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{90 - 6 + 4} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 \times 1}{3 \times ((4 + 6 + 0) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 2 - 1}{3 \times (4 \times (60 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{(3 + 4) \times (6 \times 08)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 1}{(4 + (3 \times 5 \times 6)) \times 9} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{((4^3) + 5) \times 6 + 9} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2 + 1)}{(4 \times 6 + 3) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 21}{4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{538 - (6 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 \times 1}{((5 + 98) \times 4) + 3} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{5 + (9 \times ((8 - 4)^3))} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 - 1}{(6 + 4) \times (8 \times (9 + 0))} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{72 \times 1}{6 \times ((8 + 4) \times 95)} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{9 \times (80 + 56)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{(9 + 8 + 0) \times 56} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 - 1}{3 + 4 \times 968 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 1)}{40 \times (8 + 3) \times 9 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 1}{(4 + 3 \times 5 \times 6) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{7^2 \times 1}{(5 \times 93 + 4) \times 86} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{(6 + 84) \times 95 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{72 \times 1}{6 \times (8 + 4) \times 950} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 1}{(6 + ((8 + 4) \times 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 + 1}{(6 + 8 - 4) \times 95} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{7 \times 2^3}{8 \times ((4 + 5) \times 91)} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 \times 3}{(1 \times 40 - 9 + 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2^3}{1 \times 5 \times (640 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 23}{1 + 5 \times 6^4 + 09} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 \times 3}{1^6 + 8 \times (4 \times 5 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 - 3}{1 + 6 \times (84 - 5) - 9} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 2^3}{8 \times (4 + 5) \times 910} \end{aligned}$

• Numerator 723

$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{72 - 3}{96 - 4} \\ &:= \frac{72 + 3}{96 + 4} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 3}{50 + 6 \times 1} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 - 3}{(8 + (1 \times 9)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 - 3}{10 + ((8 - 4) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 - 3}{1 - (0 - (84 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 2 - 3}{(1 - (0 - 8 \times 4)) \times 5} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{7 + 2 + 3}{(1 + 08) \times 4 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 2) \times 3}{(1 + 08) \times 45} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 + 3}{(1 - (5 \times 9)) \times (-06)} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 \times 3}{(6 - 9) \times (4 \times (-08))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 2) \times 3}{6 \times (9 \times (40 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 2 - 3}{(8 + (1 \times 9)) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 3}{845 + 91} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{723}{140985} \\ &:= \frac{723}{156409} \\ &:= \frac{723}{168459} \\ &:= \frac{723}{845910} \end{aligned}$
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● Numerator 724

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{724}{905} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{9 \times 05} &:= \frac{7 \times 2 - 4}{5 \times (0 + 6 + 8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{196385} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{(1 + 9 \times 6^3 + 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{72 - 4}{90 - 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{31856} &:= \frac{7 - 2 - 4}{(3 + 1^8) \times (5 + 6)} &:= \frac{72 - 4}{(1^9 + 6^3) \times 85} \\ &:= \frac{72 + 4}{90 + 5} &&:= \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{(318 \times 5) - 6} &\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{389150} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times 4}{(3 \times 8 \times 9 - 1) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{724}{1086} &:= \frac{7 \times 2 - 4}{1 - (0 - (8 + 6))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{38915} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times 4}{((3 \times 8 \times 9) - 1) \times 5} &:= \frac{72 - 4}{(3 + 8 \times 91) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{(1 + 08) \times 6} &&:= \frac{72 - 4}{(3 + (8 \times 91)) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{391865} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{3^9 - 18 \times (6 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{72 - 4}{108 - 6} &\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{59368} &:= \frac{7 - 2 - 4}{(5 \times (9 + 3 + 6)) - 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{593680} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{5 \times (9 + 3^6) \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{72 + 4}{108 + 6} &&:= \frac{7 + 2 - 4}{5 - (9 \times (3 - 6 \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 725

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{725}{9860} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 5}{9 \times (8 + 60)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{725}{186093} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times 5}{(1 + 8 + 60) \times 93} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{725}{96048} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times 5}{(9 + 60) \times 48} &\blacktriangleright \frac{725}{198360} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 5}{19 \times 8 \times 3 \times 6 + 0} \\ &&\blacktriangleright \frac{725}{381640} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 5}{3^8 - 1 - 6^4 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 726

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{1089} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 6}{(1 + 08) \times 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{726}{1584} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 6}{(1 + 5) \times (8 - 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{726}{4598} &:= \frac{7 + 2 - 6}{4 \times 5 - 9 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{72 - 6}{10 + 89} &&:= \frac{7 + 26}{(1 + 5) \times (8 + 4)} &:= \frac{72 + 6}{4 + (5 \times 98)} \\ &:= \frac{72 + 6}{108 + 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{726}{1980} &:= \frac{7 + 26}{1 + (9 + 80)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{726}{5148} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 6}{(5 \times 14) + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{1430} &:= \frac{7 + 26}{1 + (4^3 + 0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{726}{4158} &:= \frac{7 - 2 + 6}{4 + (1 + 58)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{726}{8019} &:= \frac{72 - 6}{(80 + 1) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{8954} &:= \frac{7+2-6}{8+(9+5 \times 4)} &:= \frac{7+26}{15 \times (8+40)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{109384} &:= \frac{7+2-6}{(10+9) \times 3 \times 8-4} \\ &:= \frac{72+6}{8+954} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{40931} &:= \frac{72-6}{(40 \times 93)+1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{149358} &:= \frac{7-2+6}{1 \times 4+9 \times (3^5+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{9438} &:= \frac{7-2+6}{(9+4) \times (3+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{51304} &:= \frac{7+2-6}{((5+1)^3)-04} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{159038} &:= \frac{7+26}{1 \times 5+903 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (2+6)}{(94-3) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{54813} &:= \frac{7 \times 2-6}{5^4-(8+13)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{315084} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times 6}{31 \times 5 \times 084} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{9801} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 6}{9 \times (80+1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{59048} &:= \frac{7+2-6}{(59 \times 04)+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{418539} &:= \frac{7 \times 2-6}{4+(1+8) \times (5-3)^9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{14058} &:= \frac{7-2+6}{((1+40) \times 5)+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{94380} &:= \frac{7 \times (2+6)}{(94-3) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{726}{15840} &:= \frac{7-2+6}{1 \times (5 \times (8+40))} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 728

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{910} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{9 \times 10} &:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{13650} &:= \frac{72-8}{(1+3) \times (6 \times 50)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{936} &:= \frac{7+28}{9+36} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{1560} &:= \frac{7+28}{15+60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{14560} &:= \frac{7 \times 2-8}{1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6+0)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{1365} &:= \frac{7^2 \times 8}{1+((3^6)+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{3549} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times 8}{3 \times (5 \times (4+9))} & &:= \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 560} \\ &:= \frac{72-8}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 5} & &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(35+4) \times 9} & &:= \frac{7-2+8}{1 \times (4 \times (5+60))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{1456} &:= \frac{7+2-8}{1^4-5+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{3640} &:= \frac{7+2-8}{3+(6-4+0)} & &:= \frac{(7^2)+8}{(14+5) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 2-8}{(1-4+5) \times 6} & &:= \frac{7 \times 2-8}{3 \times (6+4+0)} & &:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8}{1 \times (4 \times 560)} \\ &:= \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56} & &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(3+6) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{35490} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(35+4) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{7-2+8}{1 \times (4 \times 5+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{4160} &:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8}{4 \times 160} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{39546} &:= \frac{7^2 \times 8}{39 \times 546} \\ &:= \frac{7+2+8}{1 \times (4+5 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{4536} &:= \frac{7-2+8}{45+36} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{45136} &:= \frac{7+2-8}{4+(((5-1)^3)-6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times 2)+8}{1 \times (4 \times (5+6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{5369} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(53+6) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{45360} &:= \frac{7-2+8}{45 \times (3 \times (6+0))} \\ &:= \frac{7+28}{14+56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{5460} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(5+4) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{46319} &:= \frac{72-8}{4^6+(3 \times (1-9))} \\ &:= \frac{(7^2)+8}{(14+5) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{13496} &:= \frac{7-2+8}{((1+3)^4)-(9+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{728}{53690} &:= \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(53+6) \times 90} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{728}{91364} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 8}{(9^{1 \times 3}) + 6 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{728}{94536} := \frac{7 + 28}{9 + 4536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{728}{365904} := \frac{7 - 2 + 8}{3 - 6 \times 5 + 9^{04}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{728}{395460} := \frac{7^2 \times 8}{39 \times 5460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{728}{451360} := \frac{7 - 2 + 8}{(4 \times 5 \times 1)^3 + 60}$$

• Numerator 729

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{1458} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 9}{1 - (4 - (5 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - 2 + 9}{1 \times (4 \times 5 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 29}{1 \times ((4 + 5) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^2) - 9}{(1 + 4 + 5) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{1350} := \frac{72 + 9}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{1368} := \frac{72 + 9}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{1485} := \frac{72 + 9}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{1863} := \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{1 + (8 \times 6 - 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{3645} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 9}{(3 + 6 - 4) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - 2 + 9}{(3 \times 6 - 4) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 29}{(3 + 6) \times 4 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^2) - 9}{(36 + 4) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{72 + 9}{(3 + 6) \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{4608} := \frac{72 \times 9}{4^6 + 0 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{72 + 9}{(4 + 60) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{5103} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 9}{5 \times (10 - 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{5184} := \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{(5 - 1) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 29}{(5 - 1^8)^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{5463} := \frac{72 + 9}{5^4 - (6 \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{6480} := \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{(6 - 4) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{6534} := \frac{72 + 9}{6 \times ((5^3) - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{10854} := \frac{7 + 29}{(108 \times 5) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{13680} := \frac{72 + 9}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{14580} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 9}{1 \times (4 \times 5 + 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{1 \times (45 \times (8 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 29}{1 \times ((4 + 5) \times 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^2) - 9}{(1 + 4 + 5) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^2) + 9}{145 \times (8 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{14850} := \frac{72 + 9}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{30618} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 9}{30 \times (6 + 1^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^2) - 9}{30 \times ((6 + 1) \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{36045} := \frac{7 + 29}{(360 - 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{36450} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 9}{(3 + 6 - 4) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - 2 + 9}{(3 \times 6 - 4) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 29}{(3 + 6) \times (4 \times 50)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^2) - 9}{(36 + 4) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{72 + 9}{(3 + 6) \times 450}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{45603} := \frac{7 + 29}{4 \times (560 + 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{51840} := \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{(5 - 1) \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{63504} := \frac{7^2 \times 9}{(6 + (3 + (5 + 0)))^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{83106} := \frac{7 + 29}{8 + ((3 + 1 + 0)^6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{163458} := \frac{7 + 29}{((1 - 6) \times 3 + 4^5) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{165483} := \frac{(7 - 2) \times 9}{(1 - 6) \times (5 - 4 \times 8^3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{184653} := \frac{72 + 9}{(1 \times 8 + 4^6) \times 5 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{354186} := \frac{72 + 9}{(3 - 5 + (4 - 1)^8) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{729}{356481} := \frac{7 \times 2 - 9}{3 \times (5 + (6 + 4) \times 81)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{7^2 - 9}{3 \times 5 \times (6^4 + 8 \times 1)} & := \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{(3^6 + 15) \times (8 + 4)} \\ & := \frac{72 \times 9}{3^5 \times (6^4 + 8 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{729}{385641} := \frac{(7 \times 2) + 9}{(3 \times 8 + 5 - 6)^{4-1}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{729}{361584} & := \frac{7 \times (2 \times 9)}{(3^6 + 15) \times 84} & \blacktriangleright \frac{729}{831465} := \frac{7 + 2 + 9}{(8^{3+1} + 4 + 6) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 730

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{1825} & := \frac{7 - 3 + 0}{1^8 \times 2 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{14892} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{14 \times 8 + 92} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{149285} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{(1 + (49 + 2) \times 8) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{1 - (8 - (2^5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{14965} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{(14 \times (9 + 6)) - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{158629} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{(1 + 5 \times 8) \times (62 - 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{4526} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{4 + (52 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{16425} & := \frac{7 - 3 + 0}{1 + (64 + 25)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{215496} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{2 \times (1 + 5 \times 49) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{4891} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{(4 \times (8 + 9)) - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{18469} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{1 - (84 \times (6 - 9))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{254916} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{(2^5 + 4) \times (91 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{5621} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{56 + 21} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{18542} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{((1 + 8 - 5)^4) - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{468295} & := \frac{7 - 3 + 0}{4 - 6 + 8 + 2^9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{5694} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{5 + (69 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{85264} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{8 \times (((5^2) \times 6) - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{618529} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{(6 + 1 + 85)^2 + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{5986} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{5 - (9 - 86)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{129648} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{12^{9-6} + 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{8249} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{8^2 + 49} & \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{142569} & := \frac{7 + 3 + 0}{(1 - 4 \times (2 - 56)) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{730}{9125} & := \frac{7 - 3 + 0}{(9 + 1^2) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 731

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{850} & := \frac{7^3 + 1}{8 \times 50} & := \frac{7 + 3 - 1}{204 + 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{452608} & := \frac{7^3 + 1}{4^5 \times 26 \times 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{4692} & := \frac{7^3 + 1}{4 \times 6 \times 92} & \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{46920} & := \frac{7^3 + 1}{4 \times (6 \times 920)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{658240} & := \frac{7^3 + 1}{((6 + 5) \times 8)^2 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{20468} & := \frac{7 - 3 - 1}{(2 \times (0 + 46)) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{65824} & := \frac{7^3 + 1}{(((6 + 5) \times 8)^2) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{7 - 3 \times 1}{2 \times 04 \times (6 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{731}{450296} & := \frac{7 - 3 - 1}{4 \times (50 + 2) \times 9 - 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 732

$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{854} := \frac{7-3+2}{8-5+4}$	$:= \frac{7-3+2}{(9+5-1) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{7+3+2}{((9+5)^{6-4}) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{915} := \frac{7+3-2}{9+1^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{16958} := \frac{7+3+2}{1 \times ((6 \times 9 \times 5) + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{148596} := \frac{7-3 \times 2}{1+4 \times (8 \times 5+9)+6}$
$:= \frac{7+3+2}{9+1+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{18605} := \frac{7+3+2}{(1^8+60) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{148596} := \frac{7-3-2}{1 \times 4+(8+59) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{1098} := \frac{7-3+2}{(1^{09})+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{54168} := \frac{7-3-2}{(5 \times (4 \times (1+6))) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{169458} := \frac{7-3-2}{1-6+9 \times 4 \times (5+8)}$
$:= \frac{7+3+2}{1-(0-(9+8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{65148} := \frac{7-3 \times 2}{6+(51+4 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{7-3+2}{1+69 \times 4 \times 5+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{1586} := \frac{7-3+2}{15-8+6}$	$:= \frac{7-3-2}{6 \times 5+148}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{419680} := \frac{7-3+2}{4 \times (1+9) \times (6+80)}$
$:= \frac{7+3+2}{1+(5^{8-6})}$	$:= \frac{7^{3-2}}{6+((5^{1 \times 4})-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{541680} := \frac{7+3 \times 2}{5 \times 4 \times (1+6 \times 80)}$
$:= \frac{7 \times 3 \times 2}{1 \times (5+86)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{65941} := \frac{7+3+2}{(6 \times (5 \times (9 \times 4))) + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{610549} := \frac{7+3+2}{(6+10) \times 5^4+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{5490} := \frac{7-3+2}{54-(9+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{95160} := \frac{7-3+2}{(9+5-1) \times 60}$	
$:= \frac{7+3+2}{(5-4) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{95648} := \frac{7-3+2}{(9+5) \times (64-8)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{732}{9516} := \frac{7-3 \times 2}{9+(5-1^6)}$		

• Numerator 734

$\blacktriangleright \frac{734}{2569} := \frac{7-3+4}{25-6+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{734}{59821} := \frac{7+3-4}{(5 \times 98)-2+1}$
$:= \frac{7+3+4}{2+(56-9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{734}{108265} := \frac{7+3-4}{10 \times (82+6)+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{734}{20185} := \frac{7+3-4}{(20 \times 1 \times 8)+5}$	

• Numerator 735

$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{840} := \frac{7+35}{8+40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{1260} := \frac{7+35}{12+60}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (3+5)}{16 \times (8+0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{1029} := \frac{7+3+5}{10+2+9}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 35}{(1+6) \times 80}$
$:= \frac{(7-3) \times 5}{10+2 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{1428} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{14^2+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{1890} := \frac{7+35}{18+90}$
$:= \frac{7+3-5}{1 \times (0-2+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{1680} := \frac{7+35}{16+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{6912} := \frac{7 \times 35}{(6 \times (9-1))^2}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{8624} := \frac{7+3+5}{8 \times (6+2^4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{48216} := \frac{7+3-5}{4 \times (82 \times 1^6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{201684} := \frac{7+3+5}{20+(16-8)^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{8960} := \frac{7+35}{8^{9-6}+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{49128} := \frac{7 \times 35}{4^{9-1 \times 2}-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{249018} := \frac{7+3-5}{2+(4+90) \times 18}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{9261} := \frac{7+3-5}{9 \times (2+6-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{64190} := \frac{7-3+5}{6 \times (41+90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{291648} := \frac{7+3+5}{(2^9-16) \times (4+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{12096} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{12^{09-6}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{86240} := \frac{7+3+5}{(8+6^2) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{7+3-5}{(2+(9+1) \times 6) \times 4 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{14602} := \frac{7+3+5}{((1+4) \times 60)-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{192864} := \frac{(7+3) \times 5}{(1+9) \times (2 \times 8+6^4)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{24108} := \frac{(7-3) \times 5}{2 \times (41 \times 08)}$	$:= \frac{(7-3) \times 5}{(1+9^2) \times 8^{6-4}}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{24618} := \frac{7 \times 35}{2 \times ((4^6)-1+8)}$	$:= \frac{7+3-5}{1+9-2+8+6^4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{29841} := \frac{7+3-5}{(2 \times (98+4))-1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{194628} := \frac{7+3-5}{(1+9 \times 4) \times 6^2-8}$	

• Numerator 736

$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{1058} := \frac{7+3+6}{10+5+8}$	$:= \frac{(7-3) \times 6}{(1+5) \times (82+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{98415} := \frac{7+3^6}{9^{8-4} \times 15}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{1285} := \frac{7+3^6}{(1+(2^8)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{(7+3) \times 6}{15 \times (82+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{105984} := \frac{7-3+6}{1 \times 05 \times 9 \times 8 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{1840} := \frac{7+3+6}{1^8 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{41952} := \frac{7+3-6}{4-(1-(9 \times (5^2)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{154928} := \frac{(7-3) \times 6}{(1+54) \times 92-8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{5290} := \frac{7+3+6}{(5^2)+90}$	$:= \frac{7-3+6}{(4-1) \times (95 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{184920} := \frac{7+3-6}{1+84+920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{12850} := \frac{7+3^6}{(1+(2^8)) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{85192} := \frac{7+3-6}{8-(5 \times (1-92))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{419520} := \frac{7-3+6}{(4-1) \times 95 \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{14582} := \frac{7+3+6}{1-(4-(5 \times (8^2)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{94208} := \frac{7-3+6}{(9-4) \times 2^08}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{15824} := \frac{7+3-6}{((1+5 \times 8) \times 2)+4}$		

• Numerator 738

$\blacktriangleright \frac{738}{1025} := \frac{7+3+8}{1 \times 025}$	$:= \frac{7+3+8}{40+59}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{738}{10496} := \frac{7+38}{10 \times (4^{9-6})}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{738}{1640} := \frac{7+3+8}{1^6 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{738}{4592} := \frac{7+3+8}{4 \times ((5+9) \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{738}{12546} := \frac{7+3-8}{1 \times ((2 \times 5 \times 4)-6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{738}{4059} := \frac{7+3-8}{4 \times 05-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{738}{5904} := \frac{7+3-8}{(5-9) \times (-04)}$	

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{14965} := \frac{7+3+8}{1+(4 \times (96-5))} & := \frac{(7+3) \times 8}{((4+6)^{1+2}) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{406925} := \frac{7+3+8}{(406-9) \times 25} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{25461} := \frac{7+3-8}{((2+5) \times (4+6)) - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{51496} := \frac{7+38}{(5^{1+4}) + 9+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{429516} := \frac{7+3-8}{(4+2 \times 95 \times 1) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{7+3+8}{2+(5^4-6 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{61254} := \frac{7-3+8}{(6+((1+2)^5)) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{45920} := \frac{7+3+8}{4 \times ((5+9) \times 20)} & := \frac{(7 \times 3) + 8}{6+(1 \times ((2+5)^4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{460512} := \frac{7+3-8}{4 \times (60 \times 5 + 12)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{45961} := \frac{7+3+8}{4^5+(96+1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{215496} := \frac{7+38}{(21 \times 5^4) + 9+6} & := \frac{(7-3) \times 8}{(4 \times (6-1))^2 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{46125} := \frac{7+3-8}{((4+61) \times 2) - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{251904} := \frac{7-3+8}{2 \times (5-1^{904})} & := \frac{7+3+8}{(46-1) \times 250} \\
 & := \frac{7+3+8}{(46-1) \times 25} & \blacktriangleright \frac{738}{254610} := \frac{(7 \times 3) + 8}{(2 \times 5)^4 + 6 - 1 + 0} & := \frac{7+3-8}{(4+6) \times 125 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{(7-3) \times 8}{((4 \times (6-1))^2) \times 5} & := \frac{7+3+8}{(2+5^4-6) \times 10}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 739

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{739}{16258} := \frac{7+3-9}{1+(6+(2+5+8))} & := \frac{(7+3) \times 9}{6 \times (((2^8) - 1) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{739}{164058} := \frac{7+3-9}{1 \times 6 \times (40+5-8)} \\
 & := \frac{7 \times 3 - 9}{1 \times (6+258)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{739}{162580} := \frac{7 \times 3 - 9}{(1^6 + 2^5) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{739}{62815} := \frac{7+3-9}{(6+(2+8+1)) \times 5} & := \frac{7+3-9}{162+58+0}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 740

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{740}{925} := \frac{7 \times (4+0)}{(9-2) \times 5}$$

● Numerator 741

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{3952} := \frac{7+4+1}{3+(9+52)} & := \frac{74-1}{592-8} & := \frac{7 \times (4+1)}{5 \times ((9-2) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{7 \times 4 - 1}{(3 \times (9-5))^2} & := \frac{7 \times 4 \times 1}{(5+9) \times 2 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{5928} := \frac{7-4 \times 1}{5-(9-28)} & := \frac{74+1}{592+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{39520} := \frac{7+4+1}{(3 \times 9+5) \times 20}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{59280} &:= \frac{7+4+1}{(5+9-2) \times 80} & := \frac{7 \times (4-1)}{(6 \times 2+9) \times 85} & \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{258609} &:= \frac{7-4-1}{2 \times (5 \times (8+60)+9)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (4+1)}{5 \times ((9-2) \times 80)} & := \frac{7 \times 4-1}{(6^2-9) \times 85} & \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{308256} &:= \frac{7-4 \times 1}{3 \times (082 \times 5+6)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 4 \times 1}{(5+9) \times (2 \times 80)} & := \frac{7 \times 41}{6+(29^{8-5})} & \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{389025} &:= \frac{7-4-1}{3 \times (8 \times 9-02) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{62985} &:= \frac{7-4 \times 1}{(6 \times 2-9) \times 85} & \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{65208} &:= \frac{7-4-1}{(6+5) \times (2 \times 08)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{741}{629850} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+1)}{(6+29) \times 850} \\ &:= \frac{7-(4-1)}{(6-2) \times ((9+8) \times 5)} & := \frac{7-4 \times 1}{6 \times (52-08)} & & := \frac{7+4+1}{6 \times 2 \times (9+8) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{7+4+1}{6 \times (2 \times ((9+8) \times 5))} & := \frac{7+4 \times 1}{((6+5)^2+0) \times 8} & & \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (4+1)}{(6+29) \times 85} & := \frac{74 \times 1}{6520-8} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 742

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{1590} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^5 \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{6095} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{(60+9) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{93651} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{93 \times (6+51)} \\ &:= \frac{7+42}{15+90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{13568} &:= \frac{7 \times (4-2)}{1 \times ((3+5-6)^8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{96831} &:= \frac{7 \times (4-2)}{9 \times ((68 \times 3)-1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{3180} &:= \frac{7 \times 4 \times 2}{3 \times 1 \times 80} & := \frac{(7 \times 4)^2}{((1+3)^5) \times (6+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{135680} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 6 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{3816} &:= \frac{7 \times (4-2)}{3 \times (8+16)} & := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{138065} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1+38+06^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{3869} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{(38 \times 6)-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{38160} &:= \frac{7 \times (4-2)}{(3+8+1) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{190853} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{(1+90 \times 8 \times 5) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{5936} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 2}{((5+9) \times 3)+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{39856} &:= \frac{7+42}{(39+8) \times 56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{398560} &:= \frac{7+42}{(39+8) \times 560} \\ &:= \frac{7+(4+2)}{5+(93+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{59360} &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{(59-3) \times 60} & & \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{(59-3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{742}{90153} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 2}{9^{(01+5-3)}} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 743

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{743}{8916} &:= \frac{7-4+3}{8 \times (9 \times 1^9)} & := \frac{7+4-3}{(8+9-1) \times 6} & := \frac{74+3}{8+916} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (4-3)}{89+1-6} & := \frac{(7-4) \times 3}{(8+9+1) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{743}{89160} &:= \frac{7+4-3}{(8+9-1) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 3}{(8+9+1) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{743}{150829} &:= \frac{7-4+3}{(1 \times 50-8) \times 29} \end{aligned} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{743}{962185} := \frac{7+4+3}{(96+2) \times 185}$$

● Numerator 745

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{1639} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{1 \times (6+3 \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{18923} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{(189 \times 2) + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{123968} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{(1+23) \times (96+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{2086} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 5}{(20 \times 8) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{21903} &:= \frac{7 \times 45}{(2+(19+0))^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{129630} &:= \frac{7+4-5}{1 \times 29 \times (6+30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{3129} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{3 \times (12+9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{28310} &:= \frac{7-4+5}{2-(8-310)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{192806} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{(-1+9^2 \times 8) \times 06} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{12069} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{(1+(20+6)) \times 9} & &:= \frac{7+4 \times 5}{2 \times ((8^3)+1+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{196382} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{19 \times (6^3-8)+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{12963} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{1 \times (29 \times (6+3))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{80162} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{(801+6) \times 2} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{16390} &:= \frac{7+4+5}{((1+6)^3)+9+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{745}{106982} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 5}{(1069+8) \times 2} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 746

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{8952} &:= \frac{7+4+6}{8+((9+5)^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{83925} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 6}{(8-3) \times (9^2 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{180532} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 6}{(1+80-5 \times 3)^2} \\ &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 6}{8 \times (9 \times (5-2))} & &:= \frac{7 \times 4 - 6}{(8+3) \times (9 \times 25)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{381952} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 6}{(3 \times 8 \times 1 \times (9-5))^2} \\ &:= \frac{74+6}{8+952} & \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{89520} &:= \frac{7+4-6}{8 \times (95-20)} & &:= \frac{7-4+6}{3 \times 8 \times (1+95) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{9325} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 6}{9 \times ((3+2) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{93250} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 6}{9 \times ((3+2) \times 50)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{12309} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 6}{(1+(2+30)) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{746}{139582} &:= \frac{7+4^6}{13 \times 9^5 + 8^2} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 748

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{935} &:= \frac{(7-4) \times 8}{(9-3) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{1632} &:= \frac{74-8}{16 \times 3^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{3162} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{31 \times 6 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{1326} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{13 \times 2 \times 6} & &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times (6 \times 32)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{5236} &:= \frac{7+4-8}{5-(2-(3 \times 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{1530} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{(1+5) \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{2516} &:= \frac{7-4+8}{2+(5 \times (1+6))} & &:= \frac{7-4+8}{5+(2 \times 36)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(7-4) \times 8}{(5+23) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{13260} & := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{13 \times 2 \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{52360} & := \frac{(7-4) \times 8}{(5+23) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{7 \times 4 + 8}{(5+2) \times 36} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{16320} & := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times (6 \times 320)} & & := \frac{7 \times 4 + 8}{(5+2) \times 360} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{5610} & := \frac{74+8}{5+610} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{19635} & := \frac{7 \times 4 - 8}{1 \times ((9+6) \times 35)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{196350} & := \frac{7 \times 4 - 8}{(1 \times 9 + 6) \times 350} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{6120} & := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{6 \times 120} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{19652} & := \frac{7-4+8}{1+(9 \times (6 \times 5 + 2))} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{9163} & := \frac{7 \times 4 \times 8}{(9-1+6)^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{20196} & := \frac{7-4+8}{201+96} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{9350} & := \frac{(7-4) \times 8}{(9-3) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{748}{31620} & := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{31 \times 6 \times 20} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 749

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{856} & := \frac{7+49}{8+56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{86135} & := \frac{7+4-9}{(8 \times 6 + 1 - 3) \times 5} & & := \frac{7+4-9}{1+250+83} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{5136} & := \frac{7+49}{((5-1)^3) \times 6} & & := \frac{(7-4) \times 9}{(8+613) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{235186} & := \frac{7 \times 4 + 9}{2+(3^5-1) \times 8 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{50183} & := \frac{7+4-9}{50+1+83} & \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{106358} & := \frac{7+4-9}{10-6+35 \times 8} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{51360} & := \frac{7+49}{((5-1)^3) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{749}{125083} & := \frac{7-4+9}{1+250 \times 8+3} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 751

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{751}{36048} & := \frac{7-5-1}{3 \times ((6-04) \times 8)} & & := \frac{7 \times (5-1)}{3 \times ((60-4) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{751}{69843} & := \frac{7-5-1}{6-(9-(8 \times 4 \times 3))} \\ & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 1}{36 \times (0+48)} & & := \frac{7 \times (5+1)}{(3+60) \times 4 \times 8} & & := \frac{7-(5-1)}{(69 \times (8-4)) + 3} \\ & := \frac{7+5 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times 04 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{751}{63084} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 1}{(6+30) \times 84} & & := \frac{7-5 \times 1}{6+(9 \times (8+4 \times 3))} \\ & := \frac{7-(5-1)}{3 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8))} & & := \frac{7-(5-1)}{6 \times (30+8+4)} & & \\ & := \frac{7-5 \times 1}{3 \times ((6 \times 04) + 8)} & & := \frac{7-5 \times 1}{6 \times ((3 \times 08) + 4)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 752

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{940} & := \frac{7-5+2}{9-4+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{1034} & := \frac{7+5^2}{10+34} & \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{3196} & := \frac{7-5+2}{3-(1-(9+6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{4136} := \frac{7-5+2}{4+(1 \times 3 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{7+5+2}{41+36} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{19364} := \frac{7-5+2}{1 \times (93+6+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{19834} := \frac{7+5^2}{1+(9+834)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{38164} := \frac{7-5+2}{3+(8 \times (1+6 \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 2}{3-(81-(6^4))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{38916} := \frac{7-5+2}{(3 \times (8 \times 9-1))-6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{39104} := \frac{7 \times (5-2)}{3 \times (91 \times 04)} \\
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 2}{(3+9) \times 104} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{41360} := \frac{7+5+2}{41+(3^6+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{69184} := \frac{7+5-2}{6+(918-4)} \\
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 2}{69 \times (1 \times 8 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{98136} := \frac{7-5+2}{(9+(81-3)) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{149836} := \frac{7-5+2}{1 \times 4 \times (9+8) + 3^6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{386904} := \frac{7+5^2}{3 \times 8 \times (690-4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{439168} := \frac{7-5+2}{(43 \times 9+1) \times 6+8} \\
 := \frac{7 \times (5-2)}{(4^3+9) \times 168} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{463091} := \frac{7+5^2}{4 \times 6+3^{09}-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{752}{691840} := \frac{(7+5) \times 2}{69 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 753

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{6024} := \frac{7-5+3}{(6^{01})+4} \\
 := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{6 \times (0+2 \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{(7 \times 5)-3}{(6-02)^4} \\
 := \frac{7+53}{60 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{12048} := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{1 \times (2 \times (0+48))} \\
 := \frac{(7-5)^3}{1 \times ((2^04) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{7+5-3}{(1+2+0) \times 48} \\
 := \frac{7+5+3}{1 \times (20 \times (4+8))} \\
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{12 \times (0+48)} \\
 := \frac{7+53}{1 \times (20 \times 48)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{21084} := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{2 \times (1 \times (0+84))} \\
 := \frac{(7-5)^3}{2 \times (108+4)} \\
 := \frac{7+5-3}{2^{1 \times 08}-4} \\
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{(2+10) \times 84} \\
 := \frac{7+53}{2 \times (10 \times 84)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{24096} := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{(2-4) \times (0-96)} \\
 := \frac{75-3}{24 \times (0+96)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{26104} := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{2 \times (6 \times 104)} \\
 := \frac{75+3}{26 \times 104} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{28614} := \frac{7-5+3}{2+((8 \times 6-1) \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{(2^8)-((6+1) \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{7+5-3}{2+((86-1) \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{29618} := \frac{7+53}{(296-1) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{42168} := \frac{7-5+3}{4 \times (2+(1 \times 68))} \\
 := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{(4+2+1) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 := \frac{(7-5)^3}{4 \times (2 \times ((1+6) \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{7+5-3}{(4 \times (2^{1+6})) - 8} \\
 := \frac{7 \times (5-3)}{(4^2) \times (1+6 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{42 \times (1 \times 6 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{75-3}{4 \times (21 \times 6 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{48192} := \frac{7-5+3}{(4-8) \times (1-9^2)} \\
 := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{4 \times 8 \times (1+9+2)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{7+5-3}{4 \times (8 \times (1 \times 9 \times 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{146082} & := \frac{7-5+3}{(1+4+60 \times 8) \times 2} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{(4+2+1) \times 6 \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{7+5+3}{48 \times ((1+9) \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{204816} & := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{204 \times 8 \times 1 \times 6} & := \frac{(7-5)^3}{4 \times 2 \times (1+6) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times 5) - 3}{4 \times 8^{19+2}} & & := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{2 \times (0 \times 4 + 816)} & := \frac{7-5+3}{(42-1-6) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{48^{19 \times 2}} & & := \frac{75-3}{(20+4) \times 816} & := \frac{75-3}{4 \times 21 \times 6 \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{7^{5-3}}{(48-1+9)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{296180} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{(296-1) \times 8+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{481920} & := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{(4+8) \times 1920} \\
 & := \frac{(7+5)^3}{48^{19+2}} & & := \frac{7+53}{(296-1) \times 80} & := \frac{7+5+3}{48 \times (1+9) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{75 \times 3}{((4+8) \times (1+9))^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{408126} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{40 \times 81 + 2 \times 6} & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{60491} & := \frac{7+5+3}{(6^0) - 91} & := \frac{7+5+3}{4+08126} & & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{90862} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 3}{(90 \times 8) + 6 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{753}{421680} & := \frac{(7+5) \times 3}{42 \times 1 \times 6 \times 80} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 754

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{1392} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{18096} & := \frac{7 \times (5-4)}{(18 \times 09) + 6} & := \frac{(7+5) \times 4}{(3 \times (6+1+9))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{2639} & := \frac{7+5+4}{2+(63-9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{26390} & := \frac{7+5+4}{2+(6 \times (3+90))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{39208} & := \frac{(7+5) \times 4}{(3+9) \times 208} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{3016} & := \frac{7-5+4}{(3+01) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{36192} & := \frac{7-5+4}{36 \times (1+9-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{103298} & := \frac{7+5-4}{10^3-2+98} \\
 & := \frac{7+5+4}{(3-01)^6} & & := \frac{7 \times (5-4)}{3 \times ((6 \times 19) - 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{361920} & := \frac{7+5-4}{(3 \times 61+9) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{9802} & := \frac{7 \times (5-4)}{9+(80+2)} & & := \frac{7+5-4}{((3 \times 61)+9) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{631098} & := \frac{7+5+4}{6 \times 31 \times 09 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{754}{13920} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{(1+3) \times (9 \times 20)} & & := \frac{7+5+4}{3 \times ((6+1+9)^2)} & & \\
 & & & := \frac{7+5 \times 4}{36^{19 \times 2}} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 756

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{924} & := \frac{7+5+6}{9 \times 2+4} & & := \frac{7+56}{9^2-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{1428} & := \frac{7+5+6}{1 \times (42-8)} \\
 & := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{92-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{1092} & := \frac{7+56}{10+9^2} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+4^2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{1932} := \frac{7+5+6}{1+(9 \times (3+2))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{2184} := \frac{7+5+6}{(21-8) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{2394} := \frac{7+5-6}{2 \times 3+9+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{3024} := \frac{7+5-6}{3 \times (0+2 \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{7-5+6}{30-2+4} \\
 := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{3 \times (0+2^4)} \\
 := \frac{7+5+6}{3 \times (0+24)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{3402} := \frac{7-5+6}{34+02} \\
 := \frac{7+5+6}{3^4+0 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{3924} := \frac{7+56}{3+(9^2 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{4128} := \frac{7+56}{(41+2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{9324} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{((9+3)^2)+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{12348} := \frac{7+5-6}{1 \times (2+(3 \times 4 \times 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{14280} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+4^2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{21840} := \frac{7+5+6}{(21-8) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{23184} := \frac{7+5-6}{2 \times ((31-8) \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{7+56}{23 \times (1 \times 84)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{23814} := \frac{7+5-6}{(23 \times 8) + (1+4)} \\
 := \frac{7-5+6}{238+14}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{24381} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{2+(4+381)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{30429} := \frac{7-5+6}{304+2 \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{31248} := \frac{7+5-6}{((3+1^2)^4)-8} \\
 := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{31 \times (24-8)} \\
 := \frac{7+5+6}{3 \times (1 \times 248)} \\
 := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{3 \times (124 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{38241} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{(38 \times 2^4)-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{41280} := \frac{7+56}{(41+2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{41328} := \frac{7+5-6}{41 \times ((3-2) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{7+5+6}{41 \times (32-8)} \\
 := \frac{7+56}{41 \times (3 \times 28)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{41832} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{4 \times (1 \times (83 \times 2))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{43218} := \frac{7+5-6}{(4+3)^{2+1^8}} \\
 := \frac{(7^5) \times 6}{(4+(3 \times (2-1)))^8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{43281} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{(43 \times 2 \times 8)-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{83412} := \frac{7+5-6}{((83 \times 4)-1) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{98412} := \frac{7+56}{9+((8^4 \times 1) \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{102438} := \frac{7+5+6}{1+02438} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{103824} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{103 \times (8+2 \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{7+5+6}{1 \times 03 \times 824}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{7+5-6}{10^3 \times 824} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{104328} := \frac{7-5+6}{(10+4 \times 32) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{104832} := \frac{7+5-6}{10^4 \times 832} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{109284} := \frac{7+5+6}{10+9^2 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{120834} := \frac{7+5-6}{120 \times 8+3-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{123480} := \frac{7+5-6}{12 \times 3^4+8+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{123984} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{(1-2+3) \times 984} \\
 := \frac{7-5+6}{(1 \times 2+39) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 := \frac{7+5+6}{1^2 \times 3 \times 984} \\
 := \frac{7+5-6}{1+2-3+984} \\
 := \frac{75+6}{123 \times 9 \times (8+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{128394} := \frac{7+5-6}{1 \times 2 \times 8^3-9+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{132048} := \frac{7+5-6}{13 \times 20 \times 4+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{134820} := \frac{7+5-6}{134 \times 8-2+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{139482} := \frac{(7-5)^6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 4 \times 82} \\
 := \frac{7-5+6}{(13+9-4) \times 82} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{143829} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{((1+4)^3-8)^2+9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{143892} := \frac{75-6}{1+(-4+3^8-9) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{148302} := \frac{7+5-6}{1-4 \times (8-302)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{183204} := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{((1+8)^3-2) \times 04}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{7+5-6}{(1+8)^3 \times 2 - 04} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{193284} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{(1 \times 9 + 3) \times 2^8 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{213948} & := \frac{7-5+6}{(2-1+3 \times 94) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{218043} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{21+80 \times 43} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{231840} & := \frac{7+5-6}{2 \times (31-8) \times 40} \\ & := \frac{7+56}{23 \times 1 \times 840} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{238140} & := \frac{7-5+6}{(2^3 \times 8-1) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{293148} & := \frac{7+56}{29^3 + (1+4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{298431} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{(2+9 \times 8) \times 4^3 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{304128} & := \frac{7 \times (5+6)}{(30 \times 4 + 1) \times 2^8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{312480} & := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{3 \times 124 \times 80} \\ & := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{(3-1) \times 2480} \\ & := \frac{7+5+6}{3 \times 1 \times 2480} \\ & := \frac{7+5-6}{(3^{1+2} + 4) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{321489} & := \frac{(7-5)^6}{3 \times 21 \times 48 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{384912} & := \frac{7+56}{(3+8) \times 4 \times 9^{1+2}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{394128} & := \frac{7+5-6}{(394-1-2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{412839} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{4 + (1+2)^8 - 3 - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{413280} & := \frac{7+5+6}{(4-1) \times 3280} \\ & := \frac{7+5-6}{41 \times (3-2) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{7+56}{41 \times 3 \times 280} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{418320} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{4 \times 1 \times 83 \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{419328} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 6}{(4+19+3) \times 2^8} \\ & := \frac{7+5+6}{(4+1 \times 9) \times 3 \times 2^8} \\ & := \frac{7+5-6}{(4+1 \times 9) \times 32 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{756}{419832} & := \frac{7+5-6}{4 \times (1^9 + 832)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 758

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{4169} & := \frac{7-5+8}{(4 \times 16) - 9} \\ & := \frac{7+5+8}{41+69} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{21603} & := \frac{7+5-8}{2 \times (1 \times (60-3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{39416} & := \frac{(7+5) \times 8}{(3+9) \times 416} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{40932} & := \frac{7+5-8}{4 \times (0 + (9 \times 3 \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{41690} & := \frac{7+5-8}{4 \times (1 + (6 \times (9+0)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{206934} & := \frac{7+5-8}{(20 \times 6 \times 9) + 3 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{290314} & := \frac{7+5-8}{2+90 \times (3+14)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{309264} & := \frac{(7 \times 5) - 8}{(30 \times 92 - 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{758}{394160} & := \frac{(7-5) \times 8}{(30 \times 9 + 2) \times 6 \times 4} \\ & := \frac{(7+5) \times 8}{(3+9) \times 4160} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 759

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{1380} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{1^3 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{1863} & := \frac{7-5+9}{1+(8+(6 \times 3))} \\ & := \frac{7+59}{18 \times (6+3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{3864} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{(38 \times 6) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{4301} & := \frac{7+5+9}{(4 \times 30) - 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{6210} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{6^2 \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{6831} & := \frac{7-5+9}{68+31} \\ & := \frac{(7 \times 5) - 9}{6 \times (8+31)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{13248} & := \frac{7-5+9}{1 \times (3 \times (2 \times 4 \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{(1 + 3) \times (24 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{14283} & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{14^2 + 8 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{18630} & := \frac{7 + 59}{(1 + 8) \times (6 \times 30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{23184} & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{2 \times ((3 - 1) \times 84)} \\ & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{(2^{3+1}) \times 84} \\ & := \frac{7 + 59}{(23 + 1) \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{61824} & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{(6 + 1) \times (8 \times 2^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{104328} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{(10 - 4)^3 \times 28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{123648} & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{(1 + 2 \times 3) \times (6 - 4)^8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{128064} & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{(1 + 28) \times 064} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{132480} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{(1 + 3) \times 24 \times 80} \\ & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 4 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{183264} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{1 \times 8 \times (32 + 6^4)} \\ & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{1 \times 83 \times (2 + 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{216384} & := \frac{7 + 59}{21 \times (6^3 + 8) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{231840} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{2^{3+1} \times 840} \\ & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{2 \times (3 - 1) \times 840} \\ & := \frac{7 + 59}{(23 + 1) \times 840} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{268134} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{2 \times (6^{8-1 \times 3} - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{268341} & := \frac{7 \times 5 + 9}{2 \times 6^{8-3} + 4 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{2 + 6 \times 8 \times 3^4 - 1} \\ & := \frac{7 + 59}{(2 + 6^{8-3}) \times (4 - 1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{340216} & := \frac{7 + 59}{(3 + 40)^2 \times 16} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{342608} & := \frac{7 + 59}{(3 + 4)^2 \times 608} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{361284} & := \frac{7 + 5 \times 9}{(3^6 - 1) \times (2 + 8 \times 4)} \\ & := \frac{7 + 5 + 9}{3 - 6 - 1 + (2 + 8)^4} \\ & := \frac{7 + 5 - 9}{3 \times (61 - 2) \times 8 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{384261} & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{(3 + 84) \times 2^6 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{759}{413862} & := \frac{7 - 5 + 9}{(4 + 1)^3 \times 8 \times 6 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 760

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{760}{249318} := \frac{7 \times 60}{(2 - 4 + 9) \times 3^{1+8}}$$

● Numerator 761

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{761}{3805} & := \frac{76 - 1}{380 - 5} \\ & := \frac{7 \times (6 + 1)}{(3 \times 80) + 5} \\ & := \frac{76 + 1}{380 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{761}{203948} & := \frac{7 - 6 \times 1}{20 + (3 \times 9 + 4) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{7 - 6 + 1}{20 \times 3 \times 9 + 4 - 8} \\ & := \frac{7 \times (6 + 1)}{2 \times (-03 + 9^4 + 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{761}{238954} & := \frac{7 \times 6 + 1}{2 \times 3^8 + 95 \times 4} \\ & := \frac{7 - 6 \times 1}{2 \times 3 \times (8 + 9 \times 5) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{761}{245803} & := \frac{7 - 6 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times 5 \times 8 + 03} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{761}{340928} & := \frac{7 - 6 \times 1}{(3 + 4 + 09) \times 28} \\ & := \frac{7 + 6 - 1}{(3 \times 4 + 09) \times 2^8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 762

$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{3810} := \frac{(7-6)^2}{3-(8-10)}$	$:= \frac{76+2}{304+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{180594} := \frac{(7+6) \times 2}{1-80 \times 5+9^4}$
$:= \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{3+(8-1+0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{14859} := \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{((14-8) \times 5)+9}$	$:= \frac{(7-6)^2}{180+59 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{4953} := \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{(4 \times (9-5))-3}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{14 \times ((8+5) \times 9)}$	$:= \frac{7-6+2}{1 \times 805-94}$
$:= \frac{(7+6) \times 2}{(4+9)^{5-3}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{35814} := \frac{(7-6)^2}{3+((5 \times 8 \times 1)+4)}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (6-2)}{1 \times 80-5+9^4}$
$:= \frac{76-2}{4+(9 \times 53)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{49530} := \frac{7-6+2}{(4+9) \times (5 \times (3+0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{193548} := \frac{(7-6)^2}{1+93+5 \times 4 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{1905} := \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{1+9-05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{81534} := \frac{7 \times 6-2}{8 \times (1+534)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{195834} := \frac{7 \times 6-2}{(1+9+5 \times 8^3) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{76-2}{19-05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{89154} := \frac{7-6+2}{((8 \times 9-1) \times 5)-4}$	$:= \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{1+9 \times (58+3-4)}$
$:= \frac{76+2}{190+5}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (6+2)}{8 \times (91 \times (5+4))}$	$:= \frac{(7-6)^2}{1+(9+5 \times (8+3)) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{3048} := \frac{(7-6)^2}{(3 \times 04)-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{135890} := \frac{7-6+2}{13+58 \times 9+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{301498} := \frac{7-6+2}{301 \times 4-9-8}$
$:= \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{(3 \times 0 \times 4)+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{140589} := \frac{(7+6) \times 2}{(1+40) \times (5+8) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{358140} := \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{(3^5-8 \times 1) \times 4+0}$
$:= \frac{7-6+2}{3 \times (0-4+8)}$	$:= \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{(1 \times 40+5) \times 8+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{398145} := \frac{(7-6) \times 2}{3+9+8+1+4^5}$
$:= \frac{7 \times (6-2)}{(30 \times 4)-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{148590} := \frac{7-6+2}{(1+4^{8-5}) \times 9+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{762}{438150} := \frac{7-6+2}{(43 \times 8+1) \times 5+0}$
$:= \frac{76-2}{304-8}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{14 \times (8+5) \times 90}$	

• Numerator 763

$\blacktriangleright \frac{763}{981} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{9 \times (8+1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{763}{185409} := \frac{(7-6) \times 3}{(1 \times 85-4) \times 09}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{763}{294518} := \frac{(7-6)^3}{2 \times 9 \times (4 \times 5+1)+8}$
$:= \frac{7+63}{9+81}$	$:= \frac{(7-6)^3}{(-1+8+5 \times 4) \times 09}$	$:= \frac{7-6+3}{(2 \times 94+5 \times 1) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{763}{2180} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 3}{2 \times 180}$	$:= \frac{7-6+3}{18 \times (5+40+9)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{763}{105294} := \frac{(7-6)^3}{105+29+4}$	$:= \frac{7+6+3}{1 \times 8 \times 54 \times 09}$	

• Numerator 764

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{1528} &:= \frac{(7-6)^4}{1-(5+2-8)} \\ &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 4}{1^{52} \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{7-6+4}{1^5 \times (2+8)} \\ &:= \frac{7+6-4}{1+((5^2)-8)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (6-4)}{1^5 \times 28} \\ &:= \frac{(7+6) \times 4}{(15-2) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (6+4)}{1 \times (5 \times 28)} \\ &:= \frac{76-4}{152-8} \\ &:= \frac{76+4}{152+8} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{7+6+4}{1+(5+28)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{3820} &:= \frac{7+6+4}{3+(82+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{15089} &:= \frac{76-4}{(150+8) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{15280} &:= \frac{(7-6)^4}{((1+5) \times 2) + 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 4}{1 \times (5 \times (2 \times 8 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (6-4)}{1^5 \times 280} \\ &:= \frac{(7+6) \times 4}{(15-2) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (6+4)}{1 \times (5 \times 280)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{21583} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 4}{(2 \times (1 \times 58)) - 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{53289} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 4}{(5 \times 3 + (2 \times 8)) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{109825} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 4}{(109+8-2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{293185} &:= \frac{(7+6) \times 4}{(2^9 \times 3 - 1) \times (8+5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 4}{2^9 \times 3 - 1^{85}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{764}{305218} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 4}{30 \times (52+1) + 8} \end{aligned}$
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● Numerator 765

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{1428} &:= \frac{7 \times 6 \times 5}{14 \times 28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{9180} &:= \frac{7-6+5}{9 \times (1 \times 8+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{14280} &:= \frac{7-6+5}{1 \times (4 \times (28+0))} \\ &:= \frac{7+6+5}{1 \times (42 \times (8+0))} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 6 \times 5}{14 \times 280} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{41820} &:= \frac{7-6+5}{4 \times (1 \times (82+0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{124083} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{1+2 \times (408-3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{124389} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(1+2) \times (4+3 \times 89)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{138924} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{((1+3 \times 8) \times 9+2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{143820} &:= \frac{(7-6)^5}{(1+4) \times 38-2+0} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{294831} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{2 \times 948+31} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{310284} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(3+10)^2 \times (8+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{318240} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(3 \times 18-2) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{(7-6)^5}{(3+1) \times (8^2+40)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (6-5)}{(3 \times 18)^2 - 4 + 0} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{14382} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{1 \times ((4 \times 3 \times 8) - 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{19380} &:= \frac{7+6+5}{19 \times (3 \times 8+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{23409} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(2 \times (3^4+0)) - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{31824} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{((3 \times 18) - 2) \times 4} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{218943} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{21 \times (8+9) \times 4+3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{231489} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(2+3 \times (1+4)) \times 89} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{241893} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(24+1-8) \times 93} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{293148} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(2^9 - 31) \times 4 - 8} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{398412} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{3 + ((9+8) \times (4-1))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{765}{419832} &:= \frac{(7-6) \times 5}{(4+1+9)^{8-3-2}} \end{aligned}$

● Numerator 768

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{1024} := \frac{7-6+8}{(1+02) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{1920} := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{1^9 \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{2304} := \frac{(7-6)^8}{2-(3-04)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{2 \times (3 \times 04)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7-6+8}{23+04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{4320} := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{43+2+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{4512} := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{45+1 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{5120} := \frac{7-6+8}{5 \times (12+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{9504} := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{95+04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{13920} := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{1+((3+9)^2+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{14592} := \frac{(7-6)^8}{1-((4 \times (5-9))-2)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7+6-8}{1+(4+(5 \times 9 \times 2))} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{145+9-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{21504} := \frac{(7-6)^8}{2^{1 \times 5}-04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{45312} := \frac{(7-6)^8}{4+(53+1 \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{49152} := \frac{(7-6)^8}{4+(9-(1-52))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{93120} := \frac{7+6-8}{4 \times ((9-1) \times 5 \times 2)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{4^{9-1 \times 5} \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{93120} := \frac{(7-6) \times 8}{9+31^2+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{145920} := \frac{(7-6)^8}{1+4+5+9 \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{213504} := \frac{(7-6)^8}{2 \times (1+3 \times (50-4))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{768}{213504} := \frac{7-6+8}{2+(1+3) \times 5^04}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 769

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{1538} := \frac{7+6-9}{1^{53} \times 8} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7-6+9}{1-(5-(3 \times 8))} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7+6+9}{1+(5+38)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7 \times 6-9}{(1+5) \times (3+8)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{76-9}{1+((5^3)+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{3845} := \frac{(7-6)^9}{(3-8) \times (4-5)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7+6-9}{3+(8+4+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{12304} := \frac{(7-6)^9}{(1-(2-3+0))^4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{13842} := \frac{7+6-9}{1 \times ((2 \times 30)+4)} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{(7-6) \times 9}{12 \times (3 \times 04)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{138420} := \frac{(7-6)^9}{1 \times (3 \times (8-4+2))} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7+6-9}{1 \times (3 \times (8+4^2))} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{(7-6) \times 9}{1 \times ((3^8-4) \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{15380} := \frac{7-6+9}{138+42} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{(7-6)^9}{1-(5-(3 \times 8+0))} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7+6-9}{(1^{53}) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{28453} := \frac{(7-6)^9}{2+(8+((4+5) \times 3))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{83052} := \frac{(7-6)^9}{83+05^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{138420} := \frac{(7-6) \times 9}{1 \times 3^{8-4} \times 20} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{(7-6)^9}{(13-8+4) \times 20} \\
 \qquad \qquad := \frac{7+6-9}{1 \times 3 \times (8+4) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{324518} := \frac{(7-6)^9}{3^2 \times (45+1)+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{769}{345281} := \frac{(7-6)^9}{34+5 \times (2+81)}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 780

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{936} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{9+3+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{1352} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{1^3+5^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{2496} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{2^4 \times (9-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{2964} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{2-(9-64)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{14352} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{(143-5) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{36452} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{(3^6)-(4 \times (5+2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{41236} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{(4^{1+2})+3^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{64532} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{(6^4)-(53+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{65312} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{6+((5^{3+1}) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{139425} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 + 0}{(1^3+9)^4+2 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{153296} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{1-5^3+2^9 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{780}{635492} &:= \frac{7+8+0}{6^3+5 \times 49^2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 781

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{781}{3905} &:= \frac{78-1}{390-5} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 1}{(3 \times 90) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 8 + 1}{3 \times (90 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{78 + 1}{390 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{781}{4260} &:= \frac{7+81}{4 \times 2 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{781}{30459} &:= \frac{78+1}{(3 \times (0 + (4^5))) + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{781}{34506} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 1}{3^4 \times (5 \times 06)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{781}{43026} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 1}{4 + 3026} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{781}{64539} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 1}{6 + 4539} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{781}{295360} &:= \frac{7+81}{2^9 \times (5^3 - 60)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 782

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{1496} &:= \frac{7+8 \times 2}{1+(49-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{1530} &:= \frac{7+8 \times 2}{15+30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{1564} &:= \frac{7-8+2}{1^5 \times (6-4)} \\ &:= \frac{7+8-2}{1+(5^{6-4})} \\ &:= \frac{7+8+2}{1 \times ((5 \times 6) + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(7+8) \times 2}{1-(5-64)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (8-2)}{(15+6) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{78-2}{156-4} \\ &:= \frac{78+2}{156+4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{7 \times (8 \times 2)}{1 \times (56 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{3519} &:= \frac{(7+8) \times 2}{3 \times (5 \times (1 \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 2}{3^5 \times 1^9} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (8+2)}{35 \times (1 \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{78-2}{351-9} \\ &:= \frac{78+2}{351+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{3910} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 2}{3 \times (9 \times 10)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{4590} &:= \frac{7+8 \times 2}{45+90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{5106} &:= \frac{7+8+2}{5+106} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{14306} &:= \frac{7+8+2}{1+(4+306)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{15096} &:= \frac{7+8 \times 2}{1 \times ((50 \times 9) - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{15640} &:= \frac{7-8+2}{1-(5-(6 \times (4+0)))} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (8-2)}{(15+6) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (8 \times 2)}{1 \times (56 \times 40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{16490} &:= \frac{7+8 \times 2}{1-(6-490)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{35190} &:= \frac{7-8+2}{3 \times (5+(1+9+0))} \\ &:= \frac{7+8-2}{3 \times (5+190)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(7+8) \times 2}{3 \times (5 \times (1 \times 90))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{50439} &:= \frac{(7+8) \times 2}{5 \times (0 + (43 \times 9))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{159436} &:= \frac{7+8+2}{1-5 \times (9 \times 4 - 3^6)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 2}{3^5 \times (1+9+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{56304} &:= \frac{7-8+2}{5+(63+04)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{365194} &:= \frac{7-8+2}{3-6+5 \times 1 \times 94} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (8+2)}{35 \times (1 \times 90)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{63104} &:= \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(6 \times 310) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{534106} &:= \frac{(7+8) \times 2}{(5+3410) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{41906} &:= \frac{7+8+2}{4+(1+906)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{95013} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 2}{9^5 - 01^3} & & \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{782}{143650} &:= \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+4^3) \times 65+0} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 783

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{1624} &:= \frac{78+3}{(1+6) \times 24} & \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{129456} &:= \frac{7+8+3}{(1+(2+9) \times 45) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{205146} &:= \frac{7-8+3}{2 \times ((05-1)^4+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{10962} &:= \frac{7-8+3}{1-09+6^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{142506} &:= \frac{7-8+3}{14 \times 2^5 - 06} & \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{264915} &:= \frac{7+8-3}{(2+6)^4+9 \times (1-5)} \\ &:= \frac{7+8-3}{(10 \times 9 - 6) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{152946} &:= \frac{7+8-3}{1 \times 5^2 \times 94 - 6} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{783}{16240} &:= \frac{78+3}{(1+6) \times 240} & &:= \frac{78-3}{15+(2+9)^4-6} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 784

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{952} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{9+5^2} & &:= \frac{7 \times (8+4)}{21 \times (5+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{13692} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{1 \times (3+(6 \times 9^2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{1036} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{1-(0-36)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{2560} &:= \frac{7 \times 84}{2^5 \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{31920} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{3 \times (19 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{1365} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{3192} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{3 \times (19 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{129360} &:= \frac{7-8+4}{1+2^9-3 \times 6+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{1652} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{1+(6+52)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{3920} &:= \frac{7+8+4}{3+(92+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{215936} &:= \frac{7 \times (8+4)}{2^{1 \times 5} \times (9^3-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{1960} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{1+(9+60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{12936} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 - 4}{129+3^6} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{2156} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-4)}{21+56} & \blacktriangleright \frac{784}{13650} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{13 \times (6 \times 50)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 785

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{785}{3140} := \frac{7-8+5}{(3-1)^4+0} \quad := \frac{7+8+5}{(3-1) \times 40} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{785}{4239} := \frac{7+8-5}{42+3+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{7+8+5}{(4+2^3) \times 9} & := \frac{7+8+5}{(4+2^3) \times 90} & := \frac{7+8-5}{1 \times 02^3 + 6^4} \\
 & := \frac{(7+8) \times 5}{(42+3) \times 9} & := \frac{7 \times (8-5)}{42 \times (3 \times (9+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{785}{130624} := \frac{(7+8) \times 5}{130 \times 6 \times 2^4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{785}{40192} & := \frac{7+8+5}{(4 \times (0-1+9))^2} & := \frac{(7+8) \times 5}{(42+3) \times 90} & := \frac{7+8+5}{13 \times (06-2)^4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{785}{42390} & := \frac{7-8+5}{4 \times (2 \times (3 \times (9+0)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{785}{90432} := \frac{7+8-5}{9 \times (0+(4 \times 32))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{785}{169403} := \frac{7+8-5}{1+6 \times 9 \times 40-3} \\
 & := \frac{7+8-5}{(4-2) \times (3 \times 90)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{785}{102364} := \frac{7+8+5}{10+2 \times (3+6^4)} &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 786

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{786}{4192} & := \frac{7+8-6}{4 \times (1+9+2)} & := \frac{7 \times (8+6)}{49 \times 125} & \blacktriangleright \frac{786}{143052} := \frac{7+8 \times 6}{1430 \times (5+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{786}{49125} & := \frac{7 \times (8-6)}{((4 \times 9)-1) \times 25} & \blacktriangleright \frac{786}{105324} := \frac{7^{8-6}}{1 \times 05 + 3^{2 \times 4}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{786}{491250} := \frac{7 \times (8+6)}{49 \times 1250} \\
 & := \frac{7 \times 8-6}{((4-9) \times (1-2))^5} & := \frac{7+8+6}{1+053^2+4} & \\
 & := \frac{78-6}{4 \times (9 \times 125)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{786}{109254} := \frac{7-8+6}{10 \times (9-2) + 5^4} & \\
 & & := \frac{7+8-6}{10^9 + 2 \times 5^4} &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 789

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{1052} & := \frac{7+8-9}{1+05+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{5260} := \frac{7+8-9}{5 \times (2+6+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{31560} := \frac{7+8-9}{(3+1^5) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{2104} & := \frac{7+8-9}{2^{1 \times 04}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{6312} := \frac{7+8-9}{6 \times ((3+1) \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{63120} := \frac{7+8-9}{6 \times ((3+1) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{7+8+9}{2^{10-4}} & := \frac{7-8+9}{(6+3-1)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{162534} := \frac{7+8-9}{(16^2+53) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{2630} & := \frac{7+8-9}{2+(6 \times 3+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{20514} := \frac{7-8+9}{205-1+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{264315} := \frac{7+8-9}{2 \times (64+3) \times 15} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{3156} & := \frac{7+8-9}{3+(15+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{789}{30245} := \frac{7+8-9}{(30+2^4) \times 5} & \\
 & := \frac{7-8+9}{3-(1-(5 \times 6))} & := \frac{7+8+9}{(30^2)+4 \times 5} &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 790

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{790}{361425} := \frac{7 + 9 + 0}{3 \times 61 \times 4 \times 2 \times 5}$$

• Numerator 791

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{791}{2034} &:= \frac{7 \times 9 \times 1}{2 \times 03^4} &:= \frac{7 + 9 \times 1}{(6 \times 3 - 2) \times 8} &:= \frac{7 + 9 \times 1}{(6 \times 3 - 2) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{791}{2486} &:= \frac{7 \times 9 \times 1}{(24 \times 8) + 6} &:= \frac{7 \times 9 \times 1}{6 \times (3 \times 28)} &:= \frac{7 \times 9 \times 1}{6 \times (3 \times 280)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{791}{4520} &:= \frac{7 \times (9 + 1)}{4 \times (5 \times 20)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{791}{8362} &:= \frac{7 + 91}{((8^3) + 6) \times 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{791}{83620} &:= \frac{7 + 91}{((8^3) + 6) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{791}{6328} &:= \frac{79 + 1}{632 + 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{791}{30284} &:= \frac{7 \times 9 \times 1}{(302 \times 8) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{79 - 1}{632 - 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{791}{63280} &:= \frac{7 + 9 - 1}{(6 + 3^2) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 9 - 1}{(6 + 3^2) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 792

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{792}{1350} &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{1 \times 3 \times 50} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{3168} &:= \frac{7 + 9 - 2}{(3 \times 16) + 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{4608} &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{(4 + 60) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{792}{1364} &:= \frac{7 + 9 + 2}{1 + (3 \times (6 + 4))} &&:= \frac{7 + 9 + 2}{3 + (1 + 68)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{5148} &:= \frac{7 + 9 + 2}{5 + (14 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{792}{1368} &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8} &&:= \frac{7 \times (9 + 2)}{316 - 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{5184} &:= \frac{7 \times (9 + 2)}{(5 + 1) \times 84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{792}{1386} &:= \frac{(7 + 9) \times 2}{(1 + 3) \times (8 + 6)} &&:= \frac{79 + 2}{316 + 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{5463} &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{5^4 - (6 \times 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{792}{1408} &:= \frac{7 + 9 + 2}{1 \times (4 \times 08)} &&:= \frac{7 \times 9 \times 2}{3 \times 168} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{6534} &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{6 \times ((5^3) - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{792}{1485} &:= \frac{(7 + 9) \times 2}{1 \times ((4 + 8) \times 5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{3465} &:= \frac{(7 + 9) \times 2}{(34 - 6) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{8514} &:= \frac{(7 + 9) \times 2}{(85 + 1) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{3564} &:= \frac{7 + 9 - 2}{3 + (56 + 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{10384} &:= \frac{7 + 9 + 2}{(10 \times 3 \times 8) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{792}{1584} &:= \frac{7 + 9 - 2}{1 - (5 - 8 \times 4)} &&:= \frac{7 \times 9 \times 2}{3 + 564} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{13680} &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{7 + 9 + 2}{1 \times (5 \times 8 - 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{3645} &:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{(3 + 6) \times 45} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{14850} &:= \frac{(7 + 9) \times 2}{1 \times ((4 + 8) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (9 + 2)}{158 - 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{4356} &:= \frac{7 + 9 - 2}{(4 + 3) \times (5 + 6)} &&:= \frac{7 + 9^2}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{79 + 2}{158 + 4} &&:= \frac{7 + 9 + 2}{43 + 56} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{15048} := \frac{(7+9) \times 2}{(150 \times 4) + 8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{15840} := \frac{7+9-2}{(15-8) \times 40}$ $\quad := \frac{7+9+2}{(1^5+8) \times 40}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{16384} := \frac{7+92}{(1+63) \times 8 \times 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{31548} := \frac{7+9+2}{(3^{1+5}) - (4+8)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{31680} := \frac{7+9+2}{(3+1 \times 6) \times 80}$ $\quad := \frac{7 \times 9 \times 2}{3 \times 1680}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{34650} := \frac{(7+9) \times 2}{(34-6) \times 50}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{34816} := \frac{7+92}{34 \times (8 \times 16)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{35816} := \frac{7+9+2}{3 - (5 - 816)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{36450} := \frac{7+9^2}{(3+6) \times 450}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{51840} := \frac{7 \times (9+2)}{(5+1) \times 840}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{53064} := \frac{(7+9) \times 2}{(530+6) \times 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{53460} := \frac{7+9+2}{5 \times (3+4 \times 60)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{85140} := \frac{(7+9) \times 2}{(85+1) \times 40}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{134568} := \frac{7+92}{(1 \times 3+4)^5 + 6+8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{154368} := \frac{7 \times (9+2)}{(1-5^4 \times (3-6)) \times 8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{156480} := \frac{7+92}{15 \times (6^4+8) + 0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{163584} := \frac{7+92}{16^3 \times 5 - 8 \times 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{163840} := \frac{7+92}{(1+63) \times 8 \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{184536} := \frac{7+9 \times 2}{1+8 \times (4-5+3^6)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{184653} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1 \times 8+4^6) \times 5-3}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{348160} := \frac{7+92}{34 \times 8 \times 160}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{351648} := \frac{7+9-2}{3 \times (516 \times 4+8)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{354186} := \frac{7+9^2}{(3-5+(4-1)^8) \times 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{361548} := \frac{(7+9) \times 2}{(3^6+1) \times 5 \times 4+8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{361584} := \frac{7+92}{3^6 \times 1 \times (58+4)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{615384} := \frac{7 \times 9+2}{(6+1)^5 \times 3+84}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{792}{653184} := \frac{7 \times (9+2)}{6 \times (5^3+1) \times 84}$
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• Numerator 793

$\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{1586} := \frac{7-9+3}{1^5 \times (8-6)}$ $\quad := \frac{7+9-3}{1+(5^8-6)}$ $\quad := \frac{7 \times (9-3)}{(1+5+8) \times 6}$ $\quad := \frac{79-3}{158-6}$ $\quad := \frac{79+3}{158+6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{2684} := \frac{7+9-3}{2 \times 6+8 \times 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{4026} := \frac{7+9-3}{40+26}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{5246} := \frac{7+9-3}{(5 \times 2^4)+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{8052} := \frac{7+9-3}{80+52}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{10248} := \frac{7+9-3}{(10 \times 2^4)+8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{15860} := \frac{7-9+3}{1+(5+(8+6+0))}$ $\quad := \frac{7 \times (9-3)}{(1+5+8) \times 60}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{18605} := \frac{7+9-3}{(1^8+60) \times 5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{20618} := \frac{7-9+3}{2-(0-(6+18))}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{25864} := \frac{7+9-3}{2 \times ((5+8 \times 6) \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{45201} := \frac{7-9+3}{4+(52+01)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{61854} := \frac{7-9+3}{6+(1 \times (8 \times (5+4)))}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{102846} := \frac{7+9-3}{10 \times 2 \times 84+6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{154208} := \frac{7+9-3}{(1+5) \times 420+8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{793}{258640} := \frac{7+9-3}{2 \times (5+8 \times 6) \times 40}$
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● Numerator 794

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{6352} &:= \frac{7-9+4}{6+(3+5+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{50816} &:= \frac{(7+9) \times 4}{(5+((0 \times 8)-1))^6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{213586} &:= \frac{7-9+4}{(21 \times 3+5) \times 8-6} \\ &:= \frac{7+9-4}{6 \times ((3+5) \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{52801} &:= \frac{7-9+4}{5+(2^{8-01})} & \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{218350} &:= \frac{7-9+4}{(2-1) \times (8+3) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{15086} &:= \frac{7-9+4}{((1-5) \times (-08)) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{63520} &:= \frac{7-9+4}{(6-3+5) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{794}{21835} &:= \frac{7-9+4}{(2 \times (1+8 \times 3)) + 5} & &:= \frac{7+9-4}{6 \times ((3+5) \times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 795

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{795}{3180} &:= \frac{7-9+5}{3+(1+8+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{795}{16430} &:= \frac{7-9+5}{1+(64-3+0)} & &:= \frac{7+9-5}{(2+416) \times 8+0} \\ &:= \frac{7+9+5}{3+(1+80)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{795}{38160} &:= \frac{7-9+5}{3 \times (8 \times (1 \times (6+0)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{795}{314820} &:= \frac{7+9-5}{(3 \times (14+8))^2 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(7+9) \times 5}{(3+1) \times 80} & &:= \frac{(7+9) \times 5}{3 \times (8 \times 160)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{795}{3816} &:= \frac{(7+9) \times 5}{3 \times (8 \times 16)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{795}{241680} &:= \frac{7-9+5}{2 \times 416 + 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 796

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{3184} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{3+(1+8+4)} & &:= \frac{7 \times (9-6)}{1-(0-(34 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{34825} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{(3-4+8) \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{7+9-6}{(3-1+8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{14328} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{1 \times ((4+3+2) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{35820} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{3 \times (58+2+0)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (9-6)}{(3+18) \times 4} & &:= \frac{7 \times (9-6)}{(1-4^3) \times (2-8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{51342} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{(5 \times (13 \times 4)) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{7+9+6}{3+(1+84)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{23084} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{2+(30+84)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{138504} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{1 \times 3 \times (8+50) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{7+(9 \times 6)}{(31 \times 8) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{30248} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{(3-(0-(2^4))) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{143280} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{(1 \times 4+3+2) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{3582} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{3+(5+8+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{31840} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{(3+1^8) \times 40} & &:= \frac{7+9-6}{((1+4) \times 3)^2 \times 8+0} \\ &:= \frac{7+9-6}{3 \times (5+8+2)} & &:= \frac{7+9-6}{(3-1+8) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{301485} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{30+1485} \\ &:= \frac{7+9+6}{35+8^2} & &:= \frac{7 \times (9-6)}{(3+18) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{308251} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{(308+2) \times 5-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{10348} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{1-(0-(3+48))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{796}{321584} &:= \frac{7-9+6}{32+1584} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{796}{341285} := \frac{7-9+6}{(3 \times 4)^{1+2} - 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{796}{348250} := \frac{7-9+6}{(3-4+8) \times 250}$$

• Numerator 798

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{1026} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{1 - (0-2-6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{14250} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{(1+4) \times (25+0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{120365} := \frac{7-9+8}{(1+20 \times (3+6)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{1064} := \frac{7-9+8}{10-6+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{16530} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{1 - (6 - (5 \times 30))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{126350} := \frac{7-9+8}{(1+2 \times (6+3)) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{1254} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{1 \times (2+5+4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{21546} := \frac{7-9+8}{2 + (154+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{145236} := \frac{7-9+8}{14 \times (5+2^3) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{1463} := \frac{7-9+8}{14-6+3}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9-8}{((2^{1 \times 5}) + 4) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{215460} := \frac{7-9+8}{(2+1) \times (5+4) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9+8}{1 + (46-3)}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9+8}{2 \times (1 \times (54 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9+8}{2 \times 1 \times 54 \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{4123} := \frac{7-9+8}{4 + ((1+2)^3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{23541} := \frac{7-9+8}{2 + (35 \times (4+1))}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9-8}{(2^{1 \times 5} + 4) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{4256} := \frac{7-9+8}{4 - (2 - (5 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9+8}{2 \times (354 \times 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{235410} := \frac{7+9+8}{2 \times 354 \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9+8}{4 \times (2+5 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{40356} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{((4^0)^3 - 5) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{261345} := \frac{7+9-8}{2 \times (6 + (1+3)^4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{5016} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{50-1 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{46512} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{4 \times (6 \times (5+12))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{325641} := \frac{7 \times 98}{(3 \times 2)^{5+6-4} + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{5320} := \frac{7-9+8}{(5-3) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{63042} := \frac{7-9+8}{6 \times ((3^0)^4 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{465120} := \frac{7 \times (9-8)}{(4+6 \times 5) \times 120}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9+8}{5 \times (32+0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7+9-8}{630+4-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{12635} := \frac{7-9+8}{(1 + (2 \times (6+3))) \times 5}$$

• Numerator 801

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{2759} := \frac{8+01}{27-5+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{5429} := \frac{8+01}{54-2+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{9345} := \frac{8+01}{(9+3 \times 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{2937} := \frac{8+01}{29-3+7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{6497} := \frac{8+01}{6 + (4+9 \times 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{23496} := \frac{8+01}{(2^3 + (4 \times 9)) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{3649} := \frac{8+01}{36-4+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{6942} := \frac{8+01}{6 + (9 \times 4 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{23674} := \frac{80+1}{2 - (3 + (6 - (7^4)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{4539} := \frac{8+01}{(4 \times (5 \times 3)) - 9}$$

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{801}{29637} &:= \frac{8-01}{296-37} \\ &:= \frac{8^{01}}{(2^{9-6}) \times 37} \\ &:= \frac{8+01}{296+37} \\ &:= \frac{80 \times 1}{296 \times (3+7)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{801}{59274} &:= \frac{8-01}{592-74} \\ &:= \frac{8+01}{592+74} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{801}{63279} &:= \frac{8-01}{(6+3-2) \times 79} \\ &:= \frac{8+01}{632+79} \\ &:= \frac{80+1}{((6+3)^2) \times 79} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{80-1}{(73+6) \times 92} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{801}{75294} &:= \frac{8-01}{7 \times ((5 \times (2 \times 9)) + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{8+01}{752+94} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{801}{276345} &:= \frac{8+01}{(2+7^{6-3}) \times (4+5)} \\ &:= \frac{8^{01}}{(2 \times 7-6) \times 345} \end{aligned}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{32574} := \frac{8+01}{3 \times (2 \times (57+4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{64792} := \frac{8+01}{647+9^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{357246} := \frac{8-01}{3+5^{7+2-4}-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{34265} := \frac{8+01}{((3^4)+2-6) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{73692} := \frac{8-01}{7+((3^6)-92)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{372465} := \frac{8^{01}}{(3+7-2) \times 465}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{36579} := \frac{8+01}{3+(6 \times (5+7 \times 9))}$	$:= \frac{8^{01}}{7+((36-9)^2)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{801}{47259} := \frac{8-01}{472-59}$	$:= \frac{8+01}{7+((3^6)+92)}$	
$:= \frac{8+01}{(4+7-2) \times 59}$		

● Numerator 802

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{802}{5614} &:= \frac{8-02}{56-14} \\ &:= \frac{8+0 \times 2}{56 \times 1^4} \\ &:= \frac{8+02}{5+(61+4)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{802}{31679} &:= \frac{8-02}{3 \times (16+7 \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{8+0 \times 2}{(3+1^6) \times 79} \\ &:= \frac{8+02}{316+79} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{8+02}{376+94} \\ &:= \frac{80-2}{3 \times ((7+6) \times 94)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{802}{46917} &:= \frac{8+0 \times 2}{469-17} \end{aligned}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{7619} := \frac{8-02}{76-19}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 01}{(3-1+6) \times 79}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{61754} := \frac{8+0 \times 2}{617-5+4}$
$:= \frac{8+0 \times 2}{76 \times 1^9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{36491} := \frac{8^{01}}{364 \times (9-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{63759} := \frac{8-02}{(6 \times (3+75)) + 9}$
$:= \frac{8+02}{76+19}$	$:= \frac{8-02}{3 \times (((6+4) \times 9) + 1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{149573} := \frac{8-02}{(1 \times 4 \times 95-7) \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{15639} := \frac{8-02}{1+((5^6-3)-9)}$	$:= \frac{8+02}{(3+6-4) \times 91}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{456739} := \frac{8+0 \times 2}{4 \times (5+6 \times 7 \times 3 \times 9)}$
$:= \frac{8+02}{156+39}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{37694} := \frac{8-02}{3 \times ((7-6) \times 94)}$	
$:= \frac{80-2}{(1+(56 \times 3)) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{8+0 \times 2}{(3+7-6) \times 94}$	

● Numerator 803

$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{1679} := \frac{8+03}{1+(6+7+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{14965} := \frac{8+03}{(14 \times (9+6)) - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{175492} := \frac{8+03}{1+7-5+49^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{1752} := \frac{8+03}{1 \times ((7+5) \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{21754} := \frac{8+03}{2 - ((1-75) \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{176295} := \frac{8+03}{1 \times 7^{6-2} + 9 + 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{4526} := \frac{8+03}{4+(52+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{25769} := \frac{8+03}{2 + ((57 \times 6) + 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{192647} := \frac{8+03}{1-9+2647}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{5621} := \frac{8-03}{5 \times (6+2-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{41756} := \frac{8-03}{4 \times (1 + ((7-5)^6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{215496} := \frac{8+03}{2 \times (1 + 5 \times 49) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{8+0 \times 3}{56 \times (2-1)}$	$:= \frac{8+0 \times 3}{417+5-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{245791} := \frac{8+03}{((2+4) \times 5 + 7) \times 91}$
$:= \frac{8+03}{56+21}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{47596} := \frac{8+03}{4 + ((7+5) \times 9 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{254916} := \frac{8+03}{(2^5 + 4) \times (91 + 6)}$
$:= \frac{8 \times 03}{56 \times (2+1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{56721} := \frac{8+03}{56+721}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{427196} := \frac{8+0 \times 3}{4271-9-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{5694} := \frac{8+03}{5+(69+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{67452} := \frac{8+03}{6 \times (7 \times (4 \times 5 + 2))}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 03}{(4+2^7+1) \times 96}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{7592} := \frac{8+03}{7+(5+92)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{126947} := \frac{8+03}{(1-(2-6) \times 9) \times 47}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{927465} := \frac{8+0 \times 3}{(9+2) \times 7 \times 4 \times 6 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{9271} := \frac{8+03}{(9 \times 2 \times 7) + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{142569} := \frac{8+03}{(1-4 \times (2-56)) \times 9}$	
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{803}{172645} := \frac{8+0 \times 3}{172 \times (6-4) \times 5}$	

● Numerator 804

$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{2613} := \frac{8 \times 04}{26 \times (1+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{6231} := \frac{8 \times 04}{62 \times (3+1)}$	$:= \frac{8-04}{1+(5 \times (2+7+6))}$
$:= \frac{8-04}{(2 \times (6-1)) + 3}$	$:= \frac{8-04}{(6 \times (2+3)) + 1}$	$:= \frac{8+0 \times 4}{152 \times (7-6)}$
$:= \frac{8+0 \times 4}{2+(6 \times (1+3))}$	$:= \frac{8+04}{62+31}$	$:= \frac{8+04}{1 \times ((5-2) \times 76)}$
$:= \frac{8+04}{26+13}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{7236} := \frac{8-04}{7+(23+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{23517} := \frac{8+0 \times 4}{235-17}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{3216} := \frac{8-04}{32-16}$	$:= \frac{8+0 \times 4}{(7+2+3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{27135} := \frac{8-04}{(2+7 \times 1) \times 3 \times 5}$
$:= \frac{8+0 \times 4}{32 \times 16}$	$:= \frac{8+04}{72+36}$	$:= \frac{8+0 \times 4}{27+(1 \times 3^5)}$
$:= \frac{8+04}{32+16}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{12395} := \frac{8+04}{1-(2 \times (3-95))}$	$:= \frac{8+04}{27 \times (1 \times 3 \times 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{5293} := \frac{8+04}{52+9 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{15276} := \frac{8 \times 04}{(1+5+2) \times 76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{804}{62913} := \frac{8+0 \times 4}{629-1 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{80 + 4}{6 \times 2 + (9^{1+3})} & := \frac{80 - 4}{(12 + 7) \times 635} & := \frac{8 - 04}{(236 - 17) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{72695} & := \frac{8 + 04}{(72 \times (6 + 9)) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{195372} & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 4}{(19 + 5 + 3) \times 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{267531} & := \frac{8 - 04}{267 \times 5 - 3 - 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{72963} & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 4}{729 - 6 + 3} & & := \frac{8 + 04}{((1 + 9) \times 5 - 3 + 7)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{271953} & := \frac{8 - 04}{27 \times (1 + 9) \times 5 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{127635} & := \frac{8 + 04}{127 \times (6 - 3) \times 5} & & := \frac{8^{04}}{(19 + 5)^3 \times 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{273159} & := \frac{8 - 04}{(2 \times 73 \times 1 + 5) \times 9} \\ & := \frac{8 \times 04}{(1^2 + 7) \times 635} & & := \frac{8 - 04}{(1 \times 9 - 5) \times 3^{7-2}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{356172} & := \frac{8 - 04}{3 + 5 + (6 \times 1 \times 7)^2} \\ & := \frac{8 - 04}{(1 + 2 \times 7 \times (6 + 3)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{215673} & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 4}{2156 - 7 - 3} \\ & := \frac{80 + 4}{(1 + 2) \times 7 \times 635} & \blacktriangleright \frac{804}{236175} & := \frac{8 + 04}{(2^3 \times 6 - 1) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 805

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{805}{1932} := \frac{8 \times 05}{1 + (93 + 2)} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{805}{29463} := \frac{8 \times 05}{(2^9 - 4 \times 6) \times 3}$$

● Numerator 806

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{5239} & := \frac{8 - 06}{5 + (2 - 3 + 9)} & := \frac{8 \times 06}{1 \times (2 \times (4 \times 93))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{43927} & := \frac{8 - 06}{4 - ((3 - (9 \times 2)) \times 7)} \\ & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 6}{(5^2) + 3 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{17329} & := \frac{8 - 06}{17 - (3 - 29)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{59241} & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 6}{592 - 4 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{8 + 06}{52 + 39} & & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 6}{1 + ((7 \times 3 - 2) \times 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{241397} & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 6}{2 + (41 - 3) \times 9 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{7254} & := \frac{8 - 06}{7 + (2 + 5 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{21359} & := \frac{8 - 06}{(2 \times (1 + 3)) + 5 \times 9} & & := \frac{8 + 06}{(2^4 \times 1)^3 + 97} \\ & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 6}{72 \times (5 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{42315} & := \frac{8 - 06}{((4 \times (2 + 3)) + 1) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{321594} & := \frac{8 - 06}{3 \times (2 \times 15 \times 9 - 4)} \\ & := \frac{8 + 06}{7 \times (2 \times (5 + 4))} & & := \frac{8 + 0 \times 6}{42 \times ((3 - 1) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{425971} & := \frac{8 - 06}{4^2 \times (59 + 7) + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{806}{12493} & := \frac{8 - 06}{1 - (2 \times ((4 - 9) \times 3))} & & := \frac{8 + 06}{4 + (2 + (3^{1+5}))} \\ & := \frac{8 + 06}{1 + (2 \times (4 \times (9 \times 3)))} & & := \frac{8 \times 06}{4 \times (2 \times 315)} \end{aligned}$$

- Numerator 807

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{1345} &:= \frac{8+07}{(1^3+4)\times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{45192} &:= \frac{8+0\times 7}{14+(5\times 26)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{5649} &:= \frac{8^{07}}{56\times (4^9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{215469} &:= \frac{8-07}{(4+(5+19))\times 2} \\ &:= \frac{8-07}{56-49} & &:= \frac{8+0\times 7}{(45\times (1+9))-2} \\ &:= \frac{8+07}{56+49} & \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{236451} &:= \frac{8\times 07}{(4\times (5+(1\times 9)))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{9415} &:= \frac{8+07}{(9\times 4-1)\times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{651249} &:= \frac{80+7}{(6^5+1+24)\times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{807}{14526} &:= \frac{8-07}{1-(4+(5-26))} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 809

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{809}{6472} &:= \frac{8^{09}}{64^{7-2}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{809}{14562} &:= \frac{8\times 09}{(1^4+5)^{6-2}} & &:= \frac{8+09}{(3\times 27+6^4)\times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8\times 09}{64\times (7+2)} & &:= \frac{8+0\times 9}{((1-4+5)\times 6)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{809}{473265} &:= \frac{8+0\times 9}{4\times (7+32)\times 6\times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8+09}{64+72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{809}{37214} &:= \frac{8+0\times 9}{372-1\times 4} \\ &:= \frac{8+0\times 9}{(6\times (4+7))-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{809}{327645} &:= \frac{8+0\times 9}{3\times (2+7)\times 6\times 4\times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 810

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{2673} &:= \frac{8\times 10}{267-3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{6237} &:= \frac{8\times 10}{623-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{94725} &:= \frac{8+10}{((9\times 47)-2)\times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{2745} &:= \frac{8+10}{(2\times 7\times 4)+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{6345} &:= \frac{8+10}{6+(3\times 45)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{346275} &:= \frac{8+10}{3^4\times (6\times 2+7)\times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{3465} &:= \frac{8+10}{(3\times (4\times 6))+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{7695} &:= \frac{8+10}{76+95} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{362475} &:= \frac{8\times 1+0}{(3^6-2-4-7)\times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{3564} &:= \frac{8\times 10}{356-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{29475} &:= \frac{8+10}{2+((94\times 7)-5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{374625} &:= \frac{8\times 1+0}{37\times (4+6)\times 2\times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{3645} &:= \frac{8\times 10}{3\times (6\times 4\times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{43965} &:= \frac{8+10}{4\times 3+965} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{462375} &:= \frac{8+10}{(4\times (6+2)^3+7)\times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8+10}{36+45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{64395} &:= \frac{8+10}{6^4+(3\times 9\times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{5346} &:= \frac{8\times 10}{534-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{810}{94365} &:= \frac{8\times 1+0}{943-(6+5)} \end{aligned}$$

- Numerator 812

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{3045} &:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{3 \times (0 + 4 \times 5)} & := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{3 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 0)))} & := \frac{8 + 12}{63 \times ((9 - 4) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{8 + 12}{30 + 45} & := \frac{8 + 1^2}{365 + 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{354960} := \frac{8 - 1^2}{(3 \times 5 \times 4 - 9) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{3596} &:= \frac{(8 - 1) \times 2}{3 + (5 + (9 \times 6))} & := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{36 \times (5 \times (4 + 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{369054} := \frac{(8 + 1) \times 2}{(3 + 6) \times (905 + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{3654} &:= \frac{81 \times 2}{3^6 \times (5 - 4)} & := \frac{(8 + 1) \times 2}{3 \times (6 \times (5 + 40))} & := \frac{8 - 1 \times 2}{3 + 6 \times (90 \times 5 + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{8 - 1 \times 2}{36 - (5 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{45936} := \frac{8 - 1^2}{(4 + (59 + 3)) \times 6} & := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{3690 - 54} \\
 &:= \frac{8 \times 1^2}{36 \times (5 - 4)} & := \frac{(8 - 1) \times 2}{4 + (59 + 3^6)} & := \frac{8 + 12}{36 + 9054} \\
 &:= \frac{8 + 1 \times 2}{3 \times (6 + 5 + 4)} & := \frac{(8 - 1)^2}{(459 + 3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{376594} := \frac{(8 - 1) \times 2}{3 - 76 + 5 + 9^4} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - 1) \times 2}{3 + (6 + 54)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{47096} := \frac{(8 - 1)^2}{(4 \times 709) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{395647} := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{3 - 95 \times (6 - 47)} \\
 &:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{3 + (65 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{49735} := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{(4 + (97 - 3)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{459360} := \frac{(8 - 1)^2}{(459 + 3) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + 1) \times 2}{3^{(6-5) \times 4}} & := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{4 \times (9 - (7 - (3^5)))} & := \frac{8 - 1^2}{(4 + 59 + 3) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{8 + 12}{36 + 54} & := \frac{8 \times (1 + 2)}{(49 - 7) \times 35} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{476035} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{4 \times (7 + 60) \times 35} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{4756} &:= \frac{8 - 1^2}{4 + (7 + 5 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{59073} := \frac{8 + 12}{5 \times ((90 + 7) \times 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{497350} := \frac{8 + 12}{49 \times (7 + 3^5) + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{9570} &:= \frac{(8 - 1) \times 2}{95 + 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{59740} := \frac{8 - 1^2}{5 \times (9 \times 7 + 40)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{639450} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{(6^3 + 9 \times 4) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{35496} &:= \frac{8 - 1^2}{((3 \times 5 \times 4) - 9) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{63945} := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{63 \times (9 - 4 + 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{812}{36540} &:= \frac{8 - 1^2}{3 \times (65 + 40)} & := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{(6^3 + 9 \times 4) \times 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 813

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{4065} &:= \frac{8^{1+3}}{(40^6) \times 5} & := \frac{8 - 1 + 3}{(4 + 06) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{5420} := \frac{8 + 1 - 3}{5 \times (4 \times (2 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{8 - 1 - 3}{4 \times ((0 \times 6) + 5)} & := \frac{8 + 13}{40 + 65} & := \frac{8 + 1 + 3}{5 \times (4^2 + 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{8 \times 1^3}{40 \times (6 - 5)} & := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 3}{4 \times (0 + 6 \times 5)} & := \frac{(8 + 1) \times 3}{(5 + 4) \times 20}
 \end{aligned}$$

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{9756} &:= \frac{8-1 \times 3}{(9-7) \times 5 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8+(71-3)}{9+(7+56)} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 1^3}{97+5-6} \\ &:= \frac{8+1^3}{9 \times ((7-5) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{81-3}{6 \times (0+975)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{75609} &:= \frac{8+1-3}{(7-(5-60)) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{97560} &:= \frac{8-1-3}{(9+7) \times (5 \times (6+0))} \\ &:= \frac{8-1 \times 3}{(9-7) \times (5 \times 60)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{296745} &:= \frac{8-1-3}{2+9 \times 6 \times (7+4 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{8-1+3}{2-96 \times (7-45)} \\ &:= \frac{8+1^3}{((2+9) \times 6+7) \times 45} \\ &:= \frac{8+1-3}{2+(9-6)^7-4+5} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{56097} &:= \frac{8-1 \times 3}{5 \times (6-(0-(9 \times 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 1^3}{5+((60 \times 9)+7)} \\ &:= \frac{8+1^3}{5+(609+7)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{247965} &:= \frac{8-1-3}{(247-9+6) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 3}{24 \times (7+9 \times 6) \times 5} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{409752} &:= \frac{8-1 \times 3}{4 \times 09 \times 7 \times 5 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{8-1+3}{40 \times 9 \times (7+5+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{547962} &:= \frac{8+1^3}{(5+4) \times (7 \times 96+2)} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{60975} &:= \frac{8-1 \times 3}{60+(9 \times 7 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{8+1-3}{6 \times ((0 \times 9)+75)} \\ &:= \frac{8-1^3}{(6+09) \times 7 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 1^3}{60 \times ((9-7) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{8 \times 1^3}{2 \times 4 \times (7+9 \times 6) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{250946} &:= \frac{8+1-3}{(2-4+7 \times 9) \times 6 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{250946} &:= \frac{8+1-3}{2-50 \times (9-46)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{602975} &:= \frac{8+1^3}{(60+29) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{813}{650942} &:= \frac{8+1^3}{6+50 \times 9 \times 4^2} \end{aligned}$

● Numerator 814

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{962} &:= \frac{8-1+4}{9+6-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{2035} &:= \frac{8-1 \times 4}{2-(0-3-5)} \\ &:= \frac{8+1 \times 4}{2 \times (0+3 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{8+14}{20+35} \\ &:= \frac{(8-1) \times 4}{2 \times (0+35)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{8+1^4}{(3-2+5) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8+1 \times 4}{3 \times (2 \times 5+6)} \\ &:= \frac{8+14}{32+56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{7326} &:= \frac{8-1 \times 4}{7+(3+26)} \\ &:= \frac{8+1-4}{7+(32+6)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(8-1) \times 4}{7 \times (3 \times 2 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{23976} &:= \frac{81-4}{2 \times (3 \times (9 \times 7 \times 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{27306} &:= \frac{8+14}{2+(7+(3^6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{32560} &:= \frac{8-1^4}{(3+2) \times (56+0)} \\ &:= \frac{8+1^4}{(3-2+5) \times 60} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{3256} &:= \frac{8-1-4}{3-(2-(5+6))} \\ &:= \frac{8-1 \times 4}{3+(2+5+6)} \\ &:= \frac{8+1-4}{(3^2)+5+6} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{8 \times 1^4}{(7+3+2) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8+1^4}{73+2+6} \\ &:= \frac{8-1+4}{73+26} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{32967} &:= \frac{81 \times 4}{3 \times (2 \times ((9-6)^7))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{814}{37296} &:= \frac{8-1+4}{3 \times (7 \times (2 \times 9+6))} \end{aligned}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{39072} := \frac{8-1-4}{(3+(9+0 \times 7))^2}$ $:= \frac{8+1^4}{(3-9) \times (0-72)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{76923} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 4}{7 \times (6 \times (9 \times 2^3))}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{79365} := \frac{8-1 \times 4}{(7+9-3) \times 6 \times 5}$	$:= \frac{8+1 \times 4}{2 \times (9-6)^7 \times 03}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{307692} := \frac{8-1 \times 4}{(30 \times 7+6) \times (9-2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{52096} := \frac{8+1-4}{5 \times (2^{0 \times 9+6})}$	$:= \frac{(8-1) \times 4}{7 \times ((9-3) \times 65)}$	$:= \frac{8+1-4}{30 \times (7+6 \times 9+2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{72039} := \frac{8 \times 1^4}{720-(3+9)}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 4}{(7+9) \times (3 \times 65)}$	$:= \frac{81 \times 4}{3^{07} \times (6 \times 9+2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{73260} := \frac{8-1-4}{7+(3+260)}$ $:= \frac{8-1 \times 4}{(7-3+2) \times 60}$ $:= \frac{8+1-4}{(73+2) \times (6+0)}$ $:= \frac{8 \times 1^4}{(7+3+2) \times 60}$ $:= \frac{(8-1) \times 4}{7 \times (3 \times 2 \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{97236} := \frac{8+14}{((9 \times (7^2)) - 3) \times 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{230769} := \frac{8 \times 1^4}{2 \times 3 \times 07 \times 6 \times 9}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{239760} := \frac{81-4}{2 \times 3 \times 9 \times 7 \times 60}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{296703} := \frac{(8+1) \times 4}{2 \times (9-6)^7 \times 03}$ $:= \frac{8-1 \times 4}{2 \times 9 \times (-6+7) \times 03}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{372960} := \frac{8-1+4}{(3+72+9) \times 60}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{692307} := \frac{8+1 \times 4}{6 \times 9^2 \times 3 \times 07}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{793650} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 4}{(7+9) \times 3 \times 650}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{923076} := \frac{8+1 \times 4}{9^2+3^{07} \times 6}$ $:= \frac{8+1^4}{9^2 \times 3 \times 07 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{73926} := \frac{8-1+4}{73+926}$		

• Numerator 815

$\blacktriangleright \frac{815}{2934} := \frac{81 \times 5}{2 \times (9 \times (3^4))}$ $:= \frac{(8-1) \times 5}{2 \times 9 \times (3+4)}$	$:= \frac{8+1^5}{3 \times 2 \times 6+0}$ $:= \frac{8+15}{32+60}$ $:= \frac{8 \times (1+5)}{3 \times 2^6+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{815}{29340} := \frac{8-1-5}{29+3+40}$
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• Numerator 816

$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{952} := \frac{8+16}{(9+5) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{(8+1) \times 6}{9 \times (5+2)}$	$:= \frac{8+16}{2+(75+4)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{3502} := \frac{8+16}{3+(50 \times 2)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{3570} := \frac{8 \times 16}{(3+5) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{8+16}{3 \times (5 \times 7+0)}$ $:= \frac{8 \times (1+6)}{35 \times (7+0)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{3927} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{3 \times ((9+2) \times 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{2754} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{27 \times (5-4)}$		

$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{4352} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{4 \times ((3 + 5)^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{40392} := \frac{8 - 1 \times 6}{4 - (0 - (3 + 92))}$	$:= \frac{8 - 1 + 6}{9 \times ((5 \times 4 - 7)^2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{4590} := \frac{8 + 16}{45 + 90}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 1^6}{4 - (0 - 392)}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(9 \times 5^4) - (7 + 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{5032} := \frac{8 + 16}{(50 \times 3) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{43520} := \frac{8 + 1 - 6}{4 + (3 \times (52 + 0))}$	$:= \frac{8 \times (1 + 6)}{(95 - 4) \times 72}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{7259} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{7 \times (2 + 59)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{43792} := \frac{8 + 16}{(4 + 3 + 7) \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{379542} := \frac{8 \times 16}{(3 \times (7 + 9) \times 5 + 4)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{9520} := \frac{8 + 16}{(9 + 5) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{47532} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{475 - (3^2)}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 1^6}{(3 + 7 \times 9 - 5)^{4-2}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{25704} := \frac{8 - 1 \times 6}{2 - (5 - (70 - 4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{49572} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{495 - (7 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{407592} := \frac{8 - 1 \times 6}{407 + 592}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{30294} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{3 - (0 - 294)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{52734} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{5 + (2 \times ((7 - 3)^4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{437920} := \frac{8 + 16}{(4 + 3 + 7) \times 920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{35904} := \frac{8 - 1 - 6}{3 + (5 - (9 \times (-04)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{93024} := \frac{8 + 1 - 6}{9 \times (30 + 2 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{495720} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{4 \times 9 \times 5 \times (7 + 20)}$
$:= \frac{8 \times 1^6}{(3 - (5 - 90)) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{95472} := \frac{8 - 1 - 6}{95 + ((4 + 7) \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{754392} := \frac{8 + 16}{(7 + 5) \times (4 + 39)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{37094} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{3^7 - 09 + 4}$	$:= \frac{8 - 1 \times 6}{9 - (5 \times (4 - 7^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{954720} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{9 \times (5 + 47) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{39270} := \frac{8 \times 1^6}{392 - 7 + 0}$	$:= \frac{8 - 1^6}{(95 - 4) \times (7 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{816}{957032} := \frac{(8 + 1) \times 6}{9 \times (5 + 7032)}$
$:= \frac{8 + 16}{3 + 9 \times 2^7 + 0}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 1^6}{9 \times ((5 + 47) \times 2)}$	
$:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{3 \times ((9 + 2) \times 70)}$		

● Numerator 817

$\blacktriangleright \frac{817}{4902} := \frac{8 + 1 + 7}{4 + (90 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{8 - 1^7}{(3 \times (9 + 6)^2 + 4) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{817}{390526} := \frac{8 - 1 \times 7}{(3 \times 9 - 05)^2 - 6}$	$:= \frac{8 + 1^7}{(3 + 96 - 2) \times 45}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{817}{396245} := \frac{8 - 1 \times 7}{(3 + 96 + 2 - 4) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{8 + 1 - 7}{((3 + 96) \times 2 - 4) \times 5}$

● Numerator 819

$\blacktriangleright \frac{819}{2340} := \frac{8 - 1^9}{(2 + 3) \times (4 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{819}{2457} := \frac{8 \times 19}{2 \times (4 \times 57)}$	$:= \frac{8 + (1 \times 9)}{2^4 + 5 \times 7}$
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$\frac{819}{2574} := \frac{8+1+9}{2+(45+7)}$	$\frac{819}{5460} := \frac{8+19}{4 \times (7+32)}$	$\frac{819}{25740} := \frac{8-1^9}{(2-4+5) \times 70}$
$\frac{819}{2730} := \frac{8-1^9}{(2-4+5) \times 7}$	$\frac{819}{6240} := \frac{(8+1) \times 9}{(5+4) \times 60}$	$\frac{819}{30576} := \frac{8-1^9}{(2^5 \times 7) - 4 + 0}$
$\frac{819}{2756} := \frac{81 \times 9}{(2-4+5)^7}$	$\frac{819}{6370} := \frac{8+1+9}{5 \times (4 \times 6 + 0)}$	$\frac{819}{34762} := \frac{8+1^9}{(3+05) \times 7 \times 6}$
$\frac{819}{3250} := \frac{8+19}{24+57}$	$\frac{819}{6734} := \frac{8+1^9}{54+6+0}$	$\frac{819}{54236} := \frac{8+1+9}{(3+2+7) \times 60}$
$\frac{819}{3276} := \frac{8-1^9}{25-7+4}$	$\frac{819}{67347} := \frac{8+1^9}{56+(4+2)}$	$\frac{819}{256347} := \frac{(8-1) \times 9}{3 \times (2 \times (7 \times 60))}$
$\frac{819}{3627} := \frac{(8+1) \times 9}{(2+7) \times 30}$	$\frac{819}{7462} := \frac{(8-1) \times 9}{6 \times (2 \times 40)}$	$\frac{819}{264537} := \frac{8+19}{((3^4 \times 7) + 6) \times 2}$
$\frac{819}{3640} := \frac{8+1^9}{27+3+0}$	$\frac{819}{7605} := \frac{(8+1) \times 9}{(6+3) \times 70}$	$\frac{819}{267345} := \frac{8+1+9}{((3-5+6) \times 7)^2}$
$\frac{819}{4732} := \frac{(8-1) \times 9}{2+(7 \times 5 \times 6)}$	$\frac{819}{20475} := \frac{8+1^9}{63+7+0}$	$\frac{819}{273546} := \frac{8+1^9}{5^4 - (23+6)}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{(8-1) \times 9}{(3+2) \times 50}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8+19}{(6-3) \times 70}$	$\frac{819}{372645} := \frac{8+1^9}{6+(734+0)}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1+9}{(3^2-7)^6}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8+1+9}{67+3^4}$	$\frac{819}{436527} := \frac{8-1^9}{(2+5 \times 63-4) \times 7}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+1+9}{(3+2+7) \times 6}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8+1^9}{67+3+4}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8 \times 1^9}{(25+6) \times 3^4 - 7}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+1^9}{3+(27+6)}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{81+9}{6+734}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8 \times 1^9}{2 \times 6^4 - 5 \times 3 + 7}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8 \times 1^9}{32 \times (7-6)}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8+1^9}{74+6+2}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1^9}{2+67 \times 34+5}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+19}{32+76}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8-1^9}{(7+6+0) \times 5}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+1+9}{(2+(7+3^5) \times 4) \times 6}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{(8-1) \times 9}{3 \times (2 \times 7 \times 6)}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8 \times (1 \times 9)}{(20+4) \times 75}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+19}{(3^4 \times 7 + 6) \times 20}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1^9}{3+((6-2) \times 7)}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8-1+9}{20^{4-7+5}}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+19}{(3^4 \times 7 + 6) \times 20}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{(8+1) \times 9}{(3+6) \times 40}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8+1+9}{(2+04) \times 75}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1^9}{(3+6-4)^5 - 7 - 2}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+1^9}{36+4+0}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8+1^9}{(20 \times (4+7)) + 5}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1^9}{3-6+5^{2+7-4}}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+1+9}{4+((7+3)^2)}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8+1^9}{(20 \times (6+5)) + 7}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1^9}{3^7 - 26 + 4^5}$
$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8+1^9}{4 \times (7+3 \times 2)}$	$\frac{819}{20657} := \frac{8 \times 19}{2 \times (4 \times 570)}$	$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1^9}{(4+(3 \times 6+5)^2) \times 7}$
		$\frac{819}{452673} := \frac{8-1^9}{(45+2+6) \times 73}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{819}{462735} &:= \frac{8 - 1^9}{4^6 - 2 \times 73 + 5} & := \frac{8 + 1 + 9}{(5 \times 2^7 + 4) \times 3 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{819}{563472} &:= \frac{8 + 1 + 9}{(56 \times 3 + 4) \times 72} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{819}{470652} &:= \frac{8 + 1^9}{470 \times (6 + 5) + 2} & := \frac{81 \times 9}{(5 \times 2^7 + 4) \times 3^6} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{819}{527436} &:= \frac{8 + 1^9}{(5 \times 2^7 + 4) \times (3 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{819}{560742} &:= \frac{8 + 1^9}{560 \times (7 + 4) + 2} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 820

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{1394} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{1 + (3 + 9 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{1763} &:= \frac{8 \times 20}{1 + (7^{6-3})} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{35916} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{((3 + 5) \times 9) + 1) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{1435} &:= \frac{8^2 + 0}{14 \times (3 + 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{4756} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{47 + 5 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{37146} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{3 + ((71 + 4) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 20}{1 + (43 + 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{6314} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{63 + 14} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{51496} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{(5^{1 \times 4}) + 9 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{1476} &:= \frac{8 \times 20}{(1 + 47) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{7134} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{7 - (1 - (3^4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{63714} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{63 + 714} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{1 + (4 + 7 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{13694} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{1 + ((3 \times 6 \times 9) + 4)} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{820}{16974} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 0}{1 \times (69 \times (7 - 4))} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 821

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{821}{36945} &:= \frac{8 - 2 - 1}{(3 + (6 + 9 \times 4)) \times 5} & := \frac{(8 \times 2) + 1}{(3^6) - (9 - 45)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{821}{96057} &:= \frac{8 + 2 - 1}{9 \times (60 + 57)} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 2 \times 1}{(3 - 6 + 9) \times 45} & := \frac{82 - 1}{(3 + 6) \times (9 \times 45)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{821}{369450} &:= \frac{8^2 - 1}{(3 + 6 \times 94) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 2 + 1}{3 \times (6 + (94 + 5))} & := \frac{8^2 - 1}{(3 + (6 \times 94)) \times 5} & := \frac{8 - 2 \times 1}{(3 - 6 + 9) \times 450} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (2 - 1)}{(3 + 6 + 9) \times 4 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{821}{45976} &:= \frac{8 - 2 \times 1}{(4 + (59 - 7)) \times 6} & := \frac{8 - 2 - 1}{(3 + 6 + 9 \times 4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 2 - 1}{(3 + (6 \times (9 + 4))) \times 5} & := \frac{8 - 2 + 1}{(45 \times 9) - (7 + 6)} & := \frac{8 - 2 + 1}{(3 + (6 + 9) \times 4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 2 \times 1}{3 \times (6 \times ((9 - 4) \times 5))} & := \frac{8 + 2 - 1}{4 \times ((5 + 9 + 7) \times 6)} & := \frac{8 \times (2 - 1)}{(3 + 6 + 9) \times 4 \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times 2) - 1}{(3^6) - (9 + 45)} & := \frac{8 + 2 + 1}{4 + ((5 + 97) \times 6)} & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times (9 - 4) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 2 \times 1}{(3^6) + (9 \times (4 - 5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{821}{60754} &:= \frac{8 + 2 + 1}{60 + 754} & := \frac{8 + 2 - 1}{(3 + 6 \times (9 + 4)) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{82 - 1}{(3^6 + 9^4) \times 5 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{821}{406395} & := \frac{8 - 2 - 1}{40 \times 63 - 9 \times 5} \end{aligned} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{821}{459760} := \frac{8 - 2 \times 1}{(4 + 59 - 7) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 2 - 1}{4 \times (5 + 9 + 7) \times 60}$$

● Numerator 823

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{823}{5761} & := \frac{8 - 2 + 3}{57 + 6 \times 1} & := \frac{(8 + 2) \times 3}{5 \times (7 \times (6 \times 10))} & := \frac{8 + 2^3}{(1 - 7 + 694) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(8 + 2) \times 3}{5 \times (7 \times 6 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{823}{176945} & := \frac{(8 - 2) \times 3}{(1 + 769 + 4) \times 5} & := \frac{8 + 2 + 3}{(1 + 7 \times 6) \times (9 + 4) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{823}{57610} & := \frac{8 - 2 - 3}{5 \times (7 \times (6 \times 1 + 0))} & := \frac{8 - 2 \times 3}{(1 + 7 + 6 \times (9 + 4)) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{8 - 2 + 3}{(57 + 6) \times 10} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 824

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{1957} & := \frac{8 + 2^4}{1^9 \times 57} & := \frac{(8 \times 2) + 4}{((1 + 35) \times 9) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{79516} & := \frac{8 + 2 - 4}{7 \times 9 + 516} \\ & := \frac{8 + 24}{19 + 57} & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 4}{1 \times ((35 + 9) \times 6)} & := \frac{8^2 + 4}{7 + ((9^5 - 1) - 6)} \\ & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 4}{1 \times (9 \times 5 - 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{19570} & := \frac{8 + 2^4}{1^9 \times 570} & \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{90537} & := \frac{8 + 2^4}{90 \times 5 + 3^7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{3605} & := \frac{(8 + 2) \times 4}{(3 \times 60) - 5} & := \frac{8^2 - 4}{19 \times (5 + 70)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{135960} & := \frac{8 - 2 - 4}{(1 + 35) \times 9 + 6 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{13596} & := \frac{8 - 2 - 4}{1 + (35 - 9 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{19673} & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 4}{1 + ((9 \times (6 \times 7)) + 3)} & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 4}{(1 \times 35 + 9) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{8 + 2 - 4}{1 - (3 - (5 + 96))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{30591} & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 4}{3 + 0591} \\ & := \frac{8 + 2 + 4}{135 + 96} & \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{51397} & := \frac{8 + 24}{51 \times 39 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{824}{75396} & := \frac{82 + 4}{7 \times 5^3 \times 9 - 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 825

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{825}{3960} & := \frac{8 + 2 + 5}{3 + (9 + 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{825}{19360} & := \frac{8 + 2 + 5}{1 - (9 - 360)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{825}{14960} & := \frac{(8 - 2) \times 5}{1 \times (4 + (9 \times 60))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{825}{39710} & := \frac{8 + 2 + 5}{3 + (9 + 710)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{825}{17930} & := \frac{(8 - 2) \times 5}{1 + (7 \times (93 + 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{825}{64130} & := \frac{8 + 2 + 5}{(6^4) - 130} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 826

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{1534} := \frac{8^2 + 6}{1 + ((5^3) + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{30975} := \frac{8 \times (2 + 6)}{30 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{410935} := \frac{8 + 2 - 6}{(410 - 9 - 3) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{1593} := \frac{8^2 + 6}{1 \times (5 \times (9 \times 3))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{54103} := \frac{(8 \times 2) - 6}{5^4 + (10 \times 3)} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{10974} := \frac{8^2 + 6}{10 \times (97 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{95403} := \frac{8 + 2 + 6}{(9 - (5^4)) \times (-03)} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{15930} := \frac{8^2 + 6}{1 \times (5 \times (9 \times 30))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{826}{374591} := \frac{8 + 2 - 6}{37 \times (4 + 5 \times 9) + 1} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 827

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{827}{1654} := \frac{8 + 2 - 7}{1 \times (6 \times (5 - 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{827}{4135} := \frac{8 + 2 - 7}{(4 - 1^3) \times 5} & := \frac{(8 + 2) \times 7}{(1 + 6) \times (5 \times 40)} \\ & := \frac{8 - 2 + 7}{1 \times (6 + 5 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{827}{41350} := \frac{8 + 2 - 7}{(4 - 1^3) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{8 + 2 + 7}{1 \times (6 \times 5 + 4)} & := \frac{(8 \times 2) - 7}{(4 - 1) \times 3 \times 50} \\ & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 7}{1 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)} & := \frac{8 + 27}{(4 + 1) \times 35} & := \frac{8 + 2 + 7}{(4 + 13) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{8 + 27}{1 + (65 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{827}{16540} := \frac{8 + 2 - 7}{1 \times (6 + (54 + 0))} & := \frac{8 + 27}{(4 + 1) \times 350} \\ & := \frac{(8 - 2) \times 7}{(16 + 5) \times 4} & := \frac{8 - 2 + 7}{1 \times (65 \times (4 + 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{827}{409365} := \frac{8 + 2 \times 7}{(40 \times 9 + 3) \times 6 \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(8 + 2) \times 7}{(1 + 6) \times 5 \times 4} & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 7}{1 \times ((6 + 5) \times 40)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{827}{453196} := \frac{8 \times 27}{(45 + 3^{1 \times 9}) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{8 \times (2 + 7)}{16 \times (5 + 4)} & := \frac{(8 - 2) \times 7}{(16 + 5) \times 40} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 829

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{829}{7461} := \frac{8 + 2 - 9}{7 - (4 - 6 \times 1)} & := \frac{8 - 2 + 9}{3 - (5 - 647)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{829}{74610} := \frac{8 + 2 - 9}{(7 - 4 + 6) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{8 - 2 + 9}{74 + 61} & \blacktriangleright \frac{829}{60517} := \frac{8 + 2 - 9}{60 + (5 + 1 + 7)} & := \frac{8 + 2 \times 9}{(7^4) - (61 + 0)} \\ & := \frac{(8 \times 2) - 9}{7 \times (4 + 6 - 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{829}{70465} := \frac{8 + 2 - 9}{(7 - (0 - (4 + 6))) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{829}{301756} := \frac{8 + 2 - 9}{301 + 7 + 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{829}{35647} := \frac{8 + 2 - 9}{(3 \times 5 \times 6) - 47} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{829}{356470} := \frac{8 + 2 - 9}{3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 4 + 70} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 830

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{1245} := \frac{8+30}{12+45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{17264} := \frac{8-3+0}{17 \times (26 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{127654} := \frac{8-3+0}{1+2 \times (76 \times 5+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{5146} := \frac{8-3+0}{(5 \times (1+4))+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{17596} := \frac{8-3+0}{1+(7 \times (5 \times (9-6)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{175296} := \frac{8-3+0}{(1+7+5-2) \times 96} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{9462} := \frac{8-3+0}{9+(4 \times 6 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{26975} := \frac{8 \times 30}{(2+6) \times 975} & \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{254976} := \frac{8-3+0}{2^{(5-4)^9+7} \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{14276} := \frac{8-3+0}{((1+4) \times 2)+76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{830}{125496} := \frac{8-3+0}{1 \times 2 \times (54+9) \times 6} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 831

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{831}{46259} := \frac{8-3+1}{46+(2^5 \times 9)} & := \frac{8-3+1}{24 \times (5 \times (9+7)-6)} & := \frac{8+3-1}{(4^{2 \times 7-9}+6) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{831}{57062} := \frac{8-3+1}{(5 \times 70)+62} & := \frac{8+3 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times (59 \times 7-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{831}{495276} := \frac{8 \times 3+1}{4+(9+5)^2 \times 76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{831}{76452} := \frac{8-3-1}{7+(((6 \times 4)-5)^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{831}{427965} := \frac{8-3 \times 1}{(4 \times 2^7+9-6) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{831}{907452} := \frac{8+3+1}{9 \times 07 \times 4 \times 52} \\ & := \frac{8-3 \times 1}{(7 \times 6+4) \times 5 \times 2} & := \frac{8-3-1}{(427-9-6) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(8 \times 3)-1}{(7-(6-45))^2} & := \frac{8-3+1}{(4^2 \times 7-9) \times 6 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{831}{245976} := \frac{8-3-1}{2 \times (4+(5+9) \times 7 \times 6)} & := \frac{8 \times (3-1)}{4^2 \times (7+96) \times 5} \end{array}$$

● Numerator 832

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{960} := \frac{8+3+2}{9+6+0} & := \frac{8 \times 3^2}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{1976} := \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{19 \times (7-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{975} := \frac{(8 \times 3)^2}{9 \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{1504} := \frac{8 \times 3+2}{1+(50-4)} & := \frac{8+32}{19+76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{1456} := \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{1 \times (4 \times 5-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{1560} := \frac{8+32}{15+60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{4056} := \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{40+5-6} \\ & := \frac{8+32}{14+56} & := \frac{8+3+2}{40^9-6} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{4160} &:= \frac{8-3+2}{41-(6+0)} & := \frac{8+3-2}{149+7+6} & := \frac{8+32}{14+7056} \\ &:= \frac{8+3+2}{4+(1+60)} & := \frac{(8-3) \times 2}{(1+((4 \times 9)-7)) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{149760} &:= \frac{(8-3) \times 2}{(1+4 \times 9-7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 3 \times 2}{4 \times (1 \times 60)} & := \frac{8+3 \times 2}{1 \times ((49-7) \times 6)} & := \frac{8-3 \times 2}{(1 \times 4+9-7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{8-3 \times 2}{4+(1 \times (6+0))} & := \frac{8 \times 3+2}{1 \times (4 \times (9 \times (7+6)))} & := \frac{8-3-2}{(1+4 \times (9-7)) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{4576} &:= \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{45-7+6} & := \frac{83 \times 2}{(1+497) \times 6} & := \frac{8-3+2}{(1+4+9+7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{(8-3) \times 2}{4+(57-6)} & := \frac{8-3 \times 2}{1 \times (4 \times (9 \times (7-6)))} & := \frac{8+3 \times 2}{(1 \times 49-7) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{(8+3) \times 2}{45+76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{17056} &:= \frac{(8+3) \times 2}{1+((70+5) \times 6)} & := \frac{83 \times 2}{(1+497) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{7104} &:= \frac{8+3+2}{7+104} & := \frac{8-3 \times 2}{1 \times ((7 \times 05)+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{176904} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1 \times 7 \times 6^{9-04}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{9750} &:= \frac{(8 \times 3)^2}{9 \times 750} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{40976} &:= \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{(4 \times (0+97))+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{194560} &:= \frac{8+3+2}{(1+9) \times (4+5 \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{14560} &:= \frac{8-3 \times 2}{1+(4+(5 \times (6+0)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{45760} &:= \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{4 \times 5+(7 \times 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{569140} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 \times 2}{5 \times (6+9^{1 \times 4})+0} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 3^2}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{79456} &:= \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{794-(5 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{14976} &:= \frac{8-3-2}{(1+(4 \times (9-7))) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{832}{147056} &:= \frac{8 \times (3-2)}{1470-56} \\ &:= \frac{8-3+2}{(1+(4+9+7)) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 834

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{6950} &:= \frac{8-3+4}{(6+9) \times (5+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{27105} &:= \frac{(8+3) \times 4}{2 \times (710+5)} & := \frac{8+3+4}{10 \times 6 \times (7+5^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{7506} &:= \frac{(8 \times 3)^4}{(7+(5+0))^6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{56712} &:= \frac{8-3-4}{5-(6-(71-2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{156792} &:= \frac{8-3-4}{1-5+6 \times (7+9) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{8+3-4}{7+(50+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{95076} &:= \frac{8-3-4}{(9 \times (5+07))+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{607152} &:= \frac{8+3+4}{60 \times 7 \times (1+5^2)} \\ &:= \frac{8-3+4}{75+06} & := \frac{8-3+4}{950+76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{15290} &:= \frac{8-3+4}{15 \times (2+9+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{834}{106752} &:= \frac{(8+3) \times 4}{1+06+75^2} \\ & & := \frac{8-3-4}{(1-06+7)^{5+2}} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 835

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{835}{1670} := \frac{8+35}{16+70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{835}{6179} := \frac{(8-3) \times 5}{6+179} & \blacktriangleright \frac{835}{46092} := \frac{8-3+5}{4 \times ((60+9) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{835}{6012} := \frac{8-3+5}{6 \times (0+12)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{835}{7014} := \frac{8-3+5}{70+14} & \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{835}{24716} := \frac{(8-3) \times 5}{24+716} & \\ & := \frac{(8-3) \times 5}{60 \times (1+2)} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 836

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{912} := \frac{8-3+6}{9+1+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{5472} := \frac{8-3+6}{(5-4) \times 72} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{25194} := \frac{8+36}{2 \times (51 \times (9+4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{1045} := \frac{8+36}{10+45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{7524} := \frac{8+3-6}{(7 \times (5+2)) - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{27094} := \frac{8+36}{2 \times (709+4)} \\ & := \frac{8-3+6}{75+24} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{54720} := \frac{8-3+6}{5 \times (4+(7 \times 20))} \\ & := \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{10 \times (4+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{75240} := \frac{8+3-6}{75 \times (2+4+0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{1254} := \frac{(8 \times 3) - 6}{(1+2) \times (5+4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{10792} := \frac{8+36}{1-(0-(7 \times 9^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{75924} := \frac{8-3+6}{75+924} \\ & := \frac{8+36}{12+54} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{214795} := \frac{8+36}{(21-4) \times 7 \times 95} \\ & := \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{1 \times (2 \times 54)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{219450} := \frac{8 \times 3 \times 6}{21 \times 9 \times 4 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{1520} := \frac{8-3+6}{1^5 \times 20} & := \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{1 \times (2 \times 540)} & := \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{2 \times 1 \times 9450} \\ & := \frac{(8+3) \times 6}{(1+5) \times 20} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{1957} := \frac{8+36}{1+(95+7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{19247} := \frac{8+36}{1+(92 \times (4+7))} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{2109} := \frac{8+36}{2+109} & \blacktriangleright \frac{836}{21945} := \frac{8 \times 3 \times 6}{21 \times (9 \times 4 \times 5)} & \\ & := \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{2 \times (1 \times 945)} & \end{array}$$

● Numerator 837

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{1296} := \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{(1-2+9) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{4650} := \frac{83+7}{(4+6) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{15624} := \frac{8+3+7}{1 \times (56 \times (2+4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{2046} := \frac{8+3+7}{20+4 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{6912} := \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{(6+9+1)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{24516} := \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{(2 \times 451) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{2916} := \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{2 \times (9 \times 1 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{10695} := \frac{8+37}{(106+9) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{29160} := \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{2 \times (9 \times (1 \times 60))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{4092} := \frac{83+7}{40 \times (9+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{12960} := \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{(1-2+9) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{54126} := \frac{8+37}{(54^{1 \times 2}) - 6} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{54219} &:= \frac{8+37}{(54^2)-1^9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{164052} &:= \frac{8+3-7}{(1+6) \times (4+0 \times 5)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{264195} &:= \frac{8 \times 3+7}{(26 \times 4-1) \times 95} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{102546} &:= \frac{8 \times 3+7}{(10-2+5^4) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{215946} &:= \frac{(8-3) \times 7}{215 \times (9 \times 4+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{421956} &:= \frac{8 \times 3+7}{4-2+1^9+5^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{104625} &:= \frac{8+3-7}{(1 \times 04+6)^2 \times 5} & &:= \frac{8-3+7}{(2^{15 \times 9}+4) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{469125} &:= \frac{8 \times 3+7}{(4+691) \times 25} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{105462} &:= \frac{8+3-7}{10 \times 54-6^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{241056} &:= \frac{(8-3) \times 7}{2^4 \times 105 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{629145} &:= \frac{83+7}{6 \times (2+9) \times (1+4^5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{126495} &:= \frac{8 \times 3+7}{(1+26 \times 4 \times 9) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{837}{246915} &:= \frac{8+3-7}{(246-9-1) \times 5} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 839

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{839}{2517} &:= \frac{8+3-9}{2+(5-17)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{839}{6712} &:= \frac{8+3-9}{6+(7+1+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{839}{72154} &:= \frac{8+3-9}{((7^2)-1-5) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{8-3+9}{2+(5 \times (1+7))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{839}{25170} &:= \frac{8+3-9}{2+(51+7+0)} & & \\ &:= \frac{8+3+9}{2+(51+7)} & &:= \frac{8-3+9}{(2+5-1) \times 70} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 840

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{840}{1365} &:= \frac{8+40}{13+65} & \blacktriangleright \frac{840}{16975} &:= \frac{8+40}{1-(6-975)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{840}{2765} &:= \frac{8+40}{2^7+6 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{840}{51639} &:= \frac{8 \times 40}{5-(16-(3^9))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 841

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{841}{7569} &:= \frac{8-4-1}{7+(5+6+9)} & &:= \frac{8-(4-1)}{(3-(0-27)) \times 6} & &:= \frac{84 \times 1}{6 \times (30 \times 7 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{8+4 \times 1}{(7-5) \times 6 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{841}{39527} &:= \frac{8-4 \times 1}{((3+9) \times 5) + (2^7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{841}{75690} &:= \frac{8-4 \times 1}{(75 \times 6) - 90} \\ &:= \frac{84-1}{756-9} & &:= \frac{8-(4-1)}{3+((9 \times (5^2))+7)} & &:= \frac{8+4 \times 1}{(7-5) \times (6 \times 90)} \\ &:= \frac{84+1}{756+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{841}{63075} &:= \frac{8-4-1}{(6-3+0) \times 75} & & \\ &:= \frac{8+41}{(75 \times 6) - 9} & &:= \frac{8-4 \times 1}{6 \times ((3+07) \times 5)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{841}{30276} &:= \frac{8-4-1}{30+(2+76)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 842

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{842}{6315} &:= \frac{8-4-2}{6+(3+1+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{842}{59361} &:= \frac{8-4-2}{(5 \times (9 \times 3)) + 6 \times 1} & & := \frac{(8+4)^2}{(6^{3 \times 1}) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{8-4+2}{(6+3 \times 1) \times 5} & &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 2}{5 + ((93 \times 6) + 1)} & & := \frac{8 \times (4-2)}{6 \times ((3+1) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 2}{6 \times ((3-1) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{842}{63150} &:= \frac{8-4-2}{(6-3 \times 1) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{842}{63571} &:= \frac{8+4-2}{(63 \times (5+7)) - 1} \\ &:= \frac{8+4^2}{(6^{3-1}) \times 5} & &:= \frac{8-4+2}{(6+3 \times 1) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{842}{91357} &:= \frac{8-4-2}{((9 \times (1+3)) - 5) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{(8+4)^2}{(6^{3 \times 1}) \times 5} & &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 2}{6 \times ((3-1) \times 50)} & & := \frac{8-4+2}{(91-3+5) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (4-2)}{6 \times ((3+1) \times 5)} & &:= \frac{8+4^2}{(6^{3-1}) \times 50} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 843

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{843}{1967} &:= \frac{8+4-3}{1 \times ((9-6) \times 7)} & &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 3}{((1+6) \times 5 \times 7) - 9} & & := \frac{8 \times (4-3)}{2 \times (10^{7-5})} \\ &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 3}{(1+9-6) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{843}{19670} &:= \frac{8+4-3}{1 \times ((9-6) \times 70)} & & := \frac{8-4-3}{(2+(10-7)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{84-3}{196-7} & &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 3}{(1+9-6) \times 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{843}{125607} &:= \frac{8-4-3}{(1+25) \times 6 - 07} \\ &:= \frac{84+3}{196+7} & &:= \frac{8-4+3}{210-(7 \times 5)} & & := \frac{8-4+3}{(-1+25 \times 6) \times 07} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{843}{5620} &:= \frac{8+4-3}{5 \times (6 \times 2+0)} & &:= \frac{8+4-3}{(2+1+0) \times 75} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{843}{16579} &:= \frac{8+4-3}{1+((6+5) \times (7+9))} & &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 3}{(2+10) \times 75} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 845

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{845}{1690} &:= \frac{(8 \times 4) - 5}{1 \times (6 \times (9+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{845}{9126} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 5}{9 \times (12 \times 6)} & & := \frac{(8 \times 4) - 5}{2 + ((1+9) \times 70)} \\ &:= \frac{8+45}{16+90} & &:= \frac{8+4-5}{(21 \times 9) - 7+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{845}{72163} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 5}{7 \times (((2+1)^6) + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (4+5)}{16 \times (9+0)} & &:= \frac{8+4+5}{(2^{1 \times 9}) - 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{845}{91260} &:= \frac{8-4+5}{912+60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{845}{2197} &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 5}{2 \times (19+7)} & & & & := \frac{(8+4) \times 5}{9 \times (12 \times 60)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(8+4)^5}{9 \times (12^6 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{845}{326170} := \frac{8+4+5}{3^{2+6} + 17^0}$$

● Numerator 846

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{1739} := \frac{8+4+6}{1 + ((7-3) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{8-4+6}{(3 + (1 \times 72)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{8+4-6}{(1 \times 539 + 7) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{2350} := \frac{84+6}{(2+3) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{8+4+6}{3 \times (1 + (7 \times (2^5)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{209573} := \frac{8+4+6}{(2 \times 09 - 5) \times 7^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{2397} := \frac{8+4-6}{(2 \times (3+9)) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{32571} := \frac{8+4-6}{(32 \times 5) + 71}$$

$$:= \frac{84+6}{(20 + 9 \times 5) \times 7^3}$$

$$:= \frac{(8-4) \times 6}{2 + (3 + 9 \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{8-4+6}{(32 \times (5+7)) + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{293750} := \frac{8+4+6}{2 \times (9+3-7)^5 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{3572} := \frac{8+4+6}{(3+5 \times 7) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{35720} := \frac{8+4+6}{(3+5 \times 7) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{8+46}{2 \times 9375 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{10293} := \frac{8+4-6}{(10^2) - (9 \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{57293} := \frac{8+4+6}{((5 \times 7)^2) - 9 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{307521} := \frac{8+4-6}{3^{07} - 5 - 2 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{15792} := \frac{8+4-6}{(15 \times 7) + 9 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{103259} := \frac{8+4+6}{1 + 03^{2+5} + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{317250} := \frac{8-4+6}{(3+1 \times 72) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{19035} := \frac{8+4-6}{1 \times (9 \times (0+3 \times 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{105327} := \frac{8-4+6}{10 \times 5^3 + 2 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{8+4-6}{3 \times (1+7 \times 2) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{8-4+6}{190+35}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{109275} := \frac{8+4-6}{10 \times 9^2 - 7 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{370125} := \frac{8+4-6}{3 \times 7 \times 0125}$$

$$:= \frac{8+4 \times 6}{1 \times (90 \times (3+5))}$$

$$:= \frac{8+46}{(1+092) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{84 \times 6}{(3 \times 70 \times 1)^2 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{21573} := \frac{8-4+6}{(21 \times (5+7)) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{152703} := \frac{8 \times 4 + 6}{(1 \times 5 + 2 \times 7)^{03}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{391275} := \frac{8+4+6}{(3+9 \times 12) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{29375} := \frac{84+6}{((2 \times (9-3)) - 7)^5}$$

$$:= \frac{8+4-6}{(1+5 \times (2+70)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{8+4-6}{(39-1 \times 2) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{31725} := \frac{8+4-6}{3 \times ((1+7 \times 2) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{846}{153972} := \frac{8+4+6}{(1-53) \times (9-72)}$$

● Numerator 847

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{847}{1925} := \frac{8-4+7}{1^9 \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{8+47}{(26+9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{847}{3025} := \frac{(8+4) \times 7}{30 \times 2 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{847}{2695} := \frac{8-4+7}{2 \times (6+9) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (4+7)}{(2+6 \times 9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{847}{6930} := \frac{8+47}{(6+9) \times 30}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{10395} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{1 \times (0 + (3 \times 9 \times 5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{12936} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{(1^2 + 9 \times 3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{13629} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{1 \times (3 + (6 \times 29))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{15092} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{1 \times ((5 + 09)^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{16093} &:= \frac{8+4+7}{1 + (60 \times (9-3))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{19250} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{1^9 \times 250} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{19635} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{1 \times ((9 \times 6 - 3) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{26950} &:= \frac{8+47}{(26+9) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{39501} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{3 + (9 + 501)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{61952} &:= \frac{8^4 \times 7}{((6 + 1 + 9)^5) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{65219} &:= \frac{8+47}{(65^2) + 1 + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{109263} &:= \frac{8+4-7}{(109-2) \times 6 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{129360} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{(1^2 + 9 \times 3) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{129536} &:= \frac{84-7}{1 \times 2^9 \times (5 + 3 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{153692} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{((1+5)^3 + 6) \times 9 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{163592} &:= \frac{8 \times (4 \times 7)}{(1 + (6 \times 3 + 5) \times 9)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{196350} &:= \frac{8-4+7}{1 \times (9 \times 6 - 3) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{216359} &:= \frac{84-7}{(21+6)^3 - 5 - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{847}{619520} &:= \frac{8^4 \times 7}{(6 + 1 + 9)^5 \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 849

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{12735} &:= \frac{8+4-9}{1 + (2 + (7 + 35))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{20376} &:= \frac{8+4-9}{(2 - (0 - (3 + 7))) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{150273} &:= \frac{8+4-9}{(150 + 27) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{8+4+9}{1 \times ((2+7) \times 35)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{36507} &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 9}{36 \times (50-7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{207156} &:= \frac{8+4-9}{(2^{07} - 1 - 5) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8 + (4 \times 9)}{(1 + (2^7 + 3)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{105276} &:= \frac{8+4+9}{(10 + 52) \times 7 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{367051} &:= \frac{8+4-9}{36^{7-05} + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{17263} &:= \frac{8+4-9}{1 - (7 - (2^6 + 3))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{849}{127350} &:= \frac{8 + (4 \times 9)}{(1 + 2^7 + 3) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{8+4+9}{1 \times (7 \times (2^6 - 3))} & &:= \frac{8+4+9}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 350} \\ &:= \frac{(8-4) \times 9}{((1^7 + 2)^6) + 3} & &:= \frac{8+4-9}{(1 + 2 \times (7-3)) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 850

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{850}{4692} &:= \frac{8 \times 50}{4 \times 6 \times 92} & \blacktriangleright \frac{850}{37162} &:= \frac{8 \times 50}{(3^7 - 1) \times (6 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{850}{417639} &:= \frac{8 \times 50}{(4^{1 \times 7} - 6) \times (3 + 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{850}{27914} &:= \frac{8 \times 50}{2 \times (7 + (9^{1 \times 4}))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{850}{139264} &:= \frac{8 \times 50}{(1 \times 3 + 9 - 2 + 6)^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{850}{29376} &:= \frac{8 \times 50}{2^9 \times (3 \times 7 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 851

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{851}{24679} &:= \frac{8 - 5 \times 1}{(2 \times (46 - 7)) + 9} &:= \frac{8 - (5 - 1)}{(6^2 \times 9) - (7 \times 4)} &:= \frac{8 - 5 - 1}{2 \times (06 + 79 \times 3)} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (5 - 1)}{2^4 \times (67 - 9)} &:= \frac{8^{5+1}}{((6 - 2)^9) \times 74} & \blacktriangleright \frac{851}{209346} &:= \frac{8 - 5 \times 1}{2 \times 093 \times 4 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 5 - 1}{(2 + 4) \times (67 - 9)} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 1}{(6 \times (2^9 - 7)) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{851}{246790} &:= \frac{8 - 5 - 1}{2 - 4 + 6 \times (7 + 90)} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (5 + 1)}{24 \times (67 - 9)} &:= \frac{8 + 5 \times 1}{(6 - 2 + 9) \times 74} & \blacktriangleright \frac{851}{309764} &:= \frac{8 - 5 \times 1}{3 \times (097 - 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{851}{62974} &:= \frac{8 - 5 - 1}{(6 - 2) \times (9 + 7 \times 4)} &:= \frac{8 + 5 + 1}{62 + 974} &:= \frac{8 \times (5 + 1)}{(30 + 9) \times 7 \times 64} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 5 \times 1}{(6 \times 2 - 9) \times 74} & \blacktriangleright \frac{851}{206793} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 - 1}{20 \times 6 \times 79 - 3} \\ & & &:= \frac{8 - 5 \times 1}{2 \times 0 \times 67 + 9^3} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 852

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{1704} &:= \frac{(8 - 5) \times 2}{1 + (7 + 04)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{6390} &:= \frac{(8 - 5) \times 2}{6 + (39 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{147396} &:= \frac{(8 - 5)^2}{1 - 4 \times (7 - 396)} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 5^2}{1 \times (70 - 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{10437} &:= \frac{8 \times (5 - 2)}{(10 + 4) \times (3 \times 7)} &:= \frac{8 - 5 - 2}{1 \times 4 + 7 + 3 \times 9 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{85 - 2}{170 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{13490} &:= \frac{(8 - 5) \times 2}{1^3 + (4 + 90)} &:= \frac{8 - 5 + 2}{1 + 4 \times (7 - 3) \times 9 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{85 + 2}{170 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{14697} &:= \frac{8 \times (5 + 2)}{14 \times (6 + 9 \times 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{307146} &:= \frac{(8 - 5) \times 2}{3^{07} \times 1 - 4 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{3976} &:= \frac{(8 - 5) \times 2}{3 \times 9 + 7 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{39476} &:= \frac{(8 - 5)^2}{3 + (9 \times (4 + 7 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - 5)^2}{(3 \times (9 + 7)) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{852}{104796} &:= \frac{8 - 5 - 2}{(10 - 4 + 7) \times 9 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 5 + 2}{3 - (9 - 76)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 853

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{853}{1706} &:= \frac{85 - 3}{170 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{853}{16207} &:= \frac{8 - 5 + 3}{1 + ((6 \times 20) - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{85 + 3}{170 + 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 854

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{976} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{9-7+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{19276} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{1+(9^2+76)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{203679} &:= \frac{8+5 \times 4}{(20+3^6-7) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{2196} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{2+(1+9+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{21960} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{(2+1^9) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{369172} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{36 \times (91-7)+2} \\ &:= \frac{8+5 \times 4}{(2+1+9) \times 6} & &:= \frac{8+5 \times 4}{(2+1+9) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{396012} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{3 \times (9 \times 60+1) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{2379} &:= \frac{8+5 \times 4}{2-(3-79)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{29036} &:= \frac{8 \times (5-4)}{2-(90 \times (3-6))} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{3172} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{(3 \times (1+7))+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{130296} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{(13^{01}+9) \times 6} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{854}{10736} &:= \frac{8-5+4}{(10 \times 7)+3 \times 6} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 856

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{856}{4173} &:= \frac{8 \times 56}{((4-1)^7)-3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{856}{73402} &:= \frac{8+56}{(7^3) \times (4^{01})} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{856}{70192} &:= \frac{8+5-6}{7 \times (0+(1+9^2))} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 857

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{857}{932416} := \frac{8+5 \times 7}{(9^3+2) \times 4 \times 16}$$

● Numerator 859

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{859}{6013} &:= \frac{8 \times 5+9}{(6+01)^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{859}{14603} &:= \frac{8+5-9}{1+(4+(60+3))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 860

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{860}{49235} := \frac{8+60}{(((4 \times 9)^2) \times 3)+5}$$

● Numerator 861

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{3075} &:= \frac{8+6 \times 1}{(3+07) \times 5} & &:= \frac{86-1}{430-5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{4592} &:= \frac{8-6+1}{4+(5+9-2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{4305} &:= \frac{8-6-1}{(4-3+0) \times 5} & &:= \frac{86+1}{430+5} & &:= \frac{8+6+1}{4-(5-(9^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{86 + 1}{4 + (5 \times 92)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{24395} & := \frac{8 - 6 + 1}{2 - (4 \times 3 - 95)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{45920} & := \frac{8 - 6 + 1}{(4 - 5 + 9) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{249075} & := \frac{8 \times (6 + 1)}{24 \times 9 \times 075} \\ & := \frac{8 + 6 \times 1}{(2 + 4) \times 9 \times 075} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{257439} & := \frac{8 - 6 - 1}{2 + 5 + 7 \times 43 - 9} \\ & := \frac{8 - 6 + 1}{2 \times (5 + 7 \times 4^3) - 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{270354} & := \frac{8 - 6 - 1}{2 + (70 + 3 + 5) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{297045} & := \frac{8 - 6 - 1}{(2 + 9 \times 7 + 04) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{8 - 6 + 1}{(29 \times 7 + 04) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{8 + 6 \times 1}{2 \times (9 + 7^{04} + 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{324597} & := \frac{8 - 6 \times 1}{(3 + 2^4 \times 5) \times 9 + 7} \\ & := \frac{8 - 6 - 1}{3 + 2 \times (4 \times 5 \times 9 + 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{350427} & := \frac{8 - 6 + 1}{3 \times ((5 \times 04)^2 + 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{407253} & := \frac{8 - 6 - 1}{(40 + 7) \times 2 \times 5 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{597042} & := \frac{8 + 6 \times 1}{(5 \times 970 + 4) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{861}{759402} & := \frac{8 + 6 + 1}{7 \times 5 \times 9 \times (40 + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 862

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{862}{3017} & := \frac{8 - 6 + 2}{(3 - 01) \times 7} \\ & := \frac{86 - 2}{301 - 7} \\ & := \frac{86 + 2}{301 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{862}{15947} & := \frac{8 - 6 + 2}{1 + (5 \times 9 + (4 \times 7))} \\ & := \frac{8 + 6 - 2}{(1 + 5) \times (9 + (4 \times 7))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{862}{159470} := \frac{8 - 6 + 2}{(1^5 + 9) \times (4 + 70)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{862}{79304} := \frac{8 \times (6 - 2)}{(7 + 9^3) \times 04}$$

● Numerator 863

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{863}{12945} & := \frac{8 - 6 + 3}{1 \times ((2 + 9 + 4) \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 3}{1^2 + (94 - 5)} \\ & := \frac{(8 - 6)^3}{12 \times (9 - 4 + 5)} \\ & := \frac{8 + 6 - 3}{(1 + (2^{9-4})) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 3}{12 \times (9 \times 4 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{863}{50917} & := \frac{8 \times (6 - 3)}{1 \times (2 \times (9 \times 4 \times 5))} \\ & := \frac{(8 - 6)^3}{(50 + 9) \times (1 + 7)} \\ & := \frac{8 + 6 + 3}{(50 + 9) \times 17} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{863}{129450} & := \frac{8 \times (6 - 3)}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 4 \times 50} \\ & := \frac{8 + 6 - 3}{(1 + 2^{9-4}) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{8 - 6 + 3}{(1 \times 2 + 9 + 4) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 3}{12 \times 9 \times 4 \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 864

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{864}{972} & := \frac{8 + 64}{9 + 72} \\ & := \frac{8 \times (6 - 4)}{9 + 7 + 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{1092} := \frac{8 + 64}{10 + 9^2}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{1350} := \frac{8 + 6 \times 4}{1^3 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{31590} := \frac{8^{6-4}}{(31 - 5) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{192375} := \frac{8^{6-4}}{19 \times 2 \times 375}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{1392} := \frac{8 + 6 + 4}{1 \times (3 \times 9 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{35712} := \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{3 + (5 \times (7^{1 \times 2}))}$	$:= \frac{8 + 6 \times 4}{(1 \times 92 + 3) \times 75}$
$:= \frac{86 + 4}{1 + ((3 + 9)^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{35910} := \frac{8 \times (6 - 4)}{35 \times (9 + 10)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{305712} := \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{305 \times 7 - 12}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{1920} := \frac{86 + 4}{(1 + 9) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{53712} := \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{(53 \times 7 \times 1) + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{307152} := \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{30 \times 71 + 5 - 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{3159} := \frac{8^{6-4}}{(3^{1 \times 5}) - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{57132} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 4}{(5 + ((7 - 1) \times 3))^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{315792} := \frac{8 + 6 + 4}{3^{15-7} + 9 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{7392} := \frac{8 + 6 + 4}{73 + 9^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{135792} := \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 9 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{317520} := \frac{8 + 6 - 4}{3 \times 1 \times (7 \times 5)^2 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{9312} := \frac{86 + 4}{9 + (31^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{135972} := \frac{8 \times (6 - 4)}{(1 + 359) \times 7 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{317952} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 4}{(3 + 1) \times (7 + 9^{5-2})}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{10395} := \frac{8 + 6 \times 4}{(10 \times 39) - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{137520} := \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{13 \times 75 - 20}$	$:= \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{3 \times 1 \times (7 + 9^{5-2})}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{10752} := \frac{8 + 6 + 4}{(107 + 5) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{137592} := \frac{8 \times 6 + 4}{((13 + 7) \times 5 - 9)^2}$	$:= \frac{8 + 6 + 4}{3^{1+7} + 9 \times (5 + 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{10935} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 4}{(1 + 09) \times (3^5)}$	$:= \frac{8 \times (6 - 4)}{13 \times 7 \times (5 + 9) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{319572} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 4}{31 \times 95 + 7 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{13905} := \frac{8 + 6 \times 4}{(13 + 90) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{137952} := \frac{8 - 6 + 4}{13 - 7 + 952}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{379512} := \frac{8 \times 6 - 4}{379 \times 51 - 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{15072} := \frac{8 + 6 + 4}{(150 + 7) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{139752} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 4}{1 - 3 + 9 \times (7 + 5)^2}$	$:= \frac{(8 - 6) \times 4}{37 \times 95 - 1^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{15309} := \frac{8^{6-4}}{(1 + (5^3 + 0)) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{153792} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 4}{(15 + 3) \times 79 + 2}$	$:= \frac{8 \times (6 - 4)}{(37 \times 95 - 1) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{15390} := \frac{8 \times (6 - 4)}{15 + (3 \times 90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{175392} := \frac{8 \times 6 + 4}{(17 + 5)^3 - 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{592731} := \frac{8 + 6 \times 4}{(5 + 9 + 2 \times 7)^3 + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{17520} := \frac{8 + 6 + 4}{1 + (7 \times (52 + 0))}$	$:= \frac{(8 - 6) \times 4}{1 \times 7 \times (5^3 - 9) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{715392} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 4}{(7 + 1 \times 5)^3 \times 92}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{27135} := \frac{8 + 6 \times 4}{((2 + 7 + 1)^3) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{864}{175932} := \frac{8 \times (6 - 4)}{1 + 7 \times 5 \times 93 + 2}$	

● Numerator 865

$\blacktriangleright \frac{865}{1730} := \frac{8 - 6 + 5}{17 - 3 + 0}$	$:= \frac{8 + 6 + 5}{1 + (7 + 30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{865}{2941} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 5}{2 - (9 - 41)}$
$:= \frac{(8 - 6) \times 5}{17 + 3 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{865}{1903} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 5}{19 + 03}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{865}{7093} := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 5}{70 + 9 + 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{865}{7439} &:= \frac{(8-6) \times 5}{74+3+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{865}{9342} &:= \frac{8 \times 6 \times 5}{((9-3)^4) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{865}{19203} &:= \frac{(8-6) \times 5}{19+203} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{865}{24739} &:= \frac{(8-6) \times 5}{247+39} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{865}{93420} &:= \frac{8 \times 6 \times 5}{((9-3)^4) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 867

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{4913} &:= \frac{8-6+7}{49-1+3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{25143} &:= \frac{8+6-7}{2+((51 \times 4)-3)} & & := \frac{8-6+7}{3 \times (9 \times (015))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{5491} &:= \frac{8+67}{5 \times (4+91)} & & := \frac{8-6+7}{2+(((5-1)^4)+3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{91035} &:= \frac{8-6+7}{910+35} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{20519} &:= \frac{8-6+7}{205-1+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{34102} &:= \frac{8+6+7}{(3+410) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{23409} &:= \frac{8-6+7}{(23+4+0) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{867}{39015} &:= \frac{8+6-7}{3 \times (90+15)} \\ & & & := \frac{8+6+7}{(23+40) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 869

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{1027} &:= \frac{8-6+9}{(10 \times 2)-7} & & := \frac{8-6+9}{52+14} & \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{142753} &:= \frac{8-6+9}{14 \times 2^7 + 5 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{2370} &:= \frac{8-6+9}{23+7+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{30415} &:= \frac{8+6-9}{(30+4+1) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{302175} &:= \frac{8-6+9}{(30+21) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{4503} &:= \frac{8-6+9}{4+(50+3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{54273} &:= \frac{8-6+9}{5-(4-(2 \times (7^3)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{5214} &:= \frac{8+6-9}{5 \times (2+1 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{869}{130745} &:= \frac{8-6+9}{(1+30 \times (7+4)) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 870

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{1392} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{1 \times ((3+9) \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{3625} &:= \frac{8+70}{(3+62) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{9425} &:= \frac{8+70}{((9+4)^2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{1624} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{(16 \times 2)-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{3654} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{3+(6+54)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{14326} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{1+((43-2) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{2436} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{2+(4+36)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{4263} &:= \frac{8 \times 70}{(4 \times 2+6)^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{19546} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{1+((9+5) \times (4 \times 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{3596} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{3+(5+(9 \times 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{5916} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{5+(91+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{870}{25346} &:= \frac{8+7+0}{2+(5 \times ((3^4)+6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{870}{36192} := \frac{8+7+0}{3+(619+2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{870}{129456} := \frac{8+7+0}{12 \times (9 \times 4 \times 5 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{870}{912456} := \frac{8+7+0}{91+2^4+5^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{870}{45936} := \frac{8+7+0}{4+(59+3^6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{870}{219356} := \frac{8+7+0}{2 \times (1+9 \times 35 \times 6)}$$

• Numerator 871

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{871}{240396} := \frac{8-7 \times 1}{2+40+39 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{871}{306592} := \frac{8-7 \times 1}{(30 \times 6 + 5 - 9) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{871}{360594} := \frac{8-7+1}{3^6+05+94}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{871}{240396} := \frac{8-7+1}{2 \times (40-3+9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{87+1}{(30 \times 6 + 5 - 9)^2}$$

• Numerator 872

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{1635} := \frac{8 \times 72}{1 \times ((6^3) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (7 \times 2)}{1 \times (6 \times 350)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{91560} := \frac{(8-7)^2}{(9 \times 1 \times 5) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (7 \times 2)}{1 \times (6 \times 35)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{54936} := \frac{(8-7)^2}{5+(49+3+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{395016} := \frac{(8-7)^2}{3+9 \times 50 \times 1^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{6104} := \frac{(8-7)^2}{6+(1^{04})}$$

$$:= \frac{(8-7) \times 2}{(5 \times (4 \times (9-3))) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{8-7+2}{3 \times (9 \times (50+1) - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{6540} := \frac{(8-7) \times 2}{6+(5+4+0)}$$

$$:= \frac{8-7+2}{(5 \times ((4+9) \times 3)) - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{451369} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{(45+(1+3)^6) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{9156} := \frac{(8-7) \times 2}{9+(1+5+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(8+7) \times 2}{5 \times ((4 \times 93) + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{872}{16350} := \frac{8 \times 72}{1 \times ((6^3) \times 50)}$$

$$:= \frac{87+2}{((5^4) \times 9) - (3 \times 6)}$$

• Numerator 873

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{873}{1649} := \frac{8+7+3}{1+(6 \times 4+9)}$$

$$:= \frac{8-7+3}{2 \times (6 \times 1^9)}$$

$$:= \frac{87-3}{261-9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{873}{1940} := \frac{8+7+3}{1^9 \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{8+7-3}{26+1+9}$$

$$:= \frac{87+3}{261+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{873}{2619} := \frac{(8-7)^3}{(2 \times 6 \times 1) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{8+7+3}{2+(61-9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{873}{2910} := \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{2+(9-1+0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{2+(6+1^9)}$$

$$:= \frac{8+73}{(26+1) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{873}{6402} := \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{6+(4^{01})}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{14259} &:= \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{1 - (4 \times (2 - (5 + 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times 7 \times 3}{(14^2) \times (5 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 73}{(142 + 5) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{19206} &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{1 + (9 - (2 \times (-06)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{1 \times ((9 + 2 + 0) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 7 + 3}{1 + ((9^2 + 0) + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{20564} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 3}{((20 \times 5) + 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{26190} &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{2 \times (6 + (1 \times (9 + 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{2 \times ((6 - 1) \times (9 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 7 + 3}{2 \times (6 \times (1 + 9 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 73}{(26 + 1) \times 90} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{54126} &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{54 + (1 \times (2 + 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{105924} &:= \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{1 - 05 + 92 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{125906} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 3}{1 \times 2590 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{142590} &:= \frac{8 + 73}{(142 + 5) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{196425} &:= \frac{(8+7)^3}{(1 + (9 - 6 + 4) \times 2)^5} \\ &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{1 \times 9 + 6 \times (4 + 2^5)} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 7 + 3}{1 \times 9 \times (6 + 4) \times 2 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (7 + 3)}{((1 \times 9 + 6) \times 4)^2 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{216504} &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{2 \times (1 + 6 \times 5) \times 04} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{254916} &:= \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{2 \times (54 \times (9 - 1) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{2 + 5 \times (4 + 9 \times 1 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 7 + 3}{2^5 \times 4 \times 9 + 16} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{260154} &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{2 + 60 \times 1 \times 5 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{264519} &:= \frac{(8-7) \times 3}{(2 \times (6 + 45) - 1) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{2 + 64 \times 5 - 19} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{421659} &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{4 \times 2^{1+6} - 5 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 7 + 3}{42 \times (1^6 + 5 \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{8 + 7 - 3}{(4 + 2^{1+6}) \times 5 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{429516} &:= \frac{(8-7)^3}{4 + 2^9 - (5 - 1) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8 - 7 + 3}{4 \times 2^9 - 5 \times 16} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (7 + 3)}{(4 + 2) \times 9^{5-1} - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{873}{624195} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 3}{(62 + 4) \times 195} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 874

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{1932} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{1 + (9 + 32)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{2530} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{2 + (53 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{5106} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{5 + 106} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{5290} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{(5^2) + 90} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{20539} &:= \frac{(8-7) \times 4}{(20 \times 5) + 3 - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{23506} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{2 + (3 + 506)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{102695} &:= \frac{8 + 7 \times 4}{(10^2 - 6) \times 9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{190532} &:= \frac{(8-7)^4}{1 + 90 + 5^3 + 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{235106} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{2 + 3 + 5106} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{874}{609132} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{(60 + 9^{1+3}) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 875

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{875}{63910} := \frac{(8+7) \times 5}{6 \times (3 + 910)}$$

● Numerator 876

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{1095} := \frac{8+76}{10+95} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{2190} := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{2 \times (1+9+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{2409} := \frac{8+76}{240-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{3504} := \frac{(8-7)^6}{3+(5-04)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{(3+(5+0)) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{3942} := \frac{(8-7) \times 6}{3^{9-4-2}} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{3-(9-42)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7 \times 6}{(3 \times (9-4))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{9052} := \frac{8+7-6}{90+5-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{10293} := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{(1^{01})+93} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{24309} := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{2 \times ((4 \times 30)-9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{39420} := \frac{(8-7)^6}{3 \times (9+(4+2+0))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{41902} := \frac{8+7+6}{3+(942+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{41902} := \frac{(8-7) \times 6}{41 \times (9-02)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{51392} := \frac{8+7-6}{(51-3) \times (9+2)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7+6}{((5^{1+3})-9) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{54312} := \frac{(8-7)^6}{(5 \times (4 \times 3 \times 1))+2} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7-6}{(5+4) \times (31 \times 2)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8-7+6}{5+(431-2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{59130} := \frac{8+7 \times 6}{(5+9+1)^3+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{91542} := \frac{(8-7) \times 6}{((9+1-5)^4)+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{109354} := \frac{(8-7) \times 6}{1 \times 09^3+5 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{123954} := \frac{(8-7) \times 6}{1+(23 \times 9+5) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{130524} := \frac{(8-7)^6}{1+(30+5+2) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{142350} := \frac{(8-7) \times 6}{1+4^{2+3}-50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{150234} := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{(1 \times 5+02)^3 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{159432} := \frac{(8-7) \times 6}{(1+5) \times (94-3) \times 2} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(8-7)^6}{1+5 \times 9 \times 4+3-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{194253} := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{1+9+42^{5-3}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{215934} := \frac{8+7 \times 6}{(2+15) \times (9^3-4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{231045} := \frac{8 \times (7-6)}{2 \times (31+04^5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{876}{950314} := \frac{8 \times 7 \times 6}{((9 \times 5)^{03}+1) \times 4} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+76}{(9 \times 5)^{03}+1^4}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 879

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{1465} := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{1 \times (4+6+5)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7+9}{(14-6) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{2051} := \frac{8+7-9}{20-5-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{3516} := \frac{(8-7)^9}{3-(5-1 \times 6)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7-9}{3+(5+16)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{3 \times (5+1+6)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8-7+9}{35-1+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{4102} := \frac{8+7+9}{(3 \times 5+1) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{4102} := \frac{8+7-9}{(4+10) \times 2} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{(4 \times 10)+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{6153} := \frac{(8-7)^9}{6+(1^{53})} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{(6+15) \times 3} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7+9}{(61-5) \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{12306} := \frac{(8-7)^9}{1 \times ((2^3+0)+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{14650} := \frac{8+7-9}{((1+2) \times 30)-6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{14650} := \frac{8+7-9}{(14+6) \times (5+0)} \\
 \qquad := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{(1-4+6) \times 50} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7+9}{(14-6) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{15236} := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{(1+(5 \times (2+3))) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{35160} := \frac{(8-7)^9}{35-(1-(6+0))} \\
 \qquad := \frac{8+7-9}{3 \times (5 \times (16+0))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{8+7+9}{(3 \times 5 + 1) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{61530} & := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{(6+15) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{8+7+9}{(61-5) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{136245} & := \frac{(8-7)^9}{(1-3 \times (6-2^4)) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{8+7+9}{1 \times 3 \times 62 \times 4 \times 5} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{152360} & := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{(1+5 \times (2+3)) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{236451} & := \frac{(8-7)^9}{2-3+6 \times 45 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{8+7+9}{2+3+6451} \\ & := \frac{8+7-9}{2 \times 3 \times (6 \times 45-1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{341052} & := \frac{(8-7)^9}{3+410-5^2} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{426315} & := \frac{(8-7) \times 9}{(4 \times (2+6^3) + 1) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(8-7)^9}{(4 \times (2+6) \times 3 + 1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{879}{456201} & := \frac{(8-7)^9}{4 \times 5 \times (6+20) - 1} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 891

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{2376} & := \frac{8+9+1}{(2 \times (3 \times 7)) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{2430} & := \frac{89-1}{2 \times (4 \times 30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{2475} & := \frac{8+9+1}{2+(4 \times (7+5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{2673} & := \frac{8 \times 9 - 1}{(2^6 + 7) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{8+9-1}{2 \times (6 \times (7-3))} \\ & := \frac{8+9+1}{2 \times (6+7 \times 3)} \\ & := \frac{89-1}{267-3} \\ & := \frac{89+1}{267+3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{3240} & := \frac{8+91}{3^2 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{3465} & := \frac{8+9+1}{(3^4) - (6+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{3564} & := \frac{8 \times (9-1)}{(3-5+6)^4} \\ & := \frac{8+9-1}{(3+5)^{6-4}} \\ & := \frac{8+9+1}{3+(5+64)} \\ & := \frac{89-1}{356-4} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{89+1}{3 \times (5 \times 6 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{3645} & := \frac{8+91}{(3+6) \times 45} \\ & := \frac{89-1}{3 \times (6 \times 4 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{4653} & := \frac{8+9+1}{4+(6 \times (5 \times 3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{4752} & := \frac{8+9+1}{4 \times ((7+5) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{5346} & := \frac{8+9-1}{((5-3)^4) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{8+9 \times 1}{(5+3 \times 4) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{89-1}{534-6} \\ & := \frac{89+1}{534+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{5463} & := \frac{8+91}{5^4 - (6 \times 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{6237} & := \frac{8 \times (9-1)}{((6-2)^3) \times 7} \\ & := \frac{89-1}{623-7} \\ & := \frac{89+1}{623+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{6534} & := \frac{8+91}{6 \times ((5^3) - 4)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{8+9+1}{(6+5) \times (3 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{7425} & := \frac{8+9+1}{(7 \times 4 + 2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{20736} & := \frac{8+91}{(2^07) \times 3 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{26730} & := \frac{8 \times 9 - 1}{(2^6 + 7) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{32076} & := \frac{8 \times (9-1)}{3 \times ((2^07) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{35640} & := \frac{89+1}{3 \times (5 \times (6 \times 40))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{36450} & := \frac{8+91}{(3+6) \times 450} \\ & := \frac{89-1}{3 \times (6 \times (4 \times 50))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{47520} & := \frac{8+9+1}{4 \times ((7+5) \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{53460} & := \frac{8+9-1}{5 \times (3 \times (4+60))} \\ & := \frac{8+9 \times 1}{5 \times (34 \times (6+0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{62370} & := \frac{8 \times (9-1)}{((6-2)^3) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{891}{64053} & := \frac{8+9+1}{6^4 + 0 - 5 + 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{891}{65340} := \frac{8+9+1}{(6+5) \times (3 \times 40)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{891}{74250} := \frac{8+9+1}{(7 \times 4+2) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{891}{72063} := \frac{8+91}{7+(20^{6-3})}$$

● Numerator 892

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{892}{7136} := \frac{8-9+2}{7+(1^36)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{892}{51736} := \frac{8-9+2}{5+(17+36)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{892}{74036} := \frac{8-9+2}{7+(40+36)}$$

$$:= \frac{8+9-2}{(7+13) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{892}{71360} := \frac{8-9+2}{7+(13+60)}$$

$$:= \frac{8+92}{71+3^6}$$

$$:= \frac{8+9-2}{(7+13) \times 60}$$

● Numerator 893

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{893}{6251} := \frac{8-9+3}{6+(2 \times (5-1))}$$

$$:= \frac{8^{9 \times 3}}{4^{5 \times (7+2 \times 1^6)}}$$

$$:= \frac{8+9 \times 3}{4 \times 5 \times 7 \times 2^{1+6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{893}{16074} := \frac{8-9+3}{(16-07) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{8-9+3}{4^{5-7+2-1+6}}$$

$$:= \frac{8+9+3}{4^5 \times (7+2+1^6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{893}{60724} := \frac{8-9+3}{60+(72+4)}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times 9 \times 3}{(4 \times (5+7))^{2+1^6}}$$

$$:= \frac{8+9-3}{4^5 \times 7^{2-1^6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{893}{62510} := \frac{8-9+3}{(6 \times 25) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times 9^3}{(4-5+7 \times 2-1)^6}$$

$$:= \frac{89-3}{4^5 \times (7^2 \times 1-6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{893}{457216} := \frac{(8 \times 9)^3}{(4+5 \times (7-2-1))^6}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (9+3)}{4^5 \times (7+2-1) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (9-3)}{(4+5+7)^{2+1} \times 6}$$

● Numerator 894

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{3576} := \frac{8-9+4}{3 \times (5-7+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{37250} := \frac{8-9+4}{3+(72+50)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{123670} := \frac{8-9+4}{1-2 \times 3+6 \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{8+9+4}{3+(5+76)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{57216} := \frac{8-9+4}{(5 \times 7-2-1) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{362517} := \frac{8+9 \times 4}{3^6 \times 2+(5-1)^7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{7152} := \frac{8-9+4}{7+(15+2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{63027} := \frac{8 \times 9+4}{6 \times (30^2-7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{35760} := \frac{8-9+4}{3+(57+60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{894}{71520} := \frac{8-9+4}{(7+1 \times 5) \times 20}$$

● Numerator 895

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{895}{14320} := \frac{8 - 9 + 5}{1 \times (4 + (3 \times 20))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{895}{103462} := \frac{8 \times 9 \times 5}{(1 \times 034 \times 6)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{895}{132460} := \frac{8 - 9 + 5}{132 + 460}$$

• Numerator 896

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{1372} := \frac{8^{9-6}}{((1 + 3) \times 7)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (9 + 6)}{10 \times (7 + 5)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{31752} := \frac{8 \times 9 \times 6}{(3^{1 \times 7}) \times (5 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{3024} := \frac{8 \times (9 - 6)}{3^{0 \times 2 + 4}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{17024} := \frac{8 - 9 + 6}{1 + (70 + 24)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{345072} := \frac{8 \times (9 - 6)}{(3 + 4^5) \times (07 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{10752} := \frac{8 - 9 + 6}{1 - (0 - (7 + 52))}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 9 - 6}{107 + 5^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{21504} := \frac{8 - 9 + 6}{2 \times (15 \times 04)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{896}{30247} := \frac{8^{9-6}}{(30^2) + (4^7)}$$

• Numerator 897

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{10465} := \frac{8 - 9 + 7}{1 - (0 - (4 + 65))}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 9 + 7}{(10 + 46) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{40365} := \frac{8 \times (9 - 7)}{4 \times (0 + (36 \times 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{163254} := \frac{8 - 9 + 7}{(1 + 6) \times (32 \times 5 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{13524} := \frac{8 \times 9 - 7}{1 \times (((3^5) + 2) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{43125} := \frac{8 \times 9 - 7}{(4 + (3 - 1 \times 2))^5}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 9 - 7}{20 \times (4 \times 5 - 1) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{14053} := \frac{8 - 9 + 7}{1 + (40 + 53)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{135240} := \frac{8 \times 9 - 7}{(1 \times 3^5 + 2) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{351624} := \frac{8 - 9 + 7}{(3 \times 51 - 6) \times 2^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{14352} := \frac{8 \times (9 + 7)}{((1^4 + 3)^5) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{136045} := \frac{8 + 9 + 7}{(1 - 3^6) \times (0 \times 4 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 9 - 7}{35 \times (1 + 6) \times 2^4}$$

$$:= \frac{8 - 9 + 7}{1 + (43 + 52)}$$

$$:= \frac{89 + 7}{(-1 + 3^6) \times 04 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{403512} := \frac{8 \times 9 - 7}{40 \times (3^{5+1} + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 9 - 7}{1 \times (4 + (3 \times 52))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{897}{143520} := \frac{8 - 9 + 7}{(1 \times 43 + 5) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (9 - 7)}{1 \times (4 \times ((3 + 5)^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (9 + 7)}{(1^4 + 3)^5 \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{8^{9-7}}{(1 - (4 - 35))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 9 - 7}{(1 + 4 + 35)^2 + 0}$$

• Numerator 901

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{901}{37842} := \frac{9 - 01}{3 \times (7 \times (8 \times (4 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{9 + 01}{378 + 42}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{901}{46852} := \frac{9 - 01}{468 - 52}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 + 01}{(4 + 6 \times 8) \times 5 \times 2} \\ & := \frac{90 \times 1}{468 \times 5 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{901}{64872} & := \frac{9 - 01}{(6 \times (4 \times (8 - 7)))^2} \\ & := \frac{9^{01}}{6 \times ((4 + 8) \times (7 + 2))} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 + 01}{6 \times (4 \times ((8 + 7) \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{901}{75684} & := \frac{9 - 01}{(7 - 5 + 6) \times 84} \\ & := \frac{9^{01}}{(7 + 56) \times (8 + 4)} \\ & := \frac{9 + 01}{7 \times (5 \times (6 \times (8 - 4)))} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{901}{237864} & := \frac{9^{01}}{2378 - 6 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{901}{238765} & := \frac{9 + 01}{(2^3 + 87 \times 6) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 902

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{1435} & := \frac{90 - 2}{1 \times (4 \times 35)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{1476} & := \frac{9 + 02}{1 + (4 + 7 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{1845} & := \frac{90 - 2}{(1 + 8) \times 4 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{3157} & := \frac{9 \times 01}{(3 + 1 + 5) \times 7} \\ & := \frac{90 - 2}{315 - 7} \\ & := \frac{90 + 2}{315 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{3854} & := \frac{9 + 02}{3 + (8 \times 5 + 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{4756} & := \frac{9 + 02}{47 + 5 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{5863} & := \frac{9 \times 01}{(5 + 8) \times (6 + 3)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{6314} & := \frac{9 - 02}{63 - 14} \\ & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 2}{63 \times 1^4} \\ & := \frac{9 + 02}{63 + 14} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 01}{(6 + 3) \times 14} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{6478} & := \frac{9 + 02}{64 + 7 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{7134} & := \frac{9 + 02}{7 - (1 - (3^4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{35178} & := \frac{9 - 02}{351 - 78} \\ & := \frac{9 + 02}{351 + 78} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 01}{(3 + 5 + 1) \times 78} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{37146} & := \frac{9 + 02}{3 + ((71 + 4) \times 6)} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{63714} & := \frac{9 + 02}{63 + 714} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{67814} & := \frac{9 + 02}{6 + (7 + 814)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{167854} & := \frac{9 + 02}{(16 + 7) \times (85 + 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{315864} & := \frac{9 + 02}{3 \times (1 - 5 - 8 + 6^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{345876} & := \frac{9 + 02}{(3 \times 4 \times 58 + 7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{902}{381546} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 2}{3 + (8 + 1 + 5^4) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 01}{381 \times 5 \times 4 - 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 903

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{4816} & := \frac{9 - 03}{4 \times (8 \times 1^6)} \\ & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{48 \times 1^6} \\ & := \frac{9 + 03}{4^{8+1-6}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{5418} & := \frac{9 - 03}{54 - 18} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{5 + (41 + 8)} \\ & := \frac{9 + 03}{(5 + 4 \times 1) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 03}{(5 + 4) \times 18} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{7826} & := \frac{9 - 03}{78 - 26} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{(7 + 8 - 2) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{9 + 03}{78 + 26} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{8127} & := \frac{9 - 03}{81 - 27} \\ & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{(8 + 1) \times (2 + 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{9 + 03}{81 + 27} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 03}{(8 + 1) \times 27} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{16254} & := \frac{9 - 03}{1 \times (6 \times (2 \times (5 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{162 \times (5 - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 03}{1 \times (6^{2+5-4})} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 03}{(1 + 6 + 2) \times 54} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{17458} & := \frac{9 - 03}{174 - 58} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 58)} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 03}{(1 + 7 - 4) \times 58} \\
 & := \frac{90 - 3}{(1 + 7 \times 4) \times 58} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{26187} & := \frac{9 - 03}{261 - 87} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{261^{87}} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 03}{261 + 87} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 03}{(2 + 6 + 1) \times 87} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{48762} & := \frac{9 - 03}{4 \times ((8 + 7 - 6)^2)} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 03}{4 \times ((87 - 6) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 03}{((4 - 8 + 7)^6) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{56287} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{562 - 8 + 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{64715} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{((6 - 4)^7 + 1) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{158627} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{1586 + 2 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{287154} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 3}{(2 - 8 \times 7) \times (1 - 54)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{457821} & := \frac{9 + 03}{4 - 5 + 78^2 + 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{903}{547218} & := \frac{9 + 03}{54 + 7218}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 904

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{904}{1356} & := \frac{9 \times 04}{1 - (3 - 56)} \\
 & := \frac{90 - 4}{135 - 6} \\
 & := \frac{90 + 4}{135 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{904}{6328} & := \frac{9 \times 04}{(6 + 3) \times 28} \\
 & := \frac{9 - 04}{63 - 28} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 04}{63 + 28} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{904}{8136} & := \frac{9^{04}}{81 \times (3^6)} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 04}{(8 + 1) \times 36} \\
 & := \frac{9 - 04}{8 + (1 + 36)} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 4}{(8 + 1) \times (3 + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 04}{81 + 36} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{904}{15368} & := \frac{9 \times 04}{(1 + 5 + 3) \times 68} \\
 & := \frac{9 - 04}{1 \times (5 \times (3 + 6 + 8))} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 04}{1 + (5 \times (36 + 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{904}{87236} & := \frac{9 \times 04}{((8 \times 72) + 3) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{904}{173568} & := \frac{9 + 0 \times 4}{(1^7 + 35) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{9 + 04}{(17 + 35) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{9 - 04}{(1 \times 7 - 3) \times 5 \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{90 - 4}{(1 + 7^3) \times (56 - 8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 905

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{905}{1267} & := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1 + 2 + 6) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{90 - 5}{126 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{905}{23168} & := \frac{9 \times 05}{(23 + 1) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{905}{37648} & := \frac{9 \times 05}{3 \times ((7 + 6) \times 48)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{905}{41268} & := \frac{9 \times 05}{4 \times (1 + (2^6 \times 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 906

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{2718} &:= \frac{9-06}{2+(7 \times 18)} \\ &:= \frac{9+0 \times 6}{2+(7+18)} \\ &:= \frac{9+06}{27+18} \\ &:= \frac{90-6}{2 \times (7 \times 18)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 06}{(2+7) \times 18} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{4832} &:= \frac{9-06}{4^{8-3 \times 2}} \\ &:= \frac{9+0 \times 6}{48 \times (3-2)} \\ &:= \frac{9+06}{48+32} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 06}{4 \times (8 \times 3^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{5134} &:= \frac{9-06}{5+(1 \times (3 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{9+06}{5-(1-(3^4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{5738} &:= \frac{9-06}{57-38} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{7248} &:= \frac{9+06}{72-48} \\ &:= \frac{9+0 \times 6}{(7-2+4) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{9+06}{(7 \times 2^4)+8} \\ &:= \frac{90-6}{7 \times (2 \times 48)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 06}{(7+2) \times 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{7852} &:= \frac{9-06}{78-52} \\ &:= \frac{9+06}{78+52} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{8154} &:= \frac{9-06}{8-(1-(5 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{9+0 \times 6}{(8-1 \times 5)^4} \\ &:= \frac{9+06}{81+54} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 06}{(8+1) \times 54} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{18724} &:= \frac{9-06}{1+(8+((7^2)+4))} \\ &:= \frac{9+0 \times 6}{18+(7 \times 24)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{132578} &:= \frac{9+06}{(13-2 \times 5)^7+8} \\ &:= \frac{9-06}{1-3 \times 2 \times (5-78)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{143752} &:= \frac{9+06}{14^3-7 \times 52} \\ &:= \frac{9-06}{1+(4 \times 3+7) \times 5^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{148735} &:= \frac{90-6}{(14+8 \times 7^3) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{187542} &:= \frac{9-06}{1^8-7+5^4+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{906}{274518} &:= \frac{9+0 \times 6}{2745-18} \\ &:= \frac{9+06}{27+4518} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 907

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{907}{3628} &:= \frac{9-07}{36-28} \\ &:= \frac{9+0 \times 7}{3 \times (6-2+8)} \\ &:= \frac{9+07}{36+28} \\ &:= \frac{90-7}{((3 \times 6)^2)+8} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 07}{(3+6) \times 28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{907}{8163} &:= \frac{9-07}{8+(1+6+3)} \\ &:= \frac{9+0 \times 7}{(8+1) \times (6+3)} \\ &:= \frac{9+07}{8 \times (1 \times 6 \times 3)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 07}{(8+1) \times 63} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{907}{56234} &:= \frac{9-07}{(5 \times ((6+2) \times 3))+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{907}{62583} &:= \frac{9-07}{6 \times ((2 \times (5+8))-3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{907}{84351} &:= \frac{9+0 \times 7}{843-5-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{907}{412685} &:= \frac{9-07}{(4^{1+2}+6) \times (8+5)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 908

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{908}{1362} &:= \frac{9 \times 08}{1 \times (3 \times 6^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{908}{24516} &:= \frac{9 + 08}{2 + (4 + (5 + 16))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{908}{7264} &:= \frac{9 - 08}{72 - 64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{908}{35412} &:= \frac{9 - 08}{3 \times (5 - (4 - 12))} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 08}{(7 + 2) \times 64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{908}{35412} &:= \frac{9 + 08}{2 + (451 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 08}{72 + 64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{908}{15436} &:= \frac{9 - 08}{1 \times (5 - (4 \times (3 - 6)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{908}{15436} &:= \frac{9 + 0 \times 8}{354 - 1 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 910

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{2548} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{2^5 + 4 - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{8463} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{84 + 6 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{3276} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{3 + (27 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{8645} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{86 + 4 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{4368} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{4 + (36 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{8736} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{87 + 3 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{4732} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{4 \times (7 + 3 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{28574} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{2 + (8 \times (5 \times 7 + 4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{4823} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{48 + 2 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{32487} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{(3 + ((2 + 4) \times 8)) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{5642} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{56 + (4 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{38675} &:= \frac{9 \times 10}{(3 + 8 \times 6) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{5824} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{58 + 2 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{54236} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{5^4 - (23 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{6734} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{67 + 3 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{54782} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{5^4 - (7 + 8 \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{6825} &:= \frac{9 - 1 + 0}{(6 + 8 - 2) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{267358} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{26 \times (7 \times 3 \times 5 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{6 + (8^2 + 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{284375} &:= \frac{9 - 1 + 0}{(2 + 8) \times (43 + 7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{7462} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{74 + 6 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{284375} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{(2 + 8 - 4 \times 3 + 7)^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{7826} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{78 + 2 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{285376} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{28 \times (5^3 - 7 - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{8372} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{83 + 7 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{910}{346528} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{(3^4 \times 6 - 5 \times 2) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 912

▶ $\frac{912}{3648}$	$:= \frac{(9-1)^2}{(36-4) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 12}{(4+5) \times 60}$	▶ $\frac{912}{36784}$	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{3 \times 6 + (7 \times 8 \times 4)}$
	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{36-(4+8)}$	$:= \frac{(9-1) \times 2}{4 \times 5 + 60}$		$:= \frac{9 \times 1^2}{3 + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 4))}$
	$:= \frac{9-1 \times 2}{((3+6) \times 4) - 8}$	$:= \frac{9+12}{45+60}$		$:= \frac{9 \times 1 \times 2}{(3^6) - (7-8+4)}$
	$:= \frac{9-1^2}{36+4-8}$	▶ $\frac{912}{5643}$	$:= \frac{(9-1) \times 2}{56+43}$	▶ $\frac{912}{38456}$
	$:= \frac{9+1^2}{(3+6-4) \times 8}$	▶ $\frac{912}{6384}$	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{6 \times (3+8-4)}$	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{(3 \times 84) - 5+6}$
	$:= \frac{9+1 \times 2}{((3+6) \times 4) + 8}$		$:= \frac{9+1^2}{(6 \times (3+8)) + 4}$	▶ $\frac{912}{38475}$
	$:= \frac{9+1+2}{3 \times ((6-4) \times 8)}$		$:= \frac{9 \times 12}{63 \times (8+4)}$	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{3 \times ((8+4) \times 75)}$
	$:= \frac{9 \times 12}{36 \times (4+8)}$		$:= \frac{(9+1) \times 2}{(6 \times 3 \times 8) - 4}$	▶ $\frac{912}{38760}$
	$:= \frac{(9-1) \times 2}{(3 \times 6 \times 4) - 8}$		$:= \frac{9+12}{63+84}$	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{(3 \times 87) - (6+0)}$
	$:= \frac{9 \times 1 \times 2}{(3^6-4) \times 8}$	▶ $\frac{912}{6840}$	$:= \frac{9+1+2}{6+(84+0)}$	▶ $\frac{912}{40356}$
	$:= \frac{(9+1) \times 2}{(3 \times 6 \times 4) + 8}$	▶ $\frac{912}{7638}$	$:= \frac{(9-1) \times 2}{(7 \times 6 \times 3) + 8}$	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{((4^03) - 5) \times 6}$
	$:= \frac{9+12}{36+48}$	▶ $\frac{912}{36480}$	$:= \frac{(9-1)^2}{(36-4) \times 80}$	▶ $\frac{912}{40736}$
	$:= \frac{91-2}{364-8}$		$:= \frac{9-1-2}{3 \times ((6+4) \times (8+0))}$	$:= \frac{9-1-2}{4 \times (0+(73-6))}$
	$:= \frac{9 \times (1+2)}{(3+6) \times (4+8)}$		$:= \frac{9-1^2}{(36+4) \times (8+0)}$	▶ $\frac{912}{50768}$
	$:= \frac{91+2}{364+8}$		$:= \frac{9+1^2}{(3+6-4) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 12}{(6+3) \times 840}$
▶ $\frac{912}{3876}$	$:= \frac{(9-1)^2}{38 \times 7 + 6}$		$:= \frac{9+1+2}{3 \times ((6-4) \times 80)}$	▶ $\frac{912}{76038}$
	$:= \frac{9+1+2}{(3 \times (8+7)) + 6}$		$:= \frac{9 \times 12}{(3+6) \times 480}$	$:= \frac{9-1^2}{7+(60 \times (3+8))}$
▶ $\frac{912}{4560}$	$:= \frac{9+1+2}{4+(56+0)}$		$:= \frac{9 \times 1 \times 2}{(3^6-4) \times 80}$	▶ $\frac{912}{78546}$
				$:= \frac{(9-1) \times 2}{((7^8-5) \times 4) + 6}$
				▶ $\frac{912}{306584}$
				$:= \frac{9+1+2}{3-065+8^4}$
				▶ $\frac{912}{345078}$
				$:= \frac{9-1^2}{3+(4+50) \times 7 \times 8}$
				▶ $\frac{912}{357846}$
				$:= \frac{(9-1) \times 2}{(3+5) \times 784+6}$
				▶ $\frac{912}{384750}$
				$:= \frac{(9-1)^2}{3 \times (8+4) \times 750}$
				▶ $\frac{912}{408576}$
				$:= \frac{9-1-2}{408-5 \times 7 \times 6}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{912}{457368} &:= \frac{(9-1) \times 2}{(45+73) \times 68} &:= \frac{9+1+2}{(4^5-8-7-3) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{912}{458736} &:= \frac{9-1-2}{(4 \times 5 \times 8+7^3) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{912}{467058} &:= \frac{9-1^2}{4^6-7+0 \times 5+8} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{912}{576384} &:= \frac{(9+1) \times 2}{5 \times (76+3) \times 8 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 913

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{5478} &:= \frac{9+1^3}{5+(47+8)} &:= \frac{9 \times (1+3)}{(5 \times 4+7) \times 80} &:= \frac{9+13}{6 \times ((8+47) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{9+1+3}{(5-4) \times 78} &:= \frac{9 \times 13}{(5+4) \times 780} &:= \frac{(9-1) \times 3}{6 \times ((8-4) \times 75)} \\ &:= \frac{9+13}{(5 \times (4 \times 7)) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{60258} &:= \frac{9+1^3}{602+58} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{245680} &:= \frac{9+13}{(2^4 \times 5-6) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{(9+1) \times 3}{5 \times (4 \times 7+8)} &:= \frac{(9+1) \times 3}{60 \times (25+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{278465} &:= \frac{9-1^3}{(2-7) \times 8 \times (4-65)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times (1+3)}{(5 \times 4+7) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{62084} &:= \frac{9 \times (1+3)}{(620-8) \times 4} &:= \frac{9-1-3}{2^7 \times (8+4) - 6-5} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 13}{(5+4) \times 78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{62748} &:= \frac{9-1+3}{6+(2+748)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{406285} &:= \frac{(9-1) \times 3}{40 \times (6+2^8+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{24568} &:= \frac{9+13}{24+568} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{65072} &:= \frac{9-1+3}{(6+50) \times (7 \times 2)} &:= \frac{9-1^3}{40 \times (6-2+85)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{25647} &:= \frac{9+13}{2+(56 \times (4+7))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{65487} &:= \frac{9-1+3}{6+((5+4) \times 87)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{684750} &:= \frac{9 \times 1^3}{(6+84) \times 75+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{54780} &:= \frac{9-1-3}{5 \times (4 \times (7+8+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{913}{68475} &:= \frac{9-1 \times 3}{(6+((8+4) \times 7)) \times 5} &:= \frac{9+13}{6 \times (8+47) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 1^3}{5 \times (4 \times 7+80)} &:= \frac{9+1^3}{(6+8-4) \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{9+1+3}{(5-4) \times 780} &:= \frac{91 \times 3}{(6+(8^4-7)) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 914

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{914}{5027} &:= \frac{9+1^4}{50-2+7} &:= \frac{9+1^4}{(70 \times (8+3)) + 5} &:= \frac{9+1-4}{7-(5-(8 \times 62))} \\ &:= \frac{9+(1+4)}{50+27} &:= \frac{9-1+4}{(70-8) \times 3 \times 5} &:= \frac{9-1^4}{(75+8) \times (6+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{914}{70835} &:= \frac{9+1-4}{708-(3^5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{914}{75862} &:= \frac{9-1-4}{(75+8) \times (6-2)} &:= \frac{9-1+4}{(75+8) \times 6 \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{9 \times 1 \times 4}{(75 + 8) \times 6^2} = \frac{9 - 1 + 4}{(2 \times 307 - 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{914}{230785} = \frac{9 - 1^4}{2 \times (30 \times 7 - 8) \times 5}$$

● Numerator 915

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{2684} = \frac{9 + 1 + 5}{2 \times 6 + 8 \times 4}$$

$$= \frac{9 \times 1 \times 5}{(2 \times 68) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{4026} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{(4^{01}) + 6}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1^5}{40 - 2 + 6}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1 + 5}{40 + 26}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{4270} = \frac{9 - 1 - 5}{(4 - 2) \times (7 + 0)}$$

$$= \frac{9 \times 1^5}{(4 + 2) \times (7 + 0)}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 15}{42 + 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{7320} = \frac{9 - 1 - 5}{7 - (3 - 20)}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1^5}{(7 - 3) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{26840} = \frac{9 - 1 - 5}{2 \times (6 \times 8 - 4 + 0)}$$

$$= \frac{9 \times 1^5}{268 - 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{27084} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{2 \times (70 + 8 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{38247} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{(3 + 8 \times 2) \times (4 + 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{62830} = \frac{9 + 1 + 5}{6 + (2 \times (8^3 + 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{68320} = \frac{9 - 1 - 5}{(68 \times 3) + 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{72468} = \frac{9 + 1^5}{(7 + (2 \times 46)) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{72834} = \frac{9 + 1^5}{((7 \times 28) + 3) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{86742} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{(86 - 7) \times (4 + 2)}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1^5}{(86 \times (7 + 4)) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{87230} = \frac{9 - 1 - 5}{(8 \times 7) + 230}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{283467} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{(2^8 - 3 + 4) \times 6 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{402783} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{4 + (-02 + 7 + 8)^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{408273} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{(40 + 8)^2 - 73}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{467382} = \frac{9 + 1 - 5}{4 + 6 \times (7^3 + 82)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{478362} = \frac{9 + 1 + 5}{4 + 7836 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{724680} = \frac{9 + 1^5}{(7 + 2 \times 46) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{915}{728340} = \frac{9 + 1^5}{(7 \times 28 + 3) \times 40}$$

● Numerator 916

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{916}{2748} = \frac{9 - 1 - 6}{2 \times (7 + 4 - 8)}$$

$$= \frac{9 \times 1^6}{2 - (7 - (4 \times 8))}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1^6}{2 - (7 \times (4 - 8))}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1 + 6}{2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 8)}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 16}{27 + 48}$$

$$= \frac{(9 - 1) \times 6}{(2 \times 7 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$= \frac{9 \times 16}{(2 + 7) \times 48}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{916}{4580} = \frac{9 + 16}{45 + 80}$$

$$= \frac{9 \times 16}{(4 + 5) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{916}{5038} = \frac{9 + 1^6}{5 \times (0 + 3 + 8)}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1 + 6}{50 + 38}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{916}{7328} = \frac{9 - 1 - 6}{7 + (3 - 2 + 8)}$$

$$= \frac{9 - 1 \times 6}{7 + ((3^2) + 8)}$$

$$= \frac{9 + 1 - 6}{7 - (3 - 28)}$$

$$= \frac{9 - 1^6}{(7 + 3 - 2) \times 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{9-1+6}{(7-3) \times 28} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{30457} & := \frac{9+1+6}{((3^{04})-5) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{73280} & := \frac{9-1-6}{(7-3-2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{9+1+6}{(7+3^2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{35724} & := \frac{9-1-6}{3+(5 \times (7+2 \times 4))} & & := \frac{9-1^6}{(7+3-2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times (1+6)}{7 \times (3^2 \times 8)} & & := \frac{9-1 \times 6}{3-(57 \times (2-4))} & & := \frac{9+1^6}{(7+3)^2 \times 8+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{8473} & := \frac{9-1^6}{84-(7+3)} & & := \frac{9 \times 1^6}{3 \times (5+(7 \times 2^4))} & & := \frac{9-1+6}{(7-3) \times 280} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{8702} & := \frac{9-1^6}{8+(70-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{38472} & := \frac{9-1-6}{3 \times (8+(4 \times (7-2)))} & & := \frac{9+1+6}{(7+3^2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{23587} & := \frac{9+1-6}{(2 \times (3+5)) + 87} & & := \frac{9+1-6}{3 \times ((8-4) \times (7 \times 2))} & & := \frac{9 \times (1+6)}{7 \times (3^2 \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{9+1+6}{2 \times 3+(58 \times 7)} & & := \frac{9 \times 1^6}{(38+4) \times (7+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{357240} & := \frac{9-1-6}{(35-7)^2-4+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{24503} & := \frac{9-1^6}{2+(4 \times (50+3))} & & := \frac{9+1^6}{(38 \times (4+7)) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{384720} & := \frac{(9+1) \times 6}{(3+8 \times 4) \times 720} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{27480} & := \frac{9-1-6}{((2-7) \times 4) + 80} & & := \frac{9-1+6}{3 \times ((8-4) \times (7^2))} & & := \frac{(9-1) \times 6}{(3 \times 8+4) \times 720} \\
 & := \frac{9-1 \times 6}{2+((7+4) \times (8+0))} & & := \frac{(9-1) \times 6}{(3 \times 8+4) \times 72} & & := \frac{9-1 \times 6}{3 \times 84 \times (7-2) + 0} \\
 & := \frac{9-1^6}{(2+7 \times 4) \times (8+0)} & & := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 6}{3 \times (84 \times (7+2))} & & := \frac{9-1-6}{(3-8+47) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{9+1+6}{2 \times ((7-4) \times 80)} & & := \frac{(9+1) \times 6}{(3+8 \times 4) \times 72} & & := \frac{9-1+6}{(38+4) \times 7 \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{9+16}{2+(748+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{43052} & := \frac{9-1-6}{4+(30 \times (5-2))} & & := \frac{9+1-6}{3 \times (8-4) \times 7 \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{(9-1) \times 6}{(2 \times 7+4) \times 80} & & := \frac{9 \times 1^6}{430-5-2} & & \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 16}{(2+7) \times 480} & \blacktriangleright \frac{916}{70532} & := \frac{9+1^6}{70 \times (5+3 \times 2)} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 917

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{917}{2358} & := \frac{(9-1) \times 7}{(23-5) \times 8} & & := \frac{9+(1-7)}{((8-2) \times 5) - 3} & & := \frac{9-1+7}{8+(2+5^3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{917}{5240} & := \frac{(9+1) \times 7}{5 \times (2 \times 40)} & & := \frac{9-1^7}{8^2+5+3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{917}{23580} & := \frac{(9-1) \times 7}{(23-5) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{917}{8253} & := \frac{9-1 \times 7}{8+(2+5+3)} & & := \frac{9+1^7}{82+5+3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{917}{82530} & := \frac{9-1-7}{82+(5+3+0)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{9 + 1^7}{(8 - 2) \times (5 \times 30)} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{917}{463085} := \frac{9 \times 1^7}{4630 - 85}$$

● Numerator 918

$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{2346} := \frac{9 \times 1^8}{2 - (3 - (4 \times 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{3672} := \frac{9 - 1 \times 8}{3 + (6 - 7 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{24735} := \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{((2 \times 47) + 3) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{9 + 18}{23 + 46}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1 - 8}{(3 - 6 + 7) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{25347} := \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{((25 \times 3) - 4) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{2430} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{2 + (43 + 0)}$	$:= \frac{9 - 1^8}{(3 + 6 + 7) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{25704} := \frac{9 - 1 \times 8}{(2 \times (5 + 7 + 0)) + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{2703} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{2 + (70 \times 3)}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{3 + (67 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1 - 8}{(2 + (5 + 7 + 0)) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{2754} := \frac{9 \times 1^8}{27 \times (5 - 4)}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{3 + (67 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{9 - 1^8}{2^5 \times (7 + 0 \times 4)}$
$:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{2 \times (7 + 5 \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{9 + 18}{36 + 72}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1^8}{2 \times (5 \times (7 \times 04))}$
$:= \frac{9 + 18}{2 + (75 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 18}{(3 + 6) \times 72}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{27540} := \frac{9 - 1 \times 8}{2 - (7 + (5 - 40))}$
$:= \frac{9 \times 18}{(2 + 7) \times 54}$	$:= \frac{(9 - 1) \times 8}{(3 + 6 + 7)^2}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{27 \times (5 \times (4 + 0))}$
$:= \frac{9 \times (1 + 8)}{27 \times (5 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (1 + 8)}{36 \times (7 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 18}{(2 + 7) \times 540}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{3024} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{(30 \times 2) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{3726} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{3 + (72 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{32640} := \frac{9 \times 1^8}{32 \times (6 + 4 + 0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{3264} := \frac{9 \times 1^8}{(3 \times 2 \times 6) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{4536} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times 3 + 6)}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(3 - 2) \times 640}$
$:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{32 \times (6 - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{5032} := \frac{9 + 18}{(50 \times 3) - 2}$	$:= \frac{9 + 18}{3 \times ((2 + 6) \times 40)}$
$:= \frac{9 + 18}{3 \times ((2 + 6) \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{5346} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{53 + 46}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 18}{3^2 \times 640}$
$:= \frac{9 \times 18}{3^2 \times 64}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{6375} := \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(6 \times 3 + 7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{36450} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{(3^6) - (4 + 50)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{3456} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{(3 + 4 - 5)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{6732} := \frac{9 \times 1^8}{67 - 3 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{36720} := \frac{9 - 1 \times 8}{(3 + 6 - 7) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{3502} := \frac{9 + 18}{3 + (50 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{7452} := \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{(7 \times 4 \times 5) - 2}$	$:= \frac{9 + 1 - 8}{(3 - 6 + 7) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{3570} := \frac{9 + 18}{3 \times (5 \times 7 + 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{918}{23460} := \frac{9 \times 1^8}{23 \times (4 + 6 + 0)}$	

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{9 - 1^8}{(3 + 6 + 7) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{74256} &:= \frac{9 \times 1^8}{7 \times (4 \times (2^5 - 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{345627} &:= \frac{9 - 1^8}{3 \times (4^5 - 6 - 2 \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{(3^6) - (7^2 + 0)} & &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(7 \times 4 - 2) \times 56} & &:= \frac{9 + 1 - 8}{3 \times (4 - 5 + 6^2 \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(3^6) - (7 + 2 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{74520} &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{(74 - 5) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{354726} &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{3^{5-4+7} + 2 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{9 \times 18}{(3 + 6) \times 720} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{235467} &:= \frac{(9 + 1) \times 8}{2 + 3 + 5 \times (4^6 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{364752} &:= \frac{9 + 18}{36 \times (4 \times 75 - 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{47362} &:= \frac{9 + 18}{((4 + 7)^3) + 62} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{235467} &:= \frac{9 - 1 + 8}{2 \times 3 - 5 + 4^6 + 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{365472} &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{3 \times 6 \times (54 \times 7 - 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{47532} &:= \frac{9 \times 1^8}{475 - (3^2)} & &:= \frac{9 + 1 - 8}{2 + 3^5 + 4 \times 67} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{375462} &:= \frac{9 - 1 \times 8}{3 + 7 \times (5 + 4 \times 6) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{4 + (7 \times 532)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{247350} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(2 \times 47 + 3) \times 50} & &:= \frac{9 - 1^8}{3 + 7 \times (5 + 462)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{52734} &:= \frac{9 \times 1^8}{5 + (2 \times ((7 - 3)^4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{247536} &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{(2 + 4) \times (7 \times 5 + 3^6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{423657} &:= \frac{9 - 1^8}{(4 \times 2 + 3^6) \times 5 + 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{54672} &:= \frac{9 + 18}{(5 \times (46 \times 7)) - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{253470} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(25 \times 3 - 4) \times 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{457623} &:= \frac{9 + 1 - 8}{4^5 - (7 - 6 + 2)^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{57324} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(5 \times (7 \times 32)) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{264537} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(2 \times 6 + (4 + 5)^3) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{742356} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(7^4 + (2 + 3) \times 5) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{60435} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{((60 \times 4) - 3) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{273564} &:= \frac{9 - 1 \times 8}{2 \times 7 \times (3 \times 5 + 6) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{742560} &:= \frac{9 \times 1^8}{7 \times 4^2 \times (5 + 60)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{63750} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 8}{(6 \times 3 + 7) \times 50} & &:= \frac{9 + 1 - 8}{(2 + 7 \times (3 \times 5 + 6)) \times 4} & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{70362} &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{7 - (0 - (36^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{918}{274536} &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 8}{2 - 7 \times (4 - 5^3) \times 6} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 921

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{921}{3684} &:= \frac{9 \times (2 + 1)}{(3 + 6) \times (8 + 4)} & &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 1}{36 + 8 + 4} & &:= \frac{9^{2+1}}{3^6 \times (8 - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{9 - 2 - 1}{36 - (8 + 4)} & &:= \frac{9 \times 21}{(3 + 6) \times 84} & &:= \frac{92 - 1}{368 - 4} \\
 &:= \frac{9 - 2 + 1}{36 - 8 + 4} & &:= \frac{9 \times 2 - 1}{(3 + 6 + 8) \times 4} & &:= \frac{92 + 1}{368 + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{9 \times (2 - 1)}{(3 + 6) \times (8 - 4)} & &:= \frac{9 \times 2 \times 1}{3 \times (6 \times (8 - 4))} & &:= \frac{9 + 21}{36 + 84} \\
 &:= \frac{9 + 2 - 1}{36 + 8 - 4} & &:= \frac{9 \times 2 + 1}{((3 + 6) \times 8) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{921}{4605} &:= \frac{9 + 2 - 1}{(4 + 6 + 0) \times 5} \\
 & & & & &:= \frac{92 - 1}{460 - 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{921}{6754} := \frac{92+1}{460+5} \\
 & \frac{921}{7368} := \frac{9 \times (2-1)}{67-5+4} \\
 & \frac{921}{7368} := \frac{9 \times (2+1)}{((7 \times 3) + 6) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{9-2 \times 1}{(7-3) \times (6+8)} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times (2-1)}{7-(3-68)} \\
 & := \frac{9+2-1}{(7-3+6) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{92-1}{7+((3^6)-8)} \\
 & \frac{921}{36840} := \frac{92+1}{7+((3^6)+8)} \\
 & \frac{921}{36840} := \frac{9+2-1}{(3 \times 6-8) \times 40} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 21}{(3+6) \times 840} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 2-1}{(3+6+8) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{921}{48506} := \frac{9-2-1}{4 \times (85-06)} \\
 & \frac{921}{50348} := \frac{9 \times (2-1)}{((5^{03}) \times 4) - 8} \\
 & \frac{921}{73680} := \frac{9 \times (2+1)}{((7 \times 3) + 6) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{9-2-1}{(7+3) \times (6 \times (8+0))} \\
 & := \frac{9+2-1}{(7-3+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{921}{86574} := \frac{9 \times 2 \times 1}{((86 \times 5) - 7) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{921}{865740} := \frac{9+2+1}{8 \times 6 \times 5 \times (7+40)}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 923

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{923}{1846} := \frac{9-2 \times 3}{1 \times (8+4-6)} \\
 & := \frac{9-2-3}{18-(4+6)} \\
 & := \frac{9+2-3}{18+4-6} \\
 & := \frac{9-2+3}{18-4+6} \\
 & := \frac{9+2+3}{18+4+6} \\
 & := \frac{9+2 \times 3}{(1+8-4) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{(9-2) \times 3}{18+4 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{9+23}{18+46} \\
 & := \frac{(9+2) \times 3}{(18 \times 4) - 6} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times (2+3)}{1 \times (84+6)} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 23}{(1+8) \times 46} \\
 & := \frac{92-3}{184-6} \\
 & \frac{923}{4615} := \frac{92+3}{184+6} \\
 & := \frac{9-2^3}{4+(6-1 \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{9-2 \times 3}{4+(6+1 \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{9-2-3}{4 \times (6-1^5)} \\
 & := \frac{9+2-3}{4 \times (6-1+5)} \\
 & := \frac{9-2+3}{(4+6 \times 1) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{9+2+3}{4+(61+5)} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times (2+3)}{(46-1) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 2^3}{4 \times (6 \times 15)} \\
 & \frac{923}{14768} := \frac{9-2^3}{((1-4+7) \times 6) - 8} \\
 & := \frac{9-2 \times 3}{(1+(4+7-6)) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{9-2-3}{((1+4+7) \times 6) - 8} \\
 & := \frac{9-2+3}{1 \times ((4 \times 7 \times 6) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{9+2^3}{1 \times (4 \times (76-8))} \\
 & := \frac{(9-2) \times 3}{1 \times (4 \times (76+8))} \\
 & := \frac{(9+2) \times 3}{1 \times ((4+7) \times 6 \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times (2+3)}{(14+76) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{9^2+3}{1 \times (4 \times (7 \times 6 \times 8))} \\
 & \frac{923}{18460} := \frac{9-2^3}{18-(4-(6+0))} \\
 & := \frac{9-2 \times 3}{(1^{84}) \times 60} \\
 & := \frac{9-2-3}{1 \times (8 \times (4+6+0))} \\
 & := \frac{9+2 \times 3}{(1+8-4) \times 60}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 \times 23}{(1+8) \times 460} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{923}{46150} & := \frac{9-2^3}{(4+6 \times 1) \times (5+0)} \\ & := \frac{9-2 \times 3}{(4+6) \times (15+0)} \\ & := \frac{9-2+3}{(4+6 \times 1) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{9 \times (2+3)}{(46-1) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 2^3}{4 \times (6 \times 150)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{923}{70148} & := \frac{9-2^3}{70+(14-8)} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 2 \times 3}{((7+01)^4)+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{923}{147680} & := \frac{9^2+3}{1 \times 4 \times 7 \times 6 \times 80} \\ & := \frac{(9+2) \times 3}{(1 \times 4+7) \times 6 \times 80} \\ & := \frac{(9-2) \times 3}{(1+47-6) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{9-2 \times 3}{1 \times 4+7 \times 68+0} \\ & := \frac{9-2^3}{1 \times 4+76+80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9-2-3}{(1 \times 4+76) \times 8+0} \\ & := \frac{9 \times (2+3)}{(14+76) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{9+2^3}{(1-4+7) \times 680} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{923}{678405} & := \frac{9+23}{6 \times 784 \times 05} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 924

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1036} & := \frac{9+24}{1-(0-36)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1365} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^3 \times 65} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1386} & := \frac{9 \times 2+4}{1+(38-6)} \\ & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{1 \times (3 \times (8+6))} \\ & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times ((3+8) \times 6)} \\ & := \frac{92-4}{138-6} \\ & := \frac{92+4}{1 \times (3 \times 8 \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1568} & := \frac{9+24}{(1^5+6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1638} & := \frac{9 \times 2+4}{1^6+38} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1650} & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{1^6 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1680} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^6 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1683} & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{1 \times ((6 \times 8)+3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1785} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{17 \times 85} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{1806} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times (80+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{3108} & := \frac{9+24}{3+108} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{3150} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{3 \times 1 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{3168} & := \frac{9+2-4}{3 \times (16-8)} \\ & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{(3-1) \times 6 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{3570} & := \frac{9 \times 2+4}{3 \times 5+70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{3675} & := \frac{92-4}{(3+67) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{3780} & := \frac{9-2+4}{3 \times (7+8+0)} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 2+4}{3+(7+80)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{5180} & := \frac{9+24}{5+180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{7035} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(70-3) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{7168} & := \frac{9+24}{(7+1-6)^8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{7315} & := \frac{9 \times 24}{((7^3)-1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{7560} & := \frac{92-4}{(7+5) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{8316} & := \frac{9-2-4}{8+(3+16)} \\ & := \frac{9-2+4}{83+16} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{8613} & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{(86+1) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{10836} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{10+((8^3)-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{13068} & := \frac{9+2-4}{1+(30+68)} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 2-4}{130+68} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{13650} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^3 \times 650} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{13860} & := \frac{9-2 \times 4}{13+(8-(6+0))} \\ & := \frac{9-2-4}{1+(38+6+0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times ((3+8) \times 60)} \\
 & := \frac{92+4}{1 \times (3 \times (8 \times 60))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{15078} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 4}{1 + ((50 \times 7) + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{15680} & := \frac{9+24}{(1^5+6) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{15708} & := \frac{9-2 \times 4}{1 - ((5-7+0) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{9+24}{1^5 + (70 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{15876} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 4}{(1^5+8) \times 7 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{17358} & := \frac{9 \times 2 - 4}{(17 \times 3 \times 5) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{17850} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^7 \times 850} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{18375} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+8 \times 3) \times 7 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{18753} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{18 + (7 \times (5^3))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{30618} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 4}{3^{06 \times 18}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{31680} & := \frac{9+2-4}{3 \times (1^6 \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{(3-1) \times 6 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{36750} & := \frac{92-4}{(3+67) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{37158} & := \frac{9 \times 2 - 4}{(37 \times 15) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{38016} & := \frac{9+2-4}{3 \times (80+16)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{51876} & := \frac{9 \times 2 - 4}{(5 + (18 \times 7)) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{71568} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{71 \times (56-8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{73150} & := \frac{9 \times 24}{((7^3) - 1) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{81576} & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{((81 \times 5) + 7) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{83160} & := \frac{9-2 \times 4}{83 + (1+6+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{86130} & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{(86+1) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{103785} & := \frac{(9-2) \times 4}{1 \times 037 \times 85} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{107856} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 4}{(10-7) \times 856} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{158760} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 4}{(1^5+8) \times 7 \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{173586} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 4}{17 \times 3^5 + 8 - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{180576} & := \frac{9 \times 2 - 4}{1 \times 8 \times 057 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{9+2-4}{18 \times (0 \times 5 + 76)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{183750} & := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+8 \times 3) \times 7 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{187356} & := \frac{9^2 - 4}{1+8-7 \times 3 + 5^6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{317856} & := \frac{9-2 \times 4}{(3+1) \times (7+85-6)} \\
 & := \frac{9+2-4}{(3 \times 17 - 8) \times 56} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{924}{715680} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 4}{71 \times 5 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 925

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{925}{637140} := \frac{9 \times 2 \times 5}{6^3 \times 7 \times (1+40)}$$

● Numerator 926

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{3704} & := \frac{9+2 \times 6}{3 \times (7 \times 04)} \\
 & := \frac{9+2^6}{(3+70) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{45837} & := \frac{9 \times 2 - 6}{4 + (583+7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{53708} & := \frac{9-2-6}{5 - (3 + (7 \times (-08)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{73154} & := \frac{9-2-6}{7 + ((3+15) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{9-2+6}{7 + (((3+1)^5) - 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{7408} & := \frac{(9-2) \times 6}{7 \times (40+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{137048} & := \frac{9 \times 2 + 6}{(1+3+70) \times 48} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 2 - 6}{1 \times 3 \times (70+4) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{9-2-6}{1 \times 37 \times (-04+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{170384} & := \frac{9-2-6}{(1+7+038) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{926}{458370} & := \frac{(9+2)^6}{45 \times (8+3)^7 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{9 - 2 - 6}{458 + 37 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 6}{45 + 8370} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 927

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{1648} &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{1 \times (6 \times 4 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 27}{16 + 48} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 2 \times 7}{(1 + 6) \times 4 \times 8} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{4635} &:= \frac{9 + 27}{4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - 2) \times 7}{(46 + 3) \times 5} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{143685} &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{14^3 + 6 + 8 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{183546} &:= \frac{9 \times 2 - 7}{(1 + 8 + 354) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 2 \times 7}{18 \times (3^5 + 4 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{(1 \times 8 + 3) \times 54 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 2 - 7}{18 \times (3 - 5 + 46)} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{1854} &:= \frac{9 + 2 - 7}{1 \times (8 \times (5 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{9 - 2 + 7}{1 \times (8 + 5 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{1 \times (8 \times 5 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 27}{1 \times (8 \times (5 + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times (2 + 7)}{18 \times (5 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 27}{(1 + 8) \times 54} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{16480} &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{16 \times (4 \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 2 \times 7}{(1 + 6) \times (4 \times 80)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{18540} &:= \frac{9 + 2 - 7}{1 \times (8 \times 5 + 40)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{1 \times (8 \times (5 + 40))} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 27}{(1 + 8) \times 540} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{364105} &:= \frac{92 + 7}{3 \times 6^4 \times 10 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{531480} &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{(5 + 31 \times 4) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{681345} &:= \frac{9 + 2 \times 7}{(6 \times 8 + 1) \times 345} \end{aligned}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{927}{3605} := \frac{9 \times (2 + 7)}{(3 + 60) \times 5}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{46350} &:= \frac{9 + 27}{4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - 2) \times 7}{(46 + 3) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{927}{53148} &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7}{(5 + (31 \times 4)) \times 8} \end{aligned}$	

● Numerator 928

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{928}{4176} &:= \frac{9 \times 2 - 8}{4 - (1 - 7 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 2 + 8}{41 + 76} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{928}{63104} &:= \frac{9 + 2 - 8}{6 \times ((3 \times 10) + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 8}{6^{3+1} - 04} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 8}{7 + 1456} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{928}{475136} &:= \frac{92 \times 8}{4^7 \times (5 + 1 \times 3 \times 6)} \end{aligned}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{928}{5104} := \frac{9 \times 2 - 8}{51 + 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{928}{71456} := \frac{9 + 2 - 8}{7 + (1 \times 4 \times 56)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{928}{13456} := \frac{9 \times 2 - 8}{134 + 5 + 6}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 2 - 8}{714 + 56}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{928}{16704} := \frac{9 + 28}{1 \times (670 - 4)}$		

● Numerator 930

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{4185} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{4+(18+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{16275} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{(1+(6+2 \times 7)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{28675} &:= \frac{9+3+0}{(2+8) \times (6 \times 7-5)} \\ &:= \frac{9+3+0}{41+8+5} & &:= \frac{9+3+0}{(((1+6)^2)-7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{87265} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{(8 \times (7+2^6))-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{7285} &:= \frac{9+3+0}{7+(2+85)} & &:= \frac{9 \times 30}{(1+62) \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{167245} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{1 \times 6+7^2+4^5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{12865} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{1 \times (2+(86-5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{17825} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{1 \times ((7+8 \times 2) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{182745} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{1 \times 8 \times 2 \times 74-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{930}{14725} &:= \frac{9-3+0}{(1+(4+7 \times 2)) \times 5} & &:= \frac{9+3+0}{1 \times (((7+8)^2)+5)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 931

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{8246} &:= \frac{9-3+1}{8^2+4-6} & &:= \frac{9 \times 3+1}{(20-7) \times 48} & \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{425068} &:= \frac{9-3+1}{(42+5) \times 068} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{8645} &:= \frac{9 \times 3+1}{(8 \times 6+4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{50274} &:= \frac{9-3 \times 1}{50+274} & \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{640528} &:= \frac{9+3 \times 1}{(6+40^5+2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{4256} &:= \frac{9-3+1}{4-(2-(5 \times 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{78204} &:= \frac{9-3-1}{7 \times ((8^2+0)-4)} & & \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 3+1}{4 \times (2+5 \times 6)} & &:= \frac{9+3+1}{7 \times ((8 \times 20)-4)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{20748} &:= \frac{9-3+1}{(2 \times (0+74))+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{931}{86450} &:= \frac{9 \times 3+1}{(8 \times 6+4) \times 50} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 932

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{1864} &:= \frac{9-3 \times 2}{1 \times (8-6+4)} & &:= \frac{9+3^2}{18 \times (6-4)} & &:= \frac{9 \times (3+2)}{1 \times (86+4)} \\ &:= \frac{9-3-2}{1 \times ((8-6) \times 4)} & &:= \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{(18-6) \times 4} & &:= \frac{93-2}{186-4} \\ &:= \frac{9-3+2}{1 \times (8 \times (6-4))} & &:= \frac{9 \times 3-2}{((1+8) \times 6)-4} & &:= \frac{93+2}{186+4} \\ &:= \frac{9^{3-2}}{1 \times (8+6+4)} & &:= \frac{9 \times 3+2}{((1+8) \times 6)+4} & &:= \frac{9+32}{1 \times (86-4)} \\ &:= \frac{9+3-2}{18+6-4} & &:= \frac{9 \times 32}{(1+8) \times 64} & \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{6058} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 2}{6 \times (0+5+8)} \\ &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 2}{1^8 \times 6 \times 4} & &:= \frac{(9-3)^2}{1 \times (8+64)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{7456} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 2}{(7+4+5) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{9+3+2}{18+6+4} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{10485} &:= \frac{9-3-2}{1-(0-(4+(8 \times 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{9-3+2}{1-(0-(4+85))} \\
 & := \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{10 \times (4 \times 8-5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{18407} & := \frac{9-3-2}{(18 \times (4+0)) + 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{18640} & := \frac{9-3 \times 2}{(1+8+6) \times (4+0)} \\
 & := \frac{9-3-2}{1 \times (8 \times (6+4+0))} \\
 & := \frac{9^{3-2}}{18 \times (6+4+0)} \\
 & := \frac{(9-3) \times 2}{1^8 \times (6 \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{9+3+2}{(1^8+6) \times 40} \\
 & := \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{(18-6) \times 40} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 32}{(1+8) \times 640} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{58716} & := \frac{9-3 \times 2}{5+(8 \times (7+16))} \\
 & := \frac{9-3+2}{(5+(8+71)) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{9^{3-2}}{5+((8 \times 71)-6)} \\
 & := \frac{(9-3) \times 2}{5 \times 8+716} \\
 & := \frac{9+3+2}{5+(871+6)} \\
 & := \frac{93-2}{5+(8 \times 716)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{61745} & := \frac{9-3-2}{(((6+1) \times 7)+4) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{9-3+2}{((6 \times 17)+4) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{64075} & := \frac{9-3-2}{(6 \times 40)+(7 \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{6 \times ((40 \times 7)-5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{67104} & := \frac{9-3 \times 2}{6^{7-1 \times 0^4}} \\
 & := \frac{9+3-2}{6+(710+4)} \\
 & := \frac{9+3^2}{6^{7+1-0^4}} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 32}{(6+(7-1+0))^4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{932}{74560} & := \frac{(9-3) \times 2}{(7+4+5) \times 60}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 934

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{934}{6071} & := \frac{9-3-4}{6-(0-7 \times 1)} \\
 & := \frac{9+3-4}{60-7-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{934}{27086} & := \frac{9-3-4}{2+(70-(8+6))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{934}{62578} & := \frac{9+3-4}{((6 \times 2 \times 5)+7) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{934}{81725} & := \frac{9-3-4}{8+(172-5)} \\
 & := \frac{9+3+4}{8 \times (1 \times (7 \times 25))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{934}{817250} & := \frac{9+3+4}{8 \times 1 \times 7 \times 250}
 \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 935

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{1870} & := \frac{9-3-5}{1+(8-7+0)} \\
 & := \frac{9+35}{1+(87+0)} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times 35}{(1+8) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{2640} & := \frac{9+3+5}{2+(6+40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{6120} & := \frac{9-3+5}{6 \times (12+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{7260} & := \frac{9+3+5}{72+60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{7480} & := \frac{9-3+5}{(7+4) \times (8+0)} \\
 & := \frac{(9-3) \times 5}{(7-4) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{8140} & := \frac{9+3+5}{8+140} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{8470} & := \frac{9+3+5}{84+70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{12870} & := \frac{9+3+5}{(1+2) \times (8+70)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{14280} & := \frac{9 \times 3-5}{1 \times (42 \times (8+0))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{16280} & := \frac{9+3+5}{(1+6^2) \times (8+0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{26180} & := \frac{9-3-5}{2 \times (6+(1 \times 8+0))} \\
 & := \frac{9+3+5}{2-(6 \times (1-80))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{28160} &:= \frac{9+3+5}{2^{8+160}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{167280} &:= \frac{9 \times 3 - 5}{16 + 7^2 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{427680} &:= \frac{9+3+5}{(4+2)^{7+6-8} + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{48620} &:= \frac{9-3-5}{48+(6-2+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{248710} &:= \frac{9-3-5}{2+4 \times (8 \times 7 + 10)} & & \\ &:= \frac{9+3 \times 5}{48 \times (6+20)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{267410} &:= \frac{9-3-5}{(2+67) \times 4 + 10} & & \\ &:= \frac{9+3-5}{(4 \times 86) + 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{935}{278460} &:= \frac{9 \times 3 - 5}{2 \times 7 \times (8 + 460)} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 936

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{1248} &:= \frac{9+3-6}{1 \times (2^4 - 8)} & &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{1 \times (8 \times (7+2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{5408} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{(5 \times 40) + 8} \\ &:= \frac{9-3+6}{1 \times (24-8)} & &:= \frac{9+36}{1+(87+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{5824} &:= \frac{9+3+6}{(58 \times 2) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{9+3+6}{1 \times (2 \times (4+8))} & &:= \frac{9 \times 36}{(1+8) \times 72} & &:= \frac{9+3 \times 6}{(5 \times 8 + 2) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{9+3 \times 6}{(1+2) \times (4+8)} & &:= \frac{9 \times (3+6)}{18 \times (7+2)} & &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{(58-2) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 3 + 6}{12+4 \times 8} & &:= \frac{93-6}{1 \times (87 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{12480} &:= \frac{9+3-6}{1^{24} \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{1 \times ((2+4) \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{2184} &:= \frac{9+3-6}{2+(1 \times 8+4)} & &:= \frac{9+3+6}{(1-2+4) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{9+36}{12+48} & &:= \frac{9-3+6}{2 \times (18-4)} & &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{1 \times ((2+4) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{1 \times (2 \times 48)} & &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{21 \times (8-4)} & &:= \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{1 \times (2 \times 480)} \\ &:= \frac{93-6}{124-8} & &:= \frac{9+36}{21+84} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{12584} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{(12 \times (5 \times 8)) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{93+6}{124+8} & &:= \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{2 \times (1 \times 84)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{17524} &:= \frac{9+3+6}{1+(7 \times (52-4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{1287} &:= \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+87} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{2418} &:= \frac{9-3+6}{24-1+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{18720} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{1^8 \times 720} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{1482} &:= \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{(14 \times 8) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{2574} &:= \frac{9-3+6}{2+(5 \times 7-4)} & &:= \frac{9 \times 36}{(1+8) \times 720} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{1508} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{1 \times (50+8)} & &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{25+74} & &:= \frac{93-6}{1 \times (87 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{1872} &:= \frac{9 \times 3 - 6}{1 - (8 - 7^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{5148} &:= \frac{9+3-6}{(5 \times (1+4)) + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{21840} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{(2-1) \times 840} \\ &:= \frac{9+3 \times 6}{1 \times ((8 \times 7) - 2)} & &:= \frac{9+3+6}{51+48} & &:= \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{2 \times (1 \times 840)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{24570} := \frac{9-3+6}{245+70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{74152} := \frac{9+3 \times 6}{7+(41 \times 52)} & := \frac{9-3+6}{(1+5) \times 7 \times (2+4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{25480} := \frac{9+3+6}{2 \times 5+480} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{81250} := \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{(8-1-2)^5+0} & := \frac{9+3-6}{(1+5) \times 7 \times 2 \times (4+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{51480} := \frac{9+3 \times 6}{5+1480} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{87412} := \frac{9+3+6}{(8-7) \times (41^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{218504} := \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{21 \times 8 \times 50+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{54782} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{(54 \times 78)+2} & := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{(8+(74 \times 1))^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{275184} := \frac{9+3-6}{(27-5-1) \times 84} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{57824} := \frac{9+3+6}{((5 \times 7 \times 8)-2) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{145782} := \frac{9-3+6}{(1+4 \times 5) \times (7+82)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{874120} := \frac{9+3 \times 6}{(8+7) \times 41^2+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{58240} := \frac{9+3 \times 6}{5 \times (8 \times (2+40))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{936}{157248} := \frac{9 \times 3-6}{(1+5) \times 7^2 \times (4+8)} & \\
 & := \frac{(9-3) \times 6}{(58-2) \times 40} &
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 937

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{937}{4685} := \frac{9+3+7}{4+(6+85)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{937}{61842} := \frac{9+3-7}{6+(18^{4-2})} & \blacktriangleright \frac{937}{421650} := \frac{9-3+7}{(4 \times 2+1) \times 650} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{937}{42165} := \frac{9+3-7}{4+(216+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{937}{82456} := \frac{9+3-7}{(8+2) \times (4 \times (5+6))} & \\
 & := \frac{(9-3) \times 7}{(82 \times 45)+6} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{937}{46850} := \frac{9 \times 3-7}{(4+6)^{8-5}+0} & := \frac{9+37}{8 \times (2^{4+5}-6)} &
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 938

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{1072} := \frac{9-3+8}{(1+07) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{10452} := \frac{9-3+8}{104+52} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{41205} := \frac{9-3+8}{41 \times (20-5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{1206} := \frac{9-3+8}{(1+2+0) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{15276} := \frac{9-3+8}{1 \times ((5-2) \times 76)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{45761} := \frac{9-3+8}{((4+5) \times 76)-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{1407} := \frac{9-3+8}{14+07} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{17420} := \frac{9-3+8}{(17-4) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{65124} := \frac{9 \times 3+8}{6 \times (5 \times ((1+2)^4))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{1742} := \frac{9-3+8}{1 \times (7 \times 4-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{20167} := \frac{9+3-8}{2 \times (0+(1+(6 \times 7)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{142576} := \frac{9 \times 3-8}{(1+42-5) \times 76} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{5427} := \frac{9-3+8}{54+27} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{21574} := \frac{9+3-8}{((2 \times 15)-7) \times 4} & := \frac{9-3+8}{1 \times 4 \times (2+5) \times 76} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{5762} := \frac{9 \times 3+8}{5 \times (7+6^2)} & := \frac{9-3+8}{2 \times (157+4)} & := \frac{9+3+8}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 5 \times 76}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9+3-8}{(1+4-2+5) \times 76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{175406} & := \frac{9+3-8}{1 \times 754 - 06} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{152760} & := \frac{9-3+8}{(1 \times 5-2) \times 760} & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{215740} & := \frac{9+3-8}{(2 \times 15-7) \times 40} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{938}{256074} & := \frac{9+3-8}{2 \times 560 - 7 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 940

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{940}{18236} & := \frac{9-4+0}{1 + ((8+2^3) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{940}{31725} & := \frac{9 \times 4 + 0}{(3^{1 \times 7 - 2}) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{940}{321856} & := \frac{9-4+0}{(3-2+1) \times 856} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{940}{21385} & := \frac{9 \times 4 + 0}{21 \times (3 \times (8+5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{940}{182736} & := \frac{9-4+0}{18 \times 2 \times (7 \times 3 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{940}{23876} & := \frac{9-4+0}{23 + (8 \times (7+6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{940}{213568} & := \frac{9-4+0}{2 \times (13 \times 5 + 6) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 941

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{941}{6587} & := \frac{9+4+1}{6 + (5+87)} & & := \frac{94+1}{752+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{941}{86572} & := \frac{9-4-1}{8 \times ((6 \times 5 - 7) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{94+1}{658+7} & & := \frac{94-1}{752-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{941}{278536} & := \frac{9-4-1}{2 \times (7 \times 85 + 3 - 6)} \\ & := \frac{94-1}{658-7} & & := \frac{9-4 \times 1}{7 + (5+28)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{941}{7528} & := \frac{9 \times 4 + 1}{(7 \times 5 + 2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{941}{75280} & := \frac{9 \times 4 + 1}{(7 \times 5 + 2) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{9+4+1}{(7+5+2) \times 8} & & := \frac{9+4+1}{(7+5+2) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{9-4-1}{(7-5+2) \times 8} & & := \frac{9-4-1}{(7-5+2) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 942

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{1570} & := \frac{9+42}{15+70} & & := \frac{9+(4 \times 2)}{((3+7) \times 6) + 8} & & := \frac{94+2}{376+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{3768} & := \frac{9-4 \times 2}{3 + ((7-6)^8)} & & := \frac{9+42}{3 \times (76-8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{7065} & := \frac{9 \times (4-2)}{70+65} \\ & := \frac{9-4-2}{3 + (7-6+8)} & & := \frac{9 \times (4+2)}{(3 \times 7 + 6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{7536} & := \frac{9-4 \times 2}{(7 \times (5-3)) - 6} \\ & := \frac{9+4-2}{3 - (7-6 \times 8)} & & := \frac{94-2}{376-8} & & := \frac{9-4+2}{7 \times (5-3+6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(9 \times 4)^2}{((7 + 5)^3) \times 6} & := \frac{9 \times (4 - 2)}{(3 \times 5 - 1) \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{75831} & := \frac{(9 - 4) \times 2}{7 \times (5 \times ((8 \times 3) - 1))} \\ & := \frac{9 \times (4 + 2)}{(75 - 3) \times 6} & := \frac{9 + 42}{((3^5) + 1 - 6) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{153860} & := \frac{9 - 4 - 2}{1 \times 5 \times (38 + 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{15386} & := \frac{9 - 4 - 2}{1 \times (5 + (38 + 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{37680} & := \frac{9 - 4 - 2}{(3 \times 7 - 6) \times (8 + 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{351680} & := \frac{9 - 4 - 2}{(3 - 5 + 16) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{31086} & := \frac{9 - 4 \times 2}{(3 \times (1 + 08)) + 6} & & := \frac{9 + (4 \times 2)}{(3 + 7) \times (68 + 0)} & & := \frac{9 \times (4 - 2)}{(3 \times 5 - 1) \times 6 \times 80} \\ & := \frac{9 - 4 - 2}{3 + (10 + 86)} & & := \frac{9 \times (4 + 2)}{(3 \times 7 + 6) \times 80} & & := \frac{9 + 42}{(3^5 + 1 - 6) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{(9 - 4) \times 2}{(3 \times 108) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{75360} & := \frac{(9 \times 4)^2}{((7 + 5)^3) \times 60} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{942}{35168} & := \frac{9 - 4 - 2}{(3 - (5 - 16)) \times 8} & & := \frac{9 \times (4 + 2)}{(75 - 3) \times 60} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 945

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{1260} & := \frac{9 + 45}{12 + 60} & := \frac{9 \times 45}{(3^06) \times 18} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{138726} & := \frac{(9 + 4) \times 5}{13 \times (8 + 726)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{1680} & := \frac{9 + 45}{16 + 80} & := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{3^06 \times 1 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{172368} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{(1 + 7) \times (236 - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{6237} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{62 - 3 + 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{943}{287615} & := \frac{9 - 4 - 3}{2 + 8 \times 76 \times 1^5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{218673} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{2^{1 \times 8} + 6 \times 7^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{8127} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{81 - 2 + 7} & & := \frac{9 \times (4 - 3)}{(2 \times 8 - 7) \times 61 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{261387} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{2 \times (6^{1+3} + 87)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{8316} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{83 - 1 + 6} & & := \frac{9 + 4 \times 3}{(28 - 7) \times 61 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{273861} & := \frac{(9 + 4) \times 5}{273 \times (8 + 61)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{13608} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{1 \times (3 \times (6 \times 08))} & & := \frac{9 + 4 - 3}{(2 + 8 \times 76 \times 1) \times 5} & & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{2 \times 7 \times 3 \times (8 + 61)} \\ & := \frac{9 \times 45}{1 \times 3^6 \times 08} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{127680} & := \frac{9 + 45}{12 \times 76 \times 8 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{276318} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{((2 + 7) \times 6)^{3-1} + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{13720} & := \frac{9 + 45}{((1 + 3) \times 7)^2 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{132678} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{1326 + 78} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{945}{30618} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 5}{3 \times (0 + 6 \times 18)} & & := \frac{9 \times 45}{(1^3 + 2)^6 \times 78} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 946

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{1032} & := \frac{9 + 46}{10 \times 3 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{1075} & := \frac{94 - 6}{10^{7-5}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{1720} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{1^7 \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{94 - 6}{(1 + 7) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{2537} & := \frac{94 - 6}{2 \times ((5^3) - 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{2580} & := \frac{9 + 4 \times 6}{2 \times 5 + 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{3182} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{31 + 8 - 2} \\ & := \frac{9 + 46}{3 + 182} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{3870} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{3 \times (8 + 7 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{7138} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{(7 \times 13) - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{13502} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{1 + (3 \times (50 + 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{15738} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{15 + (7 \times 3 \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{17028} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{170 + 28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{21758} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{(2^{1+7}) + 5 - 8} \\ & := \frac{9 + 4 \times 6}{2 - (1 - 758)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{32508} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{3^2 \times (50 - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{37152} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{3 \times ((7 + 1 \times 5)^2)} \\ & := \frac{9 + 4 \times 6}{(3 \times (7 + 1 \times 5))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{85312} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{8 \times ((5^3) - 1^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{87032} & := \frac{(9 - 4) \times 6}{8 \times ((7^{03}) + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{107328} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{(10 + 73 \times 2) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{94 - 6}{10^{7-3} - 2 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{135278} & := \frac{(9 - 4) \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 52) \times 78} \\ & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 527 - 8} \\ & := \frac{9 + 4 - 6}{13 \times (5 + (2 + 7) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{207518} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{20 + 7^{5-1} - 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{946}{375218} & := \frac{9 - 4 + 6}{(3^7 - 5) \times 2 - 1^8} \\ & := \frac{94 - 6}{((3^7 - 5) \times 2 - 1) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 947

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{947}{5682} & := \frac{9 + 4 - 7}{(5 \times 6) + 8 - 2} \\ & := \frac{9 - 4 + 7}{(5 \times (6 + 8)) + 2} \\ & := \frac{9 + 4 + 7}{56 + 8^2} \\ & := \frac{9 + 47}{56 \times (8 - 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{947}{8523} & := \frac{9 + 4 - 7}{(8 + 5 \times 2) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{9 - 4 + 7}{85 + 23} \\ & := \frac{9 + 4 + 7}{(8 + 52) \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 \times 4 - 7}{(85 + 2) \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{947}{13258} & := \frac{9 + 4 - 7}{1 + (3 + (2 \times (5 \times 8)))} \\ & := \frac{9 - 4 + 7}{1 \times (3 \times ((2 + 5) \times 8))} \\ & := \frac{9 + 4 + 7}{1 \times ((3 + 2^5) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{947}{56820} & := \frac{9 \times 4 - 7}{(5 \times 68) + 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{947}{85230} & := \frac{9 + 4 - 7}{(8 + 5 \times 2) \times 30} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 + 4 + 7}{(8 + 52) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{947}{132580} & := \frac{9 \times 4 - 7}{(1 + 3 \times 2) \times 580} \\ & := \frac{9 - 4 + 7}{1 \times 3 \times (2 + 5) \times 80} \\ & := \frac{9 + 4 + 7}{(1 \times 3 + 2^5) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 948

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{948}{6320} & := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 8}{6 \times 320} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{948}{21567} & := \frac{9 \times 4 - 8}{(21 \times 5 \times 6) + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{948}{172536} & := \frac{9 + 4 + 8}{1 \times 72 \times 53 + 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 950

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{950}{3648} &:= \frac{9 \times 50}{36 \times 48} & \blacktriangleright \frac{950}{138472} &:= \frac{9 \times 50}{(1+3)^8 + 4 \times 7 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{950}{3724} &:= \frac{9 \times 50}{((3 \times 7)^2) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{950}{172368} &:= \frac{9 \times 50}{1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 3^6 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 951

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{3487} &:= \frac{9-5-1}{3 \times 4 - 8 + 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{7608} &:= \frac{95+1}{760+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{264378} &:= \frac{9 \times 5 - 1}{(2+6)^4 \times 3 - 7 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 5 \times 1}{3 \times (48+7)} & &:= \frac{9+5-1}{(7+6+0) \times 8} & &:= \frac{9-5-1}{2+64 \times (3 \times 7 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{9+5+1}{3-(4-(8 \times 7))} & &:= \frac{95-1}{760-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{324608} &:= \frac{9-5-1}{32^{4+6-08}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{3804} &:= \frac{95+1}{380+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{38674} &:= \frac{9-5-1}{((3 \times 8 - 6) \times 7) - 4} & &:= \frac{9+51}{(3+2) \times 4^6 + 0 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{9^{5-1}}{3^8 \times 04} & \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{68472} &:= \frac{9-5-1}{6^{8+4-7-2}} & &:= \frac{95+1}{(3-2) \times 4^6 \times 08} \\ &:= \frac{9-5-1}{3 \times (8-04)} & &:= \frac{9-(5-1)}{6 \times ((8+4) \times (7-2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{684720} &:= \frac{9+5 \times 1}{6 \times (8+4) \times 7 \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{9-(5-1)}{(3 \times 8+0) - 4} & &:= \frac{9 \times 5 - 1}{(6 \times 8 - 4) \times 72} \\ &:= \frac{95-1}{380-4} & &:= \frac{9+5-1}{6 \times (84+72)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{951}{6340} &:= \frac{9 \times (5+1)}{(6+3) \times 40} & &:= \frac{9+5 \times 1}{6 \times ((8+4) \times (7 \times 2))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 952

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{1036} &:= \frac{9+5^2}{1-(0-36)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{4386} &:= \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{43+86} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{13804} &:= \frac{9-5-2}{1+((3 \times 8+0)+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{1734} &:= \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{17+34} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{4760} &:= \frac{9+5+2}{4+(76+0)} & &:= \frac{9-5+2}{1 \times (3+(80+4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{1836} &:= \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{18+36} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{6384} &:= \frac{9+5^2}{6^3+8+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{14076} &:= \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{1+(407+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{3108} &:= \frac{9+5^2}{3+108} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{7168} &:= \frac{9+5^2}{(7+1-6)^8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{14637} &:= \frac{(9-5) \times 2}{1-(4-(6 \times (3 \times 7)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{3468} &:= \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{34+68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{8160} &:= \frac{9 \times (5+2)}{(8+1) \times 60} & &:= \frac{9+5+2}{1+((4 \times 63)-7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{3876} &:= \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{38+76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{13468} &:= \frac{9+5^2}{13+468} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{34816} &:= \frac{9 \times (5+2)}{3 \times (48 \times 16)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{36148} &:= \frac{9 + 5^2}{3 + ((6^1 \times 4) - 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{63784} &:= \frac{9 - 5 - 2}{6 - ((3 - 7) \times 8 \times 4)} & &:= \frac{(9 + 5)^2}{(8 - 1)^{6+3-4}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{37604} &:= \frac{9 - 5 - 2}{3 + (76 + 0 \times 4)} & &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 2}{((6 \times (3 \times 7)) + 8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{134708} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 2}{1 + 3 \times 4 \times 70 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 2}{(3 + (76 + 0)) \times 4} & &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 2}{6^3 + (7 \times 84)} & &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 2}{(1 \times 3 + 4 \times 70) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{40817} &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 2}{(40 + 8 + 1) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{74368} &:= \frac{9 + 5^2}{(74 \times 36) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{148036} &:= \frac{9 - 5 - 2}{1 \times 4 \times 80 - 3 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{48076} &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 2}{480 - 76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{81634} &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 2}{((8 - 1^6)^3) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{348160} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 + 2)}{3 \times 48 \times 160} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{952}{63104} &:= \frac{(9 + 5) \times 2}{(6 \times 310) - 4} & &:= \frac{(9 + 5) \times 2}{(8 - (1^{63}))^4} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 953

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{953}{7624} &:= \frac{9 - 5 - 3}{(7 - 6) \times 2 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{953}{76240} &:= \frac{9 - 5 - 3}{(7 \times 6 \times 2) - 4 + 0} & &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 3}{10 \times 8 \times (6 + 4) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 3}{(7 \times 6 \times 2) + 4} & &:= \frac{(9 + 5) \times 3}{7 \times (6 \times (2 \times 40))} & & \\ &:= \frac{(9 + 5) \times 3}{7 \times (6 \times 2 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{953}{108642} &:= \frac{(9 + 5) \times 3}{(108 + 6) \times 42} & & \\ &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 3}{7 \times (6 - 2 + 4)} & &:= \frac{9 - 5 - 3}{1 + (-08 + 64) \times 2} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 954

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{1378} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{1 - (3 - (7 + 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{6731} &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 4}{(6 \times 7 \times 3) + 1} & &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 4}{2^{7-1-3+6}} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 54}{13 + 78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{7632} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{7 + (63 + 2)} & &:= \frac{9 \times (5 + 4)}{(2^7 \times 1) \times 3 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{1802} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{1 - (8 \times (-02))} & &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 4}{(7 \times 6 \times 3) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{28673} &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 4}{2 + ((8 \times 67) + 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{3286} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{3 + (2 \times (8 + 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{8162} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{81 - 6 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{37206} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 4}{(3 + (7^2 + 0)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{3816} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 4}{38 - 1 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{18762} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{1 \times (8 + ((7 + 6)^2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{38160} &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 4}{(3 + 8 + 1) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 4}{3 \times 8 + 16} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{21306} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{21 + (30 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{68317} &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 4}{6^{8-3-1} - 7} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 4}{3 \times (8 + 16)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{27136} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{2^{7+136}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{127836} &:= \frac{95 + 4}{((1 + 2)^7 + 8 \times 3) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{132076} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{1 + 3 + 207 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{316728} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 4}{(31 + 6) \times 72 - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{713062} &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 4}{7 \times (1 + 30) \times 62} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{173628} &:= \frac{9 \times 5 \times 4}{(1 + (7 - 3)^6 - 2) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{328176} &:= \frac{9 \times 5 - 4}{328 \times (1 + 7 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{837612} &:= \frac{9 \times 5 \times 4}{(8 + 3^7) \times 6 \times 12} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{261873} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 4}{2 \times 61 \times (8 + 7 + 3)} & &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{3^2 \times 8 \times (1 + 7 \times 6)} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{271360} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 + 4)}{2^7 \times 1 \times 3 \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{368721} &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 4}{3^6 + (8 \times 7)^2 \times 1} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{954}{306128} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 - 4)}{(3 \times 06 + 1)^2 \times 8} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 956

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{3824} &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 6}{38 - 2 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{37284} &:= \frac{(9 - 5)^6}{(37 + 2) \times 8^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{103487} &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 6}{10 \times 3^4 + 8 \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 6}{38 - 2 + 4} & &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 6}{3 \times (72 + 8 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{230874} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 6}{2 \times 3 + 08 + 7^4} \\ &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 6}{(38 \times 2) + 4} & &:= \frac{(9 + 5) \times 6}{(37 + 2) \times 84} & \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{347028} &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 6}{(3 \times (4 + 7))^{02} \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 6}{3 \times (8 + 24)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{42781} &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 6}{((4^2) \times 7 \times 8) - 1} & &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 6}{3 \times (4 + 7)^{02} \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times 5) + 6}{3 \times (8^2 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{103248} &:= \frac{(9 - 5) \times 6}{1 \times 0324 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{372840} &:= \frac{(9 + 5) \times 6}{(37 + 2) \times 840} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{4302} &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 6}{4 \times (3^{01})} & &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 6}{10 \times 3^2 \times (4 + 8)} & & \\ &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 6}{43 + 02} & &:= \frac{9 + 5 + 6}{10 \times (3 + 24) \times 8} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{956}{17208} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 6}{172 + 08} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 957

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{1624} &:= \frac{9 + 57}{(1 + 6) \times 2^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{6380} &:= \frac{9 \times (5 + 7)}{(6 + 3) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{30624} &:= \frac{9 \times 5 - 7}{(306 - 2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{2146} &:= \frac{9 + 57}{2 + 146} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{6438} &:= \frac{9 + 57}{6 + 438} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{32016} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 7}{(3 + 20) \times 16} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{2610} &:= \frac{9 + 5 \times 7}{2 \times (6 \times 10)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{8613} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 7}{86 + 13} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{32480} &:= \frac{9 + 57}{(32 - 4) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{3248} &:= \frac{9 + 57}{(32 - 4) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{26013} &:= \frac{9 + 5 \times 7}{2 \times (601 - 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{40368} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 7}{((4^{03}) - 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{4263} &:= \frac{9 + 5 \times 7}{4 + (2^6 \times 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{28014} &:= \frac{9 - 5 + 7}{2 + (80 \times 1 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{61248} &:= \frac{9 + 5 - 7}{(6 + 1) \times (2 \times 4 \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9+5+7}{(6+1) \times (24 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{9 \times (5+7)}{(6^{1+2}) \times 4 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{128064} & := \frac{9+5 \times 7}{(12+80) \times 64} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{164082} & := \frac{9-5+7}{(-1+6 \times 4) \times 082} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{168432} & := \frac{9-5+7}{(1^{68}+43)^2} \\ & := \frac{9+5 \times 7}{(1+6+84-3)^2} \\ & := \frac{9+5+7}{(1+6) \times 8 \times (4^3+2)} \\ & := \frac{9+5-7}{1+6+(8 \times 4+3)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{214368} & := \frac{9 \times (5+7)}{21 \times 4 \times 36 \times 8} \\ & := \frac{9+5-7}{(214-3 \times 6) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{238641} & := \frac{9-5+7}{2-3+(8+6)^{4-1}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{612480} & := \frac{9 \times (5+7)}{6^{1+2} \times 4 \times 80} \\ & := \frac{9+5+7}{(6+1) \times 24 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{957}{812406} & := \frac{9+5 \times 7}{812 \times (40+6)} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 958

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{958}{1437} & := \frac{9+5-8}{1+(4-3+7)} \\ & := \frac{9-5+8}{1-(4-(3 \times 7))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{958}{21076} & := \frac{9+5-8}{2+(10 \times (7+6))} \\ & := \frac{9+5 \times 8}{2+1076} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{958}{23471} & := \frac{9+5-8}{(2 \times ((3^4)-7))-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{958}{42631} & := \frac{9+5-8}{4+(263 \times 1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{958}{236147} & := \frac{9+5-8}{2 \times (3^6+14)-7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{958}{426310} & := \frac{9+5-8}{(4+263) \times 10} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 960

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{1472} & := \frac{9+6+0}{1+((4+7) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{1728} & := \frac{9+6+0}{17+2+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{4352} & := \frac{9+6+0}{4+((3+5)^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{5824} & := \frac{9+6+0}{5+(82+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{8512} & := \frac{9+6+0}{8+(5^{1+2})} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{13824} & := \frac{9+6+0}{(1^3+8) \times 24} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{18432} & := \frac{9+6+0}{1 \times (8 \times (4+32))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{31872} & := \frac{9+6+0}{(((3-1)^8)-7) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{418752} & := \frac{9+6+0}{(4-1)^8+7-5^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{960}{435712} & := \frac{9+6+0}{4 \times (3^5 \times 7+1^2)} \end{aligned}$$

• Numerator 961

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{961}{4805} & := \frac{9-6+1}{(4-8) \times (-05)} \\ & := \frac{96+1}{480+5} \\ & := \frac{9 \times (6+1)}{4 \times 80-5} \\ & := \frac{96-1}{480-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{961}{30752} & := \frac{9-6-1}{(3-((0 \times 7)-5))^2} \\ & := \frac{9-6 \times 1}{3 \times (0+(7+5^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{961}{80724} &:= \frac{9-6+1}{8 \times (0 + (7 \times (2+4)))} & := \frac{9+6-1}{2 \times 5 \times 370-4} & := \frac{9+6 \times 1}{4 \times 30 \times (5+2) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{9+6+1}{8 \times (0 + (7 \times 24))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{961}{430528} & := \frac{9-6 \times 1}{((4+30) \times 5-2) \times 8} & := \frac{9+6-1}{4 \times (30 \times 52+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{961}{208537} &:= \frac{9+6 \times 1}{(20 \times 8-5) \times 3 \times 7} & := \frac{9-6-1}{4 \times (3+05^2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{961}{253704} &:= \frac{9-6+1}{2+5 \times 3 \times 70+4} & := \frac{9-6+1}{4^{3+0 \times 5} \times 28} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 962

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{1480} &:= \frac{9 \times 6 - 2}{1^4 \times 80} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 2}{(3 \times 75) + 1 + 8} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 2}{(1 \times 5 \times 8 - 7) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{4810} &:= \frac{9+6+2}{4+(81+0)} & := \frac{9 \times (6-2)}{(3+75) \times 18} & := \frac{9-6-2}{((1+5) \times 8+7) \times 3+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{14578} &:= \frac{9+6-2}{1+(4 \times (57-8))} & := \frac{9 \times 6+2}{3^7+(5-1 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{175084} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 2}{(1+7+5) \times 084} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{15873} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 2}{1 \times ((5 \times 8-7) \times 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{47138} &:= \frac{9-6-2}{4+(7+(1 \times 38))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{180375} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 2}{(18-03) \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{(9+6) \times 2}{(158+7) \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{73815} &:= \frac{9 \times 6-2}{7 \times (38 \times 15)} & := \frac{9 \times (6-2)}{18 \times 0375} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{17834} &:= \frac{9+6-2}{((1+78) \times 3)+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{75813} &:= \frac{9 \times 6-2}{7-(5-(8^{1+3}))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{375180} &:= \frac{9 \times (6-2)}{(3+75) \times 180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{30784} &:= \frac{9-6-2}{(3 \times 0 \times 7)+8 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{84175} &:= \frac{9 \times (6+2)}{84 \times (1 \times 75)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{417508} &:= \frac{9-6-2}{41-7+50 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{9+(6 \times 2)}{3 \times (0+(7 \times 8 \times 4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{138750} &:= \frac{9+6-2}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 75+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{841750} &:= \frac{9 \times (6+2)}{84 \times 1 \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{37518} &:= \frac{9-6-2}{3 \times (7+(5+1^8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{962}{158730} &:= \frac{(9+6) \times 2}{(158+7) \times 30} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 963

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{1284} &:= \frac{9-6+3}{1 \times (2 \times (8-4))} & := \frac{9+6+3}{1 \times (2 \times (8+4))} & := \frac{9+63}{12+84} \\ &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 3}{1 \times (2 \times 8-4)} & := \frac{9 \times (6-3)}{(1^2+8) \times 4} & := \frac{96-3}{128-4} \\ &:= \frac{9+6-3}{1 \times (2^{8-4})} & := \frac{96 \times 3}{12 \times 8 \times 4} & := \frac{96+3}{128+4} \\ & & := \frac{9 \times 6-3}{(1+(2 \times 8)) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{2140} &:= \frac{9+6+3}{(2-1) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{4280} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 3}{4 \times (2+8+0)} &:= \frac{9+6+3}{(1-(5-40)) \times 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{40125} &:= \frac{9+6-3}{4 \times (0+125)} \\ &:= \frac{96 \times 3}{(4^2) \times 80} &:= \frac{9 \times (6-3)}{1 \times (54 \times 08)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{48150} &:= \frac{9+6-3}{(4+8 \times 1) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{4708} &:= \frac{9+6+3}{(4+7+0) \times 8} &:= \frac{(9+6) \times 3}{15 \times (40+8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{107428} &:= \frac{9+6+3}{10^{7-4} \times 2+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{4815} &:= \frac{9+6-3}{(4+8 \times 1) \times 5} &:= \frac{9 \times (6+3)}{(1+5)^4 + 0 \times 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{172805} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 3}{(17+2) \times (80+5)} \\ &:= \frac{9+6+3}{4+(81+5)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{18725} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 3}{(18+7) \times (2+5)} &:= \frac{9 \times (6-3)}{17 \times (280+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{8025} &:= \frac{9-6+3}{(8+02) \times 5} &:= \frac{9 \times 6 \times 3}{18 \times (7 \times 25)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{175480} &:= \frac{9 \times (6-3)}{(1+7) \times 5^4 - 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{12840} &:= \frac{9-6+3}{(12+8) \times (4+0)} &:= \frac{(9+6) \times 3}{(1+(87 \times 2)) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{187250} &:= \frac{(9+6) \times 3}{(1+87 \times 2) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{9+6-3}{(12-8) \times 40} &:= \frac{9+63}{1 \times (8 \times (7 \times 25))} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 3}{1^8 \times 7 \times 250} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times (6-3)}{(1^2+8) \times 40} &:= \frac{9 \times (6+3)}{(1+8) \times (7 \times 25)} &:= \frac{9 \times 6 \times 3}{18 \times 7 \times 250} \\ &:= \frac{96 \times 3}{12 \times 8 \times 40} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{20758} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 3}{207-(5+8)} &:= \frac{9 \times (6+3)}{(1+8) \times 7 \times 250} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 6-3}{(1+(2 \times 8)) \times 40} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{24075} &:= \frac{9-6+3}{(2-(4 \times (-07))) \times 5} &:= \frac{9+63}{1 \times 8 \times 7 \times 250} \\ &:= \frac{9+63}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 40} &:= \frac{9+6+3}{(2+4+0) \times 75} &\blacktriangleright \frac{963}{514028} &:= \frac{9+6+3}{(5+1) \times 40^2+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{15087} &:= \frac{9-6+3}{150-(8 \times 7)} &:= \frac{9+63}{24 \times (0+75)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{963}{15408} &:= \frac{9+6-3}{1 \times ((5 \times 40) - 8)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 964

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{964}{1205} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 4}{1 \times (20-5)} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 4}{(1+7) \times (3^{5-2})} &:= \frac{96+4}{(3-(0-1 \times 2))^5} \\ &:= \frac{96-4}{120-5} &:= \frac{9 \times 6 \times 4}{(1+7) \times (3^5 \times 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{964}{78325} &:= \frac{(9+6) \times 4}{(7+8) \times 325} \\ &:= \frac{96+4}{120+5} &:= \frac{96+4}{(1+7) \times ((3 \times 5)^2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{964}{137852} &:= \frac{9 \times 6+4}{13+(7 \times (8+5))^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{964}{17352} &:= \frac{9-6+4}{1+(73+52)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{964}{30125} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 4}{3 \times (0+125)} &:= \frac{(9-6) \times 4}{(1-(3-7) \times 8) \times 52} \\ &:= \frac{9+6-4}{173+5^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9-6+4}{13 \times 7 \times (8+5-2)} & := \frac{9 \times 64}{210 \times 8 \times 75} \\ & := \frac{9+6-4}{1 \times 3+785 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{964}{283175} := \frac{(9-6) \times 4}{(2 \times 8 \times 3-1) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{964}{173520} & := \frac{9 \times 6 \times 4}{(1+7) \times 3^5 \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{964}{783250} := \frac{(9+6) \times 4}{(7+8) \times 3250} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{964}{210875} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 4}{(2+1) \times 0875} & := \frac{9 \times 6 \times 4}{(7+8)^3 \times (2+50)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 965

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{12738} & := \frac{9+6-5}{127-3+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{3281} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 5}{3 \times (2 \times 8+1)} & := \frac{9-6+5}{24 \times (3+1+80)} \\ & := \frac{9+6+5}{(12+7 \times 3) \times 8} & & := \frac{(9+6) \times 5}{(32 \times 8)-1} & := \frac{9+6-5}{2 \times (4+3) \times 180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{24318} & := \frac{9+6-5}{2 \times ((4+3) \times 18)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{38214} & := \frac{9+6-5}{382+14} & \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{283710} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 5}{2 \times (8+3^7+10)} \\ & := \frac{(9-6) \times 5}{(24-3) \times 18} & \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{127380} & := \frac{9-6+5}{(1+2^7+3) \times 8+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{283710} & := \frac{9+6+5}{28 \times 3 \times 7 \times 10} \\ & := \frac{9+6+5}{2 \times (4+(31 \times 8))} & & := \frac{9+6+5}{(12+7 \times 3) \times 80} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{28371} & := \frac{9+6-5}{(2^8)+(37+1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{132784} & := \frac{9+6-5}{(1+3 \times 2 \times 7) \times 8 \times 4} & & \\ & := \frac{9+6+5}{28 \times (3 \times 7 \times 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{965}{243180} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 5}{(24-3) \times 180} & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 967

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{967}{4835} & := \frac{9+6-7}{4 \times (8-3+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{967}{34812} & := \frac{9+6-7}{3 \times (4 \times (8 \times (1+2)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{967}{48350} & := \frac{9+(6 \times 7)}{(48+3) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{9-6+7}{48-3+5} & & := \frac{9-6+7}{348+12} & \blacktriangleright \frac{967}{348120} & := \frac{9+6-7}{3 \times 48 \times 1 \times 20} \\ & := \frac{9+(6 \times 7)}{4+(8+(3^5))} & & := \frac{(9-6)^7}{3 \times (4 \times (81^2))} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{967}{5802} & := \frac{9-6+7}{58+02} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 968

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{968}{1320} & := \frac{9-6+8}{13+2+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{968}{1452} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 8}{(1^4+5)^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{968}{1573} & := \frac{(9-6) \times 8}{(1+5+7) \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{3025} := \frac{(9-6) \times 8}{3 \times (025)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{4312} := \frac{9-6+8}{(4+3 \times 1)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{9+68}{(4+3)^{1+2}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{4752} := \frac{9-6+8}{47+5+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{12375} := \frac{96-8}{(12+3) \times 75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{13475} := \frac{96-8}{(1+34)^{7-5}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{14520} := \frac{9+6-8}{1+(4+(5 \times 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{9-6+8}{145+20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{15730} := \frac{(9-6) \times 8}{(1+5+7) \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{24057} := \frac{96-8}{(2-(4+(-05)))^7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{27104} := \frac{9+6-8}{2 \times (7 \times (10+4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{73205} := \frac{(9-6) \times 8}{(7^3+20) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{123750} := \frac{96-8}{(12+3) \times 750}$$

$$:= \frac{96-8}{(1+34) \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{968}{347512} := \frac{9+6-8}{(3+4) \times (7 \times 51+2)}$$

● Numerator 970

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{970}{4365} := \frac{9+7+0}{4+(3+65)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{970}{8245} := \frac{9-7+0}{(8 \times 2) - 4 + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{970}{28615} := \frac{9-7+0}{((2+8) \times 6) - 1^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{970}{43165} := \frac{9-7+0}{(4 \times (3 \times (1+6))) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{970}{136285} := \frac{9-7+0}{1-3+6^2 \times 8-5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{970}{318645} := \frac{9-7+0}{3+1+8+645}$$

● Numerator 971

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{971}{5826} := \frac{9-7 \times 1}{(5-8) \times (2-6)}$$

$$:= \frac{97-1}{582-6}$$

$$:= \frac{97+1}{582+6}$$

$$:= \frac{9+71}{5 \times (8 \times 2 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{9+7-1}{(5+8+2) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{971}{58260} := \frac{9-7-1}{5 \times (8 - (2 - (6+0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{9-7 \times 1}{58+(2+60)}$$

$$:= \frac{9-7+1}{5 \times ((8-2) \times (6+0))}$$

$$:= \frac{9+71}{5 \times (8 \times 2 \times 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{9+7-1}{(5+8+2) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{971}{83506} := \frac{9-7+1}{(8+(35+0)) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{971}{265083} := \frac{9-7 \times 1}{2-6+50 \times (8+3)}$$

$$:= \frac{9-7+1}{(265+08) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{971}{284503} := \frac{9-7-1}{2 \times 84+5^3}$$

● Numerator 972

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{972}{1458} := \frac{9+7+2}{14+5+8}$$

$$:= \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(1^4+5) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{972}{3456} := \frac{9+7+2}{(3+4-5)^6}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{972}{3468} := \frac{9+72}{(3+45) \times 6} \\
 \frac{972}{3645} := \frac{9 \times 72}{34 \times 68} \\
 \frac{972}{4536} := \frac{(9+7)^2}{3 \times (64 \times 5)} \\
 \frac{972}{4860} := \frac{9-7+2}{3 \times (6+4-5)} \\
 \frac{972}{5346} := \frac{9+7+2}{4 \times (5 \times 3+6)} \\
 \frac{972}{5346} := \frac{9-7+2}{((5-3)^4)+6} \\
 \frac{972}{6318} := \frac{9+7-2}{5+(3 \times (4 \times 6))} \\
 \frac{972}{6318} := \frac{9+7+2}{53+46} \\
 \frac{972}{6318} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(5 \times 34)+6} \\
 \frac{972}{10368} := \frac{9-7+2}{(6 \times 3 \times 1)+8} \\
 \frac{972}{10368} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(6^{3 \times 1})-8} \\
 \frac{972}{13608} := \frac{9+7+2}{(1+03) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 \frac{972}{13608} := \frac{9-7+2}{1+(3+(60-8))} \\
 \frac{972}{14580} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(1^4+5) \times 80} \\
 \frac{972}{15648} := \frac{9+72}{1^5 \times (6^4+8)} \\
 \frac{972}{16038} := \frac{9-7+2}{1 \times (6 \times (0+3+8))} \\
 \frac{972}{30618} := \frac{9-7+2}{3 \times (0-(6 \times (1-8)))} \\
 \frac{972}{34560} := \frac{9+72}{(3+45) \times 60} \\
 \frac{972}{34680} := \frac{9 \times 72}{34 \times 680} \\
 \frac{972}{36450} := \frac{(9+7)^2}{3 \times (64 \times 50)} \\
 \frac{972}{81654} := \frac{9-7+2}{3 \times ((6+4) \times (5+0))} \\
 \frac{972}{81654} := \frac{9+7+2}{(3^6)-(4+50)} \\
 \frac{972}{134568} := \frac{9 \times 72}{((8-1) \times (6^5))+4} \\
 \frac{972}{134568} := \frac{9 \times (7-2)}{(13+4^5) \times 6+8} \\
 \frac{972}{134865} := \frac{9-7+2}{1+34+8 \times 65} \\
 \frac{972}{138564} := \frac{9+7+2}{(1-3) \times (8+5-6^4)} \\
 \frac{972}{143586} := \frac{9+7+2}{1+(435+8) \times 6} \\
 \frac{972}{143856} := \frac{9+7+2}{(1+438+5) \times 6} \\
 \frac{972}{164538} := \frac{9+7+2}{1-(6-4^5) \times 3-8} \\
 \frac{972}{165483} := \frac{9-7+2}{165+4+8^3} \\
 \frac{972}{183456} := \frac{9+72}{(1+8 \times 34) \times 56} \\
 \frac{972}{183465} := \frac{9-7+2}{(1+8)^3-4+6 \times 5} \\
 \frac{972}{315846} := \frac{9+7+2}{3+1 \times 5846} \\
 \frac{972}{351864} := \frac{9-7+2}{(3^5-1^8) \times 6-4} \\
 \frac{972}{354186} := \frac{9+7+2}{3^{5+4-1}-8+6} \\
 \frac{972}{356481} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(3+5+6^4) \times (8+1)} \\
 \frac{972}{361584} := \frac{97+2}{(3+6) \times (1-5+8^4)} \\
 \frac{972}{365148} := \frac{97+2}{3^6 \times 51+4+8} \\
 \frac{972}{368145} := \frac{9-7+2}{3 \times (6 \times (81+4)-5)} \\
 \frac{972}{431568} := \frac{9-7+2}{4 \times 3 \times (156-8)} \\
 \frac{972}{453168} := \frac{9+7+2}{(4^5+31-6) \times 8} \\
 \frac{972}{453681} := \frac{9-7+2}{4+(5+3 \times 6) \times 81} \\
 \frac{972}{458136} := \frac{97+2}{(45-8-1)^3+6} \\
 \frac{972}{561438} := \frac{9+7+2}{(5+6^{1 \times 4}+3) \times 8} \\
 \frac{972}{653184} := \frac{(9+7)^2}{(6+5+31) \times 8^4} \\
 \frac{972}{653184} := \frac{9+72}{6^5 \times (3+1^8 \times 4)} \\
 \frac{972}{814536} := \frac{97+2}{81 \times 4^5+3 \times 6}
 \end{array}$$

● Numerator 973

$$\frac{973}{4865} := \frac{(9-7) \times 3}{(4+8-6) \times 5} = \frac{(9-7)^3}{4 \times (8-6) \times 5} = \frac{9+7+3}{4+(86+5)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 \times (7 + 3)}{(4 + 86) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{973}{21406} & := \frac{9 + 7 - 3}{(2 \times 140) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{973}{48650} & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 3}{(4 + 8 - 6) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{(9 - 7)^3}{4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{9 \times (7 + 3)}{(4 + 86) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{973}{64218} & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 3}{(6 + 4^2) \times 18} \\ & := \frac{(9 - 7)^3}{(64 + 2 \times 1) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{973}{85624} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 3}{(8 \times 56) - 2 \times 4} \\ & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 3}{8 \times ((5 + 6) \times (2 + 4))} \\ & := \frac{(9 - 7)^3}{8 \times ((5 + 6) \times 2 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{9 + 7 \times 3}{8 \times (5 \times (62 + 4))} \\ & := \frac{9 + 7^3}{((8 \times (5 + 6))^2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{973}{856240} & := \frac{9 + 7^3}{(8 \times (5 + 6))^2 \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 974

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{974}{30681} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 4}{(30 \times 6) + 8 + 1} \\ & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 4}{(30 + 6) \times (8 - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{974}{250318} & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 4}{(2^{5+03} + 1) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{9 + 7 - 4}{2 \times (50 \times 31 - 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{974}{362815} := \frac{9 + 7 - 4}{(3^6 + 2 \times 8) \times (1 + 5)}$$

● Numerator 975

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{975}{2340} & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 5}{2 \times (3 \times 4 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{975}{12480} & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 5}{1 \times (2^4 \times (8 + 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{975}{16380} & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 5}{(1 + 6) \times (3 \times 8 + 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{975}{38610} & := \frac{(9 - 7) \times 5}{386 + 10} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 976

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{1342} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{1 \times (3 + (4 \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{(9 + 7) \times 6}{134 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{1830} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{18 - 3 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{2013} & := \frac{(9 + 7) \times 6}{201 - 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{13542} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{1 \times (3 + (54 \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{14823} & := \frac{(9 + 7)^6}{1 \times (48^{2+3})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{28304} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{(28 + 30) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{9 + 7 - 6}{(2^8) + (30 + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{31842} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{3 \times (1 + (84 + 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{48312} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{(4 + 8) \times (31 + 2)} \\ & := \frac{9 + 7 - 6}{483 + 12} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{208315} & := \frac{(9 + 7) \times 6}{(2 + 08^{3+1}) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{238510} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{23 \times 85 \times 1 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{315248} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{(315 + 2 \times 4) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{976}{381250} & := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{((3 - 8) \times (1 - 2))^5 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{976}{158234} := \frac{9 - 7 + 6}{1^5 + 8 \times 2 \times 3^4}$$

● Numerator 978

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{978}{6520} &:= \frac{9 \times (7 + 8)}{(6 \times 5)^2 + 0} &:= \frac{9 + 7 - 8}{(1 + 05) \times 6 \times 24} &\blacktriangleright \frac{978}{435210} &:= \frac{9 + 7 - 8}{(4 + 352) \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{978}{10432} &:= \frac{9 \times (7 + 8)}{10 \times (4 \times 3)^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{978}{251346} &:= \frac{(9 - 7) \times 8}{2^5 - 1^3 + 4^6} &\blacktriangleright \frac{978}{462105} &:= \frac{(9 + 7) \times 8}{(4 \times 6)^2 \times 105} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{978}{43521} &:= \frac{9 + 7 - 8}{4 + 352 \times 1} &&:= \frac{9 + 7 - 8}{25 \times (1 + 3^4) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{978}{105624} &:= \frac{9 - 7 + 8}{10 \times (56 \times 2 - 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{978}{413205} &:= \frac{9 + 7 - 8}{4 \times 13^2 \times 05} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 980

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{980}{1764} &:= \frac{9 \times 80}{1^7 \times 6^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{980}{3675} &:= \frac{9 \times 80}{36 \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 981

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{981}{6540} &:= \frac{9 + 8 + 1}{6 \times (5 \times (4 + 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{981}{327654} &:= \frac{9 - 8 \times 1}{(3 + 27) \times (6 + 5) + 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{981}{437526} &:= \frac{9 - 8 \times 1}{4 \times 3 \times 7 \times 5 + 26} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{981}{67035} &:= \frac{9 + 8 + 1}{6 \times ((70 \times 3) - 5)} &&:= \frac{9 - 8 + 1}{3 - 2 + 7 \times 6 + 5^4} &&:= \frac{9 - 8 + 1}{4 \times 3 \times 75 - 2 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{981}{70632} &:= \frac{9 - 8 \times 1}{7 - (0 - (63 + 2))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{981}{340625} &:= \frac{9 \times (8 + 1)}{(3^4 - 06)^2 \times 5} &&:= \frac{98 \times 1}{4 \times (3^7 \times 5 - 2 - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{981}{207536} &:= \frac{9 \times 8 \times 1}{2^{07} \times (5^3 - 6)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{981}{426735} &:= \frac{9 - 8 \times 1}{4 - 2 + 6 \times 73 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{981}{243506} &:= \frac{9 \times (8 - 1)}{2^4 - 3 + 5^{06}} &&:= \frac{9 - 8 + 1}{4 + 2 \times (6 \times 73 - 5)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 982

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{982}{1473} &:= \frac{(9 - 8) \times 2}{(1^{47}) \times 3} &:= \frac{98 + 2}{147 + 3} &:= \frac{98 \times 2}{14 \times (7 \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + 8) \times 2}{1 + (47 + 3)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{982}{7365} &:= \frac{(9 - 8) \times 2}{7 - (3 - (6 + 5))} &:= \frac{(9 \times 8) - 2}{(1 + 4) \times (7 \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{98 \times 2}{14 \times 7 \times 3} &\blacktriangleright \frac{982}{14730} &:= \frac{(9 - 8)^2}{1 + (4 + (7 + 3 + 0))} &:= \frac{98 - 2}{(1 + 47) \times 30} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times 8) - 2}{(1 + 4) \times 7 \times 3} &&:= \frac{(9 - 8) \times 2}{(1^{47}) \times 30} &\blacktriangleright \frac{982}{40753} &:= \frac{(9 - 8) \times 2}{(40 \times (7 - 5)) + 3} \\ &:= \frac{98 - 2}{(1 + 47) \times 3} &&:= \frac{9 - 8 + 2}{1 + (47 - 3 + 0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{982}{41735} &:= \frac{(9 - 8) \times 2}{(4 \times (17 + 3)) + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{982}{47136} &:= \frac{(9-8)^2}{4+(7+(1+36))} &:= \frac{9+8 \times 2}{5-(1+(0-(6^4)))} &:= \frac{9+8^2}{7+5614} \\ &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 2}{4 \times (7-(1-(3 \times 6)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{982}{61375} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 2}{(6 \times (13+7))+5} \\ &:= \frac{9-8+2}{(4+(7+13)) \times 6} & &:= \frac{(9 \times 8)-2}{((6-1)^3) \times 7 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{9+8 \times 2}{471+3^6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{982}{73650} &:= \frac{(9-8)^2}{7+(3+(65+0))} \\ &:= \frac{(9+8) \times 2}{4 \times ((71-3) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{982}{75614} &:= \frac{(9-8)^2}{7 \times (5+(6 \times 1^4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{982}{51064} &:= \frac{(9-8)^2}{(5 \times 10)+6-4} & &:= \frac{9-8+2}{7-((5-61) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 983

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{983}{26541} &:= \frac{(9-8)^3}{2+(6+(5 \times 4-1))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{983}{57014} &:= \frac{(9-8)^3}{57-(0-1^4)} &:= \frac{9 \times 8^3}{(2 \times 6)^5 \times (4+1)+0} \\ &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 3}{(2+6-5)^4 \times 1} & &:= \frac{9-8+3}{(57+01) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{9-8+3}{2 \times (6 \times (5+4 \times 1))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{983}{265410} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 3}{((2+6-5)^4) \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{983}{46201} &:= \frac{(9-8)^3}{(4 \times (6 \times 2+0))-1} & &:= \frac{(9-8)^3}{(26+5-4) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times (8-3)}{46^2-01} & &:= \frac{9-8+3}{2 \times 6 \times (5+4) \times 10} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 984

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{1056} &:= \frac{9+8 \times 4}{(10 \times 5)-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{3075} &:= \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{307-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{1230} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 4}{1 \times (2+3+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{6150} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 4}{(6-1) \times (5+0)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{12 \times 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{16072} &:= \frac{9+8+4}{(1+6+0) \times (7^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{1536} &:= \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1 \times ((5-3)^6)} & &:= \frac{9 \times (8+4)}{1 \times ((6 \times 07)^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{1560} &:= \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1 \times (5+60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{17256} &:= \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1 \times (725-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{1752} &:= \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1 \times (75-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{62730} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 4}{(6^2 \times 7)+3+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{2376} &:= \frac{9+8 \times 4}{23+76} & \blacktriangleright \frac{984}{107256} &:= \frac{(9-8)^4}{1-(07-25) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 985

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{2167} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{2 + (16-7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{23640} &:= \frac{(9-8)^5}{2 - (3 \times 6 - 40)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{41370} &:= \frac{(9-8)^5}{4 + (1 + (37+0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{2364} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{2 \times (3 \times (6-4))} & & & & := \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{(4-1^3) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{4137} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{(4-1^3) \times 7} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{142037} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{((1+4) \times 20 + 3) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{6304} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{6 + (30-4)} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{214730} &:= \frac{(9-8)^5}{2 \times 1 \times 4 + 7 \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{21473} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{((2+14) \times 7) - 3} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{431627} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{4 + 3^{162 \times 7}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{21670} &:= \frac{(9-8)^5}{21 - (6-7+0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{985}{34672} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 5}{3 + (4 + ((6+7)^2))} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 986

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{1305} &:= \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{130 + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{25143} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 6}{2 \times 5 + 143} & \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{234175} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 6}{(23 - 4 \times 1) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{2175} &:= \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{(2+1) \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{32045} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 6}{3 \times (20 + 45)} & & := \frac{(9-8) \times 6}{(2+4+15) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{3451} &:= \frac{9 \times (8-6)}{3 \times (4 \times 5 + 1)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{34510} &:= \frac{(9-8)^6}{(3+4) \times (5 \times 1 + 0)} & & := \frac{(9-8)^6}{(2+4+1) \times 5 \times 7 + 0} \\ & := \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{(3+4) \times 51} & & & & := \frac{9-8+6}{(2+(4-1)^5) \times 7 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{5423} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 6}{(5+(4+2)) \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{54230} &:= \frac{(9-8)^6}{(5^{4-2}) + 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{251430} &:= \frac{(9-8)^6}{2 + (5-1)^4 - 3 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{7105} &:= \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{7 \times 105} & & & & := \frac{(9-8) \times 6}{(5+(4+2)) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{21750} &:= \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{(2+1) \times 750} & & & & := \frac{9+8+6}{5+(42 \times 30)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{986}{24157} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 6}{(2+4+15) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

● Numerator 987

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{1645} &:= \frac{9 \times (8-7)}{1 \times (6+4+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{2350} &:= \frac{98+7}{(2+3) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{6251} &:= \frac{9 \times (8-7)}{62-5 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{9+8+7}{1-(6-45)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{4512} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{4 \times (5+1+2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{6345} &:= \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{6+(34+5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{14523} := \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{1 \times ((4 \times (5^2)) + 3)} & := \frac{9+8 \times 7}{5 \times ((13^2) \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{154630} := \frac{9 \times (8-7)}{(1^5 + 46) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{15463} := \frac{9 \times (8-7)}{(1^5 + 46) \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{52640} := \frac{9+8+7}{5 \times (2^6 \times (4+0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{210654} := \frac{98 \times 7}{2+10 \times (6+5)^4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{16450} := \frac{9 \times (8-7)}{(1+6-4) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{62510} := \frac{9 \times (8-7)}{(62-5) \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{341502} := \frac{(9-8)^7}{(3 \times 41 + 50) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{20163} := \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{(20 \times (1+6)) + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{65142} := \frac{(9-8)^7}{6 \times (5 + (1 \times (4+2)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{352641} := \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{(3+52+6) \times 41} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{21056} := \frac{9 \times (8-7)}{(2^{1 \times 05}) \times 6} & := \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{(6+5 \times 1) \times 42} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{461352} := \frac{98+7}{4 \times 6135 \times 2} \\
 := \frac{9+8+7}{2^{10+5-6}} & := \frac{9-8+7}{(65+1) \times 4 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{513240} := \frac{9+8 \times 7}{5 \times 13^2 \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{45120} := \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{4 \times ((5-1) \times 20)} & := \frac{9+8-7}{6 \times ((51+4) \times 2)} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{51324} := \frac{(9-8)^7}{5 - (1 - (3 \times 2^4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{135642} := \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 64 + 2} & \\
 := \frac{9+8-7}{5 \times (13 \times 2 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{987}{145230} := \frac{(9-8) \times 7}{1 + 4^5 + 2 + 3 + 0} &
 \end{array}$$

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